

Application of Neural Networks for the Estimation of the Shear Strength of Circular RC Columns

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Abstract-This study aims to develop Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) for predicting the shear strength of circular Reinforced Concrete (RC) columns. A set of 156 experimental data samples of various circular RC columns were utilized to establish the ANN model. The performance results of the ANN model show that it predicts the shear strength of circular RC columns accurately with a high coefficient of determination (0.99) and a small root-mean-square error (4.6kN). The result comparison reveals that the proposed ANN model can predict the shear strength of the columns more accurately than the existing equations. Moreover, an ANN-based formula is proposed to explicitly calculate the shear strength of the columns. Additionally, a practical Graphical User Interface (GUI) tool is developed for facilitating the practical design process of the circular RC columns.

Keywords-artificial neural networks; circular reinforced concrete column; graphical user interface; shear strength

I. INTRODUCTION

Circular Reinforced Concrete (RC) columns have been widely used in civil engineering structures. Shear strength is one of the most critical values considered in the design process. Estimation of this parameter can be performed by experiments or design code provisions. However, experimental tests require time-consuming implementations and are costly. Moreover, many studies pointed out that the current design code equations in calculating the shear strength of RC columns may give a large dispersion compared to the experimental results [1-4]. Therefore, it is necessary to develop soft-computing models, which ensure the accuracy demands and have less modeling effort and cost. Machine Learning (ML) models have been extensively applied for various engineering problems since they possess great advantages such as computational efficiency and sufficient consideration of uncertainties [5-14]. Numerous studies utilized ML techniques to estimate the responses of RC structures and elements [15-22]. Specifically, ML models have

been used to predict the shear strength of rectangular RC columns in [4, 23]. Additionally, several studies have carried out data-driven models to estimate the shear strength of circular RC columns [1-3, 23]. Authors in [1] collected 47 experimental datasets to develop ANNs for calculating the shear strength of RC columns. They highlighted that the ANN model obtained better results compared to the design codes. Authors in [2] developed the Gene Expression Programming (GEP) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) models to predict the shear strength of short circular RC columns with 200 numerical data sets. The results revealed that those ML techniques outperformed other design code formulas. Recently, a set of linear and nonlinear equations, based on regression analysis, were proposed in [23] for the estimation of the maximum shear strength of circular RC columns.

Previous studies mostly proposed ML models for calculating the shear strength of circular RC columns. However, the previous models were not transferred to practical tools, which can be used in design problems. Designers and analysts have difficulty in applying those soft-computing models. Additionally, the influence of the input variables on the predicted shear strength was not investigated. So far, only the proposed equation of [23] can be practical in the design purpose. In this study, we aim to develop a GUI to simplify the calculation procedure of the shear strength of circular RC columns. For that, ANNs are constructed based on 156 experimental data samples of RC columns. Moreover, an ANN-based formula for shear strength calculation of the column is proposed in the present study.

II. DATASET

To construct the neural network model, 156 experimental data samples of circular RC columns were collected from the literature [24]. Nine input parameters, including geometric dimensions, reinforcing bar details, material properties, and axial load, need to be provided to predict the shear strength of

the columns. Geometric dimensions comprise the height of the column (L), the diameter of the cross – section (D). Reinforcement details include the longitudinal reinforcement ratio (ρ_l), the transversal reinforcing bar ratio (ρ_s), and the spacing of the transversal reinforcements (s). Material properties are the yield strength of the longitudinal (f_{yl}) and transversal (f_{ys}) reinforcing bars and the compressive strength of concrete (f'_c). The axial load (P) is also considered.

III. EXISTING EQUATIONS FOR SHEAR STRENGTH OF CIRCULAR RC COLUMNS

In this study, we employed 5 typical equations, which were proposed in [25-29] for calculating the shear strength of circular RC columns, as expressed in Table II.

TABLE I. STATISTICAL PROPERTIES OF INPUT VARIABLES OF THE DATASET

Input variable	D (mm) (X_1)	L (mm) (X_2)	ρ_l (%) (X_3)	ρ_s (%) (X_4)	s (mm) (X_5)	f'_c (MPa) (X_6)	f_{yl} (MPa) (X_7)	f_{ys} (MPa) (X_8)	P (kN) (X_9)
Min	152	250	0.46	0.10	9	19	294	207	0.0
Mean	402	1429	2.69	1.03	61	37	420	430	736
Max	1520	9140	5.58	4.27	305	90	565	1000	6770
SD	175	1234	1.03	0.73	40	15	57	135	1010
COV	0.44	0.86	0.38	0.70	0.65	0.39	0.14	0.31	1.37

SD: standard deviation; COV: coefficient of variation

TABLE II. CIRCULAR RC COLUMNS SHEAR STRENGTH EQUATIONS

No.	Reference	Expression	Eq.
1	ACI 318 [25]	$V_1 = V_c + V_s$ $V_c = 0.166 \left(1 + \frac{P}{13.8A_g} \right) Dd\sqrt{f'_c}$ $V_s = \frac{A_{st}f_{ys}d}{s}$ <p>d is the effective depth of cross section; $d = 0.8D$ A_g is the gross section of the columns. A_{st} is the transversal reinforcement area</p>	(1)
2	Ascheim and Moehle [26]	$V_2 = V_c + V_s$ $V_c = 0.3 \left(k + \frac{P}{13.8A_g} \right) 0.8A_g\sqrt{f'_c}$ $k = \frac{4-\mu}{3}, \mu \text{ is the displacement ductility}$ $V_s = \frac{A_{st}f_{ys}d}{s \tan(30^\circ)}; d = 0.8D$	(2)
3	Biskinis et al. [27]	$V_3 = V_p + k(V_c + V_s)$ $V_c = 0.16 \max(0.5; 100\rho_l) \left(1 - 0.16 \min \left(5; \frac{a}{d} \right) \right) A_c\sqrt{f'_c}$ $V_s = \frac{A_{st}}{s} (d - d')f_{ys}$ $V_p = \frac{d-x}{2a} \min(P; 0.55A_c f'_c)$ <p>x is the neutral axis depth, d' is the depth of the compression reinforcement layer; $k = 1 \sim 0.75$ for $\mu < 1 \sim 6$ A_c is the concrete area of cross section.</p>	(3)
4	Moehle et al. [28]	$V_4 = k(V_c + V_s)$ $k = 0.7 \leq 1.15 - 0.075\mu \leq 1.0$ $V_c = 0.5\sqrt{f'_c} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{P}{0.5\sqrt{f'_c}A_g}} \right) \left(A_g \frac{D}{L} \right)$ $V_s = \frac{\pi A_{st}f_{ys}D'}{2s} \cot(45^\circ); D' = D - 2 \times \text{cover}$	(4)
5	Priestley et al. [29]	$V_5 = V_c + V_s + V_p$ $V_c = 0.8A_g k\sqrt{f'_c}$ $k = 0.29 \text{ for } \mu < 2$ $k = 0.29 - 0.12(\mu - 2) \text{ for } 2 < \mu < 4$ $k = 0.10 \text{ for } \mu > 4$ $V_s = \frac{\pi A_{st}f_{ys}D'}{2s} \cot(30^\circ); V_p = \frac{D-c}{2a} P$	(5)

Fig. 1. Distributions of the dataset.

The distributions of input parameters of the dataset are shown in Figure 1. The statistical properties of the experimental results are described in Table I. In this table, the 9 input variables to consider in performing ANN models are numbered from X_1 to X_9 .

IV. PERFORMANCE OF THE NEURAL NETWORK MODEL

The ANN model was used for predicting the shear strength of circular RC columns. An ANN model contains three layers:

- The input layer, where input parameters are entered.
- Hidden layer(s).
- The output layer, where the predicting result is obtained.

To perform the ANN algorithm, the following processes are required.

- Firstly, the input data are provided to the input layer, the signals are transferred through the connections, from one node (neuron) to another in the network. This procedure is called the forward pass.
- Secondly, after obtaining the output from the forward pass, it is required to evaluate this output by comparing it with the target using the Mean Squared Error (MSE).
- Thirdly, the network adjusts its weighted values according to a learning rule and using the error. Successively iterative adjustments will cause the network to produce the output, which is increasingly close to the target. After enough iterations, the training can be stopped based upon certain criteria.

Fig. 2. Structure of the proposed neural network.

Figure 2 shows the structure of the ANN model, in which 9 variables are defined for the input layer, while 5 neurons are selected for the hidden layer. The predicted shear strength is the output variable of the network. The iteration for optimizing the network and choosing the optimal model is shown in Figure 3. It demonstrates that after 9 epochs the process is converged and the MSE value is 0.0003462, highlighting a very small error. Figure 4 shows the performance of the ANN model with all data used. The difference between the test data and the predicted values is trivial, mostly less than 2%. This result implies that the ANN model predicted well the shear strength of the circular RC column.

Fig. 3. Selection of the best ANN model.

Fig. 4. Performance of all data.

Various architectures were tried, in which the training ratio changed from 0.6 to 0.85 and the number of hidden layers varied from 1 to 20. As a result, the best ANN architecture with the highest value of coefficient of determination (R^2) and the lowest value of Root-Mean-Square Error (RMSE) in training, testing, and validating phase was chosen. This ANN model comprises training ratio of 0.75, testing and validating ratios of 0.125, and 5 neurons in the hidden layer.

In the current study, we used 3 statistical parameters, which are R^2 , RMSE, and $a20 - index$, to evaluate the performance of ANN model. The definitions of these indicators are expressed by following equations:

$$R^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (t_i - o_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (t_i - \bar{o})^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{N} \right) \sum_{i=1}^N (t_i - o_i)^2} \quad (7)$$

$$a20 - index = \frac{n20}{N} \quad (8)$$

where t_i and o_i represent the target and output of i^{th} data point, respectively, \bar{o} is the mean of output data samples, N is the total number of the dataset, and $n20$ is the number of data satisfying $0.8 \leq \left| \frac{V_{exp}}{V_{predict}} \right| \leq 1.2$, in which V_{exp} and $V_{predict}$ are the shear strengths obtained from experiments and predictions respectively.

Table III shows the statistical parameters of the performance of the ANN model. It is found that the R^2 values are very high (i.e. 0.99) and the RMSE is very small. Additionally, the $a20 - index$, which represents whether the

samples fit the predicted values considering a deviation of ±20% compared with the test results, are close to unity. These results emphasize that the ANN model performed very well.

A comparison of shear strength between the predicted models (i.e. the 5 existing equations and the ANN model) is illustrated in Figure 5. It can be observed that the scattering of the regression obtained from the ANN model is significantly smaller than that from the other models. This highlights that the developed ANN model outperformed the other existing models which were based on design codes and previous studies.

TABLE III. ANN PERFORMANCE STATISTICAL PROPERTIES

Phase	R ²	RMSE (kN)	a20-index
Training	0.9980	5.490	0.9828
Testing	0.9917	6.026	1.0000
Validation	0.9807	1.862	1.0000
All data	0.9949	4.596	0.9872

We also developed a GUI in Matlab to facilitate the prediction of the shear strength of circular RC columns, as shown in Figure 6. Nine input parameters need to be provided. The shear strength of the column is readily obtained by clicking the Start Predict button after filling the inputs. It spends a few seconds to achieve the predictive results. The GUI tool is provided freely at https://github.com/duyduan1304/GUI_cirRC_columns.

V. ANN-BASED FORMULA AND GUI FOR CALCULATING SHEAR STRENGTH OF CIRCULAR RC COLUMNS

To apply the proposed ANN model in the design practice, a convenient tool needs to be established. An ANN-based formula is proposed, in which the 9 input parameters are considered, as shown in (9) and (10).

$$V_{max}^{Predict} = 263.10 \times (V_{max}^N + 1) + 14.00 \quad (9)$$

$$V_{max}^N = h_0 + \sum_{i=1}^5 h_i H_i \quad (10)$$

where $H_i = \tanh(c_{i0} + c_{i1}X_1 + c_{i2}X_2 + \dots + c_{i9}X_9)$, and h_0 , h_i , and c_{ij} ($j = 1 \div 9$) are coefficients. Since the equation is based on the ANN model, the accuracy is already verified in the previous section. The coefficients of (10) are provided in Table IV.

Fig. 5. Comparison between the predictive models and the test results.

TABLE IV. COEFFICIENTS OF (10)

i	h _i	c _{i0}	c _{i1}	c _{i2}	c _{i3}	c _{i4}	c _{i5}	c _{i6}	c _{i7}	c _{i8}	c _{i9}
0	-0.4004										
1	-2.0669	-0.5781	1.6751	1.6594	-0.1383	-0.3201	-0.3521	0.4429	-0.0890	-0.2107	0.8183
2	0.7730	0.0411	4.5936	-3.0741	0.4458	-0.4895	0.5590	1.0053	-1.0579	-1.5919	-0.6568
3	1.2947	-0.4285	-2.9629	3.2788	0.0685	-0.3139	0.7816	0.7325	-0.1291	-0.2473	-1.0247
4	0.2651	0.9082	4.1902	0.1640	0.4885	0.6303	0.1474	0.7892	1.3074	-0.6409	-0.4272
5	-3.4530	-0.1804	1.6534	-2.3002	-0.6223	0.5371	-2.2544	-2.1388	-1.3028	-0.3572	1.6519

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A practical ANN model was developed to calculate the shear strength of circular RC columns using 156 experiment data samples. The performance result of the proposed model was compared to that of 5 published models. The main conclusions of this study are.

- The proposed ANN model outperforms the existing equations in calculating the shear strength of circular RC columns. The performance of the model is verified using R², RMSE, and a20 – index values with respect to the predict-to-test strength ratio.

Fig. 6. GUI for calculating the shear strength of circular RC columns.

- An ANN-based formula, which accounts for 9 input variables, is proposed for the estimation the shear strength of the RC column.
- A practical GUI tool is developed for using in the design practice of circular RC columns.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Caglar, "Neural network based approach for determining the shear strength of circular reinforced concrete columns," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 3225–3232, Oct. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2009.06.002>.
- [2] H. Ketabdari, F. Karimi, and M. Rasouli, "Shear strength prediction of short circular reinforced-concrete columns using soft computing methods," *Advances in Structural Engineering*, vol. 23, no. 14, pp. 3048–3061, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1369433220927270>.
- [3] A. Fiore, G. C. Marano, D. Laucelli, and P. Monaco, "Evolutionary Modeling to Evaluate the Shear Behavior of Circular Reinforced Concrete Columns," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2014, Sep. 2014, Art. no. e684256, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/684256>.
- [4] A. Said and N. Gordon, "Predicting Shear Strength of RC Columns Using Artificial Neural Networks," *Journal of Building Materials and Structures*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 64–76, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.34118/jbms.v6i2.69>.
- [5] H.-T. Thai, "Machine learning for structural engineering: A state-of-the-art review," *Structures*, vol. 38, pp. 448–491, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2022.02.003>.
- [6] V.-L. Tran, D.-K. Thai, and S.-E. Kim, "Application of ANN in predicting ACC of SCFST column," *Composite Structures*, vol. 228, Nov. 2019, Art. no. 111332, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2019.111332>.
- [7] V.-L. Tran, D.-K. Thai, and D.-D. Nguyen, "Practical artificial neural network tool for predicting the axial compression capacity of circular concrete-filled steel tube columns with ultra-high-strength concrete," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 151, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 106720, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2020.106720>.
- [8] V.-L. Tran and S.-E. Kim, "Efficiency of three advanced data-driven models for predicting axial compression capacity of CFDST columns," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 152, Jul. 2020, Art. no. 106744, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2020.106744>.
- [9] T.-H. Nguyen, N.-L. Tran, and D.-D. Nguyen, "Prediction of Axial Compression Capacity of Cold-Formed Steel Oval Hollow Section Columns Using ANN and ANFIS Models," *International Journal of Steel Structures*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 1–26, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13296-021-00557-z>.
- [10] N.-L. Tran, T.-H. Nguyen, V.-T. Phan, and D.-D. Nguyen, "A Machine Learning-Based Model for Predicting Atmospheric Corrosion Rate of Carbon Steel," *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 2021, Dec. 2021, Art. no. e6967550, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6967550>.
- [11] T.-H. Nguyen, N.-L. Tran, and D.-D. Nguyen, "Prediction of Critical Buckling Load of Web Tapered I-Section Steel Columns Using Artificial Neural Networks," *International Journal of Steel Structures*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 1159–1181, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13296-021-00498-7>.
- [12] S. Tahzeeb and S. Hasan, "A Neural Network-Based Multi-Label Classifier for Protein Function Prediction," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 7974–7981, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4597>.
- [13] S. A. A. Biabani and N. A. Tayyib, "A Review on the Use of Machine Learning Against the Covid-19 Pandemic," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8039–8044, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4628>.
- [14] K. Aldriwish, "A Deep Learning Approach for Malware and Software Piracy Threat Detection," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7757–7762, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4412>.
- [15] S. Mangalathu, G. Heo, and J.-S. Jeon, "Artificial neural network based multi-dimensional fragility development of skewed concrete bridge classes," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 162, pp. 166–176, May 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2018.01.053>.
- [16] S.-H. Hwang, S. Mangalathu, J. Shin, and J.-S. Jeon, "Machine learning-based approaches for seismic demand and collapse of ductile reinforced concrete building frames," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 34, Feb. 2021, Art. no. 101905, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.job.2020.101905>.
- [17] V.-L. Tran and S.-E. Kim, "A practical ANN model for predicting the PSS of two-way reinforced concrete slabs," *Engineering with Computers*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 2303–2327, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00366-020-00944-w>.
- [18] H. Naderpour, M. Mirrashid, and P. Parsa, "Failure mode prediction of reinforced concrete columns using machine learning methods," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 248, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 113263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2021.113263>.
- [19] D.-D. Nguyen, V.-L. Tran, D.-H. Ha, V.-Q. Nguyen, and T.-H. Lee, "A machine learning-based formulation for predicting shear capacity of squat flanged RC walls," *Structures*, vol. 29, pp. 1734–1747, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2020.12.054>.
- [20] D.-K. Thai, T. M. Tu, T. Q. Bui, and T.-T. Bui, "Gradient tree boosting machine learning on predicting the failure modes of the RC panels under impact loads," *Engineering with Computers*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 597–608, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00366-019-00842-w>.
- [21] S. Mangalathu and J.-S. Jeon, "Classification of failure mode and prediction of shear strength for reinforced concrete beam-column joints using machine learning techniques," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 160, pp. 85–94, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2018.01.008>.
- [22] S. Mangalathu, H. Jang, S.-H. Hwang, and J.-S. Jeon, "Data-driven machine-learning-based seismic failure mode identification of reinforced concrete shear walls," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 208, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 110331, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.110331>.
- [23] M. R. Azadi Kakavand, H. Sezen, and E. Taciroglu, "Data-Driven Models for Predicting the Shear Strength of Rectangular and Circular Reinforced Concrete Columns," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 147, no. 1, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 04020301, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ST.1943-541X.0002875](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0002875).
- [24] W. Ghannoum *et al.*, "NEES: ACI 369 Rectangular Column Database," 2015, <https://datacenterhub.org/resources/255>.
- [25] *ACI 318-(2014), Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete and Commentary*. Farmington Hills, MI, USA: ACI Concrete, 2014.
- [26] M. Ascheim and J. P. Moehle, "Shear Strength and Deformability of RC Bridge Columns Subjected to Inelastic Cyclic Displacements," University of California, Berkeley, CA, USA, UCB/EERC-92/04, Mar. 1992. Accessed: Aug. 31, 2022.
- [27] D. E. Biskinis, G. K. Roupakias, and M. N. Fardis, "Degradation of Shear Strength of Reinforced Concrete Members with Inelastic Cyclic Displacements," *Structural Journal*, vol. 101, no. 6, pp. 773–783, Nov. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.14359/13452>.
- [28] J. P. Moehle, K. J. Elwood, and H. Sezen, "Gravity Load Collapse of Building Frame During Earthquakes," *Special Publication*, vol. 197, pp. 215–238, Apr. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.14359/11935>.
- [29] M. J. N. Priestley, R. Verma, and Y. Xiao, "Seismic Shear Strength of Reinforced Concrete Columns," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 120, no. 8, pp. 2310–2329, Aug. 1994, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(1994\)120:8\(2310\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1994)120:8(2310)).

A User-Friendly Dynamic Reactor Simulator Built in Microsoft Excel

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Abstract-Computer plant simulation is being used in all aspects of engineering, through many simulation software packages. However, almost all of them require licenses that must be purchased by engineering colleges intending to use simulation in their teaching. As public educational institutions everywhere are facing a scarcity of economic resources, they can resort to a freeware steady-state plant simulator, however, there is no availability of reliable, free dynamic plant simulators. In addition, published experiences on developing dynamic simulators use programming languages requiring paid licenses (e.g. Matlab) and thus have limited relevancy to schools struggling to cut expenses. This article first uses a set of typical college objectives to discuss the advantages of building their own dynamic simulators, and then shows the development of a user-friendly dynamic simulator of a batch reactor constructed entirely within Microsoft Excel, which, in contrast to the programming languages used in related reports, is already widely used by universities around the world.

Keywords-batch reactor; dynamic simulation; visual basic

I. INTRODUCTION

The typical bachelor Chemical Engineering degree program includes the subject of computer plant simulation in its last semesters [1]. One of the aims of the subject is that the student becomes familiar with commercial simulators, both dynamic and stationary. While some universities are able to purchase simulator licenses, this is not the case of most public institutions in developing countries, where financial resources are limited. As global trademark agreements have led to the prohibition of using unlicensed software in teaching, some institutions have resorted to free-ware software, of which reliable steady-state process simulators can be found (notably, the Cape Open Simulator [2]). However, no reliable, sufficiently tested, and license-free dynamic simulators are

currently at hand. Fortunately, the academic staff of most colleges has the skills required to develop and program process simulators containing most of the elements of professional software. This work shows, taking a batch reactor as an example, how such a simulator can be developed using the functionalities included in the widely used Microsoft Excel program.

The use of transient state simulation to promote industrial performance is well documented, both in its discrete-event version [3-5] and in its continuous form. Regarding the latter, literary reviews can be found in [6] on the application of neural networks in simulating chemical and biochemical processes and in [7] on the modeling of energy systems. Specific applications of simulation can be found in [8] where simulations to optimize plant design with respect to environmental objectives are applied and, more recently, in [9] that pressure dynamics to the simulation of a combined cycle gasification plant are incorporate. Authors in [10] simulated a petrochemical wastewater treatment plant, authors in [11] dealt with a desalination plant energized by ocean waves, authors in [12] optimized the drying process of phosphate pellets, authors in [13] emphasized on energy use when studying a benzene-toluene-xylene distillation system, and authors in [14] treated the control of the activated sludge process.

Regarding the software used to perform the simulations reported in the literature, the usage of simulation environments (e.g. Aspen) and high-level programming languages that provide routines facilitating simulation (e.g. Matlab) has recently increased, as opposed to the use of general-purpose languages (e.g. C++ or Fortran). For example, authors in [15] studied distillation tower sequences with Aspen Dynamics and Matlab Simulink, authors in [16] simulated a polymerization reactor using ChemCAD, and authors in [17] studied a heat

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integrated reactor applying Aspen-HYSYS. Authors in [18] used Matlab and COSMOL Multiphysics to simulate heterogeneous catalysis, authors in [19] applied Aspen Dynamics for studying the control of a combustion system, authors in [20] modeled an activated sludge process using INSEL, and authors in [21] used Aspen and Matlab to evaluate a predictive control scheme for CO₂ absorption plants. Didactic applications of dynamic simulations are reported in [22], in which the authors used Aspen HYSIS to train engineers in statistical methods to analyze distillation systems and in [23] where the Honeywell Unisim Design software was applied to simulate an isopropyl alcohol plant and train its operators. Instances of reports on the development of process simulators for didactic purposes are found in [24], in which a steady-state free-ware simulator was designed to which third parties could make additions in a "wiki" scheme, called Lazarus, running on UML language, and [25, 26] in which educational software was developed to analyze the dynamics of exchanger networks. Finally, authors in [27] used an online simulator to train operators to manage overpressures in natural gas systems, authors in [28] built the "LABVIRTUAL" platform, with educational material including simulators, and authors in [29] developed a Matlab-based dynamic simulator for chemical reactors.

Previous reports on the development of dynamic simulators for training purposes use either a commercial simulator or an advanced programming language (Matlab). However, the usage of such software requires the purchase and continual renovation of licenses. This limits the relevancy of the mentioned approaches to cash-strapped public schools in developing countries, who may find simulators running on easily accessible, universally used programming languages, like the one sketched in [30], far more useful. The current work builds on the latter reference by discussing, from the perspective of institutional objectives, the convenience for schools to build their own simulators, and presenting a complete description of an Excel-based dynamic simulator of a batch reactor. The shown simulator contains many of the features offered by professional software (button-based operations, filling the blank inputs, dialogue boxes, etc.).

II. METHODS

This article has two main purposes, for which different methods are applied:

- The first is to show, the convenience for colleges on developing their own simulators. This is done through objective analysis [31]: a hierarchy of fundamental objectives is built and the probable impact of the alternative on the objectives is assessed.
- The second is to present the dynamic simulator of a batch reactor developed in Microsoft Excel.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of Institutional Objectives

Generally speaking, public education institutions have two conflicting objectives: an academic one, related to the development of professional skills of their students and an

economical one, which refers to minimizing cost. This is shown in the structure in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Fundamental objectives hierarchy.

When contemplating the purchase of an educational tool, an institution should balance its price and the way it may benefit student formation. This is shown in Figure 2, where the objective damaged by the alternative is pointed at by a dotted arrow while that which is benefited by a solid one.

Fig. 2. Purchase impact on objectives.

The academic objectives aim for the student to acquire relevant professional skills. This is shown in Figure 3, where C_{ij} denotes skill i of subject j (for example, $C_{1,QG}$ refers to skill 1 of the subject "General Chemistry"). Figure 3 represents three skills covered in the subject "Process Simulation": $C_{1,SP}$, $C_{2,SP}$, and $C_{3,SP}$. $C_{3,SP}$ is defined as "The student will use commercial process simulators" [1]. Figure 3 breaks down the $C_{3,SP}$ skill into its steady-state simulation element SS part and a dynamic simulation one, Dyn .

Fig. 3. Details of academic objectives.

If a school hasn't already bought a simulator license, then it views the purchase impact on $C_{3,SP}$ as not worth its cost. For the steady-state simulation part of $C_{3,SP}$, this is solved by downloading one of the trustable, free-ware stationary plant simulators that can be found on-line. However, as there is no availability of transient state simulators with these qualities, the part of $C_{3,SP}$ dealing with dynamic simulation goes uncovered. Nevertheless, if the institution was to build its own dynamic simulator, this deficiency would be corrected (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Institutional options.

B. Process Description

The reactor to be simulated is based on the case described in [32], which features a steam heating jacket at temperature T_S and a cooling coil. A pair of consecutive reactions occur in the reactor.

Reaction $A \rightarrow B$ has a second order kinetics while $B \rightarrow C$ is a first order reaction and component B is the desired product.

The assumptions used in the model are:

- The reactor is thermally insulated and perfectly mixed.
- The temperature of the water in the coil is described by its average T_C value.
- Condensed steam is disposed at its saturation temperature.
- Reaction volume V and specific heat capacity C_p are constant.
- The heat transfer coefficient U_j of the heating jacket is constant while the one of the cooling coil U_C depends on the F_C cooling water flow according to:

$$\frac{1}{U_C} = \frac{1}{4550F_C^{0.8}} + \frac{1}{10.8} \quad (1)$$

Species and energy balances produce the following three differential equations, which describe reactor dynamics:

$$\frac{dC_A}{dt} = -k_1 C_A^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dC_B}{dt} = k_1 C_A^2 - k_2 C_B \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{(-\Delta H_1)}{\rho C_P} k_1 C_A^2 + \frac{(-\Delta H_2)}{\rho C_P} k_2 C_B + \frac{U_j A_j}{\rho C_P V} (T_S - T) - \frac{U_C A_C}{\rho C_P V} (T - T_C) \quad (4)$$

C_A and C_B are the concentrations of species A and B, $(-\Delta H_1)$ and $(-\Delta H_2)$ the enthalpies of reactions $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow C$ respectively, ρ and C_p are the liquid density and specific heat capacity, and U_j and U_C are the global heat transfer coefficients of the heating jacket and cooling coil of heat transfer area respectively, A_j and A_C . Reaction constants k_1 and k_2 and the temperature T are related by:

$$k_1 = \alpha_{10} \exp\left(\frac{-E_1}{RT}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$k_2 = \alpha_{20} \exp\left(\frac{-E_2}{RT}\right) \quad (6)$$

where E_1 and E_2 are the reaction activation energies and α_{10} and α_{20} their respective frequency factors. When the reactor is in closed-loop operation, the water flow to the cooling coil (F_C) and the steam temperature in the heating jacket (T_S) are manipulated to control the reactor temperature (T). In order to improve the yield of product B, the temperature set-point (T_d) may follow a time (t) dependent trajectory [32].

$$T_d(t) = 54 + 71 \times \exp(-2.5 \times 10^{-3} t) \quad (7)$$

As there are two manipulated variables, T_S and F_C , and one controlled variable T , the controller adjusts, through a proportional-integral control logic, the value of a parameter u , that linearly sets the value of the manipulated variables between their maximum and minimum values, according to:

$$T_S = (T_{S,max} - T_{S,min})u + T_{S,min} \quad (8)$$

$$U_C = (U_{C,min} - U_{C,max})u + U_{C,max} \quad (9)$$

The implicit Euler method is used to solve the differential equations and a Newton-Raphson procedure is used to solve the nonlinear algebraic equations in each integration step.

C. Simulator Description

The simulator was implemented as an Excel Macro. It is delivered to the user as an Excel file, the opening of which produces Figure 5. Clicking on the "Batch reactor" button displays the user interface (Figure 6). At the interface top (Figure 7) the simulation time and initial conditions are set: concentrations of A and B and temperature. The final values of these variables will appear in the "Final CA", "Final CB" and "Final T" dialog boxes. The user can propose a step size for the integration (10s is the default value). If the implicit Euler method does not converge for this step size, the program reduces it until convergence can be achieved. The step size used is shown the "Final step size (h)" box.

Fig. 5. Initial screen.

dialog boxes become active so the heat transfer areas per unit volume for the cooling coil and steam jacket are entered. If the "With heat transfer" option is selected, fields become active for the user to specify how the cooling water flow and steam temperature are to be managed. When selecting the "Open Loop" option, the user must input a value for the water flow and steam temperature, which remains constant throughout the simulation. If the cooling does not begin at time zero, a cooling commencement time can be specified (Figure 9). If the "Closed Loop" option is checked, the user should decide the temperature set point value management scheme: if the option "Automatic" is active, the temperature set point follows the time-dependent path of (7). If "Manual" is selected, the user inputs the temperature set point. Additionally, the proportional gain (K_C) and integral reset time (τ) of the temperature controller must be specified.

Fig. 6. User interface.

Fig. 9. Control loop specification.

The functionality of the interface (Figure 6) is completed by the buttons "Close", which closes it, "Start Simulation", which begins integrating the differential equations, and "Details", which displays the problem equations. Once "Start Simulation" is clicked, the interface hides and a progress bar appears (Figure 10). The columns A-F of the Excel sheet are cleared as the new results will appear there.

Fig. 7. Run initial state and parameters.

Fig. 8. Heating/cooling characteristics.

Fig. 10. Progress bar.

Once the simulation is completed, the simulation interface reappears and a dialog box asks if the results are to be graphed

The characteristics of the heating/cooling are set to the right of the interface (Figure 8). If "Adiabatic" is selected, no heat transfer is considered and when "With heat transfer" is chosen,

(Figure 11). If "Yes" is answered, the results are placed in the spreadsheet, and the graphs are updated with the most recent results (Figure 12). If "No" is clicked, the dialog box disappears, and the user can read the final concentrations and temperature in the corresponding dialog boxes.

Fig. 11. "Simulation completed" message.

Fig. 12. Final charts.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

As public education institutions receive taxpayer's money, they must use their resources efficiently, minimizing expenses that are perceived as unnecessary. Due to this, some institutions have opted not to purchase simulator licenses, thus limiting their students' acquisition of the skills related to the usage of this type of software. As far as the steady-state simulation of chemical processes is concerned, this can be solved by using a simulator downloadable for free, as some of them have been extensively validated. This is not the case, however, for the simulation of processes in a dynamic or transient state, where there are no free simulators that have been sufficiently tested. However, higher education institutions in most countries have the necessary human capacities to produce their own process simulators. This paper argues, based on a set of typical

institutional objectives, that this is a convenient alternative for schools, and illustrates how a dynamic simulator developed using the Microsoft Excel software, an everywhere present tool, looks like. It is hoped that this will encourage more institutions to develop their own dynamic process simulators.

The main advantage of the shown simulator is its running on Microsoft Excel that is already widely used by most engineering faculties in developing countries, and so it can be used without purchasing another license. One of its shortcomings, compared to the most powerful commercial dynamic process simulators available (eg. HYSYS dynamics), is that it doesn't show an animation of the real-time behavior of the variables, but rather calculates a response and then plots it. This, however, suffices for tuning of controllers and studying the dynamics of the system when faced with several disturbances, which are some of the main applications of simulation.

Finally, the presented simulator requires that the version of MS Office its run in codifies Macros in the Visual Basic programming language. This does not appear to be a serious limitation, as MS Excel has maintained this condition in versions as old as Office 95, and new desktop versions of MS Office are projected to continue to use Visual Basic as their Macro-Programming language for the foreseeable future. However, cloud or web-based versions of Excel (eg. in Office 365) as well as open versions of Office are transitioning to a java-script kind of language for macro programming, and the simulator in its current form cannot be expected to run in these programs. The simulator would need to be re-programmed in said languages, of made to run directly in a Visual Basic stand-alone programming suite. The basic simulation functionalities shown here, however, would be maintained in these changed simulator versions.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Licenciaturas," *Tecnológico Nacional de México*. <https://www.tecnm.mx/?vista=Licenciaturas>.
- [2] "COCO - the CAPE-OPEN to CAPE-OPEN simulator." <https://www.cocosimulator.org/>.
- [3] B. O. Odedairo and N. Nwabuokei, "Framework for Operational Performance Measurements in Small and Medium Scale Industries Using Discrete Event Simulation Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3103–3107, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2106>.
- [4] M. L. C. Hernandez, L. V. Rosas, R. F. R. Mantilla, G. J. E. Martínez, and V. V. Romero, "Supply Chain Cooperation by Agreed Reduction of Behavior Variability: A Simulation-based Study," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1546–1551, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1039>.
- [5] M. L. C. Hernandez, E. K. V. Hernandez, and S. L. Dominguez, "A Decision-Analytic Feasibility Study of Upgrading Machinery at a Tools Workshop," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 182–189, Apr. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.139>.
- [6] C. Renotte, A. Vande Wouwer, Ph. Bogaerts, and M. Remy, "Neural Network Applications in Non-Linear Modelling of (Bio)Chemical Processes," *Measurement and Control*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 197–201, Sep. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1177/002029400103400702>.
- [7] Adams II T. A., Ed., *Modeling and Simulation of Energy Systems - Processes, Special Issue*. MDPI, Basel, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.3390/books978-3-03921-519-5>.
- [8] P. E. Bauer and R. Maciel Filho, "Incorporation of environmental impact criteria in the design and operation of chemical processes," *Brazilian*

- Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 21, pp. 405–414, Sep. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0104-66322004000300005>.
- [9] D. Huang, H. Zhang, S. Weng, and M. Su, "Modeling and Simulation of IGCC Considering Pressure and Flow Distribution of Gasifier," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 10, Oct. 2016, Art. no. 292, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app6100292>.
- [10] I. M. Ariff and M. Bakir, "Dynamic Simulation of Petrochemical Wastewater Treatment Using Wastewater Plant Simulation Software," *MATEC Web of Conferences*, vol. 203, no. 1, Jan. 2018, Art. no. 03005, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201820303005>.
- [11] Y.-H. Yu and D. Jenne, "Numerical Modeling and Dynamic Analysis of a Wave-Powered Reverse-Osmosis System," *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 4, Dec. 2018, Art. no. 132, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse6040132>.
- [12] V. Meshalkin, V. Bobkov, M. Dli, and V. Dovi, "Optimization of Energy and Resource Efficiency in a Multistage Drying Process of Phosphate Pellets," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 17, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 3376, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12173376>.
- [13] S. Silviana, F. Dalanta, D. Q. A'yuni, L. Khoiriyah, P. R. Nabila, and M. F. Alfariis, "Design simulation and economic optimization of a benzene-toluene-xylene system distillation process upon the energy cost," *E3S Web of Conferences*, vol. 202, 2020, Art. no. 10003, <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202020210003>.
- [14] A. Lemita, S. Boulahbel, and S. Kahla, "Gradient Descent Optimization Control of an Activated Sludge Process based on Radial Basis Function Neural Network," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6080–6086, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3714>.
- [15] M. Khodadoost and J. Sadeghi, "Dynamic Simulation of Distillation Sequences in Dew Pointing Unit of South Pars Gas Refinery," *Journal of Chemical and Petroleum Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 109–116, Dec. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.22059/jchpe.2011.1512>.
- [16] I. Šoljić Jerbić, S. Kuzmić, and A. Jukić, "Dynamic Simulation of Batch Polymerization Reactor and Sensitivity Analysis of Styrene Homopolymerization," *Kemija u industriji: Časopis kemičara i kemijskih inženjera Hrvatske*, vol. 64, no. 3–4, pp. 151–167, Mar. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.15255/KUI.2013.039>.
- [17] T. P. Adhi and M. I. Prasetyo, "Process Stability Identification Through Dynamic Study of Single-bed Ammonia Reactor with Feed-Effluent Heat Exchanger (FEHE)," *MATEC Web of Conferences*, vol. 156, 2018, Art. no. 03003, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201815603003>.
- [18] A. K. Patan, M. Mekala, and S. K. Thamida, "Dynamic Simulation of Heterogeneous Catalysis at Particle Scale to Estimate the Kinetic Parameters for the Pore Diffusion Model," *Bulletin of Chemical Reaction Engineering & Catalysis*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 420–428, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.9767/brec.13.3.2098.420-428>.
- [19] T. Wanotayaroj, B. Chalermisinsuwan, and P. Piumsomboon, "Dynamic simulation and control system for chemical looping combustion," *Energy Reports*, vol. 6, pp. 32–39, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2019.11.038>.
- [20] F. Calise, U. Eicker, J. Schumacher, and M. Vicidomini, "Wastewater Treatment Plant: Modelling and Validation of an Activated Sludge Process," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 15, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 3925, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13153925>.
- [21] Q. Li, W. Zhang, Y. Qin, and A. An, "Model Predictive Control for the Process of MEA Absorption of CO₂ Based on the Data Identification Model," *Processes*, vol. 9, no. 1, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 183, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9010183>.
- [22] I. M. Joao and J. M. Silva, "Designing Solutions by a Student Centred Approach: Integration of Chemical Process Simulation with Statistical Tools to Improve Distillation Systems," *International Journal of Engineering Pedagogy (iJEP)*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 4–18, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijep.v7i3.6795>.
- [23] J. Puskás, A. Egedy, and S. Németh, "Development of operator training simulator for isopropyl alcohol producing plant," *Education for Chemical Engineers*, vol. 22, pp. 35–43, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ece.2017.11.003>.
- [24] S. M. Riachi, M. Duarte, and J. A. Scortechini, "Diseño De Un Simulador De Procesos Químicos Para Uso Colaborativo Y Didáctico," *REFCAL: Revista Electrónica Formación y Calidad Educativa*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 71–82, Apr. 2014.
- [25] L. M. F. Lona, F. A. N. Fernandes, M. C. Roque, and S. Rodrigues, "Developing an educational software for heat exchangers and heat exchanger networks projects," *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 1247–1251, Jul. 2000, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0098-1354\(00\)00324-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0098-1354(00)00324-0).
- [26] S. J. M. Cartaxo, P. F. G. Silvino, and F. A. N. Fernandes, "Transient analysis of shell-and-tube heat exchangers using an educational software," *Education for Chemical Engineers*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. e77–e84, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ece.2014.05.001>.
- [27] Y. Lee, C. Ko, H. Lee, K. Jeon, S. Shin, and C. Han, "Interactive plant simulation modeling for developing an operator training system in a natural gas pressure-regulating station," *Petroleum Science*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 529–538, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12182-017-0170-5>.
- [28] J. F. O. Granjo and M. G. Rasteiro, "Enhancing the autonomy of students in chemical engineering education with LABVIRTUAL platform," *Education for Chemical Engineers*, vol. 31, pp. 21–28, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ece.2020.03.002>.
- [29] R. Molina, G. Orcajo, Y. Segura, J. Moreno, and F. Martínez, "KMS platform: A complete tool for modeling chemical and biochemical reactors," *Education for Chemical Engineers*, vol. 34, pp. 127–137, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ece.2020.09.003>.
- [30] M. L. C. Hernández, T. R. G. Gómez, G. B. Brugada, and D. E. R. Vargas, "Desarrollo Del Simulador Dinámico De Un Reactor Batch Con Fines Didácticos (building a Dynamic Simulator of a Batch Reactor for Educational Purposes)," *Pistas Educativas*, vol. 43, no. 139, pp. 34–49, Dec. 2021.
- [31] R. L. Keeney, *Value-Focused Thinking: A Path to Creative Decisionmaking*. Cambridge, MA, USA: Harvard University Press, 1996.
- [32] A. K. Jana, *Chemical Process Modelling and Computer Simulation*, 2nd ed. New Delhi, India: Phi Learning pvt Ltd., 2011.

Assessment of the Soil Structure Inertial Interaction Effect on the Behavior Coefficient Using Simplified Methods

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Abstract-This study aims to assess the effect of the Soil Structure inertial Interaction (SSI) on the behavior coefficient (R). For this purpose, R was estimated with and without SSI. The pushover N2 method and its extension SSI-N2 method were applied to the plain Reinforced Concrete (RC) frame structures. For calculating the SSI effect on R, four shear wave velocities V_s , representing rocky soil, firm soil, loose soil, and very loose soil, with three soil damping ratios $\zeta_g\%$ for each soil type were considered. The estimated values of R using the N2 method were 4.1, 4.97, 5.75, and 6.96 for rocky soil, firm soil, loose soil, and very loose soil respectively. For the SSI-N2 method, R values were in the range of 3.67-3.97 for rocky soil, 4-4.69 for firm soil, 4.01-5.09 for loose soil, and 4.14-5.81 for very loose soil. In the Algerian code, R was kept constant for each soil type, and its value is 3.5 and 5 with and without infill masonry respectively. Soil shear wave velocity and the soil damping ratio must be taken into account in calculating R. The redundancy, overstrength, and ductility reduction coefficients were determined by taking into account the SSI. The SSI effect can change the values of R, so it must be taken into account when calculating R.

Keywords-behavior coefficient; N2 method; SSI-N2 method; RPA 99 v 2003; redundancy; overstrength; ductility

I. INTRODUCTION

An earthquake-resistant structure is designed to be subject to structural and non-structural damage during a strong seismic event without sudden collapse. This can be achieved by non-linear time history analysis [1] which is rather complicated and the responses depend on the registration component. Seismic codes have simplified this task by using inelastic response spectra. For this purpose, the elastic response spectra values are divided by the reduction coefficient or behavior coefficient (R) [2-4]. There are also many approaches to assessing inelastic performance using the pushover method [5-7]. The N2 method [8], the displacement coefficient method [9], and the capacity spectrum method [10] are included in many seismic codes (ATC40 [11], FEMA 356 [12], and EC8 [3]). These methods are used in the estimation of the ductility reduction coefficient. The behavior coefficient is also determined by a product of the

ductility reduction coefficient, the redundancy coefficient, and the overstrength coefficient [13, 14]. In the Algerian seismic code RPA 99 v 2003 [2] and Eurocode 8 [3], the behavior coefficient value depends on the typology of structure and the ductility without accounting for overstrength. The ductility reduction coefficient also depends on the interaction between the structure and the soil (SSI). Authors in [15] proposed a simplified approach to consider the inertial SSI effects on the ductility reduction coefficient by the combination of the nonlinear replacement oscillator method [16] and the N2 method. In [17], the effect of the height of Reinforced Concrete (RC) frames on overstrength, redundancy, and ductility response modification coefficients were estimated by the pushover method and nonlinear incremental dynamic analysis. The effect of vertical geometric irregularity on the R values of RC structures with Moment Resisting Frame (MRF) systems was studied in [18]. In this analysis, the capacity spectrum method according to ATC 40 was used.

In this paper, the behavior coefficient of a 2d RC frame structure is estimated by two simplified methods: the N2 method [8] and the SSI-N2 method [15]. In this study, 4 soil types and 3 soil damping ratios for each soil type were considered when taking into account the soil structure inertial interaction effect on the behavior coefficient value.

II. BEHAVIOR COEFFICIENT

In this study, the behavior coefficient is calculated by considering the 3 reduction coefficients (redundancy, ductility, and overstrength), according to [13, 14]:

$$R = R_\mu \cdot R_\rho \cdot R_\Omega \quad (1)$$

where R_μ , R_ρ , and R_Ω are ductility, redundancy, and overstrength reduction coefficients. Based on the pushover capacity curve in Figure 1 of [17], the above coefficients can be expressed as:

$$R_\mu = \frac{F_e}{F_y}, R_\rho = \frac{F_y}{F_1}, \text{ and } R_\Omega = \frac{F_1}{F_d} \quad (2)$$

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III. N2 AND SSI-N2 METHODS

The SSI-N2 method is an extension of the N2 method [5] proposed in [15, 19], where the SSI is introduced in the N2 method by using the replacement oscillator concept [16]. The replacement Single Degree Of Freedom (SDOF) system has the same effective values for the first mode of vibration of the structure (height h_{eff} , mass m , lateral stiffness k , and damping c), and 3 degrees of freedom (Figure 2). The stiffness k_u and k_θ , the damping C_u and C_θ represented in Figure 1, were expressed by the impedance function as follows:

$$K_u = \alpha_u k_u \quad (3)$$

$$C_u = \beta_u \frac{k_u r_u}{V_s} \quad (4)$$

$$K_\theta = \alpha_\theta k_\theta \quad (5)$$

$$C_\theta = \beta_\theta \frac{k_\theta r_\theta}{V_s} \quad (6)$$

where V_s is the mean shear wave velocity representing the site effects. The quantities $\alpha_u, \alpha_\theta, \beta_u$, and β_θ are adimensional parameters that take into account the influence of the excitation frequency on the impedance and k_u and k_θ represent the static stiffness of a half-space disk and are defined as follows:

$$k_u = \frac{8}{2-\nu} G_{ru}, \quad k_\theta = \frac{8}{3(1-\nu)} G_{r\theta} \quad (7)$$

$$a_u = 1, \beta_u = b_1 \quad (8)$$

$$a_\theta = 1 - b_1 \frac{(b_2 a_0)^2}{1+(b_2 a_0)^2} - b_3 a_0^2 \quad (9)$$

$$\beta_\theta = b_1 b_2 \frac{(b_2 a_0)^2}{1+(b_2 a_0)^2} \quad (10)$$

The coefficients a_0, b_1, b_2 , and b_3 are functions of Poisson coefficient ν [2], r_u, r_θ are the equivalent radii of foundation and are expressed as: $r_u = \sqrt{\frac{A_f}{\pi}}$, $r_\theta = \sqrt[4]{\frac{4I_f}{\pi}}$, where A_f and I_f are the area and inertia moments of the foundation. From the above expressions, the period and the damping ratios of the equivalent system with soil-structure interaction are calculated by the following expressions:

$$\tilde{T} = T \sqrt{1 + k \left[\frac{1}{K_u} + \frac{h_{eff}^2}{K_\theta} \right]} \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{\zeta} = \frac{T^2}{\tilde{T}^2} \zeta + \left[1 + \frac{T^2}{\tilde{T}^2} \right] \xi_g + \left[\frac{T_u^2}{\tilde{T}^2} \xi_u + \frac{T_\theta^2}{\tilde{T}^2} \xi_\theta \right] \quad (12)$$

where h_{eff} is the distance from the base to the fundamental mode inertial forces gravity center.

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{m d_y}{F_y}}, \quad \zeta = \frac{c}{2m\omega}, \quad m = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \phi_i \quad (13)$$

T and ζ are the fundamental mode period and the damping ratios of the equivalent system on a rigid base. m_i and ϕ_i represent the mass and the modal value of the fundamental mode for the floor i , d_y and F_y represent the yield displacement and the actual strength of the equivalent SDOF [8].

$$\omega_u^2 = \frac{K_u}{m}, \quad T_u = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_u}, \quad \zeta_u = \frac{c_u}{2m\omega_u} \quad (14)$$

where ω_u, T_u and ζ_u represent the natural frequency, the period, and the damping ratios of the equivalent soil structure system where the structure is assumed to be perfectly rigid and the rotation of the foundation is blocked.

$$\omega_\theta^2 = \frac{K_\theta}{m}, \quad T_\theta = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_\theta}, \quad \zeta_\theta = \frac{c_\theta}{2m\omega_\theta} \quad (15)$$

where ω_θ, T_θ and ζ_θ represent the natural frequency, the period, and the damping ratios of the equivalent soil structure system where the structure is assumed to be perfectly rigid and the translation of the foundation is blocked.

Fig. 1. The replacement SDOF for SSI.

The N2 method was used to determine the ductility μ of the equivalent system (without SSI). To take into account the inelastic interaction effects, an equivalent ductility coefficient is defined according to [13]:

$$\tilde{\mu} = 1 + (\mu - 1) \frac{T^2}{\tilde{T}^2} \quad (16)$$

The strength reduction coefficient proposed in [21] has been used in the case of soil-structure interaction:

$$\tilde{R}_\mu = (\tilde{\mu} - 1) \frac{\tilde{T}}{T_c} + 1 \quad \tilde{T} \leq T_c \quad (17)$$

$$\tilde{R}_\mu = \tilde{\mu} \quad \tilde{T} > T_c \quad (18)$$

The \tilde{R}_μ allowed to plot the new demand spectrum ($S_{ay}(\tilde{T}, \tilde{\zeta}), S_{dy}(\tilde{T}, \tilde{\zeta})$), based on the elastic spectrum, and the following relationships:

$$\tilde{S}_{ay}(\tilde{T}, \tilde{\zeta}) = \frac{S_{ae}(\tilde{T}, \tilde{\zeta})}{\tilde{R}_\mu(\tilde{T})} \quad (19)$$

$$\tilde{S}_{dy}(\tilde{T}, \tilde{\zeta}) = \frac{T^2}{4\pi^2} \tilde{S}_{ay}(\tilde{T}, \tilde{\zeta}) \quad (20)$$

The displacement demand \tilde{S}_d of the replacement SDOF on a flexible base is obtained by the intersection between the new capacity spectrum and the new inelastic demand spectrum ($S_a(T, \tilde{\zeta}), S_d(T, \tilde{\zeta})$). Thus the global displacement demand on a flexible base is calculated by the relationship: $\tilde{U} = \Gamma \tilde{S}_d$ where Γ is the modal participation coefficient.

IV. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDIED RC FRAME STRUCTURE

The studied 2d RC frame structure is shown in Figure 2. The columns and beams are calculated to satisfy the strong column weak beam condition (collapse through global mechanism) according to the Algerian code [2]. The design load F_d is 300.14kN, calculated with S_d/g equal to 0.197 using the inelastic response spectrum ($S_d/g, T(s)$) of the Algerian code

for rocky soil ($T_c=0.3$), where 5% damping ratio and 3.5 behavior coefficient, were considered. The frames were characterized by a span length of 5.5m, 6 spans, inter-story height of 3.0m, and 6 stories. The columns had a rectangular section of $400 \times 300 \text{mm}^2$; the beams had a rectangular section of $300 \times 200 \text{mm}^2$ and the reinforcement details are represented in Figure 3. The material characteristics are $F_{ck} = 35 \text{MPa}$, $E_c = 30 \text{GPa}$ for the concrete and $F_{yk} = 450 \text{MPa}$, $E_s = 210 \text{GPa}$ for the reinforcing bars. The used loads in the pushover analysis and floor masses are presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Studied 2d RC frame structure.

Fig. 3. Reinforcement details of the studied structure.

The period, the linear displacement shape, and the modal mass participating ratio for the fundamental mode of vibration are $T = 1.02\text{s}$, $\phi^T = [1, 0.91, 0.77, 0.57, 0.34, 0.12]$, and $\Gamma = 0.795$ respectively.

V. METHODOLOGY

Our study focused on the evaluation of the site effect on the behavior (reduction) coefficient. For this reason, 4 soil types (four shear wave velocities V_s) were considered: rocky, firm, loose, and very loose soil (Table I). For each soil type, 3 damping soil ratios $\zeta g\%$ had been taken into account: 5%, 10%, and 20% [22]. The lateral load pattern used in the pushover analysis is uniform [16]. The capacity curve is determined by Sap 2000 software [12]. The generalized force-deformation curves used in the FEMA-356 standard were adopted [16].

TABLE I. SOIL CHARACTERISTICS

Soil type	Shear modulus G (kN/m^2)	Poisson coefficient	Shear wave velocity V_s (m/s)
Rocky soil	648000	0.28	1000
Firm soil	180800	0.39	600
Loose soil	75000	0.45	300
Very loose soil	33500	0.5	150

The elastic response spectrum ($S_a/g, T(s)$) is that of the RPA99 v 2003 seismic code. For each soil type, damping ratio of 5%, peak ground acceleration of 0.5g, and behavior coefficient of 1 were considered (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. The elastic response spectrum for each soil type.

Ductility μ is estimated by [8]:

$$\mu = R_\mu \quad T > T_c \quad (21)$$

$$\mu = (R_\mu - 1) \frac{T_c}{T} + 1 \quad T \leq T_c \quad (22)$$

$$R_\mu = \frac{S_{ae}}{S_{ay}} \quad (23)$$

S_{ae} represents the acceleration value corresponding to the period T of the equivalent SDOF, in the elastic response spectrum ($S_a/g, T(s)$). The acceleration S_{ay} is determined by:

$$S_{ay} = \frac{F_y}{m} \quad (24)$$

where F_y and m are the actual strength of the equivalent SDOF and its mass respectively.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pushover curves (base shear versus roof displacement for global structure ($F(\text{kN}), U(\text{m})$), the equivalent model ($F_y(\text{kN}), u(\text{m})$), and the bilinear idealization of the equivalent model, are presented in the Figure 6 with $F_y=F/\Gamma$ and $u=U/\Gamma$ [5]. The transformation constant (modal participation coefficient) is $\Gamma = 1.31$ and the equivalent mass amounts to $m = 118.58 T$. Figure 6 shows the pushover curves of the global structure on a fixed base with the necessary forces to calculate the reduction coefficients.

Fig. 5. Pushover curves and bilinear idealization.

For each soil type and damping soil ratio, the design strength F_d , the first yielding strength F_1 , and the actual strength F_y are shown in Figures 7 – 10. F_{y5} , F_{y10} , and F_{y20} represent the actual strength of the global structure with 5%, 10%, and 20% of the damping soil ratios $\zeta g\%$ respectively. The

values of the redundancy coefficient ($R_p = F_y/F_1$) are in the range 1.05-1.48 and close to $R_p = 1.3$ prescribed by Eurocode 8 [3]. The overstrength coefficient ($R_\Omega = F_1/F_d$) is 2.1 which is in good agreement with the values found in [23]. The ductility reduction coefficient ($R_\mu = F_e/F_y$) values were determined with the N2 method (without SSI) and the SSI-N2 method (with SSI) (see Figure 11).

Fig. 6. Pushover curve of global structure on the fixed base.

Fig. 7. Pushover curve of global structure: rocky soil.

Fig. 8. Pushover curve of global structure: firm soil.

Fig. 9. Pushover curve of global structure: loose soil.

Fig. 10. Pushover curve of global structure: very loose soil.

Fig. 11. R_μ (N2) and $R_{\mu ssi}$ (SSI-N2).

Fig. 12. R_p VS $\zeta_g\%$ and soil type.

We noted that R_μ values with SSI (1.47-1.88) are lower than those estimated without SSI (1.51-2.56). In Figures 7-10, F_y varies with $\zeta_g\%$ and soil type. To clarify this relationship, the variation of the redundancy coefficient ($R_p = F_y/F_1$) versus $\zeta_g\%$ and soil type is represented in Figure 12. This Figure shows the decrease of R_p when $\zeta_g\%$ is increased in all soil types. Indeed, the damping ratio ζ of the equivalent system is proportional to $\zeta_g\%$ (12), thus the decrease of $\tilde{S}_{ay}(\tilde{T}, \zeta)$. The behavior coefficient, estimated for each soil type with the N2 method, is shown in Figure 13. According to RPA 99 v 2003 seismic code, the behavior coefficient in RC frame structure is 3.5 and 5 for infill and without infill masonry respectively. The estimated R values using the N2 method are 4.1, 4.97, 5.75, and 6.96 for rocky soil, firm soil, loose soil, and very loose soil respectively (Figure 13). The calculated R values with the SSI-N2 approach are shown in Figure 14 and are in the range 3.67-3.97 for rocky soil, 4-4.69 for firm soil, 4.01-5.09 for loose soil, and 4.14-5.81 for very loose soil. These values are lower than those of R without SSI (Figure 13) and depend on both $\zeta_g\%$ and the type of soil (shear wave velocity V_s). Therefore, damping soil ratios $\zeta_g\%$ and soil type should not be neglected when calculating the behavior coefficient R.

Fig. 13. Behavior coefficient without SSI (N2).

Fig. 14. Behavior coefficient with SSI (SSI-N2).

Table II summarizes the variation in the period T and ductility μ . \tilde{T} and $\tilde{\mu}$ are the period and ductility taking into account the SSI. According to (7), when decreasing shear modulus G , k_u and k_θ decrease therefore \tilde{T} in (11) increase and $\tilde{\mu}$ in (16) increase.

TABLE II. VARIATION OF PERIOD AND DUCTILITY VS. SHEAR WAVE VELOCITY V_s

Soil type	$T(s)$	$\tilde{T}(s)$	μ	$\tilde{\mu}$
Rocky soil	0.66	0.69	1.51	1.47
Firm soil	0.66	0.73	1.83	1.68
Loose soil	0.66	0.79	2.12	1.79
Very loose soil	0.66	0.9	2.65	1.89

The behavior coefficient for the studied frame structure has been estimated by different methods quoted in [24] and shown in Table III.

TABLE III. BEHAVIOR COEFFICIENT WITH DIFFERENT METHODS

Soil type	Newmark & Hall [24]	Giuffre &Giannini [24]	Krawinkler & Nassar [24]
Rocky soil	1.51	1.57	1.51
Firm soil	1.83	1.85	1.80
Loose soil	2.12	2.10	2.09
Very loose soil	2.07	2.39	2.62

For each soil type, the estimated behavior coefficients R in Table III are close to each other. Compared to the R of the Algerian code (3.5 and 5), the estimated R using the N2 method or the calculated R using the SSI-N2 method, the R values in Table III are conservative. The mentioned methods in Table III did not take into account the effect of the shear wave velocity and the damping soil ratio on the R value [23]. Due to the big difference between the R values calculated by the methods in Table III and the R values calculated by the N2 and SSI-N2 methods, the effect of V_s and $\zeta_g\%$ on R values cannot be neglected.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the behavior coefficient R has been estimated with and without soil structure inertial interaction. For this purpose, the pushover N2 method and its extension SSI-N2 method were applied in plan RC frame structures to evaluate the effect of SSI on R value. Four shear wave velocities representing rocky, firm, loose, and very loose soil, with three soil damping ratios for each soil type, were considered. The obtained values of R were compared with the values in the Algerian code and with those calculated by 3 other methods. Based on the obtained results, the following can be concluded:

- The N2 simplified method enabled us to estimate the reduction coefficients for each soil type, and thus the behavior coefficients. Their values were 4.1, 4.97, 5.75, and 6.96 for the rocky soil, firm soil, loose soil, and very loose soil respectively
- The SSI-N2 simplified method allowed us to estimate the reduction coefficients for each soil type and soil damping $\zeta_g\%$. Their values were in the range of 3.67-3.97, 4-4.69, 4.01-5.09, and 4.14-5.81 for rocky soil, firm soil, loose soil, and very loose soil respectively. These values are lower than those calculated by the N2 method for each soil type.
- The redundancy reduction coefficient increased with decreasing the soil damping ratio.
- The ductility reduction coefficient increased with decreasing soil shear wave velocity.
- The R values must be calculated while taking into account the shear wave velocity and the soil damping ratio.
- The estimated R values without taking into account the SSI effect are conservative.
- The N2 and SSI-N2 methods allow us to calculate the behavior coefficient only in buildings where the first mode is predominant and therefore it must be developed to take into account all the modes that have a significant contribution to the response of the building. The effect of torsion also cannot be neglected in the seismic response and therefore on the behavior coefficient, so it must be taken into account in these methods.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. D. Hatzigeorgiou and A. A. Liolios, "Nonlinear behaviour of RC frames under repeated strong ground motions," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 10, pp. 1010–1025, Oct. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2010.04.013>.
- [2] *Algerian Earthquake Resistant Regulations R P a 99/ Version 2003*. 2003.
- [3] *SS-EN 1998-1(2004), Eurocode 8: Design Of Structures For Earthquake Resistance - Part 1: General Rules, Seismic Actions And Rules For Buildings*. London, UK: British Standards Institution, 2004.
- [4] N. Null, *Seismic Evaluation and Retrofit of Existing Buildings*. American Society of Civil Engineers, 2014.
- [5] F. Abdelhamid, D. Yahiaoui, M. Saadi, and N. Lahbari, "Lateral Reliability Assessment of Eccentrically Braced Frames Including Horizontal and Vertical Links Under Seismic Loading," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8278–8283, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4749>.

- [6] R. A. Hakim, M. S. A. Alama, and S. A. Ashour, "Seismic Assessment of an RC Building Using Pushover Analysis," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 631–635, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.428>.
- [7] M. Javanpour and P. Zarfam, "Application of Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA) Method for Studying the Dynamic Behavior of Structures During Earthquakes," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1338–1344, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.902>.
- [8] P. Fajfar and P. Gaspercic, "The N2 Method for the Seismic Damage Analysis of Rc Buildings," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 31–46, 1996, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-9845\(199601\)25:1<31::AID-EQE534>3.0.CO;2-V](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-9845(199601)25:1<31::AID-EQE534>3.0.CO;2-V).
- [9] C. D. Comartin *et al.*, "A summary of FEMA 440: Improvement of nonlinear static seismic analysis procedures," in *13th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Vancouver, BC, Canada, Aug. 2004, pp. 1–14.
- [10] Y.-Y. Lin and K.-C. Chang, "An improved capacity spectrum method for ATC-40," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 32, no. 13, pp. 2013–2025, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.312>.
- [11] ATC 40, *Seismic Evaluation and Retrofit of Concrete Buildings*. Redwood City, CA, USA: Applied Technology Council, 1996.
- [12] FEMA 356, *Prestandard and Commentary for the Seismic Rehabilitation of Buildings*. Washington, DC, USA: Building Seismic Safety Council for the Federal Emergency Management Agency, 2000.
- [13] C. Rojahn, A. Whittaker, and G. Hart, *ATC-19 Structural Response Modification Factors*. Redwood City, CA, USA: Applied Technology Council, 1995.
- [14] ATC-34, *Critical Review of Current Approaches to Earthquake Resistant Design*. Redwood City, CA, USA: Applied Technology Council, 1995.
- [15] M. Mekki, S. M. Elachachi, D. Breysse, D. Nedjar, and M. Zoutat, "Soil-structure interaction effects on RC structures within a performance-based earthquake engineering framework," *European Journal of Environmental and Civil Engineering*, vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 945–962, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19648189.2014.917056>.
- [16] J. Aviles and L. E. Perez-Rocha, "Soil–structure interaction in yielding systems," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 32, no. 11, pp. 1749–1771, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.300>.
- [17] M. Ferraioli, "Behaviour Factor of Ductile Code-Designed Reinforced Concrete Frames," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2021, Feb. 2021, Art. no. e6666687, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6666687>.
- [18] M. M. Ahmed, M. A.-B. Abdo, and W. A. E.-W. Mohamed, "Evaluation of Seismic Response Modification Factor (R) for Moderate-Rise RC Buildings with Vertical Irregular Configuration." 2021, <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1141410/v1>.
- [19] M. Mekki, "Approche probabiliste dans la determination des courbes de vulnerabilite des structures en genie civil," Ph.D. dissertation, Universite de Bordeaux, Nouvelle-Aquitaine, France, 2015.
- [20] J. Bielak, "Dynamic behaviour of structures with embedded foundations," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 259–274, 1974, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.4290030305>.
- [21] T. Vidic, P. Fajfar, and M. Fischinger, "Consistent inelastic design spectra: Strength and displacement," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 507–521, 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.4290230504>.
- [22] SAP CSI, *Integrated software for structural analysis and design*. Berkeley, CA, USA: Computers and Structures Inc, 2000.
- [23] S. Sharifi and H. Toopchi-Nezhad, "Seismic Response Modification Factor of RC-Frame Structures Based on Limit State Design," *International Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 9, pp. 1185–1200, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40999-017-0276-6>.
- [24] M. Mouzzoun, O. Moustachi, and A. Taleb, "Evaluation du facteur de comportement pour le calcul parasismique des batiments en beton arme (Assessment of the behaviour factor for seismic design of reinforced concrete buildings)," *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 23–32, 2013.

The Effect of Adding Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPS) on Polymer-Modified Mortar

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Abstract-This study assessed the efficiency of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) waste as a 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60% substitute for fine aggregate in the manufacturing of lightweight cement composites. A 4% low-cost latex paint emulsion was added to the cement mortar to reinforce it as an alternative to the more expensive polymer admixtures. This improved the bonding between the cement matrix and the EPS particles because SBR films were produced in the cement matrix. The flexural strength of regular EPS concrete may also be significantly increased by SBR treatment. Eight alternative mix designs were created and evaluated for compressive and flexural strength, thermal conductivity, water absorption, and dry density. The polymer-modified mortar was created using a 0.4 water/cement ratio of local cement, polymer, and polystyrene. The results showed that compared to the standard combination at 28 days of aging, the compressive strength increased up to 29.26Mpa, flexural strength increased to 6.83Mpa, dry density increased up to 1930kg/m³, and absorption decreased by 4.95. Thermal conductivity decreased by 0.8291W/m.k.

Keywords-Polymer Modified Mortar (PMM); polymer; polystyrene; compressive strength

I. INTRODUCTION

Chemically or steam-processed polystyrene foam components are heated at high temperatures to produce Expanded Polystyrene (EPS), a Lightweight Artificial Aggregate (LWA). Round, closed-cell polystyrene particles have a density between 20 and 35kg/m³ and are composed of 98% air [1, 2]. Sandwich panels, floor decks, and curtain walls with increased thermal and acoustic insulation often use these lightweight nonstructural components. [2]. Environmentally friendly and inexpensive sound materials are becoming more popular. EPS is often used in packaging with minimum absorption and low cost because of its low density, hydrophobic characteristics, and excellent thermal insulation. Globally, an estimated amount of 14 million metric tons of polystyrene are manufactured each year and a large portion of the produced waste is placed in landfills [3, 4]. Styrene Butadiene Rubber (SBR) latexes may reduce bleeding and segregation in the cementitious matrix [5]. The network and the filler are two distinct parts of a polymeric composite. The dispersed stage and fortification are other names for this stage.

The disseminated media is responsible for further structural progress. The goal is to better connect the matrix to the filling [6] Polymer-Modified Mortar (PMM). With the right mix of cement and latex, PMM is an ideal product for use in the construction industry. Concrete and mortar characteristics may be altered by polymers. This material has higher tensile strength, improved chemical resistance, long-term use, and less environmental impact [7]. Latex improves the adhesive or bonding strength of materials such as pastes, mortars, concretes, tiles, bricks, steel, wood, and stone compared to the industry's unaltered counterparts [8]. Instead of cement, SBR is used in civil engineering to improve the hardened properties of concrete [9]. Adding SBR to strong concrete alters its physical properties. SBR is the most often used cement mortar modifier. The resulting cement hydrate and polymer layer have excellent adhesion properties. This results in less deformation and a more excellent crushing and flexural strength than conventional concrete [10]. SBR latex is widely used in a variety of modified solutions to enhance impermeability and frost resistance.

SBR latex has often been used to repair reinforced concrete structures. Several studies found that adding SBR latex to cement mortar increased bonding and flexural and tensile strength. This study attempts to improve the bonding between EPS particles and cement paste by including SBR latex in EPS concrete mixtures, improving compressive strength, flexural strength, thermal conductivity, and water absorption.

II. MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION

A. Cement

This study used OPC Cement I 42.5N. Tables I and II show its chemical and physical characteristics, which are in accordance with Iraq's specification No. 5/2019 [11].

B. Fine Aggregates

The used fine aggregates met the criteria in [12], had excellent gradation, were free of dangerous chemicals that might affect the examination's findings, went through the 0.6mm sieve, and passed the sieving test.

C. Water

According to [13], the utilized water was pure and devoid of contaminants.

D. Polymer

The SBR polymer was utilized without any treatment to make the Polymer Cement Mortar (PCM) mixes. Table III lists the SBR polymer's physical characteristics.

E. Expanded Polystyrene Beads

This study used spherical EPS beads with a maximum nominal size of 5mm instead of fine aggregates in certain instances. Table IV shows the physical characteristics of the EPS beads and the particle size gradient discovered during the EPS sieve analysis. Figure 1 shows the prepared EPS beads in a spherical shape.

Fig. 1. Expanded polystyrene beads.

TABLE I. CEMENT'S CHEMICAL COMPONENTS

Oxide composition	Result	Limits of [12]
CaO	62	-
SiO ₂	20.1	-
Al ₂ O ₃	4.24	-
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.16	-
SO ₃	2.15	≤ 2.8% if C3A>3.5 ≤ 2.5% if C3A<3.5
MgO	3.65	≤ 5%
Loss on ignition	3.42	≤ 4%
Insoluble residue	0.71	≤ 1.5%
Cement compounds [24]		
C ₃ S		59.02
C ₂ S		29.65
C ₃ A		4.21
C ₄ AF		12.65

TABLE II. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF CEMENT

Physical properties	Test result	Limits of [12]
Specific surface area, Blaine method, (m ² /kg).	295	≥ 250 m ² /kg
Setting time		
-Initial setting (min)	1:38	≥ 45 min
-Final setting (min)	3:45	≤ 600 min
Compressive strength of mortar (MPa)		
2-days	20.4	≥ 10 N/m ²
28-days	27.5	≥ 42.5 N/m ²
Soundness % (autoclave)	0.35	≤ 0.8

TABLE III. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF SBR POLYMER

Specifications given by the company	
Appearance	Milky white
Specific Gravity	1.02 ± 0.2 @ 250°C
Chloride content	Nil (EN 934-2)
PH value	7 - 10.5

TABLE IV. CHEMICAL AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF EPS

Sieve size	Passing%	ASTM C 330
4.75mm	6.5	5-40
2.36mm	1.5	0-20
Physical properties		
SO ₃ %	-	
Specific gravity	-	
Absorption	0	
Maximum particle size	5	

III. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

A. Mixing

An electric mechanical mixer with a capacity of 0.1m³ was used. Cement and fine aggregates were first added to the mixer and stirred for 1min. Following the proper dilution with water, the SBR polymer dispersion was added and mixed for around 3min at low speed. Finally, the other EPS particles were blended with the initial materials for an additional two minutes. Due to their low density, compared to other ingredients in the combination, this was done to guarantee that the polystyrene granules would not volatilize. The remaining water was added to the components that had already been mixed slowly and steadily for another 3 to 5min to get a homogeneous mixture free of segregation. Table V displays the percentages of the materials utilized in this production.

TABLE V. DETAILS OF MIXTURE PROPORTIONS

Mix	C:S	W/C%	Polymer:cement%	EPS%	Flow (mm)
E1	1:3	0.58	0%	0%	85
E2	1:3	0.4	4%	0%	100
E3	1:3	0.4	4%	10%	145
E4	1:3	0.4	4%	20%	147
E5	1:3	0.4	4%	30%	150
E6	1:3	0.4	4%	40%	155
E7	1:3	0.4	4%	50%	165
E8	1:3	0.4	4%	60%	190

B. Casting, Compaction, and Curing

Metal sheets were placed on top of the molds to prevent the samples from evaporating while remaining in the molds for 24h. This is the most effective way to cure polymer-containing concrete [14]. After being soaked in water for 72h, the samples were removed from the molds and left to dry until evaluation. The total number of samples prepared in this study was 168.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Flow Test

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate how an increase in replacement% helped boost the flow for EPS samples [15], validating that the hydrophobic properties of EPS aggregates were the higher value of the cause of the flow test. The natural aggregates exhibited angular shapes, while EPS particles were spherical. Therefore, more EPS causes more lubrication between the particles, which reduces friction and increases the flow test [16].

Fig. 2. Flow and effect relationship of EPS and SBR addition.

Fig. 3. Flow test.

B. Compressive Strength

This test was conducted using cubic specimens 50x50x50mm in size [17]. The test ages were 3, 7, and 28 days, and 3 cubes were examined for each age. The SBR concrete without EPS had the maximum compressive strength (up to 42.6MPa), surpassing the benchmark mix. In terms of combinations, the percentages of EPS by weight of fine aggregates were 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60%. Adding more polystyrene, the inadequate film formation caused a considerable reduction in the compressive strength of the polymer EPS concretes. The greatest compressive strength value was found for the 10% polystyrene replacement ratio (up to 29.26MPa), as shown in Figures 4 and 5. Compressive strength dropped as the percentage of polystyrene increased [18].

Fig. 4. Relationship of compressive strength and EPS.

Fig. 5. Testing cubic concrete sample.

C. Flexural Strength

Flexural strength determines how materials react to simple beam loads [19]. This test employed dimensional prismatic specimens (40x40x160mm) with various curing ages (7, 14, and 28 days). Three prisms were examined for each age. Figures 6 and 7 show the results. Figure 6 shows that the sample with a 10% substitution with EPS had flexural strength values that were greater than the standard, and even greater than the values of the SBR 4% mixing container. As the EPS ratio decreased, the flexural strength increased. An increase in flexural strength was accompanied by a rise in density because polymeric coatings increased the flexural strength of cured concrete [20].

Fig. 6. Relationship between flexural strength and EPS.

Fig. 7. Testing a prismatic concrete sample.

D. Thermal Conductivity

Cylinders measuring 100x200mm were produced to measure thermal conductivity [21]. The test was carried out at 28 days of age on 3 samples for each age. Thermal conductivity and density were shown to be closely related. Figures 8 and 9 show that thermal conductivity decreased when density declined. Porosity increased with EPS levels, which resulted in a reduction in heat conductivity. Adding SBR to the combinations had a considerable negative impact on thermal conductivity. The findings demonstrate that the density and volume of EPS impacted the thermal conductivity of the concrete. The partial replacement of fine aggregate with EPS was responsible for the change brought about in the lower density and greater air spaces of EPS beads, which resulted in the reduction of thermal conductivity outcomes of mixtures [22].

E. Water Absorption

The beads were hydrophobic because they were made of polystyrene sulfonate EPS. Figure 10 shows that the results of the absorption test worsened as EPS content increased. With increased EPS particles, mortars become more porous internally, making it easier for water to enter the mortar [23].

Fig. 8. Relationship between thermal conductivity and density.

Fig. 9. Testing a cylinder concrete sample.

Fig. 10. Relationship between absorption (%) and EPS.

V. CONCLUSION

The evaluation of thermal conductivity, flexural strength, and compressive strength of polymer-modified mortar and expanded polystyrene beads led to the following conclusions:

- At 28 days, the reference mixture's compressive strength at 10% replacement increased by 5.46%. Systematic reductions were made when the use of EPS use increased.
- At 28 days, the 10% replacement attained the greatest flexural strength of 6.83MPa.
- SBR enhanced overall porosity, decreased density, and created artificial micropores. Because of this, the partial substitution of aggregate with EPS may be blamed for the lower thermal conductivity. The material's insulating quality also increased due to the samples' decreased thermal conductivity.
- EPS demonstrated a successful use as a substitute material in the construction of nonstructural elements. It also provided a solution to the disposal of expanded polystyrene waste. Concrete's density and compressive strength decreased as the proportion of EPS substitute increased. The 10% EPS was best suited for non-structural uses, such as wall building and ornamental moldings. However, since it tends to break quickly under strain, 30, 40, 50, and 60% replacement should not be utilized for non-structural reasons. Therefore, it is advised to include polystyrene in

concrete mixtures when low-density (lightweight) concrete is desired and resistance is unnecessary.

- At 28 days, the 10% EPS replacement combination's water absorption was 4.95% lower than the reference mixture.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. N. Lakshmikanthan, B. S. Harshvardhan, J. Prabakar, and S. Saibabu, "Investigation on Wall Panel Sandwiched With Lightweight Concrete," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 225, Dec. 2017, Art. no. 012275, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/225/1/012275>.
- [2] J. Assaad, E. Chakar, and G.-P. Zéhil, "Testing and modeling the behavior of sandwich lightweight panels against wind and seismic loads," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 175, pp. 457–466, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2018.08.041>.
- [3] S. H. Soomro *et al.*, "Synthesis and Characterization of Poly(styrene)-block-Poly(acrylic acid) and Organoclay Based Hybrid Composite Materials," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3411–3415, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2273>.
- [4] N. A. Memon, A. H. Larik, M. A. Bhutto, N. A. Lakho, M. A. Memon, and A. N. Memon, "Effect of Prepackaged Polymer on Compressive, Tensile and Flexural Strength of Mortar," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 3044–3047, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2039>.
- [5] J. J. Assaad and N. Gerges, "Styrene-butadiene rubber modified cementitious grouts for embedding anchors in humid environments," *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, vol. 84, pp. 317–325, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2018.11.035>.
- [6] D. K. Bangwar, M. A. Soomro, N. A. Laghari, M. A. Soomro, and A. A. Buriro, "Improving the Bond Strength of Rice Husk Ash Concrete by Incorporating Polymer: A New Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2595–2597, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1791>.
- [7] B. A. Herki and J. M. Khatib, "Valorisation of waste expanded polystyrene in concrete using a novel recycling technique," *European Journal of Environmental and Civil Engineering*, vol. 21, no. 11, pp. 1384–1402, Nov. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19648189.2016.1170729>.
- [8] J. M. Khatib, B. A. Herki, and A. Elkordi, "7 - Characteristics of concrete containing EPS," in *Use of Recycled Plastics in Eco-efficient Concrete*, F. Pacheco-Torgal, J. Khatib, F. Colangelo, and R. Tuladhar, Eds. Woodhead Publishing, 2019, pp. 137–165.
- [9] Y. Ohama, "Polymer-based admixtures," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 189–212, Jan. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-9465\(97\)00065-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-9465(97)00065-6).
- [10] K. K. Kim, J. Yeon, H. J. Lee, and K.-S. Yeon, "Feasibility Study of SBR-Modified Cementitious Mixtures for Use as 3D Additive Construction Materials," *Polymers*, vol. 11, no. 8, Aug. 2019, Art. no. 1321, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11081321>.
- [11] "Iraqi Standard No. 5: Portland Cement. Standardization and Quality Control Central Organization," Baghdad, Iraq, 2019.
- [12] "Iraqi Specification No. 45: Aggregates of Natural Resources Used in Concrete and Construction in Iraq," Baghdad, Iraq, 1984.
- [13] "Iraqi Specification No. 1703: Water Used for Concrete and Mortar," Baghdad, Iraq: Central Organization for Standardization and Quality Control, Baghdad, Iraq 1992.
- [14] "Standard Practice for Making and Curing Concrete Test Specimens in the Laboratory," ASTM, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard C 192/C 192M-02.
- [15] "Standard Test Method for Flow of Hydraulic Cement Mortar," ASTM, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard C1437-20, 2001.
- [16] N. Hilal, N. Hamah Sor, and R. H. Faraj, "Development of eco-efficient lightweight self-compacting concrete with high volume of recycled EPS waste materials," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 28, no. 36, pp. 50028–50051, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-14213-w>.

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- [17] "Standard Test Method for Compressive Strength of Hydraulic Cement Mortars (Using 2-in. or [50-mm] Cube Specimens)," ASTM, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard C109/C109M-20.
- [18] T. K. M. Ali, N. Hilal, R. H. Faraj, and A. I. Al-Hadithi, "Properties of eco-friendly pervious concrete containing polystyrene aggregates reinforced with waste PET fibers," *Innovative Infrastructure Solutions*, vol. 5, no. 3, Jul. 2020, Art. no. 77, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41062-020-00323-w>.
- [19] "Standard Test Method for Flexural Strength of Hydraulic-Cement Mortars," ASTM, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard C348-21, 2008.
- [20] A. Dixit, S. D. Pang, S.-H. Kang, and J. Moon, "Lightweight structural cement composites with expanded polystyrene (EPS) for enhanced thermal insulation," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 102, pp. 185–197, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2019.04.023>.
- [21] "Standard Test Method for Steady-State Heat Flux Measurements and Thermal Transmission Properties by Means of the Guarded-Hot-Plate Apparatus," ASTM, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard C177-19, 2019.
- [22] A. A. Sayadi, J. V. Tapia, T. R. Neitzert, and G. C. Clifton, "Effects of expanded polystyrene (EPS) particles on fire resistance, thermal conductivity and compressive strength of foamed concrete," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 112, pp. 716–724, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2016.02.218>.
- [23] A. H. Medher, A. I. Al-Hadithi, and N. Hilal, "The Possibility of Producing Self-Compacting Lightweight Concrete by Using Expanded Polystyrene Beads as Coarse Aggregate," *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 46, no. 5, pp. 4253–4270, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-020-04886-9>.
- [24] A. M. Neville and J. J. Brooks, *Concrete Technology*, 6th ed. UK: Longman Scientific and Technical, 1995.

The Impact of Industrial Air Pollution on the Urban Environment of Setif

Modeling and Mapping of Total Suspended Particles

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Abstract-Setif is one of the urban agglomerations most exposed to the problem of air pollution, which mostly arises from the industrial zone located on its immediate outskirts, as is the case with a large number of Algerian cities. Due to its size and the nature of its activities, Setif is a significant source of industrial pollution. Numerous experts agree that the majority of present air pollution analysis techniques are limited to predicting the dispersion of pollutants. However, restricting oneself to these usually rigid aspects impedes the proper management of this sort of urban nuisance harming the city and its surroundings. Consequently, the aim of this study is to propose an approach for assessing the danger of air pollution that can be simply applied to any terrain. This technique includes three primary stages. Initially, ARIA Impact software is used to develop a model of the Total Suspended Particles (TSP). Using the Analytic Hierarchy Process technique, the many human, material, and environmental issues are then plotted on a map. The last step is to build synthesis maps by crossing the theme maps developed in the first two steps. Consequently, the anticipated outcome of this study is that the industrial zone of Setif will serve as the basis for a methodological exercise generated from a real-world situation. The examination of the current case study will illustrate the reliability of dispersion models in the evaluation of industrial pollution provided that certain essential aspects are recognized and handled effectively.

Keywords-air pollution; industrial zone; modeling; mapping; Setif

I. INTRODUCTION

Setif, the capital of the Algerian highlands, is a mostly agricultural city that has prospered from a substantial industrial infrastructure, including a 282-hectare industrial zone. Due to its size and the nature of activities conducted there, the industrial zone of Setif generates all types of nuisance and

pollution, especially atmospheric pollution due to the emission of pollutants and noxious gases, which are likely to harm the environment and the local population. Many contaminants are released into the atmosphere. Even though their concentrations are very low (usually measured in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), they pose a threat to human health [1].

Pollutant dispersion in the atmosphere is a significant concern for the scientific community and many researches concentrate on the modeling of the dispersion of industrial air pollution. Authors in [2] have experimented with the dispersion of pollutants from a chimney using two measurement techniques: laser tomography, which enables the visualization of the evolution of a feather over a long distance, and PIV, which aims to determine the speed and vorticity fields. Authors in [3] proposed an air dispersion model to monitor and compute the fluctuation of the concentration of a pollutant at various distances from the source using a real-world numerical example. In the same vein, the author of [4] created a technique dubbed Flow'Air-3D based on an operational computer code that enables the near-real-time monitoring of pollutants on an industrial site. The latter has deduced that atmospheric dispersion modeling is an intriguing analytical method since it permits the monitoring of an industrial site and the mapping of concentrations in the area around the site. Further, authors in [5] have dealt with the modeling of atmospheric dispersion phenomena and the study of air flows at the boundary layer. Fuzzy logic was used to quantify the uncertainties associated with ammonia leakage at an industrial facility. Dealing with the issue of industrial emissions in metropolitan areas, researchers in [6] addressed the requirement to anticipate the concentration of air pollutants such as negative ozone and volatile organic compounds based on a model of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). Authors in [7] performed a random investigation of

PM10 and PM2.5 (Particulate Matter with maximum diameter of 10 and 2.5 μ m respectively) in various metropolitan locations to examine the presence of other air pollutants, which is the focus of the current study. Notably, the current research focused on dust particles resulting from the open burning of solid waste and traffic patterns, which have a substantial impact on air quality. Authors in [8] centered on a novel method given in the form of an econometric model for the estimation of pollutant emissions created by civil aviation and affecting airports and the urban fabric around this neuralgic structure. Author in [9] undertook a methodological review that sought to comprehend the biogeochemical cycles that regulate the amounts of various air contaminants. According to him, numerical modeling is a scientific method of enveloping that involves solving mathematical equations reflecting the biogeochemical cycles and their dynamics. This strategy depends heavily on the computational capabilities of computers.

In this regard, the current paper will concentrate on one of these components of air pollution by, to begin with, modeling the dispersion of pollutants created by the electrochemical complex that comprises a substantial portion of the Setif industrial zone. Moreover, digital mapping to geographically locate the influence of this pollution on the urban environment of Setif is implemented. The novelty of this work consists in the use of cartography to simulate the amount of pollution in the city of Setif and its effect on the urban environment.

II. PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY

A. The Industrial Zone of Setif

According to the 2022 annual report compiled by the Establishment for the Management of Industrial Zones, among Algeria's 113 industrial zones, the Setif zone, situated 2km south of the city of Setif, is now one of the most prominent. Its significance is determined by the quantity and caliber of businesses situated there. There are now 202 firms in the zone, of which 32 are state- and 170 are private-owned, occupying 68 and 144 hectares respectively. The industrial zone is bounded to the east by the Wilaya road number 112 heading to Batna, to the west by the Constantine-Alger portion of the railway, to the south by the agglomeration known as Ain Trik, and to the north by the zone of Setif adjacent to the activity zone [10] (Figures 1, 2).

B. Operating Companies in the Industrial Zone

The first industrial units were established in the industrial zone of Setif between 1970 and 1982 [10]. These units are quite diverse in terms of their type of activity. Hence, production, realization, storage, distribution, and service provision units dispersed can be distinguished by sector. As seen in Figure 3, the enterprises operate in various plastics-related, electrochemical, electrical, building and construction material, food processing, and service sectors. The nature of the operations conducted there can be considered to be light industrial, not requiring a great deal of raw materials and labor, and using little space, water, and energy (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Location of the the industrial zone in relation to the city of Setif (screenshot from Google Earth, © CNES/Airbus, Landsat/Copernicus, Maxar Technologies).

Fig. 2. General overview of the industrial zone of Setif.

Fig. 3. Distribution of industrial companies in the area of Setif by sector of activity (data source: Industrial Zone Management Establishment).

C. The Industrial Zone as a Source of Air Pollution

According to the field study carried out and the data acquired by the director of the environment of Setif, the most polluting industrial units in terms of atmospheric pollution are mainly: the brickyard (EL AFAK: construction materials and ceramics), the national electrochemical products (NCEP) with its three components: lead refining, electrolytes, batteries and accumulators, and to a lesser degree the plastic processing units

such as: KPLAST, SOFIPLAST, ALMOULES and CALPLAST (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Location of the the NCEP complex (source: Industrial Zone Management Establishment treated by the authors, 2022).

Fig. 5. Chimney of the NCEP complex - lead refining unit.

For the complex NCEP, the sulfuric vapors emitted from its chimney release acids. At the same time, lead dust is primarily a result of the massive exploitation of lead, which is essential for this electrochemical industry. However, it is important to note the existence of a system for the treatment of atmospheric rejects at the level of this complex (Figure 5).

The data presented below confirm that the values of gas concentrations (NO_x , total hydrocarbons) are below the standards recommended by various international organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the USA Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), with the exception of total dust loaded with lead (in suspension), which recorded a dust concentration of 406.72g/m^3 exceeding the standard set by EPA (Figure 6) and WHO (Figure 7).

These aggressive air pollutants deteriorate the hues, alter the look of the structures, giving them an unattractive appearance, and cause physical degradation in all circumstances. Lead emissions are a significant cause of environmental pollution. Once deposited on soil, plants, and

surface waterways, lead may enter the food chain. According to [11], lead particles may be carried great distances in the atmosphere, sometimes up to hundreds of kilometers from their source, before being deposited by precipitation. As lead is neither biodegradable nor degradable, the body takes around 20 years to clear it. The neurological effects of lead poisoning in childhood may last a person's whole life [11].

Fig. 6. Atmospheric discharges (lead-containing dusts) from NCEP.

Fig. 7. Atmospheric discharges (hydrocarbons and NO_x) from NCEP.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

As stated above, this research entails 3 main phases. Using the ARIA Impact, the TSP emerging from the electrochemical complex as the primary source of air pollution is primarily estimated. Then, using many thematic maps of the city of Setif, different human, material, and environmental stakes susceptible to this form of industrial nuisance are detected. Lastly, a cross-reference of the digital maps created during the previous 2 stages will be used to illustrate the magnitude of the air pollution and its influence on the urban environment of Setif.

A. Phase One: Modeling the TSP Using the ARIA Impact Software

The modeling aims to anticipate the concentrations of different pollutants around the industrial site of the electrochemical complex NCEP and their mode of dispersion over the whole city of Setif. The pollutants modeled will be the Total Suspended Particles (TSP) rejected by the lead refining plant. ARIA Impact enables the development of meteorological data and the determination of the influence of emissions from a single or many points, lines, or surface sources. Using climatic data characteristic to the location, it is possible to simulate many years of operation. At the end of this simulation, themed maps (Figures 11-13) were created to illustrate the scope of the air pollution caused by the Setif industrial zone.

1) Materials Required for Modeling

The use of ARIA Impact software requires the following hardware:

- A baro-thermo-hygrometer (BTHR918) was used to measure the ambient temperature, atmospheric pressure, and relative humidity. This device allows controlling these climatic elements: air temperature (accuracy of 0.1°C), relative humidity (accuracy of 1% RH), and atmospheric pressure (accuracy of 0.3mb).
- A High Volume Sampler (HVS): The Portable Tripod High Volume Air Sampler GT2001 from Andersen is a compact unit that consists mainly of a protective housing, an electric motor, a high flow fan (1.1-1.7m³/min), a support capable of holding a 20cm×25cm filter, and a flow selector/flow time indicator. The TSP drawn in enters through the space between the cover and the support structure of the filter holder. The air velocity required for effective TSP collection is between 20 and 35cm/s. The shape of the collector roof allows the intake air to be well distributed on the surface of a G810 binderless glass fiber filter where the suspended dust is trapped. The TSP sampler is certified by the U.S. EPA.
- Portable gas analyzers: PHYWE portable gas analyzers are used to measure the concentration of CO₂, CO, NO, and total hydrocarbons. Their use requires a preliminary calibration thanks to appropriate gas bottles. The analyzers are connected to gas probes that are automatically recognized by the portable analyzers. These probes integrate a measuring cell with an infrared transmitter and receiver.

2) General Conditions for Modeling

As previously indicated, the modeling will anticipate the concentrations of different pollutants in the vicinity of the electrochemical complex at the level of the Setif industrial zone in order to compare them with the applicable international criteria. The contaminants modeled are mostly TSP. Notably, other pollutants such as benzene, arsenic, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, and butadiene are excluded from this modeling because they do not pose a risk due to the fact that the melting process (rotary kiln) permits sufficiently high temperatures to achieve their nearly complete combustion. Those modeling periods for which criteria have been defined are used. The followed standards are stated in Tables I and II:

TABLE I. AIR QUALITY STANDARDS

Time Interval	TSP
24 hours	260µg/m ³
1 year	70µg/m ³

Source: authors assisted by the Consulting Firm of Expertise in Environment and Industrial risks, 2022

TABLE II. PARTICLES AND LEAD DEPOSITION GUIDELINES

Pollutant Interval	Particles
1 year	350mg/m ² .day

Source: authors assisted by the Consulting Firm of Expertise in Environment and Industrial Risks, 2022

3) Input Data Required for Modeling

The software used for the modeling requires hourly meteorological data as well as topographical data of the modeled area. The hourly meteorological data for the Setif region are summarized in Table III. The physical data are summarized and reported in Table IV.

TABLE III. METEOROLOGICAL DATA DEPLOYED FOR MODELING

Parameter	Average
Temperature (°C)	36.5
Atmospheric pressure (mb)	600
Relative humidity (%)	21

Source: authors assisted by the Consulting Firm of Expertise in Environment and Industrial Risks, 2022

TABLE IV. PHYSICAL DATA

Parameter	Unit	Concentration	EPA standard
Total suspended dusts	µg/m ³	406.72	260
CO ₂	ppm	244	Greenhouse gases
Total hydrocarbons	ppm	0.129	0.24 for 3 hours
CO	ppm	0	35 for 1 hour
NO	ppm	0	0.25 for 1 hour for NO _x

Source: authors assisted by the Consulting Firm of Expertise in Environment and Industrial Risks, 2022

4) Emission Sources

The emission stack for gases from the melting process taking place in the rotary kiln represents the emission source that is distinguished by the following characteristics:

- Emission factors corresponding to existing processes were applied for TSP pollutants.
- These emissions are stationary and point sources.
- The pollutants are discharged at the stack of the above-mentioned source.
- The gas cleaning efficiency retained in the present study is 75%.
- Emission parameters are calculated based on the consumption of an annual quantity of 9000 tons of scrap metal and are summarized in Table V.

TABLE V. EMISSION PARAMETERS

Sources of Release	Solder flux	
Chimney height (m)	15	
Chimney diameter (m)	1.2	
Output temperature (K)	328	
Output speed (m/s)	1.2	
Purification efficiency	75%	99%
Mass Flow Rate (g/s)		
Lead particles	4 10 ⁻³	0.1
TSP	0.15	0.6

Source: authors assisted by the Consulting Firm of Expertise in Environment and Industrial Risks, 2022

5) Limitations of Using the ARIA Impact Software

Some quantities are relatively easy to measure regularly (quantities of atmospheric or water discharges, volumes of industrial waste). However, others are much more difficult to measure, either because of their very nature (nature of the

pollutants: gases, heavy metals) or because of their randomness or rarity (mechanism of diffusion of the pollutants according to their nature and the meteorological conditions). Generally, the likelihood of the phenomena will be determined using historical data and the consultant's observations.

B. Phase Two: Digital Mapping of Human, Material, and Environmental Issues

The spatialization of the stakes involves identifying, locating, and assessing the vulnerability of the three primary classes of stakes (human, environmental, and material) to the many types of pollution caused by the industrial zone of Setif. The approach entails a decomposition of the data collected initially by the statistical services of the municipality of Setif, followed by a recomposition according to the population density and the presence of material and environmental stakes on the space of the city in the form of homogeneous sets based on the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology [12]. This technique offers the benefits of being user-friendly, versatile, and adaptive.

1) Thematic Map of Human Issues

The current study will concentrate on the human stakes in 12 urban districts. These goals may be assigned vulnerability criteria to improve the use of basic residential density. Therefore, the population density given as the number of people per hectare are taken into account, as indicated in Table VI. The statistics are given by the municipality's statistical services. The thematic map of the human stakes distributed on the urban sectors of the city of Setif is illustrated in Figure 8.

TABLE VI. URBAN DISTRICTS CONSTITUTING THE CITY OF SETIF

Number	District	2018 Population	Surface area (hectares)
01	Saal Bouzid	45784	288.90
02	Belkhired Hassen	28973	527.37
03	05 Juillet 1962	38518	165.50
04	08 Mai 1945	60464	236.05
05	Tlidjene Abderahmane	24445	326.50
06	El Hassi	16281	1409.38
07	Laid Edhahoui	70829	2607.66
08	Cheikh El Aifa	79600	2484.67
09	Ferhat Abbas	71941	583.03
10	M. lemine Debaghine	50872	2742.32
11	1 ^{er} Novembre 54	67599	506.34
12	Ain Trick	21350	1215.78

Source: authors assisted by the Consulting Firm of Expertise in Environment and Industrial Risks, 2022

2) Thematic Map of Material and Economic Issues

The material issues can be classified into 5 major classes, divided into more detailed targets as shown in Figure 9.

- Residential buildings: Collective housing, residential subdivision (individual housing).
- Buildings with economic activities: Banks, etc.
- Buildings with various activities: Administration, worship (mosques), education (schools, universities), health (hospitals, clinics, health centers), heritage, entertainment (youth centers, cinemas, amusement parks, etc.), cemetery.

- Transport infrastructure: urban roads, public transport, pedestrian areas.
- Energy networks: electricity and gas.

Fig. 8. The produced map of human issues present in the city of Setif.

Fig. 9. The produced map of material and economic issues present in the city of Setif.

3) Thematic Map of Environmental Issues

Finally, grouping the environmental issues resulted in 8 major groups which are:

- Developed green space.
- Agricultural space.
- Protected natural areas: classified wooded areas, sensitive natural areas.
- Aligned trees.

- Potable water catchment areas.
- Water resources: Main watercourses, secondary watercourses.
- Remarkable natural heritage.

It should be noted that the environmental and material criteria were compiled using the database developed by the Center of Studies and Realizations in Urbanism of Setif as part of the study of the Inter-municipal Master Plan for Urban Development and Planning of Setif.

Fig. 10. The produced map of environmental issues in the city of Setif.

C. PHASE Three: Cross-Referencing of Thematic Maps and Location of Urban Sectors Exposed to the Problem of Air Pollution of Industrial Origin

During the last step of this digital mapping technique, the urban vulnerability of the city of Setif will be highlighted via theme synthesis maps, from which the urban regions most vulnerable to the pollution issue, will be spatialized with great accuracy. This technique will continue by superimposing and intersecting theme maps: those of the atmospheric pollutant modeling performed in the first phase and the thematic map of human, material, and environmental concerns from the second phase. Thus, with the technology of digital mapping, particularly that of the superposition of vectorial layers, a thematic map of synthesis will be created, depicting the urban sectors sensitive to the air pollution emerging from the Setif industrial zone.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Modeling (Phase I)

The amount of exposure can be determined by comparing the values of the maximum concentrations of the modeled contaminants to the appropriate environmental criteria. Each contaminant will be treated individually. Dust generated from the combustion of boilers and furnaces is less than 1µm in size.

Remember that for the modeling of air pollutants emitted from the chimney of the electrochemical complex, TSP with 75% purification efficiency were deployed. The maximum daily concentration and yearly mean concentration of TSP are projected to be 15.54 and 0.272g/m³ respectively (Figures 11 and 12). The predicted yearly average deposition is 0.74mg/m².day (Figure 13).

Fig. 11. Daily maximum concentrations of total particles related to the refining operations around the NCEP site (µg/m³).

Fig. 12. Annual average concentrations of total dust related to refining operations around the NCEP site (µg/m³).

B. Digital Mapping (Phases II and III)

The susceptibility map to industrial air pollution was developed by superimposing multiple thematic maps relevant to the topic, namely the air pollution maps derived by the modeling of the TSP (Figures 11-13) and those of the pervasive concerns at the municipal level (Figures 8-10). Cross-referencing these maps resulted in the following conclusions.

As shown by the maps of theme synthesis (Figures 14-16), the urban sectors most sensitive to the issue of industrial air pollution are those with a large population density in the vicinity of the industrial zone of Setif. Thus, the urban fabrics most exposed to this type of environmental risk would be the

entire southern portion of the city, including the city center and its surrounding historical suburbs, such as Tlidjène neighborhood, Beau Marché street, Bounechada street, Faubourg de la Gare, and Ain Sfiha. These sectors are marked as D2, D5, and D6 in Figure 14. On the other hand, the neighborhood of Ain Trik, which represents urban sector D12 in Figure 14, is clearly the area that continues to experience industrial air pollution at the most alarming rate. This is mostly due to the impacts of the prevailing winds (northerly winds) as the primary vector for the dispersion of gaseous pollutants on the one hand and the high population density on the other. As for the area of Setif, whose susceptibility is categorized as average, it encompasses a significant amount of the city, including the old districts Yahiaoui, Belair, Cheminots, Langare, Maaboud, the amusement park, the hospital, the financial city, and the administrative city. The unseen, but severe long-term impacts of air pollution on human health and the built environment threaten these tangible and of economic interests districts.

Fig. 13. Annual TSP from refining operations around the NCEP site (mg/m².day).

Fig. 14. Vulnerability of humans issues to industrial air pollution in the city of Setif.

Fig. 15. Vulnerability of material and economic issues to industrial air pollution in the city of Setif.

Fig. 16. Vulnerability of environmental issues to industrial air pollution in the city of Setif.

In the same context, the environmental stakes posed by the green spaces and agricultural land (all categories combined) located in the immediate vicinity of the industrial zone of Setif have been ranked as moderately vulnerable due to the fluorine pollution demonstrated by multiple plants and laboratories. Lastly, the industrial zone, with its urban areas marked as D9 and D10 and the remainder of the city marked as D7 and D8 in Figure 16 would be generally spared and hence be the least susceptible to these pollution issues.

V. CONCLUSION

The current study has confirmed that the Setif region creates several kinds of air pollution, originating mostly from the electrochemical complex NCEP through an excessive emission of carbon dioxide, sulfur dioxide, sulphuric vapors, and lead-laden dust. Lead dust and acid-releasing sulfuric vapors are primarily products of the electrochemical industry's vast exploitation of lead. These air pollutants provide a significant source of environmental pollution for all forms of city-wide problems.

The final thematic maps show that high-population-density urban areas around the Setif industrial zone are under risk. The most vulnerable urban fabric is the city core (formerly an intramural city) and its historical suburbs, with AinTriq having the most industrial air pollution. The industrial zone and the rest of the city have minimal vulnerability to environmental hazards.

This research's strategy is applicable to other Algerian cities. It allowed the exact definition of TSP and their effects on Setif. The current technique can replace previous methods which predict the dispersion of air contaminants without considering their spatial and geographical effect on urban areas. Thus, the focus is placed on the methodological aspect of the instrument and not the outcomes particular to the region under study. The recommended method uses basic data from local technical services and generally available, easy-to-use modeling software (Aria Impact). Digital mapping technologies were used to create clear and realistic thematic maps. The developed cartographic assistance aims to help decision makers decrease industrial air pollution in metropolitan areas. It is

possible to reduce atmospheric pollutants by implementing ambitious initiatives to install manufacturing chimneys with electrostatic screens. In addition, the issue must be resolved drastically upstream by conducting significant and exhaustive impact assessments and standardizing the stack heights in proportion to the overall topography of the surrounding urban fabric. The most acceptable solution to preserve the urban environment of the cities is to use clean technologies with emissions that adhere to standard requirements.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Allag, "Contribution À L'étude De La Dispersion Des Polluants," Ph.D. dissertation, Ferhat Abbas University Setif-1, Setif, Algeria, 2018.
- [2] P. Bournot, P. Caminat, N. Mahjoub, and J. Stefanini, "Experimental study of the plume emitted by a smokestack," in *Proceedings of PSFVIP-4*, Chamonix, France, 2003.
- [3] M. Saeedi, H. Fakhraee, and M. R. Sadrabadi, "A Fuzzy Modified Gaussian Air Pollution Dispersion Model," *Research Journal of Environmental Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 156–169, <https://doi.org/10.3923/rjes.2008.156.169>.
- [4] F. Vendel, "Modélisation de la dispersion atmosphérique en présence d'obstacles complexes : application à l'étude de sites industriels," Ph.D. dissertation, Ecole Centrale de Lyon, 2011.
- [5] R. Chutia, S. Mahanta, and D. Datta, "Uncertainty modelling of atmospheric dispersion model using fuzzy set and imprecise probability," *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 737–746, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.3233/IFS-120680>.
- [6] J. S. Khan, S. Khoso, Z. Iqbal, S. Sohu, and M. A. Keerio, "An Outlook of Ozone Air Pollution through Comparative Analysis of Artificial Neural Network, Regression, and Sensitivity Models," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3387–3391, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1944>.
- [7] A. A. Siyal, S. R. Samo, Z. A. Siyal, K. C. Mukwana, S. A. Jiskani, and A. Mengal, "Assessment of Air Pollution by PM10 and PM2.5 in Nawabshah City, Sindh, Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3757–3761, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2440>.

- [8] D. A. Pamplona and C. J. P. Alves, "Civil Aircraft Emissions Study and Pollutant Forecasting at a Brazilian Airport," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5217–5220, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3227>.
- [9] Y. Roustan, "Modélisation de la dispersion atmosphérique du mercure, du plomb et du cadmium à l'échelle européenne.," Ph.D. dissertation, Ecole des Ponts ParisTech, Paris, France, 2005.
- [10] A. Rouabeh, "L'industrialisation et le fait urbain à travers la zone industrielle de Sétif," Ferhat Abbas University Setif-1, Setif, Algeria.
- [11] O. Chanel *et al.*, *Plomb dans l'environnement: quels risques pour la santé?* INSERM, 1999.
- [12] M. Emre Guler, "Incorporating Multi-Criteria Considerations into Supplier Selection Problem Using Analytical Hierarchy Process: A Case Study," *Yaşar Üniversitesi E-Dergisi*, vol. 3, no. 12, pp. 1787–1810, Jun. 2008.
- [13] "Lead Regulations," *US EPA*, Feb. 12, 2013. <https://www.epa.gov/lead/lead-regulations>.
- [14] J. Emery, N. Marilleau, N. Martiny, and T. Thévenin, "Le modèle SCAUP: Simulation multi-agents à partir de données de CAPteurs Urbains pour la Pollution atmosphérique automobile," *Cybergeo: European Journal of Geography*, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4000/cybergeo.34767>.
- [15] T. Zhang, G. Li, Y. Yu, Y. Ji, and T. An, "Atmospheric diffusion profiles and health risks of typical VOC: Numerical modelling study," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 275, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 122982, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122982>.
- [16] O. Popov *et al.*, "Risk Assessment for the Population of Kyiv, Ukraine as a Result of Atmospheric Air Pollution," *Journal of Health & Pollution*, vol. 10, no. 25, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 200303, <https://doi.org/10.5696/2156-9614-10.25.200303>.
- [17] E. Sharma, R. C. Deo, R. Prasad, A. V. Parisi, and N. Raj, "Deep Air Quality Forecasts: Suspended Particulate Matter Modeling With Convolutional Neural and Long Short-Term Memory Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 209503–209516, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3039002>.
- [18] S. E. Gillooly *et al.*, "Development of an in-home, real-time air pollutant sensor platform and implications for community use," *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 244, pp. 440–450, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.10.064>.
- [19] R. Baron and J. Saffell, "Amperometric Gas Sensors as a Low Cost Emerging Technology Platform for Air Quality Monitoring Applications: A Review," *ACS Sensors*, vol. 2, no. 11, pp. 1553–1566, Nov. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssensors.7b00620>.
- [20] G. R. McKercher, J. A. Salmond, and J. K. Vanos, "Characteristics and applications of small, portable gaseous air pollution monitors," *Environmental Pollution (Barking, Essex: 1987)*, vol. 223, pp. 102–110, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.12.045>.
- [21] E. Esposito *et al.*, "Assessing the Relocation Robustness of on Field Calibrations for Air Quality Monitoring Devices," in *AISEM Annual Conference on Sensors and Microsystems*, 2017, pp. 303–312, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-66802-4_38.

Assessment of Shear Strength Models of Reinforced Concrete Columns

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Abstract-Shear strength is a crucial parameter in designing Reinforced Concrete (RC) columns considering the effects of lateral loads such as wind or earthquakes. Numerous design codes and published studies have proposed equations for calculating the shear strength of RC columns. However, a discrepancy exists between the calculated models and the experimental results. The aim of this study is to evaluate the calculated models for the shear strength of rectangular RC columns based on 735 data sets, obtained from the literature. Six code-based and empirical models are investigated in this paper. The four code-based models include ACI 318 (2014), CSA (2014), Eurocode 8 (2005), and FEMA 273 (1997), and the two empirical models are proposed by Ascheim & Moehle (1992) and Sezen & Moehle (2004). The shear strengths of RC columns are calculated for the six models using inputs from the experimental database. Finally, the results are evaluated using statistical indicators, including coefficient of determination and root-mean-squared error. The results reveal that Eurocode 8 (2005) is the best model, followed by Sezen & Moehle (2004) and Canada CSA (2014) since the results of those models are close to the experimental ones and shown to be more conservative than the others.

Keywords-design code; empirical formula; experimental data; rectangular RC column; shear strength

I. INTRODUCTION

Reinforced Concrete (RC) columns are critical structural members in buildings and bridges. Failure of these members can lead to the partial or total collapse of structures. The load bearing capacity of columns depends on their geometric dimensions, materials, detailing, or applied loads [1-3]. There are three typical failure modes of RC columns under lateral loads, including flexure, shear, and flexure-shear failure modes. Flexure failure occurs when the lateral stiffness is reduced due to cracking and spalling of the concrete cover, yielding of the longitudinal reinforcements, and crushing of core concrete. Meanwhile, the shear failure mode is governed if diagonal

cracks are predominant. Flexure-shear failure forms after yielding of rebars and is combined with shear failure. It should be noted that the shear failure mode is unexpected and it is avoided in designing columns, especially structures in earthquake-prone areas. Shear strength is the most important parameter in the design of RC columns, specifically when considering the effects of lateral loads such as earthquakes or wind. Currently, there are numerous design codes and published studies, which proposed equations for calculating shear strength of RC columns. Typical design codes are ACI 318 (2014) [4], CSA (2014) [5], Eurocode 8 (2005) [6], and FEMA 273 (1997) [7]. Additionally, some empirical models were developed by some authors such as Ascheim & Moehle (1992) [8] and Sezen & Moehle (2004) [9]. However, a discrepancy between calculated models and experimental results is existing. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the different calculated models based on a large experiment database.

The aim of this study is to assess the different calculated shear strength models of rectangular RC columns, in which code-based and empirical-based formulas are considered. For that, an extensive database including 735 experimental results is collected from the literature. Six calculated models are investigated, consisting of the four mentioned design codes [4-7] and [8-9]. It should be noted that the equation proposed in [8] is also used in ASCE/SEI-41-06 (2007) [10]. The shear strength of rectangular RC columns is calculated for the six models using the collected database. Finally, the calculated results are evaluated using statistical properties comprising of the coefficient of determination and the root-mean-squared error.

II. CALCULATED MODELS OF SHEAR STRENGTH OF RECTANGULAR RC COLUMNS

In this study, we employed 6 typical equations for calculating the shear strength of RC columns, from current

design codes and well-known previous studies, as described in Table I.

TABLE I. SHEAR STRENGTH MODELS CONSIDERED IN THIS STUDY

Model	Equation	
ACI 318 [4]	$V = 0.166 \left(1 + \frac{P}{13.8A_g} \right) b_w d \sqrt{f'_c} + \frac{A_{sh} f_{yh} d}{s}$ <p>P is the axial load, A_g is the gross cross-section area of the column, b_w is the effective shear width of column section, d is the effective depth of the column, f'_c is the compressive strength of concrete, A_{sh} and f_{yh} are the area and yield strength of transverse reinforcement, and s is the spacing of stirrups.</p>	(1)
CSA [5]	$V = \min \left(\beta b_w d_v \sqrt{f'_c} + \frac{A_{sh} f_{yh} d}{s} \cot \theta, 0.25 f'_c b d \right)$ $d_v = 0.9d$ <p>b is the width of column section, β is a factor accounting for the shear resistance of cracked concrete, θ is the angle of inclination of diagonal compressive stresses to the longitudinal axis of the column.</p>	(2)
Eurocode 8 [6]	$V = V_p + k(V_c + V_w)$ $V_c = 0.16 \max(0.5; 100\rho_l) \left(1 - 0.16 \min\left(5; \frac{a}{d}\right) \right) A_c \sqrt{f'_c}$ $V_w = \frac{A_{sw}}{s} (d - d') f_{yw}$ $V_p = \frac{D-x}{2a} \min(P; 0.55 A_c f'_c)$ $A_c = b_w d, (d = 0.8h)$ <p>ρ_l is the longitudinal reinforcement ratio, a is the distance from the maximum moment section to the point of inflection (i.e. M/V)</p>	(3)
FEMA 273 [7]	$V = 0.29 \lambda \left(k + \frac{P}{13.8A_g} \right) b d \sqrt{f'_c} + \frac{A_{sh} f_{yh} d}{s}$ <p>λ is a coefficient depending on concrete weigh (= 1.0). $k = 1.0$ for low ductility demand. $k = 0$ for moderate and high ductility demand.</p>	(4)
Ascheim & Moehle [8]	$V = 0.3 \left(k + \frac{P}{13.8A_g} \right) 0.8A_g \sqrt{f'_c} + \frac{A_{sh} f_{yh} d}{s \tan(30^\circ)}$ $k = \frac{4-\mu}{3}, \mu \text{ is the displacement ductility}$ $d = 0.8H$	(5)
Sezen & Moehle [9]	$V = k \left(\frac{0.5 \sqrt{f'_c}}{a/d} \sqrt{1 + \frac{P}{0.5A_g \sqrt{f'_c}}} \right) 0.8A_g + k \frac{A_{sh} f_{yh} d}{s}$ $d = D - \text{cover}$ $k = 1 \text{ for } \mu < 2.0; k = 0.7 \text{ for } \mu > 6.0;$ $0.7 \leq k = 1.15 - 0.075\mu \leq 1.0 \text{ for } 2.0 \leq \mu \leq 6.0$ <p>a is the shear span, (i.e. the distance from the loading point to the boundary).</p>	(6)

III. COLLECTED DATABASE

A significant database, which covers a wide range of scenarios, was collected to evaluate the calculated shear strength models. A total of 735 experimental data sets of rectangular RC columns were extensively collected from [11-36]. Figure 1 depicts the configurations and reinforcement properties of the rectangular RC column. It should be noted that L is the column height, B and H are the width and depth of the column section respectively, and ρ_l and ρ_h are the longitudinal and transversal reinforcement ratios respectively. The statistical properties of the experimental results are

described in Table II. The frequency histograms of input parameters and failure modes of the 735 data samples are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Configurations and properties of rectangular RC columns.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF THE DATABASE INPUT PARAMETERS

Input parameter	L (mm)	B (mm)	H (mm)	s (mm)	f'_c (MPa)	f_yt (MPa)	f_yh (MPa)	ρ _l (%)	ρ _h (%)	P (kN)
Min	225	150	100	20	20	313	215	0.20	0.01	0.0
Mean	1286	284	301	101	49	448	496	2.15	0.94	1130
Max	3000	610	610	457	141	745	1470	4.50	4.00	5492
SD	647	109	115	77	27	77	222	0.69	0.94	1069
COV	0.53	0.38	0.38	0.76	0.55	0.17	0.45	0.32	0.99	0.95

IV. EVALUATION OF THE CALCULATED SHEAR STRENGTH OF THE RC COLUMNS

To quantitatively evaluate the shear strengths calculated from models in Table I, statistical parameters are employed including coefficient of determination (R^2) and Root-Mean-Squared Error ($RMSE$). R^2 value represents the percentage of data close to the regression line. The higher the R^2 , the more the accuracy of the calculated model and vice versa. $RMSE$ is used for quantifying the difference (error) between the calculated and the experimental value. The smaller the $RMSE$, the more the accuracy of the calculated model and vice versa. The definitions of R^2 and $RMSE$ are described in (7) and (8).

$$R^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (t_i - o_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (t_i - \bar{o})^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{n} \right) \sum_{i=1}^n (t_i - o_i)^2} \quad (8)$$

where t_i and o_i are the test and calculated results of the i sample, n is number of the samples of the database, \bar{o} is the mean of calculated results.

Fig. 2. Distributions of input database.

Figure 3 shows the comparison between the shear strengths of the RC columns calculated by the six models and the test results. The dash line represents the 1:1 line, while the red line is the regression. It can be seen that the models of EC8, Sezen & Moehle, and CSA provide a smaller scattering than others, and results are mostly under the 1:1 line. In other words, the calculated results are smaller than those of experiments. Moreover, the results based on ACI 318, FEMA 273, and Ascheim & Moehle have a bigger scattering. These deviations may be caused by the ductility ratio and the diagonal compressive force in the columns.

Table III summarizes the calculated statistical parameters, i.e. R^2 and $RMSE$ for the investigated models. Additionally, the properties of the ratio $V_{calculate}/V_{test}$, are also obtained, in which minimum (Min), maximum (Max), Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), and Coefficient of Variation (CV) are determined. The results show that EC8 [6] is the most accurate model with the highest R^2 value ($= 0.892$) and the smallest $RMSE$ ($= 163\text{kN}$). Moreover, [9] and [5] are also good models with $R^2 = 0.766$ and 0.68 , and $RMSE = 185\text{kN}$ and 220kN respectively. Besides, the mean values of $V_{calculate}/V_{test}$ of

those models are smaller than 1.0, thus, the results calculated by [5, 6, 9] are conservative. It can be seen that the equations of [4, 7, 8] provide lower accuracy. Based on the results, we suggest the use of equations of the models of [5, 6, 9] for calculating the shear strength of rectangular RC columns.

Fig. 3. Comparison between the six calculated models and the test results.

TABLE III. STATISTICAL PROPERTIES FOR THE EVALUATION OF THE SHEAR STRENGTH OF RC COLUMNS

Model	R^2	RMSE	Statistical properties of $V_{calculate}/V_{test}$				
			Min	Max	Mean	SD	CV
ACI 318 [4]	0.608	202	0.19	20.88	1.40	1.42	1.01
CSA [5]	0.680	220	0.18	9.88	0.93	0.74	0.80
EC8 [6]	0.892	163	0.07	4.84	0.64	0.37	0.57
FEMA 273 [7]	0.448	238	0.07	19.62	1.15	1.33	1.15
Ascheim & Moehle [8]	0.476	251	0.21	35.78	2.14	2.41	1.13
Sezen & Moehle [9]	0.766	185	0.09	8.51	1.02	0.71	0.69

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents and analyzes six code- and empirical-based models for the shear strength calculation of rectangular RC columns. A set consisting of 735 experimental data samples of rectangular RC columns was collected. The accuracy of the models is evaluated by statistical parameters. The following conclusions are drawn from the current study:

- EC8 [6] is the most accurate model for estimating the shear strength of rectangular RC columns, followed by Sezen & Moehle [9] and CSA [6].

- The equations of ACI 318 [4], FEMA 273 [7], and Ascheim & Moehle [8] have a lower accuracy.
- It should be noted that this study considered rectangular RC columns. For other RC column types, such as circular or hollow sections, further investigation is required.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Hamzaoui and T. Bouzid, "The Proposition of an EI Equation of Square and L-Shaped Slender Reinforced Concrete Columns under Combined Loading," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7100–7106, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4048>.
- [2] H. Ullah, M. Rizwan, M. Fahad, and S. a. A. Shah, "Seismic Evaluation of the RC Moment Frame Structure using the Shake Table," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6674–6679, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3959>.
- [3] A. R. Khoso, J. S. Khan, R. U. Faiz, M. A. Akhund, A. Ahmed, and F. Memon, "Identification of Building Failure Indicators," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4591–4595, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2872>.
- [4] *ACI318-(2008), Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete (ACI 318-08) and Commentary*. Farmington Hills, MI, USA: American Concrete Institute, 2008.
- [5] *CSA-(2014), Design of concrete structures (CSA A23. 3-14)*. Toronto, ON, Canada: Canadian Standards Association, 2014.
- [6] *SS-EN 1998-1(2004), Eurocode 8: Design Of Structures For Earthquake Resistance - Part 1: General Rules, Seismic Actions And Rules For Buildings*. London, UK: British Standards Institution, 2004.
- [7] *FEMA 273, NEHRP Guidelines For The Seismic Rehabilitation Of Buildings*. Washington, DC, USA: Building Seismic Safety Council for the Federal Emergency Management Agency, 1997.
- [8] M. Ascheim and J. P. Moehle, "Shear Strength and Deformability of RC Bridge Columns Subjected to Inelastic Cyclic Displacements," University of California, Berkeley, CA, USA, UCB/EERC-92/04, Mar. 1992.
- [9] H. Sezen and J. P. Moehle, "Shear Strength Model for Lightly Reinforced Concrete Columns," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 130, no. 11, pp. 1692–1703, Nov. 2004, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2004\)130:11\(1692\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2004)130:11(1692)).
- [10] *ASCE/SEI 41-06(2007), Seismic Rehabilitation of Existing Buildings*. Reston, VA, USA: American Society of Civil Engineers, 2007.
- [11] W. Ghannoum *et al.*, "NEES: ACI 369 Rectangular Column Database," *DEEDS*, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.4231/D36688J50>.
- [12] M. A. Belkacem, H. Bechtoula, N. Bourahla, and A. A. Belkacem, "Effect of axial load and transverse reinforcements on the seismic performance of reinforced concrete columns," *Frontiers of Structural and Civil Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 831–851, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11709-018-0513-3>.
- [13] D. Wang, H.-N. Li, and G. Li, "Experimental study on dynamic mechanical properties of reinforced concrete column," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 32, no. 23, pp. 1793–1806, Dec. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0731684413492451>.
- [14] J. Xiao and Ch. Zhang, "Seismic behavior of RC columns with circular, square and diamond sections," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 801–810, May 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2007.01.010>.
- [15] H. Rodrigues, A. Furtado, and A. Arede, "Behavior of Rectangular Reinforced-Concrete Columns under Biaxial Cyclic Loading and Variable Axial Loads," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 142, no. 1, Jan. 2016, Art. no. 04015085, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ST.1943-541X.0001345](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0001345).
- [16] J. Melo, H. Varum, and T. Rossetto, "Experimental cyclic behaviour of RC columns with plain bars and proposal for Eurocode 8 formula improvement," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 88, pp. 22–36, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2015.01.033>.
- [17] J. C. M. Ho, "Experimental Tests on High-Strength Concrete Columns Subjected to Combined Medium Axial Load and Flexure," *Advances in Structural Engineering*, vol. 15, no. 8, pp. 1359–1374, Aug. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1260/1369-4332.15.8.1359>.
- [18] D. Wu, Y. Ding, J. Su, Z.-X. Li, L. Zong, and K. Feng, "Effects of tie detailing configurations on reinforcement buckling and seismic performance of high-strength RC columns," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 147, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 106791, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2021.106791>.
- [19] C. T. N. Tran, "Experimental and analytical studies on the seismic behavior of reinforced concrete columns with light transverse reinforcement," Ph.D. dissertation, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore, 2010.
- [20] Y. C. Ou, D. P. Kurniawan, and N. Handika, "Shear behavior of reinforced concrete columns with high-strength steel and concrete under low axial load," in *Reinforced Concrete Columns with High Strength Concrete and Steel Reinforcement*, Toronto, ON, Canada, Oct. 2012, vol. 293, pp. 145–160.
- [21] Y.-A. Li, Y.-T. Huang, and S.-J. Hwang, "Seismic Response of Reinforced Concrete Short Columns Failed in Shear," *Structural Journal*, vol. 111, no. 4, pp. 945–954, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.14359/51686780>.
- [22] V. Popa, D. Cotofana, and R. Vacareanu, "Effective stiffness and displacement capacity of short reinforced concrete columns with low concrete quality," *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 2705–2721, Dec. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-014-9618-9>.
- [23] C. Jin, Z. Pan, S. Meng, and Z. Qiao, "Seismic Behavior of Shear-Critical Reinforced High-Strength Concrete Columns," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 141, no. 8, Aug. 2015, Art. no. 04014198, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ST.1943-541X.0001167](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0001167).
- [24] M. M. EL-Attar, H. Z. El-Karmoty, and A. A. EL-Moneim, "The behavior of ultra-high-strength reinforced concrete columns under axial and cyclic lateral loads," *HBRC Journal*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 284–295, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hbrj.2014.10.003>.
- [25] T.-S. Eom, S.-M. Kang, H.-G. Park, T.-W. Choi, and J.-M. Jin, "Cyclic loading test for reinforced concrete columns with continuous rectangular and polygonal hoops," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 67, pp. 39–49, May 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2014.02.023>.
- [26] E. A. Opabola, K. J. Elwood, and S. Oliver, "Deformation capacity of reinforced concrete columns with smooth reinforcement," *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 2509–2532, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-018-00540-w>.
- [27] C. Goksu, H. Yilmaz, S. R. Chowdhury, K. Orakcal, and A. Ilki, "The Effect of Lap Splice Length on the Cyclic Lateral Load Behavior of RC Members with Low-Strength Concrete and Plain Bars," *Advances in Structural Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 639–658, May 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1260/1369-4332.17.5.639>.
- [28] Y. Zhang, S. Zheng, X. Rong, L. Dong, and H. Zheng, "Seismic Performance of Reinforced Concrete Short Columns Subjected to Freeze-Thaw Cycles," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 13, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 2708, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9132708>.
- [29] S. Bousias, A.-L. Spathis, and M. N. Fardis, "Seismic Retrofitting of Columns with Lap Spliced Smooth Bars Through FRP or Concrete Jackets," *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 653–674, Oct. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632460601125714>.
- [30] K. K. Arani, M. D. Ludovico, M. S. Marefat, A. Prota, and G. Manfredi, "Lateral Response Evaluation of Old Type Reinforced Concrete Columns with Smooth Bars," *Structural Journal*, vol. 111, no. 4, pp. 827–838, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.14359/51686734>.
- [31] T. P. Pham and B. Li, "Seismic Performance of Reinforced Concrete Columns with Plain Longitudinal Reinforcing Bars (with Appendix)," *Structural Journal*, vol. 111, no. 3, pp. 561–572, May 2014, <https://doi.org/10.14359/51686572>.
- [32] J. Zhang, R. Cai, C. Li, and X. Liu, "Seismic behavior of high-strength concrete columns reinforced with high-strength steel bars," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 218, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 110861, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.110861>.

-
- [33] N. H. Dinh, S. Park, and K.-K. Choi, "Seismic performance of reinforced concrete columns retrofitted by textile-reinforced mortar jackets," *Structure and Infrastructure Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 1364–1381, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15732479.2019.1708958>.
- [34] C.-G. Kim, H.-G. Park, and T.-S. Eom, "Effects of Type of Bar Lap Splice on Reinforced Concrete Columns Subjected to Cyclic Loading," *Structural Journal*, vol. 116, no. 2, pp. 183–194, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.14359/51711142>.
- [35] H.-J. Hwang, J.-O. Noh, and H.-G. Park, "Structural capacity of reinforced concrete columns with U-shaped transverse bars," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 216, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 110686, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2020.110686>.
- [36] K.-K. Choi, G. T. Truong, and J.-C. Kim, "Seismic performance of lightly shear reinforced RC columns," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 126, pp. 490–504, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2016.07.060>.

Investigation of the Effect of Normal Incidence of RF Wave on Human Head Tissues Employing Cu and Ni Grid PET Films

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Abstract-The rising number of frequency bands and the demand for wireless communication devices has become a growing concern regarding health and safety. The human head is a vulnerable body part when exposed to mobile phones. To ensure a high level of protection of the head from undesirable Electromagnetic Field (EMF) emissions, a shield is incorporated in this paper between the head and the mobile smartphone. The shielding material used to protect the head from the RF emissions is Copper (Cu) grid transparent Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) film and Copper (Cu) grid transparent PET film with Nickel (Ni) coating forming a laminated mesh. The RF emission metric from the smartphone is determined to evaluate the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) numerically with a variation in frequencies ranging from 850MHz to 5.47GHz at normal wave incidence by the Transmission Line Method. The variation in frequency is observed in two head models, one of an adult and one of a child. Compared with the no shield condition, a significant SAR reduction is observed when PET-Cu or PET-Cu-Ni conductive coating transparent shielded mesh is embodied on the front part of the mobile phone between the phone and the head. In the child 7-layered head model at 5.47GHz, a significant reduction in SAR is observed from 10.5W/kg to 0.00001W/kg using the Cu grid PET film and to 0.0000032W/kg using Cu and Ni grid PET film.

Keywords-RF radiation emissions; Specific Absorption Rate (SAR); shielding effectiveness; copper grid PET film; conductive coating

I. INTRODUCTION

Many researchers have recently proposed altogether new designs of 5G antennas for cellular or wireless application to mitigate the effect of RF absorption emitted from mobile handsets [1-3]. The wireless communication devices emit most of the Electromagnetic Fields (EMFs) from unwanted electromagnetic interference [4]. A proper Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) technique is the need of the hour to mitigate such undesirable emissions from the devices, such as mobile smartphones [5]. Though many regulatory bodies

specify the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) permissible limits, as and when the devices migrate to 5G frequency bands and higher and the radiation emission from the devices surges [6]. The EMFs and radiation spectrum consist of an extensive range of frequencies covering non-ionizing and ionizing radiation [4]. The non-ionizing radiation results in thermal and non-thermal effects on human bodies. The thermal effects are caused due to heating of the body due to a temperature rise in the tissues. The National Radiological Protection Board (NRPB) discussed the possibility of reducing the body SAR limit over 10g of tissue from averaged 10W/kg to 5W/kg, because the data indicated that the temperature rise in the eye and brain may exceed 1°C [7]. There is a fear of biological hazards occurring with the rise of temperature in the biological tissues of the brain of humans.

In order to protect the human head from the non-ionizing radiation of mobile smartphones, a shield can be incorporated between the human head and the mobile phone on the front side. The property of Shielding Effectiveness (SE) for a single or a laminated shield can be determined as a metric to measure the performance of any shielding material used. Many shielding materials have been used in the past to shield EM waves, such as polymer-based composites that include polymer matrixes and structured polymer composites, foams and aerogels, textile-based shielding materials, graphene, CNT-based or nanocomposites-based materials, etc. Due to various disadvantages and fitting the material for a particular scientific application, the researchers are now shifting their focus to transparent shielding material [4-5].

Most materials and their blends have been used in shielding the EM wave in various applications such as aerospace, electrical and electronic equipment, medical electronics, and wireless networks and devices. A very limited literature is available for the SAR measurement and distributions studies and implementation using shielding for mobile phone applications. Even with the implementation of SAR distribution, mobile phone emissions have been reduced using the usual electromagnetic software simulations [8-9]. Most of

the relative published studies have considered a modification in the mobile antenna design for their theoretical or experimental validation of SAR reduction.

Authors in [10] fabricated a transparent conductive electrode made of metal mesh film composed of Nickel mesh embedded on PET substrate achieving optical transparency of 84%. The Ni mesh was embedded with polymer poly (3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene): poly (styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT: PSS) for supercapacitor application [10]. Galvanic deposition of Cu-Ag and Ni-Ag on Ag seed mesh was obtained in X-band and K-band respectively. The SE increased from 23.2 to 43.7dB with 82.2% transparency, while 47.6dB SE was achieved for Cu-Ag mesh and Ni-Ag mesh respectively for electronic devices [11]. A Cu mesh with PET sheet as substrate was fabricated with visible transmittance of 85% in [12]. The shielding efficiency was tested in the range 12-18GHz and was 41dB. Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) layer was doped on PET substrate with 83.5% transparency for flexible electronics in [13]. The Cu/Ni/PEDOT: PSS Transparent Conducting Film (TCF) was fabricated with a transmittance of 86% for Joule heating purposes in [14].

A transparent shielded mesh film is employed as a shield in the current study, considering the disadvantages of several shielding materials. The primary properties of transparent materials are light weight, non-corrosiveness, flexibility, and durability for applications in electronics. An alternative to Transparent Conducting Oxides (TCO) is Transparent Conductive Coatings exhibiting the non-variant nature of electrical properties under flexing. Optical transparency is a crucial feature of transparent materials, which is inversely proportional to SE. SE of more than 60dB can be achieved with transparent shielded mesh film [15].

The novelty of the proposed work is the theoretical mitigation of the SAR absorbed in two head models of different ages from mobile smartphones operating at various bands from (850 to 5470MHz). Moreover, the SAR is minimized with the aid of SE of the laminated shielded mesh film by Transmission Line Method at the worst-case normal incidence of EM RF wave. The shielding material is transparent PET film with conductive Cu and Ni coatings forming a laminated mesh film.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Transparent Conductive Metal Mesh PET Film

The transparent material used for the mathematical analysis is PET film with copper and nickel mesh conductive coatings. The structure constitutes a laminated shielded mesh. It is essential to derive shield and conductive mesh impedance and propagation constant in terms of conductivity, permeability, and permittivity [16]. Equations (1) and (2) give the PET film's shield impedance.

$$\eta = (1 + j) \sqrt{\frac{\pi f \mu}{\sigma}} \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma = \sqrt{j\omega\mu(\sigma + j\omega\epsilon)} \quad (2)$$

$$R_m = \frac{1}{\sigma\delta \left(1 - e^{-\frac{l_m}{\delta}}\right)} \left(\frac{g}{2a}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$X_m = z_0 \left(-\frac{g}{\lambda}\right) \left[\ln \left(\sin \left(\frac{a\pi}{g} \right) \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

$$Z_m = \frac{1}{\eta_0} (R_m + jX_m) \quad (5)$$

where R_m and X_m are the resistance and reactance respectively of the Cu and Ni conductive coating. δ is the skin depth, g and $2a$ are mesh spacing and line-width, and l_m is the mesh thickness which is 100 and 50nm for Cu and Ni coating respectively [17]. The impedance Z_m of conductive mesh coatings is, thus, given by (5).

B. Head Models with Tissues

The head height of the adult and child head models is 25 and 23.5cm with diameters of 16.01 and 14.06cm respectively [18-20]. Multi-layered head models are considered in the current research. Head models with 4 and 7 layers of tissues are taken for analysis. Skin, fat, bone, and brain are the layers considered in the 4-layered model, whereas skin, fat, bone, dura, CSF, gray matter, and white matter are the tissue layers considered in the 7-layered model [21]. Their representation is shown in Figures 1 and 2. The analysis using the Transmission Line Method considers the spherical models to be planar (4 and 7 layers) as in Figures 3 and 4. The tissue thickness of the head is given in Tables I and II.

Fig. 1. Four-layered adult or child head model (Table I).

TABLE I. TISSUE THICKNESS OF 4 LAYERS IN ADULT AND CHILD HEAD MODELS [19-20]

Model	Tissue layer	Thickness (mm)
Adult	Skin	1
	Fat	2
	Bone	7
	Brain	70.05
Child	Skin	1
	Fat	0.5
	Bone	6.5
	Brain	62.3

C. SE Derivation

The reflection and transmission coefficients are derived from tissue medium's thickness, impedances, and propagation constants [22]. The conductivity and relative permittivity of each tissue medium is obtained from [23].

Fig. 2. Seven-layered adult or child head model (Table II).

TABLE II. TISSUE THICKNESS OF 7 LAYERS IN ADULT AND CHILD HEAD MODELS [21]

Model	Tissue layer	Thickness (mm)
Adult	Skin	1
	Fat	2
	Bone	7
	Dura	1.5
	CSF	2
	Gray Matter	3.7
	White Matter	62.85
Child	Skin	1
	Fat	0.5
	Bone	6.5
	Dura	0.5
	CSF	1.5
	Gray Matter	3.6
	White Matter	56.7

Also, the total transmission coefficient for the radiated EM wave is derived for the head model alone and then with the copper and nickel grid PET film (PET film with Cu mesh, and PET film with Cu, Ni mesh) from (6), (7), and (8).

$$T = p \prod_{k=Skin}^{Gray\ Matter} [(1 - q_{<k>} e^{-2\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}})] e^{-\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}} \quad (6)$$

$$T = p \prod_{k=PET+Cu}^{Gray\ Matter} [(1 - q_{<k>} e^{-2\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}})] e^{-\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}} \quad (7)$$

$$T = p \prod_{k=PET+Cu+Ni}^{Gray\ Matter} [(1 - q_{<k>} e^{-2\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}})] e^{-\gamma_{<k>} l_{<k>}} \quad (8)$$

where p represents the transmission coefficient, which is the product of the intrinsic impedances across the media and q represents the reflection coefficient, calculating the impedances across two consecutive interfaces.

D. SAR Computation from the SE of Head Models

Equation (6) represents the total transmission coefficient T of the radiated electromagnetic wave, considering the power entered into the skin through the layers of fat, bone, dura, CSF, and gray matter and propagated into the white matter. Equation (7) represents T of the radiated electromagnetic wave, considering the power entering into the Cu grid PET film through the intermediate tissue layers and gray matter respectively. The total radiated power into the white matter goes through the layers of Cu and Ni grid PET laminated shielded mesh film, skin, fat, bone, dura, CSF, and gray matter. The SE (dB) is evaluated from T as in (9) [24]. The E_i is computed from the incident wave power density delegated by the ICNIRP standard for mobile phone frequencies [25]. E_r is obtained from the SE of the head without and with the laminated shielded mesh from (10).

$$SE = -20 \log_{10}|T| \quad (9)$$

$$SE = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{E_i}{E_r} \right) \quad (10)$$

The SAR is computed from the SE of the human head models (adult and child). By the ICNIRP guidelines, the power densities of the incident wave at frequencies of 5.47, 4.5, 3.6, and 2.3GHz, are $40W/m^2$, $36.556W/m^2$ at 1.8GHz and $19.175W/m^2$ at 0.85 GHz [25]. The SAR absorbed (W/kg) by i (brain/white matter) in a (4/7-layered head model) of an adult and child is given by:

$$SAR = \frac{\sigma_i E_t^2}{\rho_i} \quad (11)$$

The allowable SAR limit proposed by ICNIRP is 2W/kg for absorption by local body parts such as head/limbs.

Fig. 3. Four-layered planar head model with the adult/child tissue thickness.

Fig. 4. Seven-layered planar head model with the adult head tissue thickness [23]. Reproduced, courtesy of The Electromagnetics Academy.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SE plots of 4- and 7-layered head models of adult and child for frequencies ranging from 850 to 5470MHz without shield, with transparent conductive metal (Cu and Ni), and with mesh PET film for normal incidence of EM wave is shown in Figures 5 and 6 and Figures 7 and 8 respectively.

The wave's frequency in any medium is directly proportional to the medium's SE. The SE against the frequency of the head model in the child is less than that of the adult head model in Figures 5-8. The SE of a child's 7-layered head model from Figure 8 is only around 20dB without the laminated shield and around 100dB with the copper grip PET film with Ni coating. Coincidence in graphs of the SE with frequency variation is noticed in the Figures because the thickness difference between Cu and Ni metal mesh coatings is only 50nm. The SAR emission absorbed by the brain in the 4-layered adult and child head models is tabulated in Tables III

and IV. At 5.47GHz frequency, the Cu grid PET Film with Ni coating has absorbed a SAR of 5.91e-7W/kg in the adult 4-layered model and the child head model absorbed a comparatively higher SAR of 0.00002W/kg. Regarding the 7-layered model, the SAR absorbed by the white matter in the adult head model is 5.27e-09W/kg, which is less compared to that of the child's head model, which is 3.16e-06W/kg at 5.47GHz.

Fig. 5. SE with frequency variation of an adult 4-layered head model for no shield condition, with transparent Cu PET mesh film, and transparent Cu and Ni PET mesh film for normal incidence of EM wave.

Fig. 6. SE with frequency variation of a child 4-layered head model for no shield condition, with transparent Cu PET mesh film, and transparent Cu and Ni PET mesh film for normal incidence of EM wave.

Fig. 7. SE with frequency variation of an adult 7-layered head model for no shield condition, with transparent Cu PET mesh film, and transparent Cu and Ni PET mesh film for normal incidence of EM wave.

Fig. 8. SE with frequency variation of a child 7-layered head model for no shield condition, with transparent Cu PET mesh film, and transparent Cu and Ni PET mesh film for normal incidence of EM wave.

TABLE III. BRAIN SAR OF THE ADULT 4-LAYERED MODEL

Frequency GHz	SAR (W/kg)		
	Without shield	With Cu Grid PET film	With Cu Grid PET Film with Ni coating
0.85	31.8	9.47E-05	5.74E-05
1.8	49.11	6.08E-05	3.71E-05
2.3	42.14	4.19E-05	2.56E-05
3.6	14.77	1.03E-05	6.34E-06
4.5	5.82	3.37E-06	2.07E-06
5.47	2.05	9.58E-07	5.91E-07

TABLE IV. BRAIN SAR OF THE CHILD 4-LAYERED MODEL

Frequency GHz	SAR (W/kg)		
	Without shield	With Cu Grid PET film	With Cu Grid PET Film with Ni coating
0.85	43.34	1.6e-4	7e-5
1.8	90.55	1e-4	6.16e-5
2.3	103.12	9.29e-5	5.68e-5
3.6	100.52	6.62e-5	4.07e-5
4.5	87.57	5e-5	3.07e-5
5.47	66.83	3.25e-5	2e-5

TABLE V. WHITE MATTER SAR OF THE ADULT 7-LAYERED MODEL

Frequency GHz	SAR (W/kg)		
	Without shield	With Cu Grid PET film	With Cu Grid PET Film with Ni coating
0.85	9.84	5.84E-05	1.77E-05
1.8	9.32	2.29E-05	7.04E-06
2.3	6.1	1.20E-05	3.70E-06
3.6	0.33	4.49E-07	1.40E-07
4.5	0.15	1.63E-07	5.14E-08
5.47	0.02	1.67E-08	5.27E-09

TABLE VI. WHITE MATTER SAR OF THE CHILD 7-LAYERED MODEL

Frequency GHz	SAR (W/kg)		
	Without shield	With Cu Grid PET film	With Cu Grid PET Film with Ni coating
0.85	24.51	1.3e-4	3.97E-05
1.8	43.77	9.67E-05	2.97E-05
2.3	44.73	7.96E-05	2.46E-05
3.6	20.86	2.70E-05	8.43E-06
4.5	20.08	2.24E-05	7.03E-06
5.47	10.55	1.00E-05	3.16E-06

IV. CONCLUSION

A theoretical investigation for the determination of the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) of age-dependent multi-layered head models exposed to RF emissions from mobile phone operating frequencies of 850MHz-5.47 GHz for normal incidence of EM wave is assessed in this paper. Absorption is found with the relevance of shielding effectiveness of the human head in the absence of any shield and in the presence of Cu grid PET film (transparent conductive metal mesh PET film/transparent Cu PET laminated mesh) and Cu grid PET film with Ni coating. The result analysis at 5.47GHz showed that the child head model had absorbed a higher radiation level of 66.83W/kg in the 4-layered model and 10.55W/kg in the 7-layered model. The same model with the transparent PET and Cu laminated shielded mesh had absorbed a SAR of 0.0000325W/kg (4-layered model) and 0.00001W/kg (7-layered model). With the PET/Cu/Ni laminated mesh, 0.00002W/kg was absorbed by brain tissue by the 4-layered model, and white matter absorbed 0.00000316W/kg in the 7-layered head model of a child. Thus, a higher amount of SAR is reduced in adult head models compared to child head models using the transparent Cu grid PET film with Ni coating. Without a shield, the child model had absorbed maximum radiation of around 67W/kg and the PET laminated mesh film absorbed a comparatively negligible amount of SAR in every case.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. T. T. My, H. N. B. Phuong, T. T. Huong, and B. T. M. Tu, "Design of a Four-Element Array Antenna for 5G Cellular Wireless Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6259–6263, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3771>.
- [2] S. Ghnimi, A. Nasri, and A. Gharsallah, "Study of a New Design of the Planar Inverted-F Antenna for Mobile Phone Handset Applications," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5270–5275, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3287>.
- [3] B. P. Nadh, B. T. P. Madhav, and M. S. Kumar, "Design and analysis of dual band implantable DGS antenna for medical applications," *Sādhanā*, vol. 44, no. 6, May 2019, Art. no. 131, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12046-019-1099-8>.
- [4] H. Aniolczyk, "EM Noise and Its Impact on Human Health and Safety," in *Advanced Materials for Electromagnetic Shielding*, M. Jaroszewski, S. Thomas, and A. V. Rane, Eds. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2018, pp. 11–33, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119128625.ch2>.
- [5] R. Kitchen, *RF and Microwave Radiation Safety*, 2nd ed. Boston, USA: Newnes, 2001.
- [6] J. S. Seybold, *Introduction to RF Propagation*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley-Interscience, 2005.
- [7] "IEEE Standard for Safety Levels with Respect to Human Exposure to Radio Frequency Electromagnetic Fields, 3 kHz to 300 GHz," *1999 Edition IEEE Std C95*, Apr. 1999, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.1999.89423>.
- [8] T. B. Rashid and H. H. Song, "Analysis of biological effects of cell phone radiation on human body using specific absorption rate and thermoregulatory response," *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*, vol. 61, no. 6, pp. 1482–1490, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mop.31777>.
- [9] A. M. Tamim, M. R. I. Faruque, M. U. Khandaker, M. T. Islam, and D. A. Bradley, "Electromagnetic radiation reduction using novel metamaterial for cellular applications," *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, vol. 178, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 108976, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2020.108976>.
- [10] Y.-H. Liu, J.-L. Xu, S. Shen, X.-L. Cai, L.-S. Chen, and S.-D. Wang, "High-performance, ultra-flexible and transparent embedded metallic mesh electrodes by selective electrodeposition for all-solid-state supercapacitor applications," *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, vol. 5, no. 19, pp. 9032–9041, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7TA01947E>.
- [11] A. S. Voronin *et al.*, "Cu–Ag and Ni–Ag meshes based on cracked template as efficient transparent electromagnetic shielding coating with excellent mechanical performance," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 56, no. 26, pp. 14741–14762, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-021-06206-4>.
- [12] S. Walia, A. K. Singh, V. S. G. Rao, S. Bose, and G. U. Kulkarni, "Metal mesh-based transparent electrodes as high-performance EMI shields," *Bulletin of Materials Science*, vol. 43, no. 1, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 187, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12034-020-02159-7>.
- [13] W. Zhou *et al.*, "Copper Mesh Templated by Breath-Figure Polymer Films as Flexible Transparent Electrodes for Organic Photovoltaic Devices," *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, vol. 8, no. 17, pp. 11122–11127, May 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.6b01117>.
- [14] L. Zhao, S. Yu, J. Li, M. Wu, L. Li, and X. Wang, "Highly reliable flexible transparent conductors prepared with Cu/Ni grid by vacuum-free solution process," *Optical Materials*, vol. 120, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 111427, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2021.111427>.
- [15] B. Ray, S. Parmar, and S. Datar, "Flexible and Transparent EMI Shielding Materials," in *Advanced Materials for Electromagnetic Shielding*, M. Jaroszewski, S. Thomas, and A. V. Rane, Eds. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2018, pp. 167–175, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119128625.ch8>.
- [16] R. B. Schulz, V. C. Plantz, and D. R. Brush, "Shielding theory and practice," *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 187–201, Dec. 1988, <https://doi.org/10.1109/15.3297>.
- [17] Y. L. and J. Tan, "Frequency Dependent Model of Sheet Resistance and Effect Analysis on Shielding Effectiveness of Transparent Conductive Mesh Coatings," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research*, vol. 140, pp. 353–368, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.2528/PIER13050312>.
- [18] B. Rajagopal and L. Rajasekaran, "SAR assessment on three layered spherical human head model irradiated by mobile phone antenna," *Human-centric Computing and Information Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 1, Aug. 2014, Art. no. 10, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13673-014-0010-1>.
- [19] A. Drossos, V. Santomaa, and N. Kuster, "The dependence of electromagnetic energy absorption upon human head tissue composition in the frequency range of 300-3000 MHz," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 48, no. 11, pp. 1988–1995, Aug. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1109/22.884187>.
- [20] S. Hout and J.-Y. Chung, "Design and Characterization of a Miniaturized Implantable Antenna in a Seven-Layer Brain Phantom," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 162062–162069, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2951489>.
- [21] S. S. Pudipeddi, P. V. Y. Jayasree, and S. G. Chintala, "Polarization Effect Assessment of Sub-6 GHz Frequencies on Adult and Child Four-Layered Head Models," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8954–8959, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5096>.
- [22] "Calculation of the Dielectric Properties of Body Tissues in the frequency range 10 Hz - 100 GHz," *IFAC*. <http://niremf.ifac.cnr.it/tissprop/htmlclie/htmlclie.php>.
- [23] S. S. Pudipeddi and P. V. Y. Jayasree, "Numerical Computation of SAR in Human Head with Transparent Shields Using Transmission Line Method," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research M*, vol. 105, pp. 31–44, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.2528/PIERM21080405>.
- [24] International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP), "Guidelines for Limiting Exposure to Electromagnetic Fields (100 kHz to 300 GHz)," *Health Physics*, vol. 118, no. 5, pp. 483–524, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1097/HP.0000000000001210>.

Development of a Prediction System for 3D Printed Part Deformation

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Abstract-The Additive Manufacturing (AM) process is applied in industrial applications. However, quality issues of the printed parts, including part distortion and cracks caused by high temperature and fast cooling, result in high residual stress. The theoretical calculation equation shows elastic behavior which is the linear behavior between strain and stress. However, in practice with the additive manufacturing process, strain and stress have nonlinear behavior. So, the prediction of the deformation of a printed part is inaccurate. The contribution of this research is the creation of an Inherent Strain (IS)-based part deformation prediction method during the Selective Laser Melting (SLM) process. To have the deformation in the design stage, we developed software for calculating the IS value and predicting the deformation. The difference between the calculated results and the experimental results is still there, so, we proposed an algorithm and developed an optimization module for the system to minimize this difference. In the final optimal printing process, the parameters are derived in order for the real printing process to have the required quality of the SLM printed part.

Keywords-selective laser melting; predicting deformation; inherent strain; heat treatment effect zone

I. INTRODUCTION

Layer by layer manufacturing or additive manufacturing has been used in many application fields such as aerospace, automotive, biomedical, and energy production and distribution. The printed parts are made from plastic or metal powder materials [1-4]. However, the quality issues of the printed parts, including part distortion, as well as the cracks caused by high temperature and fast cooling, result in high residual stress. This is a challenge that limits the industry acceptance of AM. To overcome this challenge, a numerical modeling method for predicting the part distortion at the design stage plays an important role, which enables design engineers

to remove failures before carrying out printing as well as to determine the optimal printing process parameters to minimize part deformation. Currently, with the rapid growth of this technology, many AM processes have been applied in industrial applications. Selective Laser Melting (SLM) is one of these AM processes. SLM is an AM process that directly produces parts from metal powder. SLM is a complex thermal-physical-chemical process of the interaction between a laser source and metallic powders [1, 5]. The SLM mechanism is shown in Figure 1. The SLM system includes the laser source, the optical system, and the deposition system. The optical system has the optical mirrors which enable the laser source to be directed onto the powder bed surface. The thin powder layer is distributed by the deposition system and melted by the laser source through the optical system. The deposition system that is the scraper or roller system enables the distribution of the powder onto the printed area. The printed layer thickness is determined by the distance of moving down of the build platform. Then, another powder layer is added on the top of the printed previous layer. This step is repeated until the entire 3D model is completed.

For printing the metal parts, there are currently many different AM processes using different combinations of stock material form, material delivery, and heat source. SLM is the most attractive method for layer by layer building of metal parts due to advantages such as the lack of post-processing. However, as the same with other AM processes, the distortion and cracks of the printed parts still occur due to the residual stress caused by the rapid heating and cooling process [6]. In the SLM process, high temperature is required for the melting of the metallic powders. Due to high temperature and fast cooling, residual stress will be generated in the printed part. The large residual stress results in part distortion which is a negative effect of the product performance. Part distortion caused by the tensile residual stress not only reduces the part

geometrical accuracy, but also affects the functional performance of the printed parts. To acquire good printed part quality, key factors such as powder properties, printing process parameters, and SLM machine characteristics must be considered.

Fig. 1. Mechanism of the selective laser melting process.

Currently, the method for keeping the quality of the printed part is trial-and-error testing. This method depends on the user's experience and requires larger manufacturing costs, while producing waste and scrap [7]. Therefore, it is necessary for predicting the part's quality at the design stage which enables to remove failures before carrying out the real printing. Many researchers have used the inherent strain method for predicting part deformation in welding processes. However, some proposals for modifying the conventional IS method have been applied to apply this method to AM processes such as the SLM process, [8, 9]. Authors in [9] proposed the extraction of the IS value from micro-scale thermo-mechanical analysis. This IS value was applied to the part-scale model to have the part deformation. However, it is challenging to predict the residual deformation in the part-scale model [10]. To overcome this challenge, a multi-scale modeling approach is proposed in [11, 12]. Currently, some commercial tools based on the IS method enable the prediction of deformation. However, the algorithms to calculate the IS value and how to apply this value to the part-scale model are not publicly available [13].

This paper presents a new method for predicting the deformation of the 3D printed part using the ISs. For carrying out this research, a method for calculating the IS value is proposed. These IS values are used for calculating the deformation. Both simulation and experiments were implemented for comparing the IS values and deformations.

II. MODEL FOR DETERMINING THE IS VALUE

A. Theoretical Model

The term of IS was firstly introduced in 1975 for analyzing the welding process. It is a general name for the expression of non-elastic strains which include the thermal strain $\epsilon_{thermal}$, phase transfer strain ϵ_{phase} , plastic strain $\epsilon_{plastic}$, and creep strain ϵ_{creep} [7]. During the SLM process with the heating and

cooling cycles, the total strain is the sum of the elastic strain $\epsilon_{elastic}$ and IS ϵ^* , as shown below:

$$\epsilon_{total} = \epsilon_{elastic} + \epsilon^* \quad (1)$$

The inherent strain is calculated as:

$$\epsilon^* = \epsilon_{thermal} + \epsilon_{plastic} + \epsilon_{phase} + \epsilon_{creep} \quad (2)$$

Strain and stress are unknown variables. We can determine the value of one of these variables by experiments. The remaining variable is determined by the equation showing the relationship between strain and stress. The commercial tools enable engineers to estimate the IS value. However, the algorithms for calculating the IS value are not published. During the printing process, the material begins at the melting temperature via the heating stage and is changed to a lower temperature via the cooling stage at a high rate. The material of the printed part will receive a compressive force due to the thermal change. Thus, the three-dimensional ISs are compressive strains, and the equations can be defined as [14]:

$$\epsilon_x^* = -\frac{W_x}{F_x}; \epsilon_y^* = -\frac{W_y}{F_y}; \epsilon_z^* = -\frac{W_z}{F_z} \quad (3)$$

in which F_x , F_y , and F_z are the zone areas where W_x , W_y , and W_z respectively are distributed. The total volume W_x of ϵ_x^* , the total volume W_y of ϵ_y^* , and the total volume W_z of ϵ_z^* in unit length are calculated as follows:

$$W_x = \zeta \cdot q_v; W_y = W_z = K \cdot q_v \quad (4)$$

in which q_v is the linear energy density (J/mm) [15]:

$$q_v = \frac{Q_{heat\ source}}{u} \quad (5)$$

ζ and K (mm/J) are longitudinal and transverse inherent strain coefficients, respectively. Figure 2 shows the components of the inherent strain ϵ_x , ϵ_y , and ϵ_z with these parameters.

Fig. 2. Inherent strain components.

The inherent strains in the x , y , and z directions for the first layer are calculated as follows:

$$\epsilon_{inh-x} = -\frac{\xi \cdot q_v}{F_x}; \epsilon_{inh-y} = -\frac{K \cdot q_v}{F_y}; \epsilon_{inh-z} = -\frac{K \cdot q_v}{F_z} \quad (6)$$

Figure 3 shows the calculation of the IS for n layers. After printing the first layer, the IS value is ϵ_{inh} . If we add the second layer via the SLM process mechanism, the first layer is re-melted with the new heat treatment effect zone, so the remaining IS value for the first layer is:

$$\varepsilon'_1 = \varepsilon_{inh} - \frac{d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh} \quad (7)$$

When the second layer is added, its IS value is:

$$\varepsilon_2 = \varepsilon'_1 + \varepsilon_{inh} = 2\varepsilon_{inh} - \frac{d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh} \quad (8)$$

If a third layer is added, the remaining IS value in the second layer is:

$$\varepsilon'_2 = \varepsilon_2 - \frac{d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh} = 2\varepsilon_{inh} - \frac{2d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh} \quad (9)$$

and the IS value in the third layer is calculated as:

$$\varepsilon_3 = \varepsilon'_2 + \varepsilon_{inh} = 3\varepsilon_{inh} - \frac{2d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh} \quad (10)$$

Repeating this SLM process for n layers, we can calculate the IS value for the n^{th} layer as follows:

$$\varepsilon_n = \varepsilon'_{n-1} + \varepsilon_{inh} = n\varepsilon_{inh} - \frac{(n-1)d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh} \quad (11)$$

For whole part, in x , y , and z directions, we have the IS value as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_x (n \text{ layer}) = n\varepsilon_{inh-x} - \frac{(n-1)d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh-x} \\ \varepsilon_y (n \text{ layer}) = n\varepsilon_{inh-y} - \frac{(n-1)d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh-y} \\ \varepsilon_z (n \text{ layer}) = n\varepsilon_{inh-z} - \frac{(n-1)d}{h} \varepsilon_{inh-z} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 3. Method for calculating inherent strain for whole part.

B. Simulation and Experiments

1) Simulation Results

The mathematical model of the heat transfer, which we used to determine the temperature distribution during the SLM process, is [16]:

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho C u \nabla T = \nabla(k \nabla T) + Q_G \quad (13)$$

where T is the temperature, ρ , C , and k are density, thermal capacity, and thermal conductivity factor respectively, u is the printing speed. Q_G is the power distribution given by the moving Goldak's double-ellipsoid heat source model as shown in Figure 4 [17], this heat source model from the welding process, however, it is also suitable for research on the SLM process. Q_G is the total of the absorbed laser in front and rear

of the Goldak heat source model [18]. We used this heat transfer model and printing process parameters (as shown in Table I) for simulation using ComsolTM. We also run tests with the same material (316L steel), however, with differences in the printing process parameters (300W laser power, 1300mm/s laser velocity, and 0.045mm layer thickness). In this case, the inherent strain in Z direction is -0.153 [19].

Fig. 4. Goldak heat source in the finite element model of the AM process.

The temperature distribution during the SLM process is shown in Figure 5. The Heat Treatment Effect Zone (HTEZ) surfaces are shown in Figures 6-8. The HTEZ surface in the ZX plane as shown in Figure 6 is calculated as follows:

$$F_x = (x + e) \cdot d - e \cdot c \quad (14)$$

with $d = 0.112\text{mm}$, $c = 0.0522\text{mm}$, $e = 0.5255\text{mm}$, and $x = 2.429\text{mm}$, we have $F_x = 0.3035\text{mm}^2$.

The HTEZ surface in the XY plane as shown in Figure 7 is calculated as follows:

$$F_y = 2(x + e) \cdot (a + b) - 2a \cdot e - f \cdot n \quad (15)$$

with $a = 0.089\text{mm}$, $b = 0.137\text{mm}$, $e = 0.5255\text{mm}$, $f = 0.258$, $n = 3.166$, and $x = 2.429\text{mm}$, we have $F_y = 0.425\text{mm}^2$.

The HTEZ surface in the ZY plane as shown in Figure 8 is calculated as:

$$F_z = 2[(a + b) \cdot d - a \cdot c] \quad (16)$$

with $a = 0.089\text{mm}$, $b = 0.137\text{mm}$, $d = 0.112\text{mm}$, and $c = 0.0522\text{mm}$, we have $F_z = 0.0413\text{mm}^2$.

Fig. 5. Goldak heat source in the finite element model of the AM process.

TABLE I. PRINTING PROCESS PARAMETERS [18]

Name	Description	Value
x_0	Path center X-Coordinate	0mm
y_0	Path center Y-Coordinate	0mm
$Q_{heat\ source}$	Laser power	250W
p	Length of the y-semi-axis of ellipsoid (mm)	0.173mm
c	Length of the z-semi-axis of ellipsoid (mm)	0.230mm
a_f	Length of the x-semi-axis of front ellipsoids (mm)	0.173mm
a_r	Length of the x-semi-axis of rear ellipsoids (mm)	0.347mm
u	Laser velocity	1100mm/s
C	Thermal capacity	$500 \times 10^{-3} \text{J}/(\text{g.K})$
λ	Thermal conductivity factor	$19.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{W}/(\text{mm.K})$
T_a	Ambient temperature	293K
h	Layer thickness	0.05mm
ha	Hatch distance	0.07mm

Fig. 6. HTEZ surface in in the ZX plane.

Fig. 7. HTEZ surface in in the XY plane.

Fig. 8. HTEZ surface in in the ZY plane.

The inherent strains in the x , y , and z directions for the first layer are calculated by applying (6) with $\zeta = 1.57 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^3/\text{J}$, $K = 0.58 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^3/\text{J}$ [14], and $q_v = 0.2273 \text{J}/\text{mm}$ for 316L stainless steel, $F_x = 0.3035 \text{mm}^2$, $F_y = 0.425 \text{mm}^2$, and $F_z = 0.0413 \text{mm}^2$, we have: $\epsilon_{inh-x} = -0.00118$, $\epsilon_{inh-y} = -0.00031$ and $\epsilon_{inh-z} = -0.003$. In comparison with the reported IS value for the first layer in the welding process, which also considers the influence of the temperature distribution to the IS value, the calculated IS value is acceptable. In the z direction, where the highest temperature is 1500°C (or 1773°K) the inherent strain value is 0.0017 [20]. Thus, the IS value for the whole part after 60 printed layers

(with layer thickness of 0.05mm and printed part height of 3mm) is calculated as follows: Assuming that the depth (d) that affects the inherent strain distribution equals to $(1/3)$ of the layer thickness (h), we have the following IS values using (12): $\epsilon_x(\text{whole part}) = -0.04742$, $\epsilon_y(\text{whole part}) = -0.0125$, $\epsilon_z(\text{whole part}) = -0.1286$.

2) Experimental Results

Experiments on printing a cantilever beam were carried out on an SLM machine at the Laboratory of Production Engineering, Ulsan University, Republic of Korea (Figure 9). The geometrical model of the cantilever beam and the printing direction (0° , 45° , and 90°) are shown in Figure 10. Specimens were printed on the MetalSys 250.

Fig. 9. Experiments on the SLM machine.

The highest deformation of the cantilever beam at the position in the z direction with 0° printing direction after cutting the part from the base plate by the Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM) machine is 1.45mm as shown in Figure 9 and Table II. The IS is calculated as follows:

$$\epsilon = -\frac{l_t - l_0}{l_0} = -\frac{13.95 - 12.5}{12.5} = -0.116 \quad (17)$$

where l_0 is the part length before cutting by EDM and l_t is the part length after cutting by EDM. Considering the z direction, with the part height before and after cutting being 12.5mm and 13.95mm, we have $\epsilon_z = -0.116$, and the deformation in the z direction is 1.45mm. The IS value in the z direction predicted by simulation is -0.1286 . The difference between simulation and experiment is considered acceptable.

TABLE II. GEOMETRY MEASUREMENT AFTER CUTTING

Geometry measurement	Distortion (mm)					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
Scan pattern (0°)	13.93	13.94	13.96	14.02	13.90	13.95
Scan pattern (90°)	13.24	13.19	13.21	13.19	13.12	13.19
Scan pattern (45°)	13.50	13.48	13.50	13.51	13.43	13.484

With the proposed method, the IS value in the z direction is $\epsilon_z = -0.1286$. From this IS value, with a total part height of $H = 12.5 \text{mm}$, the deformation (δ) of the printed part in the Z direction is 1.608mm, which is calculated by:

$$\delta = |\epsilon_z(\text{whole part})| \cdot H \quad (18)$$

Fig. 10. Specimens printed by SLM.

III. ARCHITECTURE OF FUNCTIONALITY MODULES

A. Module for Calculating the HTEZ Surfaces

To develop the proposed system, we drive out the architecture of functionality modules. Figure 11 shows the architecture of the module for calculating HTEZ surfaces. With the input parameters such as 3D model of part, layer thickness (h), hatch distance (ha), scanning speed (u), and laser power (Q), the databases of the system are updated which are printing parameter database and part dimension database. In the printing parameter database u , Q and the heat source (Goldak model) with parameters such as c , b , a_f , a_r , are used for calculating the absorbed laser. Other databases are also built which are the material properties (thermal capacity, thermal expansion, and thermal conductivity factor), and the coefficient for printing (lattice parameter, laser interaction time). The thermal capacity (C) in material properties database and the absorbed laser are used for calculating the temperature distribution through the heat transfer equation. From the temperature distribution and the material properties and coefficient for printing databases, we have the HTEZ parameters (x , e , c , d , a , b , f , n). Then, we calculate the HTEZ surfaces (F_x , F_y , F_z).

Fig. 11. Architecture of the module for calculating HTEZ surfaces.

B. Module for Calculating the IS for One Layer

Figure 12 shows the architecture of the module for calculating the IS value for one layer. With the input parameters including the printing process parameters, and the HTEZ surfaces, the system allows to calculate the melting energy, the laser power, and the linear energy density. Then, the linear energy density (q_v) and the layer thickness are used for calculating the longitudinal, transverse IS coefficients (ζ , K). From the q_v , ζ , and K , we calculate the IS value for one layer using (6).

Fig. 12. Architecture of the module for calculating IS for one layer.

C. Module for Calculating the IS for the Whole Part

Figure 13 shows the architecture of the module for calculating the IS value for whole part. With the input parameters including the IS value for one layer, part dimension, and printing parameters, the layer number and the HTEZ depth are calculated. Then, these data are used for calculating the IS value for the whole part using (12).

Fig. 13. Architecture of the module for calculating the IS for the whole part.

D. Module for Optimizing the Difference Between the Simulations and the Experiments

Figure 14 shows the architecture of the module for optimizing the difference between the simulations and the experiments. From the simulation and experimental results, the system enables to calculate the new IS value in case the difference between them in the printed part deformation is more than 0.01.

Fig. 14. Architecture of the module for optimizing the difference between the simulation and experiment.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SYSTEM

Fig. 15. Architecture of the system for calculating inherent strain.

To acquire the deformation in the design stage, we developed software for calculating the IS and for predicting the printed part deformation. The developed system includes 4 modules: a module for calculating the HTEZ surfaces, a module for calculating the IS for one layer, a module for

calculating the IS of whole part, and a module for optimizing the difference between the simulations and the experiments.

For programming the proposed system, we used C++ language in Visual Studio 2019 environment. The system architecture is shown in Figure 15 which describes the information flow among the modules. Figure 16 shows the interface module which shows the integration of modules for one complete system. With the input data including printing process parameters (such as volumetric energy density, layer thickness, hatch distance, scanning speed, and efficiency) and the HTEZ surfaces, the developed system allows to calculate the IS value for one layer as shown in Figure 17. The volumetric energy density value is 40J/mm³ [21]. From the calculated IS values for one layer and part information (such as length, width, and part height), the developed system enables to calculate the IS value of the whole part in x, y, z directions as shown in Figure 18.

Fig. 16. Screenshot of the system interface with four modules.

V. CONCLUSION

The contribution of this research is the creation of an inherent strain-based part deformation prediction method during the Selective Laser Melting (SLM) process. To determine the Inherent Strain (IS) value, a micro-scale model for analyzing the temperature distribution was created. The IS value for one layer is calculated from the temperature gradient. For calculating the IS value for the whole part, the HTEZ is used. Then, the IS value is used to determine the part deformation. The proposed methodology has been developed and evaluated using 316L stainless steel cantilever beams, and both simulated and experimental results were obtained. To acquire the deformation in the design stage, we developed the IS-based deformation prediction software. The functionality of the developed system was tested successfully.

Future research can be conducted with the consideration of other factors affecting the printed part quality in order to minimize part deformation. In addition, other printing processes also should be added to the developed system.

Fig. 17. Screenshot of the module for calculating inherent strain for one layer.

Fig. 18. Screenshot of the module for calculating IS of whole part.

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REFERENCES

- [1] T. Sunar and M. Cetin, "An Experimental Study on Boron Carbide Reinforced Open Cell Aluminum Foams Produced via Infiltration Technique," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3640–3645, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2419>.
- [2] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Statistical Approach of the Flexural Strength of PLA and ABS 3D Printed Parts," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8248–8252, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4739>.
- [3] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Theoretical and Experimental Research on the Influence of FDM Parameters on Tensile Strength and Hardness of Parts Made of Poly(lactic Acid)," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7458–7463, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4311>.
- [4] D. G. Zisopol, A. I. Portoaca, I. Nae, and I. Ramadan, "A Comparative Analysis of the Mechanical Properties of Annealed PLA," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8978–8981, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5123>.
- [5] B. Schoinochoritis, D. Chantzis, and K. Salonitis, "Simulation of metallic powder bed additive manufacturing processes with the finite element method: A critical review," *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture*, vol. 231, no. 1, pp. 96–117, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0954405414567522>.
- [6] E. Kundakcioglu, I. Lazoglu, and S. Rawal, "Transient thermal modeling of laser-based additive manufacturing for 3D freeform structures," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 85, no. 1, pp. 493–501, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-015-7932-2>.
- [7] I. Setien, M. Chiumenti, S. van der Veen, M. San Sebastian, F. Garcandiá, and A. Echeverría, "Empirical methodology to determine inherent strains in additive manufacturing," *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, vol. 78, no. 7, pp. 2282–2295, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.camwa.2018.05.015>.
- [8] M. Bugatti and Q. Semeraro, "Limitations of the inherent strain method in simulating powder bed fusion processes," *Additive Manufacturing*, vol. 23, pp. 329–346, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2018.05.041>.
- [9] X. Liang, Q. Chen, L. Cheng, Q. Yang, and A. To, "A Modified Inherent Strain Method for Fast Prediction of Residual Deformation in Additive Manufacturing of Metal Parts," in *Solid Freeform Fabrication 2017: Proceedings of the 28th Annual International Solid Freeform Fabrication Symposium – An Additive Manufacturing Conference*, Austin TX, USA, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.26153/tsw/16972>.
- [10] X. Liang, Q. Chen, L. Cheng, D. Hayduke, and A. C. To, "Modified inherent strain method for efficient prediction of residual deformation in direct metal laser sintered components," *Computational Mechanics*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 1719–1733, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00466-019-01748-6>.
- [11] S. N. Ahmad *et al.*, "FEM Simulation Procedure for Distortion and Residual Stress Analysis of Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 834, no. 1, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 012083, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/834/1/012083>.
- [12] M. Schänzel, A. Ilin, and V. Ploshikhin, "New approach for fast numerical prediction of residual stress and distortion of AM parts from steels with phase transformations," in *10th International Seminar 'Numerical Analysis of Weldability*, Gratz, Austria, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.3217/978-3-85125-615-4-54>.
- [13] Q. Chen *et al.*, "An inherent strain based multiscale modeling framework for simulating part-scale residual deformation for direct metal laser sintering," *Additive Manufacturing*, vol. 28, pp. 406–418, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2019.05.021>.
- [14] L. Yazhi, "Research on Inherent Strain Distribution in Welded Low-Alloy Components," in *2014 Sixth International Conference on Measuring Technology and Mechatronics Automation*, Jan. 2014, pp. 512–515, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMTMA.2014.125>.
- [15] Č. Donik, J. Kraner, I. Paulin, and M. Godec, "Influence of the Energy Density for Selective Laser Melting on the Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of Stainless Steel," *Metals*, vol. 10, no. 7, Jul. 2020, Art. no. 919, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met10070919>.
- [16] A. A. Saprykin, E. A. Ibragimov, and E. V. Babakova, "Modeling the Temperature Fields of Copper Powder Melting in the Process of Selective Laser Melting," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 142, Dec. 2016, Art. no. 012061, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/142/1/012061>.
- [17] Z. Samad, N. M. Nor, and E. R. I. Fauzi, "Thermo-Mechanical Simulation of Temperature Distribution and Prediction of Heat-Affected Zone Size in MIG Welding Process on Aluminium Alloy EN AW 6082-T6," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 530, no. 1, Mar. 2019, Art. no. 012016, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/530/1/012016>.
- [18] V. Nain, T. Engel, M. Carin, D. Boisselier, and L. Seguy, "Development of an Elongated Ellipsoid Heat Source Model to Reduce Computation Time for Directed Energy Deposition Process," *Frontiers in Materials*, vol. 8, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmats.2021.747389>.
- [19] H.-S. Park, H. S. Shin, and N.-H. Tran, "A new approach for calculating inherent strain and distortion in additive manufacturing of metal parts," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 121, no. 9, pp. 6507–6521, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-022-09766-0>.
- [20] T.-J. Kim, B.-S. Jang, and S.-W. Kang, "Welding deformation analysis based on improved equivalent strain method considering the effect of temperature gradients," *International Journal of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 157–173, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijnaoe-2015-0012>.
- [21] A. Leicht, M. Fischer, U. Klement, L. Nyborg, and E. Hryha, "Increasing the Productivity of Laser Powder Bed Fusion for Stainless Steel 316L through Increased Layer Thickness," *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 575–584, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-020-05334-3>.

The Application of LQG Balanced Truncation Algorithm to the Digital Filter Design Problem

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Abstract-This paper presents a method for using a model reduction algorithm to design low-order digital filters. Designing an IIR digital filter that meets the specifications often leads to a high-order digital filter. To reduce the computation time and increase the response rate of the filter, we need to reduce the order of the high-order digital filter. Applying the LQG balanced truncation algorithm to reduce the demand for high-order digital filters shows that low-order filters can completely replace high-order digital filters. The simulation results show that the use of the LQG balanced truncation algorithm in order to reduce the filter order is correct and efficient.

Keywords-model order reduction algorithm; LQG balanced truncation algorithm; digital filter

I. INTRODUCTION

A filter is a circuit that removes or "filters out" a specified range of frequencies. In other words, it decomposes the spectrum of the signal into frequency components that will pass and frequency components that will be suppressed. Analog filters use analog electronic circuits made up of components such as resistors, capacitors, and optical amplifiers to produce the required filtering effect. A digital filter uses a digital processor to perform numerical calculations on the sampled values of the signal [1-7]. The processor can be a general-purpose computer such as a PC or a dedicated DSP (Digital Signal Processor) chip. We know that during digital signal processing, the bandwidth of the frequency band can be varied as filters will suppress unwanted frequency components and the bandwidth of the processed signal will decrease and we can reduce the sampling frequency to match the signal's spectral width, which will reduce the number of computations in the digital filter.

Compared with analog filters, digital filters have the following advantages: it is easy to change the filter structure without affecting the hardware, they are easy to design, deploy, and test, digital filters are extremely stable with time and temperature, they have high signal processing flexibility, and they can handle both low-pass and high-pass filtering accurately [1-2]. Due to the superior properties of digital filters, the application of digital filters is increasingly being expanded in the fields of telecommunications, speech processing, image

processing, antenna systems, digital audio engineering, and multiplexing systems.

Filter design involves constructing a filter transfer function that satisfies a given frequency response. To design a digital filter, there are two basic ways:

- Method 1: Design an analog filter that satisfies the given requirements and then apply the equivalent transformation to form a digital filter.
- Method 2: Apply computer-aided optimization methods to determine whether a digital filter satisfies the requirements.

Of these two designs, the first is commonly applied due to its ease of implementation. The second method is highly complex, so it is rarely used. To design an analog filter, it is necessary to solve two problems: The first is to determine the main requirements of the filter to be designed. The second is to determine whether the filter is designed to be FIR (Finite-Impulse Response) or IIR (Infinite-Impulse Response.)

- Design of the FIR filter: the output is the impulse response vector $h = [h_0, h_1, h_2, \dots, h_N]$.
- Design an IIR filter: the output is the coefficient vectors of the numerator and denominator of the transfer function $b = [b_0, b_1, \dots, b_N]$ and $a = [1, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N]$.

The FIR filter has the advantage of a stable, linear phase characteristic. Its disadvantage is that when a large frequency response is desired, the large filter length N increases computational cost. The IIR filter has the advantages of low computational cost and efficient implementation in cascade of 2^{nd} -order circuits. The disadvantages of the IIR filter are that there is instability due to the quantization of the coefficients which can push the poles outside the unit circle and that it is not possible to achieve linear phase over the entire Nyquist interval.

FIR response models are preferred over IIR models in practical applications such as signal processing [1, 2], telecommunications [8], and control systems [9-11]. However, the IIR model often arises from signal and system modeling and controller and filter design [1, 2, 11], so it is still used in

practice. Since the FIR model is more popular than the IIR model, efficient methods are often used to approximate the IIR model using the FIR model.

The IIR model approximation problem can be stated as follows: Given an IIR model $\mathbf{G}(z)$, which is a stable rational transfer function, find $\mathbf{T}(z) = t_0 + t_1 z^{-1} + \dots + t_{m-1} z^{-m+1}$ such that the norm $\|\mathbf{F}\|$, which is the transfer function error $\mathbf{F}(z) = \mathbf{G}(z) - \mathbf{T}(z)$, is minimized, choosing which standard to evaluate the error due to the requirements of each problem. Due to the existence of an approximation problem in the design of IIR filters, they are usually of high order. High-order filters will lead to many disadvantages in the process of using filters, so in the filter design process, it is necessary to apply model reduction methods to reduce the order of high-order filters. The problem of model order reduction can be stated as follows: Consider a linear, continuous, time-invariant parameter system with many inputs and many outputs, described in state space by the following system of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u} \\ \mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

in which $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{R}^n$, $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbf{R}^p$, $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{R}^q$, $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times n}$, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times p}$, and $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbf{R}^{q \times n}$. The goal of the order reduction problem for the model described by the system of (1) is to find the model described by the system of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_r &= \mathbf{A}_r \mathbf{x}_r + \mathbf{B}_r \mathbf{u} \\ \mathbf{y}_r &= \mathbf{C}_r \mathbf{x}_r \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_r \in \mathbf{R}^r$, $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbf{R}^p$, $\mathbf{y}_r \in \mathbf{R}^q$, $\mathbf{A}_r \in \mathbf{R}^{r \times r}$, $\mathbf{B}_r \in \mathbf{R}^{r \times p}$, and $\mathbf{C}_r \in \mathbf{R}^{q \times r}$, with $r \leq n$ so that the model described by the system of (2) can replace the model described by the system of (1), and at the same time satisfy some of the following requirements:

- The order reduction error is small and can be evaluated.
- The order reduction algorithm needs to calculate efficiently and stability.
- The order reduction algorithm can be performed automatically based on the formula for calculating the upper bound of the order reduction error.
- Important properties of the root system, such as stability and passivity, should be preserved in a reduced order system.
- It must be suitable for each specific requirement of each order reduction problem.

Over the years, hundreds of studies have been published that dealt with solving the problem of order reduction of high-order models. Most of them focused on solving the problem of order reduction for linear systems. Depending on the properties of the original system that need to be preserved in the order reduction system, there are many different order reduction methods. However, they can be classified based on the following basic techniques:

- Singular Perturbations Analysis (SPA) [12].
- Modal Analysis (MA) [13-16].
- Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) analysis [19].
- Moment Matching (MM or Krylov methods) [17].
- Combined SVD and MM [18].

Among the above order reduction techniques, we pay the most attention to the group of methods based on SVD analysis and information from the single Hankel values of the system. The most important proposal of this group of methods is the balanced truncation method [20]. The balanced truncation method is implemented by applying the equivalence condition to the simultaneous diagonalization of the control and observed Gramian matrix of the system. Through the process of diagonalizing two Gramian matrices, it is possible to convert the original model represented in any basis system into an equivalent system representing the coordinate system in internal equilibrium space. From that equilibrium space, the low-order model can be found by removing the eigenvalues that contribute little to the relationship between the input and the output of the system, as well as the states that are less controlled and observed. The balanced truncation method was further developed in [21], and the relationship with Hankel's norm was determined in [22, 23]. In addition to the balanced truncation method, the SVD-based method has a number of other methods such as the stochastic balancing method [24], [25], the LQG balancing truncation algorithm [26], etc. Each order model reduction algorithm has its advantages and disadvantages and should be used for appropriate cases.

In this paper, we are most interested in the LQG balancing truncation algorithm [26] and use it to reduce the high-order filter.

II. THE LQG BALANCED TRUNCATION ALGORITHM

Given a linear, continuous, time-invariant parameter system with many inputs and outputs, described in state space by (1) and according to the balanced truncation algorithm, to determine the transition matrix \mathbf{T} , we need to determine the control gramian matrix and the observed gramian matrix by solving a system of Lyapunov equations. However, the condition for the system of Lyapunov equations to have a solution is that the original system (1) must be stable. If the original system (1) is unstable, we cannot solve the system of Lyapunov equations. To solve this problem, the LQG balanced truncation algorithm [26] proposes to calculate the controllable Gramian matrix and the observable Gramian matrix of the unstable system through an extended Riccati system of equations. Once the control and observation Gramian has been determined, it becomes possible to determine the transition matrix \mathbf{T} . The detailed content of the LQG balanced truncation algorithm [26] is as follows:

Input: The system (\mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C}) is described in (1) (unstable system).

Step 1: Calculate the control gramian matrix **P** and the observed gramian matrix **Q** according to the extended Riccati system of equations as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{AP} + \mathbf{PA}' - \mathbf{PC}'\mathbf{C}'\mathbf{P} + \mathbf{BB}' &= 0 \\ \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{QA} - \mathbf{QBB}'\mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{C}'\mathbf{C} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: Determine the triangular matrix on **R** by Cholesky analysis of the controlled gramian matrix:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{RR}^T$$

Step 3. Use matrix **R** to calculate SVD analysis of control gramian matrix as follows:

$$\mathbf{RQR}^T = \mathbf{UAV}^T$$

Step 4: Calculate matrix **L** = **V**^{1/2}.

Step 5: Calculate the non-singular matrix **T**⁻¹ = **R**^T**UL**^{-1/2}.

Step 6: Calculate (**A**, **B**, **C**) = (**T**⁻¹**AT**, **T**⁻¹**B**, **CT**).

Step 7: Choose *r* such that *r* < *n*, where *r* is the order of the reduced system. Represent (**A**, **B**, **C**) in block form as follows:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{11} & \mathbf{A}_{12} \\ \mathbf{A}_{21} & \mathbf{A}_{22} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{B}_1 \\ \mathbf{B}_2 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{C} = [\mathbf{C}_1 \quad \mathbf{C}_2]$$

where **A**₁₁ ∈ *R*^{*r*×*r*}, **B**₁ ∈ *R*^{*r*×*p*}, **C**₁ ∈ *R*^{*q*×*r*}.

Output: Reduced system (**A**₁₁, **B**₁, **C**₁).

III. REDUCING THE ORDER OF THE DIGITAL FILTER

Consider a IIR digital filter with a transfer function in the form of **H**(*z*) in (3) and the general structure of a ladder IIR filter [1-2]:

$$\mathbf{H}(z) = \frac{b_0z^N + b_1z^{N-1} + \dots + b_{N-1}z + b_N}{a_0z^N + a_1z^{N-1} + \dots + a_{N-1}z + a_N} \quad (3)$$

In [27], the authors have determined the transfer function model of the 6th-order IIR digital filter as follows:

$$\mathbf{H}(z) = \frac{\mathbf{A}(z)}{\mathbf{B}(z)}$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}(z) &= -0.1242z^5 + 0.1581z^4 + 0.5273z^3 + 0.2154z^2 - 0.0647z + 0.6889 \\ \mathbf{B}(z) &= z^6 - 1.095z^5 + 1.299z^4 - 1.113z^3 + 1.028z^2 - 0.6043z + 0.426 \end{aligned}$$

The 6th-order IIR digital filter has a non-minimum phase form and has a polarity very close to the unit circle in the *z*-plane. Therefore, it is prone to digital errors and is not suitable for performing Digital Signal Processing (DSP). At the same time, the order of the digital filter is high, so when used in practice, there will be many disadvantages. To overcome this implementation difficulty, we need to reduce the order of the IRR digital filter. To do so, we convert the 6th-order digital

filter to the form of linear analog filter through the transformation *z* = *s* + 1. The obtained result is:

$$\mathbf{H}(s) = \frac{\mathbf{C}(s)}{\mathbf{D}(s)}$$

with:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}(s) &= -0.1242s^5 - 0.4629s^4 - 0.0823s^3 + 1.504s^2 + 1.959s + 1.401 \\ \mathbf{D}(s) &= s^6 + 4.905s^5 + 10.82s^4 + 13.13s^3 + 9.533s^2 + 3.834s + 0.9407 \end{aligned}$$

Performing order reduction of the 6th-order digital filter according to the steps of the LQG balanced truncation algorithm [26], the results are:

Step 1: The control Gramian matrix **P** and the observed Gramian matrix **Q** have the following form:

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1607 & 0.0009 & -0.2016 & -0.0036 & 0.0943 & -0.0013 \\ 0.0009 & 0.4125 & 0.0118 & -0.4250 & -0.0607 & 0.0813 \\ -0.2016 & 0.0118 & 0.8439 & 0.0004 & -0.8583 & -0.0320 \\ -0.0036 & -0.4250 & 0.0004 & 0.8738 & 0.1547 & -0.3196 \\ 0.0943 & -0.0607 & -0.8583 & 0.1547 & 1.8095 & 0.1140 \\ -0.0013 & 0.0813 & -0.0320 & -0.3196 & 0.1140 & 0.3995 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.3205 & 0.4039 & 0.4465 & 0.5228 & 0.3373 & 0.3733 \\ 0.4039 & 0.5175 & 0.5839 & 0.6999 & 0.4634 & 0.5471 \\ 0.4465 & 0.5839 & 0.6753 & 0.8327 & 0.5671 & 0.7160 \\ 0.5228 & 0.6999 & 0.8327 & 1.0586 & 0.7419 & 0.9968 \\ 0.3373 & 0.4634 & 0.5671 & 0.7419 & 0.5336 & 0.7543 \\ 0.3733 & 0.5471 & 0.7160 & 0.9968 & 0.7543 & 1.1679 \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 2-4: The matrices **R**, **U**, and **L** have the following form:

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4008 & 0.0023 & -0.5030 & -0.0089 & 0.2353 & -0.0033 \\ 0 & 0.6423 & 0.0202 & -0.6616 & -0.0954 & 0.1266 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.7685 & 0.0121 & -0.9604 & -0.0471 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.6602 & 0.1596 & -0.3563 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.8929 & 0.1551 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.4798 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.0412 & 0.0204 & -0.5517 & -0.7850 & 0.1946 & -0.1985 \\ -0.1800 & -0.1740 & -0.2263 & -0.1283 & -0.8878 & 0.2855 \\ -0.1460 & -0.6028 & -0.4883 & 0.4562 & 0.0765 & -0.4037 \\ 0.3772 & -0.7024 & 0.1683 & -0.2285 & 0.2089 & 0.4900 \\ 0.7612 & -0.0154 & 0.1140 & -0.0702 & -0.3421 & -0.5342 \\ 0.4720 & 0.3352 & -0.6038 & 0.3195 & 0.0868 & 0.43669 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} 1.0691 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.355 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.0109 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0078 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0065 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0001 \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 5: The non-singular matrix **T** has the form:

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4244 & 0.5900 & 0.7316 & 0.9695 & 0.7049 & 1.0172 \\ -0.5988 & -0.6398 & -0.5389 & -0.3893 & -0.0826 & 0.4162 \\ -0.2020 & -0.0591 & -0.0283 & -0.0529 & 0.0361 & -0.1311 \\ -0.1191 & -0.0274 & 0.0346 & 0.0053 & -0.0172 & 0.0589 \\ 0.0182 & -0.0757 & -0.0336 & 0.0415 & -0.0335 & 0.0146 \\ -0.0203 & 0.0185 & -0.0160 & 0.0158 & -0.0084 & 0.0101 \end{bmatrix}$$

Step 6: The system is in equilibrium equivalent form:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0120 & -0.4910 & 0.0785 & 0.0465 & 0.0073 & -0.0081 \\ 0.4910 & -0.4415 & 0.3529 & 0.2060 & 0.0301 & -0.0343 \\ 0.0785 & -0.3529 & -1.8800 & -1.2871 & -0.8508 & 0.3832 \\ 0.0465 & -0.2060 & -1.2871 & -0.9049 & -1.6577 & 0.3143 \\ -0.0073 & 0.0301 & 0.8508 & 1.6577 & -0.0255 & 0.0558 \\ 0.0081 & -0.0343 & -0.3832 & -0.3143 & 0.0558 & -1.6653 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.4244 \\ -0.5988 \\ -0.2020 \\ -0.1191 \\ 0.0182 \\ -0.0203 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{C} = [0.4244 \quad 0.5988 \quad -0.2020 \quad -0.1191 \quad -0.0182 \quad 0.0203]$$

The results of the order reduction of the digital filter are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. RESULT OF ORDER REDUCTION OF THE 6th ORDER FILTER

Order	$H_r(s)$	$\ H - H_r\ _\infty$
5	$\frac{-0.1238s^4 - 0.2611s^3 + 0.405s^2 + 0.7221s + 0.8147}{s^5 + 3.24s^4 + 5.188s^3 + 4.469s^2 + 1.952s + 0.5468}$	$9.7456 \cdot 10^{-4}$
4	$\frac{-0.1235s^3 - 0.2711s^2 + 1.003s + 0.01749}{s^4 + 3.214s^3 + 1.635s^2 + 0.7117s + 0.01141}$	0.0437
3	$\frac{-0.1376s^2 - 0.08334s + 0.6907}{s^3 + 2.309s^2 + 1.161s + 0.4662}$	0.0266
2	$\frac{-0.1784s + 0.3335}{s^2 + 0.4294s + 0.2358}$	0.0904

The step response and the bode response are two basic responses that evaluate the quality of the filter. Therefore, we will use them to evaluate the quality of the low-order digital filter. The step response and bode response of the low-order digital filters are shown in Figures 1-4. We can see that the step response of the 5th-order digital filter coincides with the step response of the 6th- order digital filter (Figure 1). In Figure 2 we see that the step response of the 3rd-order digital filter almost coincides with the step response of the 6th-order digital filter and the step response of the 4th-order digital filter has a small deviation from the step response of the 6th-order digital filter. The step response of the 2nd-order digital filter has a large deviation from the step response of the 6th-order digital filter. Figure 4 shows the bode response of the 5th-order digital filter. It is noted that the 4th-order digital filter completely coincides with the bode response of the 6th-order digital filter.

Fig. 1. Step response of 5th- and 6th-order digital filters.

Fig. 2. Step response of 6th-, 4th-, 3rd-, and 2nd-order digital filters.

Fig. 3. Bode response of the 6th-, 5th-, and 4th-order digital filters.

In Figure 4, we see that:

- In the frequency range $\omega < 9.37\text{rad/s}$, the frequency amplitude response of the 3rd-order digital filter coincides with the frequency amplitude response of the 6th-order digital filter.
- In the frequency range $\omega > 9.37\text{rad/s}$, the frequency amplitude response of the 3rd-order digital filter has a small deviation from the frequency amplitude response of the 6th-order digital filter.

Fig. 4. Bode response of the 6th-, 3rd-, and 2nd-order digital filters.

- In the frequency range $\omega < 2.07\text{rad/s}$ and $\omega > 12.5\text{rad/s}$, the frequency phase response of the 3rd-order digital filter coincides with the frequency phase response of the 6th-order digital filter.
- In the frequency range $2.07\text{rad/s} < \omega < 12.5\text{rad/s}$, the frequency phase response of the 3rd-order digital filter has a small deviation from the frequency phase response of the 6th-order digital filter.
- In the frequency range $\omega < 2.7\text{rad/s}$, the frequency amplitude response of the 2nd-order digital filter coincides with the frequency amplitude response of the 6th-order digital filter.
- In the frequency range $\omega > 2.7\text{rad/s}$, the frequency response of the 2nd-order digital filter has a large deviation from the frequency response of the 6th-order digital filter.
- In the frequency range $\omega < 1.33\text{rad/s}$ and $\omega > 29.8\text{rad/s}$, the frequency phase response of the 2nd-order digital filter coincides with the frequency phase response of the 6th-order digital filter.
- In the frequency range of $1.33\text{rad/s} < \omega < 29.8\text{rad/s}$, the frequency phase response of the 2nd-order digital filter has a large deviation from the frequency phase response of the 6th-order digital filter.

Comment: If minimum order reduction error is desired, the 5th-order digital filter can be used instead of the 6th-order digital filter. If we want a low-order digital filter with the smallest order, but with quality almost equivalent to that of a 6th-order digital filter, we can choose a 3rd-order digital filter to replace the 6th order digital filter.

The novelty of the current paper is that the LQG algorithm has been used to determine a low-order filter that can replace the high-order filter. The paper has evaluated the error of order reduction according to both the formula for evaluating the order reduction error and the error on step response characteristics and bode response characteristics. In [27], the author does not specify the order of the order reduction system, only focuses on converting the filter from IIR form to FIR form by order reduction algorithms and then evaluates the limit of order reduction error at some frequencies. In the future, we will

evaluate the order reduction error at frequency points to compare the obtained results with the results in [27].

IV. CONCLUSION

Digital filters have many advantages, so they are widely used in technical fields. The most common digital filter design method is usually to design first an analog filter and then convert it to digital filter form. Digital IRR filters often arise in engineering problems, so they are increasingly utilized and studied in research. The design of digital IRR filters often has to apply approximation methods, so the resulting filter is often of high order. To make the digital IRR filter simple and low in computational cost, we need to apply model order reduction algorithms to reduce the order of the high-order IRR filter. This article has applied the LQG balanced truncation algorithm to reduce the order of a 6th-order digital filter. The results of comparison and evaluation of low-order filters show that the resulting 5th-order digital filter can replace the 6th-order digital filter without any change in filter quality. Also, a 3rd-order digital filter can be used instead of a 6th-order digital filter if it is accepted that the quality of the low-order filter is only approximately that of the 6th-order filter. The simulation results show the correctness of the filter order reduction results using the LQG balanced truncation algorithm.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. K. Mitra, *Digital Signal Processing: A Computer-Based Approach*, 2nd ed. New York, NY, USA: McGraw-Hill, 2001.
- [2] R. W. Oppenheim and A. V. Schaffer, *Discrete-Time Signal Processing*, 7th ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Prentice-Hall, 1989.
- [3] S. Saad, "Enhancement of Solar Cell Modeling with MPPT Command Practice with an Electronic Edge Filter," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7501–7507, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4304>.
- [4] N. Ambati, G. Immadi, M. V. Narayana, K. R. Bareddy, M. S. Prapurna, and J. Yanapu, "Parametric Analysis of the Defected Ground Structure-Based Hairpin Band Pass Filter for VSAT System on Chip Applications," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7892–7896, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4495>.
- [5] S. Nuanmeesri and W. Sriurai, "Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network Model Development for Chili Pepper Disease Diagnosis Using Filter and Wrapper Feature Selection Methods," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7714–7719, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4383>.
- [6] E. Ali, D. Narwani, A. M. Bughio, N. Nizamani, S. H. Siyal, and A. R. Khatri, "Analyzing the Impact of Loop Parameter Variations on the Transient Response of Second Order Voltage-Switched CP-PLL," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6687–6690, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3969>.
- [7] S. K. Bitra and S. Miriyala, "An Ultra-Wideband Band Pass Filter using Metal Insulator Metal Waveguide for Nanoscale Applications," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7247–7250, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4194>.
- [8] M. J. Juntti and B. Aazhang, "Finite memory-length linear multiuser detection for asynchronous CDMA communications," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 611–622, Feb. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1109/26.592564>.
- [9] C. E. Garcia, D. M. Prett, and M. Morari, "Model predictive control: Theory and practice—A survey," *Automatica*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 335–348, May 1989, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-1098\(89\)90002-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-1098(89)90002-2).
- [10] W. H. Kwon, "Why not use FIR filters for control?: FIR filters for state space models," in *Proceedings of the 4th Asian Control Conference*, Singapore, 2002, pp. 6–17.

- [11] L. Ljung, *System Identification: Theory for the User*, 2nd ed. London, UK: Pearson, 1998.
- [12] K. Fernando and H. Nicholson, "Singular perturbational model reduction of balanced systems," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 466–468, Apr. 1982, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1982.1102932>.
- [13] M. Aoki, "Control of large-scale dynamic systems by aggregation," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 246–253, Jun. 1968, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1968.1098900>.
- [14] N. K. Vu, H. Q. Nguyen, K. T. Ngo, and P. N. Dao, "Study on Model Reduction Algorithm Based on Schur Analysis," in *Research in Intelligent and Computing in Engineering*, R. Kumar, N. H. Quang, V. Kumar Solanki, M. Cardona, and P. K. Pattnaik, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2021, pp. 179–188.
- [15] N. K. Vu and H. Q. Nguyen, "Model Order Reduction Algorithm Based on Preserving Dominant Poles," *International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 2047–2058, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12555-019-0990-8>.
- [16] V. N. Kien and N. H. Quang, "Model reduction in schur basic with pole retention and H2 norm error bound," *Journal of Mechanical Engineering Research and Developments*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 279–293, 2021.
- [17] K. H. A. Olsson, "Model Order Reduction with Rational Krylov Methods," Ph.D. dissertation, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden, 2005.
- [18] J.-R. Li and J. White, "Low Rank Solution of Lyapunov Equations," *SIAM Journal on Matrix Analysis and Applications*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 260–280, Jan. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1137/S0895479801384937>.
- [19] B. Moore, "Principal component analysis in linear systems: Controllability, observability, and model reduction," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 17–32, Feb. 1981, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1981.1102568>.
- [20] L. Pernebo and L. Silverman, "Model reduction via balanced state space representations," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 382–387, Apr. 1982, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1982.1102945>.
- [21] K. Glover, "All optimal Hankel-norm approximations of linear multivariable systems and their L_∞ -error bounds," *International Journal of Control*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 1115–1193, Jun. 1984, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207178408933239>.
- [22] U. Desai and D. Pal, "A transformation approach to stochastic model reduction," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 29, no. 12, pp. 1097–1100, Dec. 1984, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1984.1103438>.
- [23] M. Green, "A relative error bound for balanced stochastic truncation," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 33, no. 10, pp. 961–965, Jul. 1988, <https://doi.org/10.1109/9.7255>.
- [24] M. G. Safonov and R. Y. Chiang, "A Schur method for balanced-truncation model reduction," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 34, no. 7, pp. 729–733, Jul. 1989, <https://doi.org/10.1109/9.29399>.
- [25] E. Jonckheere and L. Silverman, "A new set of invariants for linear systems—Application to reduced order compensator design," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 28, no. 10, pp. 953–964, Oct. 1983, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAC.1983.1103159>.
- [26] W. Gawronski and J.-N. Juang, "Model reduction in limited time and frequency intervals," *International Journal of Systems Science*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 349–376, Feb. 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207729008910366>.
- [27] L. Chai, J. Zhang, C. Zhang, and E. Mosca, "Hankel-Norm Approximation of IIR by FIR Models: A Constructive Method," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 55, no. 2, pp. 586–598, Mar. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSI.2007.913615>.

Deep Convolutional Neural Network Architecture for Plant Seedling Classification

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Abstract-Weed control is essential in agriculture since weeds reduce yields, increase production cost, impede harvesting, and degrade product quality. As a result, it is indeed critical to recognize weeds early in their vegetation cycle to evade negative impacts to crop growth. Earlier traditional methods used machine learning to determine crops along with weed species, but they had issues with weed detection efficiency at early growth stages. The current work proposes the implementation of a deep learning method that provides accurate results for precise weed recognition. Two different deep convolution neural networks have been used for our classification framework, namely Efficient Net B2 and Efficient Net B4. The plant seedlings dataset is utilized to investigate the proposed work. The evaluation metrics average accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were used. The findings demonstrate that the proposed approach is capable of differentiating between 12 species of a plant seedling dataset which contains 3 crops and 9 weeds. The average classification accuracy and F1 score are 99.00% for our Efficient Net B4 model and 97.00% for the Efficient Net B2. In addition, the proposed Efficient Net-B4 model performance is compared to the one of existing models on the plant seedlings dataset and the results showed that the proposed model Efficient Net B4 has superior performance. We intend to detect diseases in the identified plant species in our future research.

Keywords-deep learning; efficient net; machine learning; plant seedling classification; weed recognition; deep convolutional neural networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Weed control is one of the most challenging aspects of precision farming. Weeds harm the plant seedlings and take up the space and nutrients required for the crops reducing crop growth, while exercising herbicides over the crops would spoil the unexpected crops. It is important to identify plant seedlings because doing so can aid in identifying various plant species. When using machine learning algorithms to monitor plant state and even model climate change, a thorough knowledge of appearances, leaflet, and leaf classes in addition to the complete plant is crucial. Weed control should begin as soon as crop germination is complete. As a result, optimal weed control is recommended during the seedling stage. Automated plant seedling classification using machine learning methods has emerged as an important and encouraging field of research for

enhancing agricultural results. Modern academics have developed numerous agricultural applications using cutting-edge deep learning algorithms. At the early stages of growth the weeds and crops look similar in appearances when the images of plant seedlings are collected during various lighting conditions, the CNN methods achieved high classification performance. The goal of the current research is to develop a model for a crop-weed discrimination system that employs deep Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) to classify 12 crops and weed plant species.

A generic image database with plant seedling classification benchmarks was acquired with the use of a conditional camera. The dataset consists of 12 species at early growth stages [1]. Authors in [2] implemented techniques using binary image conversion and SVM to differentiate between crop and weed and obtained an accuracy of around 50%. A review work was done in [3] in the introduction of artificial intelligence for crop and weed management. Authors in [4] used deep learning architectures, namely Resnet, VGG16, and InceptionV3 for banana disease detection. Authors in [5] utilized prediction models on CNN, SVM, and KNN for apple classification and recognition. Authors in [6] conducted research regarding plant image classification tasks, for instance classifying maize plants and weeds by utilizing segmented images at initial stages of growth, with a training accuracy of 97.00%. Image processing and identification have been the subjects of [7-8]. Weed identification is challenging to ambiguous crop constraints and differing rocky or sandy identities, and long established classification techniques are most likely to fail in this task [9]. Authors in [10] proposed a classification model for plant seedlings. The authors attempted to improve classification efficiency by combining seedling and individual leaf classification. Bayes belief integration was used for classification design.

A deep encoder-decoder CNN was updated with a 14-channel image containing vegetation index values for segmentation to solve crop-weed classification consisting of sugar beet plants and weeds in [11]. In [12], a CNN network was able to determine unsupervised feature characterizations from 44 different plant species with high accuracy. In [13], instance segmentation was utilized to identify crops and weeds.

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The authors were able to classify crops and weeds with an accuracy of 60%. For a large dataset to obtain good accuracy we need graphical processing units, in addition, during the training operation, continuous modifications of the training parameters are needed in order to obtain a balanced output [14]. An image classifier model using deep CNNs was used to determine the accuracy of CNN, SVM, and KNN in [15]. Author in [16] proposed a CNN framework for classifying plant seedlings. The main topic of the endeavor involves classifying young plant seedlings using a CNN while monitoring accuracy and precision metrics. A hybrid architecture using Alex Net and VGG Net was implemented to determine the model accuracy and F1 score for a plant seedlings dataset with 94.38% average accuracy. In [17], in order to classify images of crop and weed seedlings, 5 pre-trained convolution network techniques were used, i.e. ResNet50, Xception, MobileNetV2, VGG16, and VGG19. ResNet50 architecture produced the best results scoring 95.23% testing accuracy [17]. Weeds and crops were classified using Residual Network 101 in [18], obtaining an overall accuracy rate of 98.47% on the validation set and 96.04% on the test set. CNN frameworks for plant seedlings classification by using ResNet50V2, MobileNetV2, and Efficient Net B0 architectures were implemented in [19]. The Efficient Net B0 method provided an average F1-Score of 96.26% and an accuracy of 96.52%. A limitation of this work is that the authors would have added more layers by increasing depth or resolution to obtain maximum accuracy.

In this paper, a novel method that fully trains a network is presented. The Proposed Efficient Net B4 model is used to provide better accuracy for image classification by compound scaling the dimension of network width, depth and resolution. For this experiment, we have used an i7 processor with Nvidia RTX 3080 Ti GPU and other supporting frameworks such as Keras and Tensor flow for the classification and analysis of the images of plant seedlings.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

The plant seedling dataset for training, validation, and testing is described in this section. The dataset was obtained from Computer Vision and Biosystems Signal Processing group, Aarhus University, an open-source website which contains plant seedling images. The dataset contains 5541 plant seedling images, namely 833 test images, 833 validation images, and 3875 training images were acquired, each representing a different stage of growth for all the 12 considered species [1, 19].

B. Dataset Distribution

The plant seedling dataset is split into 3 sections: testing (15%), validation (15%), and training (70%). The testing set is used in evaluating the performance of the trained model. We made sure that testing and validation sets had no duplicates. The plant seedling dataset distribution is displayed in Table I and the test set of 12 plant seedling species is shown in Figure 1.

TABLE I. PLANT SEEDLING DATASET WITH CLASS WISE DISTRIBUTION

Class	Species	Training	Validation	Testing	Total
1	Black grass	217	46	46	309
2	Charlock	316	68	68	452
3	Cleavers	235	50	50	335
4	Chickweed	497	108	108	713
5	Common wheat	177	38	38	253
6	Fat hen	376	81	81	538
7	Loose silky-bent	532	115	115	762
8	Maize	179	39	39	257
9	Scentless mayweed	425	91	91	607
10	Shepherd's purse	192	41	41	274
11	Small-flowered cranesbill	404	87	87	578
12	Sugar beet	325	69	69	463
Total Images		3875	833	833	5541

Fig. 1. Test set of the 12 plant seedling species.

C. Test Data Set

The motivation of our research work was to investigate the Efficient Net [19, 27] architecture because this model outperforms other CNN models in terms of accuracy and efficiency. The Efficient Net model has received little attention when considering datasets of plant seedlings. In this paper, a new mobile-size baseline is established. Efficient Net, compound scaling, and neural architecture are used. Efficient Models introduced a new baseline network (B0-B7) to provide better accuracy for image classification by compound scaling size (e.g. depth, width, and resolution) of the network by having a balanced output for the above parameters. A compound scaling technique is suggested in [19] that consistently scales width, depth, and resolution according to a set of guiding principles. They suggest the following formula:

$$s. t. \alpha \cdot \beta^2 \cdot \gamma^2 \approx 2$$

$$\alpha \geq 1, \beta \geq 1, \gamma \geq 1$$

where depth: $d = \alpha^\phi$, width: $w = \beta^\phi$, resolution: $r = \gamma^\phi$, ϕ is a user-defined coefficient that regulates the resources (e.g. FLOPs, or floating point operations) available for model scaling, and α, β, γ allocate resources according to depth, width, and resolution. A convolution operation uses a certain amount of FLOPs in relation to d, w^2 and r^2 . In the equation above,

this information is reflected. For each new ϕ , the number of required FLOPs increases by 2^ϕ . The authors scaled it up using the following method starting with EfficientNet-B0:

- Fix $\phi = 1$. We assume that the resource is twice as available at any given scaling step as it was at the one before.
- Perform a quick grid search across α , β , and γ to ensure that the restriction in the above equation is not violated.
- The authors discovered that the values $\alpha=1.2$, $\beta=1.1$, and $\gamma=1.15$ perform optimally.
- Fix α , β , and γ , then scale up the EfficientNet-B0 with various ϕ to get recent scaled networks, i.e. Efficient Net B0-B7 [27].

TABLE II. MODIFICATIONS IN NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

Layer (type)	Output shape	Parameters
Efficient Net B4 (Functional)	(None,7,7,1792)	17673823
global_max_pooling2d_5 (Global Max Pooling2D)	(None,1792)	0
flatten_6(Flatten)	(None,1792)	0
dense_12(Dense)	(None,1024)	1836032
batch_normalization_4 (Batch Normalization)	(None,1024)	4096
dropout_5(Dropout)	(None,1024)	0
dense_13(Dense)	(None,512)	524800
batch_normalization_5 (Batch Normalization)	(None,512)	2048
dropout_6(Dropout)	(None,512)	0
dense_14(Dense)	(None,128)	65664
batch_normalization_6 (Batch Normalization)	(None,128)	512
dropout_7(Dropout)	(None,128)	0
dense_15(Dense)	(None,12)	1548
Total Parameters		20,108,523
Trainable Parameters		3,237,772
Non- Trainable Parameters		16,870,751

D. The Proposed Methodology

In the proposed methodology, the first step is to obtain a plant seedling data set. Once we acquire the image dataset, the next step is to pre-process the raw images in order to keep only relevant information. The preprocessing steps consist of resizing the image into 380×380 resolution for Efficient Net B4 and 280×280 resolution for Efficient Net B2 model, sharpening the image to highlight fine details by removing blurring and highlighting edges, and applying segmentation to the objects of interest, which are the leaves of the plant, and finally applying masking. After preprocessing we split the dataset into training, validation, and testing parts with ratio of 70:15:15 and passed it into a custom designed model using the Efficient Net B4 as the base model. The Modified Efficient Net B4 can be used in many different ways:

- Training the whole Efficient Net architecture.
- Applying transfer learning paradigm to extract features from the pre-trained Efficient Net on plant seedling dataset.
- Applying the transfer learning paradigm along with fine-tuning of the architecture by adding a few more layers like

pooling, flattening, and normalization followed by a few dense layers and a final layer with softmax activation function.

Fig. 2. The proposed methodology.

E. Pipeline for Image-Processing

For training, each image in the plant seedlings dataset was scaled to 380×380 (resolution scaling) for Efficient Net B4 and 280×280 for Efficient Net B2. We synthetically increased the dataset size by using image augmentation through rotating, zooming, and horizontal and vertical flipping. Gaussian filter was first used to smooth the image. As can be seen, the background of the plant images has numerous pointless rock-formed borders. Because these edges would only provide background noise, we converted the values of the discontinuous pixels into continuous ones. Our next step was to identify the relevant information in the image and remove any unnecessary background. To classify an object, a binary image that we wish to represent must be created. We will just need to look at the beneficial object's shape, making the classification procedure considerably simpler. To accomplish this, we converted the RGB image to the much more useful HSV format, which makes it much easier to discriminate between colors. There is now no overlap because the object can be easily distinguished from the background, but still there is some noise and flaws in the image, so as a follow-up, we slightly eroded it. We rescaled all images, created a mask for every image and then applied segmentation on each sample. Each image in the dataset was subjected to the processing pipeline by a function that we defined which outputs the processed dataset. Figure 3 shows the pre-processed images of the training model.

Fig. 3. Pre-processed images of plant seedlings.

F. Transfer Learning

In order to complete tasks that are related to one another, transfer learning is another used high-level concept. We could not directly apply the pre-trained weights for interpretation and expect excellent performance due to the different fields of the dataset images. As a result, we carried out refinement to customize towards the original domain of the images. For an Efficient Net B4 model, few more layers were added and minor parameter adjustments to the trained model were made in this step. There are numerous approaches to fine tuning. These incorporate the use of a pre-trained design for feature extractors out of which features were fed to each classifier, for fine adjustment to all or a few parameters at the last number of layers in the pre-trained modeling.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

We cover the implementation and training of Efficient Net B4 and Efficient Net B2 in this section to ensure reproducibility.

A. Learning Rate Change

The learning rate is classified by the best significant hyper-parameters to obtain quick and reliable training for neural networks. A large range of the loss gradient is applied to the latest parameters in order to alter them in the orientation of the reduced loss. In order to do this, the network's learning rate was linearly increased in a certain range of values after each network had been trained for a few epochs. We observed the change in validation loss by decreasing the learning rate from 0.01 to 0.001. After this change, the validation loss is considerable. The final plot of the validation loss against epoch is displayed in Figure 4.

B. Fine Tuning Efficient Net B2

All layers in the Efficient Net B2 were trained using gradient updates and a learning rate of 0.001. We applied Stochastic Gradient Descent optimizer for custom dense layers and a default decay rate for this implementation.

C. Fine Tuning Efficient Net B4

Since training was unstable, we have added a few more layers for Efficient Net B4. Based on multiple runs with hyper parameter tuning as well as grid search techniques, we found the best parameters suitable for our problem for Efficient Net B4 architecture with a learning rate of 0.001, RHO value of 0.9, epsilon of 1e-08 and default decay values. We applied Adam Optimizer for the custom dense layers.

D. Performance Evaluation Metrics

The effectiveness of any classification model cannot be assessed with common criteria. The performance metrics considered for each model are accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, support, and confusion matrices.

E. Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix provides details about the classifier's errors, including the kinds of errors that are occurring. The performance of a classification model's predicting power was compiled in an N×N table (N represents the number of classes).

It is a matrix that shows the relationship between the model's categorization and its real label (predicted label). A correct estimation of an image's class is referred to as a True Positive (TP). When the model suggests an image's class incorrectly, it produces a False Positive (FP). Whenever the model correctly estimates a negative class of the image, it produces a True Negative (TN). False Negative (FN) will occur when it incorrectly predicts a negative class of an image. The accuracy score is applied to assess our model's performance wherein TPc, FPc and FNc signify True Positives, False Positives and False Negatives. Pc indicates a class' specific precision metric that says, out of all points that are predicted to be positive, how many are actually positive. Rc represents a class specific recall metric that says, out of all positive points, how many are actually positive. N represents the overall collection of images, whereas Nc denotes the overall collection of images of class c and C denotes the overall collection with regard to classes. S denotes the mean of average weighted (F1) over all cross validation folds.

$$P_c = \frac{TP_c}{TP_c + FP_c} \quad (1)$$

$$R_c = \frac{TP_c}{TP_c + FN_c} \quad (2)$$

$$f_{1,c} = 2 \frac{P_c R_c}{P_c + R_c} \quad (3)$$

$$avg_{weighted}(f_1) = \sum_{c=1}^C \frac{N_c}{N} \cdot f_{1,c} \quad (4)$$

$$S = \frac{1}{N_{fold}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{fold}} avg_{weighted}(f_1) \quad (5)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We used (1) to (4) to evaluate the performance. The topmost validation accuracy obtained on Efficient Net B4 model is 99% whereas for Efficient Net B2 is 97%. Figures 4 and 5 show the accuracy and loss curves of training and validation sets for Efficient Net B4 and Efficient Net B2 respectively.

Fig. 4. Efficient Net B4 model performance.

Fig. 5. Efficient Net B2 model performance.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Black-grass	0.87	0.89	0.88	46
Charlock	1.00	1.00	1.00	68
Cleavers	1.00	1.00	1.00	50
Common Chickweed	1.00	1.00	1.00	108
Common wheat	1.00	1.00	1.00	38
Fat Hen	1.00	1.00	1.00	81
Loose Silky-bent	0.96	0.95	0.95	115
Maize	1.00	1.00	1.00	39
Scentless Mayweed	1.00	1.00	1.00	91
Shepherds Purse	1.00	1.00	1.00	41
Small-flowered Cranesbill	1.00	1.00	1.00	87
Sugar beet	1.00	1.00	1.00	69
accuracy			0.99	833
macro avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	833
weighted avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	833

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Black-grass	0.80	0.89	0.85	46
Charlock	1.00	1.00	1.00	68
Cleavers	1.00	1.00	1.00	50
Common Chickweed	1.00	1.00	1.00	108
Common wheat	1.00	0.79	0.88	38
Fat Hen	0.95	1.00	0.98	81
Loose silky-bent	0.92	0.95	0.94	115
Maize	1.00	1.00	1.00	39
Scentless Mayweed	1.00	1.00	1.00	91
Shepherds Purse	1.00	1.00	1.00	41
Small-flowered cranesbill	1.00	1.00	1.00	87
Sugar beet	1.00	0.94	0.97	69
accuracy			0.97	833
macro avg	0.97	0.96	0.97	833
weighted avg	0.97	0.97	0.97	833

Fig. 6. Plant seedlings classification report of (a) Efficient Net B4 and (b) Efficient Net B2 on the test data set.

The performance metrics on the test dataset for precision, recall, F1-score, and support are depicted in Figure 6. The average weighted accuracy of the Efficient B4 model is 99% whereas the Efficient Net B2 model has 97%. For Efficient Net B4, classes black grass and loose silky bent have F1-score equal to 0.88 and 0.95. For the remaining plant species the F1-score is 1 indicating that all the plants are correctly classified. For the Efficient Net B2 model, classes black grass, common wheat, fat-hen, loose silky bent, and sugar beet have F1-score of 0.85, 0.88, 0.98, 0.94, and 0.97 while the remaining plant species are correctly classified. Figures 7 and 8 demonstrate the confusion matrix for the test data set in support of the 12-class configuration of the plant seedlings dataset during testing. The plant seedling dataset consists of 12 species representing 12 rows and 12 columns of the matrix, which analyzes correct classification using 833 test images. In the confusion matrix, the rows indicate the current classification, while the columns

indicate the predicted score. From the confusion matrix of the Efficient Net B4 model we can infer that 6 images of black grass and 5 images of loose silky bent are misclassified while the remaining plant species are predicted correctly. For the Efficient Net B2 model, 5 images of black-grass, 4 images of common wheat, 6 images of loose silky bent, and 4 images of sugar beet are incorrectly classified and the remaining are classified correctly. The conclusion is that the Efficient Net B4 model performed better than the B2 model.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrix of the plant seedling test dataset of Efficient Net B4.

Fig. 8. Confusion matrix of the plant seedling test dataset of Efficient Net B2.

The proposed Efficient Net B2 and Efficient Net B4 methods were compared with existing methods [16-19] for the plant seedlings dataset and the results are shown in Table III. We can see that the proposed Efficient Net B4 method outperforms the latest competitive approaches in terms of accuracy and F1-score.

TABLE III. METHOD COMPARISON ON THE PLANT SEEDLING DATASET

Ref.	Method	Accuracy (%)	F1-score (%)
[16]	Alexnet + VGGNet	94.38	93.57
[17]	Resnet 50	95.23	95.00
[18]	Residual Network 101	98.47	95.72
[19]	Efficient Net B0	96.52	96.26
Proposed	Efficient Net B2	97.00	97.00
	Efficient Net B4	99.00	99.00

Figure 9 depicts examples of charlock and sugar beet images of the test set that are correctly classified with the proposed Efficient Net B4 model.

Fig. 9. Correctly classified charlock and sugar-beet images.

Figure 10 depicts loose silky-bent and black-grass, images which are misclassified plant seedling images of weed species, because they almost look similar. Black grass class contains 6 images and loose silky bent class contains 5 images which are misclassified.

Fig. 10. Incorrectly classified loose silky bent and black grass images.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, deep convolution neural networks were investigated for identifying plant species at early growth stages. The proposed Efficient Net B4 model for plant seedling

classification dataset which contains 12 species of crops and weed achieved a high level of accuracy and average F1-score rate, precision, and recall of 99.00%. When compared with other known methods, the proposed model shows a significant increase in accuracy in the considered plant seedlings dataset. Nevertheless, throughout our investigations, we discovered that images from two specific groups, black-grass and loose silky-bent, had been incorrectly classified. There are some limitations in distinguishing crops and weeds during the seedling stage: (a) image resolution is insufficient to allow differentiation among susceptible soil, plant seedlings, and weeds, (b) there are spectral and apparent similarities in the initial stages, as there is a competition among weeds and useful crops, and (c) the detection method and the soil background reflectance overlap. The proposed model can be further extended and improved with the use of a larger dataset.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. M. Giselsson, R. N. Jorgensen, P. K. Jensen, M. Dyrmann, and H. S. Midtby, "A Public Image Database for Benchmark of Plant Seedling Classification Algorithms." arXiv, Nov. 15, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1711.05458>.
- [2] S. Murawwat, A. Qureshi, S. Ahmad, and Y. Shahid, "Weed Detection Using SVMs," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2412–2416, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1647>.
- [3] N. C. Eli-Chukwu, "Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture: A Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4377–4383, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2756>.
- [4] S. L. Sanga, D. Machuve, and K. Jomanga, "Mobile-based Deep Learning Models for Banana Disease Detection," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5674–5677, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3452>.
- [5] S. Alqethami, B. Almtanni, W. Alzhrani, and M. Alghamdi, "Disease Detection in Apple Leaves Using Image Processing Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8335–8341, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4721>.
- [6] C.-C. Andrea, B. B. Mauricio Daniel, and J. B. Jose Misael, "Precise weed and maize classification through convolutional neuronal networks," in *Second Ecuador Technical Chapters Meeting*, Salinas, Ecuador, Oct. 2017, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ETCM.2017.8247469>.
- [7] G. Sehgal, B. Gupta, K. Paneri, K. Singh, G. Sharma, and G. Shroff, "Crop Planning using Stochastic Visual Optimization," in *IEEE Visualization in Data Science*, Phoenix, AZ, USA, Oct. 2017, pp. 47–51, <https://doi.org/10.1109/VDS.2017.8573443>.
- [8] S. T. Hang and M. Aono, "Open world plant image identification based on convolutional neural network," in *Asia-Pacific Signal and Information Processing Association Annual Summit and Conference*, Jeju, Korea (South), Dec. 2016, pp. 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1109/APSIPA.2016.7820676>.
- [9] A. Lee, *Comparing Deep Neural Networks and Traditional Vision Algorithms in Mobile Robotics*. Swarthmore, PA, USA: Swarthmore College, 2017.
- [10] A. Kamilaris, A. Kartakoullis, and F. X. Prenafeta-Boldo, "A review on the practice of big data analysis in agriculture," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 143, pp. 23–37, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2017.09.037>.
- [11] M. Dyrmann, P. Christiansen, and H. S. Midtby, "Estimation of plant species by classifying plants and leaves in combination," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 202–212, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1002/rob.21734>.
- [12] W. M. A. H. B. W. Zefri and S. Nordin, "Plant Recognition System Using Convolutional Neural Network," *IOP Conference Series: Earth*

- and *Environmental Science*, vol. 1019, no. 1, Dec. 2022, Art. no. 012031, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1019/1/012031>.
- [13] A. Milioto, P. Lottes, and C. Stachniss, "Real-Time Semantic Segmentation of Crop and Weed for Precision Agriculture Robots Leveraging Background Knowledge in CNNs," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, Brisbane, QLD, Australia, Dec. 2018, pp. 2229–2235, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRA.2018.8460962>.
- [14] W.-S. Jeon and S.-Y. Rhee, "Plant Leaf Recognition Using a Convolution Neural Network," *International Journal of Fuzzy Logic and Intelligent Systems*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 26–34, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5391/IJFIS.2017.17.1.26>.
- [15] J. Champ, A. Mora-Fallas, H. Goeau, E. Mata-Montero, P. Bonnet, and A. Joly, "Instance segmentation for the fine detection of crop and weed plants by precision agricultural robots," *Applications in Plant Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 7, 2020, Art. no. e11373, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aps3.11373>.
- [16] H. A. Elnemr, "Convolutional Neural Network Architecture for Plant Seedling Classification," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 10, no. 8, pp. 319–325, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2019.0100841>.
- [17] K. Gupta, R. Rani, and N. K. Bahia, "Plant-Seedling Classification Using Transfer Learning-Based Deep Convolutional Neural Networks," *International Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Information Systems*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 25–40, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJAEIS.2020100102>.
- [18] A.-A. Binguitcha-Fare and P. Sharma, "Crops and weeds classification using Convolutional Neural Networks via optimization of transfer learning parameters," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 2284–2294, 2019.
- [19] N. Makanapura, C. Sujatha, P. R. Patil, and P. Desai, "Classification of plant seedlings using deep convolutional neural network architectures," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2161, no. 1, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 012006, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2161/1/012006>.
- [20] J. G. A. Barbedo, "A review on the main challenges in automatic plant disease identification based on visible range images," *Biosystems Engineering*, vol. 144, pp. 52–60, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2016.01.017>.
- [21] N. Teimouri, M. Dyrmann, P. R. Nielsen, S. K. Mathiassen, G. J. Somerville, and R. N. Jorgensen, "Weed Growth Stage Estimator Using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 5, May 2018, Art. no. 1580, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18051580>.
- [22] M. Dyrmann and R. N. Jorgensen, "RoboWeedSupport: weed recognition for reduction of herbicide consumption," in *Precision agriculture '15*, Wageningen, Netherlands: Wageningen Academic Publishers, 2015, pp. 571–578.
- [23] S. Hochreiter, "The Vanishing Gradient Problem During Learning Recurrent Neural Nets and Problem Solutions," *International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 107–116, Apr. 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218488598000094>.
- [24] M. Anthimopoulos, S. Christodoulidis, L. Ebner, A. Christe, and S. Mougiakakou, "Lung Pattern Classification for Interstitial Lung Diseases Using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network," *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 1207–1216, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2016.2535865>.
- [25] N. R. Rahman, Md. A. M. Hasan, and J. Shin, "Performance Comparison of Different Convolutional Neural Network Architectures for Plant Seedling Classification," in *2nd International Conference on Advanced Information and Communication Technology*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Nov. 2020, pp. 146–150, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICAICT51780.2020.9333468>.
- [26] S. Umamaheswari and A. V. Jain, "Encoder–Decoder Architecture for Crop-Weed Classification Using Pixel-Wise Labelling," in *International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Signal Processing*, Amaravati, India, Jan. 2020, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/AISP48273.2020.9072992>.
- [27] M. Tan and Q. Le, "EfficientNet: Rethinking Model Scaling for Convolutional Neural Networks," in *36th International Conference on Machine Learning*, Long Beach, CA, USA, Jun. 2019, pp. 6105–6114.
- [28] C. R. Alimboyong and A. A. Hernandez, "An Improved Deep Neural Network for Classification of Plant Seedling Images," in *15th International Colloquium on Signal Processing & Its Applications*, Penang, Malaysia, Mar. 2019, pp. 217–222, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSPA.2019.8696009>.
- [29] S. Malliga, S. V. Kogilavani, D. Jaivignesh, and S. Jeevananth, "Classification of Plant Seedlings Using Deep Learning Architectures," *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, vol. 29, no. 3s, pp. 1024–1030, Mar. 2020.

Soil Liquefaction Potential in Different Seismic Zones of Bihar, India

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Abstract-Liquefaction potential analysis for the liquefiable as well as non-liquefiable soils of Bihar state has been performed in this paper based on the actual field data from three seismic zones, i.e. zone III, zone IV, and zone V. The analysis has been performed following the simplified procedure given in [1] and later modified in [2]. The results show that districts under seismic zone III are comparatively more resistant to liquefaction in most cases, districts of zone IV are relatively more prone to liquefaction up to a few depths, and districts of zone V are most liquefiable. Liquefaction resistance is primarily depending upon the fine content of soil and SPT N-values.

Keywords-standard penetration test; cyclic stress ratio; cyclic resistance ratio; soil liquefaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Liquefaction is the phenomenon in which the strength and stiffness of the soil are reduced by earthquake shaking and/or another dynamic loading. When an earthquake of suitable intensity shakes a deposit of loose saturated coarse-grained cohesionless soils, then the grain structures are triggered towards a more compact packing. However, it is not possible to drain off the pore water because it does not have sufficient time to do so during an earthquake. The pore water pressure then shoots outward because the applied stresses are taken up by the incompressible water and the effective stresses approach zero:

$$\sigma' = \sigma - u \quad (1)$$

where σ' is the effective stress, σ is the total stress, and u is pore water pressure.

In the case of cohesionless soil ($c = 0$), shear strength (τ) reduces to zero when effective stress approaches zero.

$$\tau = c + \sigma' \tan \phi' \quad (2)$$

where ϕ' is the effective internal resistance of the soil.

Liquefaction is one of the most disastrous seismic hazards. India has experienced the world's greatest earthquakes in the last few decades which lead to soil liquefaction and consequential damages.

Authors in [1] presented a simplified procedure for the evaluation of the liquefaction potential of soil using the

assemblage of available field data of liquefied or non-liquefied soil during earthquakes. The author in [3] studied the field data from different countries for the evaluation of the liquefaction potential of soil in earthquake magnitude $M_w = 7.5$ and the result was then extended to earthquakes of other magnitudes and for silty soil. Authors in [4] presented a critical review of sandy soil deposits. It was found that the sand that has more than 10% fine content has a much higher resistance to liquefaction than clean sand having the same SPT N value. For clean sands with SPT N_1 values greater than 25, silty sands containing more than 10% fines with SPT N values greater than 20, or sandy silts with more than 20% clay will not undergo any extensive damage. Sands containing gravel particles have lower resistance than the clean sands without gravel for the same SPT N-values. Authors in [5] presented the influence of SPT procedures in the evaluation of liquefaction resistance. They also proposed the curve of liquefaction resistance for sands with the variations of SPT N-values and fines content. Authors in [6] proposed a simple correction factor to counteract the effect of overburden pressure on the results of the Standard Penetration Test (SPT) performed in sands. Authors in [7] studied the possible frequency of earthquakes in India and found that India has relatively higher frequencies of great earthquakes and lower frequencies of moderate earthquakes. Authors in [8] studied the liquefaction potential as per the case history of the Bihar-Nepal Earthquake on 21 August 1988. Based on three prevailing approaches, they found the differences with regard to relative density and depth of liquefaction potential and suggested further research. Authors in [9] studied the mechanism of liquefaction and soil failure during the 1994 Northridge earthquake with detailed subsurface investigations. They found that the variation of the Ground Water Table (GWT) in combination with the heterogeneous nature of alluvial fan sediments is responsible for complex patterns of ground deformation. Authors in [10] found that clay particles are mainly responsible for the liquefaction characteristics of the soil. Authors in [2] convened a workshop sponsored by the National Center for Earthquake Engineering Research (NCEER) with 20 experts to review developments in the field of liquefaction in the past. They have given many updates and augmentations to the simplified procedure proposed in [1]. Authors in [11] studied the

likelihood of the initiation of soil liquefaction by SPT-based probabilistic and deterministic correlations. Authors in [12] closely studied the possible factor of the Bhuj 2001 earthquake and found that deep fluid inflow plays a crucial role in the intensity of disasters. Authors in [13] studied the Liquefaction Potential Index (LPI) of Mumbai city. They evaluated the factors of safety to predict the liquefaction potential along the depths of soil with a 2% probability of exceedance in 50 years using an SPT-based simplified procedure. Authors in [14] described the influence of earthquake ground motion on the liquefaction resistance of the soil. Authors in [15] investigated the paleoliquefaction from four sites in north Bihar and one site in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Based on the available data, they found the recurrence interval of 124 ± 63 years for great earthquakes like the 1934 earthquake in Bihar. They also concluded that the Plains of Bihar are most vulnerable to the seismic activity originating from the Himalayas as well as the terai Plains of Nepal. Authors in [16] studied the quality of groundwater in Bihar. Authors in [17] studied the post-earthquake effect in Kathmandu valley after Gorkha, Nepal earthquake on 25 April 2015. They found seven locations of sand blows based on geotechnical investigation records. Authors in [18] reinterpreted the dynamic behavior of sandy soils subjected to recent historical earthquakes in Japan and demonstrated that the aged soils have higher resistance towards liquefaction than that suggested by their current design code. Authors in [19] studied four districts of Bihar, i.e. Samastipur, Darbhanga, West-Champaran, and Araria based on reliability techniques for the prediction of seismic liquefaction. Authors in [20-26] described stability methods for the soil types in Bihar. Authors in [27] evaluated the effect of plasticity on the liquefaction potential of fine-grained soil in the seismically active regions of Bihar based on Multi-Linear Regression (MLR) analysis and reliability analysis, i.e. First Order Second Moment (FOSM), and established a co-relation between the factor of safety against liquefaction, reliability index, and liquefaction probability.

According to the literature survey, Bihar is one of the most vulnerable states concerning seismic activities. Tremendous work has been conducted in the field of liquefaction, but little in the region. This study has been done to overcome this shortcoming and to have more accurate predictions of liquefaction in the seismic zones of Bihar, i.e. zone III, zone IV, and zone V and their relative vulnerability towards liquefaction. Here, a general correlation between liquefaction potential, depth, fines content, and SPT-N value has been established to be used as a handy tool. The method adopted here for the analysis is the method recommended by Indian Standard which is originally based on the simplified empirical method of [1] and later on modified by different researchers in this field.

II. METHODOLOGY

The prime concern is to know whether the soil is susceptible to liquefaction or not, so that suitable measures can be adopted in advance if required. For this purpose, the Factor Of Safety (FOS) against liquefaction is estimated according to the method described in Annex F of Indian Standard code [28] IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016, which is based on the Simplified

Procedure proposed in [1] and later modified in [2]. The proneness of soil towards liquefaction is assured by estimating the FOS at different depths below Natural Ground Level (NGL). The FOS is estimated by dividing the Cyclic Resistance Ratio (CRR) required to induce liquefaction in the soil by the Cyclic Stress Ratio (CSR) produced by an earthquake.

$$FOS = \frac{CRR}{CSR} \quad (3)$$

A. Evaluation of CSR

Authors in [1] formulated the following expression for the calculation of (CSR):

$$CSR = 0.65 \left(\frac{a_{max}}{g} \right) \left(\frac{\sigma_{vo}}{\sigma'_{vo}} \right) r_d \quad (4)$$

where a_{max} = Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) at the ground surface, g = gravity acceleration, σ_{vo} = total vertical stress at the point of interest, σ'_{vo} = effective vertical stress at the same point, and r_d = reduction factor.

The value of the reduction factor was initially given in [1] which was later approximated in [29]:

$$r_d = \frac{1.000 - 0.4113z^{0.5} + 0.04052z + 0.001753z^{1.5}}{1.000 - 0.4177z^{0.5} + 0.05729z - 0.006205z^{1.5} + 0.001210z^2} \quad (5)$$

IS 1893 (part 1):2016 recommends using the ratio (a_{max}/g) equal to seismic zone factor if the value of PGA is not available.

TABLE I. SEISMIC ZONE FACTOR

Seismic zone factor	II	III	IV	V
Z	0.10	0.16	0.24	0.36

B. Evaluation of CRR

$$CRR = CRR_{7.5} (MSF) K_{\sigma} K_{\alpha} \quad (6)$$

where $CRR_{7.5}$ = CCR for earthquake magnitude $M_w = 7.5$, MSF , K_{σ} , and K_{α} are the correction factors for earthquake magnitude other than 7.5 (commonly known as magnitude scaling factor), overburden stress, and static shear stress respectively.

Authors in [2] re-evaluated the 1982's data set to get the revised MSF given by:

$$MSF = 10^{2.24} / M_w^{2.56} \quad (7)$$

The high overburden correction factor is required for a depth greater than 15m is [30]:

$$K_{\sigma} = (\sigma'_{vo} / P_a)^{f-1} \quad (8)$$

where P_a is the atmospheric pressure measured in the same unit as effective overburden pressure (σ'_{vo}) and the value of f depends on relative density (D_r):

$$f = \begin{cases} 0.8 \sim 0.7 & \text{for } D_r = 40\% \text{ to } 60\% \\ 0.7 \sim 0.6 & \text{for } D_r = 60\% \text{ to } 80\% \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

As per the report correction for static shear stress [28], K_{α} , is required only for sloping ground which may be assumed to be in routine practice.

The SPT N-value measured in the field is corrected for the 60% hammer efficiency and standardized equipment using the expression:

$$N_{60} = NC_{60} \quad (10)$$

where $C_{60} = C_{HT} * C_{HW} * C_{SS} * C_{RL} * C_{BD}$ and C_{HT} , C_{HW} , C_{SS} , C_{RL} , and C_{BD} are the correction factors for the height of fall, hammer weight, sampler setup, rod length, and borehole diameter respectively.

The N_{60} value computed is normalized to approximately 100kPa effective overburden pressure as suggested in [6]:

$$(N_1)_{60} = C_N N_{60} \quad (11)$$

where:

$$C_N = (P_a / \sigma'_{v0})^{0.5} \leq 1.7 \quad (12)$$

Authors in [22] developed an equation for counteracting the effect of fines content to get an equivalent clean sand value $(N_1)_{60cs}$:

$$(N_1)_{60cs} = \alpha + \beta(N_1)_{60} \quad (13)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= 0 & \beta &= 1 & \text{for } FC \leq 5\% \\ a &= e^{[1.76 - \frac{190}{FC^2}]} & \beta &= 0.99 + \frac{FC^{1.5}}{1000} & \text{for } 5\% < FC \leq 35\% \\ a &= 0.5 & \beta &= 1.2 & \text{for } FC > 35\% \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

An expression for cyclic resistance ratio for a 7.5 magnitude earthquake was formulated in [31] based on a clean sand base curve plot originally proposed in [5]:

$$CRR_{7.5} = \frac{1}{34 - (N_1)_{60cs}} + \frac{(N_1)_{60cs}}{135} + \frac{50}{[10 \times (N_1)_{60cs} + 45]^2} - \frac{1}{200} \quad (15)$$

This expression is valid for $(N_1)_{60} < 30$. For $(N_1)_{60} \geq 30$, soils are too dense and non-liquefiable.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis has been done based on the big input data set which includes the depth of strata, its dry density, moisture content, fineness content, and SPT N-values. The rotary method of boring was adopted with a borehole diameter of 150mm throughout the project. For the analysis of the whole project the magnitude of the earthquake, M_w , was taken as 7.5. Three major district data from seismic zone III, five from seismic zone IV, and three from seismic zone V are summarized here in Tables II-IV for representation. The other districts from that zones show almost similar results. The soil of Nawada and Buxar districts has initially lower resistance to liquefaction which is almost near to the FOS-1 line but at 3m depth there is a sudden increase in the FOS of Buxar due to the increase in SPT N-value. Bhojpur has comparatively higher resistance against liquefaction in seismic zone III.

Fig. 1. Variation of the factor of safety with depth in seismic zone III

TABLE II. LIQUEFACTION ANALYSIS OF ZONE III (PGA: 0.16, MSF: 1, K_a : 1)

District	Depth (m)	γ (kN/m ³)	FC	N-value	σ_v (kPa)	σ'_v (kPa)	r_d	CSR	C_{60}	N_{60}	C_N	$(N_1)_{60}$	$(N_1)_{60cs}$	K_σ	$CRR_{7.5}$	CRR	FOS
Buxar GWT: 1.10m	1.50	19.62	95.20	10	29.43	25.51	0.990	0.12	0.65	6.50	1.70	11.04	13.75	1.00	0.15	0.15	1.24
	3.00	19.91	97.20	22	59.74	41.10	0.979	0.15	0.69	15.25	1.56	23.78	29.04	1.00	0.41	0.41	2.78
	4.50	19.72	97.20	14	88.73	55.38	0.969	0.16	0.74	10.31	1.34	13.85	17.12	1.00	0.18	0.18	1.13
	6.00	19.82	94.10	18	118.90	70.83	0.958	0.17	0.82	14.81	1.19	17.60	21.62	1.00	0.24	0.24	1.42
	7.50	19.82	94.20	20	148.62	85.84	0.943	0.17	0.82	16.46	1.08	17.76	21.82	1.00	0.24	0.24	1.41
	9.00	19.91	96.40	21	179.23	101.73	0.923	0.17	0.82	17.28	0.99	17.13	21.06	1.00	0.23	0.23	1.35
	10.50	19.91	96.60	23	209.10	116.89	0.894	0.17	0.87	19.92	0.92	18.43	22.61	1.00	0.25	0.25	1.51
Nawada GWT: 3.50m	1.50	18.64	3.20	9	27.96	27.96	0.990	0.10	0.65	5.85	1.70	9.94	9.94	1.00	0.11	0.11	1.09
	3.00	18.64	4.30	11	55.92	55.92	0.979	0.10	0.69	7.62	1.34	10.19	10.19	1.00	0.11	0.11	1.13
	4.50	18.34	5.00	22	82.55	72.74	0.969	0.11	0.74	16.20	1.17	18.99	18.99	1.00	0.20	0.20	1.78
	6.00	18.25	6.80	26	109.48	84.95	0.958	0.13	0.82	21.40	1.08	23.21	23.49	1.00	0.26	0.26	2.06
	7.50	18.25	2.70	25	136.85	97.61	0.943	0.14	0.82	20.57	1.01	20.82	20.82	1.00	0.23	0.23	1.64
	9.00	18.25	3.00	26	164.22	110.26	0.923	0.14	0.82	21.40	0.95	20.38	20.38	1.00	0.22	0.22	1.54
	10.50	18.25	6.30	28	191.59	122.92	0.894	0.14	0.87	24.26	0.90	21.88	22.05	1.00	0.24	0.24	1.67
	12.00	18.15	7.00	31	217.78	134.40	0.857	0.14	0.87	26.85	0.86	23.16	23.48	1.00	0.26	0.26	1.83
	13.50	18.05	3.10	35	243.68	145.58	0.811	0.14	0.87	30.32	0.83	25.13	25.13	1.00	0.29	0.29	2.09
15.00	18.05	3.50	39	270.76	157.94	0.761	0.14	0.87	33.78	0.80	26.88	26.88	0.87	0.34	0.29	2.15	
Bhojpur GWT: 6.90m	1.50	19.72	74.30	11	29.58	29.58	0.990	0.10	0.65	7.15	1.70	12.15	15.08	1.00	0.16	0.16	1.56
	3.00	19.72	84.60	12	59.15	59.15	0.979	0.10	0.69	8.32	1.30	10.81	13.47	1.00	0.15	0.15	1.42
	4.50	19.72	85.50	14	88.73	88.73	0.969	0.10	0.74	10.31	1.06	10.94	13.63	1.00	0.15	0.15	1.45
	6.00	19.82	79.30	17	118.90	118.90	0.958	0.10	0.82	13.99	0.92	12.83	15.90	1.00	0.17	0.17	1.70
	7.50	19.82	80.30	19	148.62	142.74	0.943	0.10	0.82	15.64	0.84	13.09	16.20	1.00	0.17	0.17	1.69
	9.00	19.91	77.40	23	179.23	158.63	0.923	0.11	0.82	18.93	0.79	15.03	18.53	1.00	0.20	0.20	1.82
10.50	19.91	78.40	25	209.10	173.78	0.894	0.11	0.87	21.66	0.76	16.43	20.21	1.00	0.22	0.22	1.95	

TABLE III. LIQUEFACTION ANALYSIS OF ZONE IV (PGA: 0.246, MSF: 1, K_a : 1)

District	Depth (m)	γ (kN/m ³)	FC	N-value	σ_v (kPa)	σ'_v (kPa)	r_d	CSR	C_{60}	N_{60}	C_N	(N_1) ₆₀	(N_1) _{60CS}	K_a	$CRR_{7.5}$	CRR	FOS
Nalanda GWT: 3.85m	1.50	18.25	92.95	5	27.37	27.37	0.990	0.15	0.65	3.25	1.70	5.52	7.13	1.00	0.09	0.09	0.57
	3.00	18.25	93.75	6	54.74	54.74	0.979	0.15	0.69	4.16	1.35	5.62	7.24	1.00	0.09	0.09	0.59
	4.50	18.34	90.95	11	82.55	76.17	0.969	0.16	0.74	8.10	1.15	9.28	11.64	1.00	0.13	0.13	0.78
	6.00	18.34	88.92	14	110.07	88.98	0.958	0.18	0.82	11.52	1.06	12.21	15.16	1.00	0.16	0.16	0.87
	7.50	18.44	91.32	17	138.32	102.51	0.943	0.20	0.82	13.99	0.99	13.82	17.08	1.00	0.18	0.18	0.91
	9.00	18.44	90.44	21	165.99	115.46	0.923	0.21	0.82	17.28	0.93	16.08	19.80	1.00	0.21	0.21	1.03
	10.50	18.44	92.59	24	193.65	128.41	0.894	0.21	0.87	20.79	0.88	18.35	22.52	1.00	0.25	0.25	1.19
	12.00	18.44	90.09	29	221.31	141.36	0.857	0.21	0.87	25.12	0.84	21.13	25.85	1.00	0.31	0.31	1.48
	13.50	18.74	91.20	30	252.95	158.28	0.811	0.20	0.87	25.99	0.79	20.66	25.29	1.00	0.30	0.30	1.47
15.00	18.74	89.77	31	281.06	171.68	0.761	0.19	0.87	26.85	0.76	20.50	25.09	0.85	0.29	0.25	1.29	
Patna GWT: 4.50m	1.50	19.33	90.90	7	28.99	28.99	0.990	0.15	0.65	4.55	1.70	7.73	9.78	1.00	0.11	0.11	0.72
	3.00	19.52	90.90	9	58.57	58.57	0.979	0.15	0.69	6.24	1.31	8.15	10.28	1.00	0.12	0.12	0.76
	4.50	19.62	90.90	12	88.29	88.29	0.969	0.15	0.74	8.84	1.06	9.40	11.78	1.00	0.13	0.13	0.85
	6.00	19.72	91.70	16	118.31	103.59	0.958	0.17	0.82	13.17	0.98	12.94	16.02	1.00	0.17	0.17	1.00
	7.50	19.72	91.70	20	147.89	118.46	0.943	0.18	0.82	16.46	0.92	15.12	18.65	1.00	0.20	0.20	1.08
	9.00	19.91	91.70	23	179.23	135.08	0.923	0.19	0.82	18.93	0.86	16.29	20.04	1.00	0.22	0.22	1.13
	10.50	19.91	92.90	24	209.10	150.24	0.894	0.19	0.87	20.79	0.82	16.96	20.85	1.00	0.23	0.23	1.17
	12.00	20.01	92.90	28	240.15	166.57	0.857	0.19	0.87	24.26	0.77	18.79	23.05	1.00	0.26	0.26	1.34
	13.50	20.01	92.90	30	270.17	181.88	0.811	0.19	0.87	25.99	0.74	19.27	23.62	1.00	0.27	0.27	1.42
15.00	20.11	90.90	33	301.66	198.65	0.761	0.18	0.87	28.59	0.71	20.28	24.84	0.81	0.29	0.23	1.30	
Saran GWT: 2.00m	1.50	19.23	92.70	6	28.84	28.84	0.990	0.15	0.65	3.90	1.70	6.63	8.45	1.00	0.10	0.10	0.65
	3.00	19.52	92.70	9	58.57	48.76	0.979	0.18	0.69	6.24	1.43	8.93	11.22	1.00	0.12	0.12	0.68
	4.50	19.62	92.70	10	88.29	63.77	0.969	0.21	0.74	7.36	1.25	9.22	11.57	1.00	0.13	0.13	0.61
	6.00	19.23	91.90	12	115.37	76.13	0.958	0.23	0.82	9.88	1.15	11.32	14.08	1.00	0.15	0.15	0.67
	7.50	19.23	91.90	15	144.21	90.25	0.943	0.24	0.82	12.34	1.05	12.99	16.09	1.00	0.17	0.17	0.73
	9.00	19.33	91.90	18	173.93	105.26	0.923	0.24	0.82	14.81	0.97	14.44	17.83	1.00	0.19	0.19	0.80
	10.50	19.33	93.00	23	202.92	119.53	0.894	0.24	0.87	19.92	0.91	18.22	22.37	1.00	0.25	0.25	1.04
	12.00	19.62	93.00	26	235.44	137.34	0.857	0.23	0.87	22.52	0.85	19.22	23.56	1.00	0.27	0.27	1.16
	13.50	19.62	93.00	28	264.87	152.06	0.811	0.22	0.87	24.26	0.81	19.67	24.10	1.00	0.28	0.28	1.25
15.00	19.72	91.70	30	295.77	168.24	0.761	0.21	0.87	25.99	0.77	20.04	24.54	0.86	0.28	0.24	1.16	
West Champaran GWT: 5.10m	1.50	19.13	94.90	28	28.69	28.69	0.990	0.15	0.65	18.19	1.70	30.93	37.61	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3.00	19.03	96.50	7	57.09	57.09	0.979	0.15	0.69	4.85	1.32	6.42	8.20	1.00	0.10	0.10	0.64
	4.50	19.03	96.60	6	85.64	85.64	0.969	0.15	0.74	4.42	1.08	4.77	6.23	1.00	0.08	0.08	0.54
	6.00	19.03	95.10	12	114.19	105.36	0.958	0.16	0.82	9.88	0.97	9.62	12.04	1.00	0.13	0.13	0.81
	7.50	19.23	95.30	23	144.21	120.66	0.943	0.18	0.82	18.93	0.91	17.23	21.18	1.00	0.23	0.23	1.31
	9.00	19.23	95.30	25	173.05	134.79	0.923	0.18	0.82	20.57	0.86	17.72	21.76	1.00	0.24	0.24	1.29
10.50	19.33	95.40	28	202.92	149.95	0.894	0.19	0.87	24.26	0.82	19.81	24.27	1.00	0.28	0.28	1.47	
Begusarai GWT: 4.00m	1.50	19.52	84.30	9	29.28	29.28	0.990	0.15	0.65	5.85	1.70	9.94	12.43	1.00	0.14	0.14	0.87
	3.00	19.52	84.30	11	58.57	58.57	0.979	0.15	0.69	7.62	1.31	9.96	12.45	1.00	0.14	0.14	0.89
	4.50	19.91	84.30	19	89.61	84.71	0.969	0.16	0.74	13.99	1.09	15.20	18.74	1.00	0.20	0.20	1.25
	6.00	19.91	84.30	23	119.49	99.87	0.958	0.18	0.82	18.93	1.00	18.94	23.23	1.00	0.26	0.26	1.46
	7.50	19.91	87.20	25	149.36	115.02	0.943	0.19	0.82	20.57	0.93	19.18	23.52	1.00	0.27	0.27	1.39
	9.00	19.91	87.20	26	179.23	130.18	0.923	0.20	0.82	21.40	0.88	18.75	23.00	1.00	0.26	0.26	1.30
	10.50	20.01	79.40	28	210.13	146.37	0.894	0.20	0.87	24.26	0.83	20.05	24.56	1.00	0.28	0.28	1.41
	12.00	20.01	79.40	30	240.15	161.67	0.857	0.20	0.87	25.99	0.79	20.44	25.03	1.00	0.29	0.29	1.47
	13.50	20.11	82.40	32	271.49	178.30	0.811	0.19	0.87	27.72	0.75	20.76	25.41	1.00	0.30	0.30	1.56
15.00	20.11	82.40	38	301.66	193.75	0.761	0.18	0.87	32.92	0.72	23.65	28.88	0.82	0.40	0.33	1.80	

Fig. 2. Variation of the factor of safety with depth in seismic zone IV.

Fig. 3. Variation of the factor of safety with depth in seismic zone V.

TABLE IV. LIQUEFACTION ANALYSIS OF ZONE IV (PGA: 0.36, MSF: 1, K_A : 1)

District	Depth (m)	γ (kN/m ³)	FC	N-value	σ_v (kPa)	σ'_v (kPa)	r_d	CSR	C_{60}	N_{60}	C_N	$(N_f)_{60}$	$(N_f)_{60CS}$	K_σ	$CRR_{7.5}$	CRR	FOS
Madhubani GWT: 0.85m	1.50	17.96	23.20	3	26.95	20.57	0.990	0.30	0.65	1.95	1.70	3.31	7.73	1.00	0.09	0.09	0.31
	3.00	17.95	17.20	6	53.85	32.76	0.979	0.38	0.69	4.16	1.70	7.07	10.56	1.00	0.12	0.12	0.31
	4.50	18.04	93.68	9	81.20	45.40	0.969	0.41	0.74	6.63	1.48	9.84	12.30	1.00	0.13	0.13	0.33
	6.00	18.07	21.08	10	108.39	57.87	0.958	0.42	0.82	8.23	1.31	10.82	15.55	1.00	0.17	0.17	0.39
	7.50	18.05	13.30	12	135.35	70.11	0.943	0.43	0.82	9.88	1.19	11.79	14.23	1.00	0.15	0.15	0.36
	9.00	18.06	7.35	28	162.55	82.59	0.923	0.43	0.82	23.04	1.10	25.35	25.78	1.00	0.31	0.31	0.72
	10.50	18.29	6.73	32	192.07	97.40	0.894	0.41	0.87	27.72	1.01	28.09	28.38	1.00	0.38	0.38	0.93
	12.00	18.35	37.70	12	220.26	110.88	0.857	0.40	0.87	10.40	0.95	9.87	12.35	1.00	0.13	0.13	0.34
	13.50	18.43	41.34	15	248.77	124.68	0.811	0.38	0.87	12.99	0.90	11.64	14.46	1.00	0.15	0.15	0.41
15.00	18.45	4.25	28	276.73	137.92	0.761	0.36	0.87	24.26	0.85	20.65	20.65	0.91	0.22	0.20	0.57	
Darbhanga GWT: 2.30m	1.50	18.04	94.80	5	27.07	27.07	0.990	0.23	0.65	3.25	1.70	5.52	7.13	1.00	0.09	0.09	0.38
	3.00	18.57	93.10	7	55.70	48.83	0.979	0.26	0.69	4.85	1.43	6.94	8.83	1.00	0.10	0.10	0.39
	4.50	18.26	86.46	9	82.18	60.60	0.969	0.31	0.74	6.63	1.28	8.51	10.72	1.00	0.12	0.12	0.39
	6.00	18.22	16.75	15	109.31	73.02	0.958	0.34	0.82	12.34	1.17	14.45	18.24	1.00	0.19	0.19	0.58
	7.50	18.68	15.50	10	140.08	89.07	0.943	0.35	0.82	8.23	1.06	8.72	11.80	1.00	0.13	0.13	0.37
	9.00	18.61	16.70	11	167.47	101.75	0.923	0.36	0.82	9.05	0.99	8.97	12.44	1.00	0.14	0.14	0.38
10.00	18.25	16.75	13	182.51	106.97	0.905	0.36	0.87	11.26	0.97	10.89	14.48	1.00	0.15	0.15	0.43	
Supaul GWT: 1.00m	3.00	19.33	71.00	8	57.98	38.36	0.979	0.35	0.69	5.54	1.61	8.95	11.24	1.00	0.12	0.12	0.36
	4.50	19.33	7.00	13	86.97	52.63	0.969	0.37	0.74	9.57	1.38	13.19	13.43	1.00	0.14	0.14	0.39
	7.50	19.33	9.00	17	144.94	81.18	0.943	0.39	0.82	13.99	1.11	15.53	16.35	1.00	0.17	0.17	0.44
	9.00	19.33	8.00	18	173.93	95.45	0.923	0.39	0.82	14.81	1.02	15.16	15.65	1.00	0.17	0.17	0.42
	10.50	19.33	8.00	19	202.92	109.72	0.894	0.39	0.87	16.46	0.95	15.71	16.21	1.00	0.17	0.17	0.45
	12.00	19.33	8.00	22	231.91	124.00	0.857	0.37	0.87	19.06	0.90	17.11	17.63	1.00	0.19	0.19	0.50
	13.50	19.33	5.00	25	260.90	138.27	0.811	0.36	0.87	21.66	0.85	18.42	18.42	1.00	0.20	0.20	0.55
	15.00	19.33	6.00	28	289.89	152.55	0.761	0.34	0.87	24.26	0.81	19.64	19.76	0.88	0.21	0.19	0.55
	18.00	19.33	7.00	35	347.86	181.09	0.667	0.30	0.87	30.32	0.74	22.53	22.84	0.84	0.25	0.21	0.71
21.00	19.33	8.00	44	405.84	209.64	0.598	0.27	0.87	38.12	0.69	26.32	26.96	0.80	0.34	0.27	1.00	

In seismic zone IV, Begusarai has the highest resistance towards liquefaction as the district is liquefiable only up to 3.5m depth below NGL. Saran is liquefiable up to 10.5m depth below NGL which shows that this district is the most susceptible to liquefaction in seismic zone IV. All the districts of zone V have a factor of safety almost below the FOS-0.5 line which means that they are most susceptible to liquefaction. Madhubani has a sudden increase in factor of safety at 9m to 10.5m depth below NGL due to a slight decrease in fines content and drastically increase in SPT N-value.

IV. DISCUSSION

From the above data set, it is found that among the districts of seismic zone III, Buxar and Bhojpur have higher fines content than Nawada, whereas the SPT N-value of Nawada is comparatively high. Begusarai districts have comparatively lower fines content than the districts of seismic zone IV. Darbhanga district has a sudden decrease in fines content from 4.5m to 6m depth, whereas Madhubani shows two local peaks at 4.5m and 13.5m. Authors in [4] found that more than 10% of fines content values of soils are less liquefiable, but in the present study, it has been found that the fines content and SPT N-values are both critical factors for the liquefaction potential of the soil. Liquefaction may occur at higher or lower fines content values if the SPT-values are lower and higher respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis results and the graphs of the FOS versus fines content and SPT N-value, the following

conclusions have been made relative to the different seismic zones of Bihar:

In seismic zone III, the soil shows comparatively more resistance to liquefaction in most cases. The FOS value is more than 1 in all cases. Bhojpur shows comparatively more resistance to liquefaction, whereas Nawada shows the lowest resistance in the mentioned zone. The soil of seismic zone IV is relatively more prone to liquefaction. The soil of Begusarai district is liquefiable up to 3.5m depth below NGL. Saran district is more vulnerable to liquefaction up to 10.5m depth below NGL. The other districts in this zone show a similar trend of liquefaction up to certain depths. All the districts in seismic zone V are most liquefiable as their FOS is much lesser than 1. Madhubani shows the peak at 10.5m depth due to a slight decrease in fines content and a sudden increase in SPT N-value. The soil of Darbhanga district has quite a lower SPT N-value and decreasing fines content with the increase in depth below NGL.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. B. Seed and I. M. Idriss, "Simplified Procedure for Evaluating Soil Liquefaction Potential," *Journal of the Soil Mechanics and Foundations Division*, vol. 97, no. 9, pp. 1249-1273, Sep. 1971, <https://doi.org/10.1061/JSEFAQ.0001662>.
- [2] T. L. Youd *et al.*, "Liquefaction Resistance of Soils: Summary Report from the 1996 NCEER and 1998 NCEER/NSF Workshops on Evaluation of Liquefaction Resistance of Soils," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 127, no. 10, pp. 817-833, Oct. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(2001\)127:10\(817\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2001)127:10(817)).
- [3] H. B. Seed, I. M. Idriss, and I. Arango, "Evaluation of Liquefaction Potential Using Field Performance Data," *Journal of Geotechnical*

- Engineering, vol. 109, no. 3, pp. 458–482, Mar. 1983, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1983\)109:3\(458\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1983)109:3(458)).
- [4] K. Tokimatsu and Y. Yoshimi, "Empirical Correlation of Soil Liquefaction Based on SPT N-Value and Fines Content," *Soils and Foundations*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 56–74, Dec. 1983, https://doi.org/10.3208/sandf1972.23.4_56.
- [5] H. Bolton Seed, K. Tokimatsu, L. F. Harder, and R. M. Chung, "Influence of SPT Procedures in Soil Liquefaction Resistance Evaluations," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 111, no. 12, pp. 1425–1445, Dec. 1985, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1985\)111:12\(1425\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1985)111:12(1425)).
- [6] S. S. C. Liao and R. V. Whitman, "Overburden Correction Factors for SPT in Sand," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 112, no. 3, pp. 373–377, Mar. 1986, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1986\)112:3\(373\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1986)112:3(373)).
- [7] S. K. Jain, "Indian Earthquakes : An Overview," *The Indian Concrete Journal*, vol. 72, no. 11, pp. 1–11, 1998.
- [8] S. Mukarjee and B. Lavania, "Soil Liquefaction in Nepal-Bihar Earthquake of August 21, 1988," in *4th International Conference on Geotechnical Engineering*, Missouri, USA, Mar. 1998.
- [9] T. L. Holzer, M. J. Bennett, D. J. Ponti, and J. C. T. Iii, "Liquefaction and Soil Failure During 1994 Northridge Earthquake," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 125, no. 6, pp. 438–452, Jun. 1999, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)1090-0241\(1999\)125:6\(438\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)1090-0241(1999)125:6(438)).
- [10] R. Liang, X. Bai, and J. Wang, "Effect of clay particle content on liquefaction of soil," in *12th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Auckland, New Zealand, Feb. 2000.
- [11] K. Cetin *et al.*, "Standard Penetration Test-Based Probabilistic and Deterministic Assessment of Seismic Soil Liquefaction Potential," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 130, no. 12, pp. 1314–1340, Dec. 2004, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(2004\)130:12\(1314\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2004)130:12(1314)).
- [12] P. Mandal and M. V. Rodkin, "Seismic imaging of the 2001 Bhuj Mw7.7 earthquake source zone: b-value, fractal dimension and seismic velocity tomography studies," *Tectonophysics*, vol. 512, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Nov. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tecto.2011.09.004>.
- [13] J. Dixit, D. M. Dewaikar, and R. S. Jangid, "Assessment of liquefaction potential index for Mumbai city," *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 2759–2768, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-12-2759-2012>.
- [14] S. Unjoh, M. Kaneko, S. Kataoka, K. Nagaya, and K. Matsuoka, "Effect of earthquake ground motions on soil liquefaction," *Soils and Foundations*, vol. 52, no. 5, pp. 830–841, Oct. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sandf.2012.11.006>.
- [15] C. P. Rajendran, B. John, K. Rajendran, and J. Sanwal, "Liquefaction record of the great 1934 earthquake predecessors from the north Bihar alluvial plains of India," *Journal of Seismology*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 733–745, Jul. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10950-016-9554-z>.
- [16] K. Praveen and L. B. Roy, "Assessment of Groundwater Quality Using Water Quality Indices: A Case Study of Paliganj Distributary, Bihar, India," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8199–8203, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4696>.
- [17] D. Gautam, F. S. de Magistris, and G. Fabbrocino, "Soil liquefaction in Kathmandu valley due to 25 April 2015 Gorkha, Nepal earthquake," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 97, pp. 37–47, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2017.03.001>.
- [18] I. Towhata *et al.*, "Liquefaction perspective of soil ageing," *Geotechnique*, vol. 67, no. 6, pp. 467–478, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeot.15.P.046>.
- [19] S. K. Umar, P. Samui, and S. Kumari, "Reliability Analysis of Liquefaction for Some Regions of Bihar," *International Journal of Geotechnical Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 23–37, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJGEE.2018070102>.
- [20] S. S. Kar and L. B. Roy, "Probabilistic Based Reliability Slope Stability Analysis Using FOSM, FORM, and MCS," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8236–8240, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4689>.
- [21] S. Saxena and L. B. Roy, "The Effect of Geometric Parameters on the Strength of Stone Columns," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 9028–9033, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5138>.
- [22] R. Lal Bahadur and P. K. "Study of soil erosion by using remote sensing and GIS techniques in Sone command area in Bihar, India," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 62, pp. 1664–1670, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.04.739>.
- [23] K. Praveen and L. B. Roy, "Study Of Groundwater Quality For Irrigation Purpose – A Case Study Of Paliganj Distributary, Bihar, India," *Natural Volatiles and Essential Oils*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3461–3477, 2021.
- [24] L. B. Roy and K. Praveen, "Study of ET0 by Using Soft Computing Techniques in the Eastern Gandak Project in Bihar, India—A Case Study," in *Soft Computing: Theories and Applications*, R. Kumar, C. W. Ahn, T. K. Sharma, O. P. Verma, and A. Agarwal, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2022, pp. 515–526.
- [25] R. Ray, S. S. Choudhary, and L. B. Roy, "Reliability analysis of soil slope stability using MARS, GPR and FN soft computing techniques," *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2347–2357, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-021-01238-w>.
- [26] R. Ray, S. S. Choudhary, and L. B. Roy, "Reliability Analysis of Layered Soil Slope Stability using ANFIS and MARS Soft Computing Techniques," *International Journal of Performability Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 7, Jul. 2021, Art. No. 647, <https://doi.org/10.23940/ijpe.21.07.p9.647656>.
- [27] S. Ghani and S. Kumari, "Probabilistic Study of Liquefaction Response of Fine-Grained Soil Using Multi-Linear Regression Model," *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series A*, vol. 102, no. 3, pp. 783–803, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40030-021-00555-8>.
- [28] *IS 1893 (2016), Criteria for earthquake resistant design of structures, part-1 general provisions and building sixth revision*. New Delhi, India: Bureau of Indian Standards, 2016.
- [29] T. F. Blake, private communication, 1996, (as cited in T. L. Youd, *et al.*, "Liquefaction Resistance of Soils: Summary Report from the 1996 NCEER and 1998 NCEER/NSF Workshops on Evaluation of Liquefaction Resistance of Soils," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 127, no. 10, pp. 817–833, 2001).
- [30] M. E. Hynes and R. S. Olsen, "Influence of confining stress on liquefaction resistance," in *Physics and Mechanics of Soil Liquefaction*, Routledge, 1999.
- [31] A. F. Rauch, private communication, 1998.

A Deep Learning Technique for Detecting High Impedance Faults in Medium Voltage Distribution Networks

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Abstract-Utility companies always struggle with the High Impedance Fault (HIF) in the electrical distribution systems. In this article, the current signal is seen in situations involving 10,400 different samples, with and without HIF, like linear, non-linear load, and capacitance switching. A better method that processes signals very fast and with low sample rates, requiring less memory and computational labor, is demonstrated by Mathematical Morphology (MM). For HIF identification, Deep Convolution Neural Networks (DCNNs) are being developed. This paper presents a novel method for signal processing with low sample rates, high signal processing speed, and low computational and memory requirements. The suggested six-layer DCNN is compared with other models, such as the four-layer and eight-layer DCNN models and the results are discussed.

Keywords-high impedance fault; mathematical morphology; deep convolution neural networks

I. INTRODUCTION

For a power system to operate securely and dependably, an adequate protective mechanism that can recognize, classify, and locate the system's defects is essential. Even though standard protection relays are able to quickly recognize low-impedance network faults [1-3], but they can't notice HIFs' small fault current, something that represents a significant safety threat. In addition, the power network experiences cascading failures as a result of the HIFs spreading into a functioning area of the grid system. Therefore, HIF detection is very important in a distribution system. Feature extraction and classifier development are the first two steps in the detection of HIF.

Numerous Signal Processing Techniques (SPTs) have been presented to extract features for the purpose of training and

testing classifiers during the pattern recognition stage using time-frequency transforms to obtain the proper patterns. This technique separates the different disturbances. The Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) includes information on signal loss and the time loss while analyzing the data for feature extraction [4, 5]. The Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) has been often used for fault analysis. It is, however, inadequate for evaluating non-stationary transient signals that have both temporal and frequency components due to its constant window length. Time-frequency analysis performs well across all detection criteria and is particularly sensitive to non-stationary signals. However, the length of the computations raises questions about the technology's suitability for protection applications. The signal can be processed using the Wavelet Transform (WT) approach by examining its low- and high-frequency components. Using the wavelet decomposition coefficient of a voltage waveform, a WT-based approach may identify HIFs. Wavelet packet transform is applied to features extracted from voltage and current signal data in order to identify and distinguish HIFs. The level 5 and level 7 approximation coefficients as well as the standard deviation of detail of the db4 mother wavelet are employed for such detection process. WT offers greater signal processing resolution. However, the implementation of this approach in protective applications is limited by its high computational complexity, high data rate, and storage space requirements [6]. Recently, Mathematical Morphology (MM) was used in HIF detection, although the technique needs to be improved.

The majority of detection techniques observe the input signal for processing while selecting a high sample rate. High sampling rates increase the amount of the needed computational space. The current study shows an improved technique that processes signals extremely quickly and with

low sampling rates, which requires less memory and computational work. To gather the HIF and non-HIF current signal data, a precise MATLAB/SIMULINK model of a genuine power distribution network was used. MM is a time-domain, nonlinear signal transformation technique. Processing time is reduced because of the usage of simpler calculations [7, 8]. Additionally, MM filters are appropriate for real-time power system activities like transmission line protection. The most important task in the signal processing technique is the extraction of critical features, which is made possible by the interaction between the signal and the Structured Element (SE). SE shape plays a key role in signal processing. The MM filter is used in this study to pre-process the current signal. While preserving fault current characteristics, this filter lowers the signal's noise level.

Deep Learning (DL) is very good at automatically extracting features from speech and image analysis. DL can capture both temporal and spatial data from the input without the need for signal manipulation [9-11]. By removing manually created feature extraction, the use of DL in fault and non-fault detection not only increases accuracy, but also streamlines the process. Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) were used to solve the high impedance fault problem, and performance against noise, training time, parameter count, and overall performance have all been discussed. For the purpose of detection and classification, a Deep Convolution Neural Network (DCNN) receives a 2D image that has been converted from the fault and non-fault signal. The 1D signal data and the 2D signal image are completely different things [12-14].

Previous literature has not taken into account multiple power quality disturbances. The proposed method is using DCNN for the problem of multiple fault and non-fault detection and signal classification. The MM filter is used in this study to pre-process fault and non-fault current signals while maintaining fault current characteristics [15-18]. This filter reduces the signal noise level. Then, using a CNN, the output signal of the mathematical morphology with and without faults is detected. The following is a list of the current study's contributions.

- By analyzing the fault and non-fault MM output signal, the DCNN layer minimizes the manual extraction of features and permits automatic feature extraction.
- Due to the high computational complexity of the CNN, a Batch Normalization (BN) layer is implemented to speed up the training procedure and minimize the number of parameters.

II. THE MATHEMATICAL MORPHOLOGY

The structure of signals is altered via a non-linear signal processing method termed MM. This method was created in its natural shape in 1975. Integral geometry and set theory are the foundations of MM. MM operates entirely in the time domain and does not compute the frequency content of a signal, as opposed to Fourier or wavelet transforms, which separate the signals' frequency information. Recently, MM has been applied to power distribution systems, particularly for fault identification [19, 20]. As a result, an effort has been made to

leverage MM in pre-processing the signals in order to lessen the workload on the computer, the amount of memory needed, and the overall detection latency. The SE is the foundation of the MM processing applications. For the execution of any MM-based operation, the choice of SE is a crucial step. The type and frequency content of the fault signal affect the choice of SE. Erosion and dilation are two essential MM changes [21, 22]. These two transformations can be creatively coupled to create other transformations that can be applied in the right situations. It has been stated that various MM-based tools are used for power system applications [23]. These instruments are produced using a variety of replications and mixes of dilation and erosion employing various structuring components [24].

A. The Choice of a Structuring Element

The SE is a necessary component of MM-based signal processing. It is an operator used in signal processing that separates a signal into sub-signals of various important properties. Depending on the types of applications, it could have different geometrical structures [25]. The one-dimensional signals obtained from power systems are examined using linear SEs. Signal transformations depend significantly on the SEs' length and height (magnitude).

B. Structuring Element Length

The window size for any MM function is determined by the length of a SE, which also determines the delayed in output. With respect to the MM operation, the output delay is equal to $(m-1)\Delta T$, where T is the sampling interval, and m is the length of the SE. It should be observed that the output delay constantly grows as the SE lengthens. Therefore, linear SE with a length of 3 has been regarded as the best for fault detection applications in order to decrease time in MM transformations.

C. Structuring Element Height

In power systems, various current and voltage densities are employed. Therefore, the samples of current or voltage signals must be standardized using the peak magnitude of their rating value before MM modifications in order to have a more general option of the SE. In normal conditions, the normalization limits the signal magnitude to roughly 1 despite the various system voltage and current levels. As a result, a SE will always be at its best for any voltage or current levels. The magnitude (or height) of each SE element can be any small arbitrary value once the waveform has been adjusted [26].

III. THE FILTERS OF MATHEMATICAL MORPHOLOGY

Assume that $X(n)$ is a signal that needs to be translated and specified in the domain $D_x = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ and $Y(m)$ is a SE defined in the domain $D_y = \{b_0, b_1, \dots, b_m\}$. The Dilation (+) of the signal $X(n)$ by $Y(m)$ is given by:

$$\text{Dilation}(n) = (X(n)+Y(m)) = \text{Max}\{X(n-m)+Y(m)\} \quad (1)$$

where $0 \leq (n-m) \leq n$, $m \geq 0$, $n > m$, and n, m are integers.

The Erosion (-) of signal $X(n)$ by $Y(m)$ is given in (2):

$$\text{Erosion}(n) = (X(n)-Y(m)) = \text{Min}\{X(n+m)-y(m)\} \quad (2)$$

where $0 \leq (n+m) \leq n$, $m \geq 0$.

As indicated above, the opening (α) and closing (β) functions are defined based on (1), (2) in (3) and (4) respectively.

$$\text{Opening } (n) = (X(n) @ Y(m)) = [(X(n) + Y(n)) - Y(m)] \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Closing } (n) = (X(n) * Y(m)) = [(X(n) - Y(m)) + Y(m)] \quad (4)$$

Different Mathematical Morphological Filters (MMFs) are developed from these MM functions and employed in real-time signal processing applications. Closing – Opening(0) and Opening – Closing(α) are defined by:

$$Co(n) = (X(n) * Y(m)) @ Y(m) \quad (5)$$

$$Oc(n) = (X(n) @ Y(m)) * Y(m) \quad (6)$$

The Mean Closure – Opening Filter (MCOF) is designed as the arithmetic mean of close and open:

$$MCOF(n) = [\text{Opening}(n) + \text{Closing}(n)]/2 \quad (7)$$

The Mean Closing – Opening and Opening – Closing Filter (MCOOCF) is the mathematical mean of Co and Oc:

$$MCOOCF(n) = [Co(n) + Oc(n)]/2 \quad (8)$$

IV. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Authors in [5, 6] analyzed HIF with non-HIF scenarios using the 33KV feeder model shown in Figure 1. This model has a distribution transformer connecting its 11KV bus to its 33KV bus. The feeders in a subsystem model have seven numbers. The sixth feeder serves as a candidate feeder. Both HIF and non-impedance fault conditions were applied to this model to analyze the capacitance switching and non-linear loads for non-high impedance fault circumstances.

Fig. 1. System fescription.

A. Fault and Non-fault Signal Data

In this work, both kinds of distribution signals—fault and non-fault signal data—are taken into account. The non-fault signal data represent normal switching, load switching, and capacitance switching, while the fault signal data represents the

HIF [27]. The data set, which is obtained from various simulation cases taken into account and is shown in Table I, is used in the proposed fault and non-fault signal detection method [28].

TABLE I. VARIOUS SIMULATION HIF AND NON-HIF CASES

Event	Simulation conditions	Total cases
HIF	Resistance of the HIF model varied from 100 to 12k. The HIF model's DC voltage varied from 1kV to 11kV. Angle of origin of the fault at 0°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 90°. Phase angles of the source voltage are 0°, 30°, 45°, and 60°.	1500 (60x5x5)
Switching loads	Load level changes at 10 cases. Angle changes in a cycle of 0°, 30°, 45°, and 60°. Phase angles of the source voltage are 0°, 30°, 45°, and 60°.	250 (10x5x5)
Switching of nonlinear loads	NLL load level changes at 24 cases. Angle changes in a cycle of 0°, 30°, 45°, and 60°. Phase angles of the source voltage are 0°, 30°, 45°, and 60°.	600 (24x5x5)
Switching of capacitance	Switching a 1MVar on and off depending on the load. Angle changes in a cycle of 0°, 30°, 45°, and 60°. Phase angles of the source voltage are 0°, 30°, 45°, and 60°.	250 (5x2x5x5)

A total of 1500 HIF cases and 1100 non-HIF cases, such as linear load switching, Non-Linear Load (NLL) switching, and capacitor switching, were considered (Table I). The generated signal has 2600 sampling points and a fundamental frequency of 50Hz (10 cycles, 0.2s). Data have been produced in each fault (1500) and non-fault (1100) case using different parameters. Thus, a total of 2600 sample points of fault and non-fault signal data examples have been produced. However, when the signal is actually acquired from the actual system through sensors, additional distortion is always imposed on the signal. Signal-to-Noise Ratios (SNRs) of 20dB to 40dB are added to the fault and non-fault signal data set in order to bring the total number of data samples up to 10,400. The specifications of the data set used in this analysis are listed in Table II.

TABLE II. THE DATA SET

	Counting samples	Quantity of noise
Training Set	2600*4 = 10,400	20 db - 40 db
Validation set	10,400*0.01 = 104	20 db - 40 db
Test set	10,400*0.01 = 104	20 db - 40 db

B. The Convolution Layer

The main layer in CNN is the Convolution Layer (CL), in which low-level features are transformed into high-level features. In order to create features, a kernel is used with the convolution operator on the input. The following is the CL's output:

$$y = f(Wr * xi + br)$$

where y is the result of CL. The weight and bias of the r^{th} layer are w^r and b^r respectively, and the activation function is $f(x)$. It understands how a neuron becomes active and produces. The tanh function is not chosen in DL, but rather the rectified linear unit - activation functions.

$$f_{\text{ReLU}} = \max(0, y)$$

C. Pooling Layer

Usually, the CL is followed by a pooling layer. Its primary use is in down sampling. The pooling layer is used to decrease the dimension of the input and retrieve crucial information after the CL. It can lessen the effects of data volatility. Max pooling is used in this work because it performs better than average pooling for both fault and non-fault waveforms. The mathematical formula for max pooling is:

$$f(y) = \max_i (y_i)$$

D. BN Layer

The BN method is used for to speed up neural networks. It is used to normalize the input by altering and scaling the activations. Unlike the previous layers, it allows each network to learn independently. Additionally, compared to dropout, it efficiently reduces over fitting. The following formula can be used to normalize the input data batch x_i :

$$y_i = \gamma * \frac{x_i - \mu_x}{\sqrt{\epsilon + \sigma_x^2}} + \beta$$

where σ_x^2 represents the batch variance and μ_x represents the batch mean. γ and β provide the learned scale and shift parameters respectively, guaranteeing that the input data have the same distribution.

E. Completely Joined Layer

The learning parameter D is included in this layer, which is also known as a "dense layer." The output of the dense layer is calculated using the formula below:

$$y = f(x * D^r + b^r)$$

F. SoftMax Layer

The probability distribution of each output class with "n" outputs is computed by the softmax layer. Thus, the softmax layer predicts the class to which the input data belong. The probability distribution is calculated using the following equation:

$$P_i = \frac{e^{x_i}}{\sum e^{x_j}}, \quad j = 0,1,2, \dots \dots n$$

where the input is x_i . The sum of all probabilities will equal to 1 if the output of p is between 0 and 1. In this work, fault and non-fault classification is done using the softmax layer [29].

V. THE PROPOSED METHOD-DCNN ALGORITHM

Figure 2 shows the proposed DCNN model's structure, which consists of two completely connected dense layers at the end of three convolution layers with pooling layers layered on top.

Fig. 2. The proposed DCNN architecture.

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Assessment Metrics

The proposed method was evaluated with the following criteria:

- The confusion chart is employed to evaluate a model's capability for classification.
- Accuracy is calculated as (true positive + true negative)/ total test instances.
- The product of the true positive and true negative determines precision.
- Recall equals the product of true positives and false negatives.
- The F1 score is determined as:

$$(Precision + Recall) 2 \times Precision$$

B. Results and Discussion

As stated above, 10,400 samples have initially been created. One percent is utilized for validation, 1% for testing, and 98% of the total data set were used for training. In DL, the training process is often carried out using a small batch. In order to appropriately calculate the training time for various scenarios, the mini-batch size for all 3 DCNN cases is set at 64. A total of 100 epochs of validation loss were tracked. In order to avoid over fitting, the training method would be completed before the scheduled epochs, since the validation loss does not decrease continuously for 20 epochs. The final model is determined by whatever model performed best in the validation set. The suggested DCNN's entire architecture was coded in Python using a Tesla K80GPU in this study.

All models' accuracy and loss values during training are calculated using the DCNN with 4, 6, and 8 layers. Table III shows the 3 final models' variables, training period, number of epochs that have passed, accuracy level, and validation losses.

TABLE III. DCNN TRAINING MODEL PERFORMANCE

Model type	Epoch's duration (s)	Optimum validation losses	Maximum validation precision	Epochs
DCNN with 4 layers	32	0.0038	0.98	49
DCNN with 6 layers	46	0.0022	0.999	32
DCNN with 8 layers	72	0.003	0.996	36

Less training parameters and classification accuracy of 99.9% are produced by the 6-layer DCNN model. The confusion matrices for each of these DCNN models, HIF (600 samples) and non-HIF (440 samples), which were trained on a total of 1040 samples, are shown in Tables IV-VI. The DCNN with 6 layers correctly identified 600 HIF samples, with 0 samples being misclassified, yielding a 99.99% accuracy rate. A total of 592 HIF samples were accurately diagnosed by the 4-layer model, whereas 8 samples were incorrectly classified, giving it a classification accuracy of 98%. Also, 598 HIF instances were accurately diagnosed by the 8-layer DCNN model, whereas 2 samples were incorrectly classified, yielding a classification accuracy of 99.6%.

TABLE IV. DCNN6'S CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual event	Predicted	
	HIFs	NHIFs
HIFs	600	0
NHIFs	1	439

TABLE V. DCNN8'S CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual event	Predicted	
	HIFs	NHIFs
HIFs	598	2
NHIFs	2	438

TABLE VI. DCNN4'S CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual event	Predicted	
	HIFs	NHIFs
HIFs	592	8
NHIFs	12	428

Table VII displays the precision, recall, and F1 score performance of the 6-layer DCNN model. While the 4-layer and 8 layer DCNN models generated 98.66% and 99.6% precision respectively, the suggested 6-layer model delivers 100% precision. Similar to this, the F1 score for a DCNN with 6 layers is 99.9%, compared to 98.33% and 99.66% of the 4- and 8-layer models respectively. As a result, the proposed 6-layer DCNN model outperformed the competition in terms of the evaluation parameters. Also, the 6-layer DCNN method outperforms the other models when compared to noisy environments. This approach reduces the detection delay to 23.66ms, making real-time applications possible.

TABLE VII. PARAMETERS OF EVALUATION OF THE THREE MODELS

Actual Event	DCNN 4		
	Precision	Recall	F1 score
HIFs	0.98666667	0.9801325	0.9833887
Actual Event	DCNN 6		
	Precision	Recall	F1 score
HIFs	1	0.99833611	0.99917
Actual Event	DCNN 8		
	Precision	Recall	F1 score
HIFs	0.99666667	0.99666667	0.99667

C. Comparing the Computation Lengths

To get greater performance, the DCNNs may be run on GPU. The GPU processor has more overall units than the CPU processor. As a result, DCNN computations run relatively quickly on a GPU. Due to its simultaneous GPU calculation, DCNN has a significantly shorter computation time. Table VIII compares the computation times on the GPU and CPU for the DCNN models using 2600 and 10400 samples.

TABLE VIII. PROCESSOR EFFECT ON TRAINING DURATION

Processor	Time interval (s)	
	2600 examples are included	10400 examples are included
Tesla K80 GPU	6	24
Intel i7 processor, CPU	18	72

VI. CONCLUSION

In order to classify HIFs and non-HIFs, this study suggests the use of a 6-layer DCNN model. The study demonstrates a new method that processes signals very quickly, with low sampling rates and reduced computational and memory load. The suggested DCNN with 6 layers is compared with other models, namely the 4- and 8-layer DCNN models. The findings show that the proposed 6-layer DCNN model has a greater accuracy while requiring less training than the other models. The 6-layer DCNN model outperforms the other models in noisy environments, it has fewer parameters, and is more convoluted. Future research will use the DCNN model to take into account more system faults.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Lazkano, J. Ruiz, L. A. Leturiondo, and E. Aramendi, "High impedance arcing fault detector for three-wire power distribution networks," in *10th Mediterranean Electrotechnical Conference. Information Technology and Electrotechnology for the Mediterranean Countries. Proceedings. MeleCon 2000 (Cat. No.00CH37099)*, Lemesos, Cyprus, Dec. 2000, vol. 3, pp. 899-902 vol.3, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MELCON.2000.879677>.
- [2] N. Narasimhulu, D. V. Ashok Kumar, and M. V. Kumar, "Classification of high impedance fault using MWT and enhanced fuzzy logic controller in power system," in *Innovations in Power and Advanced Computing Technologies (i-PACT)*, Vellore, India, Apr. 2017, pp. 1-13, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPACT.2017.8244946>.
- [3] A.-R. Sedighi, M.-R. Haghifam, and O. P. Malik, "Soft computing applications in high impedance fault detection in distribution systems," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 76, no. 1, pp. 136-144, Sep. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epr.2005.05.004>.
- [4] A. Aljohani, "Centralized Fault Detection and Classification for Motor Power Distribution Centers Utilizing MLP-NN and Stockwell Transform," in *IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Europe*

- (ISGT-Europe), The Hague, Netherlands, Oct. 2020, pp. 222–226, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISGT-Europe47291.2020.9248886>.
- [5] K. Sekar and N. K. Mohanty, "Combined Mathematical Morphology and Data Mining Based High Impedance Fault Detection," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 117, pp. 417–423, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.05.161>.
- [6] K. Sekar and N. K. Mohanty, "A fuzzy rule base approach for High Impedance Fault detection in distribution system using Morphology Gradient filter," *Journal of King Saud University - Engineering Sciences*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 177–185, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksues.2018.12.001>.
- [7] M. V. Reddy and R. Sodhi, "A rule-based S-Transform and AdaBoost based approach for power quality assessment," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 134, pp. 66–79, May 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epr.2016.01.003>.
- [8] A. H. A. Bakar, M. S. Ali, C. Tan, H. Mokhlis, H. Arof, and H. A. Illias, "High impedance fault location in 11kV underground distribution systems using wavelet transforms," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 55, pp. 723–730, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2013.10.003>.
- [9] M. Mishra and P. K. Rout, "Detection and classification of micro-grid faults based on HHT and machine learning techniques," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 388–397, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-gtd.2017.0502>.
- [10] B. K. Chaitanya, A. Yadav, and M. Pazoki, "An Intelligent Detection of High-Impedance Faults for Distribution Lines Integrated With Distributed Generators," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 870–879, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSYST.2019.2911529>.
- [11] L. G. de Oliveira, M. de L. Filomeno, L. F. Colla, H. Vincent Poor, and M. V. Ribeiro, "Analysis of typical PLC pulses for sensing high-impedance faults based on time-domain reflectometry," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 135, Feb. 2022, Art. no. 107168, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2021.107168>.
- [12] S. Gautam and S. M. Brahma, "Detection of High Impedance Fault in Power Distribution Systems Using Mathematical Morphology," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 1226–1234, Feb. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2012.2215630>.
- [13] K. Rai, F. Hojatpanah, F. B. Ajaei, J. M. Guerrero, and K. Grolinger, "Deep learning for high-impedance fault detection and classification: transformer-CNN," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 34, no. 16, pp. 14067–14084, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-022-07219-z>.
- [14] D. Pylarinos and I. Pellas, "Investigation of an Insulator Flashover in an 150 kV OTL of the Power System of Crete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4851–4858, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3198>.
- [15] S. R. Samantaray, "Decision tree-initialised fuzzy rule-based approach for power quality events classification," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 538–551, Apr. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-gtd.2009.0508>.
- [16] S. Kavaskar and N. K. Mohanty, "Detection of High Impedance Fault in Distribution Networks," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5–13, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2018.04.006>.
- [17] S. Lavanya, S. Prabakaran, and N. Ashok Kumar, "Behavioral Dynamics of High Impedance Fault Under Different Line Parameters," *International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 370–374, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.37391/ijeer.100251>.
- [18] M. G. M. Zanjani, H. K. Karegar, H. A. Niaki, and M. G. M. Zanjani, "High Impedance Fault Detection of Distribution Network by Phasor Measurement Units," *Smart Grid and Renewable Energy*, vol. 4, pp. 297–305, Jun. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.4236/sgre.2013.43036>.
- [19] S. Lavanya, S. Prabakaran, and N. A. Kumar, "Literature Review: High Impedance Fault in Power System and Detection Techniques," *Mathematical Statistician and Engineering Applications*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 944–958, Jun. 2022.
- [20] K. Sekar, K. Kanagarathinam, S. Subramanian, E. Venugopal, and C. Udayakumar, "An Improved Power Quality Disturbance Detection Using Deep Learning Approach," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2022, 2022, Art. no. 7020979.
- [21] S. Lavanya, S. Prabakaran, and N. A. Kumar, "Analysis of High Impedance Fault using Discrete Wavelet Transform Technique," *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, vol. 70, no. 8, pp. 238–246, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V70I8P225>.
- [22] A. E. Emanuel, D. Cyganski, J. A. Orr, S. Shiller, and E. M. Gulachenski, "High impedance fault arcing on sandy soil in 15 kV distribution feeders: contributions to the evaluation of the low frequency spectrum," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 676–686, Apr. 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1109/61.53070>.
- [23] S. Andrews Zachariah, B. Satish Shenoy, J. Jayan, and K. D. Pai, "Experimental investigation on dynamic and static transverse behaviour of thin woven Carbon/Aramid hybrid laminates," *Journal of King Saud University - Engineering Sciences*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 273–281, May 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksues.2020.09.015>.
- [24] A. Tariq, K. L. Khatri, M. I. U. Haque, M. A. Raza, S. Ahmed, and M. Muzammil, "Investigation of the Effects of Distributed Generation on Protection Coordination in a Power System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7628–7634, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4338>.
- [25] N. Narasimhulu, D. V. Ashok Kumar, and M. Vijaya Kumar, "Detection and Classification of High Impedance Fault in Power Distribution System using Hybrid Technique," *Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers*, vol. 29, no. 8, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 2050118, <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218126620501182>.
- [26] A. Mahari and H. Seyedi, "High impedance fault protection in transmission lines using a WPT-based algorithm," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 67, pp. 537–545, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2014.12.022>.
- [27] C. J. Lee, J. B. Park, J. R. Shin, and Z. M. Radojevic, "A new two-terminal numerical algorithm for fault location, distance protection, and arcing fault recognition," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 1460–1462, Dec. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2006.876646>.
- [28] R. Eslami, S. H. H. Sadeghi, and H. A. Abyaneh, "A Probabilistic Approach for the Evaluation of Fault Detection Schemes in Microgrids," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 1967–1973, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1472>.
- [29] D. Khalil Ibrahim, E. S. T. Eldin, E. M. Aboul-Zahab, and S. M. Saleh, "Real time evaluation of DWT-based high impedance fault detection in EHV transmission," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 80, no. 8, pp. 907–914, Aug. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epr.2009.12.019>.

Smart Collection of Waste Bread in Algeria Using the Internet of Things

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Abstract—Algerians are among the largest consumers of bread throughout the year and produce large amounts of bread waste. As bread is made from imported wheat, these losses on currency are a heavy loss for the national economy. To minimize these losses, Algeria needs to encourage the recycling of stale bread to minimize the cost of importing soft wheat and valorize it for farmers. This paper presents a framework based on the Internet of Things (IoT) to monitor and collect waste bread from recycling bins. This system could assist Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Algeria in bread waste collection, by monitoring the level of filling of the outdoor waste bins. The proposed system's architecture used a Mega 2560 microcontroller, HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensors, and SIM 808/900 modules.

Keywords—waste bread; recycling; smart city; IoT; Arduino

I. INTRODUCTION

Algerian consumers are among the people who consume the most bread throughout the year. University restaurants, hospitals, and school canteens are considered the largest waste cells that affect daily bread consumption. The absence of consumption culture increases bread waste, causing problems for poultry farmers, livestock, and garbage management. The waste of bread made with imported wheat in foreign currency is a serious loss to the national economy [1]. Algeria should promote the recycling of stale bread to minimize these economic losses. The recycling process is based on several steps starting with the collection of waste through its sorting and processing to the marketing of the recycled products. The collecting operations of each country are carried out in different ways, according to their level of civism and industrialization. Waste collection in developed countries is performed in a selective way called "selective sorting", while this operation is performed manually in underdeveloped countries by people or employees while sorting the waste by nature according to the demand [2, 3].

Today, the world is witnessing an increasing use of the Internet of Things (IoT) which uses devices that collect massive amounts of data and attracts the interest of both academia and industry [4]. The enhanced capability of applications, cloud services, and databases to communicate

with IoT devices produces a vast number of new interconnections between current and new systems. IoT devices are expected to reduce the cost of waste collection using the information exchanged among bins, containers, and trucks [5]. This study aims to investigate the recycling and recovery of waste bread by reviewing IoT techniques for the smart collection of stale bread systems and proposes an efficient management method to improve the collection systems in the source area, which is the most important stage of waste management, and can lead to a reduction in the bill for importing soft wheat and animal food products.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Bread Waste Situation

The Algerian Ministry of Commerce revealed that during the period between April 13 and 24, 2021, only the first 12 days of Ramadan, 535 tons of bread (2,139,884 breads) equivalent to 45 tons/day (178,323 breads) were wasted at national level, with a financial value estimated at 20 million Algerian dinars [6]. Official statistics show that an average of 2.7 million breads are not consumed daily. The financial value of the wasted quantities was estimated by the Ministry of Commerce at 20 million Algerian dinars, which represents more than 1.5 million Algerian dinars per day. Table I presents the provinces that recorded the highest rate of waste bread.

TABLE I. HIGHEST RATES OF WASTE BREAD

No	Province	Quantity of breads(units)
1	Blida	321,924
2	Bechar	161,648
3	Tlemcen	150,696
4	Djelfa	139,364
5	Annaba	118,680
6	Tebessa	115,152
7	Oran	108,200

Moreover, Algeria imports large quantities of soft wheat to ensure the production of flour destined for bakeries. Table II illustrates a yearly account of soft wheat imports. On the other hand, there is the problem of covering the food needs of farms (bovine/ovine and poultry), whose numbers are large and their

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annual import bills for corn, soya, and are increasing. The collection and processing of stale bread can be a solution to this problem by using automatic recovery solutions and resulting in environmental protection and sustainable development. Some waste collection establishments sort bread from other waste to restore and sell it to cattle and poultry breeders.

TABLE II. COST OF IMPORTED SOFT WHEAT

Year	Quantity (tons)	Cost of imported soft wheat (billion \$)
2017	6,832,777	1.4
2018	7,179,399	1.6
2019	5,800,844	1.3

B. Methodological Approach

The rapid evolution of technology has led to the development of increasingly complex systems, capable of processing information flows of diverse nature and origin and whose access must remain nevertheless simple and fast [7]. The proposed system could assist Algerian SMEs in collecting waste bread by monitoring the fullness status of outdoor bins with a list of requirements. Several studies examined the domain of smart waste management (household/solid) using different materials and techniques [8-17]. In this context, this study adopted an appropriate approach to the specificity of the product, stale bread, the area, and the country. The solution framework is based on wireless sensor nodes connected to the intelligent bins manager with a monitoring station by sending the bins filling level status for analysis and control of waste. This solution involves the following features:

- **Optimal fill level setting:** This allows the user or system operator to specify the fill level they consider optimal. Exceeding this limit will result in notifications for collection.
- **Check bin status:** This allows a user to view at any time the fill level of a bin using a web application.
- **Notifications:** This feature allows the users to be notified whenever the fill level exceeds the specified optimum levels.
- **Reports:** This feature allows the system to generate reports when needed.

After successful installation and login, the user can request the system to display the status of a bin from a web application. This request should trigger actions to check the bin filling level and pass the values through an Arduino microcontroller to the user's device browser. The user must register and then log in to interact with the system. Using smart bins and IoT, data should be collected and presented in a meaningful way to waste managers, as described in the proposed conceptual IoT infrastructure model. Figure 1 shows the flowchart of the proposed approach after starting the system and connecting composites. The IoT infrastructure model works in the following manner:

1. Citizens fill the smart bins.
2. The filling height is measured with an ultrasonic sensor.

3. The height is transmitted to the cloud via SMS or WiFi or a hybrid system with a GSM module.
4. The server receives the data.
5. A notification for a transporter is sent.
6. The bin is emptied.
7. The transporter goes to the sorting and grouping center.
8. The bread is unloaded and the stock status is changed.
9. The stock status is transmitted to the system to notify recyclers.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed system.

Fig. 2. The smart bin.

An ultrasonic sensor, a GSM Module SIM808/SIM 900 MHz Quad-Band, and an Arduino UNO microcontroller should be installed on the upper part of the bin cover, as shown in Figure 2. The system would be active when the garbage is in a closed position and the ultrasonic sensor should detect any changes in the height of the garbage volume. The data of the garbage height are then processed by the Arduino Uno microcontroller Mega 2560 and then sent to a firebase real-time database using the HTTP protocol and the GPRS Network via

the GSM SIM808/SIM 900 module [18]. To enable wireless connectivity and sensing capabilities, a microcontroller was installed in each collection box. Figures 3 and 4 show the three main components. The ultrasonic sensor is capable of determining the level of the collection box. The Arduino board supplies power for the ultrasonic sensor and allows for a customized program to control the sensor and the Wi-Fi module. The ultrasonic sensor will then operate and scan for any changes in the level of the collection box.

Fig. 3. Arduino Uno (Mega 2560) connected with the HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor.

The Wi-Fi module board connects the Arduino board with the Wi-Fi network and the database server to store the measured waste level via the ultrasonic sensor.

Fig. 4. (a) Module SIM 808, (b) Module SIM 900.

Following the collection, the products are sent to a sorting facility where they would be sorted mechanically to optimize the operations of transformation. This operation can also be completed by manual sorting using a conveyor belt. Once the operation of sorting is finished, the waste is ready to be integrated into the transformation operation by factories that will transform it into ready-to-use materials.

Fig. 5. Transportation to the regional recycling center.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed system was designed to assist Algerian SMEs in collecting waste bread by monitoring the filling status of outdoor recycle bins. IoT devices are expected to reduce the cost of waste collection by using the information exchanged between bins, containers, and trucks. These devices enable automation and accelerate the identification of waste for processing. As there are no similar studies on using IoT for smart collection of stale bread, the proposed system was compared with studies on recycling other products. This study utilized the same communication technologies with [5, 6, 17] for solid and [10-16, 18] for household waste. The architecture design adopted a model that responds to:

- The specificity of the product: To avoid the high cost of the system as the main objective was to recycle at a lower cost.
- The specificity of the region and the lack of Internet connection in some collection sites: This was accomplished by a hybrid architecture using a SIM 808 reader for sending SMS and SIM 900 which supports GPRS internet connection.

The proposed architecture can be implemented in a metropolitan area. The main advantage of this system is that it is very independent and transparent. Instead of using GSM and GPRS modules, the server could directly send the messages and the hardcoded coordinates. This could reduce the working and maintenance cost of these embedded bins.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper discussed a smart collection system of waste bread in Algeria, proposing a solid waste monitoring system. A framework based on IoT and Arduino was presented for collecting waste bread from the bins to the recycling establishment. The system was designed to assist Algerian SMEs to collect waste bread by monitoring the fullness status of outdoor bins. This system's features are:

- It can monitor the fill level in a short time.
- It can notify the persons in charge simply and with good interactivity.
- It is a secure system with access restrictions.
- It can provide usage reports

The level of waste in each bin is monitored and transmitted to a central management platform and can be accessed remotely to check and perform the collection process in any web browser. In future work, the proposed architecture will be extended to other actions that could encourage and promote the collection of waste bread by integrating them into the system platform.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Hocine and L. Sebbache, "La Ressource Alimentaire Pain et ses Deshets a l' Aune de l'Intelligence Territoriale par 'Economie Sociale et Circulaire'. Cas d'el-Harrach Dans la Banliere est Algeroise," *Revue d'Economie & de Gestion*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 114–123, 2018.
- [2] K. Louisa, "Economic Advantages of the Recycling Business," *The Journal of Research and Scientific Studies*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 513–231, 2022.
- [3] M. Naghel, A. Farhi, and A. Redjem, "Household Waste Management Challenges: The Case of M'sila, Algeria," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8675–8682, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4925>.
- [4] S. Benkhaled, M. Hemam, M. Djeddar, and M. Maimour, "An Ontology – based Contextual Approach for Cross-domain Applications in Internet of Things," *Informatica*, vol. 46, no. 5, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.31449/inf.v46i5.3627>.
- [5] K. Pardini, J. J. P. C. Rodrigues, S. A. Kozlov, N. Kumar, and V. Furtado, "IoT-Based Solid Waste Management Solutions: A Survey," *Journal of Sensor and Actuator Networks*, vol. 8, no. 1, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jsan8010005>.
- [6] "Ministry of Trade Algeria." <https://www.commerce.gov.dz/en/>.
- [7] B. A. Youcef and B. Rachid, "A fast prototype for modeling IP cores using in SoC with UML Marte.," *Informatica*, vol. 45, no. 6, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.31449/inf.v45i6.3675>.
- [8] N. Radwan and S. A. Mangi, "Municipal Solid Waste Management Practices and Opportunities in Saudi Arabia," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4516–4519, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2870>.
- [9] A. Ablelhalim and B. Roukia, "For an integrated management of household and similar waste in the city of Bejaia: Outline of a coordination approach between the actors," *Architecture et Environnement de l'Enfant*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 25–39, 2021.
- [10] V. Pavan Sankeerth, V. Santosh Markandeya, E. Sri Ranga, and V. Bhavana, "Smart Waste Management System Using IoT," in *Inventive Computation Technologies*, Ghaziabad, India, 2020, pp. 661–668, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33846-6_71.
- [11] C. Wang, J. Qin, C. Qu, X. Ran, C. Liu, and B. Chen, "A smart municipal waste management system based on deep-learning and Internet of Things," *Waste Management*, vol. 135, pp. 20–29, Nov. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2021.08.028>.
- [12] M. Ashwin, A. S. Alqahtani, and A. Mubarakali, "Iot based intelligent route selection of wastage segregation for smart cities using solar energy," *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, vol. 46, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 101281, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101281>.
- [13] A. Suvarnamma and J. A. Pradeepkiran, "SmartBin system with waste tracking and sorting mechanism using IoT," *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, vol. 5, Dec. 2021, Art. no. 100348, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2021.100348>.
- [14] N. Abdullah, O. A. Alwesabi, and R. Abdullah, "IoT-Based Smart Waste Management System in a Smart City," in *Recent Trends in Data Science and Soft Computing*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 2019, pp. 364–371, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99007-1_35.
- [15] T. Faisal, M. Awawdeh, and A. Bashir, "Design and development of intelligent waste bin system with advertisement solution," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 940–949, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.11591/eei.v10i2.2753>.
- [16] A. Salehi-Amiri, N. Akbapour, M. Hajiaghahi-Keshteli, Y. Gajpal, and A. Jabbarzadeh, "Designing an effective two-stage, sustainable, and IoT based waste management system," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 157, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 112031, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.112031>.
- [17] M. Xue, W. Hu, L. Huanyu, and Y. Fu, "Beneficial Reuse of Municipal Solid Waste Incineration Bottom Slag in Civil Engineering," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8306–8310, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4693>.
- [18] K. D. Kang, H. Kang, I. M. S. K. Ilankoon, and C. Y. Chong, "Electronic waste collection systems using Internet of Things (IoT): Household electronic waste management in Malaysia," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 252, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 119801, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119801>.

Epenthesis: The Movement of the Urdu Alveolar-Fricative Sound into the Punjabi Palatal-Affricate Sound

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Abstract-Pakistan is a multilingual country where the Urdu language serves as lingua franca. Although Urdu is the national and official language of Pakistan, it bears the status of the second language (L2) in most of the regions due to the dominance of regional languages. The Punjabi language is the first language (L1) of the people of Punjab. This study intends to investigate the interlanguage influence and extralinguistic factors of phonological variants produced in the process of epenthesis of Punjabi palatal-affricate (/dʒ/) with the deletion of Urdu alveolar-fricative (/z/). The analysis of this study has been conducted using PRAAT software which proved that the native Punjabi speakers replace the /z/ sound with the /dʒ/ sound no matter if it occurs at the start, middle, or the end of a word. Moreover, this process of epenthesis is the result of the influence of the native language, i.e. Punjabi. The outcome of the analysis indicates that the gender and dwelling (urban or rural) of the participants have nothing to do with epenthesis. However, the education of the participants is the main reason for epenthesis.

Keywords-epenthesis; phonological variant; interlanguage influences; extralinguistic factors

I. INTRODUCTION

Being the national language of Pakistan, Urdu serves as lingua franca for all the regions of the country, where regional languages are spoken as the first language (L1), i.e. Punjabi in Punjab, Pashto in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and Sindhi in Sindh. The relationship of influence between Urdu and regional languages is reciprocal, as the medium of instructions at educational institutions of Pakistan is Urdu [1-3]. As far as Punjabi is concerned, it shares a lot of its diction with Urdu due to their cultural similarities. In other words, variants of various Urdu words are found in Punjabi. Since several words are the same in Urdu and Punjabi, the Punjabi speakers pronounce

these (Urdu origin) words with phonological variations due to the influence of their first language. Similar to Urdu and Punjabi, several other languages have influenced each other in many ways, e.g. phonological, orthographic, and accentual variations [4-7]. Therefore, many research works have been conducted to analyze the influence of one language on another.

Authors in [8] investigated the process of phonological variations and the way laterals have been developed in the last three generations of Punjabi-English bilinguals residing in the United Kingdom. The findings of the study conclude that the speakers of the third generation still have high phonetic distinctions among their Punjabi and English as compared to the first and second generation. Moreover, the accent of younger speakers (third generation) does not match with the native English speakers, although they have developed a unique accent which is similar to British Asian English. Authors in [9] analyzed prevocalic /r/ in the non-rhotic expression of English speakers of the UK through articulatory and acoustic data. The data obtained from 24 speakers show that the patterns of lingual variation of rhotic expression is similar to the non-rhotic expression of the English speakers. Moreover, the authors suggested that a specific lip posture of Anglo-English /r/ is different from /w/ due to their exposure of labiodental variants and the stream of air that maintains a contrast between /r/ and /w/.

Authors in [10] analyzed the cues which are important to contrast between Urdu and Hindi laryngeal stops. They argue that murmured and breathy voices are the key features to differentiate among the voiced aspirates in the process of sound production. In other words, the authors found that aspirated sound (breathy voice quality) is sufficient for the identification

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of voiced aspirates even if one of the other two key features (prevoicing and aspiration) is missing. Authors in [11] argue that the phonemic realization of /r/ in two Scottish towns is variable due to various linguistic and sociolinguistic factors [11]. Their findings show that the realization of /r/ bears a change from the alveolar tap to the approximant in one of the selected towns whereas the other town shows no variation and thus can be considered as linguistically orthodox. Moreover, the variation in the realization of the same phoneme /r/ largely depends upon the phonological environment of the area in which it is spoken.

It is evident from the existing literature that few studies draw the comparison of various linguistic and non-linguistic factors of Urdu and Punjabi. Therefore, the current research work analyzes the movement of the Urdu alveolar-fricative phoneme (/z/) into the Punjabi palatal-affricate phoneme (/dʒ/) using PRAAT software. Four different but mutual tokens of Urdu and Punjabi have been selected for this study to analyze the reciprocal influence of both languages. To ensure the phonological variations, samples have been collected on the basis of literacy, living style, and gender.

II. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the methodology for analyzing the movement of the Urdu alveolar-fricative into the Punjabi palatal-affricate has been provided in detail. Data collection is outlined in subsection A while the detail of the analysis process using PRAAT software is presented in subsection B.

A. Data Collection

To investigate interlanguage phonological variation through epenthesis of the Punjabi palatal-affricate phoneme (/dʒ/) with the deletion of the Urdu alveolar-fricative phoneme (/z/) semantic fields were made for the collection of data from the native Punjabi speakers. Eight Punjabi native speakers have been selected as sample for the purpose of analysis. Among the selected Punjabi native speakers, 4 were educated and 4 were uneducated. Data were recorded using voice recorder without telling the subjects so that the responses may be recorded in natural frequency. The subjects have been kept anonymous.

B. Analysis Process

The PRAAT is open-source software that has been widely used by the research community to perform speech analysis in various disciplines [12]. To perform the analysis, the PRAAT software converts the sound file into frames and calculates multiple pitch values within the frame length [13]. Therefore, PRAAT has been used to analyze the phonemic movement from alveolar-fricative to palatal-affricate. The key steps we took for the analysis process using PRAAT have been mentioned as follows:

- Step 1: Record the selected words for 4 seconds or longer.
- Step 2: Open the selected sound files in PRAAT and chose "Edit" from the main menu.
- Step 3: Select the stable part of the file from the sound editor and extract the stable part to focus on the targeted phonemes.

- Step 4: Activate the pitch, energy, and spectrum functions to complete voice analysis.
- Step 5: Repeat the above-mentioned steps until achieving satisfactory results to perform analysis as fair as possible.

In PRAAT, the length of the time interval is measured from the pitch value of a sound when the sound signal is higher than the average sound signal. The range of the pitch is defined between maximum and minimum values of the intensity of the sound signal.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation results of this study are discussed in this section. The analysis is conducted through different samples and analysis process using PRAAT. The samples include 8 different Punjabi native speakers, namely an educated adult male, an uneducated adult male, an educated adult female, an uneducated adult female, an uneducated rural male, an uneducated urban male, an educated rural male, and an educated urban male.

Fig. 1. Comparison of the pronunciation of the word "Zaleel" (dishonored): (a) educated male, (b) uneducated male.

The speech samples consist of 4 lexemes, i.e. Zaleel (dishonored), Namaz (prayer), Roza (observing fast), and Raza (name). Figures 1-4 illustrate the speech analysis of the selected lexemes with the chosen Punjabi native speakers. The speech analysis results of "Zaleel" and "Namaz" are presented in Figures 1-2. The comparison of the word "Zaleel" in terms of pronunciation by educated and uneducated males has been drawn in Figure 1.

Fig. 2. Comparison of the pronunciation of the word "Namaz" (prayer): (a) educated female, (b) uneducated female.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the pronunciation of the word "Roza" (observing fast): (a) uneducated rural male, (b) uneducated urban male.

Figure 2 shows the comparison of pronunciation of the word "Namaz" by educated and uneducated females. Figure 1(a) shows that the /z/ phoneme, at the initial position of the

word /zli:l/, has been pronounced by an educated male as alveolar-fricative /z/, whereas an uneducated male pronounced the same phoneme as palatal-affricate /dʒ/, as shown in Figure 1(b). On the other hand, Figure 2 shows the same phoneme at the ending position of the word "Namaz" which has been pronounced as alveolar-fricative /z/ by an educated female in Figure 2(a) whereas an uneducated female pronounced the same phoneme as palatal-affricate /dʒ/ in Figure 2(b).

Fig. 4. Comparison of the pronunciation of the word "Raza" (name): (a) educated rural male, (b) educated urban male.

Figures 3-4 present the speech analysis results of the words "Roza" and "Raza". Figure 3 reflects the comparison of the pronunciation of "Roza" between uneducated rural and uneducated urban males. Figure 3(a) shows that the /z/ phoneme, in the middle of the word /rɔ:za:/, has been pronounced as alveolar-fricative /z/ by an uneducated rural male. On the other hand, an uneducated urban male pronounces the same phoneme as palatal-affricate /dʒ/ as shown in Figure 3(b). Figure 4 showcases the pronunciation comparison of "Raza" between an educated rural male and an educated urban male. The phoneme /z/ is in the middle of the word /rza:/ and has been pronounced by both the participants as a palatal-affricate /z/.

Pitch is a fundamental acoustic feature for the analysis of the speech process. The pitch of the phoneme /z/ is higher than that of /dʒ/ as shown in Figure 1, although both are voiced phonemes. Similarly, phoneme /z/ has higher pitch than /dʒ/ as shown in Figure 2. The results indicate that the epenthesis of /dʒ/ at the place of /z/ depends on the premise of being educated or not. However, gender is not a decisive factor for this epenthesis. The pitch of the phoneme /dʒ/ in Figure 3(a)

and (b) remained almost unchanged, whereas the pitch of phoneme /z/ is higher in Figure 4(a) than (b). It can be deduced from the results that the urban or rural setting of the participants has nothing to do with the replacement of /z/ with /dʒ/, but the factor whether the participant is educated or not is the major reason for epenthesis. The educated participants are less likely to accept the influence of native Punjabi language, as the medium of instructions at educational institutions is Urdu. The spectrograms in Figures 1-4 show a very slight difference as alveolar-fricative and palatal-affricate are both voiced phonemes and create more vibration in vocal cords than the voiceless phonemes.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Epenthesis is a prominent feature of interlanguage variations. It has been observed from the analysis that the initial, middle, and final position of the Urdu alveolar-fricative phoneme (/z/) is always epenthesis by the Punjabi palatal-affricate phoneme (/dʒ/), a permanent feature of the phenomenon having only one variable of orthographic knowledge of Urdu language. This interlanguage influence of the second language has been developed in the educated native Punjabi speakers permanently. Therefore, they pronounce /z/, not /dʒ/, however, uneducated native Punjabi speakers pronounce it as /dʒ/ because they did not acquire the influence of Urdu.

In future work, we intend to extend our analysis to the influence of Punjabi language on English and Arabic using PRAAT and machine learning algorithms. The reciprocal influence of Punjabi and Urdu can be analyzed at phrase or sentence level. In this way, we plan to analyze the impact of the native language on the national language in terms of phonological variations along with syntactic variations.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Korn, "A grammar for Balochi: challenges of describing a language that maybe is not one," presented at the 2nd conference "Descriptive Grammars and Typology," Paris, France, Dec. 2021.
- [2] A. Amanat, A. Hussain, and M. U. Tariq, "Major Influencing Factors in the Learning of Saraiki, Punjabi, Urdu, and English Languages in the Punjab, Pakistan," *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 630–640, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.52567/pjsr.v3i4.323>.
- [3] H. R. Khan, M. A. Hasan, M. Kazmi, N. Fayyaz, H. Khalid, and S. A. Qazi, "A Holistic Approach to Urdu Language Word Recognition using Deep Neural Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7140–7145, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4143>.
- [4] Q. Hussain, M. Proctor, M. Harvey, and K. Demuth, "Punjabi (Lyallpuri variety)," *Journal of the International Phonetic Association*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 282–297, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002510031900021>.
- [5] L. Ping, X. Jing, B. Othman, F. Yuefei, Z. B. A. Kadir, and X. Ping, "An Intercultural Management Perspective of Foreign Student's Adaptation in Chinese Universities: A Case Study of China Three Gorges University," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 3971–3977, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2589>.
- [6] M. Rabiei and A. Gasparetto, "A Methodology for Recognition of Emotions Based on Speech Analysis, for Applications to Human-Robot Interaction. An Exploratory Study," *Paladyn, Journal of Behavioral Robotics*, vol. 5, no. 1, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.2478/pjbr-2014-0001>.
- [7] H. V. T. Chi, D. L. Anh, N. L. Thanh, and D. Dinh, "English-Vietnamese Cross-Lingual Paraphrase Identification Using MT-DNN," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7598–7604, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4300>.
- [8] S. Kirkham and J. Wormald, "Acoustic and articulatory variation in British Asian English liquids," in *Proceedings of the XVIII International Congress of Phonetic Sciences*, Jan. 2015, pp. 1–5.
- [9] H. King and E. Ferragne, "Loose lips and tongue tips: The central role of the /r/-typical labial gesture in Anglo-English," *Journal of Phonetics*, vol. 80, May 2020, Art. No. 100978, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2020.100978>.
- [10] J. Schertz and S. Khan, "Acoustic cues in production and perception of the four-way stop laryngeal contrast in Hindi and Urdu," *Journal of Phonetics*, vol. 81, Jul. 2020, Art. No. 100979, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2020.100979>.
- [11] T. Jauriberry, "Variation and change of middle-class /r/ in Standard Scottish English," *Lingua*, vol. 256, Jun. 2021, Art. No. 103059, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lingua.2021.103059>.
- [12] P. Boersma and D. Weenink, "Praat: doing Phonetics by Computer." <https://www.fon.hum.uva.nl/praat/> (accessed Sep. 13, 2022).
- [13] L. Zhang and J. Barnden, "Affect Sensing Using Linguistic, Semantic and Cognitive Cues in Multi-threaded Improvisational Dialogue," *Cognitive Computation*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 436–459, Dec. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12559-012-9170-3>.

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Classification of Macromolecules Based on Amino Acid Sequences Using Deep Learning

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Abstract-The classification of amino acids and their sequence analysis plays a vital role in life sciences and is a challenging task. Deep learning models have well-established frameworks for solving a broad spectrum of complex learning problems compared to traditional machine learning techniques. This article uses and compares state-of-the-art deep learning models like Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), and Gated Recurrent Units (GRU) to solve macromolecule classification problems using amino acid sequences. The CNN extracts features from amino acid sequences, which are treated as vectors with the use of word embedding. These vectors are fed to the above-mentioned models to train robust classifiers. The results show that word2vec as embedding combined with VGG-16 performs better than LSTM and GRU. The proposed approach gets an error rate of 1.5%.

Keywords- CNN; LSTM; amino acid; macromolecules

I. INTRODUCTION

The last decade has witnessed the great success of deep learning as it has brought revolutionary advances in many application domains including computer vision, natural language processing, and signal processing. The key idea behind deep learning is the consideration of feature learning and classification in the same network architecture, using back-propagation to update model parameters and learn discriminative feature representations. Notably, many novel deep learning methods have been proposed, which improve classification performance significantly [1-3]. Studying deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) in life sciences is essential for understanding organisms. Current sequencing technologies make it possible to read DNA sequences at a lower cost. DNA databases are increasing daily, and the power of modern computing is required. Classifying DNA sequences is a critical and essential task. Four major classes of organic macromolecules are always found in all life forms on Earth:

carbohydrates, lipids (or fats), proteins, and nucleic acids. The significant macromolecule classes are similar in that they are large polymers assembled from small repeating monomer subunits. Proteins are large, complex molecules that play many critical roles in the body. They are made up of hundreds or thousands of smaller units called amino acids, which are attached in long chains. Twenty different types of amino acids can be combined to make a protein. The sequence of amino acids determines each protein's unique 3-dimensional structure and specific function. The interaction of protein with protein and protein with DNA/RNA (ribonucleic acid) plays a pivotal role in protein function. Experimental detection of residues in protein-protein interaction surfaces must come from determining the structure of protein-protein, protein-DNA, and protein-RNA complexes. However, experimental determination of such complexes lags far behind the number of known protein sequences. Hence, there is a need to develop reliable computational methods for identifying protein-protein, protein-RNA, and protein-DNA interface residues. Identifying macromolecules and detecting specific amino acid residues that contribute to the strength of interactions is a fundamental problem with broad applications ranging from rational drug design to the analysis of metabolic and signal transduction networks.

This article aims to utilize deep learning models to classify the macro molecule types based on the amino acid sequence and residue count. We used state-of-the-art deep learning models like CNN [4], LSTM [5], GRU [6]. We used word embedding to represent the amino acid sequences as vectors. The CNN extracts features from amino acid sequences, which are treated as vectors. These vectors are then fed to the models mentioned above to train robust classifiers. Our results show that word2vec embedding combined with VGG-16 performs better than LSTM and GRU.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The revolution in machine learning, mainly deep learning [7-10], allowed the study and extraction of complex patterns from data and made the machine models more robust. For instance, authors in [7] proposed deep learning techniques to perform brand and logo recognition tasks using multiple modern CNN models. In [8], a CNN model was applied to handwritten character recognition and was compared to a standard handwritten digit recognition task. It was found that CNNs efficiently deal with the variability of 2D shapes and outperform the other techniques. A variable size replicated CNN in [9] gathers relevant input information and eliminates irrelevant variabilities. A CNN model was proposed in [10] for the study and investigation of the accuracy and efficiency of new image datasets via transfer learning. Authors in [11] targeted learning as an informative feature representation of protein sequence as the input of neural network models to obtain the final predicting output of the belonging protein family. Authors in [12] proposed a framework with a deep 1D CNN, which is robust in both fold recognition and the study of sequence-structure relationships to classify protein sequences. Authors in [13] developed a framework with a CNN that used the idea of translation to convert DNA sequences to word sequences for final classification. Likewise, recurrent neural networks have shown promising results in many machine learning tasks. For example, an LSTM-based end-to-end approach was proposed in [14] for sequence learning, where the model makes nominal assumptions on the sequence structure. Similarly, authors in [15] described that recurrent neural networks could perform better on a challenging machine translation task. In the current article, we aim to evaluate the deep learning techniques CNN, LSTM, and GRU for macromolecule classification. It is well established that these techniques work well on sequence-based tasks, even with long-term dependencies.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

We used the protein data bank dataset [21]. A DNA molecule consists of two long polynucleotide chains composed of 4 types of nucleotide subunits, called a DNA chain. These may be adenine (A), cytosine (C), guanine (G), or thymine (T). The dataset contains two files with a different number of entries. One file has 467304 entries with 5 columns (Table I). The other file contains protein meta-data, i.e. resolution, extraction method, experimental technique, etc. with 141401 entries and 14 columns. We merged the two files based on structure IDs. The pre-processing step is to drop all the entries with NaN value or if a label or sequence is missing. After removing the missing values, the sequence is checked for the removal of tags and numbers. Once the dataset is cleaned, the sequence is divided into tri-gram, each sequence now combining three character strings. For example, CGC GAA TTC GCG. The final block may not have all three, and we added 0 to make it an equal slice (padding). The final output contains two columns, one for sequence and one for the label. As discussed above, there are 432474 rows in the processed data with 4 labels. These are all unbalanced data, and this issue will be discussed below.

TABLE I. TYPES OF MACROMOLECULE PROTEINS

Type	Label	Data structure	Entries
Structure ID	structureid	Object	140250
Chain ID	chainid	Object	2837
Sequence	protein sequence	Object	104813
Residue count	No. of residues ATCG's	Integer	4737
Macromolecule type	Macromolecule type	Object	14

B. Biological Structures in the Dataset

The central dogma of life is that DNA makes RNA, RNA makes amino acids, and amino acids make proteins. DNA and RNA are made of four types of nucleotides (A, T, C, G). The nucleotide sequence is the combination of these nucleotides in a row. Three nucleotides combine to form a codon, building a block of amino acids. The amino acids then are combined to form proteins. To make a protein, at least 20 amino acids are necessary. Consider the following real example. ATT is a codon, which consists of three nucleotides. This codon represents amino acid (isoleucine) represented by the letter "I." TTT is another codon, i.e. another amino acid (phenylalanine) and is characterized by the letter "F." These "IF"s are combined with others to make proteins. The letters in the codon represent nucleotides, while the letters in the protein sequence represent amino acids. At least 20 amino-acids must be combined to make a functional protein. The maximum number depends on when a stop codon is met. Such a codon can be met after 20 or after 500 amino acids. The amino acid sequence determines the type of proteins.

IV. THE PROPOSED METHOD

Figure 1 shows the block diagram of the proposed system. This system can be broadly divided into 3 tasks. The first 2 are dataset processing and embedding. We have different choices in embedding, but word2vec [16], Fast-Text [17], and GloVe [18] are well-known embedding techniques in Natural Language Processing (NLP). These embedding techniques have been tested in different bioinformatics tasks with promising results. Another famous embedding method is one-hot vector. We used word2vec in this study. The final task is the CNN, in which the number of network layers must be determined. We also need to find hyper-parameters along with the model's size, height, and width. The output layer is a SoftMax layer used to classify the sequence. Classifying macromolecule types using sequences can be seen as a sequence classification problem. This is analogous to the sentence classification task in NLP. Thus, we apply a skip-gram analysis from NLP research to model our problem. There are various sequence models in the deep learning domain. We used LSTM, GRU, and 1D convolution for our problem. Recurrent neural networks, such as LSTM, are specifically designed to support input data sequences. Figure 2 shows the layout of the model. CNNs can learn the complex dynamics within the temporal ordering of input sequences and use internal memory to remember or use information across long input sequences. As it is crucial to any deep learning task, we applied data preprocessing before feeding them to our model. Preprocessing includes handling missing values and downsampling the dominant class to balance data distribution.

300 performs better, and we will keep this setting unless mentioned otherwise.

A. CNN Model Results

Figure 5 shows the validation and training loss over the 50 epochs with an embedding dimension of 50. We used an early stopping algorithm to save and use our best model. Training loss is 0.028, while validation loss is 0.034.

Fig. 5. Training and validation loss.

Fig. 6. Model training and validation accuracy.

Fig. 7. Confusion matrix for all classes.

Figure 6 shows the accuracy curve for the same setting, where the final training accuracy is 99.2% and the test accuracy

is 98.8%. The micro-average and macro-average are almost the same. To further dig out the details, we drew the confusion matrix of all four classes, as shown in Figure 7, where the accuracy of each class is nearly the same, as we can see from the diagonal color. Figure 8 shows the CNN model's Precision, Recall, and F1-Score. The model has precision of 0.98, 0.97, 0.98, and 1.00 for classes of DNA, Hybrid, RNA, and Protein respectively. Recall and F1-Score can also be easily observed in Figure 8.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
DNA	0.98	1.00	0.99	49
Hybrid	0.97	0.97	0.97	35
Protein	0.98	0.98	0.98	47
RNA	1.00	0.97	0.99	36
micro avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	167
macro avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	167
weighted avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	167

Fig. 8. Precision, Recall, and F1-Score.

B. Additional Simulations

One hundred estimators initialized Random Forest (RF) [22], showing 96.83% test accuracy for more than 90,000 test sequences. We tested the RF for balanced and unbalanced data, and the results were almost identical. Table II shows each class's Precision, Recall, and F1-Score. The results are not good enough compared to CNN, but RF is much faster and less expensive than CNNs. We are reporting these results to show that traditional machine learning algorithms also work better for some visual question answering times.

TABLE II. RANDOM FOREST RESULTS

Label	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Protein	0.96	0.99	0.97
DNA	0.90	0.80	0.85
RNA	0.93	0.69	0.79
Hybrid	0.94	0.88	0.91
Macro-avg.	0.93	.84	0.88
Weighted-avg	0.96	0.96	0.96

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT NETWORKS

Model	T. Acc.	T. Loss	Val-Acc.	Val-Loss
CNN	98.19%	0.0486	97.74%	0.0819
GRU	90.79%	0.2691	89.70%	0.2715
LSTM	95.12%	0.3982	95.14%	0.1962
CNN-GRU	94.85%	0.1509	92.74%	0.1962
RF	95.17%	0.4019	94.87%	0.4906
VGG16	99.11%	0.0288	98.10%	0.0297

The next step is to compare different state-of-the-art algorithms like LSTM, RF, and GRU with the proposed CNN. We used TensorFlow embedding in this case with 50-dimension vectors. In this case, the LSTM and GRU have the same network structure and use the same number of cells, i.e. 512. Table III shows the comparison of accuracy and loss across the different networks. The Table shows that VGG-16 [19] performs better with word2vec as embedding. For example, the training accuracy (T. Acc.) and the validation accuracy (Val. Acc.) for the VGG-16 are 99.11 and 98.10

respectively. Moreover, the training loss (T. Loss) and the validation loss (Val. Loss) for the VGG-16 are 0.0288 and 0.0297 respectively. The 7-layer CNN also performs better compared to LSTM and GRU. All CNNs are of one dimension. The other models' results can be easily read in Table III.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this article, we used NLP techniques to classify the protein sequences and very good results based on accuracy and precision were achieved. The CNN and CNN-FRU models have better performance than the other models. Although we didn't train the models for long epochs, we still obtained high accuracy with CNN. Moreover, the data are highly non-normalized. These models perform much better when the data are normalized. Future work includes classifying the data with more models.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep residual learning for image recognition," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, May 2016, pp. 770-778, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.90>.
- [2] C.-L. Liu, Hsaio W.-H., and Tu Y.-C., "Time series classification with multivariate convolutional neural network," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 66, no. 6, pp. 4788-4797, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2018.2864702>.
- [3] C. Szegedy, V. Vanhoucke, S. Ioffe, J. Shlens, and Z. Wojna, "Rethinking the Inception Architecture for Computer Vision," in *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 2818-2826, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.308>.
- [4] Y. LeCun and Y. Bengio, "Convolutional networks for images, speech, and time series," in *The handbook of brain theory and neural networks*, Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, 1998, pp. 255-258.
- [5] S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long Short-Term Memory," *Neural Computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735-1780, Nov. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735>.
- [6] J. Chung, C. Gulcehre, K. Cho, and Y. Bengio, "Empirical Evaluation of Gated Recurrent Neural Networks on Sequence Modeling." arXiv, Dec. 11, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1412.3555>.
- [7] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton, "ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 84-90, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3065386>.
- [8] Y. Lecun, L. Bottou, Y. Bengio, and P. Haffner, "Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 86, no. 11, pp. 2278-2324, Aug. 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1109/5.726791>.
- [9] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton, "Deep learning," *Nature*, vol. 521, no. 7553, pp. 436-444, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>.
- [10] M. Hussain, J. J. Bird, and D. R. Faria, "A Study on CNN Transfer Learning for Image Classification," in *Advances in Computational Intelligence Systems*, 2019, pp. 191-202, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-97982-3_16.
- [11] T. K. Lee and T. Nguyen, "Protein Family Classification with Neural Networks," [Online]. Available: <https://cs224d.stanford.edu/reports/LeeNguyen.pdf>.
- [12] J. Hou, B. Adhikari, and J. Cheng, "DeepSF: deep convolutional neural network for mapping protein sequences to folds," *Bioinformatics*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 1295-1303, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btx780>.
- [13] N. G. Nguyen *et al.*, "DNA Sequence Classification by Convolutional Neural Network," *Journal of Biomedical Science and Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 280-286, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jbise.2016.95021>.
- [14] I. Sutskever, O. Vinyals, and Q. V. Le, "Sequence to Sequence Learning with Neural Networks." arXiv, Dec. 14, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1409.3215>.
- [15] D. Bahdanau, K. Cho, and Y. Bengio, "Neural Machine Translation by Jointly Learning to Align and Translate." arXiv, May 19, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1409.0473>.
- [16] T. Mikolov, I. Sutskever, K. Chen, G. Corrado, and J. Dean, "Distributed representations of words and phrases and their compositionality," in *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems - Volume 2*, Red Hook, NY, USA, Sep. 2013, pp. 3111-3119.
- [17] A. Joulin, E. Grave, P. Bojanowski, M. Douze, H. Jégou, and T. Mikolov, "FastText.zip: Compressing text classification models." arXiv, Dec. 12, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1612.03651>.
- [18] J. Pennington, R. Socher, and C. Manning, "GloVe: Global Vectors for Word Representation," in *Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, Doha, Qatar, Jul. 2014, pp. 1532-1543, <https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/D14-1162>.
- [19] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, "Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition." arXiv, Apr. 10, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1409.1556>.
- [20] G. Huang, Y. Li, G. Pleiss, Z. Liu, J. E. Hopcroft, and K. Q. Weinberger, "Snapshot Ensembles: Train 1, get M for free." arXiv, Mar. 31, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1704.00109>.
- [21] R. P. D. Bank, "RCSB PDB: Homepage," *Protein Data Bank*. <https://www.rcsb.org/>.
- [22] L. Breiman, "Random Forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5-32, Oct. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>.

A Novel Model for Breast Cancer Detection and Classification

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Abstract-Breast cancer is a dreadful disease that affects women globally. The occurrences of masses in the breast region are the main cause of breast cancer development. It is important to detect breast cancer as early as possible as this might increase survival rate. The existing research methodologies have the problems of increased computation complexity and low detection accuracy. To overcome such problems, this paper proposes an efficient breast cancer detection and classification system based on mammogram images. Initially, the mammogram images are preprocessed so unwanted regions and noise are removed and the contrast of the images is enhanced using Homo Morphic Adaptive Histogram Equalization (HMAHE). Then, the breast boundaries are identified with the use of the canny edge detector. After that, the pectoral muscles present in the images are detected and removed using the Global Pixel Intensity-based Thresholding (GPIT) method. Then, the tumors are identified and segmented by the Centroid-based Region Growing Segmentation (CRGS) algorithm. Next, the tumors are segmented and clustered and feature extraction is carried out from the clustered tumors. After that, the necessary features are selected by using the Chaotic Function-based Black Widow Optimization Algorithm (CBWOA). The selected features are utilized by the Convolutional Squared Deviation Neural Network Classifier (CSDNN) which classifies the tumors into six different categories. The proposed model effectively detects and classifies breast tumors and its efficiency is experimentally proved by comparison with the existing techniques.

Keywords-classification; feature selection; Chaotic Function-based Black Widow Optimization Algorithm (CBWOA); Convolutional Squared Deviation Neural Network (CSDNN) classifier

I. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is one of the most challenging and fatal diseases worldwide. It is responsible for the loss of millions of lives every year [1]. The instances of growth of Breast Cancer (BC) amongst women in the age group of 30-40 years have increased significantly over the last few decades in India [2]. BC is one of the most frequent cancers in developed and developing countries [3]. BC starts when malignant lumps begin to grow from the breast cells [4]. Globally, BC is the second most common type of cancer and a major cause of human morbidity and mortality, disproportionately affecting women [5, 6].

However, according to [7], more than 30% of cancer cases will survive in the long term if they accept accurate early detection [7]. Therefore, early detection of BC is crucial for patients' health and treatment. Early detection relies on testing and examining the pre-presentation of any symptoms [8]. Any suspected breast lump or growth should be immediately checked by the appropriate medical professional, in addition to regular screening tests [9]. Mammography BC diagnostic methods include X-rays, CT scans, ultrasound imaging, etc. It is complicated for doctors to diagnose cancer based on mammogram images due to the complexity of premature BC, combined with the low brightness of mammogram images [10]. Thus, enhancing the detection efficiency via the CAD system of deep learning techniques is essential.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Authors in [11] developed an effective computer-aided diagnosis system for breast cancer. Feature weighting was employed because it boosted the classification performance more than feature subset selection. The results showed that the proposed wrapper method had a better ability to attain higher accuracy as compared to the existing techniques. The method had low specificity in breast cancer diagnosis. Authors in [12] explored an improved Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) model for the classification of breast masses into the normal or abnormal and benign or malignant categories. It utilized Lifting Wavelet Transform (LWT) to extract the features from the region of interest in mammogram images. Finally, classification was performed using a combination of an extreme learning machine and Moth Flame Optimization (MFO-ELM) technique. The recommended CAD model obtained better performance and also, achieved minimum computational time as compared to other existing models. Authors in [13] proposed Multi-Scale generalized Radial Basis Function (MSRBF) neural networks for image feature extraction, medical image analysis, and classification for breast cancer detection. Initially, the image data were rendered into a Multiple-Input-Single-Output (MISO) system. The Forward Regression Orthogonal Least Squares (FROLS) algorithm was used to solve the system as a model structure detection problem and found the output layer weights. The experimental results showed that the method reached classification accuracy above

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93% in the two mammography databases and 86.7% in BreakHis. However, the DCT method needs large processing power. Interested researchers in healthcare can also find interesting research on the automatic detection of breast cancer and biomedical images [14-27].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. The Proposed Model

BC which grows in the breast cells is a malignant tumor, which has the potential of spreading to other body parts. BC infects 2.1 million women every year and is the most common sort of cancer, according to the World Health Organization (WHO). Furthermore, amongst women, the highest number of cancer-associated deaths is associated with BC. In general, the causes for BC are not defined and an exact justification for the occurrence of BC in certain women over others has not been provided yet. Nevertheless, to specify the incidence of BC, there are some common facts about BC symptoms. Most of these symptoms do not appear in the early development stages. Therefore, the process of detecting cancer in its early stage is quite challenging. In order to identify the BC development in the earlier stages itself, a non-invasive methodology termed digital mammography is utilized. DBT along with breast masses or tumors can be seen at increased radiological densities, i.e. they are seen as white, on mammograms. Thus, owing to overlay with DBT, the identification of malignant breast masses becomes a complicated task. Thus, false positives, false negatives, and over-diagnosis are issues which affect mammography. Radiologists are aided with the usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI) via enhanced BCD utilizing mammography. In this paper, ground on the mammogram images, an effectual BCD system has been proposed by utilizing a CSDNN classifier. Analyzing the mammogram images by utilizing CSDNN and mining detection methodologies and classifying the tumor is the main aim of this work. Figure 1 presents the block diagram of the proposed model.

Fig.1. The general structure of the proposed model for breast cancer classification.

B. Preprocessing

Preprocessing is an important step for removing undesirable noise and irrelevant details and for improving the quality and information content of the original image. The proposed work begins with preprocessing which consists of two steps, i.e. removing unwanted regions and contrast enhancement and noise removal.

Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE) is an image processing technique that is used to enhance the contrast of images. AHE divides the image into distinct blocks and computes histogram equalization for each section. Thus, AHE computes many histograms, each corresponding to a distinct section of the image. It enhances the local contrast and definitions of edges in all distinct regions of the image. Hence, in order to improve the performance of the AHE algorithm, in this work, the Homo Morphic (HM) filtering is incorporated with the existing AHE algorithm. Initially, the input images are filtered by the HM filter. HM filtering is commonly used for correcting the non-uniform illumination in images. Moreover, it simultaneously normalizes the brightness across an image and increases contrast.

C. Breast Boundary Detection

After preprocessing, the pre-processed images $R_{pre(m)}$ are applied to Canny Edge Detector, which is a widely used edge detection algorithm to locate sharp intensity changes and find object boundaries in an image. The proposed work utilizes the Canny Edge Detector for detecting breast boundaries. It contains 5 steps called noise reduction, gradient calculations, non-maximum suppression, double threshold, and edge tracking.

D. Pectoral Detection and Removal

The output images from the Canny Edge Detector with the detected breast boundaries $R_{CED(m)}$ are applied to the Global Pixel Intensity-based Thresholding (GPIT) method for removing the pectoral muscles. If the pectoral muscles are present in the images, they may complicate the feature extraction process and result in false classification. To overcome this problem, the pectoral muscles are identified and removed with the GPIT method. The normal thresholding method has the drawback that the selected threshold should correspond to a valley of the histogram. This method does not work well with variable illumination. So, to overcome this drawback, the threshold value is calculated from the pixel intensity of an image. Here, the mean intensity value of all the pixels in the image is used as a global threshold. It can be computed as:

$$\delta_{th} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{(i,j) \in N} I_{R_{CED(m)}}(i,j) \quad (1)$$

where N is the total number of pixels, $I_{R_{pec_rem(m)}}(i,j)$ denotes the intensity of the pixel, and δ_{th} denotes the threshold value computed based on the mean value of the pixel intensity value.

E. Tumor Identification

After the pectoral muscles were removed, the images $R_{pec_rem(m)}$ are inputted to the Centroid-based Region Growing Segmentation (CRGS) algorithm for tumor segmentation in the breast. In general, a tumor occurs when cells divide and grow excessively in the body. Region growing is a simple and efficient approach to segment the objects from an image. The process of region growing is to map the individual pixel to a set of pixels representing distinct image

regions and to grow them until they cover the entire image. The existing region growing algorithm has a limitation, that is, to choose the appropriate seed points and region growing criteria. The random selection of these two factors directly affects the quality of image segmentation. To overcome this limitation, in this paper, the initial seed point is calculated by using the centroid of the maximum area covered by the image. This improvisation drastically increases the segmentation accuracy and overcomes the over and under segmentation issues.

F. Tumor Clustering

After segmentation, the images with the segmented regions $R_{seg(m)}$ are clustered by Divisive Similarity Clustering (DSC). Divisive clustering is a top-down clustering approach, which separates the number of objects successively into finer groupings. The DSC algorithm mostly uses Euclidean distance to calculate the distance between the data points. Although it is a common distance measure, Euclidean distance is not scale invariant which means that the computed distances might be varied and inaccurate. Moreover, the Euclidean distance is not suitable for a large amount of data so that the cosine similarity function is calculated, which provides a better similarity result than the Euclidean distance and achieves better clustering accuracy.

G. Feature Extraction

After clustering, the important features are extracted from the clustered benign L_{Ben} and malignant L_{Mal} regions. Feature extraction helps reducing the amount of redundant data from the data set. In the end, data reduction increases the speed of the learning process. In the proposed work, the important features such as Grey-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM), shape features, Local Tetra Pattern (LTrP), color intensity, and Gabor features are extracted.

- The GLCM method is a way of extracting second-order statistical texture features. The extracted texture features are autocorrelation, contrast, correlation, cluster shade, dissimilarity, energy, entropy, homogeneity, maximum probability, and difference variance.
- Shape features correspond to the physical structure or the geometric shapes of the objects present in the image.
- LTrP demonstrates the spatial structure of the local texture using the direction of the center pixel. It is the first-order derivative of the center pixel along the 0° and 90° directions.
- Gabor features extract local pieces of information which are then combined to recognize an object. From the response of the Gabor filter, the Gabor features are constructed at several orientations and frequencies.
- Color intensity represents the image from a different perspective. It represents the frequency distribution of color bins in an image. It counts similar pixels and stores them. These features extracted from images are then used for image recognition. The extracted features are denoted as:

$$\hat{h}_n = \{\hat{h}_1, \hat{h}_2, \hat{h}_3, \dots, \hat{h}_N\} \quad (2)$$

where \hat{h}_n denotes the number of the extracted features.

H. Feature Selection

After feature extraction, the important features are selected using the Chaotic Function-based Black Widow Optimization Algorithm (CBWOA). The BWO algorithm is a meta-heuristic algorithm that delivers fast convergence and avoids local optima. BWO is a good method to solve several types of optimization problems as it keeps the balance between the exploration phase and the exploitation phase. Its fundamental steps and flowchart are given in Figures 2-3. In the proposed model, the optimal features, which enhance the classification accuracy, are selected by utilizing the optimization algorithm.

```

Input: Extracted feature set  $\hat{h}_n$ 
Output: Selected features  $\hat{h}_{n(opt)}$ 

Begin
Initialize population  $\hat{h}_n$ , Cannibalism rate, mutation rate, maximum number of iteration  $t_{max}$ 
Evaluate fitness
Set  $t = 1$ 
While ( $t < \max\ iter$ )
  For  $i = 1$  to number of reproduction  $K$  //procreate and cannibalism
    Select the pair of parents using  $\hat{h}_n^{ch}(t+1) = \eta * \hat{h}_n^{ch}(t) * (1 - \hat{h}_n^{ch}(t))$ 
    Generate children using  $S_1, S_2$ 
    Destroy father and some children based on cannibalism rate
    Evaluate fitness value
    Store best individual
  End for
  Select number of individuals based on the mutation rate
  For  $i = 1$  to number of mutations  $l$  //Mutation
    Select a solution from new population
    Mutate selected individuals
    Evaluate fitness value
    Generate new population
  End for
  Update new population
End while
Return the selected features
End
    
```

Fig. 2. Pseudo-code of the proposed CBWOA.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the proposed CBWOA.

I. CSDNN Classification

The selected optimal features $\hat{h}_{n(opt)}$ are inputted to the Convolutional CSDNN classifier. A CNN is a multilayer neural

network that contains many hidden layers that perform two important functions, convolution and pooling. Generally, neural networks suffer from the weight initialization problem. In the traditional neural network, the weight value is randomly initialized which causes the classifier to produce a false classification. So, in the proposed classifier, the weight value is initialized based on the mean and variance of its input. The architecture of the proposed CSDNN is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Architecture of the proposed CSDNN.

1) Convolution Layer

The convolution layer performs the convolution operation between the input features and the weight values (kernels) which is then applied to the non-linear activation layer to return the rectified feature map. The weight updating of CSDNN is done by the mean and variance of the input values. It can be expressed as:

$$\mu_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{h}_{n(opt)} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (\hat{h}_{n(opt)} - \mu_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}})^2 \quad (4)$$

where $\mu_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}}$, $\sigma_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}}$ are the mean and variance of the input features, and N is the total number of features.

The progress of feature maps in the convolution layer is expressed in (5):

$$L_{Conv}^{fea(n)} = \Omega(\sum \hat{h}_{n(opt)} * \chi_{wt(\mu_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}}, \sigma_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}})}) + \Theta \quad (5)$$

where $L_{Conv}^{fea(n)}$ denotes the obtained feature map, Ω is the non-linear activation function, $\chi_{wt(\mu_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}}, \sigma_{\hat{h}_{n(opt)}})}$ denotes the weight values generated based on the mean and variance of the input, and Θ denotes the bias value for each feature map.

2) Pooling Layer

This layer reduces the size of the input feature map obtained after the convolution. For dimensionality reduction, the max-pooling function is used which detects the most dominating features for faster classification. Thus, the pooled feature map of the pooling layer is expressed as:

$$L_{pool}^{fea(n)} = \mathfrak{R}_{mp}(L_{Conv}^{fea(n)}) \quad (6)$$

where $L_{pool}^{fea(n)}$ denotes the pooled feature map and $\mathfrak{R}_{mp}(\bullet)$ denotes the max-pooling function.

3) Fully Connected Layer

After a number of convolution and pooling operations, the pooled output is flattened and is applied to the fully connected layer. The fully connected layer feeds the input to the SoftMax layer, which uses the softmax function to convert the input scores into a sum of output probabilities.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In order to examine the proposed system (Figure 2), numerous experiments were conducted to evaluate the performance of the proposed model and are presented in this section. The proposed breast cancer detection system is developed in the working platform of MATLAB. The dataset description is described in the next section. All chosen samples were first stored into major classes as benign, malignant, and normal classes and subsequently into sub classes.

A. Dataset Description

The performance of the proposed methodology is evaluated by using publicly available data. Sample images have been collected from [28]. The dimension of the input image is 1024x1024 pixels in ‘pgm’ format. The input mammogram images consist of dense tissue variations, breast density percentage, and breast density variations. These features are helpful to detect breast cancer. Thus, the dataset has 3 main classes: normal, benign (DCIS), malignant and their subclasses.

B. Pre-processing Performance Analysis

In this section, the proposed HMAHE’s performance is analogized with the prevailing Histogram Equalization (HE), Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE), along with Contrast Stretching (CS) techniques regarding Minimum Squared Error (MSE), Structure Similarity Index Measure (SSIM), Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR), and Variance Ratio values.

The ratio of the maximum possible power of an image to the power of corrupting noise, which affects the quality of its representation, is named PSNR. The PSNR performance of the proposed and other known methods is analyzed in Figure 5. Good image quality along with fewer errors introduced to the image is attained by achieving a high PSNR value. Accordingly, the PSNR value for the proposed methodology is 61.89734. The PSNR values for CLAHE, HE, and CS frameworks are 58.86085, 58.00242, and 58.37713 respectively, which are lower than that of the proposed technique, proving that the proposed system shows better performance.

C. Segmentation Performance Analysis

By analogizing specificity, accuracy, F-measure, and sensitivity with the outputs of prevailing Active Contour (AC), Watershed (WS), and Region Growing (RG) methodologies, the accuracy of the proposed CRGS segmentation model is determined.

Fig. 5. Performance estimation based on PSNR.

Fig. 6. Performance analysis based on sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and F-measure.

To estimate the performance of segmentation frameworks utilized to extract objects of interest from images, metrics like specificity, accuracy, F-measure, and sensitivity are important. The proposed and previous segmentation mechanisms' performance in terms of accuracy, F-measure, sensitivity, and specificity is depicted in Figure 6. The sensitivity and specificity values achieved by the proposed technique are 0.794568 and 0.998382. The previous systems have sensitivity and specificity of 0.525349 and 0.113123 for AC, 0.377702 and 0.988604 for RG, and 0.395193 and 0.947311 for WS. The accuracy and F-measure of the proposed system are 0.991286 and 0.846746, which are higher than the existing frameworks'. Therefore, it is concluded that the proposed model segments the objects from the images more effectively.

D. Clustering Performance Analysis

Clustering methods that have high accuracy and time efficiency are more efficient for discovering the required number of clusters. In this sub-section, the performance of the proposed DSC clustering method is evaluated based on the clustering accuracy. For performance evaluation, the proposed method is weighted against the existing Hierarchical Clustering (HC), Fuzzy C-Means (FCM), and K-Means clustering techniques. Table I shows the accuracy of the proposed and existing clustering techniques. The clustering accuracy achieved by the proposed method is 0.961111, whereas the existing methods gave lower accuracy of 0.694444 (HC), 0.544444 (FCM), and 0.627778 (K-Means), indicating that the proposed method has better performance. The graphical representation of the above discussion is shown in Figure 7.

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BASED ON CLUSTERING ACCURACY

Methods	Clustering accuracy
Proposed DSC	0.961111
HC	0.694444
FCM	0.544444
KMEANS	0.627778

Fig. 7. Performance analysis of the proposed and existing methods based on clustering accuracy.

E. Feature Selection Performance Analysis

The performance of the proposed CBWOA optimization method used for selecting the optimal features was evaluated by comparing the fitness level attained for the number of iterations, and computation time with the existing methods of Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO).

Fig. 8. Fitness vs. Iterations.

The convergence graph of fitness value vs. iteration number is shown in Figure 8. Compared to the existing methods, the fitness value achieved by the proposed method is higher for a varying number of iterations. The proposed method has a 0.957153 fitness value at a minimum of 5 iterations and a 0.988095 fitness value at a maximum of 50 iterations. In the same way, the existing methods have fitness values lower than the proposed method. It is concluded that the proposed method has higher optimal prediction nature than PSO and GA.

F. Classification Performance Analysis

Table II shows the performance of the proposed and existing classifiers with reference to some quality metrics such as sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, and F-measure. Sensitivity delivers the ability to label positive breast cancer cases as positive, whereas specificity indicates the ability to identify

negative breast cancer cases as negative. In order to get an accurate prediction, these values should be high. F-measure is a measure of the model's accuracy, which is calculated by using the precision and recall value.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF PROPOSED AND EXISTING CLASSIFIERS

Metrics	CSDNN	CNN	NN	ANFIS	SVM
Sensitivity	0.958333	0.325	0.566667	0.808333	0.575
Specificity	0.993056	0.8875	0.927778	0.968056	0.929167
Accuracy	0.988095	0.807143	0.87619	0.945238	0.878571
F-measure	0.958333	0.325	0.566667	0.808333	0.575

Fig. 9. ROC curve.

The ROC graph for estimating the performance of the proposed and existing classifiers is shown in Figure 9. An overview of true positives and false negatives is provided by the ROC graphs. The better performance is indicated by the classifiers that give curves closer to the top-left corner. The test is less accurate when the curve comes closer to the 45-degree diagonal of the ROC space. Accordingly, we can see that the proposed model is more accurate than the prevailing techniques.

V. DISCUSSION

The proposed method efficiently removes the unwanted regions from breast mammogram images, and outperforms existing works with their inefficient preprocessing functions. The proposed method uses an effective feature selection phase. The main contribution of the feature selection phase is to reduce the complications of the classifier. Thus, the classifier can classify the features with least resource consumption. Most of the existing methodologies have inadequate feature extraction and selection phase [29], drastically reducing their precision level. Furthermore, in the proposed work, a modified classifier is used, in which the optimal weight values are selected by the mean and variance of its input. In most of the existing works, the classifier deals with random weight values [30]. When compared to existing methodologies, the proposed work exhibits better accuracy rates. Moreover, the proposed work classifies the multiple types of breast cancer with less time and cost.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The main goal of the proposed model is to detect breast tumors and classify them according to the type of the detected tumor. In this framework, mammogram images are analyzed

and tumors are identified by CRGS methods. If the tumor is found in a mammogram image, then the type of tumor is identified with the CSDNN method. The performance of the proposed CRGS and CSDNN methods were compared with some traditional methods with respect to some evaluation metrics. The experimental results revealed that both CRGS and CSDNN methods achieve greater performance than the existing methods. The proposed CRGS method obtained an accuracy of 0.991286 whereas the proposed CSDNN method attained an accuracy of 0.988095. This performance analysis clearly states that the proposed model accurately detects and classifies breast tumors.

In the future, a more advanced classifier may be integrated to enhance the performance of the proposed model.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Ekici and H. Jawzal, "Breast cancer diagnosis using thermography and convolutional neural networks," *Medical Hypotheses*, vol. 137, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 109542, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mehy.2019.109542>.
- [2] D. Singh and A. K. Singh, "Role of image thermography in early breast cancer detection- Past, present and future," *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, vol. 183, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 105074, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2019.105074>.
- [3] M. Abdar and V. Makarenkov, "CWV-BANN-SVM ensemble learning classifier for an accurate diagnosis of breast cancer," *Measurement*, vol. 146, pp. 557–570, Nov. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2019.05.022>.
- [4] D. A. Omondigbe, S. Veeramani, and A. S. Sidhu, "Machine Learning Classification Techniques for Breast Cancer Diagnosis," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 495, Jun. 2019, Art. no. 012033, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/495/1/012033>.
- [5] P. Jasbi *et al.*, "Breast cancer detection using targeted plasma metabolomics," *Journal of Chromatography B*, vol. 1105, pp. 26–37, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2018.11.029>.
- [6] M. Swellam, R. F. K. Zahran, H. Abo El-Sadat Taha, N. El-Khazragy, and C. Abdel-Malak, "Role of some circulating MiRNAs on breast cancer diagnosis," *Archives of Physiology and Biochemistry*, vol. 125, no. 5, pp. 456–464, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13813455.2018.1482355>.
- [7] N. Liu, E.-S. Qi, M. Xu, B. Gao, and G.-Q. Liu, "A novel intelligent classification model for breast cancer diagnosis," *Information Processing & Management*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 609–623, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2018.10.014>.
- [8] M. M. Rahman, Y. Ghasemi, E. Suley, Y. Zhou, S. Wang, and J. Rogers, "Machine Learning Based Computer Aided Diagnosis of Breast Cancer Utilizing Anthropometric and Clinical Features," *IRBM*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 215–226, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irbm.2020.05.005>.
- [9] Ü. Budak, Z. Cömert, Z. N. Rashid, A. Şengür, and M. Çibuk, "Computer-aided diagnosis system combining FCN and Bi-LSTM model for efficient breast cancer detection from histopathological images," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 85, Dec. 2019, Art. no. 105765, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2019.105765>.
- [10] R. S. Patil and N. Biradar, "Automated mammogram breast cancer detection using the optimized combination of convolutional and recurrent neural network," *Evolutionary Intelligence*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1459–1474, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12065-020-00403-x>.
- [11] S. Dalwinder, S. Birmohan, and K. Manpreet, "Simultaneous feature weighting and parameter determination of Neural Networks using Ant Lion Optimization for the classification of breast cancer," *Biocybernetics and Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 337–351, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbe.2019.12.004>.
- [12] D. Muduli, R. Dash, and B. Majhi, "Automated breast cancer detection in digital mammograms: A moth flame optimization based ELM

- approach," *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, vol. 59, May 2020, Art. no. 101912, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2020.101912>.
- [13] C. Beltran-Perez, H.-L. Wei, and A. Rubio-Solis, "Generalized Multiscale RBF Networks and the DCT for Breast Cancer Detection," *International Journal of Automation and Computing*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 55–70, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11633-019-1210-y>.
- [14] T. A. Assegie, "An optimized K-Nearest Neighbor based breast cancer detection," *Journal of Robotics and Control (JRC)*, vol. 2, no. 3, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.18196/jrc.2363>.
- [15] H. Dhahri, E. Al Maghayreh, A. Mahmood, W. Elkilani, and M. Faisal Nagi, "Automated Breast Cancer Diagnosis Based on Machine Learning Algorithms," *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, vol. 2019, pp. 1–11, Nov. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4253641>.
- [16] H. N. Iqbal, A. B. Nassif, and I. Shahin, "Classifications of Breast Cancer Diagnosis using Machine Learning," *International Journal of Computers*, vol. 14, pp. 86–86, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.46300/9108.2020.14.13>.
- [17] S. Chaudhury *et al.*, "Effective Image Processing and Segmentation-Based Machine Learning Techniques for Diagnosis of Breast Cancer," *Computational and Mathematical Methods in Medicine*, vol. 2022, pp. 1–6, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/6841334>.
- [18] R. Chauhan, P. K. Vinod, and C. V. Jawahar, "Exploring Genetic-histologic Relationships in Breast Cancer." arXiv, Mar. 14, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2103.08082>.
- [19] A. Al-Gburi, N. Alwan, E. Al-Tameemi, and W. H. Al-Dabbagh, "Opportunistic Screening for Early Detection of Breast Cancer in Iraq," *International Medical Journal*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 28–32, Feb. 2021.
- [20] M. Monirujjaman Khan *et al.*, "Machine Learning Based Comparative Analysis for Breast Cancer Prediction," *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, vol. 2022, pp. 1–15, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/4365855>.
- [21] S. Sharma, R. Mehra, and S. Kumar, "Optimised CNN in conjunction with efficient pooling strategy for the multi-classification of breast cancer," *IET Image Processing*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 936–946, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1049/ipr2.12074>.
- [22] V. Chaurasia, M. Pandey, and S. Pal, "Prediction of Presence of Breast Cancer Disease in the Patient using Machine Learning Algorithms and SFS," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1099, no. 1, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 012003, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1099/1/012003>.
- [23] J. Quist, L. Taylor, J. Staaf, and A. Grigoriadis, "Random Forest Modelling of High-Dimensional Mixed-Type Data for Breast Cancer Classification," *Cancers*, vol. 13, no. 5, Feb. 2021, Art. no. 991, <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers13050991>.
- [24] A. B. S. Salamh and H. I. Akyüz, "A Novel Feature Extraction Descriptor for Face Recognition," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8033–8038, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4624>.
- [25] N. Kumar, A. Hashmi, M. Gupta, and A. Kundu, "Automatic Diagnosis of Covid-19 Related Pneumonia from CXR and CT-Scan Images," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 7993–7997, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4613>.
- [26] N. K. Al-Shammari *et al.*, "Cardiac Stroke Prediction Framework using Hybrid Optimization Algorithm under DNN," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7436–7441, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4277>.
- [27] A. Kehili, K. Dabbabi, and A. Cherif, "Early Detection of Parkinson's and Alzheimer's Diseases using the VOT_Mean Feature," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6912–6918, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4038>.
- [28] "MIAS Mammography," *Kaggle*. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/kmader/mias-mammography>.
- [29] M. Gupta, N. Kumar, N. Gupta, and A. Zaguia, "Fusion of Multi-Modality Biomedical Images Using Deep Neural Networks." Nov. 11, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-983420/v1>.
- [30] N. Kumar, N. Narayan Das, D. Gupta, K. Gupta, and J. Bindra, "Efficient Automated Disease Diagnosis Using Machine Learning Models," *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, vol. 2021, pp. 1–13, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/9983652>.

A Study of One-dimensional Weak Shock Propagation Under the Action of Axial and Azimuthal Magnetic Field: An Analytical Approach

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Abstract-The present paper presents an analytical study of the one-dimensional weak shock wave problem in a perfect gas under the action of a generalized magnetic field subjected to weak shock jump conditions (R-H conditions). The magnetic field is considered axial and azimuthal in cylindrically symmetric configuration. By considering a straightforward analytical approach, an explicit solution exhibiting time-space dependency for gas-dynamical flow parameters and total energy (generated during the propagation of the weak shock from the center of the explosion) has been obtained under the significant influence of generalized magnetic fields (axial and azimuthal) and the results are analyzed graphically. From the outcome, it is worth noticing that for an increasing value of Mach number under the generalized magnetic field, the decay process of physical parameters (density, pressure, and magnetic pressure) is a bit slower, whereas the velocity profile and total energy increase rapidly with respect to time. Moreover, for increasing values of Shock-Cowling number the total energy grows rapidly with respect to time.

Keywords-weak shock waves; analytical solution; Rankine-Hugoniot conditions; magnetogasdynamics

I. INTRODUCTION

In general, the complex physical phenomena occurring in nature are non-linear and are described by mathematical models in the form of Non-linear Partial Differential Equations (NPDEs). During the last few decades such nonlinear mathematical models are getting a vital role in the fields of natural, engineering, and medical sciences such as plasma physics, solid-state physics, fluid mechanics, optical fibers, geophysics, biomechanics, etc. and many efforts have been made for confronting the exact and numerical solutions of such physical systems [1-6]. Due to the high complexity, finding the

exact (closed form) solution of such realistic models is thus a challenging and rigorous task because it comprises many physical and natural intricacies and only in certain cases can we explicitly unravel the solutions.

Mathematically, the nonlinear wave (shock wave) propagation phenomenon is formulated as a quasilinear hyperbolic system of partial differential equations. The shock wave occurs in gaseous media by a dynamical mechanism in which an immense amount of energy is abruptly released over a small interval of time during the propagation of wave discontinuity, e.g. prolonged rapid electrical discharges in the air such as thunder-strokes, explosions of long thin wires, etc. It is well known that shock processes usually occur due to the high temperature in which the gas ionizes, so the effect of the magnetic field also becomes significant. The understanding of the influence of the magnetic field on wave propagation phenomenon and the resulting flow field is of great importance as it involves many applications in the field of space science research, atmospheric sciences, nuclear sciences, etc. The study of shock wave propagation under the action of a magnetic field for a perfect gas are important for the interpretation of the phenomena encountered in astrophysics from the theoretical and experimental points of view, as the ideal magnetogasdynamic flow involves a plasma in which the diffusion effects are negligible.

Many researchers [7-11] have worked to better understand the magnetic field effects on the dynamics of shock waves. In keeping with [7-11], authors in [12] discussed the self-similar solution of the blast wave problem with identical geometry under constant axial current. Authors in [13] studied one dimensional steady flow of a perfect gas and reported the first

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complete explicit shock solution in the aligned field magnetogasdynamics. In [14], the authors considered spherical shock propagation in a magnetized medium and found that the model has some limitations on real flare produced shocks, taking into account isothermal flow conditions in planar and identical geometry. Authors in [15] reported the existence of self-similar solutions for blast waves and observed that the magnetic field effects play a significant role in the theory of blast waves. Authors in [16] used the asymptotic approach and analyzed the decay behavior of sawtooth profile for planar and cylindrical gas dynamical flows headed by weak wave front under the action of axial magnetic field. Authors in [17] studied the evolution and formation of the 1-dimensional magneto-hydrodynamic shock wave in the approximation of the low plasma-to-magnetic pressure ratio and obtained an analytical expression for shock formation. A detailed theoretical, experimental, and computational review on magneto aerodynamics was presented in [18] and the features of shock structure in the presence of magnetic field were discussed.

Within the above mentioned framework, several investigations have been recently performed for finding the analytical solution of ideal MHD equations. Authors in [19] obtained a particular solution of strong discontinuity waves in ideal magneto-gasdynamic flow via lie group transformation analysis and studied the effect of the applied magnetic field on the evolutionary behavior of reflected and transmitted waves which arises when a magnet-acoustic wave collides with a shock. The methodology proposed in [20, 21] gave the precise solution of the shock wave problem involving strong discontinuities in magneto-gas-dynamic regime. The convergence of the shock wave in the cylindrical symmetry was investigated in [22] and rendered analytical asymptotic results on the shock trajectory for small radii. By using the method of generalized wavefront expansion, authors in [23] derived nonlinear coupled evolution equations and assessed how the magnetic field, either axial or azimuthal, influences the formation of weak shock waves in an ideal gas. Authors in [24] presented the numerical description of the flow field in magnetogasdynamics and analyzed that the presence of magnetic field suppresses the instabilities in the point explosion problem. Authors in [25] reported an approximate analytical solution for propagation of cylindrical shock waves in isothermal flow conditions with azimuthal magnetic field. Authors in [26] initiated the analysis of weak shock propagation in a simplified van der Waals gas influenced by thermal radiation under optically thin limit. Authors in [27] studied the strong explosion problem in perfect gasdynamics with magnetic field effects using power series solution and recovered the result described by [28] in the absence of magnetic field. Recently, authors in [29] scrutinized the point explosion problem in perfect magneto-gasdynamic flow on stellar surface and reported an explicit exact solution of fluid characteristics (density, velocity, and pressure) which expounds time-position dependence. Authors in [30] highlighted the impact of dust-laden particles on the evolution of magnetic shock waves and analyzed the behavior of half N-wave. Authors in [31, 32] solved the Riemann problem for the hyperbolic system of conservation laws and examined the study of discontinuous solutions in non-ideal material media.

In this article, our goal is to construct a closed-form solution (which exhibits a space-time dependence) to the weak shock wave problem in an ideal gas for cylindrically symmetric flow under the influence of axial and azimuthal magnetic fields (modelled in the form of Shock-Cowling number, $C_0 = 2h_0/\rho_0 G^2$) and to investigate how the magnetic field and the Mach number affect the thermodynamic flow characteristics. It has been assumed that the mass density distribution obeys a power law of the radial distance from the centre of explosion. Furthermore, we derived an analytical expression for the total energy of the weak shock wave, influenced by the magnetic field. The way the behavior of physical parameters such as density, velocity, pressure, magnetic pressure and energy is affected by the Mach number and the presence of magnetic field, is also assessed.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE PROBLEM

To outline the approach, we consider a basic set of governing conservation equations, consisting one-dimensional compressible cylindrically symmetric unsteady adiabatic motion of a perfect gas under the influence of magnetic field in which viscous stress is negligible. Mathematically, this system of Euler's equations corresponding to mass balance, momentum balance, energy and magnetic pressure balance in non-conservative form is given by [33-35]:

$$\rho_t + u\rho_x + \rho u_x + (\rho u/x) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\rho(u_t + uu_x) + p_x + h_x + (2jh/x) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$p_t + up_x + \rho c^2\{u_x + (u/x)\} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$h_t + uh_x + 2h\{u_x + \{(1-j)u/x\}\} = 0 \quad (4)$$

In the above equations, $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $t > 0$ stand for the spatial and time variables, $\rho(x, t)$ refers to the mass density, $p(x, t)$ is the pressure, $u(x, t)$ is the flow velocity, h the magnetic pressure defined as $h = \mu H^2/2$ with μ as the magnetic permeability, and H is the transverse magnetic field. The entity c accounts for the equilibrium speed of sound and is defined as $c^2 = \Gamma p/\rho$ where $\Gamma = c_p/c_v$ ($1 < \Gamma < 2$) is the adiabatic exponent and thermodynamic constants c_p and c_v denote the specific heat of the gas at constant pressure and at constant volume respectively. Here and hereafter nonnumeric subscripts with respect to physical characteristics indicate partial differentiation unless stated otherwise. The constant $j = 0$ exhibits the axial magnetic field and $j = 1$ the azimuthal magnetic field. For motion in ideal gasdynamic medium, the governing dynamical equations (1)-(4) are supplemented with the following constitutive relation (or equation of state):

$$p = \rho R T \quad (5)$$

where R is the specific gas constant and T is the temperature.

Let $\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}(t)$ be the shock-location at time t moving with the shock speed $\mathcal{G} = \frac{d\mathcal{R}}{dt}$ into the medium immediately ahead of the shock given by $u_0 = 0$, $p_0 = \text{constant}$, $\rho_0 = \rho_0(x)$ and $h_0 = h_0(x)$, where the thermodynamic profiles with subscript 0 express the values in the pre-shock region. It has been also assumed here that weak shock propagation obeys a power

law $\rho_0 = \rho_c \mathcal{R}^J$, in which the density of the pre-shock (undisturbed) region ρ_0 varies with respect to the shock radius. Here, ρ_c is a dimensional constant and J a constant. The value of constant J is to be determined in the ongoing analysis.

It is well known that the energy produced during the propagation of a weak shock wave in any gas medium is equal to the sum of the kinetic energy and internal energy of the gas and is a constant. The balance equation for the total energy E_T in an ideal magneto-gas-dynamic flow is given by:

$$E_T = \int_0^{\mathcal{R}} \left[\frac{1}{2} u^2 + \frac{1}{(\Gamma-1)} \left(\frac{p}{\rho} - \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} \right) + \left(\frac{h}{\rho} - \frac{h_0}{\rho_0} \right) \right] \rho x dx \quad (6)$$

In view of the relation $\int_0^{\mathcal{R}} \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} x dx = \frac{\mathcal{R}^2}{2}$ obtained from Lagrangian equation of continuity, (6) yields the following expression for total energy:

$$E_T = \int_0^{\mathcal{R}} \left[\frac{\rho u^2}{2} + \frac{p}{(\Gamma-1)} + h \right] x dx - \frac{p_0 \mathcal{R}^2}{2(\Gamma-1)} - \frac{h_0 \mathcal{R}^2}{2} \quad (7)$$

III. FORMULATION OF SHOCK-JUMP CONDITIONS

At the outset, for the formulation of shock-jump conditions, we recast the fundamental set of balance equations (1) – (4) in conservation form which yields:

$$\rho_t + (\rho u)_x = -(\rho u/x) \quad (8)$$

$$(\rho u)_t + (\rho u^2 + p + h)_x = -(\rho u^2/x) - (2jh/x) \quad (9)$$

$$\left(\frac{\rho u^2}{2} + \frac{p+(\Gamma-1)h}{(\Gamma-1)} \right)_t + \left(\frac{\Gamma p u}{(\Gamma-1)} + \frac{\rho u^3 + 4uh}{2} \right)_x = \frac{\Gamma p u}{(1-\Gamma)x} - \frac{\rho u^3 + 4hu}{2x} \quad (10)$$

$$\left(h^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)_t + \left(u h^{\frac{1}{2}} \right)_x = \left\{ h^{\frac{1}{2}}(j-1)u/x \right\} \quad (11)$$

The Rankine-Hugoniot conditions across the shock front that connects the flow ahead and behind the shock waves can be derived from (8)-(11) and are given by:

$$\rho u - \rho_0 u_0 = \mathcal{G}(\rho - \rho_0) \quad (12)$$

$$(\rho u^2 + p + h) - (\rho_0 u_0^2 + p_0 + h_0) = \mathcal{G}(\rho u - \rho_0 u_0) \quad (13)$$

$$\left(\frac{\Gamma p u}{\Gamma-1} + \frac{\rho u^3 + 4uh}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{\Gamma p_0 u_0}{\Gamma-1} + \frac{\rho_0 u_0^3 + 4u_0 h_0}{2} \right) = \mathcal{G} \left[\left(\frac{\rho u^2}{2} + \frac{p+h(\Gamma-1)}{(\Gamma-1)} \right) - \left(\frac{\rho_0 u_0^2}{2} + \frac{p_0+h_0(\Gamma-1)}{(\Gamma-1)} \right) \right] \quad (14)$$

$$\left(u h^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) - \left(u_0 h_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) = \mathcal{G} \left(h^{\frac{1}{2}} - h_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (15)$$

Substituting the values of flow profiles from (12), (13), and (15) in (14) yields the following cubic equation in terms of density profile $\rho(x, t)$:

$$(\Gamma - 2)C_0 \mathcal{G}^2 \rho^3 + \{ (2p_0 + \rho_0 C_0 \mathcal{G}^2) + p_0(\Gamma - 1)M^2 \} \Gamma \rho_0 \rho - \Gamma(\Gamma + 1)p_0 \rho_0^2 M^2 = 0 \quad (16)$$

where $M = \mathcal{G}/c_0$ represents the Mach number with $c_0 = (\Gamma p_0/\rho_0)^{1/2}$ and $C_0 = 2h_0/\rho_0 \mathcal{G}^2$ denotes the Shock-Cowling number.

On solving the cubic equation (16), one obtains the values of the thermo-dynamical characteristics u , p , and h in terms of

the density parameter ρ . Thus, (16) along with (12), (13), and (15) allow us to obtain the Rankine-Hugoniot jump conditions as follows:

$$\rho = \frac{\Gamma+1}{\Gamma-1} \left\{ 1 + \frac{2}{(\Gamma-1)M^2} \right\}^{-1} \rho_0 \quad (17)$$

$$u = \frac{2}{\Gamma+1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{M^2} \right) \mathcal{G} \quad (18)$$

$$p = \left[\frac{2 \left\{ 1 - \frac{\Gamma-1}{2\Gamma M^2} \right\}}{\Gamma+1} + \frac{C_0 \left\{ \left(\Gamma-1 + \frac{2}{M^2} \right)^2 - (\Gamma+1)^2 \right\}}{2 \left\{ \Gamma-1 + \frac{2}{M^2} \right\}^2} \right] \rho_0 \mathcal{G}^2 \quad (19)$$

$$h = \frac{C_0(\Gamma+1)^2}{2 \left\{ \Gamma-1 + \frac{2}{M^2} \right\}^2} \rho_0 \mathcal{G}^2 \quad (20)$$

IV. DERIVATION OF THE ANALYTICAL SOLUTION TO THE WEAK SHOCK WAVE PROBLEM

In this section we shall derive an exact solution of compressible Eulerian equations (1)-(4) governing the one-dimensional unsteady propagation of weak shock waves in generalized magnetogasdynamics by using an analytical approach proposed in [6]. In order to find an exact solution, subject to the Rankine-Hugoniot's ratios (17)-(20), we establish an expression immediately behind the shock front for the physical characteristics of pressure and magnetic pressure of the flow, in terms of the other thermo-dynamical variables, density and flow velocity, given as:

$$p = \frac{4(\Gamma-1)^2 \left\{ 1 - \frac{\Gamma-1}{2\Gamma M^2} \right\} + C_0(\Gamma+1) \left[(\Gamma-1)^2 - (\Gamma+1)^2 \left\{ 1 + \frac{2}{(\Gamma-1)M^2} \right\}^{-2} \right]}{8(\Gamma-1) \left(1 - \frac{1}{M^2} \right)^2 \left\{ 1 + \frac{2}{(\Gamma-1)M^2} \right\}^{-1}} \rho u^2 \quad (21)$$

$$h = \frac{C_0(\Gamma+1)^3 \left\{ 1 + \frac{2}{(\Gamma-1)M^2} \right\}^{-1}}{8(\Gamma-1) \left(1 - \frac{1}{M^2} \right)^2} \rho u^2 \quad (22)$$

An inspection of (21) and (22) leads the Eulerian nonlinear system (2)-(4) to the following form:

$$u_t + \frac{uu_x}{(1+\mathcal{F})^{-1}} - \frac{u\rho_t}{\rho\mathcal{F}^{-1}} + \frac{u^2}{x} \left[\frac{2jC_0(\Gamma-1+\frac{2}{M^2})^{-1}}{8(\Gamma+1)^{-3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{M^2} \right)^2} - \mathcal{F} \right] = 0 \quad (23)$$

where $\mathcal{F} = \frac{4 \left\{ 1 - \frac{(\Gamma-1)}{2\Gamma} \frac{1}{M^2} \right\} + C_0(\Gamma+1)}{8 \left\{ \Gamma-1 + \frac{2}{M^2} \right\}^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{M^2} \right)^2}$ and:

$$u_t + uu_x + \frac{(\Gamma-1)}{2} u \left(u_x + \frac{u}{x} \right) = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$u_t + uu_x + \frac{u}{2} \left[u_x + \frac{(1-2j)u}{x} \right] = 0 \quad (25)$$

Plugging (23) and (24) and performing some algebraic manipulations, we get the resulting equation as:

$$\mathcal{S}(t) = \rho u^{(2-\mathcal{L})} (x)^{\mathcal{M}-\mathcal{L}} \quad (26)$$

where $\mathcal{S}(t)$ denotes the single function of time and the values of the constants \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{M} are given as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{(\Gamma-1)}{2\mathcal{F}} \text{ and } \mathcal{M} = 2j \frac{C_0(\Gamma+1)^3 \left\{ 1 + \frac{2}{(\Gamma-1)M^2} \right\}^{-1}}{8(\Gamma-1) \left(1 - \frac{1}{M^2} \right)^2 \mathcal{F}}$$

Using (26) and after some analytical steps, the mass-balance equation (1) of the compressible Euler system is eventually recast in the following form:

$$\frac{(2-\mathcal{L})}{u} u_t + (1-\mathcal{L})u_x - (\mathcal{L}-\mathcal{M}+1)\frac{u}{x} - \frac{1}{s} \frac{ds}{dt} = 0 \quad (27)$$

On solving (24) and (27) we have:

$$u = \frac{1}{[\Gamma\mathcal{M}+2(\mathcal{L}+\Gamma)]s} \frac{dx}{dt} \quad (28)$$

By substituting the value of flow velocity from (28) in (27) and after simplification we have:

$$S(t) = S_0(t)^{-\mathcal{W}} \quad (29)$$

where $\mathcal{W} = \frac{2(\mathcal{L}+\Gamma)-\mathcal{L}\Gamma-\mathcal{M}}{\Gamma}$ and S_0 is an arbitrary constant.

On using the Rankine-Hugoniot jump boundary conditions (17) and (18), we obtain explicit expressions for the radius of shock front \mathcal{R} and constant \mathcal{J} as:

$$\mathcal{R} = (t)^{\frac{(\Gamma+1)}{2\Gamma(1-\frac{1}{M^2})}} \quad (30)$$

$$\mathcal{J} = \frac{2\Gamma(M^2-1)\{2-(\mathcal{L}+\mathcal{W})\}+(2\mathcal{L}-\mathcal{M}-2)(\Gamma+1)M^2}{(\Gamma+1)M^2} \quad (31)$$

Eventually, in reference of jump conditions (17)-(20), the analytical solution of the flow-field variables to the weak shock wave problem modelled in the prior section is given as:

$$\rho = S_0(\Gamma)^{2-\mathcal{L}} \frac{(x)^{2\mathcal{L}-\mathcal{M}-2}}{(t)^{(\mathcal{L}+\mathcal{W})-2}} \quad (32)$$

$$u = \frac{\{2\mathcal{L}(1-\Gamma)+\Gamma(2+\mathcal{L})-\mathcal{M}\}}{\Gamma\{2(2\mathcal{L}+\Gamma)-\mathcal{L}(2+\Gamma)-\mathcal{M}\}} \frac{x}{t} \quad (33)$$

$$p = \frac{S_0(x)^{2\mathcal{L}-\mathcal{M}} \left[\frac{1-\frac{(\Gamma+1)^2}{(\Gamma-1+\frac{2}{M^2})^2}}{4\{C_0(\Gamma+1)\}^{-1}} \right]}{2(\Gamma)^{\mathcal{L}}(t)^{(\mathcal{L}+\mathcal{W})} \left(1-\frac{1}{M^2}\right)^2 \left(\Gamma-1+\frac{2}{M^2}\right)^{-1}} \quad (34)$$

$$h = \frac{S_0 C_0 (x)^{2\mathcal{L}-\mathcal{M}} \left(\Gamma-1+\frac{2}{M^2}\right)^{-1}}{8(\Gamma)^{\mathcal{L}}(t)^{(\mathcal{L}+\mathcal{W})} (\Gamma+1)^{-3} \left(1-\frac{1}{M^2}\right)^2} \quad (35)$$

By applying the values of the physical flow parameters from (32)-(35), the explicit cumbersome solution for total energy E_T is given as:

$$E_T = \Lambda. (t) \frac{(\Gamma+1)M^2\{2(\mathcal{L}+1)-\mathcal{M}\}-2\Gamma(\mathcal{L}+\mathcal{W})(M^2-1)}{2\Gamma(M^2-1)} \quad (36)$$

where:

$$\Lambda = \frac{S_0 \left[\frac{C_0(\Gamma+1)^3}{\left\{\Gamma-1+\frac{2}{M^2}\right\}} + 4\left(1-\frac{1}{M^2}\right)^2 \frac{2(\Gamma+1)\left\{\frac{1}{2\Gamma(\Gamma-1)M^2}+\frac{C_0}{4}\right\}}{\{2(\mathcal{L}+1)-\mathcal{M}\}^{-1}\left\{\Gamma-1+\frac{2}{M^2}\right\}^{-1}} \right]}{8\{2(\mathcal{L}+1)-\mathcal{M}\}(\Gamma)^{\mathcal{L}}\left(1-\frac{1}{M^2}\right)^2 + \frac{4\left\{1-\frac{(\Gamma-1)}{2\Gamma}\frac{1}{M^2}\right\}+C_0(\Gamma+1)\left[1-(\Gamma+1)^2\left\{\Gamma-1+\frac{2}{M^2}\right\}^{-2}\right]}{\left\{1+\frac{2}{(\Gamma-1)M^2}\right\}^{-1}}}$$

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formulation of precise (closed form) and analytical solutions is of utmost importance in the field of natural and engineering sciences as these solutions are very helpful to understand and classify the involved physical phenomena. The expressions (32)-(36) depict explicitly the analytical solution of physical flow characteristics (such as density, velocity, pressure, and magnetic pressure) and total energy, to the cylindrical symmetric weak shock wave problem in an ideal supersonic magnetogasdynamic flow. It should be noted that the exact solutions obtained for the density, pressure, and magnetic pressure flow are greatly affected by the generalized magnetic field and shock Mach number. However, velocity profile and shock radius remain unchanged under the influence of the magnetic field, whereas the effect of shock Mach number appears significantly.

Figures 1-3 illustrate the behavior of flow characteristics density, pressure and magnetic pressure, for the propagation of cylindrical weak shock wave in azimuthal magnetic field with the variation in Mach number M with respect to time t . The values of the constants utilized for numerical computation have been taken as: $S_0 = 1$, $\Gamma = 1.67$, and $C_0 = 0.05$. For the sake of convenience, the effect of magnetic field h has been entered through Shock-Cowling number C_0 .

Fig. 1. Dispersal of density profile with time at various values of Mach number.

Fig. 2. Dispersal of pressure profile with time at various values of Mach number.

Fig. 3. Dispersal of pressure profile with time at various values of Mach number.

From Figures 1-3, it is evident that for increasing value of shock-Mach number, the decay process of physical parameters (density, velocity, and pressure) gets a bit slower with respect to time. Further, it is observed that for the case of axial magnetic field ($j = 0$), and various values of the ratio of specific heats (Γ), the behavior of density, pressure and magnetic pressure remains unchanged, however, for smaller values of Shock-Cowling number, the discussed flow profiles decay rapidly with respect to time as compared to larger values of C_0 which closely coincide with the results obtained in [36, 37] for non-magnetic flow.

Figure 4 exhibits the behavior of velocity profile for cylindrical weak shock wave in ideal magneto-gas-dynamic flow with the variation in M with respect to t . It is observed that when increasing the value of M , the velocity profile of the cylindrical weak shock waves at the shock front under the influence of the magnetic field increases rapidly with time. Additionally we perceive that as compared to $\Gamma = 1.67$, the fluid velocity characteristics enhances faster for the adiabatic index $\Gamma = 1.4$. Figures 5 and 6 demonstrate the behavior of the energy carried by the cylindrical weak shock wave in magneto-gas-dynamic regime with respect to t for varying values of Mach number and Shock-Cowling number respectively.

Fig. 4. Dispersal of velocity profile with time at various values of Mach number.

Fig. 5. Dispersal of total energy with time at various values of Mach number.

Fig. 6. Dispersal of total energy with time at various values of Shock-Cowling number.

It is evident from Figure 5 that when the value of M increases, the energy of the cylindrical weak shock waves under the influence of the magnetic field increases much faster with time. Moreover, it can be noted, that for the case of axial magnetic field ($j = 0$), the values of the total energy with respect to time for varying M get a bit slower as compared to the azimuthal magnetic field ($j = 1$), which confirms the experimental considerations. In Figure 6, the behavior produced due to the varying Shock-Cowling number reveals that increasing the values of C_0 causes a rapid upsurge in the total energy with respect to time. Furthermore, it should be noted, that for the case of axial magnetic field, for increasing values of C_0 , the values of the total energy with respect to time are much closer, which means that the effect of azimuthal magnetic field has a more considerable impact on the behavior of energy with respect to time.

VI. CONCLUSION

In the present work, we performed an analytical investigation of the problem of propagation of quasi-one-dimensional unsteady state compressible non-viscous adiabatic cylindrical weak shock wave in a perfect gas-dynamical regime, under the influence of axial and azimuthal magnetic fields. For this purpose, the simple and efficient analytical technique proposed in [20] has been used and the exact

solutions for the physical flow characteristics, such as density, velocity, pressure, and magnetic pressure, were obtained in the form of space-coordinates and time relations. Also, the cumbersome expression for total energy (i.e. the sum of kinetic and potential energy) carried by weak shock flow in the considered plasma influenced with magnetic field (axial and azimuthal) having dependency of space-time is determined. To describe the effect of Mach number and magnetic field (modeled in the form of the Shock-Cowling number) on flow-field characteristics and total energy carried are graphically presented. All the computations for this purpose have been done with the computational software package MATHEMATICA 9.0.

Since the shock proliferation processes are associated with a high-temperature gas dynamics phenomenon, thermal radiation has a significant impact on the wave phenomenon due to its coupling with the magnetic field and its various applications in terms of theoretical and industrial aspects. In addition, for such physical processes, the consideration that the medium is perfect is no longer valid. Therefore, an analytical investigation of the current study into realistic gas-dynamic regimes, and thermal radiation effects, is a potentially interesting area for future work.

Based on the results of the present study, the following conclusions are made:

- For increasing value of shock-Mach number, the decay process of physical parameters (flow velocity, density, and pressure) gets a bit slower with respect to time for a fixed value of C_0 , which clearly resembles the pattern of non-magnetic flow.
- An increase in the value of Mach number causes a rapid increase to the flow velocity of weakly nonlinear waves with respect to time. Consequently, we perceive that as compared to the specific heat ratio $\Gamma = 1.67$, the velocity characteristics grows faster for the adiabatic index $\Gamma = 1.4$.
- The total energy of the cylindrical weak shock waves under the influence of the azimuthal magnetic field increases much faster with respect to time for an increasing value of Mach number. However, as compared to the azimuthal magnetic field ($j = 1$), in the of the axial magnetic field ($j = 0$), the total energy with respect to time enhances a bit slower for varying Mach number, which validates the theoretical considerations.
- In azimuthal magnetic field, for increasing value of Shock-Cowling number (C_0) and with fixed values of Mach number, the total energy grows rapidly with respect to time. Moreover, for the case of axial magnetic field, the behavior remains unchanged although the values are much closer, which makes leads to the conclusion that as compared to the axial magnetic field, the effect of the azimuthal magnetic field has considerable impact on the behavior of energy with respect to time.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. M. Johnson, "Closed-form shock solutions," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. 745, Apr. 2014, Art. no. R1, <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2014.107>.
- [2] T. Gegechkori, G. Mamniashvili, A. Peikrishvili, V. Peikrishvili, and B. Godibadze, "Using Fast Hot Shock Wave Consolidation Technology to Produce Superconducting MgB₂," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2374–2378, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1690>.
- [3] W. Zhang, L. Zou, X. Zheng, and B. Wang, "Numerical study on the interaction of a weak shock wave with an elliptic gas cylinder," *Shock Waves*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 273–284, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00193-018-0828-y>.
- [4] A. Ferrari, "Analytical solutions for one-dimensional diabatic flows with wall friction," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. 918, Jul. 2021, Art. no. A32, <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2021.278>.
- [5] L. Saidi, S. Mekroussi, S. Kherris, D. Zebbar, and B. Mébarki, "A Numerical Investigation of the Free Flow in a Square Porous Cavity with Non-Uniform Heating on the Lower Wall," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 7982–7987, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4604>.
- [6] A. G. da Silva Jr, J. A. Martins, and E. C. Romao, "Numerical Simulation of a One-Dimensional Non-Linear Wave Equation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8574–8577, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4920>.
- [7] C. Greifinger and J. D. Cole, "Similarity Solution for Cylindrical Magnetohydrodynamic Blast Waves," *The Physics of Fluids*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 1597–1607, Dec. 1962, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1706571>.
- [8] N. Geffen, "Magnetogasdynamic Flows with Shock Waves," *The Physics of Fluids*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 566–571, Apr. 1963, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1706774>.
- [9] C. K. Chu, "Dynamics of Ionizing Shock Waves: Shocks in Transverse Magnetic Fields," *The Physics of Fluids*, vol. 7, no. 8, pp. 1349–1357, Aug. 1964, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1711380>.
- [10] T. S. Lee and T. Chen, "Hydromagnetic interplanetary shock waves," *Planetary and Space Science*, vol. 16, no. 12, pp. 1483–1502, Dec. 1968, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-0633\(68\)90061-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-0633(68)90061-5).
- [11] A. H. Christer and J. B. Helliwell, "Cylindrical shock and detonation waves in magnetogasdynamics," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 705–725, Dec. 1969, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112069002424>.
- [12] G. D. Ray, "Similarity solutions for cylindrical blast waves in magnetogasdynamics," *The Physics of Fluids*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 559–560, Apr. 1973, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1694381>.
- [13] L. A. Bertram, "Magnetogasdynamic shock polar: exact solution in aligned fields," *Journal of Plasma Physics*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 325–347, Jun. 1973, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022377800007534>.
- [14] D. Summers, "An idealised model of a magnetohydrodynamic spherical blast wave applied to a flare produced shock in the solar wind," *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, vol. 45, pp. 151–158, 1975.
- [15] I. Lerche, "Mathematical Theory of Cylindrical Isothermal Blast Waves in a Magnetic Field," *Australian Journal of Physics*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 279–302, 1981, <https://doi.org/10.1071/ph810279>.
- [16] V. D. Sharma, L. P. Singh, and R. Ram, "The progressive wave approach analyzing the decay of a sawtooth profile in magnetogasdynamics," *The Physics of Fluids*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 1572–1574, May 1987, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.866222>.
- [17] B. Vrsnak and S. Lulic, "Formation Of Coronal Mhd Shock Waves – I. The Basic Mechanism," *Solar Physics*, vol. 196, no. 1, pp. 157–180, Sep. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005236804727>.
- [18] J. S. Shang, "Recent research in magneto-aerodynamics," *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 1–20, Jan. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-0421\(00\)00015-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-0421(00)00015-4).
- [19] M. Pandey, R. Radha, and V. D. Sharma, "Symmetry analysis and exact solutions of magnetogasdynamic equations," *Quarterly Journal of Mechanics and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 61, no. 3, pp. 291–310, Aug. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1093/qjmam/hbn011>.
- [20] S. Murata, "New exact solution of the blast wave problem in gas dynamics," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 327–330, Apr. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2005.05.052>.

- [21] L. P. Singh, A. Husain, and M. Singh, "An Analytical Study of Strong Non Planer Shock Waves in Magnetogasdynamics," *Advances in Theoretical and Applied Mechanics*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 291–297, 2010
- [22] D. I. Pullin, W. Mostert, V. Wheatley, and R. Samtaney, "Converging cylindrical shocks in ideal magnetohydrodynamics," *Physics of Fluids*, vol. 26, no. 9, Sep. 2014, Art. no. 097103, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4894743>.
- [23] L. P. Singh, D. B. Singh, and S. D. Ram, "Growth and decay of weak shock waves in magnetogasdynamics," *Shock Waves*, vol. 26, no. 6, pp. 709–716, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00193-015-0607-y>.
- [24] M.. J. Siddiqui, R. Arora, and A. Kumar, "Shock waves propagation under the influence of magnetic field," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, vol. 97, pp. 66–74, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2016.12.020>.
- [25] G. Nath and S. Singh, "Approximate analytical solution for shock wave in rotational axisymmetric perfect gas with azimuthal magnetic field: Isothermal flow," *Journal of Astrophysics and Astronomy*, vol. 40, no. 6, Dec. 2019, Art. no. 50, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12036-019-9616-z>.
- [26] P. Gupta, R. K. Chaturvedi, and L. P. Singh, "The propagation of weak shock waves in non-ideal gas flow with radiation," *The European Physical Journal Plus*, vol. 135, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 17, <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/s13360-019-00041-y>.
- [27] M. Devi, R. Arora, and D. Singh, "Blast waves propagation in magnetogasdynamics: power series method," *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung A*, vol. 75, no. 12, pp. 1039–1050, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1515/zna-2020-0202>.
- [28] A. Sakurai, "On the Propagation and Structure of the Blast Wave, I," *Journal of the Physical Society of Japan*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 662–669, 1953, <https://doi.org/10.1143/JPSJ.8.662>.
- [29] A. Husain, S. A. Haider, and V. K. Singh, "Efficient exact solution of blast waves in magneto-gas-dynamic flow at stellar surfaces," *Advances and Applications in Mathematical Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 8, pp. 1599–1608, Jun. 2021.
- [30] P. Gupta and L. P. Singh, "On the evolution of magnetic shock wave in the mixture of gas and small solid dust particles," *Chinese Journal of Physics*, vol. 77, pp. 1912–1926, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjph.2021.12.027>.
- [31] P. Gupta, L. P. Singh, and R. Singh, "Riemann problem for non-ideal polytropic magnetogasdynamics flow," *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*, vol. 112, pp. 6–12, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnonlinmec.2019.02.012>.
- [32] P. Gupta, R. K. Chaturvedi, and L. P. Singh, "Solution of Riemann problem of conservation laws in van der Waals gas," *Waves in Random and Complex Media*, pp. 1–19, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17455030.2021.2017068>.
- [33] S.-I. Pai, *Magnetogasdynamics and Plasma Dynamics*. Vienna, Austria: Springer, 1962.
- [34] G. B. Whitham, *Linear and Nonlinear Waves*. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 1974.
- [35] V. P. Korobeinikov, *Problems in the Theory of Point Explosion in Gases*. Providence, RI, USA: American Mathematical Society, 1976..
- [36] L. P. Singh, S. D. Ram, and D. B. Singh, "Exact solution of planar and nonplanar weak shock wave problem in gasdynamics," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, vol. 44, no. 11, pp. 964–967, Nov. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2011.07.012>.
- [37] J. P. Chaudhary and L. P. Singh, "Exact Solution of the Weak Shock Wave in Non-ideal Gas," *International Journal of Applied and Computational Mathematics*, vol. 4, no. 6, Oct. 2018, Art. no. 136, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40819-018-0570-2>.

Artificial Bee Colony with Crossover Operations for Discrete Problems

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Abstract-The Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) is an algorithm designed to solve continuous problems. ABC has been proven to be more effective than other biological-inspired algorithms. However, it is needed to modify its functionality in order to solve a discrete problem. In this work, a natural modification to the original ABC is made to make it able to solve discrete problems. Six neighborhood operators are proposed to simulate the original behavior of ABC. Moreover, several Traveling Salesman Problem Library (TSPLIB) problems were used to examine the proposed method. The results of the proposed method are promising.

Keywords-Artificial Bee Colony (ABC); discrete problem; TSP

I. INTRODUCTION

A heuristic is a method for solving a problem that does not guarantee convergence to a global optimum but can offer a good enough solution. There are two types of heuristics for addressing a combinatorial optimization problem: perturbative and constructive heuristics [1]. A constructive heuristic creates a comprehensive solution from the bottom-up. A perturbative heuristic, on the other hand, changes an existing solution in order to find better solutions in the neighborhood of the present solution (i.e. operates neighborhood search operations). Problem-specific heuristics are used to solve particular problems. The nearest neighborhood heuristic and the multiple fragment heuristic are examples of constructive heuristics for the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP), whereas perturbative heuristics include swap mutation, insert mutation, reverse mutation, order crossover, and partially mapped crossover.

A problem of the ABC algorithm is that it is originally designed for continuous problems so modification should be applied to make it work with other problem types. ABC integrating grenade explosion and Cauchy operator to avoid

random search and solving the Dynamic Economic Emission Dispatch (DEED) problem was established in [2]. Authors in [3, 4] used ABC for routing and performance enhancement of wireless sensor networks. Authors in [5] modified ABC to solve constrained optimization problems. Instead of the greedy selection of the original ABC, the modified ABC used Deb's rules for constrained problems. MABC is a Modified ABC for solving the stage shop scheduling problem [6]. The MABC uses tabu search in the employee phase instead of the greedy selection. Moreover, the onlooker bee phase was also modified and the idea of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) was used instead of random search. Authors in [7] analyzed the performance of a discrete ABC algorithm with a neighborhood operator. The original ABC uses two solutions for neighborhood search while the discrete ABC uses one solution for the neighborhood search.

The aim of this paper is to simulate the original neighborhood search behavior of ABC. The main contribution of this work is the use of a crossover operation as a neighborhood search and the introduction of six neighborhood operators which simulate the original ABC neighborhood searching behavior.

II. THE TRAVELING SALESMAN PROBLEM

The TSP is one of the most commonly investigated optimization problems. The statement of TSP is simple however, it remains a challenging problem. The TSP can be defined as finding the shortest path, for a given set of cities, starting from a base city, visiting all other cities once, and returning to the base city. The description of the TSP is an indirect weighted graph $G = (S, L)$, where S symbolizes the set of cities, and L symbolizes the set of links that connect the cities. Each link which connects two cities is assigned a length

value d_{ij} , where $i, j \in L$. The problem is called symmetric TSP when the distance between two cities is the same regardless of direction, i.e. $d_{ij} = d_{ji}$. On the other hand, it is called asymmetric TSP when there is at least one link with a different distance with respect to direction, that is, the distances are direction-dependent and $d_{ij} \neq d_{ji}$. TSP is NP-hard problem. Equation (1) can be used to find the total possible solutions [8]:

$$Total\ solutions = \frac{(n-1)!}{2} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of nodes or cities.

For example, if we have 60 cities and each city is connected to all other cities, the total possible solutions will be $\frac{(60-1)!}{2} = 6.9341559e+79$. In the case of evaluating 1 billion possible solutions per second, it would take about 2.2×10^{63} years to check all possible solutions [9]. From the above example, it is obvious how large the search space is. Although good techniques are used to reduce the search space (e.g. nearest neighbor [11]), the TSP is still classified as an NP-hard problem.

The TSPLIB benchmark [10] provides a large collection of TSP cases and is represented as a standard coordinate data system. Figures 1, 2 show an example of a TSP before finding the solution and the optimal solution respectively.

Fig. 1. A TSP problem.

Fig. 2. TSP solution.

III. THE ARTIFICIAL BEE COLONY ALGORITHM

The ABC algorithm is a well-studied algorithm developed to solve continuous function optimization problems [11]. It simulates the foraging behavior a swarm of bees perform to find food. ABC is successfully used in many fields like energy management of for mobile devices [12] and for routing of mobile agents in Internet of Things (IoT) applications [13]. In ABC, the bees are divided into 3 groups: employed, onlookers, and scouts. Employed bees search for food sources and share information with an onlooker bee. The onlooker bee tries to search for a better food source in the neighborhood by using the knowledge passed from the employed bees. If the food source is abandoned, the employed bees responsible for that food source become scout bees and randomly search for the new food sources. In ABC, employed and onlooker bees accomplish the exploitation, while scout bees control the exploration process. In ABC, the employed bees use (2) to search neighbors by moving from an old position x_{ij} to the new position v_{ij} if and only if the new position's fitness is better than the fitness of the old position:

$$v_{ij} = x_{ij} + \phi_{ij}(x_{ij} - x_{kj}) \quad (2)$$

Where x_i is the old position and v_i is the new position of i^{th} employed. ϕ_{ij} is a random real number in the range of $[-1,1]$, j is an arbitrary integer number between 1 and the dimension of the problem, while k is a random number between 1 and the number of employed bees. On the other hand, the onlooker bee selects a food source and evaluates all employed bees depending on the probability calculated by:

$$p_i = \frac{fit_i}{\sum_{j=1}^{SN} fit_j} \quad (3)$$

where fit is the fitness values of the solution (food source) of the employed bee, which is calculated by:

$$fit_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1+f(x_i)}, & f(x_i) \geq 0 \\ 1 + |f(x_i)|, & f(x_i) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $f(x_i)$ stands for the value of the objective function to be optimized. Like the employed bee, the onlooker bee uses (3) to update the position and explore the selected food source.

Algorithm 1 The standard artificial bee colony (ABC).

1. Initialization Phase
2. REPEAT
3. Employed Bees Phase
4. Onlooker Bees Phase
5. Scout Bees Phase
6. Memorize the best solution achieved so far
7. UNTIL(Cycle=Maximum Cycle Number or a Maximum CPU time)

Fig. 3. Standard ABC algorithm.

When a food source cannot be further exploited within a pre-defined trial limit, it will be abandoned, and the corresponding employed bee becomes a scout bee and randomly searches for a new food source. Such a combination of the exploration and exploitation search in ABC is important. It allows the algorithm to search the solution space for high-

quality solutions and prevents them from getting stuck in local optima. In ABC, the employed bees maintain the current solution while the onlooker bees allow the best solution to be exploited. Furthermore, scout bees try to remove stagnating solutions and explore new solutions. Figure 3 shows the standard ABC algorithm.

IV. ARTIFICIAL BEE COLONY FOR TSP

TSP is a discrete problem and ABC is designed to solve continuous problems. The neighborhood operator which is a replacement for (2) is used in [7, 14] to make ABC able to solve TSPs. However, in the original ABC, the process of updating the solution is done by choosing another solution (randomly from the employee bee and using a roulette wheel in onlooker bee) and trying to enhance a solution. In this work, six neighborhood operators are proposed to simulate the original behavior of ABC.

A. Random Swap Crossover (RSC)

Random swap involves swapping the position of two randomly selected cities, starting from the first solution to the second solution, and rearranging the final solution to fix the position of the cities inserted. Consider, for example, the following two solutions of the 7-city TSP(1,2,3,4,5,6,7) and (1,5,7,6,2,3,4). First, select two random points as i and j . In our example $i = 3$ and $j = 5$. Then copy the i -th item from the second solution into the first solution (7→3). Then, the repair algorithm runs to map the i -th item in the first solution to the position of the old i -th item (3→7) and repeats the same operation for the j -th item as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Random Swap Crossover

B. Random Swap Subsequence Crossover (RSSC)

RSSC operation is the same as that of RSC, with one difference, which is the subsequence to swap in a solution from solution to solution. For example, if we have two solutions like in Figure 4 where $i = 2$ is the start position of sequence and $k = 3$, where k is the sequence length. First, copy the i -th item from the second solution into the first solution (5→2). Then, the repair algorithm maps the i -th item in the first solution to the position of the old i -th item (2→5) and repeats the same operation k times.

C. Random Insertion Crossover (RIC)

In RIC, a city from the first solution is randomly picked, removed from the second solution, reinserted into a random position in the second solution, and the repair algorithm is

executed as explained in RSC. Figure 6 shows the RIC operation.

Fig. 5. Random Swap Subsequence Crossover.

Fig. 6. Random Insertion Crossover.

D. Random Insertion of Subsequence Crossover (RISC)

In RISC, a subsequence from a solution is randomly picked and then inserted into a second solution. The repair algorithm is again executed as in RSC. Figure 7 shows the RISC operation.

Fig. 7. Random Insertion of Subsequence Crossover.

E. Random Reversing Crossover (RRC)

RRC is the same as RSC, with one difference, which is the inversion of the inserted cities when copying from the first to the second solution as shown in Figure 8.

F. Random Swap Subsequence Reverse Crossover (RSSRC)

It is the same as RISC with the difference that the inserted sequence is inverted before insertion as shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 8. Random Reversing Crossover.

Fig. 9. Random Swap Subsequence Reverse Crossover.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, the proposed method was implemented using C#. The algorithm was tested in 12 TSP problems (pr76, kroA100, kroB100, kroC100, kroD100, kroE100, rd100, gr120, pr124, bier127, ch130, pr136) taken from the TSPLIB benchmark library [12]. The code was run on a 2.80 GHz Intel Core i7 processor with 16 GB RAM. The same parameter values were used in all experiments to make sure of a fair judgment between all different methods. Each method ran the same TSP benchmark 30 times. The best and the average solutions were collected for every 30 runs.

The experimental results obtained by the discrete ABC algorithm with crossover and ABC with neighborhood operators explained in [7] are shown in Table I (RSC), Table II (RSSC), Table III (RIC), Table IV (RISC), Table V (RRC), and Table VI (RSSRC).

TABLE I. RANDOM SWAP Crossover

Problem	RSC		RS	
	error	avg error	error	avg error
pr76	46.99748	54.72502	73.58703	91.39779
kroA100	80.78658	96.99104	139.8036	163.6677
kroB100	79.63055	88.92176	135.0029	152.0174
kroC100	74.64938	98.85922	131.963	163.369
kroD100	85.98666	94.72684	136.2168	155.6664
kroE100	71.01233	92.52387	132.8938	153.7324
rd100	69.38053	85.36747	116.7762	145.2078
gr120	78.45001	94.11505	138.0726	154.8065
pr124	136.2697	168.2421	241.074	265.6827
bier127	47.11283	69.60656	105.9739	118.8277
ch130	86.30115	104.0835	161.9804	183.4746
pr136	87.92729	112.748	181.9473	197.9853

TABLE II. RANDOM SWAP SUBSEQUENCE CROSSOVER

Problem	RSSWC		RSS	
	error	avg error	error	avg error
pr76	59.73151	71.36817	25.39687	47.79393
kroA100	86.09153	108.4756	84.81346	110.7512
kroB100	77.17357	101.3199	78.25753	100.5301
kroC100	98.665	111.3994	90.92968	118.8134
kroD100	85.83639	103.1306	82.44576	105.7127
kroE100	90.4749	102.0346	80.2021	106.9497
rd100	83.67889	97.02318	74.71555	98.79351
gr120	85.07635	95.13253	88.61999	113.2892
pr124	131.1164	149.0558	138.3534	185.6913
bier127	69.38587	78.58206	52.21082	70.05222
ch130	107.234	120.3644	97.10311	122.9116
pr136	102.9296	115.7102	114.7532	142.3517

TABLE III. RANDOM INSERTION CROSSOVER

Problem	RIWC		RI	
	error	avg error	error	avg error
pr76	27.94312	39.36553	10.94685	20.9037
kroA100	38.01334	61.09639	35.77671	52.17602
kroB100	37.36507	55.50231	33.21892	51.09405
kroC100	52.78327	65.16459	30.12193	57.67137
kroD100	47.56269	60.26111	35.18832	53.36621
kroE100	44.0638	59.97311	31.6431	52.00773
rd100	31.66877	55.39022	31.32743	58.60598
gr120	48.2858	60.77883	53.31317	72.07241
pr124	68.42453	89.73748	63.58123	101.3253
bier127	41.45855	49.50531	47.90162	69.3766
ch130	57.54501	70.97709	74.04255	116.2635
pr136	54.72967	68.41197	77.31782	104.5502

TABLE IV. RANDOM INSERTION OF SUBSEQUENCE CROSSOVER

Problem	RISWC		RIS	
	error	avg error	error	avg error
pr76	49.2266	58.47	50.86031	66.37531
kroA100	76.14416	86.6875	104.2618	130.5938
kroB100	69.49099	81.44588	90.89472	113.5918
kroC100	79.03031	90.92808	100.8964	130.3549
kroD100	67.30065	81.70236	93.09665	119.8395
kroE100	64.37375	81.873	99.69639	124.8651
rd100	70.0885	81.38938	94.96839	115.2503
gr120	66.30654	77.97273	90.01729	121.2134
pr124	101.5297	117.2478	137.2438	200.9112
bier127	54.447	69.39636	67.83112	81.2194
ch130	79.1653	93.60993	111.9476	146.4146
pr136	74.26735	87.27759	135.192	156.8362

TABLE V. RANDOM REVERSING CROSSOVER

Problem	RRWC		RR	
	error	avg error	error	avg error
pr76	21.22307	26.50754	8.847839	13.58325
kroA100	18.54547	29.62665	8.4486	14.70384
kroB100	19.15563	27.48035	4.879309	12.21972
kroC100	6.691075	17.47819	1.227822	4.689023
kroD100	13.33333	18.1679	1.185185	4.019753
kroE100	15.1942	26.48397	15.15869	20.62213
rd100	25.02455	34.71413	28.01964	40.71358
gr120	19.04861	30.61965	4.089297	13.66924
pr124	16.38715	23.30662	5.198294	10.8402
bier127	32.74267	44.25733	17.94681	30.11028
ch130	26.09536	34.55156	22.58505	34.33286
pr136	21.25158	28.10493	8.609355	15.42815

The results clearly show that the proposed method is better for all considered problems and RSC, RISC, RRSSRC

methods. In RSSC, it got a better result in 9 cases. On the other hand, RIC solves half of the problems with better results than the other methods. However, the RRC operator gives poor performance compared to the random-reverse neighborhood operator.

TABLE VI. RANDOM SWAP SUBSEQUENCE REVERSE CROSSOVER

Problem	RSSRWC		RSSR	
	error	avg error	error	avg error
pr76	58.71911	70.09199	102.3012	114.1171
kroA100	93.22902	113.2607	182.3983	192.9061
kroB100	84.36837	103.8512	168.6645	178.0544
kroC100	85.88848	111.2542	169.8588	194.1552
kroD100	81.38443	105.0621	168.5404	185.8098
kroE100	90.64709	104.1044	169.0955	182.4486
rd100	84.93047	103.8972	168.8748	183.0523
gr120	85.86863	100.5695	161.8986	180.8902
pr124	131.9532	156.3919	283.1865	311.2413
bier127	67.18267	82.61759	125.0528	135.4019
ch130	107.2831	123.7621	212.455	223.1844
pr136	103.5847	120.2145	208.8197	229.9761

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the Artificial Bee Colony algorithm is modified with new neighborhood operators to solve discrete problems. The proposed method was tested on 12 TSP problems from the TSPLIB. The results show that Random Swap Crossover, Random Insertion of Subsequence Crossover, and Random Swap Subsequence Reverse Crossover operations give a good performance. The proposed method is similar to the original Artificial Bee Colony algorithm and gives promising results.

Our future work will focus on introducing new neighborhood operators and optimizing the implementation of the proposed method. Furthermore, due to the encouraging result, the proposed method can be easily integrated into other optimization algorithms.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Gu, Q. Wang, X. Li, and X. Li, "A surrogate-assisted multi-objective particle swarm optimization of expensive constrained combinatorial optimization problems," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 223, Jul. 2021, Art. No. 107049, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knsys.2021.107049>.
- [2] I. Marouani, A. Boudjemline, T. Guesmi, and H. H. Abdallah, "A Modified Artificial Bee Colony for the Non-Smooth Dynamic Economic/Environmental Dispatch," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3321–3328, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2098>.
- [3] S. D. Chavan and A. V. Kulkarni, "Event Based Clustering Localized Energy Efficient Ant Colony Optimization (EBC_LEE-ACO) for Performance Enhancement of Wireless Sensor Network," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3177–3183, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2121>.
- [4] H. Ehteshami, S. Javadi, and S. M. Shariatmadar, "Improving the Power Quality in Tehran Metro Line-Two Using the Ant Colony Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2256–2259, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1551>.
- [5] D. Karaboga and B. Akay, "A modified Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm for constrained optimization problems," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 3021–3031, Apr. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2010.12.001>.
- [6] M. M. Nasiri, "A modified ABC algorithm for the stage shop scheduling problem," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 28, pp. 81–89, Mar. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2014.12.001>.
- [7] M. S. Kıran, H. İşcan, and M. Gündüz, "The analysis of discrete artificial bee colony algorithm with neighborhood operator on traveling salesman problem," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 9–21, Jul. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-011-0794-0>.
- [8] D. B. Fogel, "An evolutionary approach to the traveling salesman problem," *Biological Cybernetics*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 139–144, Dec. 1988, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00202901>.
- [9] J. McCaffrey, "Test Run - Ant Colony Optimization," *MSDN Magazine Issues*, vol. 27, no. 2, Feb. 2016, [Online]. Available: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/archive/msdn-magazine/2012/february/test-run-ant-colony-optimization>.
- [10] G. Reinelt, "TSPLIB—A Traveling Salesman Problem Library," *ORSA Journal on Computing*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 376–384, Nov. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.1287/ijoc.3.4.376>.
- [11] D. Karaboga and B. Basturk, "A powerful and efficient algorithm for numerical function optimization: artificial bee colony (ABC) algorithm," *Journal of Global Optimization*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 459–471, Oct. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10898-007-9149-x>.
- [12] S. ArunKumar, B. V. Kumar, and M. Pandi, "Artificial bee colony optimization based energy-efficient wireless network interface selection for industrial mobile devices," *Computer Communications*, vol. 154, pp. 1–10, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comcom.2020.01.067>.
- [13] H. Gao, Z. Fu, C.-M. Pun, J. Zhang, and S. Kwong, "An Efficient Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm With an Improved Linkage Identification Method," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 52, no. 6, pp. 4400–4414, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2020.3026716>.
- [14] S. S. Choong, L.-P. Wong, and C. P. Lim, "An artificial bee colony algorithm with a Modified Choice Function for the traveling salesman problem," *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 44, pp. 622–635, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2018.08.004>.

Solar-Wind Hybrid Power Generation System Optimization Using Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES)

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Abstract-This paper proposes a renewable energy hybrid power system that is based on photovoltaic (PV) and wind power generation and is equipped with Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES). Wind and solar power generation are two of the most promising renewable power generation technologies. They are suitable for hybrid systems because they are environmentally friendly. However, like most renewable energy sources, they are characterized by high variability and discontinuity. They generate a fluctuating output voltage that damages the machines that operate on a stable supply. Therefore, the energy storage system SMES with the function to reduce output voltage fluctuation problems is introduced. SMES is found to be the most effective energy storage device as a result of its quick time response, high power density, and high energy conversion efficiency. In this paper, modeling of a hybrid system with SMES is built using MATLAB/Simulink. Blocks such as the wind model, PV model, and energy storage model are built separately before combining into a complete hybrid system with SMES. Varying wind speed and solar irradiance values are taken as the input parameters. The obtained results from the simulation reveal that a system with SMES is more reliable than a system without SMES.

Keywords-hybrid energy storage system; renewable energy; photovoltaic (PV) system; wind; power quality; Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES)

I. INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, the exploitation of renewable energy resources has attracted considerable attention due to the negative impact on the environment and the increased cost of fossil fuels used in conventional power plants. Many renewable

energy sources, like solar, wind, hydro, and tidal can be exploited. Among them, solar and wind have the most rapid growth. Without any hazard emission of pollutants, energy conversion is made possible through wind and PV cells.

A hybrid system is more advantageous as an individual power generation system, even though it is not completely reliable. In case of a power outage or complete shutdown in one of the systems, the remaining one can still supply power. Hence, in the present study, solar and wind power generations are combined to create a hybrid power system. This system, consisting of two unpredictable energy sources, will produce fluctuating output energy and thus cannot ensure the minimum level of power continuity required by the load [1-3]. Combining the renewable hybrid system with batteries as a storage system, in order to increase the duration of energy autonomy, will make optimal use of the utilized renewable energy resources and this, in turn, can guarantee high supply reliability.

At present, multiple energy storage technologies are being developed and such examples include Flywheel Energy System (FES), Compressed Air Energy Storage (CAES), Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage (SMES) [4], and Phase-Change Materials (PCM). In this paper, a SMES is introduced into the hybrid wind and PV power generation system. The added energy storage will store energy during the low load demand period and help stabilize the system's generated output voltage.

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II. MODELING OF THE HYBRID SYSTEM

A. Modeling of the PV System

In this project, we chose to use KC200GT PV module as a reference to develop the PV block model. The PV system was modeled and developed based on the equations from [5]. The parameters of the PV model are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. PV ARRAY PARAMETERS AT 250°C, 1000w/m²

Parameter	Value
I_{mp}	7.61 A
V_{mp}	26.3 V
I_{sc}	8.21 A
P_{max}	200.143 W
V_{OC}	32.9 V
K_v	-0.1230 V/K
K_i	0.0032 A/K
N_s	54
N_p	4

The PV power system model is made up of 3 subsystem blocks (Figures 1-3), which are:

- Photovoltaic Current (I_{pv})
- Saturation Current (I_o)
- Photovoltaic Current Output (I_m)

Fig. 1. Photovoltaic current block model.

Fig. 2. Saturation current block model.

Fig. 3. Photovoltaic current output block model.

The parameters that affect the PV power system output are solar irradiance (G) and temperature (T). Both PV current and saturation current block models are connected in the PV current output block model, as illustrated in Figure 3.

B. Modeling of Wind Turbine Power System

The wind turbine power system consists of a wind turbine model and a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) block that was already available on the Simulink library of MATLAB. These permanent magnet machines are characterized by having large air gaps, which reduce the flux

linkage even in machines with multi-magnetic poles [6-8]. The static characteristics of wind turbines can be described by the relationship between the total power in the wind and the mechanical power of wind turbines [9-11].

The wind turbine model block is connected to a PMSM and a rectifier as shown in Figure 4. Varying wind speed is given as the input to the wind turbine and the output mechanical torque from the turbine is directed to the PMSM that converts mechanical energy into electrical energy. The three phase AC output from the PMSM is then sent to the rectifier where it is converted into the DC output.

Fig. 4. Wind power system.

TABLE II. PARAMETERS OF THE PERMANENT MAGNET SYNCHRONOUS MACHINE BLOCK

Parameters	Value
Nominal mechanical output power (W)	8.5e3
Base power of the electrical generator (VA)	8.5e3/0.9
Base wind speed (m/s)	12
Maximum power at base wind speed (pu of nominal mechanical power)	0.8
Base rotational speed (kpu of base generator speed)	1

TABLE III. PARAMETERS OF THE WIND TURBINE BLOCK

Parameter	Value
Stator phase resistance R_s (ohm)	0.425
Inductance L_d (H)	0.000395
Flux linkage established by magnets (V.s)	0.433
Torque constant	5
Inertia J (kg.m ²)	0.1197
Friction factor F (N.m.s)	0.001189

The simulation of the wind power system is shown in Figure 4 and the parameters of the PMSM block and wind turbine model block are presented in Tables II and III respectively.

C. Modeling of the SMES System

A SMES device is a DC current device that stores energy in the magnetic field. The DC current flowing through a superconducting wire in a large magnet creates the magnetic field [12]. The basic operation of the SMES coil can be explained by the simplified electrical model in Figure 5.

In this model, the SMES coil is connected to the source and is loaded by three switches: S1, S2, and S3. Here, the coil is a dynamic storage system. Charging and discharging of the coil is maintained by a Power Conditioning System (PCS) which controls the switches independently by generating suitable control of a signal. The operation of the switches is described by the flowchart in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. Simplified equivalent circuit of the SMES coil.

Fig. 6. Flowchart of charging-discharging involved in the SMES system.

1) First case

As seen in the circuit diagram, the superconducting coil is directly connected to the input voltage, whereas the load is through the aid of power electronics switches. The supply is denoted by "S" and the demand by "D". If $D < S$, S1 and S2 must be closed and switch S3 is open. This combination is used to charge the coil.

Fig. 7. Circuit of charging SMES coil.

2) Second Case

When switches S3 and S2 are closed and switch S1 is open, the coil will be in the steady storage condition.

Fig. 8. Circuit of the steady storage case.

3) Third case

In this case, switches S1 and S2 are open and switch S3 is closed and the coil will be discharging.

Fig. 9. Circuit of the case of discharging of the SMES coil.

D. Controller Circuit

An appropriate control system was required to control the charging and discharging sequence of the SMES. This was accomplished by using a PI controller-based DC-DC chopper as shown in Figure 10. It operates by constantly comparing the reference voltage with the feedback value of the controller. The error difference between these two will be added to the voltage output from the hybrid system [13]. This total output voltage will then be compared with the expected hybrid output voltage using a comparator. If the output of the hybrid system is less than the reference value, then the DC-DC chopper sends signal zero (0) to the switch, otherwise, a signal one (1) will be sent. Signal zero (0) indicates a switch open and SMES discharging, whereas signal one (1) indicates that the IGBT switch is closed and SMES is charging.

Fig. 10. DC-DC chopper controller block model.

III. SIMULATION CASE STUDIES

In this section, various case studies are been considered. In each case, the input solar irradiance and the wind speed were considered different. Hybrid system power characteristics, i.e. input solar irradiance and input wind speed, with and without SMES and SMES power characteristics are plotted for each case.

A. Simulation Results of the SMES System

Modeling of the charge-discharge circuit for the SMES is executed using MATLAB/Simulink. The circuit (Figure 14) is implemented for a purely resistive load. The parameters of the SMES model are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV. SMES PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
System frequency	50 Hz
Line reactor resistance	0.0015 Ω
DC-Link capacitance	1 F
Load resistance	1 Ω
Superconducting coil	0.008H
PID Controller Gain	KP =0.5, KI = 0.00001, KD= 1

Fig. 11. Energy waveform during coil charging and discharging.

Fig. 12. Power waveform during coil charging and discharging.

Fig. 13. Current waveform during coil charging and discharging.

From the results, it is evident that the SMES can store very high energy, around 1000MJ, whereas the power level is close to 12MW and the current increases until it reaches around 100kA. During the discharge of the coil, the power injection time is also very low (2s).

B. Simulation Results of the Hybrid System without SMES

The two renewable generator types are connected in series. Each generator produces a voltage output of 200V, so practically the output voltage was 400V. We simulated the hybrid system for 3 cases to see the influence of the intermittency of the wind and irradiation on the charging voltage. The system supplies an electrical load (R, L) with $R= 30\Omega$ and $L= 2H$.

Fig. 14. SMES system block model.

- Case 1: Irradiation and wind speed are constant, $G= 1000w/m^2$, $V= 12m/s$. Figures 15, 16 show the Voltage rate and the power characteristic.

Fig. 15. Voltage rate.

Fig. 16. Power characteristic.

- Case 2: The irradiation is of Step form and the wind speed remains constant. Figures 17, 18 show the Voltage rate and the power characteristic.

Fig. 17. Voltage rate.

Fig. 18. Power characteristic.

- Case 3: Constant irradiation and step form wind speed. Figures 19, 20 show the Voltage rate and the power characteristic.

Fig. 19. Voltage rate.

Fig. 20. Power characteristic.

From Figures 15-20, it is clear that when the wind or irradiation or both decrease, the load voltage decreases along with power.

C. Simulation of the Hybrid Wind-PV System with SMES

This study seeks to stabilize the voltage in the event of loss of one or both renewable generators. So, we integrated an energy storage system using a superconducting SMES coil, whose role is to intervene in the event of a voltage drop [14]. The simulation time of Figure 24 is 10s. We simulated the system for the case where the loss of the two generators from which the irradiation and wind speed have a step form. Figures 21-25 show the simulation results.

Fig. 21. Charge voltage curve with SMES.

Fig. 22. Hybrid system power curve with SMES.

Fig. 23. Hybrid system charging current curve with SMES.

Fig. 24. Curve of Power with and without SMES.

According to Figure 21, during the period from 0s to 4s the voltage reached 400V. From 4s to 7s the two generators were lost and the voltage was restored thanks to the intervention of the SMES, which was able to keep it stable. Therefore, we can see the great contribution of SMES to the stability of the hybrid system. Figure 24 represents the comparison of the power with

and without SMES for the case of the loss of the two generators from 4s to 7s. We noticed that the power without SMES decreases when the wind and the irradiation decreased and on the other hand, with SMES, the power remains stable and is fixed at a value of 5200W.

Fig. 25. Block diagram of the hybrid wind-PV system with SMES (the inside of sub-models is shown in Figures 1-4, 14).

D. Discussion

When both PV and wind generators are connected to the system, the load demand is met. If only one of the PV or the wind generators generates power, then the power demand of the system cannot be fulfilled since the two generators are connected in series to give an added output voltage. From the hybrid system power graph, it is seen that voltage drops when one generator is lost or disturbed making the system unstable. When the SMES is added to the system, it provides power with very fast response time, which ensures the constant output power of the hybrid system. This is clearly shown in the graph of the hybrid system power with and without SMES (Figure 24). Based on the simulation results, SMES technology can also be used on conventional generating systems for load leveling and spinning reserve.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a hybrid system that combines the wind and PV models has been developed, and the application of the energy storage system SMES is presented in the developed model. The overall hybrid system with and without SMES was tested with varying irradiation levels and wind speed for the PV model and the wind model to determine the function of SMES inside the hybrid system. Through the charging and discharging process of SMES during the simulation, the output voltage fluctuations caused by the intermittent energy sources in the power generation system were reduced. It has been seen from the simulation results that SMES can improve the quality of the

output fluctuations, and thus increase the reliability of the hybrid power system.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kumar, K. S. Sandhu, S. P. Jain, and P. Sharath Kumar, "Modeling and Control of Micro-Turbine Based Distributed Generation System," *International Journal of Circuits, Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 65–72, 2009.
- [2] A. Al-Shereiqi, A. Al-Hinai, M. Albadi, and R. Al-Abri, "Optimal Sizing of Hybrid Wind-Solar Power Systems to Suppress Output Fluctuation," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 17, Jan. 2021, Art. No. 5377, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14175377>.
- [3] A. Safaei, S. H. Hosseinian, and H. A. Abyaneh, "Enhancing the HVRT and LVRT Capabilities of DFIG-based Wind Turbine in an Islanded Microgrid," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2118–2123, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1541>.
- [4] A. Zebar and L. Madani, "SFCL-SMES Control for Power System Transient Stability Enhancement Including SCIG-based Wind Generators," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5477–5482, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3422>.
- [5] S. Sumathi, L. Ashok Kumar, and P. Surekha, *Solar PV and Wind Energy Conversion Systems*. Springer International Publishing, 2015.
- [6] P. Vas, *Electrical Machines and Drives: A Space-Vector Theory Approach*, 1st ed. Oxford, UK; New York, NY, USA: Clarendon Press, 1993.
- [7] T. J. E. Miller, *Brushless Permanent-Magnet and Reluctance Motor Drives*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 1989.
- [8] K. Okedu, "Wind Turbine Driven by Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator," *The Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 168–175, Oct. 2011.

- [9] A. Manyonge, R. Manyala, F. Onyango, and J. Shichika, "Mathematical Modelling of Wind Turbine in a Wind Energy Conversion System: Power Coefficient Analysis," *Applied Mathematical Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 91, pp. 4527–4536, Jan. 2012.
- [10] Y. D. Song, B. Dhinakaran, and X. Y. Bao, "Variable speed control of wind turbines using nonlinear and adaptive algorithms," *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, vol. 85, no. 3, pp. 293–308, Apr. 2000, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-6105\(99\)00131-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-6105(99)00131-2).
- [11] A. Goudarzi and F. Ghayoor, "Modelling of Wind Turbine Power Curves (WTPCs) Based on the Sum of the Sine Functions and Improved version of Particle Swarm Optimization (IPSO)," in *2020 International SAUPEC/RobMech/PRASA Conference*, Cape Town, South Africa, Jan. 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SAUPEC/RobMech/PRASA48453.2020.9041008>.
- [12] T. Ise, M. Kita, and A. Taguchi, "A hybrid energy storage with a SMES and secondary battery," *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1915–1918, Jun. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASC.2005.849333>.
- [13] G. H. Kim *et al.*, "A novel HTS SMES application in combination with a permanent magnet synchronous generator type wind power generation system," *Physica C: Superconductivity and its Applications*, vol. 471, no. 21, pp. 1413–1418, Nov. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physc.2011.05.206>.
- [14] A. B. Lajimi, S. A. Gholamian, and M. Shahabi, "Modeling and Control of a DFIG-Based Wind Turbine During a Grid Voltage Drop," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 121–125, Oct. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.60>.

Time-Dependent Reliability Assessment of a Continuous I-shaped Steel Beam Considering Corrosion Effects

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Abstract—Among other fields, climate change has a great influence on metal corrosion that reduces the durability and reliability of steel structures. A time-dependent reliability analysis includes time-dependent climate scenarios and deterioration processes as well as random variables, material properties, and dimensions. The extent of corrosion damage is calculated by tracking the evolution of the corrosion process using Monte Carlo simulations. The current paper presents a time-dependent reliability assessment of a continuous I-shaped steel beam, considering the corrosion effects of climate change in Vietnam. The results showed that the safety probability of a continuous steel beam considering metal corrosion from the pristine to 100 years reduces from 96.77% to 63.08%. These findings can be used to assess and provide a cost-technical analysis of climate adaptation measures.

Keywords—time-dependent reliability; continuous I-shaped steel beam; corrosion damage; Monte Carlo simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Continuous steel beams that contain two or more spans are typically used in steel frame buildings and bridges. The design of continuous beams not only ensures the strength condition but also minimizes their weight and material costs. A steel beam can be influenced in the long term by corrosion, leading to an acceleration of structural deterioration. Therefore, a time-dependent reliability assessment of continuous steel beams is very important, especially in the context of climate change. The assessment of the reliability and durability of steel structures for metal corrosion attracted the interest of many studies. The structural reliability of ships, offshore structures, and pipelines takes into account essential theoretical concepts and realistic data [1]. An investigation of corrosion behavior was conducted

on a scale of 1:5 of a transport container sunk in a seabed [2]. Evaluations and surveys on structural reliability considering metal corrosion in steel frame structures and steel-concrete composite beams were conducted in [3-6]. Meanwhile, an assessment process was proposed to consider the effects of climate change on the atmospheric corrosion rate of steel structures, taking into account changes in ambient temperature, carbon dioxide, relative humidity, wind, precipitation, and pollution [7]. However, the structural reliability and durability of continuous I-shaped steel beams with corrosion damage have not been assessed so far. This study aimed to evaluate the time-dependent reliability of continuous I-shaped steel beams, considering the effects of corrosion based on a climate change scenario. The climate change scenario was assumed from 2020 to 2120 with Time Of Wetness (TOW), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), chlorides (Cl), and Temperature (T) as input parameters, and adopted the corrosion model proposed in [8]. The time-dependent reliability assessment was a combination of the Monte Carlo (MC) simulation and the Finite Element Method (FEM), estimating the corrosion loss of the cross-section of a steel beam. The computations were conducted in MATLAB. The numerical results of the corrosion reliability and durability behaviors were determined for exposure times of 10 to 100 years.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Climate Change Scenario

This study considered a climate change scenario that included TOW, SO₂, Cl, and T as input parameters [9]. Their ranges were as follows:

- $445.40 \leq \text{TOW} \leq 518.80$ h/year

- $80.00 \leq SO_2 \leq 98.26 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
- $25.85 \leq Cl \leq 36.78 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$
- $25.53 \leq T \leq 28.10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 1 shows the curves of the environmental parameters, each one corresponding to a scenario of climate change.

Fig. 1. Climate change scenarios assumed from 2020 to 2120.

B. Atmospheric Corrosion Rate Model

Metal atmospheric corrosion is a complex process and depends on a large number of interacting environmental factors. The atmospheric corrosion of carbon steel in various environments was intensively studied and proposed in [8]. This study adopted this corrosion model to evaluate the reliability of the structures. The following model was used to estimate corrosion loss:

$$d(t) = A \cdot t^B \left(\frac{TOW}{c}\right)^D \cdot \left(1 + \frac{[SO_2]}{E}\right)^F \cdot \left(1 + \frac{[Cl]}{G}\right)^H \cdot e^{J(T+T_0)} \quad (1)$$

where $d(t)$ is the corrosion depth in μm , t is the exposure time in years, TOW is the Time Of Wetness in h/year, $[SO_2]$ is the sulfur dioxide concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, $[Cl]$ is the chloride deposition rate in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$, T is the average temperature in $^\circ\text{C}$, T_0 is an empirical coefficient, and $A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, J$ are numerical values, which can be found in [8].

C. Nominal and Distributions of Material Properties

The nominals and distributions of material properties were based on [10], while the cross-sections and loadings were adopted from [11].

D. Safety Condition of the Continuous Steel Beam

The safety condition of the continuous steel beam was based on the Eurocode design of steel buildings EC3-1-1 [12]. The safety condition is given by:

$$G(X) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{M_{Ed}}{M_{c,Rd}} - 1, 0\right) \frac{1}{n} \leq 0 \\ \left(\left[\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{pl,y,Rd}}\right]^\alpha + \left[\frac{M_{z,Ed}}{M_{pl,z,Rd}}\right]^\beta - 1, 0\right) \frac{1}{n} \leq 0 \\ \left(\frac{V_{Ed}}{V_{c,Rd}} - 1, 0\right) \frac{1}{n} \leq 0 \\ \left(\left(W_{pl,y} - \frac{\rho A_s^2}{4t_w}\right) \frac{f_y}{\gamma_{M0}} - M_{y,c,Rd}\right) \frac{1}{n} \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

E. Monte Carlo Simulation

The MC simulation method is based on the use of pseudo-random numbers and the law of large numbers to assess the reliability of any system. If the safe domain is defined by the condition $f(X) > 0$, where X is a random vector containing all input random variables, the unsafe probability of the system is determined by:

$$P_f = \int I_{f(X)<0} f_X(x) dx = E[I_{f(X)<0}] \quad (3)$$

where $I_{f(X)<0}$ is the indicator function, defined by

$$I_{f(X)<0} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } f(X) < 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } f(X) \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

According to the theory of statistics, if there are N realizations of the random vector X by propagating the randomness, a sample of N realizations of the indicator function can be obtained. The expected value of the indicator function can be approximately determined by taking the mean of the sample, as expressed in:

$$\hat{P}_f = E[I_{f(X)<0}] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N I_{f(X)<0}^i \quad (5)$$

A 95% confidence interval for the estimation was defined in [13] as:

$$\hat{P}_f \left(1 - 1.96 \sqrt{\frac{1-\hat{P}_f}{N\hat{P}_f}} \right) \leq P_f \leq \hat{P}_f \left(1 + 1.96 \sqrt{\frac{1-\hat{P}_f}{N\hat{P}_f}} \right) \quad (6)$$

Reliability assessment was evaluated using MC simulations in MATLAB. The verification of the MATLAB code has already been presented in [3, 4, 14-16].

III. TIME-DEPENDENT RELIABILITY COMBINING FEM, METAL CORROSION MODELING, AND MONTE CARLO SIMULATION

The computational program for the reliability assessment of the continuous steel beam was developed using FEM, the corrosion model with input parameters based on the climate change scenario, and the MC simulations.

A. Convergence of the Monte Carlo Simulation at Pristine

A continuous I-shaped steel beam with 3-spans was examined, having the geometry of structure and cross-section as shown in Figure 2. The nominal values and distributions of the random variables are shown in Table I. The nominal values and the distributions of the material properties were adopted from [10], while the cross-sectional dimensions and applied load were adopted from [11]. Reliability assessment was applied in pristine conditions ($t = 0$ years). Figure 3 shows the convergence tests of the MC simulations at the design time ($t = 0$) for the continuous steel beam. The convergence test of the continuous steel beam was achieved after 2340 samplings in 28.5min, and the safety probability of the structure was up to 96.77%. The test was conducted using an Intel® Core™ i7-3930 CPU at 3.20-4.20Hz. This result also shows that although there was a safety factor of 1.15 in the analysis, the reliability of the structure was only $P_s = 96.77\%$, because of the randomness of input parameters. Thus, the assessment of the structure’s reliability is necessary, especially considering the metal corrosion over time.

Fig. 2. Continuous I-shaped steel beam with 3-spans.

TABLE I. STATISTIC PROPERTIES OF RANDOM VARIABLES FOR RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT

Properties	Variables	Nominal	Mean/nominal	COV	Distribution	Ref.
Geometric	L	6000 (cm)	-	-	Deterministic	-
Material	f_y	248.0 (GPa)	1.10	0.06	Lognormal	[11]
	E	200.0 (GPa)	1.10	0.06	Lognormal	[11]
	G	81.0 (GPa)	1.10	0.06	Lognormal	[11]
Loading	DL^*	50.0 (kN/m2)	1.05	0.10	Normal	[10]
	LL^*	30.5 (kN/m2)	1.05	0.10	Normal	[10]
Cross-section beam	B	200.0 (mm)	1.00	0.05	Normal	[10]
	H	480.0 (mm)	1.00	0.05	Normal	[10]
	t_f	20.0 (mm)	1.00	0.05	Normal	[10]
	t_w	10.0 (mm)	1.00	0.05	Normal	[10]

Fig. 3. Convergence of the safety probability (above) and failure probability (below) in the Monte Carlo simulation of the continuous steel beam at the design time ($t = 0$).

B. Effect of Metal Corrosion on the Safety Probability

The reliability assessment of the continuous steel beam was carried out for different corrosion durations of 10, 20, 50, and 100 years. The summary of the safety probability in the Monte Carlo simulation of the continuous steel beam, considering its metal corrosion, is shown in Table II and Figure 4.

TABLE II. SAFETY PROBABILITY OF THE CONTINUOUS STEEL BEAM FROM 0 TO 100 YEARS

Years	0	10	20	50	100
Safety probability (%)	96.77	81.44	75.91	68.61	63.08

Fig. 4. Reliability decline of the continuous steel beam in 0-100 years.

Table II and Figure 4 show that the safety probability of the continuous steel beam, considering metal corrosion from the pristine to 100 years using MC simulation, reduced from 96.77% to 63.08%. In other words, the safe probability after 10, 20, 50, and 100 years of corrosion reduced by 15.33%, 20.86%, 28.16%, and 33.69% respectively. It should be noted that the used convergence criteria of 1.5% justify the confidence of the estimated reliability.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the time-dependent reliability of a continuous I-shaped steel beam, considering the influence of metal corrosion. The numerical results were based on the corrosion model with input parameters from the climate change scenario and Monte Carlo simulation. In the structural reliability assessment, a wide range of corrosive exposure times from 10 to 100 years was considered. The findings of this study can be summarized as follows:

- A climate change scenario in Vietnam from 2020 to 2120 was considered in the structural reliability assessment of a continuous I-shaped steel beam.
- A computational program was developed in MATLAB to assess the time-dependent reliability of a continuous I-shaped steel beam, considering corrosion effects.
- The safety probability of the continuous I-shaped steel beam, considering the metal corrosion from pristine to 100 years, reduced from 96.77% to 63.08%.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. E. Melchers, "The effect of corrosion on the structural reliability of steel offshore structures," *Corrosion Science*, vol. 47, no. 10, pp. 2391–2410, Oct. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2005.04.004>.
- [2] A. Kosaki, "The corrosion behavior of one-fifth scale lid models of transport cask submerged in sea bottom," *Corrosion Science*, vol. 47, no. 10, pp. 2361–2376, Oct. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2004.10.015>.
- [3] T. H. Nguyen and D. D. Nguyen, "Reliability Assessment of Steel-Concrete Composite Beams considering Metal Corrosion Effects," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2020, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 8817809, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8817809>.
- [4] M. Rohani, G. Shafabakhsh, A. Haddad, and E. Asnaashari, "Sensitivity Analysis of Workspace Conflicts According to Changing Geometric Conditions," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1429–1435, Feb. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1012>.
- [5] N. L. Tran and T. H. Nguyen, "Reliability Assessment of Steel Plane Frame's Buckling Strength Considering Semi-rigid Connections," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5099–5103, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3231>.
- [6] T. H. Nguyen, "Global Sensitivity Analysis Of In-Plane Elastic Buckling Of Steel Arches," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6476–6480, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3833>.
- [7] M. N. Nguyen, X. Wang, and R. H. Leicester, "An assessment of climate change effects on atmospheric corrosion rates of steel structures," *Corrosion Engineering, Science and Technology*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 359–369, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1179/1743278213Y.0000000087>.
- [8] D. E. Klinesmith, R. H. McCuen, and P. Albrecht, "Effect of Environmental Conditions on Corrosion Rates," *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 121–129, Feb. 2007, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0899-1561\(2007\)19:2\(121\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0899-1561(2007)19:2(121)).
- [9] "Viet Nam: Environment and climate change assessment," Asian Development Bank, Mandaluyong, Philippines, 2013.
- [10] B. Ellingwood, J. G. MacGregor, T. V. Galambos, and C. A. Cornell, "Probability Based Load Criteria: Load Factors and Load Combinations," *Journal of the Structural Division*, vol. 108, no. 5, pp. 978–997, May 1982, <https://doi.org/10.1061/JSDEAG.0005959>.
- [11] M. F. Bartlett, "Updating Standard Shape Material Properties Database for Design and Reliability," *Engineering Journal-American Institute of Steel Construction*, vol. 40, pp. 2–14, 2003.
- [12] "Design of Steel Structures - Part 1.4: General rules - Supplementary rules for stainless steels.," European Committee for Standardization, CEN Brussels, ENV 1993-1-4, 1996.
- [13] M. Lemaire, A. Chateaufort, and J. C. Mitteau, *Fiabilité des structures: Couplage mécano-fiabiliste statique*. Paris: Hermes-Lavoisier, 2005.
- [14] N.-L. Tran, T.-H. Nguyen, and V.-P. Phan, "Reliability assessment of Buckling Strength for Battered Built-up Columns steel considering shear deformations," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 869, no. 5, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 052041, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/869/5/052041>.
- [15] D. X. Hung and N. T. Ha, "Assessment reliability of plan frame in the buckling condition using stochastic finite element method," *Journal of Science and Technology in Civil Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 23–30, Mar. 2016.
- [16] N. Ha T, "Reliability assessment of frame steel considering semi-rigid connections," *Journal of Materials and Engineering Structures « JMES »*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 119–126, Mar. 2019.

Local Instability Analysis for Axial Compressive Steel Columns

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Abstract-This study presents a nonlinear analysis method for steel columns considering local instability under axial compression. The stress-strain relationship of steel is developed while considering the effects of local instability utilizing the energy principles. The second-order effects are considered by stability functions, while the plasticity of steel is captured by a fiber finite element method. Nonlinear equilibrium equations are solved by the generalized displacement control method. As a result, the proposed formulations are effective, accurate, and reliable in predicting the load-carrying capacity and local instability of steel columns.

Keywords-second-order effect; local instability; stability function; steel column; plasticity

I. INTRODUCTION

Steel structures are widely used in several fields (mechanical and civil engineering, aerospace, etc.). The advantages of steel are its high strength, ductility, flexibility, and fast construction, however, instability is an important weak point of steel structures that must be evaluated carefully. Many experimental tests [1-7] were carried out to examine local buckling of steel columns (welded steel columns, high strength steel columns, stainless steel columns, etc.). Examples of local instability of a high strength steel column can be seen in [4]. Authors in [8] studied the local buckling strength of steel columns considering uniformly idealized distributed residual stress. A finite difference method was employed for predicting the plate buckling curves. Boundary conditions for plates were simply supported at loading edges, and free, simply supported, and fixed at the remaining edges. The theoretical results were compared with the experimental tests of 8 square welded steel columns. Author in [9] researched flange local instability of a steel beam with wide-flange shapes. Authors in [10] proposed explicit expressions for the collapse and elastic post-buckling of simply supported plates considering geometric imperfection. In 1977, authors in [11] studied lateral-torsional buckling of local-buckled beams employing a finite element formulation in conjunction with the effective width concept. In this solution, both elastic stiffness and geometric stiffness matrices must be updated at each load step. Authors in [12] developed a finite

strip method for the post local-buckled analysis of prismatic thin walled structures under axial compression. Authors in [13] investigated local instability of thin-walled steel box columns. Thin-walled steel box columns were pinned at two ends and were subjected to an eccentrically applied load. In 1997, authors in [5] tested local instability of stub thin-walled circular steel tubes with or without internal restraint considering residual stress and geometric imperfection. More recently, some other studies on local instability for steel members under fire load have been published [6, 14-18].

Local buckling can be easily investigated using plate, shell, or solid elements with the Finite Element Method (FEM). Authors in [19] simulated and proposed the behavior analysis of short concrete-filled steel tube columns using the FEM software ABAQUS. The effects of local buckling of steel tubes were considered by using shell elements. Authors in [20] developed a finite element simulation for normal-strength CFST members with shear connectors under bending. Authors in [21-23] analyzed several types of structures using the FEM without considering local instability. However, it is not efficient with regard to computational time if these 2D or 3D elements are used. Using line elements, local buckling is implicitly evaluated using design equations of AISC-LRFD specification [24, 25]. Authors in [26-33] studied several works on the nonlinear inelastic behavior of steel frames, but the effects of local instability were not investigated.

In this study, the displacement FEM using one fiber element per member [34-39] is improved to consider local instability. A numerical procedure based on the generalized displacement control method [40] is developed to solve the nonlinear equations of the structural system. The proposed formulations are shown in detail in the following sections.

II. STEEL BEHAVIOR CONSIDERING LOCAL BUCKLING

Local buckling of steel profiles under axial compression is considered by the stress-strain curve as drawn in Figure 2. It is assumed that the whole section will start to buckle at a critical strain ε_{cr}^C greater than the yielding strain ε_y . The inelastic

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post-instability response is estimated based on a strain energy method of the component plates as formulated in (1)-(5). The relation between the effective width of the plate b_e and the full width b is:

$$\frac{b_e}{b} \approx \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_y} = \frac{U_B - U_A}{U_B} \quad (1)$$

where σ_y is the yielding stress, ε_y is the yielding strain, U_B and U_A are the strain energy before and after the occurred inelastic local instability. They are formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} U_B &= \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_y \sigma_y + (\varepsilon_{cr} - \varepsilon_y) \sigma_y \\ &= \left(\varepsilon_{cr} - \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_y \right) \sigma_y \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$U_A = \frac{1}{2} (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_{cr}) (\sigma_y + \sigma) \quad (3)$$

in which the critical strain ε_{cr} is calculated from the critical stress σ_{cr} as [41]:

$$\varepsilon_{cr} = \frac{\sigma_{cr}}{E} = \frac{k\pi^2}{12(1-\nu^2)(b/t)^2} \quad (4)$$

where E and ν are the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of material, b is the considering width of the plate, t is the thickness of the plate, and k is the buckling coefficient given in [42].

Fig. 1. Assumed stress-strain curve for local buckling of steel.

After substituting (2) and (3) into (1), the inelastic post-local instability behavior can be estimated by:

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_y} = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha \left(\frac{1 - \frac{\varepsilon_{cr}}{\varepsilon}}{1 - \frac{\varepsilon_y}{2\varepsilon}} \right)} \quad (5)$$

where α is an adjusting parameter of the slope of the post-instability behavior.

III. FORMULAS FOR THE NONLINEAR COLUMN ELEMENT

A. Second-Order and Shear Deformation Effects

The stability functions proposed in [43] are employed to simulate the second-order effect by using only one element per member. From [34, 35, 38, 39], the incremental equilibrium equation of a column element, considering both shear deformation and the second-order effects is written as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Delta P \\ \Delta M_{yA} \\ \Delta M_{yB} \\ \Delta M_{zA} \\ \Delta M_{zB} \\ \Delta T \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{EA}{L} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_{1y} & C_{2y} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_{2y} & C_{1y} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{1z} & C_{2z} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{2z} & C_{1z} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{GJ}{L} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta \delta \\ \Delta \theta_{yA} \\ \Delta \theta_{yB} \\ \Delta \theta_{zA} \\ \Delta \theta_{zB} \\ \Delta \phi \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where ΔP , ΔT , ΔM_{yA} , ΔM_{yB} , ΔM_{zA} , and ΔM_{zB} are the axial force, torsion and bending moments respectively, $\Delta \delta$, $\Delta \phi$, $\Delta \theta_{yA}$, $\Delta \theta_{yB}$, $\Delta \theta_{zA}$, and $\Delta \theta_{zB}$ are the axial shortening and rotations respectively, A is the sectional area, J is the moment of inertia around the z axis, L is the element length, G is the shear modulus of steel, and C_{1y} , C_{2y} , C_{1z} , and C_{2z} are respectively the flexural stiffness coefficients considering the shear deformation, estimated as:

$$C_{1y} = \frac{k_{1y}^2 - k_{2y}^2 + k_{1y} A_{sz} GL}{2k_{1y} + 2k_{2y} + A_{sz} GL} \quad (7)$$

$$C_{2y} = \frac{-k_{1y}^2 + k_{2y}^2 + k_{2y} A_{sz} GL}{2k_{1y} + 2k_{2y} + A_{sz} GL} \quad (8)$$

$$C_{1z} = \frac{k_{1z}^2 - k_{2z}^2 + k_{1z} A_{sy} GL}{2k_{1z} + 2k_{2z} + A_{sy} GL} \quad (9)$$

$$C_{2z} = \frac{-k_{1z}^2 + k_{2z}^2 + k_{2z} A_{sy} GL}{2k_{1z} + 2k_{2z} + A_{sy} GL} \quad (10)$$

where $k_{1n} = S_{1n} (EI_n / L)$ and $k_{2n} = S_{2n} (EI_n / L)$. S_{1n} and S_{2n} are the stability functions with the axis of n ($n = y, z$) and are written as:

$$S_{1n} = \begin{cases} \frac{h_n L \sin(h_n L) - (h_n L)^2 \cos(h_n L)}{2 - 2 \cos(h_n L) - h_n L \sin(h_n L)} & \text{if } P < 0 \\ \frac{(h_n L)^2 \cosh(h_n L) - h_n L \sinh(h_n L)}{2 - 2 \cosh(h_n L) + h_n L \sinh(h_n L)} & \text{if } P > 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$S_{2n} = \begin{cases} \frac{(h_n L)^2 - h_n L \sin(h_n L)}{2 - 2 \cos(h_n L) - h_n L \sin(h_n L)} & \text{if } P < 0 \\ \frac{h_n L \sin(h_n L) - (h_n L)^2}{2 - 2 \cosh(h_n L) + h_n L \sinh(h_n L)} & \text{if } P > 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

which $h_n^2 = |P|/EI_n$. EA and EI_n are the axial and flexural stiffnesses of the column and are calculated by:

$$EA = \sum_{j=1}^p w_j \left(\sum_{i=1}^m E_i A_i \right)_j \quad (13)$$

$$EI_y = \sum_{j=1}^p w_j \left[\sum_{i=1}^m E_i (A_i z_i^2 + I_{yi}) \right]_j \quad (14)$$

$$EI_z = \sum_{j=1}^p w_j \left[\sum_{i=1}^m E_i (A_i y_i^2 + I_{zi}) \right]_j \quad (15)$$

where p is the number of meshed sections per element, m is the number of fibres divided on the meshed sections, w_j is the weight parameters for Lobatto quadrature at the j^{th} section [44], E_i and A_i are the elastic modulus of the material and the area of i^{th} fiber respectively, I_{yi} and I_{zi} are the y-axis and z-axis moments of inertia of the i^{th} fiber around its centroid, y_i and z_i are the coordinates of the i^{th} fiber to the central bending axis of the section as illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Meshing of the steel column.

B. Effects of Plasticity

To predict the plasticity along the member, a fiber column model as plotted in Figure 2 is used. Figure 3 shows the residual stress pattern shape [45] used in this study. The section deformations are estimated by three strain resultants: the axial strain ϵ and curvatures χ_z and χ_y . The force resultants are the axial force N and the flexural moments M_z and M_y . The sectional forces and deformations are calculated as:

$$\text{Sectional force } \{Q\} = [N \quad M_y \quad M_z]^T \quad (16)$$

$$\text{Sectional deformation } \{q\} = [\epsilon \quad \chi_y \quad \chi_z]^T \quad (17)$$

Fig. 3. Assumed residual stress pattern for the steel column.

IV. VERIFICATION

In [46], two experimental tests were carried out for I-sections with strengthening stiffeners at column bases. The elastic modulus is 200000MPa and the yield stress is 265MPa. The ratio of the width per the thickness (b/t) of specimens changed from 20 to 25. The initial residual stresses measured in [46] were 17% to 19% of the yield stress as listed in Table I, along with the column geometries. The load ratio-axial shortening curves captured by the proposed formulation are compared with ABAQUS in Figures 4 and 5. It can be seen that the proposed curve including local buckling nearly matches with the result of ABAQUS (Figure 4). Table II presents a comparison of the ultimate compressive load estimated by experimental tests, ABAQUS, and the proposed formulation (LB: Local Buckling). The ultimate load estimated by the proposed formulation is slightly higher than the results of experimental tests and ABAQUS. There are big differences between considering local buckling or not in the analysis procedure. The clear differences occur due to the plastic elastic regime of the steel fibers.

TABLE I. GEOMETRIES OF SPECIMENS TESTED IN [46]

Specimen	Geometric characteristics					
	b (mm)	t (mm)	b/t	A (mm ²)	L (mm)	σ_r/σ_y
HI1	60	3	20	1062	900	0.18
HI2	75	3	25	1332	900	0.19

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF ULTIMATE COMPRESSION LOAD

Specimen	P_{Test} (kN) [46]	P_{Ana}/P_{Test}		
		ABAQUS	Proposed (with LB)	Proposed (without LB)
HI1	260	0.949	1.011	1.090
HI2	250	1.075	1.205	1.427

Fig. 4. Load ratio-axial shortening curve of HI1 column.

Fig. 5. Load ratio-axial shortening curve of HI2 column.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the finite element analysis formulation for the second-order inelastic steel columns considering local instability was developed successfully. By using one element per member, the proposed formulation reduced computational time and computer resources. The results are in good accordance with the results of ABAQUS and the experimental tests. The proposed formulation can be applied in the development of practical engineering software.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Uy, "Local and post-local buckling of concrete filled steel welded box columns," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 47–72, Aug. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0143-974X\(98\)80102-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0143-974X(98)80102-8).
- [2] L. Gardner and M. Theofanous, "Discrete and continuous treatment of local buckling in stainless steel elements," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 64, no. 11, pp. 1207–1216, Nov. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2008.07.003>.
- [3] G. Shi, K. Xu, H. Ban, and C. Lin, "Local buckling behavior of welded stub columns with normal and high strength steels," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 119, pp. 144–153, Mar. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2015.12.020>.
- [4] A. Sharhan, W. Wang, X. Li, and H. Al-azzani, "Steady and transient state tests on local buckling of high strength Q690 steel stub columns," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 167, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 108214, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2021.108214>.
- [5] M. D. O'Shea and R. Q. Bridge, "Local buckling of thin-walled circular steel sections with or without internal restraint," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 137–157, Feb. 1997, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0143-974X\(97\)80891-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0143-974X(97)80891-7).
- [6] K.-C. Yang, S.-J. Chen, C.-C. Lin, and H.-H. Lee, "Experimental study on local buckling of fire-resisting steel columns under fire load," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 553–565, Apr. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2004.07.001>.
- [7] G. Shi, W. Zhou, and C. Lin, "Experimental Investigation on the Local Buckling Behavior of 960 MPa High Strength Steel Welded Section Stub Columns," *Advances in Structural Engineering*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 423–437, Mar. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1260/1369-4332.18.3.423>.
- [8] F. Nishino and L. Tall, "Residual Stress and Local Buckling Strength of Steel Columns," *Proceedings of the Japan Society of Civil Engineers*, vol. 1969, no. 172, pp. 79–96, 1969, https://doi.org/10.2208/jsej1969.1969.172_79.
- [9] M. G. Lay, "Flange Local Buckling in Wide-Flange Shapes," *Journal of the Structural Division*, vol. 91, no. 6, pp. 95–116, Dec. 1965, <https://doi.org/10.1061/JSDEAG.0001371>.
- [10] R. G. Dawson and A. C. Walker, "Post-Buckling of Geometrically Imperfect Plates," *Journal of the Structural Division*, vol. 98, no. 1, pp. 75–94, Jan. 1972, <https://doi.org/10.1061/JSDEAG.0003145>.
- [11] S. T. Wang, M. I. Yost, and Y. L. Tien, "Lateral buckling of locally buckled beams using finite element techniques," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 469–475, Jun. 1977, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949\(77\)90084-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7949(77)90084-0).
- [12] T. R. Graves Smith and S. Sridharan, "A finite strip method for the post-locally-buckled analysis of plate structures," *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 12, pp. 833–842, Jan. 1978, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7403\(78\)90009-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7403(78)90009-7).
- [13] J. Y. Richard Liew, N. E. Shanmugam, and S. L. Lee, "Local buckling of thin-walled steel box columns," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 119–145, Jan. 1989, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0263-8231\(89\)90039-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0263-8231(89)90039-6).
- [14] M. Knobloch and M. Fontana, "Strain-based approach to local buckling of steel sections subjected to fire," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 44–67, Jan. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2005.04.007>.
- [15] C. Maraveas, "Local Buckling of Steel Members Under Fire Conditions: A Review," *Fire Technology*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 51–80, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10694-018-0768-1>.
- [16] Z. Xing, M. Kucukler, and L. Gardner, "Local buckling of stainless steel plates in fire," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 148, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 106570, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2019.106570>.
- [17] W. Wang, X. Li, and H. Al-azzani, "Experimental study on local buckling of high-strength Q960 steel columns at elevated temperatures," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 183, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 106716, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2021.106716>.
- [18] Z. Xing, M. Kucukler, and L. Gardner, "Local buckling of stainless steel I-sections in fire: Finite element modelling and design," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 161, Apr. 2021, Art. no. 107486, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2021.107486>.

- [19] P. C. Nguyen, D. D. Pham, T. T. Tran, and T. Nghia-Nguyen, "Modified Numerical Modeling of Axially Loaded Concrete-Filled Steel Circular-Tube Columns," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7094–7099, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4157>.
- [20] S.-E. Kim *et al.*, "Finite element simulation of normal – Strength CFDST members with shear connectors under bending loading," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 238, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 112011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2021.112011>.
- [21] T.-T. Tran, M. Hussan, D. Kim, and P.-C. Nguyen, "Distributed plasticity approach for the nonlinear structural assessment of offshore wind turbine," *International Journal of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering*, vol. 12, pp. 743–754, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnaoe.2020.09.003>.
- [22] T.-T. Tran, P.-C. Nguyen, G. So, and D. Kim, "Seismic behavior of steel cabinets considering nonlinear connections and site-response effects," *Steel and Composite Structures*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 17–29, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.12989/scs.2020.36.1.017>.
- [23] T.-T. Tran *et al.*, "Probabilistic Seismic Demand Model and Seismic Fragility Analysis of NPP Equipment Subjected to High- and Low-Frequency Earthquakes," *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, vol. 195, no. 12, pp. 1327–1346, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2021.1920796>.
- [24] S.-E. Kim, J. Lee, and J.-S. Park, "3-D second-order plastic-hinge analysis accounting for local buckling," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 81–90, Jan. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296\(02\)00122-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296(02)00122-0).
- [25] S.-E. Kim and J. Lee, "Improved refined plastic-hinge analysis accounting for local buckling," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 1031–1042, Aug. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296\(00\)00105-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296(00)00105-X).
- [26] C. Ngo-Huu, P.-C. Nguyen, and S.-E. Kim, "Second-order plastic-hinge analysis of space semi-rigid steel frames," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 60, pp. 98–104, Nov. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2012.06.019>.
- [27] P.-C. Nguyen and S.-E. Kim, "Nonlinear elastic dynamic analysis of space steel frames with semi-rigid connections," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 84, pp. 72–81, May 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2013.02.004>.
- [28] P.-C. Nguyen, N. T. N. Doan, C. Ngo-Huu, and S.-E. Kim, "Nonlinear inelastic response history analysis of steel frame structures using plastic-zone method," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 85, pp. 220–233, Dec. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2014.09.002>.
- [29] P.-C. Nguyen and S.-E. Kim, "Nonlinear inelastic time-history analysis of three-dimensional semi-rigid steel frames," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 101, pp. 192–206, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2014.05.009>.
- [30] P.-C. Nguyen and S.-E. Kim, "Distributed plasticity approach for time-history analysis of steel frames including nonlinear connections," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 100, pp. 36–49, Sep. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2014.04.012>.
- [31] P.-C. Nguyen and S.-E. Kim, "Advanced analysis for planar steel frames with semi-rigid connections using plastic-zone method," *Steel and Composite Structures*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 1121–1144, Jan. 2016.
- [32] P.-C. Nguyen and S.-E. Kim, "Investigating effects of various base restraints on the nonlinear inelastic static and seismic responses of steel frames," *International Journal of Non-Linear Mechanics*, vol. 89, pp. 151–167, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnonlinmec.2016.12.011>.
- [33] P.-C. Nguyen and S.-E. Kim, "A new improved fiber plastic hinge method accounting for lateral-torsional buckling of 3D steel frames," *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 127, pp. 666–675, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2017.12.031>.
- [34] P.-C. Nguyen and S.-E. Kim, "An advanced analysis method for three-dimensional steel frames with semi-rigid connections," *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design*, vol. 80, pp. 23–32, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.finel.2013.11.004>.
- [35] P.-C. Nguyen and S.-E. Kim, "Second-order spread-of-plasticity approach for nonlinear time-history analysis of space semi-rigid steel frames," *Finite Elements in Analysis and Design*, vol. 105, pp. 1–15, Nov. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.finel.2015.06.006>.
- [36] P. C. Nguyen, "Nonlinear Inelastic Earthquake Analysis of 2D Steel Frames," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6393–6398, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3855>.
- [37] P. C. Nguyen, B. Le-Van, and S. D. T. V. Thanh, "Nonlinear Inelastic Analysis of 2D Steel Frames: An Improvement of the Plastic Hinge Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 5974–5978, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3600>.
- [38] P.-C. Nguyen and T. D. Tran, "Impacts of residual stress and shear deformation on 2D steel frames using fiber plastic hinge element: nonlinear behavior and strength," *SN Applied Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 7, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 686, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-021-04638-w>.
- [39] P.-C. Nguyen, T.-T. Tran, and T. Nghia-Nguyen, "Nonlinear time-history earthquake analysis for steel frames," *Heliyon*, vol. 7, no. 8, Aug. 2021, Art. no. e06832, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e06832>.
- [40] Y.-B. Yang and M.-S. Shieh, "Solution method for nonlinear problems with multiple critical points," *AIAA Journal*, vol. 28, no. 12, pp. 2110–2116, 1990, <https://doi.org/10.2514/3.10529>.
- [41] G. H. Bryan, "On the Stability of a Plane Plate under Thrusts in its own Plane, with Applications to the 'Buckling' of the Sides of a Ship," *Proceedings of the London Mathematical Society*, vol. s1-22, no. 1, pp. 54–67, Nov. 1890, <https://doi.org/10.1112/plms/s1-22.1.54>.
- [42] J. H. Lee, "Local Buckling Behaviour and Design of Cold-formed Steel Compression Members at Elevated Temperatures," Ph.D. dissertation, Queensland University of Technology, Brisbane, QLD, Australia, 2004.
- [43] W.-F. Chen, *Structural Stability: Theory and Implementation*, Illustrated edition. Englewood Cliffs, NJ, USA: Prentice Hall, 1987.
- [44] H. H. Michels, "Abscissas and weight coefficients for Lobatto quadrature," *Mathematics of Computation*, vol. 17, no. 83, pp. 237–244, 1963, <https://doi.org/10.1090/S0025-5718-1963-0158540-4>.
- [45] S. Kitipornchai and A. D. Wong-Chung, "Inelastic Buckling of Welded Monosymmetric I-Beams," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 113, no. 4, pp. 740–756, Apr. 1987, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(1987\)113:4\(740\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1987)113:4(740)).
- [46] B. Uy, "Local and Postlocal Buckling of Fabricated Steel and Composite Cross Sections," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 127, no. 6, pp. 666–677, Jun. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2001\)127:6\(666\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2001)127:6(666)).

Environmental Noise Reduction based on Deep Denoising Autoencoder

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Abstract-Speech enhancement plays an important role in Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) even though this task remains challenging in real-world scenarios of human-level performance. To cope with this challenge, an explicit denoising framework called Deep Denoising Autoencoder (DDAE) is introduced in this paper. The parameters of DDAE encoder and decoder are optimized based on the backpropagation criterion, where all denoising autoencoders are stacked up instead of recurrent connections. For better speech estimation in real and noisy environments, we include matched and mismatched noisy and clean pairs of speech data to train the DDAE. The DDAE has the ability to achieve optimal results even for a limited amount of training data. Our experimental results show that the proposed DDAE outperformed the baseline algorithms. The DDAE shows superior performances based on three-evaluation metrics in noisy and clean pairs of speech data compared to three baseline algorithms.

Keywords- DDAE; limited data; noise reduction; autoencoders

I. INTRODUCTION

Speech enhancement is a key part of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) [1]. It has been implemented in many commercial products for decades, but in order to achieve human-level performance, it requires further improvement in real-world scenarios [2], e.g. when we talk to a person or a voice recognition system like an ATM verification call, many environmental noises are added and transmitted, posing difficulties to the system. To deal with such noises, speech

signal processing algorithms have been developed to improve the quality and intelligibility.

Neural network-based algorithms are more efficient in learning high-order statistical information automatically by using nonlinear processing units and are efficient for noise reduction [3, 4]. Many algorithms are proposed to train deep neural networks efficiently for speech enhancement and noise reduction [5-7]. Deep learning algorithms have been used to extract speech features and for acoustic modeling [2]. The denoising autoencoder has been used for image processing and other classification applications to extract robust features when the input is a binary masked feature for each autoencoder. For speech feature extraction, a recurrent denoising autoencoder for ASR was proposed for noise reduction in [8]. There are many conventional methods for speech signal processing. For speech enhancement, the most used algorithms are Log Minimum Mean Square Error (logMMSE) [9], Karhunen-Loeve Transforms (KLT) [10], and Robust Principal Component Analysis (RPCA) [11], which are designed with specific additive background noise based on statistical speech properties and noisy signals. However, these methods do not work in real settings when people talk in a noisy environment. Consequently, it is essential to build a framework to deal with the various types of noise in real-world environments.

This article introduces an explicit denoising framework called the Deep Denoising Autoencoder (DDAE), a variant of the denoising autoencoder. However, unlike previous works, where the input is noisy speech and the output is clean speech

for training, the DDAE is trained on datasets of matched noisy and clean pairs of speech and mismatched noisy and clean pairs of speech for speech estimation in real and live environments. In the DDAE, the parameters in the encoder and decoder (formed by multiple layers of neural networks) are optimized based on the backpropagation criterion, where all denoising autoencoders are stacked up instead of recurrent connections. The DDAE has the ability to achieve optimal results even with a limited amount of training data. Our experimental results of DDAE were compared with the speech enhancement algorithms RPCA, KLT, and logMMSE. Based on three evaluation metrics, the DDAE outperforms these three baseline algorithms in matched and mismatched noisy and clean speech.

II. THE DDAE FRAMEWORK

This article uses the DDAE framework presented in [12], which removes the noise quickly and efficiently. The DDAE can achieve optimal results even with inadequate training data. It uses the noisy signal to produce clean speech features efficiently, even under mismatched testing conditions. Unlike [13], where the denoising autoencoder was trained using clean speech only, we trained the denoising autoencoder with both noisy and clean speech data. Figure 1 shows a single-layer hidden neural autoencoder, trained on clean speech with noisy and speech data as input. It consists of one nonlinear and one linear encoding and decoding stage:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} h(\mathbf{y}_i) &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}_1 \mathbf{y}_i + \mathbf{b}) \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i &= \mathbf{W}_2 h(\mathbf{y}_i) + \mathbf{c} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{W}_1 and \mathbf{W}_2 are the weight matrices for encoding and decoding neural network connections respectively. Typically, regularization takes place when $\mathbf{W}_1 = \mathbf{W}_2^T = \mathbf{W}$. Also, \mathbf{b} is the input layer's bias vector, whereas \mathbf{c} represents the output layer's bias vector. Similarly, \mathbf{y}_i is the noisy speech signal equivalent to the clean signal \mathbf{x}_i . The nonlinear logistic function utilized by the hidden neuron is $\sigma(\mathbf{x}) = (1 + e^{-\mathbf{x}})^{-1}$. By optimizing the objective function in (2), the parameters are determined as follows:

$$L(\theta) = \sum_i \|\mathbf{x}_i - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i\|_2^2 \quad (2)$$

where the set of the parameters is defined as $\theta = \{\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}\}$. In addition to using $\mathbf{W}_1 = \mathbf{W}_2^T = \mathbf{W}$, we apply regularization on weights and hidden neural output. This improves the generalization and prevents overfitting, which is defined as follows:

$$J(\theta) = L(\theta) + \alpha \|\mathbf{W}\|_2^2 + \beta_p(h(\mathbf{y}_i)) \quad (3)$$

where $\|\mathbf{W}\|_2^2 = \sum_{ij} w_{ij}^2 \cdot p(h(\mathbf{y}_i))_{ij}^2$ is a regularization function defined on the output neurons of the hidden layers, and α and β are its weight coefficients. Thus, the parameters may be derived as follows:

$$\theta^* \triangleq \arg \min_{\theta} J(\theta) \quad (4)$$

There are numerous unconstrained optimization algorithms to solve (4) for the estimation of $\mathbf{W}^*, \mathbf{b}^*, \mathbf{c}^*$. In this framework, the linear search-based algorithm of quasi-Newton is applied.

Figure 1 depicts the DDAE training procedure using noisy and clean voice samples. The DDAE can be constructed by

stacking up several autoencoders. For the training of the DDAE, a dense layer of wisied pretraining and fine-tuning is employed. When another hidden layer is introduced during the pretraining phase, the output of the previous hidden layer is used as the input of the subsequent autoencoder. The transformed noisy and clean speech data are used for training in denoising. As illustrated in Figure 1, the training pair for the first autoencoder is \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{x} , and followed by $h\mathbf{y}_i$ and $h\mathbf{x}_i$ or the subsequent autoencoder. During the fine-tuning step, the initial network parameters are fixed as those obtained from the pretraining step. These training stages may produce a better overall result than training the DDAE with random initialization.

Fig. 1. The training process of the DDAE with noisy and clean speech data.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETTING

This section evaluates the proposed DDAE framework and the baseline algorithms for speech enhancement tasks. A clean, continuous Taiwan Mandarin Hearing In Noise Test (TMHINT) data set with 100 utterances was used for training by adding 5 noise types (machine, babble, party crowd, restaurant, vacuum cleaner) and 5 signal-to-noise ratios (SNR). Therefore, the total training dataset for noisy speech contains 2500 utterances. The first testing scenario is a matching case in which 40 utterances are added with the same two types of noises (babble and party crowd) with 5 SNR levels. Thus, the total number of match case utterances are 400. More details of the dataset can be found in [14].

We have investigated the accuracy of noise reduction, speech enhancement, and intelligibility using 3 different metrics with a defined standard range set. The range for PESQ is between -0.5 to 4.5 . As the value of PESQ increases, the quality of speech enhancement will increase. Similarly, the range for Short-Time Objective Intangibility (STOI) is between 0 and 1 . As the value of STOI increases, the number of words identified by the listener will increase. The Speech Distortion Index (SDI) is the opposite of the first two metrics, ranging between 0 and 1 . As the value of SDI decreases, so does the quality of speech enhancement. Most conventional speech enhancement algorithms are designed to filter out noisy speech

using the gain function estimation. This article compares 3 traditional algorithms, logMMSE, KLT, and RPCA, with the proposed DDAE. The unprocessed speech is named Noisy. The experimental results were evaluated using 2 matched noise types with two SNR conditions (6dB, -6dB) and 4 mismatched noise types with 3 SNR conditions (-2, 0, 2), as shown in Table I. The DDAE was trained using 5 layers, each containing 2048 neurons..

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP OF THE TMHINT DATASET

Train set	2500 utterances Noise type: Machine, cafeteria babble, crowd party, restaurant, vacuum cleaner SNR levels: -6dB, -3dB, 3dB, 6dB, 10dB
	Test set
Mismatched condition 800 utterances Noise type: Applause, baby cry, grocery store, pink noise SNR levels: -2dB, 0dB, 2dB	

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate and compare the results of the baseline algorithms with DDAE based on 3 evaluation criteria using different scenarios and SNR levels as mentioned in Table I.

Table II shows the average PESQ results, normalized across the different SNRs. Compared to the baseline algorithms, the DDAE framework has a better PESQ score, i.e. improved speech quality, for both matched and mismatched noise types. Table II demonstrates that the DDAE framework (5 hidden layer configuration, each layer containing 2048 hidden neurons) outperformed the 3 baselines algorithms, with the exception of most pink noise, where the logMMSE outperformed the DDAE framework and the other algorithms under mismatched stationary noise conditions. In addition, the DDAE exhibited a better PESQ score of speech enhancement than logMMSE, RPCA, and KLT by maintaining high scores for STOI. For instance, the average PESQ score of the DDAE is 2.55, while the PESQ scores of RPCA, logMMSE, and KLT are 2.18, 2.15, and 1.90 respectively. Compared to the baseline algorithms, on average, the PESQ score of the DDAE is higher than RPCA, logMMSE, and KLT by 16.97 %, 18.60%, and 34.21%, respectively.

TABLE II. DDAE COMPARISON WITH THE BASELINE ALGORITHMS BASED ON THE AVERAGE PESQ SCORE

Noise type	Framework				
	Noisy	KLT	logMMSE	RPCA	DDAE
Matched noise (seen noise)					
Babble	2.26	1.89	2.21	2.25	2.58
Crowd party	2.26	1.85	2.15	2.24	2.61
Mismatched noise (unseen noise)					
Applause	2.13	1.76	1.89	1.99	2.95
Baby cry	2.17	1.77	1.97	2.02	2.50
Grocery	2.19	1.80	2.09	2.18	2.26
Pink noise	2.32	2.38	2.58	2.40	2.38
AVG	2.23	1.90	2.15	2.18	2.55

Table III illustrates the average STOI score for the DDAE and baseline algorithms, with 6 noise types with different SNRs. The Table shows that the DDAE has a better STOI score for all types of noise. Moreover, the DDAE demonstrated better average speech enhancement capabilities by maintaining high STOI scores. Compared to the baseline algorithms, the average STOI score of the DDAE is higher than RPCA, logMMSE, and KLT by 16.39%, 65.11%, and 10.93% respectively.

TABLE III. ALGORITHM COMPARISON BASED ON AVERAGE STOI SCORE

Noise Type	Framework				
	Noisy	KLT	logMMSE	RPCA	DDAE
Matched Noise (seen noise)					
Babble	0.58	0.58	0.38	0.55	0.68
Crowd party	0.63	0.61	0.46	0.66	0.71
Mismatched Noise (unseen noise)					
Applause	0.69	0.68	0.57	0.697	0.73
Baby cry	0.71	0.71	0.54	0.71	0.73
Grocery	0.45	0.58	0.29	0.45	0.60
Pink noise	0.52	0.68	0.31	0.52	0.74
AVG	0.59	0.64	0.43	0.61	0.71

Table IV shows the average SDI results averaged over the different SNRs for the 6 considered noise types. The Table shows that the DDAE performs better than the other algorithms for all types of noise. In addition, the DDAE demonstrated better speech enhancement capabilities. Compared to the baseline algorithms, the SDI score of the DDAE is 22.64%, 24.07%, and 12.96%, lower than the RPCA, logMMSE, and the performance of DDAE significantly outperformed the them. Figure 2 depicts the spectrogram of a test utterance contaminated with non-stationary noise applause at SNR = -2dB achieved by different models. For comparison, the spectrograms of clean and noisy speech signals are also presented in Figure 2(a)-(b). The spectrograms of the test utterance enhanced by logMMSE, KLT, and RPCA algorithms are shown in Figures 2(c)-(e), while Figure 2(f) depicts the spectrogram of the enhanced speech signals produced by the DDAE. Figure 2 clearly demonstrates that the DDAE framework efficiently restores clean speech under very challenging conditions (non-stationary noise, -2dB SNR) and effectively suppresses noise components from the noisy signal (Figure 2(b)). DDAE suppresses noise components more effectively and produces better speech quality than the previous approaches.

TABLE IV. ALGORITHM COMPARISON BASED ON THE AVERAGE SDI SCORE

Noise Type	Framework				
	Noisy	KLT	logMMSE	RPCA	DDAE
Matched noise (seen noise)					
Babble	0.61	0.45	0.48	0.50	0.40
Crowd party	0.61	0.48	0.48	0.50	0.38
Mismatched noise (unseen noise)					
Applause	0.61	0.55	0.585	0.58	0.41
Baby cry	0.61	0.56	0.59	0.56	0.38
Grocery	0.61	0.52	0.55	0.53	0.50
Pink noise	0.61	0.25	0.57	0.53	0.39
AVG	0.61	0.47	0.54	0.53	0.41

Fig. 2. Spectrograms of (a) clean, (b) noisy, (c) logMMSE, (d) KLT, (e) RPCA, and (f) DDAE. A noise of -2dB was added to the test utterance.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, the DDAE framework for speech enhancement of environmental noise is presented. The proposed framework provides a more understandable speech to the listener. The major contributions of this study are the introduction of the DDAE framework, which enhances speech intelligibility over 4 different baseline methods, and the confirmation, based on experimental data, that this proposed framework can improve speech performance. These contributions allow our proposed architecture to serve as a straightforward and efficient means of bridging the acoustic mismatch condition.

The DDAE framework provides better generalization and a universal approximation capability. For mismatch and non-stationary conditions, DDAE has better generalization performance compared to the conventional speech enhancement techniques. The experimental results demonstrate that even with insufficient training data, our proposed framework outperformed KLT, logMMSE, and RPCA under both matched and mismatched noise conditions at varying SNR levels. This is confirmed by the evaluation results, which show that DDAE outperforms the other algorithms on all levels, except for stationary noise where the logMMSE approach performs better. In addition, the comparative findings demonstrate that our method provides superior enhancement performance based on 3 widely used objective metrics. It is essential to find the ideal compromise between the parameter efficiency and the speech enhancement performance of the model. However, the majority of the baseline models cannot deliver great parameter efficiency. The experimental results suggest that the proposed model is superior to other speech enhancement frameworks in terms of trade-off.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Helali, Z. Hajaiej, and A. Cherif, "Real time speech recognition based on PWP thresholding and MFCC using SVM," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6204-6208, Oct., 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3759>.
- [2] G. E. Dahl, D. Yu, L. Deng, and A. Acero, "Context-Dependent Pre-Trained Deep Neural Networks for Large-Vocabulary Speech Recognition," *IEEE Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 30-42, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASL.2011.2134090>.

- [3] X. Lu, M. Unoki, S. Matsuda, C. Hori, and H. Kashioka, "Controlling Tradeoff Between Approximation Accuracy and Complexity of a Smooth Function in a Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Space for Noise Reduction," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 61, no. 3, pp. 601-610, Oct. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2012.2229991>.
- [4] Y. Bengio, "Learning Deep Architectures for AI," *Foundations and Trends® in Machine Learning*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1-127, Nov. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1561/2200000006>.
- [5] A. A. Alasadi, T. H. Aldhayni, R. R. Deshmukh, A. H. Alahmadi, and A. S. Alshebami, "Efficient Feature Extraction Algorithms to Develop an Arabic Speech Recognition System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5547-5553, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3465>.
- [6] A. Samad, A. U. Rehman, and S. A. Ali, "Performance Evaluation of Learning Classifiers of Children Emotions using Feature Combinations in the Presence of Noise," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5088-5092, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3193>.
- [7] M. Ranzato, F. J. Huang, Y.-L. Boureau, and Y. LeCun, "Unsupervised Learning of Invariant Feature Hierarchies with Applications to Object Recognition," in *2007 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, Minneapolis, MN, USA, Jun. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2007.383157>.
- [8] A. L. Maas, Q. V. Le, T. M. O'Neil, O. Vinyals, P. Nguyen, and A. Y. Ng, "Recurrent Neural Networks for Noise Reduction in Robust ASR," in *Proceedings of The International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, & Signal Processing*, Dec. 2012.
- [9] Y. Ephraim and D. Malah, "Speech enhancement using a minimum mean-square error log-spectral amplitude estimator," *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 443-445, Apr. 1985, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TASSP.1985.1164550>.
- [10] U. Mittal and N. Phamdo, "Signal/noise KLT based approach for enhancing speech degraded by colored noise," *IEEE Transactions on Speech and Audio Processing*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 159-167, Mar. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1109/89.824700>.
- [11] E. J. Candès, X. Li, Y. Ma, and J. Wright, "Robust principal component analysis?," *Journal of the ACM*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 11:1-11:37, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1145/1970392.1970395>.
- [12] X. Lu, Y. Tsao, S. Matsuda, and C. Hori, "Speech enhancement based on deep denoising autoencoder," in *Interspeech 2013*, Aug. 2013, pp. 436-440, <https://doi.org/10.21437/Interspeech.2013-130>.
- [13] P. Vincent, H. Larochelle, I. Lajoie, Y. Bengio, and P.-A. Manzagol, "Stacked Denoising Autoencoders: Learning Useful Representations in a Deep Network with a Local Denoising Criterion," *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 11, pp. 3371-3408, Sep. 2010.
- [14] L. L. N. Wong, S. D. Soli, S. Liu, N. Han, and M.-W. Huang, "Development of the Mandarin Hearing in Noise Test (MHINT)," *Ear and Hearing*, vol. 28, no. 2 Suppl, pp. 70S-74S, Apr. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1097/AUD.0b013e31803154d0>.

Determination of the Harmonic Losses in an Induction Motor Fed by an Inverter

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Abstract-The advancement, development, improvement, and increased use of power electronic converters led to the efficient speed control of electrical drives. The most famous three-phase induction motor-related control to Pulse-Width Modulation (PWM) technique is used to operate multilevel inverters such as variable-frequency or six-step Voltage Source Inverter (VSI). Switching devices of the inverter are used in the drive systems and act as the main source of harmonics. When the induction motor is fed from the PWM inverter, it will be supplied by low order (5th, 7th, 11th) time harmonic voltage. The motor performance is affected by the presence of these time harmonic components because the additional losses generated in the motor defect its performance, generate pulsating torque, and reduce efficiency. In this work, the analysis of a dynamic model of an induction motor in transient and steady-state operation is developed, considering the effect of time-harmonic voltages generated by the inverter, skin effect, skew effect, temperature rise effect, iron core loss, stray load loss, and magnetic saturation on the motor performance. The performance of the motor is studied by the time-harmonic equivalent circuit and by the fundamental equivalent circuit. The motor performance in terms of efficiency and power factor is compared with the experimental results for both sinusoidal and VSI motor feeds in order to validate the model accuracy.

Keywords-dynamic modeling; additional losses; 3-phase bridge inverter; 3-phase diode rectifier; harmonic equivalent circuit; switching functions

I. INTRODUCTION

It has been observed that the electrical machine losses increase if the supply voltage has harmonics. This gained attention at the early '70s, as the machines were supplied with static six-step inverters. The additional Ohmic losses were produced in the machine windings due to the flowing of harmonic currents. The Ohmic losses in the rotor windings of the induction machines can increase considerably due to the skin effect. There is also an increase in the machine iron losses due to the flowing of harmonic currents [1-5]. At low harmonic frequency (< 2.5kHz), the harmonic losses are also increased with the machine load due to the slight reduction of the machine inductances caused by the saturation effect [6-7]. Measuring the harmonic losses in electrical machines is a very

complex task, and its determination by subtracting the output power from the input power is very sensitive to errors of measurement [8]. At the beginning of this century, the calculation of harmonic losses was extended by numerical methods with computer analysis based on the Finite Element Method (FEM) [9-11]. In numerical methods, the computational process is a heavy burden and the complete structure of the machine has to be known [12]. The early adopted six-step inverters showed a defect in machine performance due to the pulsating torques and increasing harmonic losses [13-14]. In modern semiconducting techniques, the switching frequency and modulation index of PWM variable speed drives can be allowed to be further increased and eliminate all harmonics below the switching frequency. Although this technique can increase the machine performance and reduce noise emissions, the machine harmonic losses cannot be reduced considerably by increasing the switching frequency above 10kHz [15-24]. To model the harmonic losses of the induction machines with different power ratings, a complete equivalent circuit including all harmonic loss components was first presented in [5]. In this circuit, the resistances are connected in parallel to the leakage inductances accounting for the harmonic stray load losses in the machine windings. The harmonic losses due to the skew-effect and skin-effect are not included in this equivalent circuit model. All the equivalent circuit impedances must be frequency-dependent to take effect on the skin [25-28].

Variable speed drives are commonly used in many industrial applications. To supply the motor with variable frequency, the induction motor is fed from the six-step uncontrolled rectifier and the rectifier output is connected to the six-step Voltage Source Inverter (VSI). Two capacitors are connected across the rectifier output to remove the ripple. Due to the motor being fed from the switching inverter, the dynamic model developed to study the motor performance must be valid for any voltage and current waveform. A complete dynamic model is required for harmonics analysis. The model must include the main parameters of the machine for transient and steady-state operation. In this paper, an accurate dynamic model of the induction motor fed from a six-step VSI is presented using the switching functions for inverter modeling and the D-Q axes synchronously rotating reference frame

model for induction motor modeling. In this comprehensive modeling, the harmonics, as additional losses, are calculated and analyzed easily. The accuracy of the model has been verified through Matlab simulations and the harmonic equivalent circuit of the machine, which is presented in this work as a powerful tool for motor performance calculation.

II. MODELING OF THE INDUCTION MOTOR

An accurate estimation parameter of the induction motor-equivalent circuit is required to implement these parameters for high-performance determination. The stator and rotor winding temperatures can be determined according to the IEEE standard 112-B by measuring the stator no-load and load currents, and

the rotor current is determined at different load conditions. The skin effect on the stator parameters can be determined from the stator geometry. The iron core resistances are determined from the no-load test considering the effect of slip and core temperature. The magnetizing reactance is calculated from the no-load test at different supply voltages and rated frequencies to consider the saturation effect. The stator and rotor winding resistances R_s and \hat{R}_r depend on temperature variation and skin effect. The stator and rotor leakage reactances $X_{\ell s}$ and $\hat{X}_{\ell r}$ depend on skin effect and saturation. The magnetizing inductance X_m depends on the magnetic saturation. The iron core resistance R_{ic} depends on motor slip and iron core temperature.

Fig. 1. The proposed fundamental circuit of induction motor.

The proposed equivalent circuit in Figure 1 contains the additional resistances R_{sssl} and R_{rssl} that model the stray losses in the stator and rotor circuits. The stray losses depend on the voltage drops due to the leakage reactance, the iron core resistances, and stator and rotor resistance. Also, the proposed equivalent circuit can deal with the effect of rotor skewing on the parameters of the rotor circuit. The iron core resistance is varied with the temperature and air-gap voltage and is calculated from the no-load test of the motor as [25]:

$$R_{ic} = V_g^2 / [K_T * (P_{nl} - I_o^2 * R_s)] \quad (1)$$

$$V_g = X_m * I_m = X_m * I_o * \sin(\phi_o) \quad (2)$$

$$I_m = \left[\frac{Q_{nl} - I_o^2 * X_{\ell s}}{X_m} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

where V_g is the magnetizing voltage per phase and is calculated in terms of magnetizing reactance X_m , magnetizing current I_m , no-load current I_o , and no-load sine of power factor angle $\sin\phi_o$. The iron core resistance was obtained in terms of air-gap voltage from the no-load test and curve-fitting technique [25]. $K_T = (1-D)$ is the temperature coefficient of the iron core loss, and D is the iron core power loss varying rate per $^{\circ}C$ determined as [25]:

$$D = [P_{ic}(T_o) - P_{ic}(T)] / P_{ic}(T_o) \quad (4)$$

where $P_{ic}(T_o)$ and $P_{ic}(T)$ represent the iron core power losses at ambient temperature and at any temperature. These iron core power losses are measured from the no-load test. P_{nl} is the active no-load power loss per phase, R_{s0} is the stator resistance per phase at ambient temperature, Q_{nl} is the reactive no-load

power loss per phase, and $X_{\ell s}$ is the stator leakage reactance per phase. The rotor load resistance $\hat{R}_r(1-s)/s$ is derived in terms of rotor phase resistance \hat{R}_r and rotor series stray loss resistance R_{rssl} as:

$$\hat{R}_r(1-s)/s = 1 / \left[1 / \left\{ \frac{\hat{R}_r(1-s)}{s} - R_{rssl} \right\} - 1 / R_{fw} \right] \quad (5)$$

where R_{fw} is the mechanical loss resistance. The nonlinearity of the machine iron core and mechanical resistances due to the saturation of the magnetic core is considered by the dynamic model to improve the accuracy of simulation results. The resistances R_{ic} and R_{fw} are determined practically from the no-load test at zero slip to be modeled by polynomial-curve fitting as:

$$R_{ic} = -0.0001985 * V_g^3 + 0.111 * V_g^2 - 23.11 * V_g + 840 \quad (6)$$

$$R_{fw} = -6.167 * V_g^4 + 0.00419 * V_g^3 - 1.074 * V_g^2 + 127.4 * V_g + 560 \quad (7)$$

The resistance of the iron core R_{ic} can be referred to on the stator and rotor circuits as a voltage drop to keep the dynamic 4th order model fixed while the effect of the iron core loss in the dynamic model of Figure 2 is considered. The reflecting resistances on the stator circuit R_{ssic} and on the rotor circuit R_{rsic} are calculated as [26]:

$$R_{ssic} = (R_{ic} * \omega_s * L_M) / [R_{ic}^2 + (\omega_s + L_M)^2] \quad (8)$$

$$R_{rsic} = s * R_{ssic} \quad (9)$$

where s is the motor slip and L_M is the magnetizing inductance per phase obtained from the no-load test as:

$$L_M = X_m / \omega_s \quad (10)$$

where $\omega_s = (2 * \pi * f)$ is the angular frequency in rad/s.

The modified magnetizing inductance L_m of the dynamic model (Figure 2) is calculated as:

$$L_m = L_M * R_{ic}^2 / [R_{ic}^2 + (\omega_s * L_M)^2] \quad (11)$$

The stray load loss resistances vary with the variation of stator and rotor resistances due to the temperature variation. These resistances are derived and introduced in the dynamic model as series resistances in the stator and rotor circuits [27]:

$$R_{SS\ell} = (\omega_s * L_{\ell s})^2 * R_s / [R_s^2 + (\omega_s * L_{\ell s})^2] \quad (12)$$

$$R_{rSS\ell} = S^2 * (\omega_s * L'_{\ell r})^2 / R'_r \quad (13)$$

where $R_{SS\ell}$ and $R_{rSS\ell}$ are the series stator and rotor winding stray-load loss resistances respectively, S is the motor slip, and $L_{\ell r}$ is the rotor leakage inductance per phase.

All induction motors and generators operate in the saturation region and their characteristics are non-linear. The variation of magnetizing reactance X_m is the main factor in producing the magnetizing voltage V_g , which is the main factor that produces the iron-core losses, rotor current, mechanical losses, and output power. The saturation reduces V_g and tends to increase. The saturation effect is taken by the relation $X_m = f(I_m)$. This function is obtained practically from the no-load test by varying the supply voltage from 125% to 25% of the rated value. Then the measurements of X_m and I_m can be interpolated by the curve fitting technique.

Fig. 2. (a) D-axis and (b) Q-axis equivalent circuit models of the induction motor in the synchronously rotating frame.

The rotor phase leakage reactance $\hat{X}_{\ell r}$ is corrected by the skew factor K_{sq} [25]:

$$\hat{X}_{\ell r} = \frac{X_m}{K_{sq}^2} (1 - K_{sq}^2) + \frac{X_{\ell r}}{K_{sq}^2} \quad (14)$$

$$K_{sq} = \sin\left(\frac{\pi * P_p}{Q_r}\right) / (\pi * P_p / Q_r) \quad (15)$$

where P_p is the machine magnetic pole-pair, and Q_r is the number of rotor slots (bars).

The rotor phase resistance is corrected by the skew factor as:

$$\hat{R}_r = \hat{R}_r / K_{sq}^2 \quad (16)$$

The rotor phase resistance and leakage reactance are corrected by the skin effect as [25]:

$$\hat{\hat{R}}_r = \hat{R}_r * [0.5 + 0.5 * \sqrt{S_r / S_m}] \quad (17)$$

$$\hat{\hat{X}}_{\ell r} = \hat{X}_{\ell r} * [0.4 + 0.6 * \sqrt{S_m / S_r}] \quad (18)$$

where S_r is the rated machine slip and S_m is the machine slip at maximum torque which can be given as [27]:

$$S_m = (\hat{R}_r + R_{rSS\ell}) / [(R_s + R_{SS\ell})^2 + (X_{\ell s} + \hat{X}_{\ell r})^2]^{1/2} \quad (19)$$

Also, the machine slip can be corrected due to the temperature effect as [25]:

$$\dot{S}_{r,m} = S_{r,m} * (T_r + K_a) / (T_{ref} + K_a) \quad (20)$$

where T_r is the rotor bar temperature at any load, T_{ref} is the temperature of insulation class level, which can be obtained from the insulation class table, and K_a is a constant equal to 225 for aluminum rotor bar type.

The dynamic electrical equations of the induction motor are derived from the proposed equivalent circuit in Figure 2 as:

$$v_{sd} = (R_s + R_{ss\ell} + R_{ssic}) i_{sd} + R_{ssic} * \dot{i}_{rd} - \omega_s * L_m * \dot{i}_{rq} \quad (21)$$

$$v_{sq} = \omega_s * (L_{\ell s} + L_m) * i_{sq} + \omega_s * L_m * \dot{i}_{rd} \quad (22)$$

$$o = R_{rsic} * i_{sd} + (\dot{R}_r + R_{rs\ell} + R_{rsic}) * \dot{i}_{rd} + \omega_{s\ell} * (\dot{L}_{\ell r} + L_m) \dot{i}_{rq} \quad (23)$$

$$o = \omega_{s\ell} * L_m * i_{sd} + \omega_{s\ell} * (\dot{L}_{\ell r} + L_m) * \dot{i}_{rd} + (\dot{R}_r + R_{rs\ell} + R_{rsic}) * \dot{i}_{rq} \quad (24)$$

where $\omega_{s\ell} = \omega_s - \omega_r = s * \omega_s$ is the slip speed in rad/s, $\omega_r = P_p * \omega_m$ is the electrical angular speed of the motor in rad/s, and $\psi_{sd}, \psi_{sq}, \dot{\psi}_{rd}$ and $\dot{\psi}_{rq}$ are the stator and rotor flux linkages in the D-Q axes of Figure 2 respectively, defined as :

$$\psi_{sd} = L_{\ell s} * i_{sd} + L_m * i_{md} \quad (25)$$

$$\psi_{sq} = L_{\ell s} * i_{sq} + L_m * i_{mq} \quad (26)$$

$$\dot{\psi}_{rd} = \dot{L}_{\ell r} * \dot{i}_{rd} + L_m * \dot{i}_{md} \quad (27)$$

$$\dot{\psi}_{rq} = \dot{L}_{\ell r} * \dot{i}_{rq} + L_m * \dot{i}_{mq} \quad (28)$$

where $i_{sd}, \dot{i}_{rd}, i_{sq}$, and \dot{i}_{rq} are stator and rotor currents in the D and Q axes respectively.

The rotor mechanical speed ω_m is calculated from the dynamic mechanical model as:

$$\frac{d\omega_m}{dt} = \frac{1}{J} (T_e - T_\ell - V_f * \omega_m) \quad (29)$$

where T_e is the electromagnetic torque of the motor, calculated as [27]:

$$T_e = \left(\frac{3}{2}\right) * P_p * L_m * (i_{sd} * \dot{i}_{rq} - i_{sq} * \dot{i}_{rd}) \quad (30)$$

where T_ℓ is the motor load torque (N.m), J is the moment of inertia ($K_g \cdot m^2$), P_p is the magnetic pole-pair number, and V_f is the viscosity resistance factor (N.m/(rad/s)).

III. MODELING OF THE SIX-STEP VOLTAGE SOURCE INVERTER

The Matlab simulation tool was utilized for the design and analysis of the power inverter system. The switching function method can be used to represent the inverter itself. Inverter harmonics and switching losses can be calculated through simulations. The switching function method is used when the exact physical forms of the power electronic switches such as transistors and thyristors are not of concern. Using the concept of the switching function, inverters can be modeled for performance calculation. The transfer function model has several advantages in modeling VSIs. The power circuit of the inverter can be simplified into input and output variables and calculated easily, the inverter topologies can be derived easily, and the implementation of gating control pulses are simpler. Based on the theory of the transfer function of the VSI, the DC input voltage V_{dc} to the inverter and the output currents (i_a, i_b, i_c) are independent variables, while the input current I_{dc} and the output line voltages (v_{ab}, v_{bc}, v_{ca}) are dependent variables. These variables are related as [20]:

$$[v_{ab}, v_{bc}, v_{ca}] = [TF] [V_{dc}] \quad (31)$$

$$[I_{dc}] = [TF] [i_a, i_b, i_c] \quad (32)$$

where [TF] is the transfer function of the VSI, expressed in the form of switching functions of the three-phase bridge VSI. Figure 3 shows the schematic diagram of the whole system containing the VSI fed 3-phase induction motor system. The sinusoidal 3-phase supply feeds the 3-phase uncontrolled diode bridge rectifier. A DC link with two capacitances is connected across the output diode rectifier to remove the ripple. The VSI behaves as a 3-phase voltage source to the induction motor.

Fig. 3. Rectifier-inverter-induction motor system.

Let S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5 , and S_6 be the switching functions for the three legs (a, b, c). S_1 and S_4 for pole (a), S_3 and S_6 for pole (b), and S_5 and S_2 for pole (c). The switching function is defined as 1 when the switch is ON and 0 when the switch is OFF. By applying Kirchoff's voltage law to the closed-loop in

the circuit in Figure 3, taking the conditions corresponding to the switching functions for each leg and after series manipulation, the motor (load) phase voltages become [29]:

$$v_{ao} = \frac{V_{dc}}{6} (2S_1 + S_2 - S_3 - 2S_4 - S_5 + S_6) \quad (33)$$

$$v_{bo} = \frac{V_{dc}}{6} (2S_3 + S_2 - S_2 - 2S_6 - S_5 + S_4) \quad (34)$$

$$v_{co} = \frac{V_{dc}}{6} (2S_5 + S_4 - S_4 - 2S_2 - S_3 + S_6) \quad (35)$$

The input DC (I_{dc}) to the 3-phase inverter is expressed in terms of switching functions ($S_1 \rightarrow S_6$) and inverter output currents (i_a, i_b, i_c) as :

$$I_{dc} = (S_1 - S_4) \cdot i_a + (S_3 - S_6) \cdot i_b + (S_5 - S_2) \cdot i_c \quad (36)$$

IV. MODELING OF THE 3-PHASE BRIDGE RECTIFIER

By using the 3-phase bridge diode rectifier, the 3-phase AG input power supply (v_a, v_b, v_c) is converted into the DC voltage (V_{dc}) output power supply to the inverter. The input supply voltages are given as:

$$v_a = V_m \cdot \sin(\omega t) \quad (37)$$

$$v_b = V_m \cdot \sin(\omega t - 2\pi/3) \quad (38)$$

$$v_c = V_m \cdot \sin(\omega t + 2\pi/3) \quad (39)$$

where V_m is the maximum supply voltage.

The switching functions ($S_1 - S_6$) of the diode bridge rectifier have the same expression as the voltage source inverter. The input and output variables of the 3-phase diode bridge rectifier are related as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_1 & S_4 \\ S_3 & S_6 \\ S_5 & S_2 \end{bmatrix} \cdot [I_{dc}] \quad (40)$$

$$[V_{dc}] = [(S_1 - S_4) \cdot (S_3 - S_6) \cdot (S_5 - S_2)] \cdot \begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

The three-phase supply voltages are converted to D-Q axis components using the transformation matrix as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_d \\ V_q \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\omega t) & \cos(\omega t + 2\pi/3) & \cos(\omega t - 2\pi/3) \\ -\sin(\omega t) & -\sin(\omega t + 2\pi/3) & -\sin(\omega t - 2\pi/3) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

where V_d and V_q are the components of the synchronously rotating D-Q axes of the supply voltages. The output DC voltage of the bridge rectifier is expressed as:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \cdot [V_d^2 + V_q^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (43)$$

V. HARMONIC EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT AND PERFORMANCE CALCULATION

The proposed fundamental equivalent circuit of the induction motor is shown in Figure 1, where $R_s, X_{\ell s}$, and $R_{ss\ell}$ are the stator winding resistance, leakage reactance, and stray load loss resistance respectively, while $\hat{R}_r, R_{rss\ell}$, and $\hat{X}_{\ell r}$ are rotor winding resistance, stray loss resistance, and leakage reactance respectively, X_m is the magnetizing reactance, R_{ic} is the iron core loss resistance, $R_{f\omega}$ is the friction and windage (mechanical) loss resistance, and $\hat{R}_r \cdot (1-s)/s$ is the motor load resistance, considering the effect of rotor stray load

resistance $R_{rss\ell}$ and mechanical resistance $R_{f\omega}$ into account, as calculated by (5).

There are two types of harmonics generated in the induction motor. The first type is the space harmonic generated in the air gap as pulsating torques due to the magnetic interaction between different phases to produce the revolving magnetic field in the air gap. Space harmonics are reduced by improved design procedures and optimization [30]. These harmonics affect the motor starting and generate noise and vibration. The second type is the time-harmonics, which are generated due to the applications of variable frequency drives in modern power systems using six-step VSIs. Time harmonics increase the motor heat by increasing the motor temperature. The time-harmonic losses are generated due to the inverter switching and are impressed in the machine as additional losses. The additional time-harmonic losses are not load-dependent. For a balanced 3-phase inverter output voltage supply, only the odd harmonics should be taken into account. The third and its multiple harmonics are in the same phase and should also not be considered. Considering only the non-triple odd harmonics (5th, 7th, 11th, etc.), the Fourier series of the phase voltages are given as [27]:

$$v_a = V_{1m} \cdot \sin(\omega_s t) +$$

$$V_{5m} \cdot \sin(5\omega_s t) + V_{7m} \cdot \sin(7\omega_s t) + \dots \quad (44)$$

$$v_{bo} = V_{1m} \cdot \sin(\omega_s t - 120^\circ) + V_{5m} \cdot \sin(5\omega_s t - 120^\circ) + V_{7m} \cdot \sin(7\omega_s t - 120^\circ) + \dots \quad (45)$$

$$v_{co} = V_{1m} \cdot \sin(\omega_s t + 120^\circ) + V_{5m} \cdot \sin(5\omega_s t + 120^\circ) + V_{7m} \cdot \sin(7\omega_s t + 120^\circ) + \dots \quad (46)$$

where V_{1m}, V_{5m}, V_{7m} are the maximum values of the fundamental, 5th, and 7th harmonic components and ω_s is the angular frequency of the supply voltage.

For each harmonic component, the motor equivalent circuit components are approximately represented by multiplying these components by a constant factor k , which represents the order of the harmonic. The fundamental circuit of Figure 1 is converted to a time-harmonic equivalent circuit as shown in Figure 4, taking the effect of core loss resistance R_{ic} as a voltage drop in the stator and rotor circuits. Resistances R_{ssick} and R_{rsick} are reflected series resistances of the iron core harmonic resistance R_{ick} at the stator and rotor windings [25].

Fig. 4. Proposed equivalent circuit for time-harmonic calculation.

Equations (44)-(46) of the output inverter phase voltage indicate that the 5th harmonic voltage component has a negative phase sequence, whereas the 7th harmonic has a positive phase

sequence like the fundamental component. The magnetic flux generated in the air gap due to the 5th harmonics opposes that due to the 7th harmonics. The rotor speed is related to the fundamental frequency, and it appears practically constant concerning the harmonic field is given as [31]:

$$S_k = \frac{(k-1)+S}{k} \text{ for forwarding rotating fields} \quad (47)$$

$$S_k = \frac{(k+1)-S}{k} \text{ for backward rotating fields} \quad (48)$$

From Figure 4, if $k.X_m$ is assumed to approach infinity and $k.(X_{\ell_s} + \hat{X}_{\ell_r})$ is greater than R_{sk} , $R_{SS\ell}$, R_{rk} , and $R_{rSS\ell}$, then the current of the k -th harmonic component is:

$$I_k = V_k / [k \cdot (X_{\ell_s} + \hat{X}_{\ell_r})] = \frac{V_{ph}}{k^2 \cdot (X_{\ell_s} + \hat{X}_{\ell_r})} \quad (49)$$

The corresponding expression of the RMS harmonic ripple current I_h is obtained by the superposition principle as [18]:

$$I_h = [I_5^2 + I_7^2 + I_{11}^2 + I_{13}^2 + I_{17}^2 + \dots]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (50)$$

The total stator and rotor windings copper losses and stray load losses due to the fundamental and harmonic ripple currents are obtained as:

$$P_{cuss} = 3 \cdot (I_{phs}^2 + I_h^2) \cdot (R_s + R_{SS\ell}) \quad (51)$$

$$P_{cuss} = 3 \cdot (I_{phs}^2 + I_h^2) \cdot (\hat{R}_r + R_{rSS\ell}) \quad (52)$$

The stray load losses are generated in the machine essentially due to hysteresis and eddy currents induced by the stator and rotor windings leakage fluxes.

If I_{phs} is the fundamental stator phase current of the motor and I_h is the total harmonic ripple of the phase current, and by applying the superposition theorem, the stator input phase current I_s when the motor is fed from the six-step VSI is obtained as :

$$I_s = [I_{phs}^2 + I_h^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (53)$$

The total input power to the motor is:

$$P_{in} = 3 \cdot V_{ph} \cdot I_s \cdot \cos\phi \quad (54)$$

The friction and windage (mechanical) power loss due to the harmonic mechanical resistance $R_{f\omega k}$ depends on the air-gap magnetizing voltage V_g and is obtained as:

$$P_{f\omega k} = 3 \cdot V_g^2 / (k^2 \cdot R_{f\omega k}) \quad (55)$$

The iron core loss of the k -th harmonic is obtained as:

$$P_{ick} = 3 \cdot V_g^2 / R_{ick} \quad (56)$$

Then, the superposition principle is applied to find the total harmonic core losses as:

$$P_{ich} = \sum_{k=5,7,\dots} P_{ick} \quad (57)$$

The fundamental iron core losses are obtained as:

$$P_{ic} = 3 \cdot V_g^2 / R_{ic} \quad (58)$$

Then, the total iron core loss is obtained as:

$$P_{ict} = P_{ic} + P_{ich} \quad (59)$$

The simplified formula for the k -th time-harmonic electromagnetic torque T_{ek} is derived by [32]:

$$T_{ek} = \frac{3 \cdot I_{rk}^2 \cdot \hat{R}_r}{S_k \cdot \omega_{sk}} = \frac{3 \cdot I_{sk}^2 \cdot \hat{R}_r}{S_k \cdot \omega_{sk}} \quad (60)$$

where $\omega_{sk} = k \cdot \omega_s$ is the angular speed of the k -th harmonic. The k -th rotor harmonic current is equal to the k -th stator time-harmonic current because $k.X_m$ is very large. The harmonic torque is generated by the interaction between the harmonic flux of the stator and the rotor flux. The harmonic torque is smaller than the fundamental motor torque because the harmonic current and fluxes are comparable to the normal and the torque generated by the harmonic components is partially canceled by the harmonic torque that moves in the negative direction. The 5th harmonic torque opposes the 7th harmonic torque, and a similar opposition happens between the 11th and 13th harmonics [18]. The k -th time-harmonic mechanical output power from the motor is derived as:

$$P_{mk} = \frac{3 \cdot I_{rk}^2 \cdot \hat{R}_r \cdot (1-S_k)}{S_k} \quad (61)$$

The total harmonic mechanical output power is obtained by the superposition theorem as:

$$P_{mh} = \sum_{k=5,7,11,\dots} P_{mk} \quad (62)$$

Then, the net mechanical output power is determined as:

$$P_m = \frac{3 \cdot I_r^2 \cdot \hat{R}_r \cdot (1-S)}{S} - P_{mh} \quad (63)$$

The efficiency of the motor fed from the six-step VSI is:

$$\eta\% = \frac{P_m}{P_{in}} \cdot 100 \quad (64)$$

The efficiency of the motor will drop when the machine is operated with VSI due to increasing losses and heat. The losses are dissipated as heat. The harmonic currents increase the copper and iron-core losses. This leads to a higher temperature in the stator winding, iron core, and rotor bars. The power factor $\cos(\phi)$ is defined as the ratio of the output mechanical power to the apparent input power P_a as:

$$P.F = \cos(\phi) = \frac{P_m}{P_{in}} = \frac{P_m}{\sqrt{3} \cdot V_{\ell} \cdot I_{\ell}} \quad (65)$$

where V_{ℓ} and I_{ℓ} are the line supply voltage and the current of the motor.

The lagging power factor can be corrected by introducing capacitors. Since VSI has capacitors on the DC bus, this provides isolation of the induction motor as the load from the network, to improve the overall power factor of the system. When the VSI starts the induction motor, low frequency applies to the motor and high starting currents will be avoided. After that, the applied voltage and frequency are increased to accelerate the motor to the steady-state speed without drawing excessive current [33].

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To examine the validity of the dynamic model of the whole system and the harmonic equivalent circuit of the motor when

fed from the six-step VSI, the motor performance is simulated in transient and steady-state operation in Matlab and the results are compared with the ones measured when the motor is fed from the sinusoidal power supply. The parameters of the fundamental equivalent circuit at 50Hz supply are given in Table I.

TABLE I. FUNDAMENTAL EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT PARAMETERS

Machine power (KW)	R_s (Ω)	R_r (Ω)	$X_{\ell s}$ (Ω)	$X_{\ell r}$ (Ω)	X_m (Ω)	Moment of inertia ($kg.m^2$)
2.0	5.1	3.5	5.0	7.5	88.0	0.03

The iron-core and the mechanical loss resistances R_{ic} and $R_{f\omega}$ are varied with air-gap voltage V_g and their relations are generated by the curve-fitting technique as given in (6)-(7). The iron core resistance R_{ic} is reflected on the stator and rotor circuits to stay in the dynamic model of the 4th order, although the iron core is considered in the model. The reflecting resistances R_{ssic} and R_{rsic} are derived by (8)-(9). The stator and rotor stray load resistances are varied with stator and rotor phase resistances and are derived by (12)-(13).

A. Results of the Dynamic Model

Figures (5)-(8) show the starting-up motor speed, electromagnetic torque, stator phase current, and rotor phase current when the motor is fed from a 50Hz six-step VSI supply. The results show that there are harmful harmonic currents in the stator and rotor. These harmonic currents affect the motor performance by introducing pulsating torques, overheating, and noise.

Fig. 5. Start-up motor speed with inverter supply.

Fig. 6. Start-up motor torque with inverter supply.

Fig. 7. Start-up motor-stator phase current with inverter supply.

Fig. 8. Start-up motor-rotor phase current with inverter supply.

Fig. 9. Start-up motor speed with sinusoidal supply.

Fig. 10. Start-up motor torque with sinusoidal supply.

Fig. 11. Start-up motor-stator phase current with sinusoidal supply.

Fig. 12. Start-up motor-rotor phase current with sinusoidal supply.

Figures (9)-(12) show the starting-up motor speed, torque, stator phase current, and rotor phase current when the motor is fed from a 50Hz sinusoidal supply using the parameters of the fundamental equivalent circuit of the motor. The results show there are no harmonic currents in the stator and the rotor of the motor.

B. Results of the Harmonic Equivalent Circuit

Figure 13 compares the measured efficiency of the motor fed from the sinusoidal and VSI supplies with that produced from the simulations in Matlab. The supply current of the VSI contains high harmonics, which contribute to additional motor losses and cause the motor efficiency to decrease by 3% compared to that of the sinusoidal supply voltage at full load operation. Similarly, Figure 14 compares the measured power factor from the VSI supply with that measured from the sinusoidal supply. Due to the harmonic currents in the VSI supply, the power factor is reduced by 0.08 compared to that of the sinusoidal supply, while the power factor in Matlab simulation is higher than that of the sinusoidal supply operation by 0.05 at full load, because the harmonic currents are not considered in the fundamental equivalent circuit of the motor.

Figure 15 compares the measured total motor losses fed from the sinusoidal and VSI supplies with that of Matlab simulations predicted from the harmonic equivalent circuit and the fundamental equivalent circuit. Due to the VSI supply which contains high harmonic currents, the measured losses from the VSI fed motor are higher than those measured from the sinusoidal supply. The generated additional losses decrease

the motor's efficiency. The predicted total losses from the harmonic equivalent circuit are 13% higher than that of the fundamental equivalent circuit. Figure 16 shows the detailed losses of the induction motor fed from the VSI supply predicted by the Matlab simulation of the harmonic equivalent circuit.

Fig. 13. Measured motor efficiency.

Fig. 14. Measured motor power factor.

Since the iron core loss is a function of air-gap voltage and frequency, the harmonic currents add extra losses to the iron core loss. The iron core loss reached 50% of the total losses at full load operation. Also, the presence of harmonic currents causes a rise in the losses of stator and rotor windings, according to (51)-(52). The stray load losses in the stator and rotor windings are also increased due to the harmonic currents. The friction and windage losses are assumed to be fixed and not affected by the harmonic currents.

VII. CONCLUSION

The recent developments in power electronics and semiconductor material technologies improved power electronic AC

drive systems. Different circuit topologies of inverters, such as the six-step VSI have been used. In the six-step VSI fed induction motor, low order time harmonics (5^{th} , 7^{th} , 11^{th}) that lead to additional motor losses are generated. These additional losses are not load-dependent and are estimated as the difference between the no-load losses with VSI and the sinusoidal supply. The increase of total losses in the VSI supply by nearly 20% is caused by the time-harmonic currents generated by the VSI and the conduction and switching losses of the inverter. As expected, the motor efficiency with PWM-VSI supply is lower than that with the sinusoidal supply by about 3%.

Fig. 15. Measured total motor losses.

Fig. 16. Details of motor losses with VSI supply.

The stray load loss is increased by 30% with the VSI supply in comparison with the sinusoidal supply. The core losses at rated power are increased by 50% with the VSI supply, because these losses depend on the air-gap voltage and supply frequency. When the motor is operated with a VSI supply instead of a sinusoidal supply, the motor power factor is reduced by 0.08 and the stator and rotor copper losses are

increased by 30% due to the harmonic current and the skin effect. The additional losses generated with the VSI supply lead to a higher temperature in the stator and rotor windings. The harmonic currents lead to extra reactive currents resulting to a decrease of the motor power factor. When the motor operates by a VSI supply, it applies low frequency and voltage to the motor in order to avoid the high inrush current. The motor supply voltage must be kept in the same proportion with the supply frequency for all motor speeds to maintain the rated torque constant and to avoid magnetic saturation. By good design of the motor structure and the output passive filter, and increasing the inverter switching frequency, the harmonics can be mitigated.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. A. Klingshirn and H. E. Jordan, "Polyphase Induction Motor Performance and Losses on Nonsinusoidal Voltage Sources," *IEEE Transactions on Power Apparatus and Systems*, vol. PAS-87, no. 3, pp. 624–631, Mar. 1968, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAS.1968.292172>.
- [2] B. J. Chalmers and B. R. Sarkar, "Induction-motor losses due to nonsinusoidal supply waveforms," *Proceedings of the Institution of Electrical Engineers*, vol. 115, no. 12, pp. 1777–1782, Dec. 1968, <https://doi.org/10.1049/piee.1968.0311>.
- [3] H. Raphael, "Additional Losses in Pwm Inverter-Fed Squirrel Cage Motors," presented at the Conf Rec IAS 12th Annual Meeting, Los Angeles, CA, USA, Oct. 1977.
- [4] F. G. G. D. Buck, "Losses and Parasitic Torques in Electric Motors Subjected to PWM Waveforms," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. IA-15, no. 1, pp. 47–53, Jan. 1979, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.1979.4503611>.
- [5] G. C. D. Sousa, B. K. Bose, J. Cleland, R. J. Spiegel, and P. J. Chappell, "Loss modeling of converter induction machine system for variable speed drive," in *Automation Proceedings of the 1992 International Conference on Industrial Electronics, Control, Instrumentation*, Aug. 1992, pp. 114–120 vol.1, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IECON.1992.254595>.
- [6] K. Bradley, W. Cao, J. Clare, and P. Wheeler, "Predicting Inverter-Induced Harmonic Loss by Improved Harmonic Injection," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 2619–2624, Sep. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPEL.2008.2002329>.
- [7] A. Boglietti, A. Cavagnino, A. M. Knight, and Y. Zhan, "Factors Affecting Losses in Induction Motors with Non-Sinusoidal Supply," in *2007 IEEE Industry Applications Annual Meeting*, Sep. 2007, pp. 1193–1199, <https://doi.org/10.1109/07IAS.2007.187>.
- [8] W. Cao, K. J. Bradley, H. Zhang, and I. French, "Experimental Uncertainty in Estimation of the Losses and Efficiency of Induction Motors," in *Conference Record of the 2006 IEEE Industry Applications Conference Forty-First IAS Annual Meeting*, Jul. 2006, vol. 1, pp. 441–447, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IAS.2006.256558>.
- [9] A. Vamvakari, A. Kandianis, A. Kladas, and S. Manias, "High fidelity equivalent circuit representation of induction motor determined by finite elements for electrical vehicle drive applications," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 1857–1860, May 1999, <https://doi.org/10.1109/20.767395>.
- [10] Z. C. Papazacharopoulos, A. G. Kladas, and S. N. Manias, "Investigation of the switching frequency harmonics impact on PWM induction motor drive efficiency," in *2001 IEEE 32nd Annual Power Electronics Specialists Conference (IEEE Cat. No.01CH37230)*, Jun. 2001, vol. 2, pp. 1203–1208, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PESC.2001.954283>.
- [11] Z. K. Papazacharopoulos, K. V. Tatis, A. G. Kladas, and S. N. Manias, "Dynamic model for harmonic induction motor analysis determined by finite elements," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 102–108, Mar. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEC.2003.821825>.
- [12] T. C. Green, C. A. Hernández-Arámbaro, and A. C. Smith, "Losses in grid and inverter supplied induction machine drives," *IEE Proceedings - Electric Power Applications*, vol. 150, no. 6, pp. 712–724, Nov. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1049/ip-epa:20030848>.

- [13] J. M. D. Murphy and M. G. Egan, "A comparison of PWM strategies for inverter-fed induction motors," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 363–369, May 1983, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.1983.4504210>.
- [14] F. C. Zach and H. Ertl, "Efficiency optimal control for AC drives with PWM inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 987–1000, Jul. 1985, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIA.1985.349569>.
- [15] S. Chen and S.-N. Yeh, "Optimal efficiency analysis of induction motors fed by variable-voltage and variable-frequency source," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 537–543, Sep. 1992, <https://doi.org/10.1109/60.148576>.
- [16] T. Kataoka, Y. Kandatsu, and T. Akasaka, "Measurement of equivalent circuit parameters of inverter fed induction motors," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 3014–3016, Sep. 1987, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMAG.1987.1065440>.
- [17] M. Sathesh Kumar, P. Ramesh Babu, and S. Ramprasad, "Four Quadrant Operation of Direct Torque Control-SVPWM based three phase Induction Motor Drive in MATLAB/SIMULINK environment," in *2012 IEEE International Conference on Advanced Communication Control and Computing Technologies (ICACCCT)*, Dec. 2012, pp. 397–402, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICACCCT.2012.6320810>.
- [18] R. Prejbeanu, "Methods to Reduce the Harmonics Generated in the Asynchronous Motor Fed by Power Converter," *Annals of The University of Craiova, Series: Automation, Computers, Electronics and Mechatronics*, vol. 11 (38), no. 1, pp. 45–50, 2014.
- [19] R. S. Kanchan and R. R. Moghaddam, "On accuracy of loss models including VSD induced additional harmonic losses for online energy efficient control of induction motor," in *2017 IEEE 12th International Conference on Power Electronics and Drive Systems (PEDS)*, Honolulu, HI, USA, Sep. 2017, pp. 1178–1183, <https://doi.org/10.1109/PEDS.2017.8289110>.
- [20] D. Uma and K. Vijayarekha, "Modeling and simulation of VSI fed induction motor drive in Matlab Simulink", *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 584–595, Apr. 2017, <http://doi.org/10.11591/ijece.v7i2.pp584-595>.
- [21] S. Firdoush, S. Kriti, A. Raj, and S. K. Singh, "Reduction of Harmonics in Output Voltage of Inverter," *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, vol. 4, no. 2, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.17577/IJERTCONV4IS02021>.
- [22] U. B. Tayab and M. A. A. Humayun, "Modeling and Analysis of a Cascaded Battery-Boost Multilevel Inverter Using Different Switching Angle Arrangement Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1450–1454, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1094>.
- [23] V. T. Ha, P. T. Giang, and V. H. Phuong, "T-Type Multi-Inverter Application for Traction Motor Control," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8321–8327, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4776>.
- [24] D. A. Tuan, P. Vu, and N. V. Lien, "Design and Control of a Three-Phase T-Type Inverter using Reverse-Blocking IGBTs," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6614–6619, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3954>.
- [25] B. A. Nasir, "An Accurate Iron Core Loss Model in Equivalent Circuit of Induction Machines," *Journal of Energy*, vol. 2020, Feb. 2020, Art. no. 7613737, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/7613737>.
- [26] B. A. Nasir, "Modeling of self-excited induction generator in synchronously rotating frame," *International Journal of Electrical & Computer Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 1–6, May 2020.
- [27] B. A. Nasir and R. W. Daoud, "Modeling of wind turbine-self excited induction generator system with pitch angle and excitation capacitance control," *AIP Conference Proceedings*, vol. 2307, no. 1, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 020022, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0032904>.
- [28] O. M. Al-Barbarawi, "Improving Performance of the Braking Process, and Analysis Torque-Speed Characteristics of the Induction Motor," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3585–3591, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2325>.
- [29] N. Htin Win and T. Naing, "Develop a Switching Function Model and Experimental Validation of Three-Phase Step- Wave Inverter Between 120°-180° conduction," in *2018 Joint International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation, Mandalay by IEEE*, Mandalay, Myanmar, Jul. 2019.
- [30] B. A. Nasir, "Design of Squirrel-Cage Self-Excited 3-phase Induction Generator," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 181–188, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.A3198.1011121>.
- [31] B. K. Bose, "The Effect of Harmonics," in *Modern Power Electronics and AC Drives*, Upper Saddle River, N.J, USA: Prentice Hall PTR, 2002, pp. 49–55.
- [32] E. O. Anyang, "The impact of variable speed drives on energy efficient induction motors," M.S. thesis, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa, 2011.
- [33] N. H. Mugheri and M. U. Keerio, "An Optimal Fuzzy Logic-based PI Controller for the Speed Control of an Induction Motor using the V/F Method," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7399–7404, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4255>.

Evaluation of the Role of Ethylene Vinyl Acetate on the Thermo-Mechanical Properties of PET/HDPE Blends

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Abstract-In this paper, blends of recycled polyethylene terephthalate (r-PET) and high-density polyethylene (HDPE) with and without a compatibilizer were prepared using a Brabender Haake Rheocord at 270°C and 32rpm. Ethylene vinyl acetate was chosen as the compatibilizer and its proportion was set to 5, 7, and 10 wt%. The thermal properties and crystallization behavior were determined by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). Micromechanical properties were also investigated using a Vickers microindentation tester. The DSC analysis indicates that the melting temperature of r-PET and HDPE in all the blends, compatibilized and uncompatibilized, remains constant and almost the same as those of the pure component. On the other hand, it is shown that the degree of crystallinity of HDPE in the blends calculated by DSC depends on the composition of the polymeric mixture. However, the Hardness (H) decreases with increasing r-PET content until 50/50 composition of r-PET/HDPE is reached, whereas for larger r-PET content values, H increases. The same trend was obtained with the addition of the compatibilizer.

Keywords-recycled polyethelene terephthalate; DSC; hardness; compatibilization

I. INTRODUCTION

Recycling plastic waste not only preserves energy and raw resources but also provides an option of plastic waste disposal [1-3]. For both economic and environmental reasons, the interest in recycling polymeric materials has significantly increased over the last few decades [4]. Recycled polymers, however, are subjected throughout thermal and mechanical processes that result in structural and morphological changes, which in turn have an impact on the material qualities. Blending recycled polymers with unmodified polymers could be an approach to enhance their properties. In practice, formulating polymer blends is a viable method for developing materials with relatively new combinations of specified features. An important portion of post-consumer waste is made up of high density polyethylene (HDPE) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET), which are widely utilized in the packaging of consumer and industrial items.

Due to the unique combination of its physical and mechanical properties, which include great thermal resistance, strong fatigue resistance, and good solvent resistance, PET has revolutionized the globe with its use [5, 6]. On the other hand, HDPE, due to its wide use in the packaging industry, contributes greatly to environmental degradation [7], in the light of the structural considerations by the absence of specific interactions and according to [8-10] affirming the non-compatibility of PET with polyolefins. Due to the poor mechanical characteristics of PET/PE blends, compatibilizers must be used in order to decrease interfacial tension, which in turn increases morphological stability and interfacial adhesion. The study of the binary PET/HDPE polymeric system with the use of compatibilizing agents has been the subject of several research works. Among the most commonly used compatibilizers in HDPE/PET blending systems are graft copolymers containing reactive Maleic Anhydride (MA), functional groups such as MA-grafted polyethylene (PE-g-MA) [11, 12], HDPE-g-MA [13], and Maleic Anhydride-grafted Styrene-Ethylene-Butene copolymer (SEBS-g-MA) [14]. Another group of compatibilizers often used in research are the random copolymers containing GMA, such as HDPE-g-GMA [15], ethylene-glycidyl methacrylate copolymer (E-GMA) [16], Ethylene Ethyl-Glycidyl Methacrylate (E-EA-GMA) [15], and Ethylene Butyl Acrylate-Glycidyl Methacrylate (EBA-GMA) [17]. Other possibilities that are also promising have been investigated, such as compatibilizing the PET/HDPE system with an epoxy chain extender [18].

The indentation test is one of the easiest methods of determining a material's micromechanical characteristics [19, 20]. This method has been successfully used in a wide range of systems and is extremely sensitive to changes in the morphology and microstructure of polymers. In one of our previous research works [21], we investigated how combining clay and a compatibilizer SEBS-MAH affected the microindentation hardness (H) of PET/HDPE.

The objective of the current study is to investigate the rheological, thermal, and mechanical properties of recycled

PET (r-PET) and HDPE blends as a function of their composition, compatibilized with Ethylene Vinyl Acetate (EVA).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The following materials were used in this investigation: recycled r-PET bottles from Bangkok Polyester Public Co., Bangkok (Thailand), commercial grade HDPE ALCUDIA 6006 (REPSOL) with Melt Flow Index (MFI): 0.56g/10 Min. The EVA used is UL00218CCN from EXON CHEMICALS with an MFI of 1.5g/10 Min. Before blending, the r-PET pellets were dried in vacuum at 105°C for 16h. The dried r-PET pellets were dry-mixed with the HDPE pellets in the following weight ratios: 25/75, 50/50, and 75/25. The blends were prepared in a Brabender Haake Rheocord type M, at 270°C and 32rpm in two steps. At first, the r-PET was fed into the chamber, and once it was melted, the HDPE and the EVA compatibilizer were added. From the preceding blends, films were prepared by compression molding in a 7102 Zwick machine (Ulm, Germany), at a pressure of 150kg/cm². The compression was performed at 275°C for a duration of 6min (4min for preheating and 2min for compression). A Zwick Universal Testing Machine (UTM) was used to study the tensile properties of the blends as per ASTM D 638 standard. The crosshead speed was 50mm/min.

The thermal study was performed with the help of a Perkin Elmer (Norwalk, Connecticut, USA) DSC-7 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) instrument in an inert N₂ atmosphere. The weights of the samples were 5–10mg. The studied temperature range was 50–300°C. The heating rate was 10°C/min. The crystallinity measured by DSC (α_{DSC}) was derived from the melting enthalpy obtained by DSC with the following expression:

$$\alpha_{DSC} = \Delta H_m / \Delta H_m^\infty \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_m and ΔH_m^∞ are the experimental melting enthalpy and the melting enthalpy for an infinitely thick crystal, respectively. For PET, the ΔH_m^∞ used was 140.1J/g [21] and for HDPE 293.86J/g [22].

Microhardness H was determined at room temperature with a Leitz (Wetzlar, Germany) microindentation tester with a square-based diamond indenter. The H value was derived from the residual projected area of indentation according to the following expression [23]:

$$H = kP/d^2 \quad (2)$$

where d is the length of the impression diagonal (m), P is the contact load applied (N), and k is a geometrical factor equal to 1.854. Loads of 0.5 and 1N were applied. The loading cycle was 0.1min. Ten indentations were performed on the surface of each sample, and the results were averaged.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the variation of the equilibrium torque as a function of the % r-PET in the blends. It was found that the torque of the blends without EVA decreases for up to a 50% increase of the amount of r-PET. Beyond this threshold, the

torque values stabilize. The same trend was observed with the addition of EVA to the different blends. It was observed that the r-PET/HDPE (50/50) blends show the lowest torque values for all formulations with and without EVA. This can be explained by the large contact area at equivolume percentage between the two polymers, thus reducing the transformation energy of the blends.

Fig. 1. Variation of the equilibrium torque as a function r-PET percentage.

Fig. 2. Effect of % EVA on the equilibrium torque.

The change in equilibrium torque was displayed as a function of % EVA in order to visualize the impact of the addition of EVA on the r-PET/HDPE (50/50) blends (see Figure 2). It was found that the torque increases with the addition of EVA up to 5% indicating that there may have been interactions between the polymers, which increase the flow resistance. Further, the torque decreases with increasing EVA content, which is probably due to the increase in the free volume created by the EVA. It was also noted from the results of the MFI (not shown here) that the MFI increases with the increasing percentage of the r-PET in the blends. This increase is not too significant at low concentrations of r-PET, but it is noticeable at high concentrations. It was also noted that the addition of EVA affects both polymers in a significant degree, slightly decreasing the MFI of HDPE and acting as a plasticizer for r-PET, while the blend values remain very complex. However, the values of the blends of r-PET/HDPE 50/50 concentration are the lowest for all formulations with EVA compared to the MFI values without EVA, showing a resistance to flow, confirming the equilibrium torque results. Figure 3 shows the variation of stress at break as a function of the incorporation rate of R-PET with and without the addition of EVA.

The stress at break values of r-PET are higher than that of HDPE while their blends show lower values than those of homopolymers. This can be explained by the dimixture between these two polymeric phases due to their incompatibility. It should be also noted that the stress values of the r-PET/HDPE 75/25 blends are very close to those of the greater amount of component, i.e. r-PET, while the r-PET/HDPE 25/75 blend has a stress value close to that of HDPE. Thus, the minor component has a dispersed spherical morphology in the major part and therefore the properties of the blends are those of the high concentration polymer as it absorbs all the stresses when subjected to a load or force. With the addition of EVA, the results are better. An addition of 5% EVA improves the stress at break of the blends up to 10%. This rise is caused by a decrease in interfacial tension, which in turn improves the adhesion between the two phases of the individual polymers. As a result, EVA has reduced the phase border energy, increasing the phase boundary area. The greater the phase boundary area, the more effectively energy can be transferred from one phase to another, improving the mechanical characteristics.

Fig. 3. Effect of the concentration of the EVA on the stress at break of the r-PET/HDPE blends.

Fig. 4. Effect of the concentration of the EVA on the elongation at break of the r-PET/HDPE blends.

The incompatibility of the r-PET blends with the HDPE of the binary blends without EVA is reflected much more in the elongation at break (Figure 4), where the values obtained are significantly lower than those of the homopolymers for all compositions. The calorimeters limit such resolutions and the T_g of one of the components of the mixture (HDPE) is below

0°C. On the other hand, the glass transition temperature of r-PET, which is around 70-80°C, was not detected in some thermograms, perhaps due to the presence of HDPE in the compositions and the melting temperature T_m of the HDPE. Authors in [24] were able to detect the T_g of r-PET in r-PET/PP blends of 75/25 composition and this temperature was almost the same as that of pure r-PET. Therefore, we limited ourselves to the study of the melting temperature and the determination of the crystallinity. The thermograms in Figures 5, 6 reveal that the T_m values of both components were nearly constant throughout all of the compositions and were the same as those of the pure polymers. $T_m = 122-131^\circ\text{C}$ for HDPE and $241-249^\circ\text{C}$ for PET. As a result, the blending method had little effect on the crystal thickness (l_c) of the components.

Fig. 5. DSC thermograms of neat polymers.

Fig. 6. DSC thermograms of the r-PET/HDPE (50/50) blends with and without EVA.

The Thomson-Gibbs equation was employed to determine the l_c value of each component. Consequently, the l_c value calculated was 25nm and 14nm for PET and HDPE respectively. The crystallization temperatures for the r-PET component were found to have somewhat decreased values. The crystallinity decreased as the r-PET level increased for all compositions (pure blends and blends with compatibilizer).

Figure 7 shows the H of the various blends as a function of the r-PET content. The H 's additivity behavior is depicted as a straight line. It is evident from the plot that neither the uncompatibilized nor compatibilized blends with EVA respect the additivity law of a binary blend as a function of composition. With increasing PET content, the blends became harder and deviated from linearity. EVA caused a reduction in H , which was more evident as the compatibilizer concentration increased. According to the two-phase model, the H of a semicrystalline polymer can be described by [22]:

$$H = H^{r-PET} \phi_1 + [H_c^{HDPE} \alpha^{HDPE} + H_a^{HDPE} (1 - \alpha)](1 - \phi) \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) considers the compositions of the blends as well as the crystalline H_c and amorphous H_a hardness of each individual component. The H values for the blends with EVA were noticeably lower than those obtained from the additivity law in accordance with (3). It is evident that the compatibilizer's two primary effects on these blends were a decrease in their crystallinity and a concurrent decrease in their hardness.

TABLE I. PURE r-PET/HDPE BLENDS AND BLENDS WITH EVA

Composition	HDPE crystallinity (%)	T_m (°C) r-PET	T_m (°C) HDPE
r-PET.HDPE (100/0)	0	249	129
r-PET.HDPE (75/25)	0.15	248	130
r-PET.HDPE (50/50)	0.23	249	127
r-PET.HDPE (25/75)	0.49	247	130
r-PET.HDPE (0/100)	0.53	247	129
r-PET.HDPE/EVA(100/0/5)	0	248	126
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (75/25/5)	0.09	249	128
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (50/50/5)	0.08	248	129
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (25/75/5)	0.12	246	129
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (0/100/5)	0.23	249	130
r-PET.HDPE/EVA(100/0/7)	0	248	129
r-PET.HDPE/EVA(75/25/7)	0.09	248	127
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (50/50/7)	0.03	249	128
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (25/75/7)	0.09	246	130
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (0/100/7)	0.10	248	129
r-PET.HDPE/EVA(100/0/10)	0	246	127
r-PET.HDPE/EVA(75/25/10)	0.10	249	129
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (50/50/10)	0.18	248	127
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (25/75/10)	0.10	247	129
r-PET.HDPE/EVA (0/100/10)	0.12	249	128

Fig. 7. Hardness dependence on the r-PET content with and without EVA.

IV. CONCLUSION

It is evident from the obtained results that PET was incompatible with HDPE, but the presence of EVA as a compatibilizer allowed combinations of these polymers. The compatibilization of blends with additional small quantities of EVA in one processing step is an interesting proposal, particularly for recycled blends, because it does not require prior expensive synthesis and leads to better results. The r-PET/HDPE 50/50 blends show the lowest torque values for all formulations with and without EVA caused by the large contact area at equivolume percentage between the two polymers. The T_m values of both components were nearly constant for all compositions and were the same as those of the pure polymers. The composition was the only factor influencing the crystallinity of the r-PET/HDPE blends (pure blends and blends with compatibilizer), whereas the PET affects the crystallizability of the HDPE component. The blending method had little effect on the crystal thickness of the components and the calculated values for PET and HDPE were 25nm and 14nm respectively. Moreover, the presence of the EVA strongly induced a hardness decrease in the blends.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Sienkiewicz, H. Janik, K. Borzędowska-Labuda, and J. Kucińska-Lipka, "Environmentally friendly polymer-rubber composites obtained from waste tyres: A review," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 147, pp. 560–571, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.01.121>.
- [2] R. S. Chen, M. H. A. Ghani, M. N. Salleh, S. Ahmad, and S. Gan, "Influence of Blend Composition and Compatibilizer on Mechanical and Morphological Properties of Recycled HDPE/PET Blends," *Materials Sciences and Applications*, vol. 5, no. 13, pp. 943–952, Nov. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.4236/msa.2014.513096>.
- [3] H. H. Khoo, "LCA of plastic waste recovery into recycled materials, energy and fuels in Singapore," *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, vol. 145, pp. 67–77, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.02.010>.
- [4] F. Gu, J. Guo, W. Zhang, P. A. Summers, and P. Hall, "From waste plastics to industrial raw materials: a life cycle assessment of mechanical plastic recycling practice based on a real-world case study," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 601–602, pp. 1192–1207, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.05.278>.
- [5] M. Pluta, Z. Bartzak, A. Pawlak, A. Galeski, and M. Pracella, "Phase structure and viscoelastic properties of compatibilized blends of PET and HDPE recyclates," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 82, no. 6, pp. 1423–1436, 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.1980>.
- [6] J. M. Lusinchi, B. Boutevin, N. Torres, and J. J. Robin, "In situ compatibilization of HDPE/PET blends," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 79, no. 5, pp. 874–880, 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4628\(20010131\)79:5<874::AID-APP120>3.0.CO;2-B](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4628(20010131)79:5<874::AID-APP120>3.0.CO;2-B).
- [7] A. S. Alghamdi, "Synthesis and Mechanical Characterization of High Density Polyethylene/Graphene Nanocomposites," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2814–2817, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1961>.
- [8] A. Palak, J. Morawiec, F. Pazzagli, M. Pracella, and A. Galeski, "Recycling of postconsumer poly(ethylene terephthalate) and high-density polyethylene by compatibilized blending," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 86, pp. 1473–1485, Aug. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.11307>.
- [9] H.-T. Chiu and Y.-K. Hsiao, "Compatibilization of Poly(ethylene terephthalate)/Polypropylene Blends with Maleic Anhydride Grafted Polyethylene-Octene Elastomer," *Journal of Polymer Research*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 153–160, Apr. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10965-005-9020-z>.
- [10] P. Chaiwutthinan, S. Suwannachot, and A. Larpkasemsuk, "Recycled poly(ethylene terephthalate)/polypropylene/wollastonite composites

- using PP-g-MA as compatibilizer: Mechanical, thermal and morphological properties," *Journal of Metals, Materials and Minerals*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 115–123, 2018.
- [11] Y. Lei, Q. Wu, C. M. Clemons, and W. Guo, "Phase structure and properties of poly(ethylene terephthalate)/high-density polyethylene based on recycled materials," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 113, no. 3, pp. 1710–1719, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.30178>.
- [12] Y. Lei, Q. Wu, C. M. Clemons, and W. Guo, "Phase structure and properties of poly(ethylene terephthalate)/high-density polyethylene based on recycled materials," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 113, no. 3, pp. 1710–1719, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.30178>.
- [13] A. Pawlak, J. Morawiec, F. Pazzagli, M. Pracella, and A. Galeski, "Recycling of postconsumer poly(ethylene terephthalate) and high-density polyethylene by compatibilized blending," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 86, no. 6, pp. 1473–1485, 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.11307>.
- [14] K. Dobrowszky and F. Ronkay, "Effects of SEBS-g-MA on Rheology, Morphology and Mechanical Properties of PET/HDPE Blends," *International Polymer Processing*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 91–99, Mar. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.3139/217.2970>.
- [15] S. Mbarek, M. Jaziri, Y. Chalamet, and C. Carrot, "Effect of the viscosity ratio on the morphology and properties of PET/HDPE blends with and without compatibilization," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 117, no. 3, pp. 1683–1694, 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.32050>.
- [16] S.-C. Li and L.-N. Lu, "Melt rheological properties of reactive compatibilized HDPE/PET blends," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 108, no. 6, pp. 3559–3564, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.28031>.
- [17] X. Lu *et al.*, "Morphology and properties of bio-based poly (lactic acid)/high-density polyethylene blends and their glass fiber reinforced composites," *Polymer Testing*, vol. 54, pp. 90–97, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2016.06.025>.
- [18] R. M. Santos *et al.*, "Thermal and Rheological Characterization of Recycled PET/Virgin HDPE Blend Compatibilized with PE-g-MA and an Epoxy Chain Extender," *Polymers*, vol. 14, no. 6, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 1144, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14061144>.
- [19] A. W. El-Morsy, M. Ghanem, and H. Bahaiatham, "Effect of Friction Stir Welding Parameters on the Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of AA2024-T4 Aluminum Alloy," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2493–2498, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1704>.
- [20] M. Elitas and B. Demir, "The Effects of the Welding Parameters on Tensile Properties of RSW Junctions of DP1000 Sheet Steel," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3116–3120, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2115>.
- [21] A. Hellati, D. Benachour, M. E. Cagiao, S. Boufassa, and F. J. Baltá Calleja, "Role of a compatibilizer in the structure and micromechanical properties of recycled poly(ethylene terephthalate)/polyolefin blends with clay," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 118, no. 3, pp. 1278–1287, 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.32090>.
- [22] F. J. Baltá Calleja and S. Fakirov, *Microhardness of Polymers*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2000.
- [23] S. Boufassa, R. Doufnoune, A. Hellati, N. Haddaoui, and M. E. Cagiao, "Effect of compatibilizing agents on the physical properties of iPP/HDPE organoclay blends," *Journal of Polymer Engineering*, vol. 33, no. 7, pp. 589–598, Oct. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1515/polyeng-2013-0048>.
- [24] R. S. Porter and L.-H. Wang, "Compatibility and transesterification in binary polymer blends," *Polymer*, vol. 33, no. 10, pp. 2019–2030, Jan. 1992, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-3861\(92\)90866-U](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-3861(92)90866-U).

Wind Power Generation Scenarios in Lebanon

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Abstract-Renewable energy in terms of solar and wind energy can be an essential part of Lebanon's strategies to add new capacity, increase energy security, address environmental concerns, and resolve the electricity crisis. In this regard, there is an urgent need to develop road maps in order to reduce the effect of global warming and enhance sustainable technological development for generating clean power in the country. Therefore, the present paper evaluates Lebanon's wind energy generation potential as an alternative solution to supply electricity to households in various locations distributed over Lebanon. In the present study, the measured data are used to evaluate the wind energy potential in Lebanon and to find suitable locations to install wind farms in the country. Accordingly, the results demonstrated that Ain ed Dabaa is the most suitable location for the installation of a wind farm. Moreover, the study aims to develop a wind energy cost analysis techno-economic model for eight conventional wind turbines and a Barber wind turbine, which was found to be very competitive. Consequently, this study showed that the implementation of a wind turbine could provide clean, economical, and continuous production of electricity in countries that suffer from daily blackouts.

Keywords-Lebanon; wind potential; conventional wind turbines; Barber wind turbine; techno-economic model

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy demand growth, global warming, climate change, and increasing consumption of fossil fuels has led to the transition from conventional fuels to renewable energy resources [1-3]. Moreover, the use of fossil fuels in the generation of electricity contributes significantly to Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions, which further contributes to climate change [4, 5]. According to [6], utilizing renewable energy as an alternative energy source will help reduce environmental problems, essentially GHG emissions and air pollution. The

use of renewable energy, including wind and solar energy, is rapidly increasing because it is economically viable and has limited environmental impact [7]. During the recent years, many studies have evaluated wind and solar energy potential as clean power sources for electricity generation in various countries. For instance, authors in [8] analyzed the performance of a 5kW rooftop photovoltaic (PV) system in Northern India. The results indicated that the annual average capacity utilization factor was 16.39%. Authors in [9] evaluated the wind potential in Taza and Dakhla cities, Morocco using the Weibull distribution function. The results demonstrated that the value of wind power density is 435.96W/m² and 122.91W/m² in Dakhla and Taza respectively. Authors in [10] estimated the potential of rooftop PV electricity in Lethbridge, Canada using LiDAR data and ArcGIS. The results showed that the developed system has a huge potential to offset the energy demand of the city. Authors in [11] assessed the performance of the Aventa AV-7 wind turbine for electricity generation in Medina. It was found that the annual generation of energy from the selected turbine is 8648kWh.

A. Electricity Situation in Lebanon

Lebanon is located on the Eastern edge of the Mediterranean Sea, between 33.8547°N latitude and 35.8623°E longitude. At present, fossil fuels (97%) and hydropower (3%) are the main sources of electrical energy in Lebanon. Generally, the production capacity of electricity reaches 3600MW, while the actual production capacity currently does not exceed 2000MW. Currently, Lebanon has 7 thermal power plants, 6 hydroelectric plants, and 2 power ships operating to generate electricity. The electricity consumption has increased due to the growth of the population and the continuing demand for new large and small appliances as shown in Figure 1 [12]. Besides, only 70% of total generated power covered the energy needs in the country as shown in Figure 2.

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Fig. 1. Electrical power demand distribution [12].

Fig. 2. Electrical power demand distribution [13].

The electricity crisis is one of the most important issues affecting the daily lives of citizens, shop owners, and small businesses in Lebanon for years. The electricity crisis in Lebanon is not new and the electricity sector has suffered from decades of mismanagement, weak policies, and the absence of proper planning. The country has been suffering from a severe shortage of energy due to the dilapidation of old power stations that were accompanied by sabotage operations during the past years. As a result, duration of power cuts for citizens increased to more than 20 hours a day. For this reason, citizens rely on domestic power generators or small home generators, both of them adding great financial burdens. According to [14, 15], private generators are utilized in all the country to meet the energy demand, and they are considered the third main source of production of electricity.

B. The Renewable Energy Situation in Lebanon

According to [14, 16], the power sector in the country contributes about 58% of total CO₂ emissions, of which 25% come from private generators. Consequently, utilizing renewable energy would reduce the consumption of fossil fuels and could be a clean source for electricity generation in the country. Authors in [17] concluded that wind power systems could be alternative sources to fulfill the electrical power required and reduce the CO₂ emissions. Moreover, according to [17], standalone wind turbines are privately utilized for the generation of electricity for homes and small private companies. Approximately 2.06% of wind power is currently used for electric power generation in Lebanon [18]. Authors in

[19] found that wind energy could be utilized in the country for electricity generation during the night. Authors in [20] concluded that the utilization of small-scale wind systems could be used for the generation of electricity from wind energy in Beirut, Sidon, and Tripoli. Authors in [21] concluded that wind turbine systems could be installed to complement the main grid with electric power during the peak hours.

Numerous researchers have investigated the potential of renewable energy, particularly wind energy in different locations in Lebanon [16, 19-25]. For instance, authors in [25] investigated the wind potential in 9 locations in Lebanon. The author concluded that a small-scale wind system could be more profitably used for these areas. Authors in [23] studied the characteristics of wind energy in five locations in Lebanon. Their results showed that the wind energy system can be an alternative solution and more cost-effective than conventional power sources. Authors in [24] assessed the wind energy potential in 8 locations in the Northern Lebanon. The results showed that wind power system can be utilized to reduce the energy shortage in the country. According to [16, 19-25], it can be concluded that:

- The utilization of wind power systems in Lebanon is limited.
- Renewable energy systems can solve the electricity crisis and reduce CO₂ emissions.
- Only a few studies investigated the wind turbine performance for generating electricity in Lebanon.

According to the literature review, no studies evaluated the potential and variability assessment of wind energy over Lebanon considering various climate conditions.

C. The Importance of the Current Study

Globally, wind energy and its associated technologies are essential to support electricity consumption and supply power in order to mitigate the electricity crisis. Besides, as an ongoing study on the assessment of renewable energy systems, primarily wind and solar energy in different locations, the present study aims to investigate the wind potential in various locations distributed over Lebanon. To achieve this, measured data for the period 2010-2017 were collected from meteorological agencies. Consequently, the Weibull distribution function was used to evaluate the characteristics of wind speed in the selected locations. The distribution parameters were estimated using the maximum likelihood method. The power density was calculated and was used to evaluate the potential of wind energy in each location. Additionally, the Power-Law exponent method was utilized to estimate the wind speed at various hub heights. Based on the literature, wind power is low and unsustainable in many regions in Lebanon. Consequently, this study aims to evaluate the techno-economic performance of the Ferris wheel-based Barber wind turbine, which is a new wind turbine technology, at low wind speed locations. Furthermore, the performance of the selected wind turbine is compared with conventional wind turbines under the same economic conditions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proposed methodology aims to assess the wind energy potential in 12 locations in Lebanon in order to identify suitable locations for future wind power systems. Then, the economic viability of wind systems is evaluated. Figure 3 illustrates the proposed methodology used in this study.

A. Study Area and Dataset

This examination was undertaken to identify the best location for installing wind power systems among the chosen locations in Lebanon. Table I summarizes the geographic information of the selected locations.

TABLE I. THE SELECTED LOCATIONS

Location	Latitude [°N]	Longitude [°E]	Elevation [m]
Younine	34.0776	36.2750	1198
Birket Aarous	34.2911	36.1456	2766
Ain ed Dabaa	34.4431	35.8992	296
Mqaybleh	34.6460	36.3577	330
Ras Ouadi Ed Darje	34.2533	36.5775	1555
Kfardebian	34.0017	35.8349	1670
Qaraoun	33.5669	35.7193	913
Khartoum	33.4079	35.3751	305
Iskandarounah	33.1550	35.1685	53
Beirut	33.8938	35.5018	40
Khiam	33.3294	35.6148	697
Hekr El Dahri	34.6306	36.0237	10

B. Wind Speed Distribution

The correct determination of the probability distribution of wind speed is a prominent factor in evaluating the wind energy potential in a region. Thus, knowing the wind speed distribution at a specific location is necessary for determining its potential. A 2-parameter Weibull distribution is commonly utilized to study the characteristics of wind speed. The Weibull Probability Density Function (PDF) $f(v)$ and the cumulative distribution function $F(v)$ expressions are [26]:

$$f(v) = \left(\frac{k}{c}\right) \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^{k-1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k\right) \quad (1)$$

$$F(v) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^k\right) \quad (2)$$

where v is the mean wind speed (m/s), k is the shape parameter, and c is the scale parameter of the Weibull distribution.

To determine the distribution parameter, the Maximum Likelihood (ML) method is used to determine k and c [27]:

$$k = \left(\frac{\sum_1^n v_i^k \ln(v_i)}{\sum_1^n v_i^k} - \frac{\sum_1^n \ln(v_i)}{n}\right)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$c = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_1^n v_i^k\right)^{1/k} \quad (4)$$

Following the Weibull distribution, (5) and (6) are utilized to estimate the average wind speed and the standard deviation of the wind speed respectively.

$$v_m = c\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{c^2 \left[\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{2}{k}\right) - \Gamma^2\left(1 + \frac{1}{k}\right)\right]} \quad (6)$$

C. Wind Power Density

To assess the potential of wind energy, (7) is utilized to determine the Wind Power Density (WPD) at a specific location:

$$\left(\frac{P}{A}\right)_W = \frac{1}{2} \rho c^3 \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{3}{k}\right) \quad (7)$$

The average value of WPD can be estimated by [21]:

$$\frac{P}{A} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^3 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{P}{A} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^3 f(v) \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\bar{P}}{A} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \bar{v}^3 \quad (10)$$

where P is wind power density (W), \bar{P} is the mean wind power density (W), A is the swept area (m^2), ρ is the air density (kg/m^3), $f(v)$ is the PDF, and \bar{v} is the mean wind speed (m/s).

D. Wind Speed Data Extrapolation at Different Hub Heights

Generally, wind speed measurements are carried out at a height of 10m above the ground. To obtain energy from wind turbines, it is necessary to estimate wind speeds at various hub heights using (11) [28]:

$$\frac{v}{v_{10}} = \left(\frac{z}{z_{10}}\right)^{\frac{0.37-0.088 \ln(v_{10})}{1-0.088 \ln(z_{10}/10)}} \quad (11)$$

where v is the wind speed at the wind turbine hub height z , v_{10} is the wind speed at the original height z_{10} .

E. Energy Output of a Wind Turbine

The produced energy by the wind turbine E_{out} can be estimated by [28]:

$$E_{out} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_{out} t \quad (12)$$

where t is time and P_{out} is determined by:

$$P_{out} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{when } v < v_{ci} \\ \frac{P_R v_{ci}^k}{v_{ci}^k - v_R^k} + \left(\frac{P_R}{v_R^k - v_{ci}^k}\right) v^k & \text{when } v_{ci} \leq v \leq v_R \\ P_R & \text{when } v_R \leq v \leq v_{co} \\ 0 & \text{when } v > v_{co} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where P_R is the rated power of the wind turbine, v_{ci} the turbine's cut-in speed, v_{co} turbine's cut-off speed, and v_R is its rated wind speed.

The average power generation of the turbine can be expressed as [29]:

$$P_{out} = P_R \left[\frac{\exp\left[-\left(\frac{v_{ci}}{c}\right)^k\right] - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{v_R}{c}\right)^k\right]}{\left(\frac{v_R}{c}\right)^k - \left(\frac{v_{ci}}{c}\right)^k} - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{v_{co}}{c}\right)^k\right] \right] \quad (14)$$

The Capacity Factor (CF) is estimated [29, 30]:

$$CF = \frac{E_{out}}{8760 P_R} \quad (15)$$

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the proposed methodology.

In this study, various wind turbines assumed the load profile for all months of the year. Nine wind turbines (Table II) with various characteristics including the Capital Cost of acquisition (CC) and O&M Cost (OMC) are selected as shown in Tables II-III. Generally, Conventional Wind Turbines (CWTs) are designed to generate electricity at high wind speeds. The cut-in speed and rated wind speed for these turbines are within the range of 3-5m/s and 12-15m/s respectively [30, 31]. CWTs are heavy and expensive to buy, install, and maintain. Therefore, the performance of the Ferris Wheel Wind Turbine (FWWT) is compared with the selected CWTs due to its advantages, such as its light design, lower weight to power ratios, etc. [32].

TABLE II. SELECTED WIND TURBINES

Model No.	Wind turbine model	Manufacture
Model#1	Enercon E5	Enercon GmbH
Model#2	Enercon E44	Enercon GmbH
Model#3	EWT DW61	Emergya Wind Technologies B.V.
Model#4	GE SLE 1.5	Winergy/Eickhoff/Bosch.
Model#5	AN Bonus 1 MW/54	Siemens Wind Power A/S
Model#6	DEWIND-62-91.5 m	DeWind
Model#7	Neg-Micon	NEG Micon A/S
Model#8	Vestas-V66	Vestas Wind Systems A/S
Model#9	Barber wind turbine	BarberWind Turbines

TABLE III. CHARACTERISTICS AND SPECIFICATIONS

Model No.	HH [m]	P_R [kW]	v_{ci} [m/s]	v_R [m/s]	v_{co} [m/s]	CC [USD]	OMC [USD/y]
Model#1	76	800	3	13	25	1750000	51250
Model#2	55	900	3	16.5	34	2337500	51250
Model#3	69	900	2.5	10	25	1918770	57158
Model#4	85	1500	3	14	25	3375000	57158
Model#5	50	1000	3	15	25	863530	25043
Model#6	91.5	1000	2.5	11.5	23	1124758	32618
Model#7	70	1000	4	14	20	1162460	33711
Model#8	67	1650	4	16	25	1768000	51272
Model#9	70	800	3	9.6	20	1400000	42000

F. Economic Viability of a Wind System

The wind energy farm’s viability is dependent on its ability to generate energy at low operating cost. In this paper, the Levelized Cost Of Electricity (LCOE) is utilized to calculate the Electricity Generated Cost (EGC) of the wind turbine [32]:

$$LCOE = \left(\frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \right) \left[1 + \frac{c_{om}}{i-e} \left[1 - \left(\frac{1+e}{1+i} \right)^n \right] \right] \quad (16)$$

where $\rho=1.23\text{kg/m}^3$ is air's density, A is the swept area (m^2), C_p is the Betz limit power coefficient (theoretical value $C_p = 0.59$), e is the escalation rate of operation and maintenance, i is the interest rate, n is the useful lifetime of the turbine in years, and C_{om} is the operation and maintenance costs during the first year.

Additionally, (17) is used to determine the simple payback period (SPP) [32]:

$$SPP = \frac{I}{8760f(v)\left[\frac{1}{2}\rho Av^3 C_p\right]P_e} \quad (17)$$

where I is the installed capital cost of the wind turbine plus the costs of civil works and P_e is the price of electricity ($\$/\text{kWh}$).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics of the Wind Speed at 10m Height

The statistical description of monthly wind speed includes mean value, Standard Deviation (SD), Coefficient of Variation (CV), Minimum (Min.), Maximum (Max.), Kurtosis (K), and Skewness (S) as summarized in Table IV for all selected locations. According to the findings, it is noticed that the maximum mean monthly wind speed of 4.90m/s is recorded in

Ain ed Dabaa, while the minimum of 2.81 is recorded in Khiam and Khartoum. The monthly wind speeds for Ain ed Dabaa and Khartoum are illustrated in Figure 4. It is observed that the maximum value of monthly wind speed of 5.82m/s is recorded in January. The highest value of 3.03m/s for Khartoum is recorded in June as shown in Figure 4. It can be seen that the CV values are moderately low, ranging from 6.52% to 17.25%. Additionally, all S values for most of the selected locations are negative, indicating that all distributions are left skewed.

Fig. 4. Mean monthly wind speed at a height of 10m.

TABLE IV. STATISTICAL ESTIMATORS OF MONTHLY WIND SPEED

Variable	Younine	Birket Aarous	Ain ed Dabaa	Mqaybleh	Ras Ouadi Ed Darje	Khiam
Mean	2.90	3.01	4.90	2.91	3.19	2.81
SD	0.45	0.31	0.53	0.30	0.45	0.18
CV	15.37	10.14	10.79	10.14	14.05	6.52
Min.	2.32	2.44	4.00	2.36	2.54	2.47
Max.	3.51	3.45	5.82	3.34	4.03	3.03
S	0.03	-0.56	-0.15	-0.56	0.52	-0.54
K	-1.46	-0.26	-0.41	-0.26	-0.19	-0.81
Variable	Kfardeblian	Qaraoun	Khartoum	Iskandarounah	Beirut	Hekr El Dahri
Mean	3.48	2.86	2.81	3.32	3.48	2.91
SD	0.41	0.19	0.18	0.57	0.41	0.30
CV	11.66	6.52	6.52	17.25	11.66	10.14
Min.	3.04	2.51	2.47	2.72	3.04	2.36
Max.	4.22	3.08	3.03	4.27	4.22	3.34
S	0.82	-0.54	-0.54	0.42	0.82	-0.56
K	-0.75	-0.81	-0.81	-1.46	-0.75	-0.26

B. Determination of Weibull Parameters

The Weibull distribution parameters for the selected locations using monthly wind speed data were determined using the ML approach. The calculated shape k and scale c parameters of all selected locations at 10m height are shown in Figure 5. The value of k ranged from 5.99 to 15.45 with an average value of 10.49. The annual value of c range was 2.88-5.04m/s with an average value of 3.32m/s. Moreover, the average wind speed and its SD were calculated using from (5) and (6) and are shown in Figure 5. It is observed that the mean wind speed and SD are within the range of 2.78-4.8m/s and 0.22-0.63m/s respectively. Moreover, the PDF indicates the frequency of different levels of speed. It can be utilized to estimate which level of wind speed is prevalent in the location. The wind speed where the distribution curve peaks are the most frequently observed wind speed for the location. Figure 6 illustrates the PDF of all selected locations.

C. Wind Power Density

To evaluate the wind potential in the selected locations, the annual WPD is computed from (7). The value of WPD for each location is tabulated in Figure 7. It is found that the value of WPD ranged from 13.18W/m² to 67.44W/m² with an average value of 21.03W/m². Based on these values, the wind energy generation potential of these locations is classified as class 1 (Poor) as shown in Table V. Therefore, small-scale wind turbines are suitable to be used in the selected regions for exploiting the available wind energy potential. Furthermore, it can be concluded that high-capacity wind turbines (MWs) with a height of 90m and above can be suitable for gathering the wind energy potential in the selected locations. This is investigated using the power-law method, i.e., the collected data at 10m height is synthesized to the 90m height at which most of the 1MW or above capacity wind turbine height is.

Fig. 5. Weibull parameters for all selected locations at a height of 10m.

Fig. 6. The probability density function for all selected locations.

TABLE I. WIND POWER CLASSIFICATION AT 10m HEIGHT

Power class	\bar{P} [W/m ²]
1 (Poor)	≤ 100
2 (Marginal)	≤ 150
3 (Moderate)	≤ 200
4 (Good)	≤ 250
5 (Excellent)	≤ 300
6 (Excellent)	≤ 400
7 (Excellent)	≤ 1000

Fig. 7. The annual value of wind power density for all selected locations.

D. Techno-Economic Model

As mentioned above, 9 wind turbines with various characteristics were selected and the wind speed at various hub heights was calculated using (11). For instance, Figure 8 illustrates the monthly variation of wind speed at various hub heights for 3 selected locations. It can be seen that the value of wind speed increases with the increasing hub height of the wind turbine.

Fig. 8. Monthly average wind speed for 3 selected locations at various hub heights.

Fig. 9. The estimated results in terms of AEP, CF, EGC, and SPP.

To investigate the performance of wind energy, 9 wind turbines with various rated powers were considered. The aim is to select the turbine that best matches the wind regime at the selected locations. The electricity cost per kWh in Lebanon, the

annual interest rate, the capital cost of acquisition, operation, and maintenance costs of wind turbines, and the life of the wind turbines are required for economic viability. These data were obtained from previous studies, trading economics, and global petrol prices. The Annual Energy Produced (AEP) and CF for the selected turbines were determined by (12) and (15) respectively. EGC and SPP were determined by (16) and (17). Figure 9 illustrates the estimated results in terms of AEP, CF, EGC, and SPP for all selected locations. It is found that the APE values ranged from 339.55MWh to 5017.35MWh with an average value of 1241.875MWh. The maximum and minimum values of APE are recorded in Ain ed Dabaa and Khartoum for a hub height of 91.5m (Model#6) and 55m (Model#2) respectively. The highest and lowest CF values are 59.23% (Ain ed Dabaa) and 2.79% (Khiam) respectively with an average value of 14.28%. Furthermore, the EGC values are within the range of 0.033-0.761USD/kWh with an average value of 0.287USD/kWh. Furthermore, the shortest payback period of 1.54 years is observed at Ain ed Dabaa for a hub height of 91.5m (Model#6).

Other researchers who analyzed the performance of a wind farm system in terms of CF, SPP, and EGC support these observations [30, 33-39]. For instance, authors in [35] found CF values within the range of 31.1-49% and 37.3-56.6% for 50m and 75m hub-height turbines. Authors in [30] found that the BWT 61m-800kW wind turbine has a payback period of 1.9-27.3 years and its EGC values were within the range of 0.04-0.43USD/kWh. In [36], it was found that the payback period for different wind farms with a capacity of 100MW ranged from 6.34 to 19.9 years. Authors in [33] found that the values of CF and EGC produced by various wind turbines were within the range of 32-38% and 0.255-0.306 USD/kWh respectively. Authors in [37] found that the CF values varied from 6.8% to 47.6% using various wind turbines with various characteristics. According to the finding of [34], the CF values of different wind turbines are estimated to be within the range of 22.9-50.6%. It should be noted that when the value of SPP exceeds the assumed lifetime of the wind turbine, it means that installing the wind turbines in locations is not economically viable for energy production for the selected wind turbine model. Moreover, according to [30, 31, 38], the SPP value for small and medium-scale wind turbines is within the range of 5-12 years. Therefore, more than 50% of the selected cities fall within the range of SPP. Based on these results, it can be concluded that:

- The results demonstrate the competitiveness of BWTs for operation compared to CWTs, especially at locations with low wind conditions.
- Although Model#6 has a lower EGC in all selected locations, Model#9 has a robust design and a wider range of applications for all classes of wind resources. Thus, model#9 would have a lower cost in the long run.
- FWWT technology is a strong candidate to increase the availability of economic, green, and sustainable energy in Lebanon.

The EGC values obtained from the current study are compared with the current electricity prices in Lebanon in

Figure 10. It is clear that the price of the electricity generated by wind turbine systems is less than the one from conventional systems. It can be concluded that the developed systems ensure the economic feasibility of the project for all locations. Wind energy will be able to solve the problem of a chronic lack of electricity and reduce the electricity bills in Lebanon.

Fig. 10. Monthly average wind speed for some selected locations and various hub heights.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Lebanon is experiencing a serious water and electricity crisis. The growing challenges faced by the population and energy sectors are outpacing the government's efforts to provide high-quality, affordable, and accessible electricity. In this context, utilizing wind energy is considered an alternative solution to supply electricity to households, reduce the effect of global warming, and enhance sustainable technological development. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop road maps for the exploitation of renewable energy sources.

In this regard, the techno-economic model for the assessment of wind energy in selected locations in Lebanon is presented in this research. In this study, the techno-economic performance of new technology of wind turbine, the Barber wind turbine (Model#9), is compared to conventional wind turbines under the same economic conditions.

The results showed that the Barber wind turbine (Model#9) is very competitive to 8 known commercial wind turbines for low wind speed conditions. Consequently, the current study may encourage stakeholders in the renewable energy sector to provide support mechanisms for the adoption of large-scale and small-scale wind systems in the country.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Fang, J. Li, and W. Song, "Sustainable site selection for photovoltaic power plant: An integrated approach based on prospect theory," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 174, pp. 755–768, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.08.092>.
- [2] S. N. Shorabeh, M. K. Firozjaei, O. Nematollahi, H. K. Firozjaei, and M. Jelokhani-Niaraki, "A risk-based multi-criteria spatial decision analysis for solar power plant site selection in different climates: A case study in Iran," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 143, pp. 958–973, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.05.063>.
- [3] E. Tercan, A. Eymen, T. Urfali, and B. O. Saracoglu, "A sustainable framework for spatial planning of photovoltaic solar farms using GIS and multi-criteria assessment approach in Central Anatolia, Turkey," *Land Use Policy*, vol. 102, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 105272, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.105272>.
- [4] B. Memon, M. H. Baloch, A. H. Memon, S. H. Qazi, R. Haider, and D. Ishak, "Assessment of Wind Power Potential Based on Raleigh Distribution Model: An Experimental Investigation for Coastal Zone," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3721–3725, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2381>.
- [5] Y. Kassem, H. Gokcekus, and H. S. A. Lagili, "A Techno-Economic Viability Analysis of the Two-Axis Tracking Grid-Connected Photovoltaic Power System for 25 Selected Coastal Mediterranean Cities," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7508–7514, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4251>.
- [6] F. Elmahmoudi, O. E. K. Abra, A. Raihani, O. Serrar, and L. Bahatti, "Elaboration of a Wind Energy Potential Map in Morocco using GIS and Analytic Hierarchy Process," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 6068–6075, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3692>.
- [7] A. G. Olabi and M. A. Abdelkareem, "Renewable energy and climate change," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 158, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 112111, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112111>.
- [8] S. K. Yadav and U. Bajpai, "Performance evaluation of a rooftop solar photovoltaic power plant in Northern India," *Energy for Sustainable Development*, vol. 43, pp. 130–138, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esd.2018.01.006>.
- [9] El Khchine, M. Sriti, and N. E. El Kadri Elyamani, "Evaluation of wind energy potential and trends in Morocco," *Heliyon*, vol. 5, no. 6, Jun. 2019, Art. no. e01830, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01830>.
- [10] F. Mansouri Kouhestani, J. Byrne, D. Johnson, L. Spencer, P. Hazendonk, and B. Brown, "Evaluating solar energy technical and economic potential on rooftops in an urban setting: the city of Lethbridge, Canada," *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 13–32, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40095-018-0289-1>.
- [11] K. S. AlQdah, R. Alahmdi, A. Alansari, A. Almoghamisi, M. Abualkhair, and M. Awais, "Potential of wind energy in Medina, Saudi Arabia based on Weibull distribution parameters," *Wind Engineering*, vol. 45, no. 6, pp. 1652–1661, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309524X211027356>.
- [12] R. B. Chahine, "Energy Strategy to Supply Electric Demands in Politically Unstable Developing Countries (Lebanon Case Study)," M.S. thesis, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, UK, 2018.
- [13] *Physical Infrastructure - Electricity Sector Overview*. Libanon: Council for Development and Reconstruction, 2016.
- [14] N. Wehbe, "Optimization of Lebanon's power generation scenarios to meet the electricity demand by 2030," *The Electricity Journal*, vol. 33, no. 5, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 106764, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tej.2020.106764>.
- [15] R. A. Farhat *et al.*, "A Multi-attribute Assessment of Electricity Supply Options in Lebanon," in *Food-Energy-Water Nexus Resilience and Sustainable Development: Decision-Making Methods, Planning, and Trade-Off Analysis*, S. Asadi and B. Mohammadi-Ivatloo, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2020, pp. 1–27.
- [16] Y. Kassem, H. Gokcekus, and W. Janbein, "Predictive model and assessment of the potential for wind and solar power in Rayak region, Lebanon," *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1475–1502, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-00866-y>.
- [17] E. Kinab and M. Elkhoury, "Renewable energy use in Lebanon: Barriers and solutions," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 16, no. 7, pp. 4422–4431, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.04.030>.
- [18] H. L. Moore and H. Collins, "Decentralised renewable energy and prosperity for Lebanon," *Energy Policy*, vol. 137, Feb. 2020, Art. no. 111102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2019.111102>.
- [19] G. Al Zohbi, P. Hendrick, and P. Bouillard, "Wind characteristics and wind energy potential analysis in five sites in Lebanon," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 40, no. 44, pp. 15311–15319, Nov. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.04.115>.
- [20] Y. Kassem, H. Gokcekus, and M. Zeitoun, "Modeling of techno-economic assessment on wind energy potential at three selected coastal regions in Lebanon," *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 5,

- no. 3, pp. 1037–1049, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-019-00589-9>.
- [21] M. Elkhoury, Z. Nakad, and S. Shatila, "The Assessment of Wind Power for Electricity Generation in Lebanon," *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects*, vol. 32, no. 13, pp. 1236–1247, Apr. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567030802706754>.
- [22] A. El-Ali, N. Moubayed, and R. Outbib, "Comparison between solar and wind energy in Lebanon," in *9th International Conference on Electrical Power Quality and Utilisation*, Barcelona, Spain, Oct. 2007, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EPQU.2007.4424155>.
- [23] G. A. Zohbi, P. Hendrick, and P. Bouillard, "Assessment of wind energy potential in Lebanon," *Research in Marine Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 401–414, 2018.
- [24] H. Gokcekus, Y. Kassem, and M. A. Hassan, "Evaluation of Wind Potential at Eight Selected Locations in Northern Lebanon Using Open Source Data," *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, vol. 14, no. 11, pp. 2789–2794, 2019.
- [25] Y. Kassem, H. Camur, M. A. H. A. Abdalla, B. D. Erdem, and A. M. R. Al-ani, "Evaluation of wind energy potential for different regions in Lebanon based on NASA wind speed database," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 926, no. 1, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 012093, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/926/1/012093>.
- [26] A. Serban, L. S. Paraschiv, and S. Paraschiv, "Assessment of wind energy potential based on Weibull and Rayleigh distribution models," *Energy Reports*, vol. 6, pp. 250–267, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2020.08.048>.
- [27] J. A. Guarienti, A. Kaufmann Almeida, A. Menegati Neto, A. R. de Oliveira Ferreira, J. P. Ottonelli, and I. Kaufmann de Almeida, "Performance analysis of numerical methods for determining Weibull distribution parameters applied to wind speed in Mato Grosso do Sul, Brazil," *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, vol. 42, Dec. 2020, Art. no. 100854, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2020.100854>.
- [28] M. M. Alayat, Y. Kassem, and H. Çamur, "Assessment of Wind Energy Potential as a Power Generation Source: A Case Study of Eight Selected Locations in Northern Cyprus," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 10, Oct. 2018, Art. no. 2697, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11102697>.
- [29] L. Bilir, M. Imir, Y. Devrim, and A. Albostan, "An investigation on wind energy potential and small scale wind turbine performance at İncek region – Ankara, Turkey," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 103, pp. 910–923, Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2015.07.017>.
- [30] S. Rehman, M. M. Alam, L. M. Alhems, and M. M. Rafique, "Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine Blade Design Methodologies for Efficiency Enhancement—A Review," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 3, Mar. 2018, Art. no. 506, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11030506>.
- [31] "Size specifications of common industrial wind turbines," *American Wind Energy Association*. <http://www.aweo.org/windmodels.html>.
- [32] K. A. Adeyeye, N. Ijumba, and J. S. Colton, "A Techno-Economic Model for Wind Energy Costs Analysis for Low Wind Speed Areas," *Processes*, vol. 9, no. 8, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 1463, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9081463>.
- [33] A. Ucar and F. Balo, "Investigation of wind characteristics and assessment of wind-generation potentiality in Uludağ-Bursa, Turkey," *Applied Energy*, vol. 86, no. 3, pp. 333–339, Mar. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2008.05.001>.
- [34] J. W. Tester, E. M. Drake, M. J. Driscoll, M. W. Golay, and W. A. Peters, *Sustainable Energy, second edition: Choosing Among Options*. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, 2012.
- [35] A. Allouhi *et al.*, "Evaluation of wind energy potential in Morocco's coastal regions," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 72, pp. 311–324, May 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.01.047>.
- [36] M. A. Alsaad, "Wind energy potential in selected areas in Jordan," *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 65, pp. 704–708, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2011.12.037>.
- [37] H. D. Ammari, S. S. Al-Rwashdeh, and M. I. Al-Najideen, "Evaluation of wind energy potential and electricity generation at five locations in Jordan," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 15, pp. 135–143, Jul. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2014.11.005>.
- [38] N. Boccard, "Capacity factor of wind power realized values vs. estimates," *Energy Policy*, vol. 37, no. 7, pp. 2679–2688, Jul. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2009.02.046>.
- [39] "Future of Wind: Deployment, investment, technology, grid integration and socio-economic aspects," *PERISCOPE*. <https://periscope-network.eu/analyst/future-wind-deployment-investment-technology-grid-integration-and-socio-economic-aspects>.
- [40] T. R. Ayodele, A. A. Jimoh, J. L. Munda, and J. T. Agee, "Viability and economic analysis of wind energy resource for power generation in Johannesburg, South Africa," *International Journal of Sustainable Energy*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 284–303, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786451.2012.762777>.

Assessment of Protective Clothing Used by Chemical Industry Workers in Pakistan

Chemical Resistance of Protective Clothing

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Abstract-Protective clothing serves as a barrier against many hazards faced by workers in the industry. This study aimed to investigate the performance of locally manufactured clothing used by workers in the chemical industries in Pakistan. The construction parameters were determined using international test procedures for all samples. Then, these were assessed for their chemical resistance behavior after various laundering intervals, following the ISO 6530:2005 test method. After the investigation, it was observed that the collected samples failed to meet the minimum criteria for penetration and repellency through their structure. The samples were unable to repel a minimum of 95% liquid chemical and penetrated it more than 5%, even at zero wash. These conditions worsened with each washing interval. Clothing materials should always be checked for their performance before use.

Keywords-chemical resistance; penetration; repellency; protective clothing; laundering; chemical industry; Pakistan

I. INTRODUCTION

Clothing is considered the second skin for the wearer and protects him against physical, chemical, and environmental hazards. While many advancements have been achieved in the manufacture of protective clothing, there is a lack of a comprehensive and detailed evaluation system in terms of experimentation and regulation [1]. Standard procedures and regulations are very necessary to implement in industries for the welfare of personnel [2]. Chemical protective clothing

materials are supposed to be the last defense line for workers dealing with toxic chemicals. Efforts must be made to make the best clothing to provide safety to its wearer. Chemicals vary in their nature from acute to chronic. The industrial working conditions require the wearing of protective clothing to protect the operating staff [3]. The clothing materials should be assessed for their performance before use. Chemical resistance can be evaluated by certain factors such as permeation time, breakthrough time, repellency, retention, penetration index, etc. [4]. Protective clothing is generally classified into various levels according to the protection rate it provides and is made of natural and synthetic fibers or a blend of both [5, 6]. Protective coveralls are generally worn by industry workers [7]. A regulatory body assesses the best protective ensemble for workers based on the toxicity and flammability of the chemicals used in various processes [8]. Accidents caused by chemical exposure in workplaces are horrendous. Workers are often exposed to toxic chemicals without safety measures while working in the industrial sector in Pakistan, resulting in many fatal accidents. Many workers, more than one-third of the respondents in [9], reported high risks associated with chemical exposure. It has been observed that although many toxic substances pose serious risks to their lives, workers expose themselves without wearing an adequate type of protective clothing. Occupational assessment related to the health and safety of workers in Pakistan has yet to receive great importance. Therefore, it is very important to determine

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measures and evaluate the performance of the provided protective equipment. The increase in the rate of deaths and injuries of factory employees is caused by the absence of a safety framework or the adoption of poorly administered safety measures [10]. The wages and salaries of most workers in Pakistan are very low. Workers usually do not bother about their health conditions and try hard to do more work regardless of checking the adequate protective measures. A survey carried out by the government of Pakistan showed that approximately 4.1 workers are seriously injured in industrial settings every year [11]. One of the main reasons for injuries is the lack of awareness about the use of protective equipment [12], while 60.9% of the workforce is not familiar with Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) [13].

It should be the responsibility of the employer to provide safety equipment to the workers. An assessment of the risks associated with chemical industries must be made to avoid accidents and injuries. Workers must have a proper protective ensemble to protect themselves from fire and chemical hazards during the handling and storage of hazardous chemicals [14]. As most chemical industries in Pakistan use locally manufactured protective clothing materials for their staff, there is a dire need to evaluate their performance before use. Protective clothing loses its quality with time due to the abrasion caused during work, rubbing during washing, and lack of proper care and cleaning procedures. This study aims to determine the clothing materials used by local chemical industries for their workers, in terms of protection against certain liquid chemicals after various washing intervals.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemical industries with head offices located in the Punjab province were approached and locally manufactured protective clothing used by their workers was collected (Figure 1). A total of five categories were identified according to their fiber content.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the research methodology.

The identification of textile fibers is of great importance. There are multiple methods to identify the generic group of fibers, such as burning, microscopic, and chemical tests [15]. The construction specifications of the collected samples were determined through qualitative and quantitative fiber analysis, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I. CONSTRUCTION PARAMETERS OF COLLECTED CLOTHING MATERIALS

Sample code	Fiber content	Yarn count: warp×weft (thread count)	Fabric mass (gsm)	Linear density (warp × weft)
AB-1	Cotton 40% Polyester 60%	113×95 (208)	150	17.21×15.43
AB-2	Cotton 70% Polyester 30%	95×75 (170)	138	16.34×16.34
AB-3	Cotton 95% Rayon 5%	105×68 (173)	162	17.29×18.91
AB-4	Cotton 98% Polyester 2%	99×76 (175)	125	18.32×15.63
AB-5	Cotton 50% Polyester 50%	110×85 (195)	121	15.34×18.45

Qualitative analysis was performed using the AATCC test method [16] to find the generic group of fibers. The samples were dipped in distilled hot water to remove impurities and were then treated with a 0.5% solution of sodium hydroxide to separate the vegetable matter. After that, the samples were washed out and dried. The dyed samples were stripped with 0.5% sodium hydrosulfite at 50°C for half an hour. Afterward, a visual examination was performed of physical parameters such as color, yarn length, fineness, number of neps, thickness, and uniformity. Fibers were identified at pre-burning, during burning, and post-burning stages through a burning test. Microscopic evaluation was also performed with longitudinal and cross-sectional views of the samples. A quantitative analysis was followed using the chemical test adopting the instructions given in the AATCC test procedure [17]. The samples from each group were taken and treated with the relative reagent to measure the solubility ratio given in the standard. The yarn count in both the warp and weft directions was determined using the standard test procedure [18]. The number of yarns in the test area of one inch was counted with the help of a magnifying counting glass. The thread count was calculated by adding the number of warp and weft yarns. The fabric mass was determined by following the standard procedure of [19]. The samples were measured in a weighing balance and the mass per unit area of m^2 was recorded with an accuracy level of $\pm 0.1\%$. The linear density in both directions was also identified [20]. The length and mass of the yarns were determined with the respective scales and calculations were carried out to measure the linear density.

The performance behavior of protective clothing must be evaluated after various washing intervals. Standard laundering procedures must be followed to verify the efficiency and adequacy of textile materials up to a specific number of intervals [21]. After identifying the construction specifications of the samples, they were laundered through the American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorists (AATCC) Monograph [22] in a front load washing machine under the agitation speed of 45 ± 10 rpm. The temperature was set to 54°C

for 11 ± 1 minutes. An approximate 0.1g/liter standard detergent was added in each wash cycle. The samples were spun at 1300rpm for about 12 minutes. The tumble drying was made at 68°C for one and a half hours.

A total of 15 laundering cycles were applied to the samples from each category. After every 5 cycles, they were labeled and processed for further testing. All test samples were kept at a temperature of 21°C and 65% relative humidity for one day [23]. The samples were assessed for their resistance against 4 liquid chemicals, i.e. sulphuric acid, sodium hydroxide, xylene, and butanol, according to the procedure defined by ISO 6530:2005 [24], through their ratios of penetration and repellency. This method helps determining the rate of penetration and repellency against these liquid chemicals [25]. The samples from each group were cut into 14×9 inch pieces and were taken as an upper layer. An absorbent sheet with a plastic back of the same dimensions was also acquired and weighed separately. Their distance was approximately 1 inch and they were placed on a collector layer. This test assemblage was tilted at 45° . Ten milliliters of each chemical were poured off through a nozzle from the test fabric and were collected in a beaker placed beneath it. After a minute, both layers were separated and weighed again. The chemical retained by the collector layer was considered for the penetration rate. The chemical in the beaker was recorded as the repellency rate. At least one of the chemicals should repel 95% and penetrate less than 5% of the samples. The rate of penetration was measured as:

$$P = \frac{A \times 100}{B} \quad (1)$$

where A is the chemical retained by the absorbent sheet and B is the chemical retained by the test specimen. The rate of repellency was calculated as:

$$R = C \times \frac{100}{B} \quad (2)$$

where C is the chemical collected in a beaker and B is the chemical retained by the test specimen.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tested clothing materials did not pass the minimum performance criteria for protecting against liquid chemicals. The samples did not repel 95% of any chemical, even at the initial washing cycles. Moreover, more than 5% of each chemical penetrated them even at zero washes. The condition worsened with each washing interval. One of the main reasons was the increase in the porosity of the fibers due to the laundering cycles, as they opened their structure and allowed the chemical to pass through more easily. The difference between samples was due to the variation in fiber content. It is always necessary to study the chemical resistance of protective clothing worn by workers for protection. Laundering thins the fibers due to the constant rubbing in the washing machine and weakens them, letting the liquid pass through them [26]. The kind of polymer plays an important role in determining the chemical behavior of fabrics [27]. It was found that specimen AB-1 performed well, followed by AB-5 and AB-2, due to the presence of polyester fibers which helped repel the chemicals. It was also found that the fabrics were made in a single layer with low mass rates, which also caused them to allow the penetration of more chemicals and repel less [28]. The increase in mass and the number of layers increases the time it takes for any chemical to penetrate the structure [29, 30]. The lamination and coating applied on the surface of fabrics also makes them strong and durable against the penetration of liquids. It was observed that the tested samples were laminated with weak finishing treatments that leaked the chemicals in the very initial washing cycles. This treatment was removed at the last interval and all liquid chemicals permeated through the fabric structure, as seen in Table II.

TABLE II. RATE OF PENETRATION AND REPELLENCY OF TESTED SPECIMENS

Laundering cycle	Sample code	Sulphuric acid		Sodium hydroxide		Xylene		Butanol	
		P	R	P	R	P	R	P	R
0	AB-1	21.7	78.7	29.6	70.8	34.8	65.7	23.8	75.4
0	AB-2	38.5	61.5	48.6	49.8	64.2	34.8	49.8	45.8
0	AB-3	51.2	45.7	68.6	32.4	79.6	22.7	57.6	39.6
0	AB-4	50.9	41.1	66.2	32.9	78.5	20.7	73.9	25.1
0	AB-5	29.7	69.6	44.8	54.9	48.2	49.2	59.1	41.4
5	AB-1	39.7	61.5	49.7	51.4	49.3	48.1	48.9	49.7
5	AB-2	42.3	56.8	55.7	41.9	49.7	49.3	48.6	47.3
5	AB-3	50.8	38.3	73.6	27.9	72.3	24.2	78.5	19.6
5	AB-4	62.6	35.4	75.8	24.8	86.6	13.2	68.3	29.6
5	AB-5	48.6	51.7	55.8	43.6	59.8	41.8	58.2	41.8
10	AB-1	41.2	61.9	49.8	49.7	63.5	33.6	41.2	58.6
10	AB-2	59.8	41.8	67.8	32.1	78.1	21.5	42.8	37.5
10	AB-3	71.2	28.4	82.5	14.9	88.5	17.3	81.1	18.5
10	AB-4	68.9	29.2	80.5	19.5	88.5	11.2	83.5	15.8
10	AB-5	68.6	31.4	65.9	31.7	83.1	15.6	82.2	18.5
15	AB-1	79.7	22.5	69.2	29.5	76.3	22.4	82.9	17.4
15	AB-2	77.8	20.9	81.4	17.2	90.9	7.5	88.9	11.4
15	AB-3	80.4	18.7	88.5	11.6	92.5	7.3	88.6	10.2
15	AB-4	88.7	10.5	90.7	9.5	94.2	5.4	91.4	8.4
15	AB-5	76.7	22.7	85.6	13.5	89.3	9.9	89.1	10.8

Note: P=Penetration %age, R=Repellency %age

The penetration and repellency of the tested specimens were directly proportional to the laundering cycles. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to measure the difference between specimens after washing intervals of 0, 5, 10, and 15 cycles. The p-values, 0.00 and 0.001, show that specimens deteriorate in their performance with each washing interval for penetration and repellency respectively, as seen in Table III.

TABLE III. STATISTIC ANALYSIS AT VARIOUS WASHING INTERVALS

Chemical resistance	Washing interval	Mean square	F	p-value
Penetration	Linear	17965.23	46.76	0.00
Repellency	Linear	15674.52	38.91	0.01

IV. CONCLUSION

This study concluded that the locally manufactured protective clothing does not provide complete protection against liquid hazards. The variation in the results was due to the variation in the construction parameters of the collected samples. The performance of the materials worsened with the increasing number of washing cycles. This study can help textile manufacturers to make amendments to their construction parameters and techniques in order to provide better protection against chemical hazards. Every industry has its performance requirements.

V. FUTURE WORK AND LIMITATIONS

This study was limited to the chemical industries, while follow-up studies should evaluate the performance of clothing used by the textile sector and medical or agricultural personnel. Follow-up studies should also investigate other items of protective clothing, such as gloves and masks, as this study was limited only to protective coveralls. Moreover, future studies should examine the risks of fire hazards. Furthermore, future studies should also investigate the perceptions and experiences of employees and employers to point out factors that will boost the establishment of safety frameworks in industries.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Karim *et al.*, "Sustainable Personal Protective Clothing for Healthcare Applications: A Review," *ACS Nano*, vol. 14, no. 10, pp. 12313–12340, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.0c05537>.
- [2] Z. Khan, Y. B. Yusof, N. H. B. Abass, M. B. I. Ahmed, and Q. B. Jamali, "Recommendations for the Implementation of ISO 9001:2015 in the Manufacturing Industry of Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7177–7180, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4075>.
- [3] E. Khalil, "A Technical Overview on Protective Clothing against Chemical Hazards," *AASCIT Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 67–76, Jun. 2015.
- [4] M. A. Uddin, S. Afroj, T. Hasan, C. Carr, K. S. Novoselov, and N. Karim, "Environmental Impacts of Personal Protective Clothing Used to Combat COVID- 19," *Advanced Sustainable Systems*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2022, Art. no. 2100176, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsu.202100176>.
- [5] A. H. Memon, M. H. Peerzada, K. Muhammad, S. A. Memon, S. A. Mangi, and G. Mujtaba, "Recent Eco-Friendly Developments in Personal Protective Clothing Materials for Reducing Plastic Pollution: A Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 4012–4018, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2674>.
- [6] US EPA, "Personal Protective Equipment," *Personal Protective Equipment*, 2020. <https://www.epa.gov/emergency-response/personal-protective-equipment>.
- [7] F. Siddiqui, M. A. Akhund, A. H. Memon, A. R. Khoso, and H. U. Imad, "Health and Safety Issues of Industry Workmen," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3184–3188, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2138>.
- [8] K. Niinimäki, G. Peters, H. Dahlbo, P. Perry, T. Rissanen, and A. Gwilt, "The environmental price of fast fashion," *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 189–200, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-020-0039-9>.
- [9] M. Khan and C. A. Damalas, "Occupational exposure to pesticides and resultant health problems among cotton farmers of Punjab, Pakistan," *International Journal of Environmental Health Research*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 508–521, Sep. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09603123.2014.980781>.
- [10] F. Lamm, C. Massey, and M. Perry, "Is There a Link between Workplace Health and Safety and Firm Performance and Productivity?," *New Zealand Journal of Employment Relations*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 75–90, <https://doi.org/10.3316/informit.135846714466567>.
- [11] Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, "Labour Force Survey 2012-13 (Annual Report)," 2013.
- [12] W. A. Khan, T. Mustaq, and A. Tabassum, "Occupation Health, Safety and Risk Analysis," *International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 1336–1346, Aug. 2014.
- [13] A. R. Khoso, M. A. Akhund, A. H. Memon, F. Siddiqui, and S. H. Khahro, "Health and Safety of Hyderabad Industries' Labor. Causes and Awareness," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2334–2339, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1626>.
- [14] Najaf Shah *et al.*, "Assessment of the Workplace Conditions and Health and Safety Situation in Chemical and Textile Industries of Pakistan," *Science Journal of Public Health*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 862–869, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.sjph.20150306.20>.
- [15] M. M. Houck, *Identification of Textile Fibers*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier Science, 2009.
- [16] "Test Method for Fiber Analysis: Qualitative," American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorists, Research Triangle Park, NC, US, Standard AATCC TM20-2021, 2021.
- [17] "Test Method for Fiber Analysis: Quantitative," American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorists, Research Triangle Park, NC, US, Standard AATCC TM20A-2021, 2021.
- [18] "Standard Test Method for End (Warp) and Pick (Filling) Count of Woven Fabrics," ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard ASTM D3775-17e1, 2018.
- [19] "Standard Test Methods for Mass Per Unit Area (Weight) of Fabric," ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard ASTM D3776/D3776M-20, 2020.
- [20] "Standard Test Method for Yarn Number Based on Short-Length Specimens," ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard ASTM D1059-17, 2019.
- [21] M. Ijaz, S. Kalsoom, and N. A. Akthar, "Abrasion Resistance of Materials Used for Chemical Protective Clothing at Various Washing Intervals," *Scientific International Journal (Lahore)*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 411–414, 2016.
- [22] "Standardization of Home Laundry Test Conditions," *AATCC Technical Manual 2017*, vol. M6-2016, pp. 457–460, 2016.
- [23] "Standard Practice for Conditioning and Testing Textiles," ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard ASTM D1776/D1776M-20, 2020.
- [24] "ISO 6530:2005 - Protective clothing — Protection against liquid chemicals — Test method for resistance of materials to penetration by liquids," International Organization for Standardization, Geneva, Switzerland, Standard ISO 6530:2005, 2005.
- [25] P. Otr̃isal, S. Florus, and R. Karkalić, "Resistance of Barrier Materials Against Toxic Compounds Permeation and Its Evaluation in Accordance with New European Norms," *International conference - The Knowledge-based Organization*, vol. 23, pp. 224–233, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1515/kbo-2017-0182>.
- [26] S. Krzemińska and W. M. Rzymiski, "Barrierity of Hydrogenated Butadiene-Acrylonitrile Rubber and Butyl Rubber After Exposure to Organic Solvents," *International Journal of Occupational Safety and*

- Ergonomics*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 41–47, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2011.11076869>.
- [27] U. Sata, E. Wilusz, S. Mlynarek, G. Coimbatore, R. Kendall, and S. S. Ramkumar, "Development of Cotton Nonwoven Composite Fabric for Toxic Chemical Decontamination and Characterization of its Adsorption Capabilities," *Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*, vol. 8, no. 1, Mar. 2013, Art. no. 155892501300800130, <https://doi.org/10.1177/155892501300800112>.
- [28] G. E. Ibrahim, A. F. Abdel-motaleb, and E. R. Mahmoud, "Achieving Optimum Scientific Standards for Producing Fabrics Suitable for Protecting Against Hazardous Chemical Liquids," *Life Science Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 342–353, 2012.
- [29] S. Krzeminskaa and W. M. Rzymiski, "Thermodynamic Affinity of Elastomer-Solvent System and Barrier Properties of Elastomer Materials.," *Acta Physica Polonica*, vol. 124, no. 1, pp. 146–150, Jul. 2013.
- [30] International Labour Organization, "Encyclopaedia of Occupational Health and Safety," 2012. https://www.ilo.org/safework/info/publications/WCMS_113329/lang--en/index.htm.

Seismic Assessment of Steel Frames Subjected to Multi-hazards

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Abstract-This paper investigates the effects induced by thunderstorm downbursts to steel building structures that have been previously damaged during strong directivity ground motion events. To achieve this objective, one four-story steel moment-resisting frame that was tested at the E-defense laboratory, Japan was analyzed in the nonlinear range using OpenSees. The seismic response was numerically simulated, obtaining a satisfactory agreement with the experimental evidence, revealing that the effects of such wind events and vertical ground motions were significant. These effects should be addressed during the design of low and medium buildings subjected to initial damage and subsequent thunderstorm downbursts and the ductility demands on structures subjected to multi-hazards can be quantified. The wind loads are applied as an externally applied dynamic load and the revised ductility demands are determined directly. The obtained results are compared to what is expected by experimental tests.

Keywords-steel building; thunderstorm downbursts; ductility demands; wind; earthquake; non-linear analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

The devastating effects of severe thunderstorms observed over the last decade have inspired researchers to study this complex phenomenon [1, 2]. Actual evidence shows that buildings damaged by earlier hazards are prone to secondary effects from consecutive multi-hazards, such as thunderstorm downbursts [3, 4]. This can increase damage after a disaster, eventually leading to the collapse of structures left unprotected after the primary hazards. A thunderstorm downburst differs from synoptic winds as it produces a small-scale follow-up divergence within a 5km radius, accompanied by intense microbursts. This configuration can cause damage corresponding to a synoptic wind sequence of 70m/s within a time interval of 5 to 20min [5, 6]. Due to the nose shape profile with different heights above the ground, the wind speed reaches its peak between 30 and 100m above the ground [7]. This phenomenon poses risks related to the collapse mechanism of low to high buildings [8, 9] There are still important knowledge gaps ranging from the design aspects to the evolution of contingency plans and strategies to increase resilience. The current guidelines have such limitations because they ignore

the co-occurrence of natural events such as earthquakes and winds [10-12]. A design framework that takes into account seismic loading and strong synoptic wind has recently been proposed [13]. Other studies focused on dealing with multi-hazards are [14, 15], although no studies have been conducted to determine the ductility requirements of damaged structures under additional effects of thunderstorm downbursts.

This paper investigates the seismic response and the effects of the downburst outflow wind at mean speeds ranging between 33m/s and 75m/s on the ductility of damaged buildings. The proposed methodology combines the principles of nonlinear static adaptive pushover analysis [16], which aims to reproduce the damage caused by the primary hazard event, and the sequential dynamic analysis [17-23], aiming to estimate the damage caused by the secondary sequential thunderstorm event.

II. CONSIDERED STEEL FRAME

A. Tested Bare Frame

The tested steel frame is described in [24-26] and only a brief explanation is given here. The test specimen consists of a 2-span 4-story moment-resistant steel frame shown in Figure 1. The two span-lengths in the main direction are 5m, while in the transversal direction the span-length is 6m. The heights of the ground floor and of the upper floors are 3.875m and 3.5m respectively. The ground floor columns are rigidly connected to 1.5m high load-bearing concrete blocks. The blocks, in turn, are clamped into the shaking table. The beam-column connections are inherently rigid and, following the practice developed after the 1995 Hyogoken-Nanbu earthquake, were detailed to force the formation of plastic hinges from the joints.

B. Description of the E-defense Experiments

The experiments consisted of shaking the sample frame with 3 scaled 3-D versions of the ground motion recorded in Takatori during the Kobe earthquake. The inputs were scaled at 40%, 60%, and 100%. The 40% input aimed to create only elastic deformations in the frame, the 60% input created inelastic deformations and nearly collapsed the frame, and the 100% input caused the frame to collapse.

Fig. 1. Tested steel frame

III. EARTHQUAKE GROUND MOTIONS

The earthquake records used in this investigation are the horizontal and vertical components of the Newhall records from the 1994 Northridge earthquake, available from the Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research (PEER) center [27] (Figure 2). The record represents a range of severe ground motions and exhibits a near-fault effect. It has been indicated [28] that the structural response depends primarily on the peak acceleration impulse in the ground motions and that the continued motion of lower amplitude has little effect on the maximal responses. The peak ground accelerations for the horizontal and vertical components are 0.578g and 0.537g respectively.

IV. WIND DATABASE RECORD

The present study created a wind recording database based on the simulation method reported in [29, 30] and on the algorithm proposed in [31]. The database was previously used to study the inelastic analysis of multi-degree of freedom

systems damaged by earthquakes posteriorly subjected to wind load [19]. The cross-spectral density of the turbulent fluctuation is taken into account in the simulation of the wind field. Therefore, the wind actions on the building frame borders have been integrated into the concentrated load acting on the supporting members of the structures. The there-second peak velocity time series at the height of maximum velocity, i.e. $Z_{U_{max}} = 10\text{m}, 50\text{m}, \text{ and } 75\text{m}$ above the ground, are illustrated in Figure 3. The maximum velocities, U_{max} , are 59, 70, and 78m/s for $Z_{U_{max}} = 10, 50, \text{ and } 75\text{m}$. This defines three different velocities along the height of the structure and thus affects the lateral load distribution and the energy absorption capacity of the structure.

Fig. 2. Earthquake records.

The static forces induced by wind were calculated using (1).

$$F_i = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_D A_i U^2 \left(\frac{z}{z_r} \right)^{2\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where the reference height (z_r) was taken as 10m, ρ represents the air density, C_D is a drag coefficient, and A is the area exposed to the wind. Eurocode 1 gives values for α between 0.12 and 0.3, whilst a value of $\alpha = 0.22$ was used to represent the wind profile in suburban areas.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A nonlinear static pushover analysis is initially presented to induce the ductility demand of the primary hazard events and identify the correlation between the base shear forces and the lateral roof displacement up to a target plastic deformation. The pushover analysis is used in order to bring the structure at a

pre-defined ductility demand level, including the descendant branch of the load-deformation curve, permitting direct control of the initially imposed damage. The transient non-stationary wind loads are subsequently applied as externally applied dynamic loads and the revised displacement ductility requirement is determined directly. Then, the ductility demands for different ductility levels can be calculated using (2):

$$\mu = \frac{d_{max}}{d_y} \quad (2)$$

where d_{max} is the target roof displacement, and $d_{yielding}$ is the corresponding yielding. The d_{max} is 0.04516, 0.05793, 0.1004, and 0.1828 for LD (Limited Damage), SD (Significant Damage), NC (Near Collapse), and CS (Collapse Start) damage states respectively, corresponding to roof displacement ductility. The yielding drift $d_{yielding}$ is 0.04516. The base shear force-roof displacement relationship of the considered steel frame is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 3. Time history of the horizontal velocity at the height of the maximum velocity.

Fig. 4. Pushover capacity curves of considered steel frame.

Nonlinear analysis was carried out for different cases of the considered steel frame subjected to: (a) horizontal and vertical motions, (b) transient wind loads alone, and (c) to a combination of wind and both vertical and horizontal motions using the finite element program OpenSees [33].

Figures 5 and 6 show the comparison of the experimental results, the Pavan post-test results, and the numerical results of

displacements and shear forces at each floor. It is observed that once the actual input ground motion was considered in the analysis, the numerical predictions agreed relatively well with the experimental results.

Fig. 5. Maximum relative displacement at every floor level.

Fig. 6. Maximum story shear.

Initially, the transient wind loads (i.e. $Z_{Umax} = 10m$, $Z_{Umax} = 50m$, and $Z_{Umax} = 75m$) are applied on the steel frame alone and the results are shown in Figures 7 and 8. The deformations of the steel frame are within the elastic range under thunderstorm downburst for $Z_{Umax} = 10m$, since the ductility is less than 1, i.e. 0.61997 (Table I). Higher ductility can be observed under thunderstorm downburst, $Z_{Umax} = 50m$ and $75m$, as shown in Figure 7. The structural deformations entered to the plastic range and the maximum ductility demands are 1.26209 and 1.74921 respectively.

The base shear forces-roof displacement relationship for the sequential multi-hazards analysis is shown in Figures 9 and 10. The 3 simulated thunderstorm downburst scenarios are applied to the damaged steel frame which has previously attained a target ductility demand level (i.e. DL, SD, NC, and CS). The maximum ductility demands of the sequential analysis are summarized in Table I. This Table demonstrates, in general, that the ductility demands of the sequential wind event tend to increase as the initial target ductility level increases.

Fig. 7. Maximum relative displacement under downburst at every level.

Fig. 8. Maximum story shear under downburst.

Fig. 9. Maximum relative displacement under multi-hazards at every level.

Under the sequential analysis of downburst outflow wind, the structure responded inelastically and higher plastic deformations than during the initial static pushover analysis were observed. The maximum ductility was found to be 5.73476, 6.02261, and 6.17760 respectively. The ductility demands increased significantly to 3.18725%, 8.36653%, and 11.15538% when the downburst reached the peak-velocity time series at the height of maximum velocity, i.e. Z_{Umax} = 10m, 50m and 75m above the ground than the ductility level of the primary event (simultaneous horizontal and vertical

excitations). Under these ductility demand levels, a collapse mechanism was formed.

The proposed approach can successfully identify the capacity limits and predict the failure mechanism of structures under sequential hazard events and can be implemented to appraise the increased ductility demands within a multi-hazard assessment framework.

Fig. 10. Maximum story shear under multi-hazards.

TABLE I. DUCTILITY DEMAND FOR VARIOUS DOWNBURST SCENARIOS

Z_{Umax} (m)	10	50	75
Wind alone	0.61997	1.26209	1.74921
Limited Damage (DL)	5.73476	6.02261	6.17760
Significant Damage (SD)	4.47039	4.69477	4.81559
Near Collapse (NC)	2.57860	2.70803	2.77772
Collapse Start (CS)	1.41685	1.48796	1.52626

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The seismic behavior of steel frame structures under sequential hazard loads in the nonlinear range is investigated in the current paper. The main conclusions from the analysis can be summarized as follows:

- The input energy from the sequential downburst outflow wind event can push the structure into plasticity, exceeding the single hazard ductility demand. The damage level experienced by the structure during the secondary hazard event increases with the ductility demands of the primary event.
- Under the sequential analysis of downburst outflow wind, the ductility demand increases significantly by 3.18725%, 8.36653%, and 11.15538% from the ductility level of the primary event when the downburst reaches the peak-velocity time series at the height of maximum velocity of 10, 50, and 75m above the ground (simultaneous horizontal and vertical excitations).
- The proposed approach can successfully identify the capacity limits and predict the failure mechanism of structures under sequential hazard events and can be implemented to appraise the increased ductility demands within a multi-hazard assessment framework.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. E. Brooks, "Severe thunderstorms and climate change," *Atmospheric Research*, vol. 123, pp. 129–138, Apr. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2012.04.002>.
- [2] A. T. Radler, P. H. Groenemeijer, E. Faust, R. Sausen, and T. Pucik, "Frequency of severe thunderstorms across Europe expected to increase in the 21st century due to rising instability," *npj Climate and Atmospheric Science*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–5, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-019-0083-7>.
- [3] "Hurricane Katia leaves two dead in Mexico as earthquake clean-up begins," *ABC News*, Sep. 10, 2017. <https://www.abc.net.au/news/2017-09-10/deadly-quake-hurricane-katia-a-one-two-punch-for-mexico/>.
- [4] F. K. Narayan Chandrika, "Mexico had two major earthquakes this month. Here's why," *CNN*, Sep. 20, 2017. <https://www.cnn.com/2017/09/20/americas/mexico-two-earthquakes-in-one-month/index.html>.
- [5] T. T. Fujita, *The Downburst: Microburst and Macroburst*, 1st ed. Chicago, IL, USA: University of Chicago, 1985.
- [6] F. T. Lombardo, D. A. Smith, J. L. Schroeder, and K. C. Mehta, "Thunderstorm characteristics of importance to wind engineering," *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, vol. 125, pp. 121–132, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2013.12.004>.
- [7] T. Theodore Fujita, "Downbursts: meteorological features and wind field characteristics," *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, vol. 36, pp. 75–86, Jan. 1990, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6105\(90\)90294-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6105(90)90294-M).
- [8] A. M. Loredou-Souza, E. G. Lima, M. B. Vallis, M. M. Rocha, A. R. Wittwer, and M. G. K. Oliveira, "Downburst related damages in Brazilian buildings: Are they avoidable?," *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, vol. 185, pp. 33–40, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2018.11.022>.
- [9] A. Tilloy, B. D. Malamud, H. Winter, and A. Joly-Laugel, "A review of quantification methodologies for multi-hazard interrelationships," *Earth-Science Reviews*, vol. 196, Sep. 2019, Art. no. 102881, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2019.102881>.
- [10] A. M. Aly and S. Abburu, "On the Design of High-Rise Buildings for Multihazard: Fundamental Differences between Wind and Earthquake Demand," *Shock and Vibration*, vol. 2015, Sep. 2015, Art. no. e148681, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/148681>.
- [11] D. Duthinh and E. Simiu, "Safety of Structures in Strong Winds and Earthquakes: Multihazard Considerations," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 136, no. 3, pp. 330–333, Mar. 2010, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ST.1943-541X.0000108](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0000108).
- [12] S. N. Thilakarathna, N. Anwar, P. Norachan, and F. A. Naja, "The Effect of Wind Loads on the Seismic Performance of Tall Buildings," *Athens Journal of Technology & Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 251–276, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.30958/ajte.5-3-3>.
- [13] S. Kwag, A. Gupta, J. Baugh, and H.-S. Kim, "Significance of multi-hazard risk in design of buildings under earthquake and wind loads," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 243, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 112623, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2021.112623>.
- [14] S. Elias, R. Rupakhety, and S. Olafsson, "Analysis of a Benchmark Building Installed with Tuned Mass Dampers under Wind and Earthquake Loads," *Shock and Vibration*, vol. 2019, Nov. 2019, Art. no. e7091819, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/7091819>.
- [15] A. E. Taha, "Vibration Control of a Tall Benchmark Building under Wind and Earthquake Excitation," *Practice Periodical on Structural Design and Construction*, vol. 26, no. 2, May 2021, Art. no. 04021005, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)SC.1943-5576.0000569](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)SC.1943-5576.0000569).
- [16] A. K. Chopra and R. K. Goel, "A modal pushover analysis procedure for estimating seismic demands for buildings," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 561–582, 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.144>.
- [17] D. Isobe and S. Tanaka, "Sequential Simulations of Steel Frame Buildings Under Multi-Phase Hazardous Loads During Earthquake and Tsunami," *Frontiers in Built Environment*, vol. 7, 2021, Art. no. 669601, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2021.669601>.
- [18] Q. Li and B. R. Ellingwood, "Performance evaluation and damage assessment of steel frame buildings under main shock–aftershock earthquake sequences," *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 405–427, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1002/eqe.667>.
- [19] O. Badla, T. Bouzid, and P. M. Vazquez, "Inelastic Analysis of Mdf Systems Damaged by Earthquakes, Posteriorly Subjected to Wind Load," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 575–593, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2021-03091675>.
- [20] S. Park, J. W. van de Lindt, D. Cox, R. Gupta, and F. Aguiniga, "Successive Earthquake-Tsunami Analysis to Develop Collapse Fragilities," *Journal of Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 851–863, Aug. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632469.2012.685209>.
- [21] R. A. Hakim, M. S. A. Alama, and S. A. Ashour, "Seismic Assessment of an RC Building Using Pushover Analysis," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 631–635, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.428>.
- [22] H. Ullah, M. Rizwan, M. Fahad, and S. a. A. Shah, "Seismic Evaluation of the RC Moment Frame Structure using the Shake Table," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6674–6679, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3959>.
- [23] P. C. Nguyen, "Nonlinear Inelastic Earthquake Analysis of 2D Steel Frames," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6393–6398, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3855>.
- [24] M. Tada, M. Ohsaki, S. Yamada, S. Motoyui, and K. Kasai, "E-Defense Tests on Full-Scale Steel Buildings: Part 3 - Analytical Simulation of Collapse," in *Research Frontiers at Structures Congress 2007*, Jun. 2012, [https://doi.org/10.1061/40944\(249\)19](https://doi.org/10.1061/40944(249)19).
- [25] K. Suita, S. Yamada, M. Tada, K. Kasai, Y. Matsuoka, and Y. Shimada, "Collapse experiment on 4-story steel moment frame: Part 2 detail of collapse behavior," in *14th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Beijing, China, Oct. 2008.
- [26] A. Pavan, R. Pinho, and S. Antoniou, "Blind prediction of a full scale 3D steel frame tested under dynamic conditions," in *14th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Beijing, China, Oct. 2008.
- [27] "PEER Ground Motion Database - PEER Center." <https://ngawest2.berkeley.edu/#disclaimer>.
- [28] R. W. Clough and K. L. Benuska, "FHA Study of Seismic Design Criteria for High-Rise Buildings," Federal Housing Administration, Washington DC, USA, Report HUD TS-3, 1966.
- [29] P. Martinez-Vazquez and N. Rodriguez-Cuevas, "Wind field reproduction using neural networks and conditional simulation," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 29, no. 7, pp. 1442–1449, Jul. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2006.08.024>.
- [30] P. Martinez-Vazquez, "Wind-induced vibrations of structures using design spectra," *International Journal of Advanced Structural Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 379–389, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40091-016-0139-4>.
- [31] E. H. Vanmarcke, E. Heredia-Zavoni, and G. A. Fenton, "Conditional Simulation of Spatially Correlated Earthquake Ground Motion," *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, vol. 119, no. 11, pp. 2333–2352, Nov. 1993, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9399\(1993\)119:11\(2333\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9399(1993)119:11(2333)).
- [32] PEER, "Guidelines for Performance-Based Seismic Design of Tall Buildings," University of California, Berkeley, CA, USA, 2010/05, 2010.
- [33] "Open System for Earthquake Engineering Simulation - Home Page." <https://opensees.berkeley.edu>.

A Novel Approach on Speaker Gender Identification and Verification Using DWT First Level Energy and Zero Crossing

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Abstract-The aim of this work is to find a new criterion for determining a range of values in order to determine the gender of a speaker. The use of the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) of the Daubechies db7 parent wavelet and the computation of the zero crossing energy from the first level of the DWT was followed by computation of the values of the criterion for both genders and comparison with the value of the speech basic frequency for both genders for the same sign or sentence. The standard has a limited range of values close to the basic frequency range of the same speaker through which we can determine gender. This criterion has been tested on several men and women databases with different repeated sentences for the same person or for both genders and it gives acceptable results that can be worked on.

Keywords-speaker gender; DWT; energy; zero crossing

I. INTRODUCTION

The difference in the linguistic characteristics of humans is characterized by the variance in frequencies of the two genders. Generally, the frequencies of women are smaller than those of men. Usually, the sound consists of vibrations with different lengths and heights. As the human ear cannot hear all the vibrations, some of them are audible, i.e. from 20Hz to 20kHz, and some are inaudible. Frequencies smaller than 20Hz are inaudible and frequencies larger than 20kHz are inaudible and painful to the human ear. Of course, as we get older, the limit of hearing drops, sometimes to 17kHz [1]. The speech signal is non-stationary, complex, and variable with time [2]. In addition, the highest frequency of the speech signal is in the order of 5kHz. The operations done on this signal, such as sampling, require frequencies according to Shannon's law that the sampling frequency is more than twice the frequency of the original signal under study. Many research works have formerly addressed the study and determination of the range of f_0 values [3], which dealt with extracting the basic frequency in the domains of time and frequency as well as wavelets. In addition, some research works deal with a comparison between estimation methods for computing the fundamental for a newborn. In [2], the authors presented techniques for determining the frequency position in time. Other research

works [4-6] were interested by this subject, on which researches are still developing since it is not possible to confirm definitively the criterion that determines the gender of the speaker according to the basic frequency domain. Authors in [7] present an efficient approach for automatic speaker identification based on cepstral features, the Normalized Pitch Frequency (NPF) with Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) and wavelet de-noising pre-processing. On the other hand, wavelet based features in combination with Spectral-Subtraction (SS) were proposed in [8] for speaker identification in clean and noisy environment. Using neural networks for speech recognition tasks, where words are constructed from sequential individual and text-independent sound segments was addressed in [9] for speaker identification. To reduce memory utilization for speaker audio segment identification, authors in [10] proposed a new on line speaker identifier model using short input audio segments. Extracting features from raw speech that captures the unique characteristics of each speaker is accomplished by the filter bank-based Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) approach [11] using Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT). The Average Framing Linear Prediction Coding (AFLPC) technique combined with wavelet transform for text-independent speaker identification systems was presented in [12]. Extracting features from raw speech that capture the unique characteristics of a particular individual using Wavelet Packet Transform (WPT) is presented in [13]. Authors in [14] identify speakers basing on cepstral feature strategy and the NPF as a new feature, for enhancing accuracy using Neural Networks (NN). A motivating application of speech signals identification, for the detection of people with heart failure by glottal features, was presented in [15]. A robust feature extraction method for a real-time speech recognition hardware system was presented in [16].

In the current work, a novel approach for speaker gender identification and verification is introduced. This new criterion is based on DWT and the intersections with zero of the DWT first level for both genders with comparison to speech fundamental frequency. The simulation results prove that the proposed approach enhances the performance of speaker

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identification, especially with the DWT and the de-noising pre-processing step.

II. SPEECH SIGNAL CHARACTERISTICS

The speech signal is an audio carrier of complex and diverse information and has features such as the fundamental frequency characteristic, which is often denoted by f_0 . Other characteristics are the energy and the frequency spectrum [17]. The vibration or the cycle of opening/closing of the vocal cords represents f_0 . This frequency characterizes only the voiced segments and evolves slowly over time [17]. The speaker frequency varies according to age and gender. It extends approximately from 60Hz to 150Hz for men and from 150Hz to 450Hz for women. The fundamental frequency extraction is not an easy task since the periodicity of vibration of the vocal cords is not always perfect [6]. The amplitude of the speech signal changes significantly over time and in the audible speech. This amplitude is much greater than in the inaudible speech and reflects to us the energy changes in the signal. One of the characteristics of the speech signal is the energy feature, usually symbolized by E, computed according to (2). This energy is very high in audible sounds compared to inaudible sounds in which the energy is weak [18].

$$E_x = \sum_n^{N-1} (X(n))^2 \quad (1)$$

According to the scheme shown in Figure 1, we symbolize the standard called Wavelet Energy Rate (WER), which is applied to the first DWT level of the speech signal under study. This signal is a spoken sentence by some speakers of different genders containing repeated and different sentences. These are samples taken from a database that was prepared specifically for this study: videos of sentences in mp4 format were taken from people of both genders. These videos are downloaded and the spoken sentences were converted to wav format. Each sentence was sampled separately according to the sampling frequency $f_e = 11025\text{hz}$, which is a frequency greater than double the frequency of the speech signal (5khz) on the basis of Shannon's law.

III. FILTERING

The filtering step is accomplished through a mathematical transformation applied on the speech signal under study using a low pass filter with cutoff frequency $f_c = 600\text{Hz}$. This low pass filter reduces the signal high frequency to $-10\log_{10} (2)\text{dB}$ in the order of -3dB , which means decreasing the signal output energy to the 71% of the original speech signal [19]. Among the most widely used filters are the Butterworth linear filters, which are similar in shape with a difference in the cut-off frequency range. This filter has the largest amplitude and is more stable with frequency in the pass range and in the transition region with moderate reduction and is selected based on amplitude accuracy [20]. The filter order represents the number of columns in the filter pass region. For example, a filter of order n has a reduction rate of $6 \times n \text{ dB/decade}$ to $20 \times n \text{ dB/decade}$. When $n=8$ its reduction is 48dB/decade [20].

Fig. 1. General scheme.

Fig. 2. Filtered speech signal.

IV. DISCRETE WAVELET TRANSFORM

DWT is based on sub-band coding, and developed after that to be a technique similar to sub-band coding called hierarchical coding [21]. It is identified by the following relationship [22]:

$$X_{DWT}[n] = x[n] * h[n] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} x[k] * h[n - k] \quad (2)$$

DWT analyzes the original signal $x(n)$ in different frequency bands with different degrees of accuracy by evaluating the signal into approximate and detailed coefficients where the approximate coefficients have the highest amplitude, the lowest frequencies, and possess most of the energy. The components of the highest frequencies are mixed with the noise existing in the original signal.

Fig. 3. First level signal DWT decomposition after filtering. (a) Approximation part a_1 of speech signal, (b) detail part of speech signal d_1 .

As previously mentioned, the DWT uses digital filtering techniques, in which the signal to be analyzed passes through filters with different cut-off frequencies at different scales. The original signal is divided into details coefficients and approximation coefficients, which are often denoted by a_k and d_k respectively, where d denotes the detailed coefficients and a denotes the approximate coefficients, while k denotes the analytical level. The two parameters are the result of the convolution of the original signal $x(n)$ with the pass filter, meaning that the approximate parameters are the result of the low pass filter convolution with the original signal and the detailed parameters are the convolution of the high pass filter with the original signal [24].

$$a_1 = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} X(k)y[2n - k] \quad (3)$$

$$d_1 = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} X(k)z[2n - k] \quad (4)$$

In the waveform analysis, the signal is analyzed and synthesized according to stages starting from dividing the signal $x(n)$ to the end of the required level and rebuilding it from the last level we stopped to the end of the first level from which we started. For example, if the original signal $x(n)$ contains 512 samples and a frequency from 0 to π , then each of the approximate and detailed coefficients in the first level has 256 samples and one half ($1/2$) the frequency of the signal, i.e. $\pi/2$, and in the second level there are 128 samples and the half frequency of the signal level, i.e. $f = \pi/4$ or $1/4$ of the original signal frequency for both approximate and detailed parameters.

As mentioned above, the wavelet transform has more flexibility in designing the pulse shape and less sensitivity to signal distortion. The DWT analyzes the original signal $x(n)$ in different frequency bands with different degrees of accuracy by analyzing the signal into approximate coefficients and detailed coefficients. The approximate coefficients have the highest amplitude and components of low frequencies and possess most of the signal energy. It is known that the speech signal is continuous and the fundamental frequency of a man's voice is around 50Hz (with period $T = 20$ ms) whereas the f_0 of a woman's voice is near 180Hz, with a period $T = 250$ ms. Also, the basic frequency for the voice of a woman and of a man rises to 500Hz and to 200Hz respectively.

V. INTERSECTIONS WITH ZERO

Intersections with zero is the number of the times the signal $x(n)$ passes through zero in a certain period of time. It is an indication of the frequency at which the energy is concentrated in the signal spectrum, as the energy is concentrated at low frequencies in audible speech, while in inaudible speech most of it is found in high frequencies. From this, the highest number of intersections with zero is at high frequencies and the lowest is at low frequencies [18]. We can say that the intersection of the signal with zero has a strong relationship with the distribution of energy with frequency. The number of intersections with zero is computed for the signal according to [25]:

$$npz = \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} |\text{sgn}[x(n)] - \text{sgn}[x(n - 1)]| \quad (5)$$

$$\text{sgn}[x(n)] = \begin{cases} +1 & x(n) \geq 0 \\ -1 & x(n) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

VI. THE PROPOSED WAVELET ENERGY RATE (WER)

The WER criterion is calculated according to (7). This new criterion allows us to determine the gender of the speaker based on the studied values. WER is the quotient of the energy E_{a_1} obtained from the approximation coefficient of the first level of the DWT applied on the signal $x(n)$ according to (8) divided by npz :

$$\text{WER} = \frac{E_{a_1}}{npz} \times \text{Tpz} \quad (7)$$

$$E_{a_1} = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (a_1(n))^2 \quad (8)$$

where a_1 is the DWT first level, E_{a_1} the DWT first signal approximation of coefficients energy, npz the DWT first level signal approximation of coefficient intersections with zero, and Tpz the intersection ratio with zero for the original signal.

The value of the WER criterion is distributed over a defined range from 50 to 180Hz for men and from 180 to 500Hz for women. These values are similar to the fundamental frequency of the speech signal f_0 , which determines the gender of the speaker as a first process, before identifying the speaking person by comparison with other values in our previously prepared database.

VII. USED COMPUTATION TOOLS

In our investigation, we used KVideo Downloader4 program to download English learning videos in mp4 format

from an Internet Database. Then, these clips were converted to wav format using on line Covertio and on line Cloud Convert. The obtained signal was sampled into some specific sentences using the Audacity program by a sampling frequency $f_s=11025\text{Hz}$ to be analyzed and studied by the Matlab A13 toolbox on a compute with the following specifications: PC Acer based on x67, processor: Intel® Core™ i3-2348M, CPU: n2.30GHz, Version SMBIOS 2.7, Operating system: Windows 10

VIII. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Through the obtained experimental results presented below, the developed approaches were applied on some different repeated sentences from male and female speakers. We run 200 experiments on the speech signal to extract about 4500 different values, after filtering the speech signal with a Butterworth filter of degree $n=8$ and sampling frequency $f_s=11025\text{Hz}$. This signal was analyzed to the first level by DWT seventh partition (db7). The number of intersections with zero to be multiplied by the ratio of the original signal intersections with zero, according to (7) and (8) are shown in Table I.

Through Tables I and II, it was found that the energy of the original signal has different values in the two genders. The energy of the original signal for men is much greater than for women and this happens for the same repeated sentence, several different sentences for the same woman or the same man, or using the same sentence for several women and several men, as shown in Figure 9.

$$E_{SH} \gg E_{SF} \quad (9)$$

where E_{SH} is the energy of the original signal for men and E_{SF} the energy of the original signal for women.

TABLE I. A SENTENCE REPEATED FOR THE SAME PERSON AND FOR SEVERAL PEOPLE (4 WOMEN AND 3 MEN)

A sentence repeated for the same person and for several people (4 women and 3 men) "do you speak english"							
	Signal	Sample number	Energy signal	Energy E_{a1}	ZCN signal	ZCN_{a1}	ZCR_{a1}
Women	Woman A 601	22243	879380	28077000	1268	4405.3	0.0570
	Woman A 602	21060	833610	25851000	1224	4282.3	0.0581
	Woman B 201	12487	271940	9406900	740	2623.8	0.0592
	Woman B 203	12820	275960	10579000	811	2874.1	0.0632
	Woman D 301	12449	1795300	9581200	768	2701.7	0.0617
	Woman D 302	12793	2313000	10444000	815	2885.4	0.0637
	Woman M 1000	15493	577710	11501000	723	2600.5	0.0467
	woman M 1003	15988	583980	12943000	795	2833.3	0.0497
Men	Man B 101	13292	5851300	6844900	526	1790.1	0.0396
	Man B 102	13667	6016100	7346700	538	1864.2	0.0394
	Man K 100	11341	317560	4442000	391	1371.3	0.0345
	Man W 400	11685	773940	4254200	364	1285.6	0.0311
	Man W 401	11638	425690	4075200	354	1245.3	0.0304

Fig. 4. Man B101 speech signal analysis (original, filtered, DWT decomposed, and energy spectrum), sentence: "do you speak English"?

Fig. 5. Woman B601 speech signal analysis (original, filtered, DWT decomposed, and energy spectrum), sentence: "do you speak English"?

Fig. 6. Woman B201 speech signal analysis (original, filtered, DWT decomposed, and energy spectrum), sentence: "do you speak English"?

Fig. 7. Comparison between woman a601 and woman b201 speech signal analysis (original, filtered, DWT decomposed, and energy spectrum), sentence: "do you speak English"?

Fig. 8. Comparison between woman b201 and man b101 speech signal analysis (original, filtered, DWT decomposed, and energy spectrum), sentence: "do you speak English"?

In the approximate coefficient a_1 signal, in the first level of the DWT, we find that the energy E_{a1} for women is greater than the energy for men and this is for the same repeated sentence or several different sentences for the same woman or the same man as shown in Tables I and II and Figure 10, or for

a repetitive sentence or several different sentences for several women and several men:

$$E_{a1H} \gg E_{a1F} \quad (10)$$

where E_{a1H} E_{a1F} represent the energy of the approximate coefficient $a1$ for men and women respectively.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the signal energy between a man and a woman.

Fig. 10. Comparison of the Energy of the DWT first level signal between a man and a woman.

It is noticeable that the number of intersections with zero (Zero Crossing Number-ZCN) in the original signal differs for the two genders with diverse values. The ZCN of the original signal for men is much greater than for women, and for the same repeated sentence, several different sentences for the same woman or the same man, and for several different sentences and several men/women as shown in Tables I-II and Figure 11.

$$npz_{SF} \gg npz_{SH} \quad (11)$$

where npz_{SH} is the intersection of the original signal with zero for men and npz_{SF} for women.

Fig. 11. ZCN comparison of for the signal between a man and a woman.

Fig. 12. ZCN comparison of in the DWT first level for the signals of a man and a woman.

On the other hand, for the approximate coefficient $a1$ signal in the first level of the DWT, we find that the zero crossing npz_{a1F} and the Zero Crossing Ratio (ZCR) for women is greater than that for men, for the same repeated sentence, several different sentences for the same woman, or for a repeated sentence or for different sentences for a number of men and

women, as shown in Tables I-II and Figure 12. Through Figure13, we conclude that the crossing ratio with zero for the same level is greater for women than for men.

$$npz_{a1F} \gg npz_{a1H} \quad (12)$$

where npz_{a1H} and npz_{a1F} represent the crossing with zero of $a1$ signal for men and women respectively.

Fig. 13. Comparison of ZCR in the DWT first level for the signal of a man and a woman.

TABLE II. WER COMPARISON FOR MEN AND WOMEN

Signal	Sample number	Energy signal	Energy signal E_{a1}	ZCN _{a1}	ZCR _{a1}	WER
4 women and 2 men with the same sentence: "do you speak English"?						
repeated 3 times						
Woman A 601	22243	879380	28077000	4405.3	0.0570	363.3295
Woman A 602	21060	833610	25851000	4282.3	0.0581	350.8538
Woman B 201	12487	271940	9406900	2623.8	0.0592	212.4698
Woman B 202	12645	274830	9855600	2715.3	0.0606	219.8762
Woman D 301	12449	1795300	9581200	2701.7	0.0617	218.7851
Woman D 302	12793	2313000	10444000	2885.4	0.0637	230.6052
Woman m1000	15493	577710	11501000	2600.5	0.0467	206.3805
Woman m1003	15988	583980	12943000	2833.3	0.0497	227.1477
Man B 101	13292	5851300	6844900	1790.1	0.0396	151.3138
Man B 104	13666	6009400	7216300	1827.3	0.0391	154.3159
Man k 100	11341	317560	4442000	1373.3	0.0345	111.5123
Man w 400	11685	773940	4254200	1285.6	0.0311	103.0833
Man w 401	11638	425690	4075200	1245.3	0.0304	99.5563
4 women with the same sentence: "see you later"						
Woman A 2001	13595	420980	12289000	3129.3	0.0664	260.8490
Woman B 2003	9503	311870	6561400	2401.4	0.0721	197.2349
Woman D 402	5277	5571700	1748100	1171.4	0.0627	93.6040
Woman m 3002	10365	322280	5379100	1826.2	0.0506	149.1963
Man C201	12686	5501500	7000400	1923.6	0.0436	158.6357
Women and men with different sentences						
Woman A 401	20629	699960	24785000	4187.6	0.0583	345.1550
Woman A 901	12242	306010	9660000	2726	0.0649	230.1245
Woman A 803	9077	237420	5131100	1984.3	0.0622	160.9541
Woman A 202	13809	374400	12119000	3059.5	0.0632	250.4241
Woman A 101	12444	388450	10553000	2946.0	0.0676	242.3755
Woman B 402	12880	486000	8577500	2319.3	0.0497	183.7694
Woman B 501	8002	132600	5120800	2172.6	0.0813	191.7493
Woman B 802	20612	662150	23670000	3982.7	0.0552	328.4199
Woman B 901	11119	258280	7549900	2346.7	0.0620	199.6459
Woman B 3003	13112	247580	11385000	3006.3	0.0665	251.8563
Woman D 502	10428	2916500	7576900	2519.8	0.0696	209.3417
Woman D 202	11089	1078200	7591400	2390.4	0.0617	195.8928
Woman D 001	12320	1556200	9288400	2666.1	0.0613	213.5040
Man B 501	13160	2597500	8359000	2153.7	0.0487	189.0446
Man B 904	10492	2106500	3325500	1081.8	0.0299	92.0017
Man B 144	11025	2578600	5503800	1718.6	0.0455	145.8184
Man B1004	10227	2481400	4480800	1520.2	0.0434	127.9606
Man B193	10998	2365600	5382100	1678.9	0.0446	143.1177
Man X102	8405	391600	5291400	2182.7	0.0748	181.4226
Man X 100	14152	1428800	13458000	3296.2	0.0668	272.9188
Man C100	11710	2518300	3975700	1196.7	0.0292	97.0313

Fig. 14. Comparison of WER for different speakers of both sexes.

The values shown in Table II give us the WER values for the studied speech signals $x(n)$. The signal is a repeated sentence for the same woman or the same man, the same sentence for several men and several women, or a speech signal containing different sentences for several men and several women, as shown in Figure 14. A comparison of these values in relation to the range of the fundamental frequency f_0 values in recently published research works was made. The result is that the WER criterion provides values approximately close to the values of f_0 for speakers of different sentences and gender. Accordingly, we can through WER specify values in a range from 50 to 180Hz for male speakers and values in a range from 180 to 504Hz for female speakers, which are almost similar to the range of fundamental frequency values which determine the speaker gender according to the value of his/her fundamental frequency using different methods. The direct computational speed of the WER is a faster and easier way to determine the gender of a speaker. Table II illustrates the comparison between WER values and Figure 14 shows their progress.

After this stage, which determines the gender of the speaker, the next stage of verifying the speaker is followed by reference to our stored database, according to the comparison process based on a suitable algorithm to authenticate and confirm the speaker as shown by the flowchart in the general scheme of Figure 1.

IX. CONCLUSION

In speech investigation, gender identification is usually performed by extracting the information from the speech signals. In this paper, we propose a novel criterion for determining the speaker gender by defining a range of sampled values using the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), and computing the energy in addition to the intersections with zero (ZCR) of the first level DWT followed by estimating the introduced criterion (WER) values for both genders. Comparison was made with the value of the speech fundamental frequency for speakers of both sexes. The proposed criterion was tested on a large database prepared for this research, containing many repeated sentences from the same person and from persons of both sexes and gives acceptable results, proving its suitability for speaker gender identification.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L. Jeancolas, "Détection précoce de la maladie de Parkinson par l'analyse de la voix et corrélations avec la neuroimagerie," Ph.D. dissertation, Paris-Saclay University, Paris, France, 2019.
- [2] R. Aïgou, "Techniques De Détection De La Période Du Pitch Par Les Méthodes Temps Fréquence Et Temps Échelle.," M.S. thesis, University of Biskra, Biskra, Algeria, 2010.
- [3] F. Bahja, *Détection du fondamental de la parole en temps-réel: Application aux voix pathologiques*. Presses Académiques Francophones, 2014.
- [4] R. Aïgou, S. Sbaa, S. Aouragh, and A. Taleb, "Détection Du Pitch Par Les Ondelettes Continues En Temps Réel Pour Un Signal Parole Basée Sur Un Seuil Adaptatif Pour Une Détermination V/Nv," *Courrier du Savoir Scientifique et Technique*, vol. 12, no. 12, pp. 21–26, May 2014.
- [5] M. A. Ben Messaoud, A. Bouzid, and N. Ellouze, "Estimation du pitch et décision de voisement par compression spectrale de l'autocorrélation du produit multi-échelle (Pitch estimation and voiced decision by spectral autocorrelation compression of multi-scale product) [in French]," in *Proceedings of the Joint Conference JEP-TALN-RECITAL 2012*, Grenoble, France, Mar. 2012, vol. 1, pp. 201–208.
- [6] Y. Fayçal, R. Amiar, S. Hecini, W. Benzaba, and L. Bendaouia, "Etude Comparative des Performances de Plusieurs Techniques de Détection de la Fréquence Fondamentale des Signaux Vocaux.," in *Proceedings of the 2nd Conférence Internationale sur l'Informatique et ses Applications (CIIA'09)*, Saida, Algeria, Jan. 2009.
- [7] M. A. Nasr, M. Abd-Elnaby, A. S. El-Fishawy, S. El-Rabaie, and F. E. Abd El-Samie, "Speaker identification based on normalized pitch frequency and Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients," *International Journal of Speech Technology*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 941–951, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10772-018-9524-7>.
- [8] M. Chandra, P. Nandi, A. Kumari, and S. Mishra, "Spectral-Subtraction Based Features for Speaker Identification," in *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Frontiers of Intelligent Computing: Theory and Applications (FICTA)*, 2015, pp. 529–536, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-12012-6_58.
- [9] S. R. Shahamiri and F. Thabtah, "An investigation towards speaker identification using a single-sound-frame," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 79, no. 41, pp. 31265–31281, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-020-09580-4>.
- [10] I. Vélez, C. Rascon, and G. Fuentes-Pineda, "Lightweight speaker verification for online identification of new speakers with short segments," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 95, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 106704, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2020.106704>.
- [11] W. Helali, Z. Hajaiej, and A. Cherif, "Real Time Speech Recognition based on PWP Thresholding and MFCC using SVM," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6204–6208, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3759>.
- [12] K. Daqrouq and K. Y. Al Zazzawi, "Average framing linear prediction coding with wavelet transform for text-independent speaker identification system," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 38, no. 6, pp. 1467–1479, Nov. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2012.04.014>.
- [13] C. Turner and A. Joseph, "A Wavelet Packet and Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients-Based Feature Extraction Method for Speaker Identification," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 61, pp. 416–421, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.09.177>.
- [14] M. A. Nasr, M. Abd-Elnaby, A. S. El-Fishawy, S. El-Rabaie, and F. E. Abd El-Samie, "Speaker identification based on normalized pitch frequency and Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients," *International Journal of Speech Technology*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 941–951, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10772-018-9524-7>.
- [15] M. Kiran Reddy *et al.*, "The automatic detection of heart failure using speech signals," *Computer Speech & Language*, vol. 69, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 101205, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csl.2021.101205>.
- [16] A. Mnassri, M. Bennis, and C. Adnane, "A Robust Feature Extraction Method for Real-Time Speech Recognition System on a Raspberry Pi 3 Board," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 4066–4070, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2533>.

- [17] A. Amehraye and S. Saoudi, *Débruitage perceptuel de la parole*. 2009.
- [18] R. Narayanam, "Voiced and Unvoiced Separation in Speech Auditory Brainstem Responses of Human Subjects Using Zero Crossing Rate (ZCR) and Energy of the Speech Signal," *International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology*, vol. 4, no. 9, pp. 370–380, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.892088>.
- [19] "Fréquence de coupure," *Wikipédia*. Feb. 11, 2022, [Online]. Available: https://fr.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Fr%C3%A9quence_de_coupure&oldid=190757368.
- [20] M. V. Daithankar and S. D. Ruikar, "Analysis of the Wavelet Domain Filtering Approach for Video Super-Resolution," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7477–7482, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4262>.
- [21] A. Pini, "Notions de base sur les filtres passe-bas antirepliement (et pourquoi ils doivent être adaptés au CAN)," *Digi-Key Electronics*, Mar. 24, 2020. <https://www.digkey.fr/fr/articles/the-basics-of-anti-aliasing-low-pass-filters>.
- [22] D. Sripath, "Efficient Implementations of Discrete Wavelet Transforms Using FPGAs," Jan. 2003.
- [23] E. Hostalkova, "Wavelet Transform," Athens, Greece, Nov. 2009.
- [24] A. Sumithra and B. Thanushkodi, "Performance Evaluation of Different Thresholding Methods in Time Adaptive Wavelet Based Speech Enhancement," *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 439–447, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.7763/IJET.2009.V1.82>.
- [25] K. Tajane, R. Pitale, and J. Umale, "Review Paper :Comparative Analysis Of Mother Wavelet Functions With The ECG Signals," *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 38–41, Jan. 2014.

The Influence of Hot Electrons on the Calculation of Ionization Rates

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Abstract- Electron-Impact Ionization (EII) is considered one of the most important ionization methods in dynamic systems, in which elements and ions are suddenly exposed to energetic electrons. In many plasma types, it has been observed that some electrons (hot) are governed by a non-Maxwellian energy distribution. This study illustrates the effects of a non-Maxwellian distribution on beryllium and Be^{+2} emission lines and their effective ionization rate coefficients. The focus on beryllium as an impacted material by electron flux aimed to evaluate the EII rates for Be and generate the corresponding datasets needed for Be^{+2} data analysis. An interaction cross-section was generated using the Flexible Atomic Code (FAC) and used in the estimation of the EII distribution energy functions to estimate the ionization rates for a non-Maxwellian distribution. The use of non-Maxwellian energy distributions for different fractions of hot electrons showed the sensitivity of these rates to the fraction of hot electrons and the forms of the electron energy distribution. The results were in good agreement with those found in the literature.

Keywords- Electron-Impact Ionization (EII); FAC; distribution function; non-Maxwellian distribution; cross-sections

I. INTRODUCTION

In plasma physics, considerable efforts are deployed to apprehend the emission of electrons during atomic ionization collisions under experimental and numerical perspectives. Electron Impact Ionization (EII) is important in dynamic systems where ions are immediately exposed to energetic electrons [1]. Such incidents may be encountered in solar flares, supernova remnants, and merging clusters of galaxies [2, 3]. EII has attracted considerable interest in the study of the distribution of the charge state of nonthermal electrons in plasma, where the high-energy tail includes a large population

of electrons residing above the EII rate. Consequently, EII is important to model astrophysical systems including non-thermal distributions [4]. Determining the spatial distribution of hot electrons in plasma is very crucial as they affect radiation production, energy balance, and plasma dynamics [5, 6]. These electrons may cause considerable energy losses and negatively impact the plasma's stability and control.

In plasma physics and nuclear fusion, non-Maxwellian distributions and hot electrons relate to plasma sources and their evolution. Besides that, they are necessary to assess the radiative properties of a broad range of plasma sources. Beryllium (Be) was used in the ITER fusion reactor project to cover the inner surface of the first wall as a plasma-facing material because of its unique physical property to contain radiation power and its ability to be less contaminated by plasma with low fuel retention. In this sense, it is very important to obtain accurate collisional data of EII on Be. The estimation of coefficient rates is based on analytical concepts developed in previous works and datasets [7]. These studies on hot electrons were related to specific experiments, and the results obtained were restricted to specific types of energy distribution used to characterize these electrons. It should be noticed that rates of collisional ionization, resonant excitation, and radiative recombination present a relative sensitivity with characteristic energy and functional shape of the electron distribution, which may have significant consequences on collisional radiative two-temperature models. These models usually include distributions of hot electrons with much greater energies than the usual transition gaps, where the sensitivity of hot electron effects for both Gaussian and Maxwellian distributions is observed separately [8].

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In this study, an analytical and numerical investigation on the ionization rates of plasma made from a population of electrons including a non-Maxwellian distribution of a given initial velocity, was conducted. The effects of the simultaneous presence of electrons with low and high energies on the calculation of ionization rate coefficients and their energy distribution functions are discussed. This approach aimed to present the influence of hot electrons and investigate the impact of the electron energy distribution functions on the measurement of the ionization rates for Be^{+2} using a non-Maxwellian energy distribution for various hot electron fraction values. The non-Maxwellian distribution used gave satisfactory results for larger fractions of hot electrons. This study focused on larger fractions of hot electrons because using a non-Maxwellian distribution gives unacceptable results on weak fractions. Compared to previous works on neutral helium ionization rates calculated using a non-Maxwellian distribution and the power-law distribution functions of electrons [9], this study exhibits a great improvement in the curves obtained, particularly for the Maxwellian and power-law distribution functions.

II. THEORETICAL ASPECT

A. Ionization Cross-sections

In laboratory or astrophysical plasma studies, it is very crucial to understand the ionization balance based on the estimation of ionization rates for different ions involved in such plasmas. Many analytical and statistical formulas are dedicated to the estimation of ionization rates and the related cross-sections. In this way, the Lotz formula has been frequently used in plasma-related fields as one of the most suitable empirical formulas to calculate the cross-sections of the ionization rates [10], based on experimental measurements of ionized elements with low Z [11, 12]. Similarly in [13], the parametric formula initially introduced in [14, 15] was used. Recently, dedicated codes were built to calculate the corresponding atomic structure and data related to interaction processes (recombination, ionization, excitation, etc.). Therefore, the Flexible Atomic Code (FAC) was mainly made to accommodate radiative transformation, direct collisional excitation, and ionization [16]. This robust package was presented in [17] to combine different atomic processes into a common theoretical system and provide a uniform, flexible, and easy-to-use user interface to access all computational tasks. FAC was used to calculate the EII cross-section, based on the Distorted Wave (DW) relativistic approximation and the interpolation-factorization methods [16, 17]. The cross-section of the transition:

for Be was generated using this code on a varying energy range from 0 to 1000eV, as shown in Figure 1. The FAC code included the DW method and generated cross-section data with a satisfactory level. Figure 2 shows the cross-sectional data of the ionization processes, obtained according to the DW method, taking into account the potential felt by the incident electron when approaching the nucleus of the target ion [18]. Thus, it was possible to generate the cross-sections needed over a large interval of incident electron energies, starting from the ionization threshold [17].

Fig. 1. Cross-section of Be obtained by FAC.

Fig. 2. Cross-section of Be^{+2} obtained by FAC.

B. The Effects of Hot Electrons on the Calculation of Ionization Rates

Free electrons in a plasma are characterized by a given energy distribution. The quantity of interest is the ionization rate coefficient per electron impact, obtained by averaging the product of the electron velocity by the corresponding ionization cross-section. In the case of direct ionization, the coefficient of ionization rates is given by [19, 20]:

$$\tau [cm^3 \cdot s^{-1}] = \int v \sigma(E) F(E) dE \quad (1)$$

where v and E are the velocity and energy of the incident electron respectively, $\sigma(E)$ represents the impact ionization cross-sections calculated by FAC, $F(E)$ is the electron energy distribution function, and E is the energy of the impacting electron. A non-Maxwellian distribution function of the energy $F(E)$ was used to calculate the ionization rates by the mean of cross-sections. The produced plasma under low pressure often exhibit a non-Maxwellian behavior of electron distributions. Such a distribution can be represented by a function of two temperatures corresponding to both hot and cold electron populations. The following non-Maxwellian distribution was chosen to study the effects of hot electrons on the ionization rates of Be [20]:

$$F_{NM}(E) = (1 - f_{hot})F_M(T_{bulk}) + f_{hot}F_X(T_{hot}) \quad (2)$$

where f_{hot} is the normalized hot electron fraction, F_M is the Maxwell energy distribution function, and T_{bulk} and T_{hot} are the bulk and hot electron temperatures respectively.

By substituting (2) in (1) and including the effective ionization cross sections generated by the FAC code for Be atoms, it was possible to obtain the ionization rates for different values of hot electron fractions f_{hot} , as shown in Figure 3 by plotting the obtained curves representing the variation of the ionization rate coefficients of Be using the non-Maxwellian distribution. This was carried out for different values of hot electron fractions f_{hot} as a function of the electron temperature T , taken between 1.0 and 10^3 eV, including the results obtained by applying a Maxwell distribution for $f_{hot}=1$. The temperature T_{bulk} was taken equal to an average value of $k_B T_{bulk}=0.85$ eV [19]. The fractions of cold electrons are less than those of hot electrons. The rate coefficients at very low temperatures are very sensitive to the cross-section behavior near the threshold and significant discrepancies may be observed between various theoretical calculations and/or empirical scaling. The plane wave of Born approximation is not valid at low energies and gives typically lower cross-sections than the DW computation method near the threshold by a factor of 2 [10].

Fig. 3. Ionization rates of Be obtained for a non-Maxwellian distribution with different values of hot electrons fraction $f_{hot}=0.7, 0.8, 0.9$, and 1.0.

Figure 3 shows that the curves obtained for the various fractions (70%, 80%, 90%) are generally quite close to the plotted for the referential fraction value $f_{hot}=1$ representing the Maxwellian distribution. As a matter of fact, in the case of low temperatures, the ionization rates are very sensitive to the cross-section behavior [21]. There are noticeable differences between theoretical and experimental methods. Examining the published results in [10] for comparison, the plotted curves of ionization rates in Figure 3 are shifted down from the Maxwellian distribution for $f_{hot}=1$ as the hot electron fraction decreases. This shows a remarkable sensitivity of the ionization rates related to hot electron fractions.

C. Distribution Functions

The electron energy distribution is highly important in plasma physics, nuclear fusion reactions, and astrophysics [22]. Consequently, collisional-radiative atomic models assessing the effect of a non-Maxwellian distribution and hot electrons are extremely important to apprehend the obtained data in atomic physics, such as in spectroscopic analysis to establish the existence and characteristics of the behavior mechanisms of

electrons in studied plasmas [23, 24]. Dedicated experiments and research on hot electrons provided valuable contributions to build suitable energy distribution functions, as given by the following expressions [20]:

Maxwellian:

$$F_M(\varepsilon, T_e) = 2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\pi T_e^3}} \exp\left[-\varepsilon/T_e\right] \quad (3)$$

Gaussian:

$$F_G(\varepsilon, T_e) = \frac{1}{T_e \sqrt{\pi}} \left(\frac{2}{1 + \operatorname{erf}(\varepsilon_0/T_e)} \right) \exp\left[-\left(\frac{\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0}{T_e}\right)^2\right] \quad (4)$$

Power-law:

$$F_p(\varepsilon, T_e) = \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{T_e^{1-\gamma}}\right) \varepsilon^{-\gamma}; \varepsilon \geq T_e \quad (5)$$

where T_e , ε , ε_0 are the energies of electrons corresponding to each distribution, and γ is the decay constant.

The energy distribution helps to examine how the used model affects the estimation of the ionization rates for given cross-sections. For plasma described by a single-temperature Maxwellian distribution, it is possible to calculate de-excitation and recombination rates with accurate precision, explicitly from the coefficients of collisional excitation and ionization rates. In the case of plasmas with atoms described by non-Maxwellian distributions, the cross-sections related to calculated rates must be integrated through the entire distribution of electron energies. A simple analytical formula could express the associated rate coefficients when using the appropriate approximation of the cross-sections as an energy-dependent function. This study aims to extend the calculations for plasmas described by a non-Maxwellian distribution. Plasmas containing a small proportion of hot electrons may be observed in the universe or in the laboratory, and induced plasmas often exhibit non-Maxwellian distributions with hot and cold electrons. Therefore, using cross-sections generated by the FAC, the ionization rates were calculated using different energy distribution functions $F(\varepsilon)$. Ionization rates were obtained for various values of hot electron fractions f_{hot} by separately substituting $F_x(\varepsilon, T_e)$ from (2) with Maxwellian (3), Gaussian (4), and Power-law (5).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 4 and 5 show the ionization rates for Be⁺² for different values of hot electron fractions using Maxwellian, Gaussian, and Power-law models in (2). In the case of the Maxwellian model shown in Figure 4, the values of the coefficient rates increased very rapidly at low temperatures. Figure 5 shows the comparison between different distribution functions for a specific value. A good agreement can be observed between the ionization rate curves for hot electron fractions ranging from 1 to 10% over the whole energy range. Furthermore, the value of the decay constant γ does not significantly affect the calculation estimation for a given value of the fraction of hot electrons [9]. The relative susceptibility of the ionization rates to the form of the electron energy distribution functions when $\gamma=2$ and the hot electron fraction assume high values have significant consequences for

collisional radiative models at two temperatures. When the temperature of electrons increases, the hot electron distribution takes a thermal form with a long tail compared to the Maxwellian distribution at thermal equilibrium electron distribution functions over the whole energy range for various values of given hot electron fractions f_{hot} .

Fig. 4. Ionization rates of Be⁺²: Coefficient rates obtained for the Maxwellian distribution function with various fractions of hot electrons f_{hot} .

Fig. 5. Ionization rates of Be⁺²: Coefficient rates obtained for Maxwellian, Gaussian, and Power-law distribution functions with $f_{hot}=0.1$.

Fig. 6. Ionization rates of Be⁺²: Coefficient rates obtained for different power distribution functions with various decay constants: (a) $\gamma=2$, (b) $\gamma=3$, (c) $\gamma=4$ and different hot electron fractions.

Figure 6 shows the ionization rates of Be⁺² obtained for different power-law distributions defined by a given decay

constant γ . Figures 6(a) and (b) show the generated results for both power 2 and 3 models at low temperatures and indicate the presence of susceptibility to the fractions of hot electrons as the value of the constant of decay γ increases. Figure 6(c) shows significant variations within the 10-100eV range, where a considerable improvement in curve shape is registered for the power 4 model ($\gamma=4$).

IV. CONCLUSION

This study used the FAC code and a non-Maxwellian distribution function to calculate the ionization rates and the corresponding cross-sections of Be and Be⁺². Most collisional rates were more sensitive to the hot electron fractions than to the exact functional form of the electron energy distributions. Greater hot temperatures naturally contain larger numbers of superthermal electrons and thus allow larger fractions of hot electrons, which may cause profound impacts. Ionization rates are very sensitive to the behavior of cross-sections. It should be also noticed that considerable differences between theoretical and empirical methods may be registered. The use of a non-Maxwellian energy distribution demonstrated that the estimated rates are sensitive to the forms of electron energy distributions used [25, 26]. In the case of beryllium, it was shown that the curves of ionization rates are responsive to the hot electron fractions of 70 and 80%. The curve of the ionization rate approaches that of [10] for the fraction of 100% of hot electrons. The results obtained from the ionization rates for Be⁺² and different energy distribution functions showed an acceptable agreement between the curves of various figures, except for the Maxwellian distribution function. Furthermore, significant deviations were observed for low temperatures in the 20-200eV energy range. Finally, exceptional sensitivity of the ionization rates for Be⁺² was shown for various fractions of hot electrons.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Salzmänn, *Atomic Physics in Hot Plasmas*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 1998.
- [2] A. S. Shlyaptseva *et al.*, "Advanced spectroscopic analysis of 0.8-1.0-MA Mo x pinches and the influence of plasma electron beams on L-shell spectra of Mo ions," *Physical Review E*, vol. 67, no. 2, Feb. 2003, Art. no. 026409, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.67.026409>.
- [3] J. Colgan, H. L. Zhang, and C. J. Fontes, "Electron-impact excitation and ionization cross sections for the Si, Cl, and Ar isonuclear sequences," *Physical Review A*, vol. 77, no. 6, Jun. 2008, Art. no. 062704, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.77.062704>.
- [4] M. Davoudabadi, J. S. Shrimpton, and F. Mashayek, "On accuracy and performance of high-order finite volume methods in local mean energy model of non-thermal plasmas," *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 228, no. 7, pp. 2468–2479, Apr. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2008.12.015>.
- [5] R. Bartiromo, F. Bombarda, and R. Giannella, "Spectroscopic study of nonthermal plasmas," *Physical Review A*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 531–537, Jul. 1985, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.32.531>.
- [6] A. Alogla, M. a. H. Eleiwa, and H. Alshortan, "Design and Evaluation of Transmitting Antennas for Solar Power Satellite Systems," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7950–7956, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4607>.
- [7] D. Mihalas and M. E. Stone, "Statistical Equilibrium Model Atmospheres for Early-Type Stars. III. Hydrogen and Helium Continua," *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 151, pp. 293–310, Jan. 1968, <https://doi.org/10.1086/149437>.

- [8] M. A. Mahmoud and K. A. Hamam, "Studies of Electron Energy Distribution Function (EEDF) in Lithium Vapor Excitation at 2S→3D Two-Photon Resonance," *Optics and Photonics Journal*, vol. 04, no. 08, pp. 195–212, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.4236/opj.2014.48020>.
- [9] S. Dilmi and A. Boumali, "Influence of the Electron Energy Distribution Function on the Calculation of Ionization Rate in Hot Plasma," *UPB Scientific Bulletin, Series A: Applied Mathematics*, vol. 79, no. 1, pp. 249–260.
- [10] T. Kato, K. Masai, and M. Arnaud, "NIFS Data 014 - Comparison of Ionization Rate Coefficients of Ions from Hydrogen Through Nickel," National Institute for Fusion Science, Nagoya, Japan, Sep. 1991.
- [11] W. Lotz, "Electron-impact ionization cross-sections and ionization rate coefficients for atoms and ions from hydrogen to calcium," *Zeitschrift für Physik*, vol. 216, no. 3, pp. 241–247, Jun. 1968, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01392963>.
- [12] W. Lotz, "Electron-impact ionization cross-sections and ionization rate coefficients for atoms and ions from scandium to zinc," *Zeitschrift für Physik A Hadrons and nuclei*, vol. 220, no. 5, pp. 466–472, Oct. 1969, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01394789>.
- [13] M. Arnaud and R. Rothenflug, "An Updated Evaluation of Recombination and Ionization Rates," *Astronomy and Astrophysics Supplement Series*, vol. 60, pp. 425–457, Jun. 1985.
- [14] S. M. Younger, "Electron impact ionization rate coefficients and cross sections for highly ionized iron," *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 541–544, May 1982, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4073\(82\)90106-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4073(82)90106-6).
- [15] S. M. Younger, "Electron-impact ionization cross sections for highly ionized hydrogen- and lithium-like atoms," *Physical Review A*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 111–117, Jul. 1980, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.22.111>.
- [16] International Atomic Energy Agency, "Flexible Atomic Code (FAC)." <https://www-amdis.iaea.org/FAC/> (accessed Sep. 26, 2022).
- [17] M. F. Gu, "The flexible atomic code," *Canadian Journal of Physics*, vol. 86, no. 5, pp. 675–689, May 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1139/p07-197>.
- [18] W. Lotz, "Electron-Impact Ionization Cross-Sections and Ionization Rate Coefficients for Atoms and Ions," *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, vol. 14, pp. 207–238, May 1967, <https://doi.org/10.1086/190154>.
- [19] A. Escarguel, F. B. Rosmej, C. Brault, T. Pierre, R. Stamm, and K. Quoth, "Influence of hot electrons on radiative properties of a helium plasma," *Plasma Physics and Controlled Fusion*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 85–93, Sep. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0741-3335/49/1/006>.
- [20] S. B. Hansen and A. S. Shlyaptseva, "Effects of the electron energy distribution function on modeled x-ray spectra," *Physical Review E*, vol. 70, no. 3, Sep. 2004, Art. no. 036402, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.70.036402>.
- [21] T. D. Märk and G. H. Dunn, Eds., *Electron Impact Ionization*, Softcover reprint of the original 1st ed. 1985 edition. New York, NY, US: Springer, 2013.
- [22] N. B. Serradj, A. D. K. Ali, and M. E. A. Ghernaout, "A Contribution to the Thermal Field Evaluation at the Tool-Part Interface for the Optimization of Machining Conditions," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7750–7756, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4235>.
- [23] R. S. Freund, "Electron Impact Ionization Cross-Sections for Atoms, Radicals, and Metastables," in *Swarm Studies and Inelastic Electron-Molecule Collisions*, New York, NY, 1987, pp. 329–346, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-4662-6_41.
- [24] J. L. S. Lino, "Cross sections for electron-impact excitation of neutral atoms," *Revista mexicana de física*, vol. 63, no. 2, pp. 190–193, Apr. 2017.
- [25] S. Dilmi and A. Boumali, "Estimation of Electron Impact Ionization Rates of Li Using a Non-Maxwellian Distribution Function," *Ukrainian Journal of Physics*, vol. 66, no. 8, pp. 691–697, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.15407/ujpe66.8.691>.
- [26] S. Saxena and L. B. Roy, "The Effect of Geometric Parameters on the Strength of Stone Columns," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 9028–9033, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5138>.

Strength and Deflection Reliability Estimation of Girder Steel Portal Frames Using the Bayesian Updating Method

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Abstract-Uncertainty is ubiquitous in any engineering system at any stage of product development and throughout a product's life cycle. As information and sensor technology develops, more and more data about engineering systems are gathered. A strong technique for calibrating models using new information and observations is Bayesian updating. The applied loads, yield strength, plastic section modulus, span, cross-section dimensions, and modulus of elasticity from the international literature have been updated through the local literature and a data survey for the interior girder portal frames to investigate the reliability index and the probability of failure of the system. First Order Reliability Method (FORM) and Monte Carlo (MC) simulations have been used to estimate the reliability and probability of failure of strength and serviceability limit state function. The results reveal that for shear force, the reliability index increased significantly from 9.03 to 16.01. At the same time, the reliability index of the bending moment and deflection increased from 4.34 to 5.30 and from 6.90 to 7.66 respectively.

Keywords-interior supporting frame; Bayesian method; sample data; prior data; posterior data; FORM; MC; reliability

I. INTRODUCTION

Most structure engineering designs are based on deterministic variables and often do not consider the variations in the material properties and the geometry of the structure [1]. For the purpose of determining the structural system's reliability, the effects of uncertainties must be quantified and propagated. Uncertainty and reliability are vital to the analysis and design of an engineering system. The reliability of the system can be stated in reference to some performance criteria. The need for reliability analysis stems from the fact that there is a presence of uncertainty in the definition, understanding, modeling, and behavior prediction of the models that describe the system [2]. Increasing amounts of data on engineering systems are collected and stored. This information can and should be used to reduce the uncertainty in engineering models and optimize the management of these systems. A coherent and effective framework for merging new information with existing models is provided by Bayesian analysis, in which prior

probabilistic models are updated with data and observations. The Bayesian framework enables the combination of uncertain and incomplete information with models from different sources and provides probabilistic information on the accuracy of the updated model [3]. The current study emphasizes on the reliability analysis of the strength and deflection of steel portal frames as new data are acquired for the independent variables of the system. The Bayesian method presents an efficient way to update the prior knowledge regarding the stiffness and strength of the frame. Finally, the FORM and MC simulations have been adopted to investigate the reliability of the deflection and strength.

II. THE BAYESIAN METHOD

In engineering, one often needs to use whatever information is available in formulating a sound basis for making decisions. This may include observed (field or experimental) data, information derived from theoretical models, and expert judgments based on experience. Moreover, the available information may need to be updated as new information or data are acquired [4]. The proper tool for combining and updating the available information is embodied in the Bayesian approach. Parameter estimation in the Bayesian approach is based on the updating formula:

$$f(\theta) = cL(\theta)p(\theta) \quad (1)$$

where $p(\theta)$ is the prior Probability Density Function (PDF) representing the initial state of knowledge about the unknown parameter θ , $L(\theta)$, is the likelihood function representing the knowledge gained from a set of observations, and the constant c is a normalizing factor. The posterior PDF, $f(\theta)$, represents the updated state of knowledge regarding the parameters θ .

A. Prior Distribution

The prior distribution represents the distribution of possible parameter values from which the parameter has been drawn. The selection of the prior distribution is an important matter in Bayesian modeling. Since the choice of the prior

distribution has a major effect on the resulting inference, this choice must be conducted with the utmost care [5].

B. Posterior Distribution

The posterior probability distribution contains all the current information about the parameter. It merges the information in both prior distribution and likelihood. This typically results in the posterior representing stronger information than separate sources of information [6]. The prior and posterior densities are presented in Table I, the mean and variance of the posterior parameters are presented in Table II.

TABLE I. RANDOM VARIABLES AND THEIR PRIOR AND POSTERIOR DENSITY DISTRIBUTIONS [4]

Basic Random Variables	Parameter	Prior and Posterior Distribution
Normal $f_x(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2\right]$	μ	Normal $\mu''_{\mu} = \frac{\mu'_{\mu}(\sigma^2/n) + \bar{x}\sigma'^2_{\mu}}{\sigma^2/n + (\sigma'_{\mu})^2}$
Lognormal $f_x(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\xi x} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\ln x - \lambda}{\xi}\right)^2\right]$	λ	Normal $f_{\lambda}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\lambda - \mu}{\sigma}\right)^2\right]$

TABLE II. MEAN AND VARIANCE OF THE PARAMETERS AND THEIR POSTERIOR STATISTICS [4]

Mean and Variance of Parameters	Posterior Statistics
$E(\mu) = \mu_{\mu}$	$\mu''_{\mu} = \frac{\mu'_{\mu}(\sigma^2/n) + \bar{x}\sigma'^2_{\mu}}{\sigma^2/n + (\sigma'_{\mu})^2}$
$Var(\mu) = \sigma_{\mu}^2$	$\sigma''_{\mu} = \sqrt{\frac{(\sigma'_{\mu})^2(\sigma^2/n)}{(\sigma'_{\mu})^2 + \sigma^2/n}}$
$E(\lambda) = \mu$	$\mu'' = \frac{u'(\xi^2/n) + \sigma^2 \ln \bar{x}}{\xi^2/n + \sigma^2}$
$Var(\lambda) = \sigma^2$	$\sigma'' = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2(\xi^2/n)}{\sigma^2 + \xi^2/n}}$

III. RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

The reliability analysis of an engineering structure requires the limit state function to evaluate its performance [7]. The concept of a limit state is used to help define failure in the context of structural reliability analysis. It is a boundary between desired and undesired performance of a structure. The limit state function can be defined as [8]:

$$g(R, Q) = R - Q \quad (2)$$

where R represents the resistance and Q represents the load effect. The state of the structure can be described using various parameters X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n , load and resistance parameters. The limit $g(X) = 0$ separates the failure domain ($g(X) < 0$) and the safety domain ($g(X) > 0$) [9].

IV. RELIABILITY ANALYSIS METHODS

Due to the randomness of nature events, the complexity of the applied loads and initial imperfections, many times it is impossible to describe the response of structural systems. As a result, various analytical and numerical approaches have been developed. Taylor Series (TS)-based approaches, such as the

FORM, and simulation-based methods, such as the MC simulation [4].

A. First-Order Reliability Method (FORM)

It is possible to expand the original model into infinite TS around the mean values:

$$g(X) = g(\mu_x) + (X - \mu_x) \frac{dg}{dX} + \frac{1}{2}(X - \mu_x)^2 \frac{d^2g}{dX^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{n!}(X - \mu_x)^n \frac{d^ng}{dX^n} \quad (3)$$

where the function and derivatives are evaluated at μ_x . It is common to include only linear terms, assuming that random input variables are independent. A function $g(X)$ of N independent random variables can be approximated by linear terms of the TS, which are [10]:

$$E(Y) \approx g(\mu_x) \quad (4)$$

$$Var(Y) \approx Var(X - \mu_x) \left(\frac{dg}{dX}\right)^2 = Var(x) \left(\frac{dg}{dX}\right)^2 \quad (5)$$

The limit state function is $g(x) = R - Q$, where R , and Q both being random variables uncorrelated and assumed to be normally distributed. The reliability index β is evaluated as a function of mean and standard deviation of resistance R and load Q as given by [9]:

$$\beta = \frac{\mu_R - \mu_Q}{\sqrt{\sigma_R^2 + \sigma_Q^2}} \quad (6)$$

The probability of failure is given by:

$$P_f = \Phi(-\beta) \quad (7)$$

where Φ is the cumulative probability distribution function of the standard normal variate.

B. Monte Carlo (MC) Method

The MC method is considered one of the most powerful and accurate simulation tools to estimate the reliability and failure probability of uncertain structures numerically. It can be applied to many practical problems allowing the direct consideration of any type of probability distribution for the random variables. Using MC simulations, an estimate of the probability of structural failure is obtained by [11]:

$$P_f = \frac{N_f}{N} \quad (8)$$

where N_f is the number of samples in the failure domain and N is the total number of samples.

V. STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

This study considers the applied loads, yield strength, plastic section modulus, girder span, cross-section dimensions, and modulus of elasticity as random variables. The sample data of the independent variables are summarized in Table III. The prior statistical characteristics of these variables collected from the literature are presented in Table IV. The posterior statistical data of the input variables have been calculated from the updating process of the prior data by the Bayesian method. The yield strength of steel F_y , has been considered as an example to

explain that process. Updating mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variance have been estimated based on the relations in (9)-(11). The posterior statistical characteristics of the independent variables are summarized in Table V.

$$\mu'' = \frac{\left[\frac{\bar{x}}{\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}\right)^2}\right] + \left[\frac{\mu'}{(\sigma')^2}\right]}{\left[\frac{1}{\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}\right)^2}\right] + \left[\frac{1}{(\sigma')^2}\right]} = \frac{\bar{x}(\sigma')^2 + \mu' \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{n}\right)}{(\sigma')^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{n}\right)} = \frac{(275)(275 \times 0.06)^2 + (275) \left(\frac{(275 \times 0.07)^2}{1}\right)}{(275 \times 0.06)^2 + \left(\frac{(275 \times 0.07)^2}{1}\right)} = 275 \text{MPa} \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma'' = \sqrt{\frac{(\sigma')^2 \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{n}\right)}{(\sigma')^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{n}\right)}} = \sqrt{\frac{(275 \times 0.06)^2 \left(\frac{(275 \times 0.07)^2}{1}\right)}{(275 \times 0.06)^2 + \left(\frac{(275 \times 0.07)^2}{1}\right)}} = 12.5 \text{MPa} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{cov}'' = \frac{\sigma''}{\mu''} = \frac{12.5}{275} = 0.04 \quad (11)$$

TABLE III. SAMPLE STATISTICAL DATA OF THE VARIABLES

Uncertainty in Variables	Mean Nominal	COV	Distribution type	Reference
Dead load, P_D	1.03	0.08	Normal	[12]
Live load, P_L	1.00	0.1	Gumbel	[13]
Moment of inertia, I_x	0.96	0.03	Normal	Local Survey
Modulus of elasticity, E_s	1.025	0.05	Normal	[14]
Modulus of elasticity, E_c	0.98	0.07	Lognormal	[15]
Member span, L	1.00	0.07	Lognormal	[16]
Plastic section modulus, Z_x	1.04	0.05	Lognormal	[17]
Yield strength of steel, F_y	1.10	0.07	Lognormal	[17]

TABLE IV. PRIOR STATISTICAL DATA OF THE VARIABLES

Uncertainty in Variables	Mean Nominal	COV	Distribution type	References
Dead load, P_D	1.03	0.08	Normal	[12]
Live load, P_L	1.00	0.1	Gumbel	[13]
Moment of inertia, I_x	0.96	0.05	Normal	[18]
Modulus of elasticity, E_s	1.00	0.02	Normal	[17]
Modulus of elasticity, E_c	1.00	0.03	Lognormal	[19]
Member span, L	1.00	0.004	Lognormal	[20]
Plastic section modulus, Z_x	1.00	0.04	Lognormal	[2]
Yield strength of steel, F_y	1.10	0.06	Lognormal	[18]

TABLE V. POSTERIOR STATISTICAL DATA OF THE VARIABLES

Uncertainty in Variables	Mean Nominal	COV	Distribution type
Dead load, P_D	1.03	0.08	Normal
Live load, P_L	1.00	0.1	Gumbel
Moment of inertia, I_x	0.96	0.005	Normal
Steel modulus of elasticity, E_s	1.01	0.016	Normal
Concrete modulus of elasticity, E_c	1.00	0.02	Lognormal
Member span, L	1.00	0.003	Lognormal
Plastic section modulus, Z_x	1.00	0.03	Lognormal
Yield strength of steel, F_y	1.10	0.04	Lognormal

VI. PARAMETRIC STUDY

A steel single-story warehouse, as shown in Figure 1, with a total length of 45m and width of 15m, and consisting of 5 bays has been considered in this parametric study. The superimposed dead load has been determined based on the

assumption of a flooring system of a concrete slab with a thickness of 100mm and a metal deck of 7.5mm, supported on floor beams of (IPE 300). The first inner frame shown in Figure 2 has been considered the most critical one as it includes the exterior face of the first interior support where the shear force is about 15% greater than the average value. The frame consists of IPE 600 steel girder and columns. The applied live loads on the girder have been determined based on the ASCE 7 specifications. The self-weight of the girder and columns have been determined depending on the cross-section dimensions and material density.

Fig. 1. Steel single-story warehouse building.

Fig. 2. Summary of the dead and live load on the interior supporting frame.

VII. DERIVED AND SIMULATED STATISTICAL PROPERTIES FOR THE STRENGTH AND DEFLECTION OF THE GIRDER

Two stages have been considered in the FORM and the MC simulation method. In the first stage, the randomness of the dependent variables has been deduced based on the prior knowledge of Table IV. In the second stage, they have been inferred based on the posterior knowledge of Table V.

A. First-Order Approximation Method

1) Flexure Analysis

The bending moment M is a function of the load P and the span L . With refereeing to (4) and (5), the mean and variance of the bending moment can be estimated by:

$$E(M) = f_m \times 0.904 \times \bar{P}L \quad (12)$$

$$Var(M) = Var(L) \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial L}\right)^2 + Var(P) \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial P}\right)^2 \quad (13)$$

where f_m is a deterministic dimensionless factor, equal to 0.56, that correlates the aforementioned bending moment to the bending moment of the corresponding simple span. The constant 0.904 is the mid-span bending moment due to the reactions from different floor beams. The nominal flexural strength M_n is a function of the yield strength F_y and the plastic section modulus Z_x . Refereeing to(4) and (5), the mean and variance of M_n can be estimated from:

$$E(M_n) = \bar{F}_y \bar{Z}_x \quad (14)$$

$$Var(M_n) = Var(F_y) \left(\frac{\partial M_n}{\partial F_y}\right)^2 + Var(Z_x) \left(\frac{\partial M_n}{\partial Z_x}\right)^2 \quad (15)$$

Based on the statistical characteristics of the independent variables illustrated in Tables IV and V, the prior and posterior statistical characteristics for bending moment M and nominal flexural strength M_n have been estimated and are presented in Tables VI and VII.

TABLE VI. PRIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE GIRDER'S STRENGTH

Random Variables	Nominal (kN.m)	Mean (kN.m)	Standard deviation (kN.m)	COV
M	577.11	585.08	53.08	0.0907
M_n	878	965.8	69.64	0.072

TABLE VII. POSTERIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE GIRDER'S STRENGTH

Random Variables	Nominal (kN.m)	Mean (kN.m)	Standard deviation (kN.m)	COV
M	577.11	585.08	53.06	0.0906
M_n	878	965.8	48.29	0.05

2) Shear Analysis

The shear force V , is a function of the load P . The mean and variance of the shear force are calculated by:

$$E(V) = f_v 3.5 \bar{P} \quad (16)$$

$$Var(V) = Var(P) \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial P}\right)^2 \quad (17)$$

where f_v is a deterministic dimensionless factor to correlate the aforementioned shear force to the shear force of the corresponding simple span and is equal to 1.0. The constant 3.5 is the shear at the support due to the reactions from different floor beams. The nominal shear force V_n is a function of the yield strength F_y and the area of the web A_w . The mean and variance of the nominal shear force are calculated by:

$$E(V_n) = 0.6 \bar{F}_y \bar{A}_w \quad (18)$$

$$Var(V_n) = Var(F_y) \left(\frac{\partial V_n}{\partial F_y}\right)^2 + Var(A_w) \left(\frac{\partial V_n}{\partial A_w}\right)^2 \quad (19)$$

TABLE VIII. PRIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SHEAR FORCE

Random Variables	Nominal (kN)	Mean (kN)	Standard deviation (kN)	COV
V	266	296.67	24.14	0.081
V_n	1011	1112	86.909	0.078

Based on the statistical characteristics of the independent variables illustrated in Tables IV and V, the prior and posterior statistical characteristics for V and V_n , have been estimated and are presented in Tables VIII and IX.

TABLE IX. POSTERIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SHEAR FORCE

Random Variables	Nominal (kN)	Mean (kN)	Standard deviation (kN)	COV
V	266	296.67	24.14	0.081
V_n	1011	1112	44.856	0.040

3) Deflection

The deflection Δ is a function of the load P , span L , modulus of elasticity E , and moment of inertia I . The mean and variance of the deflection are calculated by:

$$E(\Delta) = f_k \frac{613 PL^3}{6000 EI} \quad (20)$$

$$Var(\Delta) = Var(I) \left(\frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial I}\right)^2 + Var(L) \left(\frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial L}\right)^2 + Var(E) \left(\frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial E}\right)^2 + Var(P) \left(\frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial P}\right)^2 \quad (21)$$

where f_k is a deterministic dimensionless factor that correlates the aforementioned deflection to the deflection of the corresponding simple span, equal to 0.32. The constant 613/6000 is the deflection at the mid-span due to the reactions from different floor beams. Based on Tables IV and V, the prior and posterior statistical characteristics for deflection are presented in Tables X and XI.

TABLE X. PRIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DEFLECTION

Random Variables	Nominal (mm)	Mean (mm)	Standard deviation (mm)	COV
Δ	45	48.08	5.05	0.105

TABLE XI. POSTERIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF DEFLECTION

Random Variables	Nominal (mm)	Mean (mm)	Standard deviation (mm)	COV
Δ	45	48.57	4.49	0.092

Fig. 3. Histogram for prior (a) M and (b) M_n sample of the typical interior girder.

B. Monte Carlo Simulation

The MC method has been adopted to simulate the processes of the flexural strength, shear, and deflection for the interior supporting frame. A MATLAB code has been used to

generate pseudo-random sampling with a size of 1000 for each input variable.

1) Flexure Analysis

The prior statistical characteristics of the bending moment M and nominal bending moment M_n are presented in Figure 3 and Table XII. The estimated posterior statistical characteristics are presented in Figure 3 and Table XIII.

TABLE XII. PRIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF M AND M_n OF THE GIRDER

Random Variables	Mean (kN.m)	Standard deviation (kN.m)	COV	Distribution types
M	583.53	38.4	0.065	Normal
M_n	968.48	69.5	0.071	Lognormal

Fig. 4. Histogram for posterior prior (a) M and (b) M_n sample of the typical interior girder.

TABLE XIII. POSTERIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF M AND M_n OF THE GIRDER

Random Variables	Mean (kN.m)	Standard deviation (kN.m)	COV	Distribution types
M	583.52	38.29	0.06	Normal
M_n	964.81	49.12	0.05	Lognormal

2) Shear Analysis

The prior statistical characteristics of the shear force V and nominal shear force V_n were estimated and are presented in Figure 5 and Table XIV. The posterior statistical characteristics of V and V_n were estimated and are presented in Figure 6 and Table XV.

Fig. 5. Histogram for prior (a) V and (b) V_n of the typical interior girder.

TABLE XIV. PRIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF V AND V_n

Random Variables	Mean (kN)	Standard deviation (kN)	COV	Distribution types
V	269.84	17.40	0.064	Normal
V_n	1111.5	86.300	0.077	Normal

Fig. 6. Histogram for posterior (a) V and (b) V_n of the typical interior girder.

TABLE XV. POSTERIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF V AND V_n .

Random Variables	Mean (kN)	Standard deviation (kN)	COV	Distribution types
V	269.35	17.62	0.065	Normal
V_n	1112.8	43.70	0.039	Normal

3) Deflection

The estimated prior and posterior statistical characteristics of deflection are presented in Figure 7 and Table XVI.

Fig. 7. Histogram for (a) prior and (b) posterior deflection sample of the girder.

TABLE XVI. PRIOR AND POSTERIOR STATISTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GIRDER DEFLECTION

Random Variables	Mean (mm)	Standard deviation (mm)	COV	Distribution types
Δ_{prior}	48.38	4.14	0.085	Normal
$\Delta_{posterior}$	47.51	3.33	0.070	Normal

VIII. RELIABILITY ANALYSIS FOR STRENGTH AND DEFLECTION OF THE GIRDER

The FORM has been adopted to estimate the reliability associated with girder's flexural strength, shear, and deflection. In the FORM, it has been assumed that all independent variables have a normal distribution. The mean and standard deviation of girder's flexural strength, shear, and have been used to evaluate the reliability index β and the probability of failure P_f due to the randomness in the load effects and resistance characteristics. Regarding flexure analysis, the mean and standard deviation of the bending moment (E_M, s_M) and the nominal flexural strength (E_n, s_n) have been estimated in Tables VI and VII. The prior and posterior β and P_f are summarized in Table XVII.

TABLE XVII. PRIOR AND POSTERIOR β AND P_f FOR THE FLEXURE STRENGTH OF THE GIRDER

Strength due to	P_f	β
$(P_D + P_L)_{prior}$	7.12414×10^{-6}	4.34
$(P_D + P_L)_{posterior}$	5.79013×10^{-8}	5.30

For shear analysis, the mean and standard deviation of the shear force (E_V, s_V) and the shear strength (E_n, s_n) were estimated and can be seen in Tables VIII and IX. The results for the prior and posterior β and P_f are summarized in Table XVIII.

TABLE XVIII. PRIOR β AND P_f FOR THE SHEAR OF THE GIRDER

Strength due to	P_f	β
$(P_D + P_L)_{prior}$	8.58359×10^{-20}	9.03
$(P_D + P_L)_{posterior}$	5.44049×10^{-58}	16.01

The estimated mean and standard deviation of deflection (E_{Δ}, s_{Δ}) and nominal deflection ($E_{\Delta_n}, s_{\Delta_n}$) shown in Tables X and XI comply to the limitations of IBC 2009. The results for the prior β and P_f are summarized in Table XIX.

TABLE XIX. PRIOR AND POSTERIOR β AND P_f FOR THE GIRDER DEFLECTION

Deflection due to	P_f	β
$(P_D + P_L)_{prior}$	2.60013×10^{-12}	6.90
$(P_D + P_L)_{posterior}$	9.29665×10^{-15}	7.66

IX. CONCLUSION

This paper has performed a prior and posterior statistical characteristics reliability analysis of the girder of the first inner frame. Through the application of the Bayesian method and the results of the prior and posterior analysis, it was shown that the greater the knowledge gained about the independent parameters, the less is the randomness in the dependent parameters, and thus enhances the reliability of the system. The results revealed that the reliability index for shear force significantly increased from 9.03 to 16.01, when the statistical parameters of the system were updated, while the reliability index of the bending moment and deflection increased from 4.34 to 5.30 and 6.90 to 7.66 respectively.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. V. Ngo, K. V. Pham, D. D. Le, K. H. Le, and K. V. Huynh, "Assessing Power System Stability Following Load Changes and Considering Uncertainty," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2758–2763, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1892>.
- [2] P. E. Hess, D. Bruchman, I. A. Assakkaf, and B. M. Ayyub, "Uncertainties in Material and Geometric Strength and Load Variables," *Naval Engineers Journal*, vol. 114, no. 2, pp. 139–166, 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-3584.2002.tb00128.x>.
- [3] D. Straub and I. Papaioannou, "Bayesian Updating with Structural Reliability Methods," *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, vol. 141, no. 3, Mar. 2015, Art. no. 04014134, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EM.1943-7889.0000839](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EM.1943-7889.0000839).
- [4] A. H.-S. Ang and W. H. Tang, *Probability Concepts in Engineering: Emphasis on Applications to Civil and Environmental Engineering, 2e Instructor Site: Emphasis on Applications to Civil and Environmental Engineering*, 2nd ed. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 2006.
- [5] A. Belay, E. O'Brien, and D. Kroese, "Truck fleet model for design and assessment of flexible pavements," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 311, no. 3, pp. 1161–1174, Apr. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2007.10.019>.
- [6] A. Mansour, H. Jan, C. Zigelman, Y. N. Jen, and S. J. Harding, "Implementation of Reliability Methods to Marine Structures," *Transactions of the Society of Naval Architects and Marine Engineers*, vol. 92, pp. 353–382, 1984.
- [7] A. U. Ebebuwa and K. F. Tee, "Reliability estimation of buried steel pipes subjected to seismic effect," *Transportation Geotechnics*, vol. 20, Sep. 2019, Art. no. 100242, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trgeo.2019.100242>.
- [8] A. Nowak and K. Collins, *Reliability of Structures*. New York, NY, USA: McGraw-Hill, 2000.
- [9] D. Mohammed and S. Al-Zaidee, "Deflection Reliability Analysis for Composite Steel Bridges," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9155–9159, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5146>.
- [10] S. S. Kar and L. B. Roy, "Probabilistic Based Reliability Slope Stability Analysis Using FOSM, FORM, and MCS," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8236–8240, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4689>.
- [11] N. L. Tran and T. H. Nguyen, "Reliability Assessment of Steel Plane Frame's Buckling Strength Considering Semi-rigid Connections," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5099–5103, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3231>.
- [12] M. S. Darmawan, A. N. Refani, M. Irmawan, R. Bayuaji, and R. B. Anugraha, "Time Dependent Reliability Analysis of Steel I Bridge Girder Designed Based on SNI T-02-2005 and SNI T-3-2005 Subjected to Corrosion," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 54, pp. 270–285, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2013.03.025>.
- [13] S. G. Buonopane and B. W. Schafer, "Reliability of Steel Frames Designed with Advanced Analysis," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 132, no. 2, pp. 267–276, Feb. 2006, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(2006\)132:2\(267\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(2006)132:2(267)).
- [14] A. Ghabussi, J. Asgari Marnani, and M. S. Rohanimanesh, "Improving seismic performance of portal frame structures with steel curved dampers," *Structures*, vol. 24, pp. 27–40, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.istruc.2019.12.025>.
- [15] P. Geyskens, A. D. Kiureghian, and P. Monteiro, "Bayesian Prediction of Elastic Modulus of Concrete," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 124, no. 1, pp. 89–95, Jan. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(1998\)124:1\(89\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1998)124:1(89)).
- [16] H. Q. Jebur and S. R. Al-Zaidee, "Non-deterministic Approach for Reliability Evaluation of Steel Portal Frame," *Civil Engineering Journal*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 1684–1697, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2019-03091363>.
- [17] K. Atua, I. Assakkaf, and B. M. Ayyub, "Statistical characteristics of strength and load random variables of ship structures," in *Probabilistic Mechanics and Structural Reliability, Proceeding of the Seventh Specialty Conference*, Worcester, MA, USA, 1996.
- [18] H. Zhang, H. Liu, B. R. Ellingwood, and K. J. R. Rasmussen, "System Reliabilities of Planar Gravity Steel Frames Designed by the Inelastic Method in AISC 360-10," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 144, no. 3, Mar. 2018, Art. no. 04018011, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ST.1943-541X.0001991](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0001991).
- [19] ACI Committee 318, *Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete: (ACI 318-19); and Commentary (ACI 318R-19)*. Farmington Hills, MI, USA: American Concrete Institute, 2019.
- [20] *Indian standard, Tolerances for fabrication of Steel Structures*. New Delhi, India: Bureau of Indian Standards, 1974.

Refinery Wastewater Treatment by a Novel Three-Dimensional Electrocoagulation System Design

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Abstract-A novel three-dimensional electrocoagulation method was used in the current work to explore the treatment of refinery wastewater. Metal-Impregnated Granular Activated Carbon (MIGAC) was employed as a third particle electrode in the inventive design. A comprehensive investigation has been conducted to evaluate its performance. BET-specific surface area, total pore volume, X-ray Fluorescence (XRF), Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) were employed for the characterization of MIGAC particle electrodes at pH=7, 30V applied voltage, 10g of particle electrodes, 175mL/min flow rate, and a supporting electrolyte (0.063M NaCl + 0.025M Na₂SO₄). The findings indicate that the effectiveness of Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) elimination increased quickly after 20min to 66.93, 69.88, 77.59, 74.14, 81.26, 79.87, and 87.14% for Conventional Electrocoagulation (CEC). Three-dimensional electrocoagulation with granular activated carbon (TEC-RGAC), TEC-MIGAC (Al), TEC-MIGAC (Fe), and TEC-MIGAC (Al:Fe) with molar ratios of (1:1), (1:2), and (2:1) respectively were utilized. While turbidity removals were 99.04, 98.87, 99.23, 94.89, 92.42, 98.85, and 99.21% for CEC, TEC-RGAC, TEC-MIGAC(Al), TEC-MIGAC(Fe), TEC-MIGAC(1:1), TEC-MIGAC(1:2), and TEC-MIGAC(2:1) respectively. The results demonstrated that the metal impregnation of GAC is an interesting method for achieving effective turbidity and COD removal from refinery wastewater. In both batch and repeat recycling tests, MIGAC with a mixture of aluminum and iron oxides removed turbidity and COD more effectively and efficiently than RGAC.

Keywords-electrocoagulation; refinery wastewater; three-dimensional electrode; metal impregnated activated carbon; COD

I. INTRODUCTION

The aquatic environment is contaminated from sewage disposal, runoff from agricultural lands, air fallout, and waste management operations, such as the discharge of effluents from oil refining [1]. Refining processes convert crude oil into petroleum and other valuable byproducts. Large amounts of water are consumed throughout those activities, resulting in a proportional amount of wastewater, which consists of cooling water, process water, storm water, and sewage [2]. It was found that the amount of wastewater was about 0.4–1.6 times the amount of processed oil. In the wastewater from refineries and petrochemical plants, there are more than 20 different types of

harmful chemicals, even though the contaminants in wastewater depend a lot on the way the process is set up. Wastewater treatment structure, operational processes, and the kind of processed oil have significant impact on the composition of refinery wastewater [3]. Suspended particles, biodegradable and refractory organics, hydrocarbons, sulfides, phenols, and nitrogen compounds are the main pollutants in these industrial wastewaters [4].

As a fundamental requirement, the quality and availability of water are very important [5, 6]. Untreated effluent discharge needs to be under safety regulations [7]. So, effective and practical wastewater treatment methods for petroleum refineries are necessary. Biodegradation [8, 9], ultrafiltration [10], adsorption [11], and coagulation [12] are some of these processes. The techniques used in electrochemical processes include electroflotation (EF) [13], Electro-fenton Oxidation (EO) [14], electrocoagulation (EC) [12], and sequential EC and EO processes [15]. They have the benefits of being simply spread and requiring the least quantity of chemicals. Many studies during the recent years have focused on EC, an effective procedure for treating finely dispersed wastewater. Because this technology is both sturdy and small, it has the potential to replace complicated procedures that need huge volumes and/or a variety of chemicals [16]. Several parameters might be utilized to monitor the wastewater from petroleum refineries. One of them is the Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), which needs comparatively less time and may be used to evaluate the water quality as a whole [17].

Electrochemical methods have showed substantial practicality in the treatment of many industrial wastewaters, such as refinery wastewater [18, 19], due to their unique capacity to oxidize or remove contaminants in the water near the properly maintained electrode. However, due to its low current density, the conventional electrochemical approach does not perform successfully throughout the wastewater treatment process [20]. Complex chemical and physical changes occur often during any EC process. Positive ionic coagulants are generated as a result of sacrificial anode oxidation when a direct current or voltage is supplied. As a result of the water reduction at the cathode, hydroxyl ions (OH⁻) and some O₂ and H₂ gas bubbles can be generated [21]. To eliminate

contaminants, EC depends on the electrochemical formation of metal ions such as aluminum and ferric iron, which act as stabilizing reagents and neutralize the electric charge. The isomeric replacement of ferric ions by aluminum ions in iron oxides breaks crystallization, resulting in a greater surface area of the total adsorbents (oxide minerals), which may increase the removal effectiveness during combined EC using aluminum and ferric electrodes [22]. Traditional EC approaches for water and wastewater treatment have frequently employed single electrodes such as ferric-ferric and aluminum-aluminum, or combination electrodes such as aluminum-ferric or ferric-aluminum, known as the two-dimensional electrode system [23]. Combinations of aluminum-ferric or ferric-aluminum electrodes have been proved to be more successful in removing impurities than single electrode systems [24].

The use of three-dimensional electrodes in combination with carbon particles has been proposed as an alternative method that may effectively improve the working electrode's specific surface area and has been used for the removal of chloramphenicol [25], metal ions [26], and cyanides [27] from wastewater, and recently the elimination of organic pollutants, such as phenols [28], dyes [29, 30], tetracycline [31], and furfural degradation [32].

Three-dimensional (3D) electrode-based electrochemical techniques have attracted a lot of attention. A particle electrode or bed electrode serves as a third electrode in 3D electrochemical methods, in addition to the two electrodes used in the traditional (two-dimensional) electrochemical systems. These particle electrodes are loaded between the anode and the cathode. In 3D electrochemical systems, granular or powdery materials are often utilized as the working electrode and as particle electrodes. When external potential is present, this particle microelectrode generates charge. Depending on the kind of electrode, the degradation of organic pollutants can occur in a variety of ways. In addition to the procedure in two dimensional electrochemical systems, the fabrication of microelectrodes in 3D electrochemical systems enhances pollutant degradation [33]. Additionally, active carbon, a particle electrode that is frequently used, encourages the electro-generation of hydrogen peroxide and the subsequent production of hydroxyl radicals [34]. Reduced energy consumption due to a higher surface area to volume ratio, enhanced mass transfer, increased pollutant removal efficiency, generation of additional oxidants, and elimination of pollutants by sorption on particle electrodes are the major properties of 3D electrode reactors [35, 36].

The main objective of this study is to create a Three dimensional Electrocoagulation Metal-Impregnated Granular Activated Carbon with a (TEC-MIGAC) system using metal (aluminum, iron, or both). This system was developed with the goal of using metal-impregnated carbon particles as an adsorbent and metal-support media by leveraging the collaborative action of aluminum and ferric ions. It was tested in treating wastewater from the Iraq's Al-Daura petroleum refinery facility. MIGAC's textural characteristics were studied using BET, XRF, EDS, and SEM, while COD removal, turbidity removal, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) removal, current efficiency, and energy consumption were measured.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

The untreated petroleum refinery effluent sample (80L) was provided by the Al-Daura refinery petroleum refinery plant, Baghdad, Iraq. It was taken from the feeding tank and was stored in covered containers at 4°C until use. Table I lists the characteristics of this sample. Because raw water's conductivity is very low, it raises the cell potential, which necessitates the addition of supportive electrolytes in order to boost conductivity. Na₂SO₄ at 3.5g/L and NaCl at 2.5g/L were employed as supporting electrolytes, which resulted in a conductivity of 12.16mScm⁻¹, which is within the range necessary to achieve low cell potential [37].

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF THE UTILIZED EFFLUENT SAMPLE

Property	Value
pH (-)	6.8
COD (ppm)	1400
Conductivity (mS/cm)	2.66
Turbidity (NTU)	227
TDS g/L	6.64
F (ppm)	0.19
Cl (ppm)	422.4
Zn (ppm)	0.08
Cu (ppm)	0.025
Mn (ppm)	0.33
Ni (ppm)	0.5

A commercial GAC was used with the physical properties shown in Table II. A mixture of anhydrous sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄) powder from Thomas Baker company and sodium chloride (NaCl) powder with 99.9% purity by weight were used as supporting electrolytes. Anhydrous ferric chloride (FeCl₃) powder with 98% purity by weight, from the Alpha Chemike company and anhydrous aluminum chloride (AlCl₃) powder with 98% purity by weight, from the Central Drug House Ltd. company, were used as metal sources for the metal impregnation process. A 1M solution of hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37%, liquid, Sigma-Aldrich) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 97%, pellets, Sigma-Aldrich) was prepared to alter the original pH of the treated effluent.

TABLE II. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF THE COMMERCIAL GAC

Parameters	Values
Test standard	ASTM-D
BET surface area (m ² /g)	950-1200
Iodine Number (mg/g)	900-1150
Total ash content	Max. 5%
Hardness	Min. 97%
Apparent density (Kg/m ³)	460±40
Moisture content	8% (as packed)
Attrition	Max. 3%
Particle size	8×30 mesh available

B. Preparation of the Metal-Impregnated Granular Activated Carbon (MIGAC)

After being sieved to a particle size of over 1mm in diameter, commercial GAC particles with a particle size of (8×30) mesh were washed with deionized distilled water to remove impurity compounds. Finally, the particles were dried

in an oven at 105°C for 24h. Subsequently, the GAC was impregnated with molar ratios 1:10 as Al: AC, 1:10 as Fe: AC, 1:1:10 as Al:Fe:AC, 1:2:10 as Al:Fe:AC, and 2:1:10 as Al:Fe:AC using AlCl_3 and FeCl_3 as the Al and Fe sources respectively. It was then mixed with 50ml deionized water at 90°C for 4h. The resulting solution was mixed in a 500ml round-bottom flask with two necks: one neck was fitted with water-cooling reflux condenser and the other was equipped with a thermometer to measure the temperature. The reaction was carried out at atmospheric pressure. Agitation and heating of the flask were done by oil bath (engine oil from Al-Daura refinery with flash point 220°C) on a magnetic stirrer hot plate. Heidolph™ 505-20000-00, 0-300°C, 0-1400rpm was utilized for obtaining homogeneous solution at a rotation speed of 200rpm, where the temperature of the mixture in the heated flask was kept constant by using voltage regulator (Single – phase AC voltage regulator, 220V regulator adjustable 0-300V, max power 500W) to control the heat of the heater. After another wash with deionized distilled water, the MIGAC was dried in a 105°C oven for 24h.

C. Experimental Procedure

A preliminary feasibility test was conducted to determine the suitability of the TEC-MIGAC system for COD and turbidity elimination from the refinery effluent. This performance was compared to those of other systems, including an adsorption and Conventional EC (CEC) system and a raw granular activated carbon with CEC system (TEC-RGAC). All batch studies were conducted under the same experimental conditions: 1.0L working volume, duration of 120min, 10g raw activated carbon or MIGAC, pH=7, and 30V applied voltage. The experiments were conducted by using the laboratory setup shown in Figure 1. The tubular electrochemical reactor (Figure 1(a)) was made from Perspex glass with 30mm diameter and 140mm height. The wastewater was pumped to the cylindrical EC cell using a peristaltic pump (RUNZE, single stage pump, made in China) with a maximum flow rate of 200mL/min. The aluminum and stainless steel disk electrodes (30mm in diameter and 5mm in thickness) were pierced with 1mm holes and were connected to a DC power source. Each electrode had total effective surface area of 7.065cm². The distance between the electrodes did not alter and was kept at 6cm despite the rapid electron transfer rate between the anode and the cathode that was caused by the particle electrodes [38]. The aluminum anode was positioned below the cathode, and water was circulated in the direction from the anode to cathode. In the case of 3D reactor, a packed bed of GAC or MIGACs was placed between the anode and the cathode. During each experiment, for the purpose of delivering an adequate voltage, a digital direct current power supply of the type (UNI-T, UTP3315PF) that ranged from 0-30V and 0-5A was used. A multimeter was used to measure the system's current and voltage. The effluent from the EC unit was sent to a settling tank, where the overflow was pumped back to the EC cell. To remove the electrodes' oxide and passivation layers, they were washed in HCl solution (35%) and acetone [39]. HCl solution (0.1N) and NaOH solution (0.1N) were used to adjust pH. NaCl and Na_2SO_4 were used as electrolytes. NaCl solution was utilized as an extra electrolyte because it has a lot of benefits, including the ability of chloride ions to considerably lessen the

negative effect of other anions such HCO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} . The carbonate ion would cause the precipitation of Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+} ions, which create an insulating layer on the electrode surface. This insulating layer would significantly lower the electrochemical cell's current efficiency and treatment conversion while substantially raising its ohmic resistance. As a result, it is proposed that among the current anions, 20% Cl^- be present to enable normal EC activity in water treatment [40]. The ambient temperature for all tests was 25 ± 2°C. After the experiment, the samples were filtered using filter papers with size 150mm before being analyzed. TDS, pH, turbidity, and the initial and final COD concentrations were also measured.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of (a) the EC cell, (b) the EC system.

D. Methods of Analysis

Using Spectro Xepos XRF (Ametek Co., Germany), the textural qualities of raw granular and MIGAC were evaluated. The morphology and microstructure were examined with SEM. At the same surface locations as the SEM, EDS was also used to undertake surface element analysis concurrently (INSPECT, F50, REI Co., Netherland). Physical properties, BET specific surface area, and total pore volume were determined using the SA-9600 model (Horibe USA brand) using nitrogen gas as adsorbate. Lovibond COD VARIO photometric detector (COD Setup, MD 200, UK) was used for COD analysis. For the COD test, a sample of 2ml of the substrate was completely thermally oxidized using a standard oxidation reagent in a cuvette tube. The combination of the substrate sample and the standard oxidation reagent was heated at 150°C for 2h to guarantee that the substrate had completely oxidized. The concentration of the COD of the organics was determined in mg/L by a COD photometer in a thermo-reactor (RD 125, Lovibond, Germany). Turbidity was measured with a compact Lovibond® infrared turbidity meter Turbi Check. The turbidity and COD removal

efficiency were evaluated based on (1), where C_i is the initial and C_f the final concentration (mg L^{-1}) [41]:

$$RE\% = \frac{c_i - c_f}{c_i} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The quantity of electrical energy that is used up throughout the EC process in order to eliminate 1kg of COD is referred to as the Energy Consumption (EC). EC may be determined in terms of kWh/kg by [42]:

$$EC = \frac{U \cdot I \cdot t \times 1000}{(COD_i - COD_f)V} \quad (2)$$

where COD_i and COD_f are the initial and final chemical oxygen demand (mg/L), U is the applied cell voltage (V), I is the current (A), t is the electrolysis time (h), and V is the effluent volume (L). A TDS-meter (161002 PurePro Inc.) was used to test the TDS, and a pH-meter (HANNA Instruments Co.) was used to determine the pH. Electrical conductivity was measured with a HANNA HI-99301 meter.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Textural Properties

Table III shows the physical properties of unprocessed GAC and MIGACs, based on nitrogen adsorption and desorption isotherms, specific surface area, and total pore volume. It is evident that following ferric-aluminum impregnation, MIGACs' specific surface area and total pore volume both significantly reduced to 893.7, 878, 874, 840, and 797.5 m^2/g and 0.21702, 0.20075, 0.19502, 0.19722, 0.18388, and 0.01376 m^3/g for MIGAC(Fe), MIGAC(Al), MIGAC(1:1),

MIGAC(1:2), and MIGAC(2:1) respectively. These decreased physical characteristic values point to a preferential distribution of metal oxides in the pore mouth. Certain micropores were subsequently obstructed, along with the development of meso- and macro-porous structures and the covering of binders to the active sites created by ferric or aluminum oxides [43, 44].

The evidence for this may also be seen rather obviously in the micro structural analysis. Images from a scanning electron microscope of RGAC (A1-4), MIGAC(Fe) (B1-4), MIGAC(Al) (C1-4), MIGAC(1:1) (D1-4), MIGAC(1:2) (E1-4), and MIGAC(2:1) (F1-4) are presented in Figure 2. While the raw GAC's porous nature is easily seen in Figure 2 (A1-4), it was observed that some porous structural collapse took place when the raw GAC was impregnated with metal, leading to clogs, as shown in Figure 2 (A1-3), (B1-3), (C1-3), (D1-3), (E1-3), and (F1-3). Also, in Figure 2, A4 can be seen showing the surface of raw GAC before impregnation and Figure 2 B4, C4, D4, E4, and F4 emphasize that the metal oxide aggregates formed on the surface of raw GAC after the wet impregnation have a spherical shape. It was calculated that the average crystallite size of metal oxides was in the range of (21.24-32.58), (21.32-27.38), (26.23-62.77), (55.67-76.49), (18.75-26.89) nm for MIGAC(Fe), MIGAC(Al), MIGAC(1:1), MIGAC(1:2), and MIGAC (2:1) respectively. From the image in Figure 2 F4, it can be seen that iron and aluminum oxides were aggregated homogeneously on the surface of the raw GAC and the range of the metal oxides was smaller than the ranges of the other GAMIs.

TABLE III. RAW GAC AND MIGAC MICROSTRUCTURES

Properties	RGAC	MIGAC (Fe)	MIGAC (Al)	MIGAC (1:1)	MIGAC (1:2)	MIGAC (2:1)
BET specific surface area (m^2/g)	1086	893.7	878.7	874	840	797.5
Total pore volume (cm^3/g)	0.21702	0.20075	0.19502	0.19722	0.18388	0.01376

TABLE IV. EDS ELEMENTAL COMPOSITION OF RAW GAC AND MIGACs

Element	RGAC		MIGAC(Fe)		MIGAC(Al)		MIGAC(1:1)		MIGAC(1:2)		MIGAC(2:1)	
	Weight %	Atomic %	Weight %	Atomic %	Weight %	Atomic %	Weight %	Atomic %	Weight %	Atomic %	Weight %	Atomic %
C	88.82	92.7	83.17	88.7	85.1	89.9	78.91	87.66	80.6	88.5	73.95	83.6
O	7.28	5.7	12.13	9.7	10.7	8.5	9.5	7.9	10	8.3	13.33	11.3
Fe	-	-	1.63	0.4	-	-	1.99	0.51	3.2	0.78	1.65	0.43
Al	0.207	0.1	0.203	0.1	1.3	0.6	1.034	0.53	0.8	0.42	1.67	0.87
Si	1.78	0.8	0.22	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.42	0.2	0.7	0.3	0.21	0.1
Cl	-	-	2.66	1	2.6	0.9	8.16	3.2	4.7	1.7	9.02	3.6
Ca	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
K	1.51	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mg	0.38	0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.18	0.1
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

At the same surface areas where the SEM was used, an element analysis of the surface was also conducted at the same time as the EDS. Table IV displays the weight and atomic percentages of the raw and MIGAC elements. It can be seen that the level of Al changed to 0.6%, 0.53%, 0.42%, and 0.87% for MIGAC(Al), MIGAC(1:1), MIGAC(1:2), and MIGAC(2:1) respectively, and the level of Fe changed to 0.4%, 0.51%, 0.78%, and 0.43% for MIGAC(Fe), MIGAC(1:1), MIGAC(1:2), and MIGAC(2:1) respectively. Aluminum and ferric iron were completely impregnated into raw GAC, as determined by the atomic percentage following impregnation.

Clearly, AlCl_3 and FeCl_3 were the source of the Cl after impregnation. Aluminum and ferric iron were likely bonded to MIGAC in the form of aluminum oxide and iron oxide, given the increased oxygen concentration in MIGAC compared to the raw GAC.

XRF chemistry analysis was used to confirm the oxide form of the metals in both raw GAC and MIGAC. Formation of oxides by metals on each other's surfaces is documented in Table V, which shows that aluminum oxide and ferric oxide are the most common forms of these metals.

TABLE V. XRF ANALYSIS WAS USED TO DETERMINE THE METAL OXIDE FORM IN RAW GAC AND MIGAC

Components	RGAC (mass%)	MIGAC(Fe) (mass%)	MIGAC(Al) (mass%)	MIGAC(1:1) (mass%)	MIGAC(1:2) (mass%)	MIGAC(2:1) (mass%)
MgO	0.4573	1.148	0.505	0.741	1.200	0.817
Al ₂ O ₃	0.2899	0.2153	0.9091	2.0521	1.9941	3.3345
SiO ₂	1.039	0.8847	0.3724	0.1434	0.1846	0.1765
P ₂ O ₅	0.3564	0.1924	0.2151	0.1826	0.1376	0.1732
SO ₃	0.09675	0.09694	0.04981	0.02413	0.02272	0.03716
Cl	0.05731	1.751	1.610	2.892	4.081	4.2253
K ₂ O	2.096	0.0645	0.0645	0.0646	0.1045	0.0666
CaO	2.919	1.346	1.619	1.031	1.579	1.239
TiO ₂	0.00307	0.00317	< 0.0013	0.00344	0.00281	0.00466
V ₂ O ₅	< 0.0011	< 0.00072	< 0.0013	< 0.0011	< 0.00068	< 0.00069
Cr ₂ O ₃	< 0.00022	< 0.00015	0.00099	0.00109	0.00050	0.00099
MnO	0.00183	0.00046	0.00056	0.00203	0.00206	0.00326
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.03133	1.677	0.04100	1.962	3.428	1.7841
CoO	< 0.00039	< 0.00039	< 0.00039	< 0.00039	< 0.00039	< 0.00039
NiO	0.00081	0.00064	0.00118	0.00122	0.00085	0.00086
CuO	0.00318	0.00566	0.00366	0.00618	0.00627	0.00678
ZnO	0.00062	0.3631	0.00126	0.00199	0.00141	0.00162

Fig. 2. SEM images of (A1-4) RGAC, (B1-4) MIGAC(Fe), (C1-4) MIGAC(Al), (D1-4) MIGAC(1:1), (E1-4), MIGAC(1:2), and (F1-4), MIGAC(2:1) at different expansion ratios.

B. Influence of Auxiliary Electrolyte Dosing

The solution's conductivity is essential for increasing process effectiveness and lowering current density. The lower potential flowing in the circuit during treatment is maintained via conductivity, which also results in less electricity being used. The conductivity of the effluent caused the heterogeneous ions to transfer in the EC method. Electrolytes Na₂SO₄ and NaCl were employed in this treatment [41]. Additionally, SO₄²⁻ ions do not corrode as much as the chloride species. The great corrosive capability of Cl⁻ ions aids in the disintegration of the coagulant. The needed voltage will be significantly lower in the presence of chloride ions than it would be in the presence of SO₄²⁻ ions. Comparing the adsorption behaviors of Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ ions on the Al electrode, it has been discovered that Cl⁻ had a lower degree of adsorption than SO₄²⁻ [45]. Chloride ions are transformed into active chlorine species when the current density is sufficiently high. These species then participate in the oxidation of ferrous ions and organic materials [46].

Table VI and Figure 3 show the effect of variable concentrations of electrolytes on the removal of chemical oxygen demand. EC process was performed using applied voltage of 30V, time 120min, pH 7, and 10g raw activated carbon. As shown in Table VI, when the wastewater treated without any added electrolyte concentration of Na₂SO₄ or NaCl, the conductivity and applied current were 2.66mS/cm and 15.1mA respectively and the COD removal was 58.8% at 20min, whereas it increased to 72.3% at 120min. The synergistic effects of raw GAC adsorption in the GAC-three dimensional EC system may be responsible for these results. After adding the electrolytes (2.5g NaCl, 3.5g Na₂SO₄, 2.5g NaCl + 3.5g Na₂SO₄, and 2.5g NaCl + 7g Na₂SO₄), the conductivity and the applied current were 7, 7.44, 12.16, and 20mS/cm and 45, 56, 87, and 98mA respectively. As shown in Figure 4, the COD removal rate was improved when a mixture of electrolytes (NaCl + Na₂SO₄) was added to the reaction system at different concentrations. Increment in removal efficiency was observed from 90.7% to 93.7% after 120min for 2.5g NaCl + 3.5g Na₂SO₄. This might be attributed to the fast flow of electrolyte ions. Additionally, no additional improvement in removal efficiency was observed when the supporting electrolyte concentration of Na₂SO₄ was raised to 7g/L, which may be caused by an expansion of the passivation layer. Therefore, 2.5g NaCl and 3.5g Na₂SO₄ were selected as the optimum electrolyte concentration and this is in agreement with the findings of the authors in [37], which used NaCl with a concentration of 4g/L to obtain 13.6mS/cm conductivity for removing carbamazepine by a three-dimensional electrochemical process utilizing particle electrodes made of carbon-based adsorbent material.

C. Feasibility Test

To find out whether the TEC-MIGAC system is appropriate for removing COD and turbidity from refinery effluents, a feasibility test was carried out. An adsorption system, a CEC system, and a Raw GAC with CEC (TEC-RGAC) system were used and their performance was compared. Because of its great adsorption capability, GAC adsorption is a well-established technology used in wastewater post-treatment and water

purification. The adsorption processes took place in the same cell without supplying an electric field.

TABLE VI. ELECTROLYTE DOSE EFFECT ON THE INITIAL CONDUCTIVITY AND COD REMOVAL

Electrolyte concentration (g/L)	Initial conductivity (μS/cm)	Current (mA)	COD removal (%)		SEC (kWh/kg COD)
			20min	120min	
Without salt	2660	15.1	58.8	72.3	0.80
2.5g NaCl	7000	45	73.6	84.6	1.64
3.5g Na ₂ SO ₄	7440	56	75.1	85.2	2.61
2.5g NaCl + 3.5g Na ₂ SO ₄	12160	87	90.7	93.7	3.68
2.5g NaCl + 7g Na ₂ SO ₄	20000	98	91.7	95.4	4.68

Fig. 3. Electrolyte dose effect on COD removal (30V, 120min, pH=7, and 10g raw activated carbon).

Fig. 4. (a) COD profile with time, (b) COD removal of the adsorption process on different impregnated activated carbon (1361mg/L initial COD, 10g of AC or MIGAC dosage, and 175mL/min flow rate).

In Batch test I, similar experimental settings were used for each experiment in the adsorption procedure (120min, 10g of AC or MIGAC dosage, and 175ml/min flow rate). In Figures 4-5 and Table VII, it can be seen that the raw GAC system's adsorption system achieved maximum COD removal. In the adsorption system by raw GAC, the COD and turbidity decreased quickly to 619mg/L and 2.48NTU respectively in the first 20min, and then slowly to 376mg/L and 2.31NTU at

120min, while 72.3% COD removal and 98.9% turbidity were obtained at the 120min treatment. COD and turbidity were reduced to 638, 640, 649, 643, and 689mg/L and 13.4, 1.94, 1.89, 32.1, and 11NTU respectively in the first 20min, and then continuously to 430, 435, 444, 450, and 505mg/L and 1.165, 2.02, 8.9, 5.98, and 10NTU at 120min for MIGAC(Fe), MIGAC(Al), MIGAC(1:1), MIGAC(1:2), and MIGAC(2:1), respectively corresponding to 68.41, 68.03, 67.38, 66.94, and 62.89% of COD removal at 120min. The high COD removal of raw GAC compared to the MIGAC systems may be due to the fact that metal oxides are preferentially dispersed in the pore mouth, blocking some micropores and constructing a mesoporous or macroporous structure, and overlaying binders to the activated sites created by ferric or aluminum oxides. This is in agreement with the results of [38]. A significant improving in TDS removal was observed for impregnated activated carbons with highest removal by MIGAC (2:1) as shown in Table VII.

Fig. 5. (a) Turbidity profile with time, (b) turbidity removal for adsorption process on the different impregnated activated carbon methods (227NTU initial turbidity, 10g of AC or MIGAC dosage, and 175mL/min flow rate).

TABLE VII. COD AND TURBIDITY REMOVAL

Type of adsorbent	COD removal %		Turbidity removal %		TDS removal %	
	20 min	120 min	20 min	120 min	20 min	120 min
GAC	54.5	72.3	98.9	98.9	0	2.89
MIGAC(Fe)	53.1	69.7	94.09	99.2	5.79	25.60
MIGAC(Al)	52.3	69.06	98.9	99.15	14.05	17.87
MIGAC(1:1)	52.9	70.24	97.6	99.16	10.14	12.07
MIGAC(1:2)	52.7	68.55	85.8	97.36	15.94	30.43
MIGAC(2:1)	49.3	66.78	95.15	97.53	50.72	52.17

In batch test II, removing turbidity and COD from real refinery wastewater was considered and comparisons were made between the CEC system with aluminum and stainless steel electrodes, TEC-RGAC, and TEC-MIGAC systems. Table VIII and Figures 6 and 7 demonstrate the performance of RGAC and MIGACs in removing turbidity and COD at an initial pH of 7 and a reaction duration of 120min, using 30V applied voltage, 10g RGAC or MIGAC, and 2.5g/L NaCl + 3.5

g/L Na₂SO₄ as supporting electrolyte. In the past, stainless steel and aluminum electrodes have been widely employed in electrochemical wastewater treatment systems due to their availability and low cost. With chloride in the solution, the primary direct electrochemical reaction may occur and is heavily dependent on it. Hypochlorous acid/hypochlorite ions (HOCl/OCl⁻), which are powerful oxidants, can be generated in the solution during the direct electrochemical reaction due to the anode and cathode ionization processes, and as a result, turbidity and COD will be reduced [47-49].

In CEC, as shown in Figures 6 and 7, COD and turbidity decreased to 450mg/L and 2.11NTU respectively, in the first 20min, then to 200mg/L and 2.06NTU in the following 100min. After 120min of treatment, 85.3% of COD and 99.04% turbidity removals were achieved.

Fig. 6. (a) COD profile with time and (b) COD removal for performance comparison between CEC system with aluminum and stainless steel electrodes, TEC-RGAC, and TEC-MIGAC systems (1361mg/L initial COD, 7 pH, 30V, 10g of RGAC or MIGAC dosage, 175mL/min flow rate and 2.5g/L NaCl + 3.5g/L Na₂SO₄ as supporting electrolyte).

As the next step, we improved and compared the removal performance of the traditional EC system by introducing TEC-RGAC and TEC-MIGACs particles. Metal ions (aluminum and ferric iron) produced from MIGACs during the EC were predicted to have a greater influence on removal efficiency. The contrary of what was anticipated happened when RGAC and MIGACs were added to the reactor and comparable efficacy was seen in both systems. After 20min response time, the turbidity and COD were promptly gone, whereas the COD removal could be attributed to the precipitation of dissolved organics. The amount of hydroxide flocs, which was associated with EC time and cell current, evaluated the effectiveness of COD removal. Longer observation times and greater cell current levels indicated higher COD elimination efficiency [50]. After 120min response time, turbidity and COD removal were 99.14% and 92.65% in the TEC-RGAC system, and 99.36, 98.97, 99.41, 99.4, and 99.43% and 91.18, 93.46, 93.75, 93.39, and 95.74% in the TEC-MIGAC systems. These results may have been brought about by the additive effect of raw GAC adsorption in the TEC-RGAC system, which has more

distinguishable textural properties than MIGAC, including BET surface area, total pore volume, and micropore structure. Traditional two-dimensional electrode systems have a low COD removal effectiveness (76.12% after 60min). By using a three-dimensional electrocoagulation reactor system, COD removal efficiency increased significantly to 87.06, 88.61, 85.75, 90.08, 90.44, and 92.65% after 60min. Also, it was found that the MIGAC with a 2:1 molar ratio of aluminum to ferric metal ions had the highest COD removal. Results showed that MIGAC could show substantially higher removal efficiency than the GAC addition due to the impact of metal (aluminum and iron) ions created by the addition on EC.

Fig. 7. (a) Turbidity profile with time and (b) Turbidity removal for performance comparison between CEC system with aluminum and stainless steel electrodes, TEC-RGAC, and TEC-MIGAC systems (227NTU initial turbidity, 7 pH, 30V, 10g of RGAC or MIGAC dosage, 175mL/min flow rate and 2.5g/L NaCl + 3.5g/L Na₂SO₄, as supporting electrolyte.

TABLE VIII. COD AND TURBIDITY REMOVAL OF CRC, TEC-GAC, AND TEC-MIGAC SYSTEMS

Type of particle electrode	COD removal %		Turbidity removal %		TDS removal %		Energy consumption (kWh/kg COD)
	20 min	120 min	20 min	120 min	20 min	120 min	
CEC	66.93	85.3	99.04	99.25	46.23	50.75	12.777
TEC-GAC	69.88	92.65	98.87	99.14	46.23	49.84	3.697
TEC-MIGAC(Fe)	74.14	91.18	99.22	99.36	45.93	53.16	3.735
TEC-MIGAC(Al)	77.59	93.46	94.88	98.97	42.77	50.3	3.768
TEC-MIGAC (1:1)	81.26	93.75	92.42	99.41	48.49	52.56	3.602
TEC-MIGAC (1:2)	79.87	93.39	98.84	99.4	48.34	52.25	3.676
TEC-MIGAC (2:1)	87.14	95.74	99.20	99.43	51.35	55.57	3.920

The fundamental issue of the GAC adsorption technique is that the porosity eventually gets saturated and inefficient, rendering the technique worthless [51]. As a consequence, it could be challenging to measure and evaluate GAC's function as a particle electrode or adsorbent if raw GAC is utilized

directly as a particle electrode in a three-dimensional EC reactor system. In this respect, another test was conducted, and the reaction time for each set was lowered to 80min, since the removal efficiency increased marginally with increasing reaction time. As shown in Figure 8, increasing the repetition cycle was associated with a decrease in COD removal efficiency in the TEC-RGAC system. However, those efficiencies were kept constant approximately in the TEC-MIGAC (2:1) system. After 10 repetitions, the apparent value of the TEC-MIGAC (2:1) system was greater than that of the TEC-RGAC system, with the TEC-MIGAC (2:1) system achieving 90.22% COD removal, while the TEC-RGAC system achieved 63.72%. Metal ions (iron/aluminum) were first dissolved during the anode reaction step of the electrocoagulation process. Instantaneously upon reaching a certain pH, they hydrolyzed to generate polymeric iron and aluminum oxyhydroxides (Fe(OH)₃ and Al(OH)₃) respectively, which are effective coagulating agents [52].

Fig. 8. Repeated test between the GAC and the TEC-MIGAC system.

D. Comparison with Previous Studies

Authors in [20] utilized an electrochemical technique with a three-dimensional multi-phase electrode. Fe particulates and air were injected into a conventional two-dimensional reactor to remediate effluents from a petroleum refinery. The initial pH and cell voltage, as well as the effect of Fe particles and air have on the electrochemical process, were both subjects of the research that was carried out as a part of the process of determining the optimal experimental settings. The results of their investigation found that the effluent had a COD removal effectiveness that was good (92.8%). Authors in [53] treated wastewater from a local petroleum refinery using an aluminum electrode and having two distinct COD levels in a continuous electrochemical cell. They investigated the impacts of inflow flow rate, initial pH, and current density. They demonstrated that EC may reduce COD by up to 57% when used under ideal circumstances. Authors in [54] treated effluents from a heavy oil refinery using a Three-Dimensional Electrode Reactor (TDER) equipped with a combination particle electrode consisting of GAC and Porous Ceramsite Particle (PCP) and an anode of the DSA type. When comparing the TDER to the two-dimensional electrode reactor, it was discovered that it was more effective at removing COD and that the combination particle electrode was advantageous in increasing the COD removal efficiency and decreasing energy consumption. Under the best experimental conditions (GAC percentage = 75%,

current density = 30mA/cm², not altered pH, and treatment time = 100min), the maximum removal of COD, total organic carbon, and toxicity units from the treated effluent were 45.5%, 43.3%, and 67.25% respectively. It was found that the metal impregnated granular activated carbon with a 2:1 molar ratio of aluminum to ferric metal ions had higher COD removal in comparison with that obtained from [38], which used metal impregnated activated carbon (Al:Fe) with a molar ratio of (1:1) as a moving particle EC electrode in a three-dimensional EC process to treat wastewater from real cotton textiles with a COD content of 685mg/L. COD removal after treatment was 81.6% after 120min of reaction time, 10g MIGAC, and 30V applied voltage at pH=7.7. Therefore, the present system exhibited excellent results in terms of COD and turbidity removal using the new design of the three dimensional electrode.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the treatment of refinery wastewater using a new three – dimensional electrocoagulation approach was proposed and investigated. The new cell utilizes Granular Activated Carbon (GAC) and Metal-Impregnated GAC (MIGAC) as third particle electrodes. The three-dimensional electrocoagulation reactor system is an interesting technology for improving refinery wastewater treatment in electrocoagulation, according to a feasibility test employing a typical two-dimensional electrode, adsorption process, and the three-dimensional electrocoagulation system, where the COD removal efficiency for the adsorption process was 72.37, 68.41, 68.04, 67.38, 66.94, and 62.84% after 120min for Raw GAC (RGAC), MIGAC(Fe), MIGAC(Al), MIGAC(1:1), MIGAC(1:2), and MIGAC(2:1) respectively while 85.3% was in the conventional two dimensional electrode system after 120min.

The COD removal efficiency was enhanced by using the three-dimensional electrocoagulation method, reaching 92.65, 93.46, 91.18, 93.75, 93.39, and 95.74% after 120min for TEC-RGAC, TEC-MIGAC(Al), TEC-MIGAC(Fe), TEC-MIGAC(1:1), TEC-MIGAC(1:2), and TEC-MIGAC(2:1), respectively based on the operating conditions of: 1361 initial COD, 7 pH, 30V, 10g of AC or MIGAC dosage for the three dimensional system, 175mL/min flow rate and 2.5g/L NaCl + 3.5g/L Na₂SO₄ as supporting electrolytes.

The results showed that the MIGAC addition exhibits considerably larger removal efficiency than the RGAC addition because of the influence of metal ions created by the MIGAC on the electrocoagulation. Besides, it was found that the MIGAC with a molar ratio of aluminum to ferric metal ion (2:1) had higher COD removal in comparison with previous studies. Also, in the present study, the energy consumption was reduced from 12.78KWh/Kg COD for the conventional two dimensional system to 3.9KWh/Kg COD when using the three dimensional TEC-MIGAC (2:1). Considering the obtained results, the 3D process allowed efficient removal of COD after a shorter period when compared with the 2D process and also decreased energy consumption.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Wake, "Oil refineries: a review of their ecological impacts on the aquatic environment," *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 131–140, Jan. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2004.08.013>.
- [2] M. A. Tony, P. J. Purcell, and Y. Zhao, "Oil refinery wastewater treatment using physicochemical, Fenton and Photo-Fenton oxidation processes," *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part A*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 435–440, Feb. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10934529.2012.646136>.
- [3] J. Saien and H. Nejati, "Enhanced photocatalytic degradation of pollutants in petroleum refinery wastewater under mild conditions," *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, vol. 148, no. 1, pp. 491–495, Sep. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.03.001>.
- [4] M. Yalda, M. M. A. Torabi, and A. Fouladitajar, "Refinery and petrochemical wastewater treatment," in *Sustainable Water and Wastewater Processing*, Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier, 2019, pp. 55–91.
- [5] A. N. Laghari, Z. A. Siyal, D. K. Bangwar, M. A. Soomro, G. D. Walasai, and F. A. Shaikh, "Groundwater Quality Analysis for Human Consumption: A Case Study of Sukkur City, Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2616–2620, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1768>.
- [6] A. A. Mahessar, A. L. Qureshi, A. N. Laghari, S. Qureshi, S. F. Shah, and F. A. Shaikh, "Impact of Hairdin, Miro Khan and Shahdad Kot Drainage on Hamal Dhand, Sindh," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3652–3656, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2389>.
- [7] A. N. Laghari, Z. A. Siyal, M. A. Soomro, D. K. Bangwar, A. J. Khokhar, and H. L. Soni, "Quality Analysis of Urea Plant Wastewater and its Impact on Surface Water Bodies," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2699–2703, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1767>.
- [8] P. A. Pugazhendi, H. Abbad Wazin, H. Qari, J. M. A.-B. Basahi, J. J. Godon, and J. Dhavamani, "Biodegradation of low and high molecular weight hydrocarbons in petroleum refinery wastewater by a thermophilic bacterial consortium," *Environmental Technology*, vol. 38, no. 19, pp. 2381–2391, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2016.1262460>.
- [9] N. M. Makkiya and I. A. W. Al-Baldawi, "Biodegradation of Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon from Al-Daura Refinery Wastewater by Rhizobacteria," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 14–23, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.31026/j.eng.2020.01.02>.
- [10] S. Arefi-Oskoui, A. Khataee, M. Safarpour, and V. Vatanpour, "Modification of polyethersulfone ultrafiltration membrane using ultrasonic-assisted functionalized MoS₂ for treatment of oil refinery wastewater," *Separation and Purification Technology*, vol. 238, May 2020, Art. no. 116495, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2019.116495>.
- [11] I. Ulhaq, W. Ahmad, I. Ahmad, M. Yaseen, and M. Ilyas, "Engineering TiO₂ supported CTAB modified bentonite for treatment of refinery wastewater through simultaneous photocatalytic oxidation and adsorption," *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, vol. 43, Oct. 2021, Art. no. 102239, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2021.102239>.
- [12] B. Singh and P. Kumar, "Pre-treatment of petroleum refinery wastewater by coagulation and flocculation using mixed coagulant: Optimization of process parameters using response surface methodology (RSM)," *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, vol. 36, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 101317, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2020.101317>.
- [13] S. H. Ammar, N. N. Ismail, A. D. Ali, and W. M. Abbas, "Electrocoagulation technique for refinery wastewater treatment in an internal loop split-plate airlift reactor," *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 6, Dec. 2019, Art. no. 103489, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2019.103489>.

- [14] R. N. Abbas and A. S. Abbas, "The Taguchi Approach in Studying and Optimizing the Electro-Fenton Oxidation to Reduce Organic Contaminants in Refinery Wastewater Using Novel Electrodes," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8928–8935, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5091>.
- [15] H. M. Ibrahim and R. H. Salman, "Study the Optimization of Petroleum Refinery Wastewater Treatment by Successive Electrocoagulation and Electro-oxidation Systems," *Iraqi Journal of Chemical and Petroleum Engineering*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 31–41, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.31699/IJCPE.2022.1.5>.
- [16] S. S. Alkurdi and A. H. Abbar, "Removal of COD from Petroleum Refinery Wastewater by Electro-Coagulation Process Using SS/Al electrodes," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 870, no. 1, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 012052, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/870/1/012052>.
- [17] G. Hayder, M. Z. Ramli, M. A. Malek, A. Khamis, and N. M. Hilmin, "Prediction model development for petroleum refinery wastewater treatment," *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, vol. 4, pp. 1–5, Dec. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2014.08.006>.
- [18] C. A. Martinez-Huitle and E. Brillas, "Decontamination of wastewaters containing synthetic organic dyes by electrochemical methods: A general review," *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, vol. 87, no. 3, pp. 105–145, Apr. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2008.09.017>.
- [19] Y. Yavuz, A. S. Kopal, and U. B. Ogutveren, "Treatment of petroleum refinery wastewater by electrochemical methods," *Desalination*, vol. 258, no. 1, pp. 201–205, Aug. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2010.03.013>.
- [20] L. Yan, H. Ma, B. Wang, Y. Wang, and Y. Chen, "Electrochemical treatment of petroleum refinery wastewater with three-dimensional multi-phase electrode," *Desalination*, vol. 276, no. 1, pp. 397–402, Aug. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2011.03.083>.
- [21] R. H. Salman, "Removal of Manganese Ions (Mn²⁺) from a Simulated Wastewater by Electrocoagulation/ Electroflotation Technologies with Stainless Steel Mesh Electrodes: Process Optimization Based on Taguchi Approach," *Iraqi Journal of Chemical and Petroleum Engineering*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 39–48, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.31699/IJCPE.2019.1.6>.
- [22] T. Satapanajaru, S. D. Comfort, and P. J. Shea, "Enhancing Metolachlor Destruction Rates with Aluminum and Iron Salts during Zerovalent Iron Treatment," *Journal of Environmental Quality*, vol. 32, no. 5, pp. 1726–1734, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2003.1726>.
- [23] V. Khandegar and A. K. Saroha, "Electrocoagulation for the treatment of textile industry effluent – A review," *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 128, pp. 949–963, Oct. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.06.043>.
- [24] R. Katal and H. Pahlavanzadeh, "Influence of different combinations of aluminum and iron electrode on electrocoagulation efficiency: Application to the treatment of paper mill wastewater," *Desalination*, vol. 265, no. 1, pp. 199–205, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2010.07.052>.
- [25] Y. Sun *et al.*, "Electrochemical treatment of chloramphenicol using Ti-Sn/ γ -Al₂O₃ particle electrodes with a three-dimensional reactor," *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 308, pp. 1233–1242, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2016.10.072>.
- [26] M. Paidar, K. Bouzek, M. Laurich, and J. Thonstad, "Application of a Three-Dimensional Electrode to the Electrochemical Removal of Copper and Zinc Ions from Diluted Solutions," *Water Environment Research*, vol. 72, no. 5, pp. 618–625, 2000, <https://doi.org/10.2175/106143000X138201>.
- [27] S. Yonghui, L. Siming, Y. Ning, and H. Wenjin, "Treatment of cyanide wastewater dynamic cycle test by three-dimensional electrode system and the reaction process analysis," *Environmental Technology*, vol. 42, no. 11, pp. 1693–1702, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2019.1677783>.
- [28] S. T. Kadhum, G. Y. Alkindi, and T. M. Albayati, "Remediation of phenolic wastewater implementing nano zerovalent iron as a granular third electrode in an electrochemical reactor," *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 1383–1392, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-021-03205-5>.
- [29] R. Shokooi *et al.*, "Comparing the performance of the peroxymonosulfate/Mn₃O₄ and three-dimensional electrochemical processes for methylene blue removal from aqueous solutions: Kinetic studies," *Colloid and Interface Science Communications*, vol. 42, May 2021, Art. no. 100394, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colcom.2021.100394>.
- [30] S. Sowmiya, R. Gandhimathi, S. T. Ramesh, and P. V. Nidheesh, "Granular activated carbon as a particle electrode in three-dimensional electrochemical treatment of reactive black B from aqueous solution," *Environmental Progress & Sustainable Energy*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1616–1622, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ep.12396>.
- [31] S. Tang *et al.*, "Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles three-dimensional electro-peroxydisulfate for improving tetracycline degradation," *Chemosphere*, vol. 268, Apr. 2021, Art. no. 129315, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.129315>.
- [32] P. Pourali, M. Fazlzadeh, M. Aaligadri, A. Dargahi, Y. Poureshgh, and B. Kakavandi, "Enhanced three-dimensional electrochemical process using magnetic recoverable of Fe₃O₄@GAC towards furfural degradation and mineralization," *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, vol. 15, no. 8, Aug. 2022, Art. no. 103980, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjch.2022.103980>.
- [33] K. GracePavithra, P. Senthil Kumar, V. Jaikumar, and P. SundarRajan, "A review on three-dimensional electrochemical systems: analysis of influencing parameters and cleaner approach mechanism for wastewater," *Reviews in Environmental Science and Bio/Technology*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 873–896, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11157-020-09550-0>.
- [34] W. Can, H. Yao-Kun, Z. Qing, and J. Min, "Treatment of secondary effluent using a three-dimensional electrode system: COD removal, biotoxicity assessment, and disinfection effects," *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 243, pp. 1–6, May 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2013.12.044>.
- [35] X. Li, C. Wang, Y. Qian, Y. Wang, and L. Zhang, "Simultaneous removal of chemical oxygen demand, turbidity and hardness from biologically treated citric acid wastewater by electrochemical oxidation for reuse," *Separation and Purification Technology*, vol. 107, pp. 281–288, Apr. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2013.01.008>.
- [36] N. R. Neti and R. Misra, "Efficient degradation of Reactive Blue 4 in carbon bed electrochemical reactor," *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 184, pp. 23–32, Mar. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2011.12.014>.
- [37] L. Correia-Sa *et al.*, "A Three-Dimensional Electrochemical Process for the Removal of Carbamazepine," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 14, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 6432, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11146432>.
- [38] K.-W. Jung, M.-J. Hwang, D.-S. Park, and K.-H. Ahn, "Combining fluidized metal-impregnated granular activated carbon in three-dimensional electrocoagulation system: Feasibility and optimization test of color and COD removal from real cotton textile wastewater," *Separation and Purification Technology*, vol. 146, pp. 154–167, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2015.03.043>.
- [39] E. Gencec, M. Kobya, E. Demirbas, A. Akyol, and K. Oktor, "Optimization of baker's yeast wastewater using response surface methodology by electrocoagulation," *Desalination*, vol. 286, pp. 200–209, Feb. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2011.11.023>.
- [40] J. B. Parsa, H. R. Vahidian, A. R. Soleymani, and M. Abbasi, "Removal of Acid Brown 14 in aqueous media by electrocoagulation: Optimization parameters and minimizing of energy consumption," *Desalination*, vol. 278, no. 1, pp. 295–302, Sep. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2011.05.040>.
- [41] D. Kumar and C. Sharma, "Remediation of Pulp and Paper Industry Effluent Using Electrocoagulation Process," *Journal of Water Resource and Protection*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 296–310, Mar. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.4236/jwarp.2019.113017>.
- [42] D. S. Ibrahim, P. S. Devi, and N. Balasubramanian, "Electrochemical Oxidation Treatment of Petroleum Refinery Effluent," *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, vol. 4, no. 8, pp. 1–5, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.14299/00000>.
- [43] M. S. Secula, A. Vajda, L. Hagu-Zaleschi, B. Cagnon, F. Warmont, and I. Mamaliga, "Iron(II)-Impregnated Activated Carbon Composites Applied as Fenton-like Catalysts for Degrading Persistent Organic

- Compounds," in *15th International Conference on Environmental Science and Technology*, Rhodes, Greece, Sep. 2017.
- [44] U. Balasubramani, R. Venkatesh, S. Subramaniam, G. Gopalakrishnan, and V. Sundararajan, "Alumina/activated carbon nano-composites: Synthesis and application in sulphide ion removal from water," *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, vol. 340, pp. 241–252, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2017.07.006>.
- [45] A. Kolics, J. C. Polkinghorne, and A. Wieckowski, "Adsorption of sulfate and chloride ions on aluminum," *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 43, no. 18, pp. 2605–2618, Jun. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-4686\(97\)10188-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-4686(97)10188-8).
- [46] R. Keyikoglu, O. T. Can, A. Aygun, and A. Tek, "Comparison of the effects of various supporting electrolytes on the treatment of a dye solution by electrocoagulation process," *Colloid and Interface Science Communications*, vol. 33, Nov. 2019, Art. no. 100210, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colcom.2019.100210>.
- [47] C. J. Israillides, A. G. Vlyssides, V. N. Mourafeti, and G. Karvouni, "Olive oil wastewater treatment with the use of an electrolysis system," *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 61, no. 2, pp. 163–170, Aug. 1997, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0960-8524\(97\)00023-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0960-8524(97)00023-0).
- [48] S. H. Lin, C. T. Shyu, and M. C. Sun, "Saline wastewater treatment by electrochemical method," *Water Research*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 1059–1066, Apr. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(97\)00327-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(97)00327-8).
- [49] A. G. Vlyssides, C. J. Israillides, M. Loizidou, G. Karvouni, and V. Mourafeti, "Electrochemical treatment of vinasse from beet molasses," *Water Science and Technology*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 271–278, Jan. 1997, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0273-1223\(97\)00398-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0273-1223(97)00398-3).
- [50] G. Varank, H. Erkan, S. Yazycy, A. Demir, and G. Engin, "Electrocoagulation of Tannery Wastewater using Monopolar Electrodes: Process Optimization by Response Surface Methodology," *International Journal of Environmental Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 165–180, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.22059/ijer.2014.706>.
- [51] K.-W. Jung, M.-J. Hwang, D.-S. Park, and K.-H. Ahn, "Performance evaluation and optimization of a fluidized three-dimensional electrode reactor combining pre-exposed granular activated carbon as a moving particle electrode for greywater treatment," *Separation and Purification Technology*, vol. 156, pp. 414–423, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2015.10.030>.
- [52] J. A. G. Gomes *et al.*, "Arsenic removal by electrocoagulation using combined Al-Fe electrode system and characterization of products," *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, vol. 139, no. 2, pp. 220–231, Jan. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2005.11.108>.
- [53] M. El-Naas, A.-Z. Sulaiman, and A. Al-Lobaney, "Treatment of petroleum refinery wastewater by continuous electrocoagulation," *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, vol. 2, no. 10, pp. 2144–2150, Jan. 2013.
- [54] L. Wei, S. Guo, G. Yan, C. Chen, and X. Jiang, "Electrochemical pretreatment of heavy oil refinery wastewater using a three-dimensional electrode reactor," *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 55, no. 28, pp. 8615–8620, Dec. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2010.08.011>.

Study and Design of a Multi-range Programmable Sensor for Temperature Measurements

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Abstract—In this paper, a wide-range high-precision sensor has been designed in order to accurately measure the temperature in a medium with arbitrary temperature variation and the implementation of a wide-spectrum temperature measurement system with a self-selected multi-sensor has been realized. This multi-sensor core is made up of different sensors combined to measure different temperature ranges. This concept can be used for high-precision temperature measurement in electrical capacitance tomography applications. The proposed technique is well suited for temperatures in boilers, industries, and everywhere high temperature measurement sensitivity is needed by using different combined temperature sensors of high precision.

Keywords—thermocouple; simulation; thermistor; RTD; temperature; linearization; LabVIEW

I. INTRODUCTION

Temperature sensors are among the most widely used sensors in the electronics industry, with applications ranging from safety calibrations to heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) in various industries. Despite their widespread use, temperature sensors and their implementation can present challenges for designers to achieve the best performance at the lowest possible cost. There are many ways to detect temperature. The most common methods use temperature sensors like thermistors, resistance temperature sensors, thermocouples, or silicon thermometers. However, choosing the right sensor is only part of the solution because that sensor must be connected to a signal chain that maintains the integrity of the signal, while providing precise compensation for the unique characteristics of the specific sensing technology to ensure an accurate digital temperature representation [1-4].

This article presents a USB-powered circuit solution to perform this task with a multi range system. This solution uses three sensors which are a Negative Temperature Coefficient (NTC) thermistor, a Resistance Temperature Detector (RTD), and a thermocouple to accurately monitor temperature [5-6].

II. IDENTIFICATION OF SENSORS AND THEIR RANGE

RTDs can be constructed in different forms and have good performance in terms of stability, accuracy, and repeatability. The RTD requires a power source to operate and uses an electrical resistance for measurement of temperature. The operation of the RTD sensor is based on the resistance-temperature relationship of the material used in its construction. The amount of change observed in the resistance value of the material due to a temperature rise per degree is measured and the sensor is calibrated accordingly [7-8]. The resistive element is fragile and always requires insulation, so insulator wires are attached to the element. For temperatures below 250°C, insulators such as silicon rubber and PVC are used for this purpose. A metal alloy chemically inert at this temperature is used as a protective sheath to house the measurement point and the leads.

A. RTD Wiring Configurations

RTDs come with two-lead, three-lead, or four-lead wires per element. A two-wire RTD is the least expensive, but the lead wire resistance unavoidably affects the measurement results. Two-wire RTDs are mostly used with short lead wires or where high accuracy is not required. The advantage of the three-wire RTD is that it removes the lead wire resistance from the measurement by adding a third lead wire. Four-wire RTD are used where superior accuracy is critical [5]. The Callendar-Van Dusen equation is commonly used to approximate the RTD curve [9]. Equation (1) is used for $-200 < ^\circ\text{C} < 0$ and (2) for $0 < ^\circ\text{C} < 850$.

$$R_T = R_0[1 + AT + BT^2 + CT^3(T - 100)] \quad (1)$$

$$R_T = R_0[1 + AT + BT^2] \quad (2)$$

where R_T is the resistance of the wire at temperature $T^\circ\text{C}$, R_0 is the resistance of the wire at temperature 0°C , A , B , and C are constants used to scale the RTD, with $A = 3.9083 \times 10^{-3} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, $B = -5.775 \times 10^{-7} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-2}$, and $C = -4.183 \times 10^{-12} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-3}$.

The temperature coefficient $\alpha = 0.00385\text{C}^{-1}$ for a platinum wire RTD is given by:

$$a(\Omega/\Omega/^\circ\text{C}) = (R_{100} - R_0) / R_0 \times 100^\circ\text{C} \quad (3)$$

B. Wheatstone Bridge Measurement Circuit

Wheatstone bridge circuits are used in sensor circuits. The bridges can be symmetric or asymmetric, balanced or unbalanced. Wheatstone bridge circuits can be used to accurately measure unknown impedance. The Wheatstone bridge has a single impedance-variable element that is inherently nonlinear, away from the balance point. Bridge circuits are commonly used to detect the temperature of a boiler or a process situated away from the actual circuit. Usually a sensor element, typically an RTD situated in the hot/cold environment provides the information about resistance change to calculate temperature [10]. Resistance-variable Wheatstone bridge circuits perform most of the front-end tasks in a design that uses inexpensive and accurate discrete parts. By incorporating an RTD element, the bridge's inherent resistance variations are kept within the accepted linearity and tolerance limits, depending on the manufacturer of the RTD [10].

Fig. 1. Wheatstone bridge circuit.

C. Linearization of the Output Bridge

The feedback compensation scheme is used to linearize the output of the bridge. The proposed scheme is shown in Figure 2, which is used with an RTD. The output of the bridge V_{op} is amplified by an instrumentation amplifier of gain A to obtain the final output V_{out} . A part of the output is added to a reference voltage V_R , employing a unity gain adder and the output of the adder provides the bridge excitation V_B .

Fig. 2. Feedback compensation scheme with RTD R_T .

$$V_{op} = \left(+ \frac{R_f}{R_{in}} \right) \left(\frac{V_{out} + V_{ref}}{2} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$V_{op} = (V_{out} + V_{ref}) \quad (5)$$

where $R_f = R_{in}$, R_f is the feedback resistor, R_{in} is the input resistor of the OPAMP, V_{out} is the the output voltage of the bridge, V_{ref} is the reference voltage, and V_{op} the summing voltage of the OPAMP

D. Thermistors

A thermistor is a temperature sensing element made of sintered semiconductor material that is characterized by large variations in resistance proportional to small changes in temperature. Thermistors generally have Negative Temperature Coefficients (NTC thermistors), which means that the resistance of the thermistor decreases as the temperature increases [5]. Thermistors are made from a combination of metals and metal oxide materials. Once combined, the materials are formed and fired into the desired shape. The thermistors can then be used as disc-shaped thermistors or can be formed and assembled with lead wires and coatings to form bead-shaped thermistors.

E. Characteristics of an NTC Thermistor

A thermistor is a temperature-sensitive resistor available in two forms: the Positive Temperature Coefficient (PTC) thermistor and the NTC thermistor. The polycrystalline ceramic PTC thermistor has a high PTC and is generally used in switching applications. The NTC ceramic semiconductor thermistor has a high resistive NTC, which causes its resistance to decrease as the temperature increases. This feature makes it a suitable device for precision temperature measurement. An NTC thermistor has 3 modes of operation: resistance versus temperature, voltage versus current, and current versus time. The mode that exploits the characteristics of resistance versus temperature provides the most accurate results. The circuits of the resistance versus temperature mode configure the thermistor in a "zero power" condition. The zero-power condition assumes that the current or voltage excitation of the device does not cause the thermistor to self-heat. The resistor formula of the thermistor is:

$$R_{th} = R_0 \exp\left[\beta\left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0}\right)\right] \quad (6)$$

where R_{th} is the resistance at temperature $T^\circ\text{C}$, R_0 the resistance at temperature 25°C , β is the temperature constant, T is the temperature of thermistor, and T_0 the temperature at 25°C .

Equation (6) shows the high degree of nonlinearity of the $4.7\text{K}\Omega$ thermistor. The rate at which the resistance of an NTC thermistor decreases with temperature is the constant β . Correction of the non-linear response of the thermistor can be done using a simpler and less expensive hardware technique which, when applied, keeps the linearization problem of the thermistor under control for a range of temperatures of $\pm 25^\circ\text{C}$. A simple approach to first-level linearization of the thermistor output is to place the thermistor in parallel with a standard (1%, metal-film) resistor and a voltage source. The value of the parallel resistance determines the median of the linear region of the thermistor circuit. The resistance value of the thermistor

(R_T) and the Steinhart-Hart equation determine the temperature of the thermistor (Figure 3). The Steinhart-Hart equation has proven to be the best mathematical expression for determining the temperature of an NTC thermistor. The equation of the output voltage with linear thermistor is:

$$V_{out} = V_{in} \left(\frac{R_T R_2}{R_T + R_2 + R_1 + R_1 (R_2 + R)} \right) \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3. Thermistor circuit with thermistor R_T .

F. Thermocouple

The operating principle of thermocouples is essentially based on the Seebeck effect. When a temperature difference occurs along a wire, charge transfer occurs. The amount of charge transfer depends on the electrical characteristics of the chosen material. When two wires of different materials are soldered on one side and a temperature difference occurs, a voltage is formed at both free ends. This voltage depends on the temperature difference along the two junctions. To measure the temperature at the junction point, the temperature at the free end must be known. When the free end temperature is unknown, the end must be extended with a compensation cable to a known temperature zone (compensation point) [11]. The compensation point temperature must be known and constant.

G. Thermocouple Linearization Techniques

A novel circuit for linearization of thermocouple signals using Analog – to – Digital (ADC) converter is proposed. The present method utilizes the ratio metric property of ADCs and the converter performs analog to digital conversion as well as linearization. The resulting circuit also has provision for scaling the linearized digital output to obtain a desired full-scale value. The digital count output L of dual-slope integration type A/D converter with differential input is given by:

$$L = \frac{C(V_{in}^+ - V_{in}^-)}{V} \quad (8)$$

where V^+ in and V^- in are the analog input voltages, V_{ref} an analog reference voltage, and C is the digital count output when $[(V_{in}^+) - (V_{in}^-)]$

If V^+ in the voltage signal $E(x)$ from a transducer circuit (x being measured), following an approach proposed by Ayman A. Ali –a linear relation between $L(x)$ and x can be achieved by suitably modifying (8) such that:

$$L(x) = \frac{C(1+K)E(x)/E_r}{1+KE(x)/E_r} \quad (9)$$

where the analog reference voltage is:

$$V_{Ref}(x) = \frac{E_r + KE(x)}{1+K} \text{ for positive } K$$

$$V_{Ref}(x) = E_r + KE(x) \text{ for negative } K \quad (10)$$

where K is a linearizing coefficient, whose optimum value is to be determined. The linearizing coefficient in terms of circuit resistances is $K=R_2/R_1$, where x is the temperature T under measurement and $E(x)$ is $E(T)$ - the thermo-e.m.f. from the thermocouple after appropriate reference junction compensation.

As an alternate approach, the linearizing arrangement is designed so that the scaling and linearizing mechanisms are independent of each other. Then the digital output count is given by:

$$L(x) = \frac{CA(1+K)E(x)/E_r}{1+KE(x)/E_r} \quad (11)$$

where A is the scaling constant. If E_r is adjusted to $E(x_f)$, the full-scale digital output is $L(x_f) = AC$. Then:

$$L(x) = \frac{L(x_f)(1+K)E(x)/E_r}{1+KE(x)/E_r} \quad (12)$$

The block diagram representation of the relevant circuit is given in Figure 2 of [12]. The proposed circuit's linearity of multi range sensors has been simulated with the virtual process having a temperature variation from 0°C to 100°C and the corresponding flowchart is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the multi-range sensor system.

A simulation of the proposed circuit characteristic was conducted in LabVIEW [10]. For the linear NTC thermistor, the given parameters were $V_{in} = 3.3V$, $R_1 = 100\Omega$ and $B = 3000$. The simulated thermocouple had a linear relation between temperature and output voltage, in a temperature range from 0°C to 60°C. For the third sensor, an RTD was used to measure the resistance change and output voltage with temperature with the following parameters: $V_{in} = 5V$, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = 100\Omega$, $R_{in} = R_f = 1000\Omega$, gain = 3.9 and $V_{ref} = 5V$.

H. Multi Range Temperature Sensor Simulation Block Diagram

The multi-range sensor system works through a varied range and employs multiple temperature sensors. Each sensor has a specific range to measure and to obtain value on the digital display and the corresponding sensor calculation. A simulation of the proposed characteristic was conducted with three linearized sensors (RTD, thermocouple, and thermistor). The diagram that integrates the graphic code of multi range sensor is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Multi range temperature sensor simulation block diagram.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The NTC thermistor sensor was simulated for temperatures from 0°C to 60°C with the circuit shown in Figure 3. A good linear relation of the output voltage of the thermistor with temperature was acquired, as shown in Figure 6. The thermocouple sensor was simulated at the same range, with the circuit shown in [12]. A good linear relation of the output voltage with the temperature was acquired, as shown in Figure 7. For the RTD sensor, linearity was observed in the widest range (from 0°C to 850°C). After applying the feedback compensation method, it has been clearly improved as shown in Figure 8. The blue line graph is of the RTD sensor without linearity for the circuit diagram shown in Figure 1, and the orange line shows the obtained linearity of the RTD sensor for the circuit diagram shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 6. Thermistor Voltage output vs input temperature.

Fig. 7. Thermocouple Voltage output vs input temperature.

Fig. 8. RTD Voltage output vs input temperature

The proposed simulated system consists of three sensors (RTD, thermistor, and thermocouple). The ranges allocated to the RTD sensor, the thermistor, and the thermocouple were from 51°C to 60°C, from 41°C to 50°C, and from 31°C to 40°C respectively. The circuit and parameters for each sensor are the ones mentioned before, but with different ranges. This is an overall temperature measurement system which means that a temperature can be sensed by any sensor in the system as shown in Figure 9. The diagram that integrates the graphic code of multi range sensors is shown in Figure 10. When the temperature of the system is within the specified sensor range, the sensor starts to measure and shows that with a white LED for the measuring sensor and red LEDs for the sensors which are not measuring (Figure 9).

Fig. 9. Representation of measuring sensors with LEDs.

The multi range system provides a linear temperature with auto-selected response over a approximate temperature range from 0°C to +50°C for the thermistor, from 50°C to +70°C for the RTD, and from 70°C to +100°C for the thermocouple.

Fig. 10. Simulation of the multi-range temperature system.

Fig. 11. The auto-selected temperature response of the proposed multi-range temperature measurement system.

A sufficient number of measurements were carried out by changing temperature ranges assigned to each sensor and the results were preserved. Thus, using the proposed method, the devised instrument can measure temperatures from a range of -50°C to around 1000°C.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PART

In this part, we present the experimental results obtained with the developed multi range sensor (Figure 12). Three temperature ranges were selected for all sensors and the measurements were carried out with the proposed circuits as shown in Figures 2-3 and Figure 2 of [12] for the respective sensors, with the same parameters used in the simulations for each one. As seen in Figure 12, the obtained range of the corresponding output voltage for thermistor is from 1.41V to 1.65V, which corresponds to 41°C to 50°C. In this range, the thermistor is active (on). For the Thermocouple, the obtained range of the output voltage is from 1.41V to 1.65V, which corresponds to 41°C to 50°C. In this range, the thermocouple is active (on). Finally, for the RTD, the obtained range of the output voltage is from 1.41V to 1.65V, which corresponds to 41°C to 50°C. In this range, the RTD is active (on).

Fig. 12. Photo of the implemented and experimented upon multi-range temperature system.

V. CONCLUSION

As a part of our study of a wide-spectrum temperature measurement system with self-selected multi-sensor, we presented the design and testing of a high-precision wide-range sensor comprising of three different sensors (thermocouple, thermistor, RTD). A range was assigned to each sensor and simulations were performed in LabVIEW. The results from the carried out experiments were in good agreement with the simulation. This concept can be used for different applications such as MRI and ECT.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Ramanathan Nagarajan, B. George, and V. J. Kumar, "A Linearizing Digitizer for Wheatstone Bridge Based Signal Conditioning of Resistive Sensors," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 1696–1705, Mar. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2017.2653227>.
- [2] F. Reverter, J. Jordana, M. Gasulla, and R. Pallàs-Areny, "Accuracy and resolution of direct resistive sensor-to-microcontroller interfaces," *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, vol. 121, no. 1, pp. 78–87, May 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sna.2005.01.010>.
- [3] L. Guendouz, S. M. O. A. Ghaly, A. Hedjiedj, J. Escanyé, and D. Canet, "Improved Helmholtz-type magnetic resonance imaging coils with high-B₁ homogeneity—Spherical and ellipsoidal four-coil systems," *Concepts in Magnetic Resonance Part B: Magnetic Resonance Engineering*, vol. 33B, no. 1, pp. 9–20, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cmr.b.20106>.
- [4] A. Gani and M. J. E. Salami, "A LabVIEW based data acquisition system for vibration monitoring and analysis," in *Student Conference on Research and Development*, Jul. 2002, pp. 62–65, <https://doi.org/10.1109/SCORED.2002.1033055>.
- [5] F. Alorifi, S. M. A. Ghaly, M. Y. Shalaby, M. A. Ali, and M. O. Khan, "Analysis and Detection of a Target Gas System Based on TDLAS & LabVIEW," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4196–4199, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2736>.
- [6] C. J. Kalkman, "LabVIEW: a software system for data acquisition, data analysis, and instrument control," *Journal of Clinical Monitoring*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 51–58, Jan. 1995, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01627421>.
- [7] S. M. A. Ghaly, "LabVIEW Based Implementation of Resistive Temperature Detector Linearization Techniques," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4530–4533, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2894>.
- [8] S. M. A. Ghaly, K. A. Al-Snaie, M. O. Khan, M. Y. Shalaby, and M. T. Oraiqat, "Design and Simulation of an 8-Lead Electrical Capacitance Tomographic System for Flow Imaging," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7430–7435, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4122>.
- [9] S. M. A. Ghaly, K. A. Al-Snaie, and A. M. Ali, "Design and Modeling of a Radiofrequency Coil Derived from a Helmholtz Structure," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 4037–4043, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2683>.
- [10] S. M. A. Ghaly, K. A. Al-Snaie, and O. K. Mohammad, "Spherical and Improved Helmholtz Coil with High B₁ Homogeneity for Magnetic Resonance Imaging," *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 12, pp. 1413–1418, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.3844/ajassp.2016.1413.1418>.
- [11] S. K. Sen, "An improved lead wire compensation technique for conventional two wire resistance temperature detectors (RTDs)," *Measurement*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 477–480, Jun. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2006.01.002>.
- [12] A. A. Aly and A. S. A. El-Lail, "International Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science(IJITCS)," *International Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 56–60.

Fault Detection Methods Suitable for Automotive Applications in Proton Exchange Fuel Cells

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Abstract-The fault conditions degrade the performance of proton exchange fuel cells and reduce their useful life. The prolonged existence of a fault condition can permanently damage the fuel cell. This paper proposes four methods for fault detection and fault type isolation. These methods were based on the coefficient of variance, ratios of change in output power to change in voltage and change in output voltage to the change in current, fuzzy membership values and Euclidian distance, and wavelet transform. These methods are non-invasive to the fuel cell and involve non-destructive testing. These methods were experimentally validated.

Keywords-PEM fuel cell; fuel cell faults; coefficient of variance; fuzzy membership values; wavelet

I. INTRODUCTION

A Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) is the most suitable fuel cell for automotive applications [1]. PEMFC performance is optimum when the operating conditions are appropriate. The fuel cell performance degrades due to poor thermal and water management [2], while prolonged water flooding can cause mechanical damage. An experiment using the Energy Intensity of reconstructed Vibrating voltage (EIV) based on the wavelet transform was proposed in [3]. The factors affecting the performance of fuel cells in automobiles are described with the help of faults [4], using cause-and-effect chain analysis. Several studies investigated fuel cell degradation [5], fault detection [6], and lifetime prediction in automobiles [7]. The degradation of the fuel cell output under various fault conditions and aging was studied in [8]. Output voltage and power degradation for the expected output are modeled as ratios that can detect the fault, and their thresholds help to isolate the defect type [9].

In [10], a diagnostic survey of fuel cell stacks was compiled to summarize faults in fuel cells, their causes, and existing methods to detect them. Statistically, water flooding is the largest (33%) contributing fault in fuel cell systems. Model-based and non-model-based methods were analyzed in [11] for fault diagnosis. A data-driven singular value decomposition method was applied in [12] to fuel cell parameters to detect faults. Data-driven diagnostics measure parameters and estimate the potential issue in a fuel cell. An aging data test was simulated for short-term prognosis in [13]. Several issues and solutions in fuel cell diagnostics were described in [14]. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) is a widely used technique in fuel cell fault diagnosis [15]. EIS has proven to be an effective tool in detecting fuel cell flooding and degradation and is also able to differentiate flood and drying faults in fuel cells [16]. EIS can be used to detect and isolate faults in fuel cells [17]. EIS experimental data were recorded for 35 days in [18] and were analyzed using Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). EIS has been used to determine the state of health of the fuel cells in electric vehicles [6] and detect catalyst degradation in fuel cells [19]. EIS is an offline technique for fault diagnosis. The estimation of online parameters for EIS was recently studied in [20]. The impedance obtained from EIS was further analyzed as wavelet energy using wavelet and wavelet packet decomposition [21]. The data obtained using EIS was converted to the frequency domain using the Morlet wavelet [22]. In [18], current interruption and injection of current pulses were used to overcome issues with the EIS method. Other methods to detect faults in fuel cells are Principle Component Analysis (PCA) [23], fuzzy inductive reasoning [24], fuzzy logic, delta V analysis using the COMSOL model [25], Kalman filter-based approach [26], external magnetic field-based tomography

methods [27], Takagi-Sugeno interval observer approach [28], and ANN-based approaches [29].

In [30], an ANN model was downloaded to an FPGA hardware platform to study 3 faults in a fuel cell system. A sliding mode algorithm was used for the observer design and MATLAB/Simulink was used to implement the ANN in [31]. Fuel cell degradation prognosis was performed based on Nonlinear Autoregressive Exogenous Neural Networks (NARX) and wavelet analysis in [32]. Degradation prognosis was also studied in [33] by using a degradation model based on the Wavelet Neural Network (WNN) and Cuckoo search algorithm. Energy management in PEMFC vehicles was studied using a MATLAB/Simulink model in [34]. Wavelet transforms were used in [35] for energy management optimization strategies on FCEVs. Model-based techniques have been described for offline [36] and online [37] fault detection. The online automotive fuel cell degradation was studied by modeling an electrical load in [4]. Fuel cell degradation over a period causes internal changes inside the cell. These internal change behaviors were studied with the help of polarization curves and an adaptive neuro-fuzzy interference system for prognosis [38]. A fuzzy logic model was applied in [39] to common automotive stress conditions to diagnose faults. In [40], mathematical models were used to determine a fuel cell's health and predict its useful life. In [41], the useful life of the fuel cell was determined using a particle filtering framework. Fuel cell State Of Health (SOH), useful remaining life, and robustness were estimated in [42] using an extended Kalman filter. In [43], artificial intelligence was used to estimate useful life and predict the degradation of a fuel cell. The echo state network is an AI tool to estimate the useful life of a fuel cell stack by considering the mean voltage of the cells [44]. A time delay NN was used along with the Auto-Regressive Moving Average (ARMA) model for the prognosis of degradation. The ARMA model was used in [45] to predict the useful life of PEM fuel cells along with a physical aging model and time delay NN. The ARMA results for the lifetime prognosis of PEM fuel cell stacks were found satisfactory when compared with back propagation neural networks and least square fitting [46]. The simulation results of Model Predictive Control (MPC) based on the ARMA model were found to have better control performance than MPC based on a rigorous linear model. Fuel cell degradation prediction based on the ARMA model was found accurate in long-term forecasting [47]. A fault model based on the Coefficient of Variance (CV) was developed and experimentally validated in [48]. The durability of the fuel cell was analyzed by characterizing the voltage consistency [49] and consistency [50] using CV.

Most fault detection methods are offline, and the above-presented studies use fixed loads. However, the load on an automotive PEMFC is dynamic. This paper focuses on online fault detection and isolation methods. Detecting fault conditions by merely measuring and analyzing the output voltage and current makes the models practical in automobile applications, as it enables analysis with minimum sensors and no downtime. This study compared the fault detection and isolation models, CV, and ratios of 4 novel methods developed using fuzzy membership functions and wavelets.

II. EXPERIMENTAL OBSERVATIONS

Experiments were conducted on two 25cm² PaxiTech fuel cells using the PEM fuel cell test setup, FCT-50S, and FCT-Lab. One cell was newly constructed and the other one was aged, having run for more than 2000 hours. The aged fuel cell had a 90% degradation in power delivery compared to the new one. Faults were injected into the aged fuel cell, and the changes in polarization curves were observed. A water-flooded cell showed around a 30% decrease in performance in terms of power delivery. The reactant gas starvation fault showed around 55% degradation in the cell performance. A high-operating-temperature fault cell could not be able to deliver power. Figure 1 shows the polarization curves of the experiments.

Fig. 1. PEM fuel cell performance in operating conditions [7].

III. DEGRADATION AND FAULT DETECTION METHODS

Four methods were used to examine performance degradation and fault detection of the fuel cell. This section presents the methods and their results.

A. Coefficient of Variance

CV is used to measure the fuel cell output voltage dispersion and degree of asymmetry [51], and analyze its reliability using the stress-strength interference method [52]. The CV is a ratio of the standard deviation σ to the mean μ , as shown in (1). CV measures the relative variability of the parameters and can be used to compare the voltage degradation of a PEMFC for a given current.

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

The coefficients of variance for the fuel cell output voltage CV_V , the current density CV_{CD} , and the cell power CV_P were calculated for aged cells and cells operating in fault conditions [48]. The experimental results showed that the CV values could differentiate the degradation performance.

B. Ratio Comparison

Experimental observations showed that fuel cell voltage drops for the current. This method compares the rate of change in the PEMFC output voltage to the change in its output current, using (2). Another ratio was calculated as the change in the PEMFC output power to the change in output voltage, shown in (3).

$$\left(\frac{dV}{di}\right)_{cell} \neq \left(\frac{dV}{di}\right)_{Healthy\ cell} \quad (2)$$

$$\left(\frac{dP}{dV}\right)_{cell} \neq \left(\frac{dP}{dV}\right)_{Healthy\ cell} \quad (3)$$

Ratios were calculated for the fuel cell under test and compared to the ratios of a healthy cell with the same specifications. The cell could have a fault condition if the ratio values do not match. Similarly, the ratios can be compared to the threshold to isolate the fault type, as shown in (4) and (5):

$$\left(\frac{dP}{dV}\right)_{cell} \approx \left(\frac{dP}{dV}\right)_{fault\ threshold} \quad (4)$$

$$\left(\frac{dV}{di}\right)_{cell} \approx \left(\frac{dV}{di}\right)_{fault\ threshold} \quad (5)$$

Figures 2 and 3 show, respectively, the ratios dP/dV and dV/di for each operating condition. The graphs show the difference in the performance of the fuel cell in a fault condition from a healthy one [9].

C. Fuzzy Membership Values and Euclidian Distance Method

The fuzzy linear membership function of the values was used to compare the output voltage and current values of the fuel cell. The fuzzy linear membership values were obtained for the dataset. These membership values were comparable as they were unit free. The fuzzy Linear Membership function for the i -th observation defines a linear membership function as:

$$\mu(x) = \left(\frac{i^{th}\ observation - lowest\ observation}{i^{th}\ observation}\right) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. dP/dV curves in different conditions [9].

Fig. 3. dV/di curve comparison between healthy and faulty operating conditions [9].

The value of the membership function lies between 0 and 1. The smallest observation has a membership value of zero ($m(x)=0$). The membership values for the current and voltage observations can be used to calculate the Euclidean distance between the standard and the observed values.

Let $\mu_i(x)$ denote the membership values for the k -th observed current value and $\mu_v(x)$ denote the membership value for the k -th observed voltage value. The corresponding point in the membership plane for the observed current and voltage values is given by $M(\mu_i(x), \mu_v(x))$. Similarly, the point in the membership plane for benchmark values obtained from healthy cell be $M'(\tilde{\mu}_i(x), \tilde{\mu}_v(x))$. The Euclidean distance between MM' can be calculated by:

$$d = \sqrt{(\mu_i(x) - \tilde{\mu}_i(x))^2 + (\mu_v(x) - \tilde{\mu}_v(x))^2} \quad (7)$$

The fuel cell operation is desirable when the distance d is minimum, whereas a larger value of d indicates that the fuel cell is operating in a potential fault condition. Figure 4 shows the fuzzy membership values obtained under various operating conditions. The distance between the fuzzy membership values can be calculated using the Euclidean distance.

Fig. 4. Comparison of fuzzy membership values.

D. Wavelet Transform

The wavelet transform can be used for non-destructive testing and monitoring the health of a system [54]. The time and frequency domains of a signal provide significant information. Wavelet and its transform are useful to analyze the time and frequency domains of a signal [53]. Equation (8) shows a "mother" wavelet or a wavelet basis function:

$$\Psi_{u,s}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \Psi\left(\frac{t-u}{s}\right) \quad (8)$$

where s is a scaling parameter that allows the dilation of the signal and u is a translational parameter that allows the translation of a signal in time. Hence, it allows time-frequency spectrum generation. However, the resolution of both time and frequency is not high. The following equations calculate a continuous wavelet transform of a time-based signal:

$$W_\Psi[f](u, s) = f, \Psi_{u,s} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 5. Haar 3 analysis of PEMFC experimental data under different operating conditions: (a) good cell, (b) old cell, (c) water flooded cell, and (d) starvation.

$$f, \Psi_{u,s} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) \Psi_{u,s}(t) dt \quad (10)$$

Let the time-based signal be $f(t)$. The time-frequency spectrum is obtained by repeating the process over the time and frequency range. However, the discrete wavelet transform can provide a sparser representation [55], as it has an advantage in analyzing signals with sudden transitions. One of the applications can be monitoring a machine failure. Moreover, the computational speed is faster than the continuous transform.

The Haar wavelet transform was used in the analysis, as it is a discrete and the simplest wavelet. The mother wavelet function for the Haar wavelet is described by:

$$\Psi(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 \leq t < 1/2, \\ -1 & 1/2 \leq t < 1, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The mother wavelet is decomposed to approximate components A_j and detailed components D_j . Approximate components are used to analyze information at low frequencies and detailed components are used to analyze information at higher frequencies. The energy of the signal was computed using the following:

$$E_j^d = \sum_k |C_j^d(k)|^2 \quad (12)$$

where C is the coefficient of the detailed component at level j of the k number of samples.

Haar 3 level decomposition was used to analyze the fuel cell experimental data. Data were analyzed using the wavelet toolbox from MATLAB 2019b. Figure 5 shows the analysis in a graphical form. The pattern of detailed decomposition levels is distinctly different from the healthy PEMFC data. The oscillations in d_1 , d_2 , and d_3 were observed in a healthy fuel cell when the voltage dropped as the current increased. However, the coefficients had oscillations since the beginning, and the waveform showed a linear drop.

Oscillations were observed in water-flooded conditions at higher currents. High magnitude oscillations were observed at higher currents in the case of reactant gas starvation conditions. Hence, the pattern in coefficients can differentiate the fuel cell performance during degradation due to the fault condition or aging.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The PEMFC performance was observed experimentally to degrade when the cell was aged or operated in a fault condition. The output performance of the PEMFC was analyzed using methods like CV, comparing ratios, fuzzy membership values, and wavelet transform. All methods used the PEMFC output voltage and current data for fault detection. CV is the simplest method to detect a fault condition. The ratios dP/dV and dV/di were found to be useful for fault detection and fault type identification. The results obtained from the fuzzy membership values of the PEMFC output voltage and current proved to be an effective method to detect faults. However, the Euclidian distance method should be used to isolate the fault type. On the other hand, the wavelet transform proved to be a better method

for fault detection and fault type isolation. The simple discrete form of the Haar wavelet transform was found to be effective. All these methods can be used for online and non-destructive fault detection.

V. CONCLUSION

Fault conditions degrading the performance of a PEMFC were experimentally investigated. As the fault detection methods proposed in this paper were online, non-invasive, and non-destructive, they can be useful in automobile applications. Methods, CV, ratios, and wavelet transform are useful for fault detection and fault type isolation. However, the fuzzy membership method requires further analysis of the Euclidian distance to isolate the fault type. The CV and fuzzy membership value methods are more suitable for online fault detection in an automotive application. However, the wavelet transform method can be used as a self-diagnosis of the fuel cell during startup.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Biberici and M. B. Celik, "Dynamic Modeling and Simulation of a PEM Fuel Cell (PEMFC) during an Automotive Vehicle's Driving Cycle," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5796–5802, Jun. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3352>.
- [2] S. S. Barhate, R. Mudhalwadkar, and A. K. Prakash, "A survey on factors affecting performance and durability of PEM Fuel Cells in Automotive applications," *International Journal of Control Theory and Applications*, vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 659–669, 2017.
- [3] T. Ma, W. Lin, Y. Yang, K. Wang, and W. Jia, "Water content diagnosis for proton exchange membrane fuel cell based on wavelet transformation," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 45, no. 39, pp. 20339–20350, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.11.068>.
- [4] X. Zhang, D. Yang, M. Luo, and Z. Dong, "Load profile based empirical model for the lifetime prediction of an automotive PEM fuel cell," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 16, pp. 11868–11878, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.02.146>.
- [5] Z. Wang, "Lifetime Prediction Modeling of Automotive Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells," presented at the WCX SAE World Congress Experience, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.4271/2019-01-0385>.
- [6] M. Becherif, M.-C. Péra, D. Hissel, and Z. Zheng, "Determination of the health state of fuel cell vehicle for a clean transportation," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 171, pp. 1510–1519, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.072>.
- [7] P. Polverino, E. Frisk, D. Jung, M. Krysanter, and C. Pianese, "Model-based diagnosis through Structural Analysis and Causal Computation for automotive Polymer Electrolyte Membrane Fuel Cell systems," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 357, pp. 26–40, Jul. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.04.089>.
- [8] S. Barhate and R. Mudhalwadkar, "Proton exchange membrane fuel cell fault and degradation detection using a coefficient of variance method," *Journal of Energy Systems*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 20–34, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.30521/jes.817879>.
- [9] S. S. Barhate and R. Mudhalwadkar, "Proton exchange membrane fuel cell dynamic model based on time series analysis for fault diagnosis," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Technology*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 351–379, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJRET.2021.118509>.

- [10] R. H. Lin, X. N. Xi, P. N. Wang, B. D. Wu, and S. M. Tian, "Review on hydrogen fuel cell condition monitoring and prediction methods," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 44, no. 11, pp. 5488–5498, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.09.085>.
- [11] A. Benmouna, M. Becherif, D. Depernet, F. Gustin, H. S. Ramadan, and S. Fukuhara, "Fault diagnosis methods for Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell system," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 1534–1543, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2016.07.181>.
- [12] L. Mao, L. Jackson, and S. Dunnett, "Fault Diagnosis of Practical Polymer Electrolyte Membrane (PEM) Fuel Cell System with Data-driven Approaches," *Fuel Cells*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 247–258, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1002/fuce.201600139>.
- [13] H. Liu, J. Chen, M. Hou, Z. Shao, and H. Su, "Data-based short-term prognostics for proton exchange membrane fuel cells," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 32, pp. 20791–20808, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.06.180>.
- [14] D. Hissel and M. C. Pera, "Diagnostic & health management of fuel cell systems: Issues and solutions," *Annual Reviews in Control*, vol. 42, pp. 201–211, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arcontrol.2016.09.005>.
- [15] D. Ritzberger, M. Striednig, C. Simon, C. Hametner, and S. Jakubek, "Online estimation of the electrochemical impedance of polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells using broad-band current excitation," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 405, pp. 150–161, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2018.08.082>.
- [16] C. Cadet, S. Jemei, F. Druart, and D. Hissel, "Diagnostic tools for PEMFCs: from conception to implementation," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 39, no. 20, pp. 10613–10626, Jul. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.04.163>.
- [17] A. M. Dhirde, N. V. Dale, H. Salehfar, M. D. Mann, and T.-H. Han, "Equivalent Electric Circuit Modeling and Performance Analysis of a PEM Fuel Cell Stack Using Impedance Spectroscopy," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 778–786, Sep. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEC.2010.2049267>.
- [18] C. Jeppesen, S. S. Araya, S. L. Sahlin, S. Thomas, S. J. Andreasen, and S. K. Kær, "Fault detection and isolation of high temperature proton exchange membrane fuel cell stack under the influence of degradation," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 359, pp. 37–47, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.05.021>.
- [19] I. Pivac, D. Bezmalinović, and F. Barbir, "Catalyst degradation diagnostics of proton exchange membrane fuel cells using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 43, no. 29, pp. 13512–13520, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.05.095>.
- [20] H. Wang, A. Gaillard, and D. Hissel, "Online electrochemical impedance spectroscopy detection integrated with step-up converter for fuel cell electric vehicle," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 1110–1121, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.10.242>.
- [21] A. Sethi and D. Verstraete, "A Comparative Study of Wavelet-based Descriptors for Fault Diagnosis of Self-Humidified Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells," *Fuel Cells*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 131–142, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1002/fuce.201900125>.
- [22] R. Du, X. Wang, H. Dai, X. Wei, and P. Ming, "Online impedance spectrum measurement of fuel cells based on Morlet wavelet transform," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 46, no. 47, pp. 24339–24352, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.05.012>.
- [23] R. H. Lin, Z. X. Pei, Z. Z. Ye, C. C. Guo, and B. D. Wu, "Hydrogen fuel cell diagnostics using random forest and enhanced feature selection," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 45, no. 17, pp. 10523–10535, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.10.127>.
- [24] I. Pivac, B. Šimić, and F. Barbir, "Experimental diagnostics and modeling of inductive phenomena at low frequencies in impedance spectra of proton exchange membrane fuel cells," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 365, pp. 240–248, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.08.087>.
- [25] L. M. Pant, Z. Yang, M. L. Perry, and A. Z. Weber, "Development of a Simple and Rapid Diagnostic Method for Polymer-Electrolyte Fuel Cells," *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, vol. 165, no. 6, Jan. 2018, Art. no. F3007, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0011806jes>.
- [26] G. Buonocunto, G. Spagnuolo, and W. Zamboni, "A Kalman filter based approach to PEM fuel cell fault detection," in *2017 IEEE 26th International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (ISIE)*, Edinburgh, UK, Jun. 2017, pp. 934–939, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISIE.2017.8001371>.
- [27] L. Ifrek, S. Rosini, G. Cauffet, O. Chadebec, L. Rouveyre, and Y. Bultel, "Fault detection for polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell stack by external magnetic field," *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 313, pp. 141–150, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2019.04.193>.
- [28] D. Rotondo, R. M. Fernandez-Canti, S. Tornil-Sin, J. Blesa, and V. Puig, "Robust fault diagnosis of proton exchange membrane fuel cells using a Takagi-Sugeno interval observer approach," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 2875–2886, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.12.071>.
- [29] A. Abbaspour, K. K. Yen, P. Forouzaneshad, and A. Sargolzaei, "Active Adaptive Fault-Tolerant Control Design for PEM Fuel Cells," in *2018 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE)*, Portland, OR, USA, Sep. 2018, pp. 3616–3622, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ECCE.2018.8557620>.
- [30] "International Journal of Energy and Environment (IJE)," *International Journal of Energy and Environment*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 353–362, 2018.
- [31] J. Liu, W. Luo, X. Yang, and L. Wu, "Robust Model-Based Fault Diagnosis for PEM Fuel Cell Air-Feed System," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 3261–3270, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2016.2535118>.
- [32] K. Chen, S. Laghrouche, and A. Djerdir, "Prognosis of fuel cell degradation under different applications using wavelet analysis and nonlinear autoregressive exogenous neural network," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 179, pp. 802–814, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.07.097>.
- [33] K. Chen, S. Laghrouche, and A. Djerdir, "Health state prognostic of fuel cell based on wavelet neural network and cuckoo search algorithm," *ISA Transactions*, vol. 113, pp. 175–184, Jul. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isatra.2020.03.012>.
- [34] A. Khadhraoui, T. Selmi, and A. Cherif, "Energy Management of a Hybrid Electric Vehicle," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8916–8921, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5058>.
- [35] T. Teng, X. Zhang, H. Dong, and Q. Xue, "A comprehensive review of energy management optimization strategies for fuel cell passenger vehicle," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 45, no. 39, pp. 20293–20303, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.12.202>.
- [36] L. Russo, M. Sorrentino, P. Polverino, and C. Pianese, "Application of Buckingham π theorem for scaling-up oriented fast modelling of Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell impedance," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 353, pp. 277–286, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.03.116>.
- [37] A. Rosich, R. Sarrate, and F. Nejari, "On-line model-based fault detection and isolation for PEM fuel cell stack systems," *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 38, no. 11, pp. 2744–2757, Jun. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2013.10.065>.
- [38] L. Mao, L. Jackson, and T. Jackson, "Investigation of polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cell internal behaviour during long term operation and its use in prognostics," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 362, pp. 39–49, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.07.018>.
- [39] B. Davies, L. Jackson, and S. Dunnett, "Expert diagnosis of polymer electrolyte fuel cells," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 42, no. 16, pp. 11724–11734, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.02.121>.
- [40] M. Jouin, R. Gouriveau, D. Hissel, M.-C. Pera, and N. Zerhouni, "Prognostics and Health Management of PEMFC – State of the art and remaining challenges," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 38, no. 35, pp. 15307–15317, Nov. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.09.051>.

- [41] M. Jouin, R. Gouriveau, D. Hissel, M.-C. Péra, and N. Zerhouni, "Prognostics of PEM fuel cell in a particle filtering framework," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 481–494, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.10.054>.
- [42] M. Bressel, M. Hilairet, D. Hissel, and B. Ould Bouamama, "Extended Kalman Filter for prognostic of Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell," *Applied Energy*, vol. 164, pp. 220–227, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.11.071>.
- [43] L. Vichard, F. Harel, A. Ravey, P. Venet, and D. Hissel, "Degradation prediction of PEM fuel cell based on artificial intelligence," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 45, no. 29, pp. 14953–14963, May 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.03.209>.
- [44] S. Morando, S. Jemei, R. Gouriveau, N. Zerhouni, and D. Hissel, "Fuel Cells prognostics using echo state network," in *IECON 2013 - 39th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, Vienna, Austria, Aug. 2013, pp. 1632–1637, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IECON.2013.6699377>.
- [45] D. Zhou, A. Al-Durra, K. Zhang, A. Ravey, and F. Gao, "Online remaining useful lifetime prediction of proton exchange membrane fuel cells using a novel robust methodology," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 399, pp. 314–328, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2018.06.098>.
- [46] T. Y. Kim, B. S. Kim, T. C. Park, and Y. K. Yeo, "Development of Predictive Model based Control Scheme for a Molten Carbonate Fuel Cell (MCFC) Process," *International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 791–803, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12555-016-0234-0>.
- [47] A. H. Detti, N. Y. Steiner, L. Bouillaut, A. B. Same, and S. Jemei, "Fuel Cell Performance Prediction Using an AutoRegressive Moving-Average ARMA Model," in *2019 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC)*, Hanoi, Vietnam, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/VPPC46532.2019.8952535>.
- [48] S. Barhate and R. Mudhalwadkar, "Proton exchange membrane fuel cell fault and degradation detection using a coefficient of variance method," *Journal of Energy Systems*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 20–34, Mar. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.30521/jes.817879>.
- [49] Y. Hou, Y. Ouyang, F. Pei, and D. Hao, "Voltage and Voltage Consistency Attenuation Law of the Fuel Cell Stack Based on the Durability Cycle Condition," presented at the WCX SAE World Congress Experience, Apr. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.4271/2019-01-0386>.
- [50] D. Zhong *et al.*, "Low temperature durability and consistency analysis of proton exchange membrane fuel cell stack based on comprehensive characterizations," *Applied Energy*, vol. 264, Apr. 2020, Art. no. 114626, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.114626>.
- [51] M. Noorkami *et al.*, "Effect of temperature uncertainty on polymer electrolyte fuel cell performance," *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 1439–1448, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.10.156>.
- [52] L. F. Liu, B. Liu, and C. W. Wu, "Reliability prediction of large fuel cell stack based on structure stress analysis," *Journal of Power Sources*, vol. 363, pp. 95–102, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2017.06.041>.
- [53] M. S. Mohammed and K. Ki-Seong, "Chirplet Transform in Ultrasonic Non-Destructive Testing and Structural Health Monitoring: A Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3778–3781, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2470>.
- [54] P. P. Vaidyanathan, *Multirate Systems and Filter Banks*. Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA: Prentice Hall, 1993.
- [55] S. P. Madhe, B. D. Patil, and R. S. Holambe, "On the Design of Arbitrary Shape Two-Channel Filter Bank Using Eigenfilter Approach," *Circuits, Systems, and Signal Processing*, vol. 36, no. 11, pp. 4441–4452, Nov. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00034-017-0519-4>.

Some Mineralogical Characteristics of the Egyptian Black Sand Beach Ilmenite Part I: Homogeneous Ilmenite and Titanhematite-Ferriilmenite Grains

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Abstract-The high-grade Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrate contains various mineral textures in addition to the main homogeneous ilmenite grains (63%), which may contain solid solutions of geikielite (MgTiO_3) and pyrophanite (MnTiO_3) mineral components. Few homogeneous ferriilmenite grains (2%) associated with the concentrated ilmenite grains are detected. The contents of Fe_2O_3 , MgO , Al_2O_3 , and Cr_2O_3 in the ferriilmenite grains range between 7.3% and 22.8%, 3.4% and 6.6%, 0.2% and 0.7%, and 0% and 1.2% respectively. The detected hematite-ilmenite exsolved intergrowths (21.4%) have titanhematite exsolutions of different shapes, sizes, and orientations. They occupy 5%-40% of the whole intergrowth and may show one or two distinct generations. In some ferriilmenite components, MnO ranges between 1.5% and 8.6%. The Cr_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 contents range between 0% and 1.2% and 0% and 3.2% respectively. They are mostly between 0% and 0.1% for either of the ferriilmenite components, while relatively greater content is present in the titanhematite components. In some grains, the titanhematite exsolution bodies are replaced by goethite or hydrated iron oxides. In others, the ferriilmenite intergrowth may be partially or completely altered into leucoxene. Some minor composite grains are detected in the concentrate, where each grain consists of two parts, one part is titanhematite-ferriilmenite and the other is ferriilmenite-titanhematite. The titanhematite exsolved components have relatively lower TiO_2 content (5.8%-23.8%). Both MgO and MnO are positively correlated with FeO rather than Fe_2O_3 . The presence of sphene in the obtained ilmenite concentrate may be responsible for the recorded amounts of SiO_2 and CaO . The Cr_2O_3 content is relatively much higher in sphene spots than in ilmenite spots, ensuring that Cr_2O_3 neither follows TiO_2 nor FeO . The nature of the problem of the relatively lower Ti content and the relatively higher Fe and Cr contents of the obtained ilmenite concentrates is the target of the article. The problem is related to the mineralogy of ilmenite or to the used physical concentration flowsheet of the separated concentrate and the ability to improve the ilmenite concentrate's specifications. It is concluded that although the homogeneous ilmenite is characterized by low Cr_2O_3 content, some of the other exsolved texture components, e.g. titanhematite and sphene, have relatively higher Cr_2O_3 , in addition to Fe_2O_3 , SiO_2 , or CaO . They can negatively affect the marketable specifications of the separated Egyptian black sand ilmenite concentrate.

Keywords-beach ilmenite; geikielite; pyrophanite; ferriilmenite; titanhematite; Egypt

I. INTRODUCTION

The Egyptian black sand contains huge reserves of 6 common economic minerals, i.e. ilmenite, magnetite, garnet, zircon, rutile, and monazite in descending order of abundance. The Egyptian black sand is present either as beach sands (Figure 1, (1)), or coastal sand dunes. The Egyptian black sand minerals are derived originally from the disintegration of rocks, they are carried by the Nile waters, and are deposited after the river meets the Mediterranean Sea. The Egyptian black sand is considered in general as Recent to Pleistocene in age [1]. The deposit mainly contains the 6 above mentioned minerals. They are associated with quartz and green silicates (amphiboles and pyroxenes). Traces of cassiterite, gold, and Pb, Zn, Hg, Ag, Th, U, Nb, Ta, and Pt minerals have also been detected [2-4]. Along the north coast of Egypt, in areas characterized by extensive beach erosion, east and west of the Rosetta estuary, some surficially highly concentrated black sands are found parallel to the shoreline. They form narrow patches with lengths that rarely attain 1Km and widths ranging from a few up to 60m [2]. However, the original amount of materials transported by the river may be related to several variables such as the flow type and the sediment load [5].

Ilmenite (FeTiO_3) is the most abundant titanium mineral. The main source of ilmenite, rutile and leucoxene, are the sand type placer deposits found at or near the coast. Ilmenite also occurs in massive rock formations in the form of titaniferous iron ores, associated with hematite and magnetite [6]. Ilmenite and rutile are used for the manufacture of titanium dioxide white pigment which is the whitest and most stable of all known white pigments, being entirely unaffected by acids or alkalis that dissolve and destroy other whites. It has the good ability to maintain its visual appearance for a considerable period of time. It is stable up to 1800°C. Ilmenite is also used for the production of metallic titanium which is characterized by high strength in relation to its density, the ability to retain its properties from -300°F to 1000°F, and its excellent corrosion resistance. Titanium forms extremely hard metallic compounds

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with carbon, silicon, nitrogen, and boron. They are used as tips for cutting tools and in abrasive stones and wheels [6-7].

The majority of the mineralogical features of the Egyptian beach ilmenite can be seen in [2, 8-16]. Many authors have reported the relatively lower TiO_2 content and the relatively higher Fe_2O_3 and Cr_2O_3 contents, while others reported the diversity of the mineralogical textures inside ilmenite grains. However, the ilmenite content of the Egyptian black sand ranges from less than 1% in the raw beach sand up to more than 50% in the naturally highly concentrated surfacial black sands. Most of the obtained Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrates are characterized by a relatively lower TiO_2 content (44-46% of ilmenite's beach sand and 46-49 wt% of ilmenite's sand dunes) and relatively greater Cr_2O_3 content (0.1-0.4%). Also, they have a relatively lower $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratio and relatively higher MgO and MnO contents.

The ilmenite ore of Abu Ghalaga mine, south eastern Desert of Egypt, occurs as massive-type interlayer gabbroic rocks [17]. The massive ilmenite ores are considered the second major type of Fe-Ti oxide mineral ores in Egypt. Authors in [18] explained that Abu Ghalaga ilmenite ore is not found as homogeneous grains but it is mainly hematite-ilmenite exsolution texture containing 36.78% TiO_2 , 25.85% FeO, 29.86% Fe_2O_3 , and 4.46% SiO_2 along with other minor oxides of Mg, Mn, Cr, and P. Abu Ghalaga and Korabkanci, south eastern Desert of Egypt, are considered two promising areas of Fe-Ti massive ore deposits [19]. The separation of ilmenite and other economic mineral concentrates from the Egyptian beach sand and other deposits are explained in [2-3, 20]. The majority of ilmenite mineral varieties are contained in the obtained highly purified concentrates using wet gravity concentration and magnetic and high tension electrostatic separation techniques. These varieties are characterized by strongly to moderate magnetic susceptibilities. Except of magnetite, some minor ilmenite varieties associated with hematite, chromite, and definite magnetic leucosene varieties are separated in definite magnetic fractions characterized by magnetic susceptibilities ranging from the ferromagnetic to the weakly paramagnetic [2].

The problem of relatively higher Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 contents in the Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrate is the subject of this article. The mineralogical characters of some different ilmenite grains will be investigated. It is necessary to detect if the problem of the high chromium and ferric iron contents in the obtained beach ilmenite concentrates is related to the used ore dressing techniques, or related to the mineralogical features of the obtained ilmenite concentrate. Answering this question can lead to the improvement of the chemical specifications and the economic marketability of the Egyptian beach ilmenite. Lowering the chromium content of the obtained concentrate can improve its use in the white pigment industry.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A bulk sample weighing about 1000 tons was collected from the surfacial naturally highly concentrated beach black sands (Figure 1, (2)), at the Mediterranean coast, 7km east of Rosetta estuary (Figure 1, (1)). The sample represents the raw sand in a 2km stretch with varying width of a few up to 20m.

The sands were manually scraped from the mantle to a depth ranging between 10 and 30cm. Using the difference in physical characters between the various economic minerals, the collected surfacial naturally highly concentrated beach raw sands were processed in the plant at Abu Khashaba site (Figure 1, (3)), using the following equipment: Full- and half- size Wilfley shaking tables for wet-gravity concentration, Carpco (HP 167) high-tension roll-type electrostatic separator for electrostatic separation, Reading cross-belts magnetic separator, and the Carpco (MIH 13-231-100) industrial high intensity induced roll dry magnetic separator for magnetic separation. Finally, a bulk conductor ilmenite fraction was obtained and subjected to the refining magnetic stage using the reading cross-belt magnetic separator, where an ilmenite concentrate assaying 99.5% ilmenite grains was obtained.

Four polished sections were prepared from 4 small representative samples and were studied under the reflected microscope and Cameca SX-100 microprobe instrument. They were taken from the obtained final ilmenite concentrate (including 2 obtained magnetic fractions of the separator), a representative sample of the obtained ferromagnetic fraction, a representative sample of all the other obtained magnetic fractions of the separator, and, finally, a representative sample of the obtained non magnetic fraction of the separator.

Fig. 1. (1) Distribution of the Egyptian black sand showing the location of the surfacial naturally highly concentrated beach black sand 7 km to the east of Rosetta estuary, Abu Khashaba. (2) The collected bulk sample of the surfacial beach black sand, dried by sunlight. (3) A part of the physical concentration plant at Abu Khashaba showing the full- and half-size Wilfley shaking tables and the two R cross belt magnetic separators.

The investigation of the different ilmenite grains was carried out by a Cameca SX-100 Electron Microprobe Analyzer (EMPA), from the Institute of Mineralogy and Crystal Chemistry, Stuttgart University, Germany. The microprobe instrument is equipped with 3 Wavelength Dispersive Spectrometers (WDS) and an Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (EDS). The whole surface of the polished sections was examined by Back Scattered Electron (BSE) images, so that ilmenite grains with 10 μ m size or even smaller could be detected. The analytical conditions were 15kV accelerating voltage, 15nA electron current, 180s counting time for each analyzed spot, and 1 to 4 μ m diameter of the focused electron beam. The following standards were used: diopside for Mg and Ca, albite for Na, corundum for Al, orthoclase for Si and K, rutile for Ti, rhodonite for Mn, Fe₂O₃ for Fe, Cr₂O₃ for Cr, V for V, and sphalerite for Zn. K α lines were used for the element analysis. Also, a binocular microscope, a reflected-light polarizing microscope, sample splitters, and various containers were utilized.

III. CALCULATION

A. Calculation of the Fe³⁺ Content and the Molecular Formula of the Studied Ilmenite Grains

In the current paper, using the formula of [21], a constructed ilmenite formula in Microsoft Excel was used for the calculation of the Fe³⁺ content and the molecular formula of of ilmenite mineral component of the studied individual ilmenite grains.

B. Calculation of Different Mineral Components of the Analyzed Spots Composed Mainly of Ferriilmenite and/or Titanhematite with or without Individual TiO₂ (Rutile)

Most of the analyzed spots of the grains were subjected to one of the following calculation methods to determine the different mineral fraction components of each analyzed spot.

1) The First Method (M1)

In this method, the adopted ilmenite Excel formula was carried out for each analyzed spot to calculate FeO % and Fe₂O₃ %. If the sum of cations is less than 2, then all iron content must be considered as FeO, completely contained within the calculated ilmenite fraction component. The calculated iron fraction as FeO % (cal) is used to calculate the corresponding content of ilmenite fraction (FeTiO₃), and its corresponding content of TiO₂ wt% as follows: ilmenite mineral fraction = FeO % (cal) \times 2.112, included TiO₂ % = FeO % (cal) \times 1.112 or = ilmenite mineral fraction (cal)/1.9. These values are concluded from (1):

Then:

$$71.85 \text{ g FeO} + 79.87 \text{ g TiO}_2 = 151.72 \text{ g FeTiO}_3$$

Or:

$$47.36 \% \text{ FeO} + 52.64 \% \text{ TiO}_2 = 100 \% \text{ ilmenite}$$

In ilmenite we have: TiO₂/FeO = 1.112, ilmenite/FeO = 2.112, and ilmenite/TiO₂ = 1.9. The calculated Fe₂O₃ % of the analyzed spot will be considered as hematite mineral

component %. The MgO % and MnO % contents of the analyzed spot are used for the calculation of the corresponding contents of individual geikielite (MgTiO₃) and pyrophanite (MnTiO₃) mineral components and also their corresponding individual contained TiO₂ %. The calculation of these values depends on the following equations:

Then:

$$40.31 \text{ g MgO} + 79.87 \text{ g TiO}_2 = 120.18 \text{ g geikielite}$$

Or:

$$33.54 \% \text{ MgO} + 66.46 \% \text{ TiO}_2 = 100 \% \text{ geikielite}$$

Then:

$$70.94 \text{ g MnO} + 79.87 \text{ g TiO}_2 = 150.81 \text{ g pyrophanite}$$

Or:

$$47.04 \% \text{ MnO} + 52.96 \% \text{ TiO}_2 = 100 \% \text{ pyrophanite}$$

Hence, in geikielite, TiO₂/MgO = 1.982, geikielite/MgO = 2.982, and geikielite/TiO₂ = 1.51. In pyrophanite, TiO₂/MnO = 1.126, pyrophanite/MnO = 2.126, and pyrophanite/TiO₂ = 1.89.

The remaining individual TiO₂ % (rutile) component can be calculated by subtracting the sum percentages of TiO₂ contained in the calculated ilmenite, geikielite, and pyrophanite individual mineral components from the bulk analyzed TiO₂ % of the analyzed spot. All the calculated contents of the mineral fractions inside the analyzed spot are added to obtain the total sums. If the calculated individual TiO₂ % has a negative value, the contained TiO₂ in the calculated three mineral fractions is higher than the actual bulk analyzed TiO₂ % of the spot. There are four reasons for this: At first, there are other analyzed oxides that must be considered and added with the analyzed TiO₂ % of the spot to be included within the bulk TiO₂ content of the spot. Also, there are some values of the analyzed oxides FeO, MgO, MnO, not included in their corresponding calculated mineral components. The third reason is that some analyzed oxides are impurities such as SiO₂ CaO, which cannot be neglected and the other analyzed oxides must be corrected. The fourth reason is that it is obvious that the content of individual TiO₂ content of the analyzed spot is negligible. However, if the obtained individual TiO₂ % values are equal to -0.01 down to -0.05 or even -0.1, these values may be due to the rounding to two decimal places for most of the treated oxides. These negative values can be neglected and the content of individual TiO₂ is considered as zero. However, in the case of obtained negative values, the second method of calculation is recommended.

2) The Second Method (M2)

In this method (M2), we act directly to the analyzed oxides of the detected spot, and the adopted ilmenite Excel formula is not applied. The contents of ilmenite mineral fractions are calculated directly from the analyzed TiO₂ % and not from the calculated FeO %. This method of calculation includes the following steps:

The calculation of the geikielite mineral content from the analyzed MgO % of the spot, the calculation of pyrophanite mineral content from the analyzed MnO % of the spot, and the calculation of the remaining TiO₂ % (R TiO₂) is conducted as follows:

$$R \text{ TiO}_2 = \text{the analyzed TiO}_2 \text{ of the spot} - [\text{TiO}_2 \text{ contained in geikielite} + \text{TiO}_2 \text{ contained in pyrophanite}] \quad (4)$$

Then, $R \text{ TiO}_2 = \text{TiO}_2 \text{ of the spot} - [\text{MgO \%} \times 1.982 + \text{MnO \%} \times 1.126]$. If the result of the last equation equals to zero or a negligible negative value, then there is no ilmenite in the analyzed spot.

In the case of the presence of excess TiO₂, then:

$$\text{Ilmenite mineral fraction} = R \text{ TiO}_2 \times 1.9 \quad (5)$$

The FeO % contained in the calculated ilmenite is calculated as follows:

$$\text{FeO \% contained in ilmenite} = \text{calculated ilmenite \%} / 2.112 \quad (6)$$

$$R \text{ FeO of the analyzed spot} = \text{the analyzed FeO \% of the spot} - \text{the calculated ilmenite \%} / 2.112 \quad (7)$$

If the analyzed TiO₂ % of the spot is completely entering in the calculated ilmenite fraction, and there is no hematite fraction in the analyzed spot, then the contained FeO % of the calculated ilmenite fraction will be exactly equal to the analyzed one.

If the result of (7) has a positive value, then there is a content of Fe₂O₃ fraction in the analyzed spot, equal to $R \text{ FeO} \times 1.1113$. Both the analyzed contents of Cr₂O₃ and Al₂O₃ of the spot are added with the calculated Fe₂O₃ % and are considered to represent the present hematite fraction of the analyzed spot. The V₂O₃ content is not added to the content of the hematite because it was noticed that V₂O₃ may follow Fe₂O₃ and sometimes TiO₂. Finally, the sum for all the determined mineral fractions was calculated.

3) The Third Method (M3)

This method of calculation is used with analyzed spots composed mainly of ferriferous rutile. It is a modified form of M2, where all the analyzed FeO % is completely considered as representative of the hematite mineral fraction. Both analyzed MgO % and MnO % are used to calculate the corresponding individual mineral fractions of geikielite and pyrophanite respectively. The remaining TiO₂ % after subtracting the TiO₂ contents included within both geikielite and pyrophanite mineral fractions from the bulk analyzed sample of the spot is considered to represent the individual TiO₂ phase in the analyzed spot. In summary, the first method (M1) of calculation is used when there is a definite amount of individual TiO₂ and the adopted ilmenite program must be used in this method to determine the contents of FeO and Fe₂O₃. M2 is used when there is no an individual content of TiO₂ while M3 is used when there is no ilmenite mineral fraction. In the two last methods, the application of the adopted ilmenite program is not required and we act directly with the the original analyses of detected oxides.

IV. RESULTS

A. General

The investigation of the different mineral textures in the obtained ilmenite concentrate and the other obtained magnetic fractions reflects that, except magnetite, the naturally highly concentrated surfacial black sands contain 42.65% different ilmenite mineral varieties and 2.51% other opaques, mainly hematite and chromite, in a total of 45.16%. It also contains 1.85% of completely altered ilmenite varieties, 1.48% magnetic and 0.37% non magnetic highly leucoxenated grains [2]. Various mineral textures were detected under the microscope. Their content percentages and their chemical compositions were calculated and investigated. 48 analyzed spots within 7 grains of homogeneous ilmenite that have Mg content relatively higher than Mn have been investigated. 26 analyzed spots within 5 homogeneous ferriilmenite grains with relatively higher Mg than Mn content were detected. Another 51 analyzed spots contained within 6 grains of homogeneous ilmenite have relatively higher Mn content. 82 other analyzed spots within 7 grains of titanhematite-ferriilmenite exsolved intergrowth and 2 composite grains consisting of 2 parts of titanhematite-ferriilmenite and ferriilmenite-titanhematite exsolved intergrowths. The corresponding different mineral component fractions of the inhomogeneous spots of the last 82 analyzed spots were also calculated. Finally, 17 analyzed spots within 3 grains of partially altered ilmenite into sphene were also investigated. The analyzed oxides of the detected spots include TiO₂, FeO, Fe₂O₃, Cr₂O₃, MnO, MgO, Al₂O₃, V₂O₃, ZnO, SiO₂, and CaO. The ilmenite molecular formula of homogeneous ilmenite spots and various mineral component fractions of the inhomogeneous analyzed spots were calculated.

B. Microscopic Investigation

The homogeneous ilmenite includes grains that appear completely homogeneous under the reflected light microscope. The majority of the grains are elongated to globular, with tabular and rod-shaped not being uncommon (Figures 2-3). Their color is dull grey with distinct brownish tint. Some grains have a characteristic reddish or pinkish brown tint. Others have relatively darker brown colors. The majority of ilmenite grains have strong pleochroism from light to a relatively darker brown color. Under crossed nicols, the homogenous ilmenite grains have strong anisotropism and change from bright, relatively lighter, brown to dull, relatively darker, brown colors. Inner reflections are generally absent. Lamellar twining is sometimes observed where twin lamellae exist in one direction along the rhombohedral 1011 planes. The relative darkness or lightness of brown colors for some of ilmenite grains may be related to the presence of either geikielite (MgTiO₃) or pyrophanite (MnTiO₃) in solid solutions with ilmenite. The ilmenite grains which probably contain geikielite solid solution, show darker color, lower reflectivity, and a reddish brown internal reflection, when compared to normal ilmenite [9]. On the other hand, pyrophanite resembles ilmenite, but shows lower reflectivity, less brown color, less strong bireflectance, anisotropism, and often beautiful reddish internal reflections [22]. Some rare ilmenite grains were found to be composed of several aggregates in the form of more or less idiomorphic grains, with intergranular films of transparent spinel granules.

When rotating the stage of the microscope, the aggregates show irregular boundaries and different positions in relation to their reflection pleochroism. However, the aggregates and their boundaries are more pronounced under the crossed nicols due to the different positions of their distinct anisotropy. This feature may be the result of deformation and recrystallization of the ilmenite during metamorphism accompanied by the migration of spinel to the grain borders [23]. Homogeneous ferriilmenite grains (Figure 2 (8)-(12)), were detected to have paler colors and relatively higher reflectivities with very light brownish tints than the normal ilmenite. The grains are ferromagnetic or strongly paramagnetic with relatively stronger mass-magnetic susceptibilities than the majority of homogenous ilmenite or titanhematite-ferriilmenite exsolved grains. Most of the grains are even lighter than titanomagnetite grains. The majority of homogeneous ferriilmenite grains have weak reflection pleochroism while under crossed nicols they have strong and distinct anisotropism. These ferriilmenite grains are the result of a considerable amount of Fe_2O_3 in the solid solution. Some of the ferromagnetic and strongly paramagnetic ferriilmenite grains were found to contain exsolution bodies of titanhematite with their long axes parallel to each other and to the (0001) direction of ilmenite. However, such exsolutions do not exceed 10 to 15% of the whole intergrowth and are particularly found as fine seriate exsolution lamellae.

The hematite-ilmenite exsolution intergrowth texture is called hemoilmenite where microintergrowths of titanhematite or ilmenohematite are enclosed in the ferric ilmenite [24]. In a considerable number of the titanhematite-ferriilmenite exsolved intergrown grains, most of the oriented titanhematite exsolution bodies are replaced by goethite or limonite while the host ferriilmenite remains unchanged (Figure 4 (1)). Some of the replaced titanhematite exsolution bodies give grey material with distinct anisotropism and obvious bluish tint relatively much lighter under the reflected light. Sometimes brownish yellow internal reflection colors are observed. This material is certainly goethite. Sometimes, some positions in the exsolved titanhematite lamellae seem to be altered to fine grained goethite or to fine aggregates of hydrated iron oxides which are dark in color, nearly isotropic and showing yellow to yellowish brown internal reflections. In this intergrowth, the titanhematite exsolutions show different shapes, sizes, and orientations in the different titanhematite-ferriilmenite grains. In most of them, the exsolution bodies of titanhematite occur in ferriilmenite with their long axes parallel to each other and to the (0001) direction of the ilmenite, showing only one generation of exsolved titanhematite (Figure 4, (2)-(4)). Some show 2 distinct generations of exsolutions. The exsolution bodies of the first generation, relatively coarser, contain fine seriate exsolutions of ferriilmenite parallel to the (0001) direction of titanhematite. The second generation, on the other hand, is relatively finer and generally parallel to the first titanhematite generation bodies and to the (0001) direction of the ferriilmenite. The titanhematite may be also found as banded or rectilinear exsolution intergrowths traversing the whole ilmenite grain. Other grains contain lensoid to elongated broad blades of exsolved intergrowths of titanhematite alternating with broad plates of the host ferriilmenite. In these two last cases, both

titanhematite and ferriilmenite exhibit swarms of oriented fine seriate exsolution bodies (Figure 4, (5)-(6)).

V. DISCUSSION

A. Homogeneous Ilmenite (63%) and Homogeneous Ferriilmenite (2%)

The homogeneous ilmenite represents the major component of the obtained ilmenite concentrate. It was found out that the investigated homogeneous grains contain both Mg and Mn in their chemical composition. Some of these grains have more Mg content than Mn, some the opposite.

1) Homogeneous Ilmenite and Ferriilmenite with more Mg than Mn content

According to [25-26], Mg-ilmenites (picroilmenites) indicate derivation of magmas from subcontinental mantle lithosphere. Authors in [27] explained that higher Mg concentrations are typically associated with more primary ilmenite grains almost 45-55 wt% TiO_2 , while authors in [28] explained that Mg-rich ilmenite is typical of mafic igneous rocks. However, the Nile river drainage has various rock types and hence, various types of ilmenite grains. Some of the investigated homogeneous ilmenite grains contain much more MgO than MnO. The 12 grains of Figure 2 (Table I), are examples of these grains. Grains (1)-(7) are detected in the obtained final ilmenite concentrate. In spot 1 (Figure 2(1), Table I), an inclusion of SiO_2 (18.82%) is associated with ilmenite. Neglecting the SiO_2 content and the recalculation of the analyzed spots by multiplying by $[100/(100-18.82)]$, spot 1 gives a well-defined ilmenite chemical formula (Table I). The other analyzed spots are ilmenite with a slight content of dissolved Fe_2O_3 . Spots 1-12 of grain (2) are ilmenite with definite dissolved Fe_2O_3 . The iron content of spots 13 and 14 is totally ferrous, the sums of cations are 2 and 1.97 respectively. In comparing these 2 spots with the other analyzed spots of the grain, it is obvious that most of their ferric iron content is leached out and some molecular water is included within their pores. The sums of total oxides are 95.4% and 92.6% respectively. These 2 spots contain also considerable amounts of molecular water. Grains (3)-(4) are ilmenite with some mixed Fe_2O_3 content as solid solutions. In the grains (1)-(4), the contents of mixed Fe_2O_3 ranges are 4.73-- 7.60%, 3.88-5.66%, 4.28-6.03%, and 3.85-4.32% respectively. In grain (5), spots 1 and 7 are beside or inside a crack of the grain. Hence, their lower sum of total oxides. In this grain, the Fe_2O_3 content ranges between 2.58 (spot 7) and 7.58 (spot 1). Both spots may contain considerable amounts of molecular water. Grains (6)-(7) are ilmenite with some mixed Fe_2O_3 content ranging between 3.71 and 6.01%. Spot 8 of grain (6) is found to be leached ilmenite. A constructed Excel formula was used for the identification and calculation of the leached ilmenite.

2) Homogeneous Ferriilmenite

Ferriilmenite grains (8)-(12) of Figure 2 (Table I) were detected within the ferromagnetic fraction associated with magnetite and titanomagnetite grains and contain relatively higher contents of mixed Fe_2O_3 , which are 22.47-22.81%, 7.33-8.72%, 21.01-22.05%, 14.52-15.25%, and 9.4-14.64% respectively.

Fig. 2. BSE images of the homogeneous ilmenite grains: (1)-(7), have more Mg than Mn content. (8)-(12) are homogeneous ferriilmenite grains.

However, MgO and Al₂O₃ contents are also relatively higher in these grains, ranging between 3.38-3.57 % and 0.2-0.25% in grain (8), 3.81-4.05% and 0.21-0.28% in grain (9), 4.38-4.65% and 0.35-0.40% in grain (10), 5.41-5.56% and 0.39-0.46% in grain (11), and 4.57-6.6% and 0.23-0.65% in grain (12) respectively. Also, the Cr₂O₃ content in these grains is relatively higher, especially in grain (11). It ranges between 1.04 and 1.21% in grain (11), while it ranges between 0 and 0.31% in the other 4 grains. Comparing these grains with the last 7 grains ensures that Al₂O₃ follows Fe₂O₃. The content of Al₂O₃ increases as the contents of Fe₂O₃ increases.

3) Homogeneous Ilmenite with More Mn than Mg Content

Mn-rich ilmenite tends to be abundant in peraluminous granite and metapelite, and is thus characteristic of ilmenite with abundant unoriented quartz inclusions [28]. The values for MnO in ilmenite from Jacupiranga Cabonate, Brazil, range between 2.2 and 3.5% with one sample having 7.9% [29-30]. The MnO content of ilmenite from Chhatrapur coast, Odisha, India, varies from 0.125 to 0.579% while the MgO content varies from 0.069 to 1.357%, indicating a solid solution series between ilmenite, pyrophanite, and geikielite [31]. In coexisting magnetite and ilmenite, MgO and MnO partition preferentially into ilmenite. MgO shows a regular pattern of distribution between them, whereas MnO is distributed irregularly [32].

Another type of ilmenite grains in the final obtained ilmenite concentrate is detected where the Mn content is larger than the MgO. These grains are shown in Figure 3, Table II as follows: in grain (1), most of the analyzed iron content is ferrous iron. Spot 1 is in a crack while spot 10 is leached ilmenite. Grain (2) is ilmenite with minor Fe₂O₃ content in spots 1-3. The iron content of spots 3-5 is mainly ferrous iron.

In grain (3), the analyzed iron content of all the analyzed spots is ferrous iron. In grain (4), ilmenite is mixed with 3.03-4.96% Fe₂O₃ content. In grains (5) and (6), the content of MnO is relatively higher and ranges between 2.67 and 3.46% for (5) and 4.52 and 6.09% for (6). Their Cr₂O₃ content is negligible. The content of mixed Fe₂O₃ in these 2 grains is relatively higher, ranging between 14.9 and 18.01% in (5) and 3.41 and 10.22% in (6). The content of Al₂O₃ is not positively correlated with the content of Fe₂O₃ in the analyzed spots. Also, in grain (6), the comparison of spots 1, 3, 5, and 9 with the others reveals that ilmenite is altered in these 4 spots into individual phases of TiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ where some of the Fe₂O₃ content is leached out. In spot 1, some of the SiO₂ content is mixed where a relatively lower content of TiO₂ wt% is recorded. Due to the presence of these 4 spots on the edge of the grain, the process of alteration is relatively higher. Hence, there are appreciable contents of molecular water inside them (Table II).

B. Hematite-Ilmenite Exsolution Intergrowth (21.4%)

The most common exsolved intergrowth type in the examined ilmenite grains is the titanhematite-ferriilmenite exsolved intergrowths. The same was also reported in [8, 33]. Similar textures of titanhematite exsolution bodies were found in [34], showing that in the majority of grains, the hematite occupies about 20 to 25% of the intergrowth. It was also shown that very coarse intergrowths are occasionally observed where the hematite occupies about 30-35% of the whole intergrowth. On the other hand, the percentage of the titanhematite intergrowths in ilmenite does not exceed 5% in some mineral deposits of Um Rus Area, Eastern Desert, Egypt [35].

Fig. 3. BSE images of homogeneous ilmenite grains with more Mn than Mg content.

TABLE I. MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND CORRESPONDING MOLECULAR FORMULAE OF THE ANALYZED SPOTS FOR HOMOGENEOUS ILMENITE GRAINS WITH A RELATIVELY HIGHER Mg CONTENT, GRAINS (1)-(7) AND FERRILMENITE GRAINS (8)-(12) OF FIGURE 2

Table with 25 columns: Grains, Spots, SiO2, MgO, MnO, CaO, ZnO, FeO, Al2O3, V2O5, Cr2O3, TiO2, Total, SiO2, MgO, MnO, CaO, ZnO, FeO, Fe2O3, Al2O3, V2O5, Cr2O3, TiO2, Total, Fe ferrous, Fe ferric, Other cations, Ti, O. Rows are grouped by figure (Fig. 2) and spot number (1-12).

Grains	Spots	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Fe ferrous	Fe ferric	Other cations	Ti	O
Fig. 2 (10)	1	0.00	4.38	0.35	0.00	0.00	49.44	0.18	0.47	0.19	42.85	97.86	0.00	4.38	0.35	0.00	0.00	30.39	21.16	0.18	0.47	0.19	42.85	99.97	0.63	0.39	0.20	0.79	3
	2	0.00	4.51	0.37	0.01	0.04	49.76	0.26	0.50	0.11	42.88	98.43	0.00	4.51	0.37	0.01	0.04	30.13	21.81	0.26	0.50	0.11	42.88	100.61	0.62	0.40	0.21	0.79	3
	3	0.00	4.62	0.37	0.00	0.00	49.45	0.20	0.49	0.17	42.92	98.23	0.00	4.62	0.37	0.00	0.00	30.00	21.62	0.20	0.49	0.17	42.92	100.39	0.61	0.40	0.21	0.79	3
	4	0.00	4.65	0.37	0.00	0.12	49.71	0.22	0.47	0.17	42.94	98.64	0.00	4.65	0.37	0.00	0.12	29.86	22.05	0.22	0.47	0.17	42.94	100.85	0.61	0.40	0.21	0.79	3
	5	0.00	4.45	0.40	0.01	0.00	49.54	0.19	0.51	0.17	43.01	98.27	0.00	4.45	0.40	0.01	0.00	30.35	21.32	0.19	0.51	0.17	43.01	100.40	0.62	0.39	0.20	0.79	3
	6	0.00	4.46	0.35	0.01	0.20	49.21	0.21	0.46	0.15	43.13	98.18	0.00	4.46	0.35	0.01	0.20	30.30	21.01	0.21	0.46	0.15	43.13	100.28	0.62	0.39	0.21	0.80	3
Fig. 2 (11)	1	0.00	5.46	0.34	0.01	0.13	43.43	0.44	0.60	1.08	44.65	96.13	0.00	5.46	0.34	0.01	0.13	29.97	14.95	0.44	0.60	1.08	44.65	97.62	0.62	0.28	0.27	0.84	3
	2	0.00	5.41	0.37	0.00	0.01	43.40	0.45	0.59	1.04	44.66	95.92	0.00	5.41	0.37	0.00	0.01	30.14	14.73	0.45	0.59	1.04	44.66	97.39	0.63	0.28	0.27	0.84	3
	3	0.00	5.53	0.41	0.02	0.00	43.66	0.44	0.58	1.05	44.72	96.40	0.00	5.53	0.41	0.02	0.00	29.93	15.25	0.44	0.58	1.05	44.72	97.92	0.62	0.28	0.27	0.84	3
	4	0.00	5.56	0.38	0.02	0.12	42.96	0.46	0.61	1.16	44.82	96.07	0.00	5.56	0.38	0.02	0.12	29.90	14.52	0.46	0.61	1.16	44.82	97.52	0.62	0.27	0.28	0.84	3
	5	0.01	5.45	0.42	0.00	0.13	43.49	0.39	0.50	1.21	44.90	96.50	0.01	5.45	0.42	0.00	0.13	30.15	14.82	0.39	0.50	1.21	44.90	97.98	0.63	0.28	0.27	0.84	3
Fig. 2 (12)	1	0.07	4.99	0.44	0.00	0.06	44.07	0.57	0.46	0.26	46.65	97.58	0.07	4.99	0.44	0.00	0.06	32.65	12.68	0.57	0.46	0.26	46.65	98.84	0.67	0.24	0.24	0.87	3
	2	0.00	6.01	0.41	0.01	0.02	44.18	0.41	0.47	0.19	46.86	98.54	0.00	6.01	0.41	0.01	0.02	31.00	14.65	0.41	0.47	0.19	46.86	100.01	0.63	0.27	0.26	0.85	3
	3	0.00	6.60	0.48	0.01	0.15	43.23	0.23	0.48	0.25	47.19	98.62	0.00	6.60	0.48	0.01	0.15	30.06	14.63	0.23	0.48	0.25	47.19	100.08	0.61	0.27	0.28	0.86	3
	4	0.00	4.66	0.42	0.00	0.02	43.83	0.61	0.60	0.24	47.65	98.02	0.00	4.66	0.42	0.00	0.02	34.12	10.79	0.61	0.60	0.24	47.65	99.10	0.70	0.20	0.22	0.88	3
	5	0.10	4.57	0.41	0.02	0.05	42.85	0.65	0.56	0.31	47.69	97.21	0.10	4.57	0.41	0.02	0.05	34.39	9.40	0.65	0.56	0.31	47.69	98.15	0.71	0.18	0.22	0.89	3

However, in studying the Egyptian beach ilmenite of Rosetta and Damietta, the size and amount of the titanhematite exsolutions vary. Sometimes they are coarse, carrying fine exsolutions of ferriilmenite and forming up to 50% of the intergrowth. Occasionally they are too fine to be identified except under high magnification, and form less than 5% of the intergrowth [9]. In the present study, in most of the investigated titanhematite-ferriilmenite exsolution intergrowths, the exsolved titanhematite bodies occupy a minimum of 5% and up to 40% of the whole intergrowth. The majority of the grains exhibiting this intergrowth type have titanhematite exsolution bodies occupying about 10 - 20% of the whole intergrowth.

In some titanhematite-ferriilmenite exsolved intergrown grains, the ferriilmenite component may be altered into rutile and hematite (Figure 4 (5)-(6) and Figure 5 (7)). The alteration of ilmenite to rutile and hematite is generally attributed to oxidation [34]. Authors in [36] demonstrated experimentally that on heating pure ilmenite in air at 730°C, it was completely oxidized into rutile and hematite with a very minor amount of brookite, but on further heating to 900°C, a mixture of rutile and pseudobrookite was formed. Similar textures have been described from highly metamorphosed epidiorite from Assynt [37]. Subgraphic intergrowth of rutile and hematite with a thin outer rim of unaltered homogeneous ilmenite of Abu Ghalaga ilmenite ore was described in [34]

In the investigated samples, the ferriilmenite lamellae were found to be occasionally either partially or completely altered into rutile and hematite. In the concentrate under examination, some minor composite grains were detected, each of them consisting of two components. The first component is titanhematite bodies in ferriilmenite, whereas the second is ferriilmenite in titanhematite (Figure 5 (8)-(9)). Several interpretations have been given to explain the different types of the titanhematite-ferriilmenite exsolution intergrowths [9, 22, 38]. Authors in [36] found that at normal temperatures, ferriilmenites with 18% Fe₂O₃ and titanhematites with 10% TiO₂ in solid solution exist in nature. According to [39], the unmixing of ilmenite and hematite from their solid solution takes place in two stages, the smaller bodies representing a

"generation II" of exsolution formed at lower temperatures whereas the earlier and relatively coarser ones were termed as "generation I". According to [39], a gap in the miscibility range between Fe₂O₃ and FeTiO₃ originates below 600°C, in which the solid solution splits into Fe₂O₃ bearing ilmenite and FeTiO₃ bearing hematite. With further temperature fall, the dissolving power of Fe₂O₃ in FeTiO₃ and of FeTiO₃ in Fe₂O₃ decreases intermittently and second generation exsolution discs are formed.

Fig. 4. BSE images of various detected titanhematites-ferriilmenites exsolved intergrowth grains.

The size of the exsolutions and the composition of the two components of the intergrowth depends on the rate of cooling, the original composition of the solid solution and the presence or absence of foreign oxides, such as MgO, MnO and Al₂O₃ [36]. The irregularity of some exsolution bodies indicates that they have grown in situ, by absorbing exsolution hematite in adjacent ferriilmenite [40]. Many of the larger exsolution lamellae are observed to have coalesced and are frequently irregular. Some of the coarse titanhematite exsolution bodies have a narrow rim of homogeneous ilmenite and seem to have grown in situ by diffusion [34]. In the present work, most of the observations given by [34, 40] were also detected. However, there are some reasons to accept the suggestion of the two generations given by [39] rather than others. These are :

- Some host ferriilmenite grains contain only one generation of the oriented titanhematite exsolution.
- Some host ferriilmenite grains contain fine titanhematite exsolution bodies irregularly distributed without definite orientation.
- The presence of the composite grains is considered the most important factor to accept the suggestion of [39]. In these grains, any individual component, either of the ferriilmenite host or of the titanhematite host, could be itself considered as a first generation of exsolution due to the unmixing of 2 solid solutions, 1 of them composed mainly of ferriilmenite and the other mainly of titanhematite, derived from an original single solution. The relative percentages of the obtained 2 solid solutions are related to the concentrations of their corresponding essential components in the original solid solution, the temperature, and the rate of cooling. At a relatively lower temperature and definite rate of cooling, each individual component (e.g. ferriilmenite) exsolves some or most of the miscible hematite inside it. The same process could also occur for the second individual component, the titanhematite, where some or most of the miscible ilmenites are exsolved with the result of a second generation, in relation to the whole composite grain, of relatively much smaller exsolution bodies in each individual component.

Fig. 5. BSE images of detected titanhematites-ferriilmenites exsolved intergrowth grains. In grain (7), the ferriilmenite component is altered into rutile and hematite. Composite grains (8)-(9) consist of two components, one being ferriilmenite- titanhematite and the other titanhematite-ferriilmenite.

After investigating the results of microprobe analysis of the various detected grains of hematite-ilmenite exsolution intergrowths contained in Figures 4-5, the following remarks can be noted. In Figure 4 (1) (Tables III-IV), spots 1-4 have considerable amounts of FeO oxidized into Fe_2O_3 which is partially leached and the remaining may have changed into goethite and/or hydrated iron oxides (Table III). In these spots, the SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , and CaO contents are relatively higher. These impurity oxides may be phases carrying molecular and/or structural water, or they are associated with the molecular water necessary for the process of oxidation and hydroxylation

of ferrous iron to ferric iron. So, the loaded impurity oxides are precipitated inside fissures. When this process of entering molecular water is repeated, bearing for these impurity oxides into fissures, an enrichment of the 3 impurity oxides occurs. Spots 6-9 and 11 are ferriilmenites where the Fe_2O_3 content ranges between 6.87 and 8.96% while the TiO_2 content ranges between 47.43 and 47.95%. In spots 5, 10, 12, and 13 some of Fe_2O_3 content is lost from the ferriilmenite component adjacent to the altered titanhematite component. Their areas contain voids and molecular and/or structural water. Hence, the Fe_2O_3 content is decreased from 5% in spot 5 to 1.07% in spot 13. On the other hand, the content of TiO_2 is increased from 47.13% in spot 5 to 49.63% in spot 13, while the content of FeO is increased from 38.01% in spot 5 to 40.78% in spot 13.

In grain (2) of Figure 4, spots 1, 2 are titanhematite. The Fe_2O_3 content ranges between 55.47 and 60.21%, the TiO_2 content ranges between 19.22 and 22.4%, and the FeO content ranges between 14.18 and 16.69%. Spots 3-8 are ferriilmenite. The Fe_2O_3 content ranges between 6.09 and 8.54%. When comparing the contents of Al_2O_3 , V_2O_5 , and Cr_2O_3 of spots 1, 2 with those of spots 3-8, it is obvious that these oxides are correlated positively with Fe_2O_3 rather than with TiO_2 . MnO and MgO are correlated positively with FeO and Fe_2O_3 , but both favor FeO rather than Fe_2O_3 . Spots 1-3 of grain (3) of Figure 4 are titanhematite with a maximum value of TiO_2 equal to 30.88%, which corresponds to 26.46% of FeO in spot 3. Spots 4-8 are almost ilmenites. The Fe_2O_3 content in these spots ranges between only 0.02 and 0.54%. When comparing the MgO and MnO contents of spots 1-3 with those of spots 4-8, it is obvious that they follow iron (Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+}), but much more Fe^{2+} than Fe^{3+} . On the other hand, both Cr^{3+} and V^{3+} follow Fe^{3+} more than Fe^{2+} or Ti^{4+} . Spots 1-4 in grain (4), are titanhematite. The maximum value of TiO_2 is 16.34% which is correlated to the 13.71% of FeO. Spots 6-10 are ferriilmenite, with Fe_2O_3 ranging between 0.47 and 2.36%. When comparing the MnO, MgO, and Cr_2O_3 contents of spots 1-4 to spots 5-10, it is notable that MnO and MgO follow Fe^{2+} rather than Fe^{3+} , while Cr_2O_3 follows Fe^{3+} rather than Fe^{2+} . Spot 5 is in a crack, with most Fe_2O_3 being leached out while the SiO_2 content is enriched. In this spot, there is a considerable amount of molecular and/or structural water and all the remaining iron is ferrous iron. Spots 1-3 of grain (5), (Figure 4, Tables III-IV) are titanhematite, containing small bodies of exsolved ilmenite. In these spots, it is obvious that the content of Cr_2O_3 is relatively higher, reflecting the positive correlation between Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 . Spots 4-9 are ferriilmenite and spots 5-9 altered to rutile and hematite with a considerable amount of molecular water, especially spots 6, 7. Spots 10-13 are ferriilmenite. In these spots, MgO and MnO are positively correlated with FeO, while Cr_2O_3 seems to vary inversely with FeO. Cr_2O_3 follows Fe_2O_3 rather than FeO. Comparing the contents of V_2O_5 in these 4 spots with those of the spots 1-4 or 5-9 reflects the positive correlation between V^{3+} with either Fe^{3+} and/or Ti^{4+} rather than Fe^{2+} . Therefore, V_2O_5 content is relatively higher in spots 1-4 which have relatively higher Fe_2O_3 content and also are relatively higher in spots 5-9 which have relatively higher TiO_2 content (Table III). In spots 14 and 15, some of the Fe_2O_3 associated with the ferriilmenite leached, resulting to increased TiO_2 content in these spots.

TABLE II. MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSES AND CORRESPONDING MOLECULAR FORMULAE OF THE ANALYZED SPOTS OF HOMOGENEOUS ILMENITE GRAINS WITH A RELATIVELY HIGHER Mn CONTENT. GRAINS (1)-(6) OF FIGURE 3

Grains	Spots	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Ferrous Fe	Ferric Fe	Other cations	Ti	O
Fig. 3 (1)	1	1.00	0.06	0.40	0.13	0.06	41.84	0.00	0.32	0.04	50.10	93.95	1.00	0.06	0.40	0.13	0.06	41.80	0.00	0.00	0.32	0.04	50.10	93.95	0.94	0.00	0.05	1.01	3
	2	0.00	0.16	0.45	0.01	0.05	45.04	0.00	0.33	0.01	52.19	98.22	0.00	0.16	0.45	0.01	0.05	45.00	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.01	52.19	98.22	0.97	0.00	0.02	1.01	3
	3	0.00	0.15	0.44	0.00	0.10	45.53	0.00	0.31	0.03	52.27	98.83	0.00	0.15	0.44	0.00	0.10	45.53	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.03	52.27	98.83	0.98	0.00	0.02	1.00	3
	4	0.00	0.15	0.45	0.00	0.03	45.20	0.00	0.38	0.04	52.30	98.56	0.00	0.15	0.45	0.00	0.03	45.20	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.04	52.30	98.56	0.97	0.00	0.02	1.01	3
	5	0.00	0.12	0.50	0.02	0.06	45.22	0.00	0.33	0.05	52.31	98.60	0.00	0.12	0.50	0.02	0.06	45.22	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.05	52.31	98.60	0.97	0.00	0.02	1.01	3
	6	0.00	0.16	0.47	0.01	0.06	45.53	0.00	0.44	0.01	52.36	99.04	0.00	0.16	0.47	0.01	0.06	45.53	0.00	0.00	0.44	0.01	52.36	99.04	0.97	0.00	0.03	1.00	3
	7	0.00	0.13	0.48	0.02	0.13	45.65	0.00	0.39	0.02	52.61	99.43	0.00	0.13	0.48	0.02	0.13	45.65	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.02	52.61	99.43	0.97	0.00	0.03	1.00	3
	8	0.00	0.13	0.42	0.00	0.05	45.04	0.00	0.36	0.01	52.66	98.68	0.00	0.13	0.42	0.00	0.05	45.04	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.01	52.66	98.68	0.97	0.00	0.02	1.01	3
	9	0.00	0.14	0.51	0.00	0.04	44.53	0.00	0.39	0.08	52.68	98.37	0.00	0.14	0.51	0.00	0.04	44.53	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.08	52.68	98.37	0.96	0.00	0.03	1.02	3
	10	0.05	0.15	0.36	0.07	0.00	35.24	0.02	0.42	0.03	57.14	93.50																	
Fig. 3 (2)	1	0.00	0.11	0.82	0.03	0.00	46.14	0.00	0.38	0.00	50.80	98.27	0.00	0.11	0.82	0.03	0.00	44.64	1.66	0.00	0.38	0.00	50.80	98.43	0.96	0.03	0.03	0.98	3
	2	0.00	0.06	0.87	0.02	0.04	46.03	0.00	0.39	0.04	50.83	98.28	0.00	0.06	0.87	0.02	0.04	44.67	1.51	0.00	0.39	0.04	50.83	98.43	0.96	0.03	0.03	0.98	3
	3	0.02	0.11	0.94	0.01	0.04	46.28	0.00	0.31	0.03	50.97	98.70	0.02	0.11	0.94	0.01	0.04	44.67	1.79	0.00	0.31	0.03	50.97	98.88	0.95	0.03	0.03	0.98	3
	4	0.00	0.08	0.82	0.00	0.05	45.50	0.00	0.47	0.02	51.11	98.04	0.00	0.08	0.82	0.00	0.05	44.97	0.59	0.00	0.47	0.02	51.11	98.10	0.97	0.01	0.03	0.99	3
	5	0.00	0.08	0.79	0.01	0.00	45.17	0.00	0.35	0.06	51.19	97.66	0.00	0.08	0.79	0.01	0.00	45.09	0.09	0.00	0.35	0.06	51.19	97.66	0.97	0.00	0.03	0.99	3
	6	0.20	0.04	0.87	0.02	0.00	45.54	0.00	0.41	0.02	51.32	98.42	0.20	0.04	0.87	0.02	0.00	45.43	0.12	0.00	0.41	0.02	51.32	98.42	0.97	0.00	0.03	0.99	3
Fig. 3 (3)	1	0.00	0.14	1.28	0.01	0.09	43.55	0.00	0.42	0.00	52.56	98.04	0.00	0.14	1.28	0.01	0.09	43.55	0.00	0.00	0.42	0.00	52.56	98.04	0.93	0.00	0.04	1.02	3
	2	0.00	0.09	1.10	0.01	0.07	44.01	0.00	0.34	0.00	52.66	98.26	0.00	0.09	1.10	0.01	0.07	44.01	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.00	52.66	98.26	0.96	0.00	0.04	1.02	3
	3	0.00	0.09	1.23	0.00	0.08	44.74	0.00	0.32	0.00	52.76	99.23	0.00	0.09	1.23	0.00	0.08	44.74	0.00	0.00	0.32	0.00	52.76	99.23	0.95	0.00	0.04	1.01	3
	4	0.00	0.10	1.15	0.01	0.02	43.57	0.00	0.33	0.02	52.81	98.01	0.00	0.10	1.15	0.01	0.02	43.57	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.02	52.81	98.01	0.93	0.00	0.04	1.02	3
	5	0.00	0.12	1.01	0.00	0.11	43.03	0.00	0.38	0.01	52.85	97.51	0.00	0.12	1.01	0.00	0.11	43.03	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.01	52.85	97.51	0.93	0.00	0.04	1.03	3
	6	0.01	0.11	1.01	0.01	0.05	43.61	0.00	0.36	0.03	52.89	98.08	0.01	0.11	1.01	0.01	0.05	43.61	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.03	52.89	98.08	0.94	0.00	0.04	1.02	3
	7	0.00	0.14	1.26	0.00	0.00	43.17	0.00	0.34	0.00	52.93	97.84	0.00	0.14	1.26	0.00	0.00	43.17	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.00	52.93	97.84	0.94	0.00	0.04	1.03	3
	8	0.00	0.13	1.18	0.00	0.14	43.89	0.00	0.34	0.00	52.96	98.63	0.00	0.13	1.18	0.00	0.14	43.89	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.00	52.96	98.63	0.94	0.00	0.04	1.02	3
	9	0.00	0.14	1.15	0.00	0.17	43.74	0.00	0.38	0.03	52.98	98.60	0.00	0.14	1.15	0.00	0.17	43.74	0.00	0.00	0.38	0.03	52.98	98.60	0.94	0.00	0.04	1.02	3
	10	0.00	0.15	1.14	0.00	0.10	42.88	0.00	0.44	0.03	53.03	97.77	0.00	0.15	1.14	0.00	0.10	42.88	0.00	0.00	0.44	0.03	53.03	97.77	0.93	0.00	0.04	1.03	3
	11	0.00	0.17	1.15	0.01	0.13	43.16	0.00	0.40	0.00	53.10	98.12	0.00	0.17	1.15	0.01	0.13	43.16	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.00	53.10	98.12	0.93	0.00	0.04	1.03	3
	12	0.00	0.15	1.28	0.01	0.03	43.16	0.00	0.36	0.04	53.14	98.18	0.00	0.15	1.28	0.01	0.03	43.16	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.04	53.14	98.18	0.92	0.00	0.04	1.03	3
	13	0.00	0.15	1.26	0.02	0.03	42.91	0.00	0.39	0.00	53.21	97.97	0.00	0.15	1.26	0.02	0.03	42.91	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.00	53.21	97.97	0.93	0.00	0.04	1.03	3
Fig. 3 (4)	1	0.00	0.34	1.60	0.06	0.00	45.75	0.00	0.34	0.01	48.49	96.60	0.00	0.34	1.60	0.06	0.00	41.33	4.91	0.00	0.34	0.01	48.49	97.09	0.90	0.10	0.06	0.95	3
	2	0.00	0.26	1.69	0.07	0.05	45.86	0.00	0.30	0.00	48.79	97.02	0.00	0.26	1.69	0.07	0.05	41.60	4.74	0.00	0.30	0.00	48.79	97.49	0.90	0.09	0.06	0.95	3
	3	0.00	0.39	1.59	0.00	0.00	46.19	0.00	0.34	0.00	49.00	97.51	0.00	0.39	1.59	0.00	0.00	41.78	4.90	0.00	0.34	0.00	49.00	97.99	0.90	0.09	0.06	0.95	3
	4	0.00	0.35	1.70	0.01	0.03	46.18	0.00	0.29	0.00	49.03	97.59	0.00	0.35	1.70	0.01	0.03	41.71	4.96	0.00	0.29	0.00	49.03	98.08	0.90	0.10	0.06	0.95	3
	5	0.00	0.38	1.49	0.00	0.00	46.30	0.00	0.37	0.00	49.13	97.67	0.00	0.38	1.49	0.00	0.00	42.01	4.77	0.00	0.37	0.00	49.13	98.14	0.90	0.09	0.06	0.95	3
	6	0.00	0.36	1.68	0.03	0.05	45.04	0.00	0.36	0.00	49.72	97.23	0.00	0.36	1.68	0.03	0.05	42.31	3.03	0.00	0.36	0.00	49.72	97.53	0.91	0.06	0.06	0.97	3
Fig. 3 (5)	1	0.00	2.44	3.11	0.00	0.12	46.52	0.00	0.28	0.00	42.53	95.00	0.00	2.44	3.11	0.00	0.12	30.66	17.62	0.00	0.28	0.00	42.53	96.76	0.66	0.34	0.18	0.83	3
	2	0.00	2.48	3.27	0.00	0.25	46.50	0.00	0.32	0.00	42.54	95.36	0.00	2.48	3.27	0.00	0.25	30.31	17.98	0.00	0.32	0.00	42.54	97.15	0.65	0.35	0.19	0.82	3
	3	0.00	2.37	3.07	0.00	0.22	45.87	0.00	0.29	0.02	42.57	94.41	0.00	2.37	3.07	0.00	0.22	30.78	16.77	0.00	0.29	0.02	42.57	96.09	0.67	0.33	0.18	0.83	3
	4	0.00	2.37	3.46	0.00	0.06	46.62	0.00	0.33	0.00	42.61	95.45	0.00	2.37	3.46	0.00	0.06	30.56	17.85	0.00	0.33	0.00	42.61	97.23	0.66	0.35	0.18	0.82	3
	5	0.00	2.43	3.12	0.00	0.18	45.97	0.00	0.30	0.05	42.64	94.70	0.00	2.43	3.12														

obvious that most iron is ferric iron. Also, the back scattered electron image of grain (6) reflects that most of titanhematite associated with TiO_2 is leached out leaving voids of various sizes. Spots 1-5 of grain (7), of Figure 5 (Tables III, IV), are titanhematite with TiO_2 content ranging between 11.5 and 23.84%. Comparing the values of FeO with TiO_2 in spots 1-3 with those of spots 4-5 reflects that there is also an individual phase of TiO_2 in spots 4-5 associated with hematite and ilmenite in the titanhematite. Spots 6-8 are ferriilmenite associated with pyrophanite in solid solution. Maximum MnO content (8.58%) occurs in spot 8. Spots 9-10 are rutile and hematite where some of Fe_2O_3 is leached out, especially from spot 10. It is obvious from the investigation of spot 6 of grain (6) of Figure 4 and spot 10 of grain (7) of Figure 5, that the leaching mechanism of Fe_2O_3 is related to the activity of molecular water which seems to be either associated with dissolved silica or the water molecules or hydroxyl anions complexed with silica and each time the associated SiO_2 after losing its water content is precipitated in the cracks or pores and finally enriched (SiO_2 content equals to 9.17% in spot 10 of grain (7)). Some minor composite grains were detected, each of them composed of two parts. The first part is titanhematite exsolution bodies in ferriilmenite and the second part is ferriilmenite exsolution in titanhematite. The contact between the two parts may be curved, irregular, or perfectly straight. In the majority of the composite grains, the part of the exsolved titanhematite in the host ferriilmenite is the essential one, and may represent up to 80% of the composite grain. On the other hand, in a few grains the part of exsolved ferriilmenite in the host titanhematite is the essential one and represents up to 60% of the composite grain. The composite grain (8) of Figure 5 (Tables III, IV) consists of 2 parts, the first part is relatively larger and consists of a ferriilmenite-titanhematite component, while the second part is relatively smaller and consists of a titanhematite-ferriilmenite component. Spots 1-2 are almost similar titanhematites, although they are not in the same part of the grain. Spots 3-5 are ferriilmenite. Also, with the exception of spot 4 in the ferriilmenite-titanhematite part and spots 3-5 in the titanhematite-ferriilmenite part, their chemical composition is almost the same. The result of the comparison of the chemical composition of titanhematite (spots 1, 2) and ferriilmenite (spots 3-5) is that MgO, MnO, and ZnO follow FeO and hence, are mixed with ilmenite rather than with hematite. However, Cr_2O_3 , V_2O_3 , and Al_2O_3 follow Fe^{3+} rather than Fe^{2+} .

Grain (9) of Figure 5 (Tables III, IV), consists of 2 parts. The first part is relatively larger and consists of a ferriilmenite-titanhematite component while the other part consists of a titanhematite-ferriilmenite component. Spots 1-5 are titanhematite inside a major ferriilmenite component. The TiO_2 content ranges between 9.02 and 17.5%. In these spots, the V_2O_3 content is relatively greater, which may reflect that V_2O_3 follows Fe_2O_3 rather than TiO_2 or FeO. Also, the MgO and MnO content of spots 1-5 indicates that they follow FeO rather than Fe_2O_3 . Spots 6-7 are pseudorutile (psr) associated with definite amounts of structural and/or molecular water (Table III). The sums of total analyzed oxides after applying an adopted Excel psr formula for the two spots are 95.13 and 96%. The 2 major oxides, TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 of each spot, are

recalculated by multiplying with 100/95.13 for spot 6 and with 100/96 for spot 7, which gives the following results: 60.38% TiO_2 and 38.31% Fe_2O_3 for spot 6 and 61.01% TiO_2 and 36.9% Fe_2O_3 for spot 7. Spots 8-9 are leached pseudorutile (lpsr) of various phases. In spots 8-9, the alteration mechanism is different than in spots 6-7, where the calculated structural water by the adopted excel program is incorrect and/or some of the analyzed TiO_2 and/or Fe_2O_3 is not included in the lpsr chemical formula. Spots 10-17 are ferriilmenite with some dissolved individual TiO_2 phase especially in the spots 14-17. The MnO and MgO contents in ferriilmenite (spots 10-17) indicate that both oxides follow FeO rather than Fe_2O_3 . Comparing the contents of V_2O_3 and Cr_2O_3 of titanhematite (spots 1-5) and ferriilmenite (spots 10-17), clearly shows that both oxides follow Fe_2O_3 rather than FeO. Comparing the V_2O_3 content in all the analyzed spots of grain (9) reflects that V_2O_3 follows Fe_2O_3 in spots 1-5 and TiO_2 in spots 10-17 (Table III).

Fig. 6. Partially altered ilmenite grain textures: (1) Titanhematite-ferriilmenite intergrowth with most of the oriented exsolved titanhematite replaced by goethite or limonitic material. Reflected light, $\times 100$. (2) Skeletal ilmenite grain with micropores arranged in a crystallographic orientation, indicating leaching out of hematite exsolution lamellae. Reflected light, $\times 100$. (3) Subgraphic intergrowth of titanhematite and ferriilmenite components with isotropic leucogenated material along the periphery of the grain and invading its inner part. Reflected light, $\times 100$. (4) Two partially leucogenated grains: the left grain shows an isotropic leucogenated rim (black) completely surrounding the core of titanhematite-ferriilmenite subgraphic intergrowth. The right grain is an ilmenite grain (light grey) containing considerable leucogenated areas (black) initiated on ilmenite parts originally replaced by sphene (dark grey). Reflected light, $\times 100$.

C. Partially Altered Ilmenite (7.3%)

1) Leached Titanhematite Component (1.5%)

In a considerable number of the titanhematite-ferriilmenite exsolution intergrown grains, the host ferriilmenite contains micropores arranged in a crystallographic orientation pattern indicating the leaching out of hematite exsolution lamellae (Figure 6(1)-(2)). The size and shape of these micropores are related to those of the preexisting replaced hematite. The same texture was detected and the grains were called skeletal ilmenite grains [41] or pitted ilmenite [12]. The tendency of the hematite bodies to be more susceptible to this type of alteration than the ilmenite host is probably due to the fact that the free ferric oxide of hematite can be more easily hydrated than the ferrous oxide combined in the ilmenite structure. However, the original grain sizes may affect their rate of alteration [42].

TABLE III. MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND CORRESPONDING MOLECULAR FORMULAE OF THE ANALYZED SPOTS OF THE TITANHEMATITE-FERRILMENITE GRAINS OF FIGURE 4(1)-(6) AND FIGURE 5(7)-(9)

Grains	Spots	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Ferrous Fe	Ferric Fe	Other cations	Ti	O
Fig. 4 (1)	1	3.09	2.30	0.40	0.12	0.07	42.05	0.59	0.54	0.04	39.59	88.79	3.09	2.30	0.40	0.12	0.07	34.59	8.28	0.59	0.54	0.04	39.59	89.62	0.79	0.17	0.23	0.81	3
	2	3.46	2.20	0.35	0.70	0.22	40.52	0.82	0.60	0.02	41.27	90.15	3.46	2.20	0.35	0.70	0.22	35.90	5.13	0.82	0.60	0.02	41.27	90.66	0.81	0.10	0.26	0.84	3
	3	1.82	2.34	0.43	0.16	0.07	40.89	0.92	0.60	0.00	41.74	88.96	1.82	2.34	0.43	0.16	0.07	34.85	6.71	0.92	0.60	0.00	41.74	89.63	0.80	0.14	0.21	0.86	3
	4	3.69	2.73	0.44	0.08	0.08	39.89	1.33	0.58	0.02	43.73	92.58	3.69	2.73	0.44	0.08	0.08	38.26	1.81	1.33	0.58	0.02	43.73	92.75	0.84	0.04	0.27	0.86	3
	5	0.12	2.33	0.33	0.02	0.02	42.51	0.06	0.51	0.06	47.13	93.09	0.12	2.33	0.33	0.02	0.02	38.01	5.00	0.06	0.51	0.06	47.13	93.58	0.84	0.10	0.12	0.94	3
	6	0.17	2.42	0.40	0.02	0.03	44.27	0.10	0.55	0.03	47.43	95.44	0.17	2.42	0.40	0.02	0.03	38.09	6.87	0.10	0.55	0.03	47.43	96.12	0.82	0.13	0.13	0.92	3
	7	0.00	2.57	0.43	0.03	0.13	45.63	0.06	0.56	0.00	47.51	96.93	0.00	2.57	0.43	0.03	0.13	37.57	8.96	0.06	0.56	0.00	47.51	97.82	0.80	0.17	0.13	0.91	3
	8	0.00	2.54	0.41	0.02	0.09	45.37	0.04	0.62	0.03	47.82	96.93	0.00	2.54	0.41	0.02	0.09	37.98	8.21	0.04	0.62	0.03	47.82	97.75	0.81	0.16	0.12	0.91	3
	9	0.00	2.52	0.38	0.05	0.06	46.01	0.09	0.55	0.00	47.88	97.54	0.00	2.52	0.38	0.05	0.06	38.07	8.82	0.09	0.55	0.00	47.88	98.41	0.80	0.17	0.12	0.91	3
	10	0.15	2.11	0.38	0.02	0.00	41.83	0.05	0.54	0.02	47.89	92.98	0.15	2.11	0.38	0.02	0.00	39.07	3.06	0.05	0.54	0.02	47.89	93.28	0.87	0.06	0.11	0.96	3
	11	0.00	2.52	0.47	0.00	0.07	45.77	0.08	0.60	0.01	47.95	97.49	0.00	2.52	0.47	0.00	0.07	38.10	8.53	0.08	0.60	0.01	47.95	98.34	0.80	0.16	0.12	0.91	3
	12	0.10	2.25	0.37	0.05	0.03	42.26	0.07	0.56	0.00	48.78	94.47	0.10	2.25	0.37	0.05	0.03	39.54	3.03	0.07	0.56	0.00	48.78	94.77	0.87	0.06	0.12	0.96	3
	13	0.16	2.01	0.36	0.06	0.04	41.75	0.07	0.58	0.02	49.63	94.68	0.16	2.01	0.36	0.06	0.04	40.78	1.07	0.07	0.58	0.02	49.63	94.78	0.89	0.02	0.11	0.98	3
Fig. 4 (2)	1	0.02	1.26	0.51	0.00	0.42	58.37	3.15	1.25	1.17	19.22	95.38	0.02	1.26	0.51	0.00	0.42	14.18	60.21	3.15	1.25	1.17	19.22	101.40	0.30	1.13	0.26	0.36	3
	2	0.02	1.51	0.44	0.03	0.35	56.62	2.99	1.18	1.06	22.40	96.59	0.02	1.51	0.44	0.03	0.35	16.69	55.47	2.99	1.18	1.06	22.40	102.13	0.35	1.03	0.25	0.42	3
	3	0.12	4.61	0.49	0.06	0.00	42.27	0.08	0.51	0.08	48.32	96.52	0.12	4.61	0.49	0.06	0.00	34.83	8.27	0.08	0.51	0.08	48.32	97.35	0.73	0.16	0.21	0.91	3
	4	0.20	4.26	0.54	0.09	0.08	43.38	0.12	0.49	0.10	48.66	97.91	0.20	4.26	0.54	0.09	0.08	35.69	8.54	0.12	0.49	0.10	48.66	98.76	0.74	0.16	0.20	0.91	3
	5	0.00	3.66	0.56	0.03	0.06	44.59	0.13	0.50	0.11	50.34	99.99	0.00	3.66	0.56	0.03	0.06	38.11	7.20	0.13	0.50	0.11	50.34	100.71	0.78	0.13	0.17	0.93	3
	6	0.00	3.59	0.61	0.02	0.08	44.09	0.11	0.58	0.15	50.45	99.67	0.00	3.59	0.61	0.02	0.08	38.26	6.47	0.11	0.58	0.15	50.45	100.32	0.79	0.12	0.17	0.93	3
	7	0.00	3.54	0.62	0.03	0.01	44.59	0.14	0.51	0.15	51.24	100.82	0.00	3.54	0.62	0.03	0.01	39.11	6.09	0.14	0.51	0.15	51.24	101.42	0.79	0.11	0.16	0.94	3
	8	0.00	3.74	0.55	0.01	0.00	44.74	0.09	0.56	0.13	51.34	101.15	0.00	3.74	0.55	0.01	0.00	38.96	6.42	0.09	0.56	0.13	51.34	101.79	0.79	0.12	0.17	0.93	3
Fig. 4 (3)	1	0.00	0.08	0.71	0.00	0.00	76.60	0.00	0.47	0.06	19.12	97.04	0.00	0.08	0.71	0.00	0.00	16.34	66.95	0.00	0.47	0.06	19.12	103.73	0.34	1.27	0.04	0.36	3
	2	0.00	0.08	0.71	0.00	0.00	75.41	0.00	0.44	0.07	20.94	97.64	0.00	0.08	0.71	0.00	0.00	17.99	63.79	0.00	0.44	0.07	20.94	104.01	0.38	1.20	0.03	0.39	3
	3	0.00	0.08	1.12	0.00	0.04	65.65	0.00	0.45	0.04	30.88	98.25	0.00	0.08	1.12	0.00	0.04	26.46	43.53	0.00	0.45	0.04	30.88	102.60	0.56	0.82	0.04	0.58	3
	4	0.00	0.12	1.89	0.01	0.00	45.03	0.00	0.35	0.00	51.92	99.31	0.00	0.12	1.89	0.01	0.00	44.56	0.51	0.00	0.35	0.00	51.92	99.36	0.95	0.01	0.05	0.99	3
	5	0.00	0.13	1.66	0.00	0.02	45.49	0.00	0.32	0.00	52.17	99.80	0.00	0.13	1.66	0.00	0.02	45.01	0.54	0.00	0.32	0.00	52.17	99.85	0.95	0.01	0.05	0.99	3
	6	0.00	0.17	1.86	0.01	0.10	44.76	0.00	0.42	0.01	52.20	99.52	0.00	0.17	1.86	0.01	0.10	44.69	0.08	0.00	0.42	0.01	52.20	99.52	0.95	0.00	0.06	0.99	3
	7	0.00	0.15	1.85	0.03	0.00	45.22	0.00	0.39	0.00	52.24	99.88	0.00	0.15	1.85	0.03	0.00	44.81	0.45	0.00	0.39	0.00	52.24	99.92	0.95	0.01	0.05	0.99	3
	8	0.00	0.11	1.73	0.00	0.00	45.20	0.00	0.37	0.01	52.40	99.84	0.00	0.11	1.73	0.00	0.00	45.18	0.02	0.00	0.37	0.01	52.40	99.84	0.95	0.00	0.05	1.00	3
Fig. 4 (4)	1	0.00	0.05	0.32	0.00	0.00	78.78	0.00	0.39	0.12	10.26	89.92	0.00	0.05	0.32	0.00	0.00	8.82	77.72	0.00	0.39	0.12	10.26	97.68	0.20	1.57	0.03	0.21	3
	2	0.00	0.04	0.36	0.02	0.00	78.08	0.00	0.39	0.08	10.62	89.59	0.00	0.04	0.36	0.02	0.00	9.09	76.65	0.00	0.39	0.08	10.62	97.25	0.21	1.56	0.03	0.22	3
	3	0.00	0.06	0.54	0.01	0.00	75.91	0.00	0.36	0.10	13.07	90.04	0.00	0.06	0.54	0.01	0.00	11.10	72.00	0.00	0.36	0.10	13.07	97.24	0.25	1.46	0.03	0.26	3
	4	0.00	0.05	0.85	0.02	0.02	73.16	0.00	0.35	0.08	16.34	90.87	0.00	0.05	0.85	0.02	0.02	13.71	66.06	0.00	0.35	0.08	16.34	97.47	0.31	1.33	0.04	0.33	3
	5	0.88	0.23	3.42	0.07	0.05	39.16	0.00	0.33	0.02	49.60	93.76	0.88	0.23	3.42	0.07	0.05	39.16	0.00	0.33	0.02	49.60	93.76	98.10	0.88	0.00	0.12	1.00	3
	6	0.00	0.28	3.50	0.00	0.00	43.23	0.00	0.34	0.00	50.18	97.53	0.00	0.28	3.50	0.00	0.00	41.10	2.36	0.00	0.34	0.00	50.18	97.76	0.89	0.05	0.09	0.97	3
	7	0.00	0.33	3.57	0.02	0.02	42.83	0.00	0.34	0.03	50.53	97.66	0.00	0.33	3.57	0.02	0.02	41.23	1.77	0.00	0.34	0.03	50.53	97.83	0.89	0.03	0.10	0.98	3
	8	0.00	0.35	3.58	0.04	0.21	42.79	0.00	0.32	0.01	50.54	97.83	0.00	0.35	3.58	0.04	0.21	40.98	2.01	0.00	0.32	0.01	50.54	98.03	0.88	0.04	0.10	0.98	3
	9	0.00	0.32	3.66	0.00	0.06	43.11	0.00	0.28	0.01	50.57	98.01	0.00	0.32	3.66	0.00	0.06	41.16	2.17	0.00	0.28	0.01	50.57	98.23	0.88	0.04	0.10	0.98	3
	10	0.00	0.24	3.69	0.00	0.00	42.39	0.00	0.33	0.07	51.29	98.02	0.00	0.24	3.69	0.00	0.00	41.97	0.47	0.00	0.33	0.07	51.29	98.07	0.90	0.01	0.10	0.99	3
Fig. 4 (5)	1	0.00	0.01	0.44	0.00	0.01	76.67	0.00	0.66	0.51	12.71	91.01	0.00	0.01	0.44	0.00	0.01	10.97	72.99	0.00	0.66	0.51	12.71	98.30	0.24	1.47	0.05	0.25	3
	2	0.00	0.05	0.49	0.01	0.14	76.30	0.00	0.56	0.44	12.73	90.73	0.00	0.05	0.49	0.01	0.14	10.72	72.86	0.00	0.56	0.44	12.73	98.00	0.24	1.47	0.05	0.26	3
	3	0.00	0.01	0.22	0.03	0.00	59.14	0.00	0.69	0.47	19.58	90.12	0.00	0.01	0.22	0.03	0.00	17.35	57.53	0.00	0.69	0.47	19.58	95.87	0.39	1.18	0.04	0.40	3
	4	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.03	0.00	59.61	0.00	0.63	0.48	32.00	92.81	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.03	0.00	28.69	34.36	0.00	0.63	0.48	32.00	96.25	0.64	0.69	0.03	0.64	3
	10	0.09	0.00	0.91	0.11	0.00	45.55	0.00	0.40	0.08	45.55	92.68	0.09	0.00	0.91	0.11	0.00	40.02	6.15	0.00	0.40	0.08</							

Grains	Spots	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Ferrous Fe	Ferric Fe	Other cations	Ti	O
Fig. 5 (7)	1	0.00	0.05	0.45	0.00	0.03	79.16	0.00	0.39	0.05	11.50	91.63	0.00	0.05	0.45	0.00	0.03	9.78	77.08	0.00	0.39	0.05	11.50	99.33	0.22	1.53	0.03	0.23	3
	2	0.00	0.03	0.30	0.00	0.00	80.31	0.00	0.12	0.01	12.83	93.60	0.00	0.03	0.30	0.00	0.00	11.17	76.82	0.00	0.12	0.01	12.83	101.28	0.24	1.50	0.01	0.25	3
	3	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.01	0.07	77.86	0.00	0.40	0.08	13.78	92.56	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.01	0.07	11.95	73.22	0.00	0.40	0.08	13.78	99.87	0.26	1.45	0.03	0.27	3
	4	0.00	0.14	1.88	0.00	0.00	66.77	0.00	0.10	0.04	23.12	92.05	0.00	0.14	1.88	0.00	0.00	18.64	53.48	0.00	0.10	0.04	23.12	97.40	0.41	1.07	0.06	0.46	3
	5	0.00	0.17	1.85	0.02	0.00	66.19	0.00	0.20	0.06	23.84	92.33	0.00	0.17	1.85	0.02	0.00	19.26	52.14	0.00	0.20	0.06	23.84	97.54	0.43	1.04	0.07	0.48	3
	6	0.00	0.10	1.62	0.00	0.00	49.21	0.00	0.29	0.02	46.69	97.94	0.00	0.10	1.62	0.00	0.00	40.18	10.03	0.00	0.29	0.02	46.69	98.94	0.86	0.19	0.05	0.90	3
	7	0.00	0.12	1.50	0.01	0.02	49.51	0.00	0.28	0.02	47.06	98.52	0.00	0.12	1.50	0.01	0.02	40.58	9.92	0.00	0.28	0.02	47.06	99.51	0.86	0.19	0.04	0.90	3
	8	0.00	0.54	8.58	0.01	0.06	38.84	0.00	0.25	0.03	48.79	97.10	0.00	0.54	8.58	0.01	0.06	34.17	5.19	0.00	0.25	0.03	48.79	97.61	0.74	0.10	0.22	0.95	3
Fig. 5 (8)	1	0.00	0.09	0.04	0.02	0.00	78.46	0.13	0.68	0.10	12.41	91.92	0.00	0.09	0.04	0.02	0.00	10.95	75.00	0.13	0.68	0.10	12.41	99.41	0.24	1.49	0.03	0.25	3
	2	0.00	0.12	0.03	0.00	0.00	77.42	0.10	0.73	0.09	12.89	91.38	0.00	0.12	0.03	0.00	0.00	11.36	73.39	0.10	0.73	0.09	12.89	98.71	0.25	1.47	0.03	0.26	3
	3	0.00	0.70	0.37	0.00	0.08	50.94	0.01	0.39	0.03	45.14	97.64	0.00	0.70	0.37	0.00	0.08	38.92	13.35	0.01	0.39	0.03	45.14	98.97	0.83	0.26	0.05	0.87	3
	4	0.00	0.72	0.33	0.00	0.03	49.66	0.00	0.42	0.06	46.67	97.88	0.00	0.72	0.33	0.00	0.03	40.34	10.35	0.00	0.42	0.06	46.67	98.91	0.86	0.20	0.05	0.90	3
	5	0.00	0.74	0.34	0.01	0.00	48.66	0.00	0.40	0.01	47.35	97.51	0.00	0.74	0.34	0.01	0.00	40.91	8.60	0.00	0.40	0.01	47.35	98.37	0.88	0.17	0.05	0.91	3
Fig. 5 (9)	1	0.00	0.03	0.21	0.00	0.00	80.08	0.00	0.59	0.09	9.02	90.03	0.00	0.03	0.21	0.00	0.00	7.84	80.26	0.00	0.59	0.09	9.02	98.05	0.18	1.62	0.03	0.18	3
	2	0.00	0.03	0.14	0.01	0.00	79.79	0.00	0.61	0.05	9.81	90.44	0.00	0.03	0.14	0.01	0.00	8.61	79.08	0.00	0.61	0.05	9.81	98.34	0.19	1.59	0.03	0.20	3
	3	0.00	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.11	79.14	0.00	0.58	0.06	9.98	90.09	0.00	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.11	8.66	78.31	0.00	0.58	0.06	9.98	97.91	0.19	1.58	0.03	0.20	3
	4	0.00	0.05	0.19	0.00	0.00	78.47	0.00	0.51	0.08	11.84	91.14	0.00	0.05	0.19	0.00	0.00	10.37	75.66	0.00	0.51	0.08	11.84	98.70	0.23	1.51	0.03	0.24	3
	5	0.00	0.04	0.82	0.00	0.00	73.87	0.00	0.49	0.00	17.50	92.72	0.00	0.04	0.82	0.00	0.00	14.85	65.58	0.00	0.49	0.00	17.50	99.27	0.33	1.30	0.04	0.35	3
	10	0.00	0.18	1.65	0.02	0.00	51.63	0.00	0.39	0.05	42.63	96.55	0.00	0.18	1.65	0.02	0.00	36.33	17.00	0.00	0.39	0.05	42.63	98.25	0.79	0.33	0.06	0.83	3
	11	0.00	0.17	2.86	0.00	0.02	47.83	0.00	0.32	0.03	45.61	96.84	0.00	0.17	2.86	0.00	0.02	37.82	11.13	0.00	0.32	0.03	45.61	97.95	0.82	0.22	0.08	0.89	3
	12	0.00	0.22	1.86	0.00	0.02	48.59	0.00	0.43	0.03	46.78	97.93	0.00	0.22	1.86	0.00	0.02	39.78	9.79	0.00	0.43	0.03	46.78	98.91	0.85	0.19	0.06	0.90	3
	13	0.00	0.23	1.91	0.00	0.08	46.77	0.00	0.36	0.02	47.61	96.99	0.00	0.23	1.91	0.00	0.08	40.42	7.05	0.00	0.36	0.02	47.61	97.69	0.88	0.14	0.06	0.93	3
	14	0.00	0.19	1.94	0.01	0.10	46.57	0.00	0.40	0.00	48.60	97.81	0.00	0.19	1.94	0.01	0.10	41.32	5.83	0.00	0.40	0.00	48.60	98.39	0.89	0.11	0.06	0.94	3
	15	0.00	0.19	1.83	0.00	0.09	45.95	0.00	0.37	0.03	48.78	97.26	0.00	0.19	1.83	0.00	0.09	41.60	4.83	0.00	0.37	0.03	48.78	97.74	0.90	0.09	0.06	0.95	3
	16	0.00	0.17	1.97	0.00	0.14	45.70	0.00	0.41	0.00	49.38	97.77	0.00	0.17	1.97	0.00	0.14	42.00	4.11	0.00	0.41	0.00	49.38	98.17	0.90	0.08	0.06	0.96	3
	17	0.00	0.17	2.22	0.00	0.00	45.52	0.00	0.31	0.04	49.82	98.08	0.00	0.17	2.22	0.00	0.00	42.26	3.62	0.00	0.31	0.04	49.82	98.44	0.91	0.07	0.06	0.96	3

2) Partially Leucoxenated Ilmenite (4.6%)

Some of ilmenite grains showed patchy intergrowths of altered and unaltered ilmenite. It is likely that some of these grains were originally composed of subgraphic intergrowth of titanhematite and ferriilmenite as the major component. Patches of isotropic leucoxenated material formed along the periphery of the grain and are invading its inner part (Figure 6(3)). The zones of leucoxene invasion seem to have been relatively richer in the titanhematite component. The leucoxenated areas have dark brown colors under the reflected light. Between crossed nicols they have yellow and yellowish red internal reflections, most probably due to microcrystalline rutile. In other grains, a leucoxenated rim is completely surrounding the core of titanhematite-ferriilmenite subgraphic intergrowth (Figure 6(4)). The unaltered component of the grains is only ilmenite, containing parts of preexisting sphene and hence most of the leucoxenated areas seem to have initiated on ilmenite parts which were originally replaced by sphene (Figure 6(4)). We think that in case of partially leucoxenated grains, the unaltered component is preferred to be inhomogeneous ilmenite. Furthermore, such partial leucoxenated zones have occurred at low temperatures similar to those prevailing during weathering, transportation, deposition, and/or post-deposition processes affecting placer deposits. The majority of homogeneous ilmenite grains seem to be more stable and resistant to such partial leucoxylation. The process of ilmenite alteration into different varieties of leucoxene, passing with leached ilmenite, pseudorutile, leached pseudorutile, and even secondary rutile will be explained in another article, so it will not be not explained in detail here.

Fig. 7. BSE images of 3 different partially altered ilmenite grains into sphene.

3) Sphene-Ilmenite Intergrowth (1.2%)

Some ilmenite grains were detected to have altered and been replaced by sphene. Some grains were detected to be of fresh ilmenite cores completely surrounded by a sphene rim (Figure 7).

TABLE IV. CALCULATED MINERAL COMPONENT FRACTIONS INCLUDED WITHIN EACH MICROPROBE ANALYZED SPOT OF THE GRAINS OF FIGURES 4-5

Grains	Spots	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Method	Gek	Pyr	Ilm	H	R	Total
Fig. 4 (1)	1	3.09	2.30	0.40	0.12	0.07	34.59	8.28	0.59	0.54	0.04	39.59	89.62	M2	6.86	0.85	65.74	12.76	0.00	86.21
	2	3.46	2.20	0.35	0.70	0.22	35.90	5.13	0.82	0.60	0.02	41.27	90.66	M2	6.57	0.73	69.40	9.35	0.00	86.06
	3	1.82	2.34	0.43	0.16	0.07	34.85	6.71	0.92	0.60	0.00	41.74	89.63	M2	6.97	0.92	69.61	9.73	0.00	87.23
	4	3.69	2.73	0.44	0.08	0.08	38.26	1.81	1.33	0.58	0.02	43.73	92.75	M2	8.15	0.93	71.89	7.85	0.00	88.82
	5	0.12	2.33	0.33	0.02	0.02	38.01	5.00	0.06	0.51	0.06	47.13	93.58	M2	6.94	0.71	80.10	5.21	0.00	92.96
	6	0.17	2.42	0.40	0.02	0.03	38.09	6.87	0.10	0.55	0.03	47.43	96.12	M2	7.22	0.86	80.17	7.15	0.00	95.39
	7	0.00	2.57	0.43	0.03	0.13	37.57	8.96	0.06	0.56	0.00	47.51	97.82	M1	7.67	0.91	79.35	9.02	0.19	97.14
	8	0.00	2.54	0.41	0.02	0.09	37.98	8.21	0.04	0.62	0.03	47.82	97.75	M1	7.57	0.88	80.21	8.28	0.13	97.06
	9	0.00	2.52	0.38	0.05	0.06	38.07	8.82	0.09	0.55	0.00	47.88	98.41	M1	7.53	0.80	80.41	8.91	0.15	97.79
	10	0.15	2.11	0.38	0.02	0.00	39.07	3.06	0.05	0.54	0.02	47.89	93.28	M2	6.30	0.80	82.25	3.28	0.00	92.62
	11	0.00	2.52	0.47	0.00	0.07	38.10	8.53	0.08	0.60	0.01	47.95	98.34	M1	7.53	1.00	80.46	8.62	0.09	97.70
	12	0.10	2.25	0.37	0.05	0.03	39.54	3.03	0.07	0.56	0.00	48.78	94.77	M2	6.69	0.79	83.46	3.12	0.00	94.07
	13	0.16	2.01	0.36	0.06	0.04	40.78	1.07	0.07	0.58	0.02	49.63	94.78	M2	5.99	0.77	85.99	1.24	0.00	93.99
Fig. 4 (2)	1	0.02	1.26	0.51	0.00	0.42	14.18	60.21	3.15	1.25	1.17	19.22	101.40	M1	3.74	1.09	29.95	64.53	0.40	99.72
	2	0.02	1.51	0.44	0.03	0.35	16.69	55.47	2.99	1.18	1.06	22.40	102.13	M1	4.51	0.94	35.25	59.51	0.37	100.58
	3	0.12	4.61	0.49	0.06	0.00	34.83	8.27	0.08	0.51	0.08	48.32	97.35	M2	13.74	1.04	73.48	8.46	0.00	96.72
	4	0.20	4.26	0.54	0.09	0.08	35.69	8.54	0.12	0.49	0.10	48.66	98.76	M2	12.71	1.14	75.31	8.80	0.00	97.97
	5	0.00	3.66	0.56	0.03	0.06	38.11	7.20	0.13	0.50	0.11	50.34	100.71	M1	10.92	1.19	80.49	7.45	0.12	100.17
	6	0.00	3.59	0.61	0.02	0.08	38.26	6.47	0.11	0.58	0.15	50.45	100.32	M1	10.71	1.29	80.81	6.73	0.13	99.69
	7	0.00	3.54	0.62	0.03	0.01	39.11	6.09	0.14	0.51	0.15	51.24	101.42	M1	10.56	1.31	82.60	6.37	0.07	100.92
	8	0.00	3.74	0.55	0.01	0.00	38.96	6.42	0.09	0.56	0.13	51.34	101.79	M1	11.14	1.17	82.27	6.65	0.04	101.27
Fig. 4 (3)	1	0.00	0.08	0.71	0.00	0.00	16.34	66.95	0.00	0.47	0.06	19.12	103.73	M1	0.22	1.52	34.51	67.01	0.00	103.26
	2	0.00	0.08	0.71	0.00	0.00	17.99	63.79	0.00	0.44	0.07	20.94	104.01	M1	0.23	1.50	37.99	63.86	0.00	103.58
	3	0.00	0.08	1.12	0.00	0.04	26.46	43.53	0.00	0.45	0.04	30.88	102.60	M1	0.23	2.39	55.89	43.57	0.05	102.13
	4	0.00	0.12	1.89	0.01	0.00	44.56	0.51	0.00	0.35	0.00	51.92	99.36	M1	0.35	4.01	94.12	0.51	0.02	99.02
	5	0.00	0.13	1.66	0.00	0.02	45.01	0.54	0.00	0.32	0.00	52.17	99.85	M1	0.38	3.53	95.05	0.54	0.02	99.53
	6	0.00	0.17	1.86	0.01	0.10	44.69	0.08	0.00	0.42	0.01	52.20	99.52	M1	0.50	3.95	94.39	0.09	0.11	99.03
	7	0.00	0.15	1.85	0.03	0.00	44.81	0.45	0.00	0.39	0.00	52.24	99.92	M1	0.44	3.94	94.64	0.45	0.05	99.52
	8	0.00	0.11	1.73	0.00	0.00	45.18	0.02	0.00	0.37	0.01	52.40	99.84	M1	0.34	3.68	95.43	0.03	0.00	99.49
Fig. 4 (4)	1	0.00	0.05	0.32	0.00	0.00	8.82	77.72	0.00	0.39	0.12	10.26	97.68	M1	0.14	0.68	18.63	77.84	0.01	97.29
	2	0.00	0.04	0.36	0.02	0.00	9.09	76.65	0.00	0.39	0.08	10.62	97.25	M1	0.10	0.77	19.21	76.73	0.03	96.84
	3	0.00	0.06	0.54	0.01	0.00	11.10	72.00	0.00	0.36	0.10	13.07	97.24	M1	0.16	1.14	23.45	72.11	0.01	96.88
	4	0.00	0.05	0.85	0.02	0.02	13.71	66.06	0.00	0.35	0.08	16.34	97.47	M1	0.14	1.81	28.95	66.13	0.05	97.08
	5	0.88	0.23	3.42	0.07	0.05	39.20	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.02	49.60	93.48	M1	0.69	7.28	82.79	0.02	1.72	92.50
	6	0.00	0.28	3.50	0.00	0.00	41.10	2.36	0.00	0.34	0.00	50.18	97.76	M1	0.83	7.43	86.80	2.37	0.01	97.45
	7	0.00	0.33	3.57	0.02	0.02	41.23	1.77	0.00	0.34	0.03	50.53	97.83	M1	0.97	7.59	87.07	1.80	0.04	97.48
	8	0.00	0.35	3.58	0.04	0.21	40.98	2.01	0.00	0.32	0.01	50.54	98.03	M1	1.04	7.62	86.55	2.02	0.26	97.49
	9	0.00	0.32	3.66	0.00	0.06	41.16	2.17	0.00	0.28	0.01	50.57	98.23	M1	0.96	7.79	86.92	2.18	0.06	97.91
	10	0.00	0.24	3.69	0.00	0.00	41.97	0.47	0.00	0.33	0.07	51.29	98.07	M1	0.73	7.85	88.63	0.54	0.01	97.76
Fig. 4 (5)	1	0.00	0.01	0.44	0.00	0.01	10.97	72.99	0.00	0.66	0.51	12.71	98.30	M1	0.02	0.92	23.17	73.50	0.01	97.63
	2	0.00	0.05	0.49	0.01	0.14	10.72	72.86	0.00	0.56	0.44	12.73	98.00	M1	0.15	1.05	22.64	73.30	0.15	97.30
	3	0.00	0.01	0.22	0.03	0.00	17.35	57.53	0.00	0.69	0.47	19.58	95.87	M1	0.01	0.47	36.64	58.00	0.04	95.17
	4	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.03	0.00	28.69	34.36	0.00	0.63	0.48	32.00	96.25	M1	0.00	0.13	60.59	34.83	0.05	95.59
	5	0.03	0.05	0.15	0.06	0.05	29.98	0.00	0.00	0.67	0.29	65.39	96.68	M3	0.15	0.32	0.00	33.61	65.12	99.20
	6	0.00	0.06	0.18	0.03	0.04	20.14	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.11	72.53	93.69	M3	0.19	0.39	0.00	22.49	72.20	95.27
	7	0.00	0.02	0.15	0.01	0.00	18.16	0.00	0.00	0.69	0.14	74.65	93.82	M3	0.04	0.32	0.00	20.32	74.45	95.14
	8	0.02	0.02	0.19	0.02	0.00	18.20	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.02	76.26	95.32	M3	0.05	0.40	0.00	20.25	76.01	96.71
	9	0.00	0.04	0.09	0.01	0.00	5.37	0.00	0.00	0.87	0.09	93.43	99.89	M3	0.11	0.18	0.00	6.05	93.27	99.61
	10	0.09	0.00	0.91	0.11	0.00	40.02	6.15	0.00	0.40	0.08	45.55	93.29	M1	0.00	1.93	84.51	6.22	0.04	92.71
	11	0.05	0.11	6.22	0.06	0.11	35.04	9.73	0.00	0.34	0.08	46.29	98.02	M1	0.33	13.21	74.01	9.81	0.13	97.49
	12	0.00	0.48	3.50	0.11	0.03	38.28	7.92	0.00	0.34	0.05	47.63	98.34	M1	1.43	7.44	80.86	7.97	0.19	97.89
	13	0.00	0.47	4.19	0.00	0.08	38.27	6.49	0.00	0.41	0.05	48.27	98.23	M1	1.40	8.90	80.83	6.54	0.09	97.76
	14	0.00	0.07	0.35	0.01	0.00	41.90	0.00	0.00	0.47	0.11	48.99	91.67	M1	0.20	0.74	88.49	0.11	1.89	91.44
	15	0.02	0.34	2.20	0.05	0.03	38.30	0.00	0.00	0.46	0.16	51.28	92.33	M1	1.00	4.67	80.89	0.16	5.57	92.29
Fig. 4 (6)	1	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.03	5.18	94.61	0.00	0.15	0.03	5.81	105.83	M1	0.01	0.04	10.93	94.64	0.04	105.65
	2	0.03	0.00	0.26	0.01	0.06	6.81	87.84	0.00	0.13	0.07	7.90	103.10	M1	0.01	0.54	14.38	87.90	0.04	102.88
	3	0.00	0.03	0.42	0.01	0.03	11.17	76.69	0.00	0.39	0.06	12.99	101.78	M1	0.08	0.89	23.60	76.74	0.05	101.36
	4	0.00	0.03	0.57	0.00	0.00	11.65	74.89	0.00	0.43	0.12	13.66	101.34	M1	0.10	1.21	24.61	75.01	0.00	100.92
	5	0.00	0.01	0.66	0.00	0.07	11.57	75.60	0.00	0.49	0.10	13.69	102.19	M1	0.04	1.40	24.43	75.70	0.07	101.64
	6	3.31	0.17	0.34	0.12	0.07	39.19	5.37	0.02	0.45	0.10	40.11	89.26	M2	0.50	0.72	74.86	9.66	0.00	85.74
	7	0.04	0.09	6.64	0.09	0.01	35.61	7.93	0.00	0.33	0.01	47.33	98.07	M1	0.27	14.11	75.21	7.94	0.10	97.63

Grains	Spots	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Method	Gek	Pyr	Ilm	H	R	Total	
Fig. 4 (6)	8	0.00	0.04	6.36	0.01	0.10	36.98	8.70	0.00	0.37	0.02	48.46	101.04	M1	0.11	13.53	78.10	8.72	0.12	100.58	
	9	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.03	0.00	37.02	0.00	0.00	0.43	0.02	57.60	95.40	M3	0.01	0.65	0.00	41.16	57.25	99.06	
	10	0.00	0.03	0.14	0.02	0.01	22.82	0.00	0.00	0.56	0.04	74.81	98.42	M3	0.08	0.29	0.00	25.41	74.60	100.38	
	11	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.05	12.45	0.00	0.00	0.64	0.01	86.25	99.45	M3	0.07	0.06	0.00	13.85	86.17	100.15	
	12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	5.84	0.00	0.00	0.64	0.00	93.48	99.97	M3	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.49	93.48	99.97	
	13	0.07	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.00	4.37	0.00	0.00	0.67	0.01	93.87	99.04	M3	0.00	0.03	0.00	4.87	93.86	98.76	
Fig. 5 (7)	1	0.00	0.05	0.45	0.00	0.03	9.78	77.08	0.00	0.39	0.05	11.50	99.33	M1	0.16	0.95	20.66	77.13	0.03	98.92	
	2	0.00	0.03	0.30	0.00	0.00	11.17	76.82	0.00	0.12	0.01	12.83	101.28	M1	0.10	0.64	23.59	76.82	0.01	101.16	
	3	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.01	0.07	11.95	73.22	0.00	0.40	0.08	13.78	99.87	M1	0.00	0.77	25.24	73.30	0.09	99.40	
	4	0.00	0.14	1.88	0.00	0.00	18.64	53.48	0.00	0.10	0.04	23.12	97.40	M1	0.43	4.00	39.36	53.52	0.00	97.31	
	5	0.00	0.17	1.85	0.02	0.00	19.26	52.14	0.00	0.20	0.06	23.84	97.54	M1	0.50	3.93	40.68	52.20	0.03	97.33	
	6	0.00	0.10	1.62	0.00	0.00	40.18	10.03	0.00	0.29	0.02	46.69	98.94	M1	0.29	3.44	84.87	10.05	0.01	98.66	
	7	0.00	0.12	1.50	0.01	0.02	40.58	9.92	0.00	0.28	0.02	47.06	99.51	M1	0.35	3.20	85.70	9.94	0.03	99.22	
	8	0.00	0.54	8.58	0.01	0.06	34.17	5.19	0.00	0.25	0.03	48.79	97.61	M1	1.62	18.23	72.17	5.22	0.08	97.33	
	9	0.00	0.06	0.14	0.00	0.07	32.64	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.00	59.82	93.10	M3	0.18	0.30	0.00	36.27	59.54	96.29	
	10	9.17	0.52	0.51	0.21	0.08	10.16	0.00	1.36	0.43	0.00	69.65	92.10	M3	1.54	1.09	0.00	12.65	68.06	83.34	
Fig. 5 (8)	1	0.00	0.09	0.04	0.02	0.00	10.95	75.00	0.13	0.68	0.10	12.41	99.41	M1	0.25	0.09	23.12	75.24	0.03	98.72	
	2	0.00	0.12	0.03	0.00	0.00	11.36	73.39	0.10	0.73	0.09	12.89	98.71	M1	0.35	0.06	23.99	73.59	0.00	97.99	
	3	0.00	0.70	0.37	0.00	0.08	38.92	13.35	0.01	0.39	0.03	45.14	98.97	M1	2.07	0.78	82.21	13.38	0.08	98.53	
	4	0.00	0.72	0.33	0.00	0.03	40.34	10.35	0.00	0.42	0.06	46.67	98.91	M1	2.15	0.70	85.20	10.41	0.03	98.49	
	5	0.00	0.74	0.34	0.01	0.00	40.91	8.60	0.00	0.40	0.01	47.35	98.37	M1	2.22	0.72	86.41	8.62	0.02	97.98	
Fig. 5 (9)	1	0.00	0.03	0.21	0.00	0.00	7.84	80.26	0.00	0.59	0.09	9.02	98.05	M1	0.10	0.44	16.56	80.36	0.01	97.46	
	2	0.00	0.03	0.14	0.01	0.00	8.61	79.08	0.00	0.61	0.05	9.81	98.34	M1	0.10	0.30	18.18	79.13	0.02	97.72	
	3	0.00	0.01	0.19	0.01	0.11	8.66	78.31	0.00	0.58	0.06	9.98	97.91	M1	0.02	0.40	18.29	78.36	0.13	97.20	
	4	0.00	0.05	0.19	0.00	0.00	10.37	75.66	0.00	0.51	0.08	11.84	98.70	M1	0.15	0.41	21.90	75.74	0.00	98.20	
	5	0.00	0.04	0.82	0.00	0.00	14.85	65.58	0.00	0.49	0.00	17.50	99.27	M1	0.10	1.74	31.36	65.58	0.00	98.78	
	6	0.00	0.23	0.17	0.02	0.00	32.80	0.00	0.00	0.45	0.06	57.45	91.18								
	7	0.00	0.21	0.42	0.02	0.06	31.86	0.00	0.00	0.43	0.02	58.55	91.58								
	8	0.00	0.34	0.18	0.03	0.02	21.06	0.00	0.00	0.52	0.01	71.88	94.03								
	9	0.00	0.26	0.16	0.00	0.00	12.39	0.00	0.00	0.62	0.01	82.73	96.16								
	10	0.00	0.18	1.65	0.02	0.00	36.33	17.00	0.00	0.39	0.05	42.63	98.25	M1	0.53	3.50	76.73	17.06	0.03	97.86	
	11	0.00	0.17	2.86	0.00	0.02	37.82	11.13	0.00	0.32	0.03	45.61	97.95	M1	0.50	6.07	79.87	11.15	0.03	97.63	
	12	0.00	0.22	1.86	0.00	0.02	39.78	9.79	0.00	0.43	0.03	46.78	98.91	M1	0.65	3.96	84.02	9.82	0.02	98.48	
	13	0.00	0.23	1.91	0.00	0.08	40.42	7.05	0.00	0.36	0.02	47.61	97.69	M1	0.68	4.05	85.37	7.08	0.09	97.27	
	14	0.00	0.19	1.94	0.01	0.10	41.32	5.83	0.00	0.40	0.00	48.60	98.39	M1	0.55	4.13	87.27	5.83	0.11	97.90	
	15	0.00	0.19	1.83	0.00	0.09	41.60	4.83	0.00	0.37	0.03	48.78	97.74	M1	0.57	3.90	87.86	4.86	0.10	97.29	
	16	0.00	0.17	1.97	0.00	0.14	42.00	4.11	0.00	0.41	0.00	49.38	98.17	M1	0.50	4.19	88.70	4.11	0.14	97.65	
	17	0.00	0.17	2.22	0.00	0.00	42.26	3.62	0.00	0.31	0.04	49.82	98.44	M1	0.52	4.71	89.26	3.66	0.01	98.15	

TABLE V. MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE SPOTS OF SOME DETECTED PARTIALLY ALTERED ILMENITE GRAINS OF FIGURE 7. THE CALCULATED MOLECULAR FORMULAE ARE GIVEN FOR THE SPOTS COMPOSED ESSENTIALLY OF ILMENITE; SPOT 2 OF (1), SPOTS 1, 4 OF (2) AND SPOTS 8-10 OF (3). SPOT 11 OF (3) IS LEACHED ILMENITE WHILE THE OTHER REMAINING SPOTS ARE SPHENE

Grains	Spots	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	Zn	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Ferrous Fe	Ferric Fe	Other cations	Ti	O			
Fig. 7 (1)	1	30.67	0.00	0.12	28.50	0.01	1.26	0.85	0.39	0.00	37.67	99.48																				
	2	0.00	0.06	2.00	0.25	0.00	44.42	0.00	0.58	0.00	51.29	98.61	0.00	0.06	2.00	0.25	0.00	43.68	0.82	0.00	0.58	0.00	51.29	98.69	0.93	0.02	0.06	0.99	3			
Fig. 7 (2)	1	0.00	0.01	0.15	0.05	0.00	81.87	0.00	0.53	0.06	8.34	91.01	0.00	0.01	0.15	0.05	0.00	7.26	82.89	0.00	0.53	0.06	8.34	99.28	0.16	1.65	0.02	0.17	3			
	2	30.73	0.00	0.08	28.58	0.00	0.63	1.01	0.31	0.00	38.03	99.38																				
	3	30.76	0.00	0.15	28.82	0.00	0.99	0.93	0.26	0.04	38.29	100.24																				
	4	0.00	0.20	3.40	0.17	0.00	43.94	0.00	0.43	0.00	50.48	98.63	0.00	0.20	3.40	0.17	0.00	41.39	2.84	0.00	0.43	0.00	50.48	98.91	0.88	0.05	0.10	0.97	3			
Fig. 7 (3)	1	30.11	0.00	0.07	28.41		0.98	0.83		0.23	38.77	99.41																				
	2	30.26	0.00	0.04	28.08		0.94	0.22		0.47	39.33	99.32																				
	3	30.38	0.00	0.00	28.50		0.28	0.62		0.16	39.71	99.65																				
	4	30.46	0.00	0.00	28.75		0.41	0.54		0.13	39.91	100.21																				
	5	30.15	0.00	0.01	28.54		0.54	0.56		0.23	39.93	99.96																				
	6	30.19	0.03	0.00	28.60		0.26	0.46		0.10	40.06	99.70																				
	7	30.28	0.00	0.04	28.74		0.26	0.76		0.09	40.10	100.27																				
	8	0.35	0.17	8.68	0.80		34.89	0.00		0.05	53.10	98.04	0.35	0.17	8.68	0.80	0.00	38.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	53.10	97.68	0.84	0.00	0.22	1.02	3			
	9	0.05	0.19	11.19	1.07		34.40	0.00		0.02	53.34	100.26	0.05	0.19	11.19	1.07	0.00	38.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	53.34	100.19	0.72	0.00	0.27	1.00	3			
	10	0.02	0.20	10.13	0.74		35.72	0.00		0.04	53.54	100.39	0.02	0.20	10.13	0.74	0.00	39.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	53.54	100.29	0.74	0.00	0.24	1.01	3			
	11	0.05	0.19	5.71	0.76		30.88	0.00		0.05	58.44	96.07																				

Furthermore, some grains were found to be partially replaced by sphene where half of the grain is fresh ilmenite and the rest is replaced by sphene. The complete absence of cavities or cracks between ilmenite and sphene indicates that the replacement process took place volume by volume [12]. According to [23], sphene is developed by magmatic resorption or hydrothermal action. Under the reflected light, the sphene is light grey with a reflectivity much lower than that of ilmenite, but somewhat higher than that of the gangue silicate minerals. In fact, its reflectivity is somewhat similar to that of cassiterite or zircon. Under crossed nicols, sphene exhibits an obvious anisotropism. However, its abundant white or slightly greyish white internal reflections may mask it.

Some of the grains composed of ilmenite associated with sphene are detected in Figure 7 (1)-(3). Spots 1 in grain (1), 2-3 in grain (2), and 1-7 in grain (3) are sphene substituting ilmenite (Figure 7, Table V). Spot 11 in grain (3) is leached ilmenite having the chemical composition of Fe^{2+} (0.12%), Fe^{3+} (1.64%), other cations (0.41%), Ti_3 , and O_9 . The losed iron cations are equal to 0.82 and the sum of total oxides is 99.28%. Spot 2 of grain (1) consists of 92.29% ilmenite, 4.25% pyrophanite, 0.80% hematite, 0.30% geikielite, and 0.38% rutile. Spots 1, 4 of grain (2) (Figure 7), are titanhematite-ferrilmenite exsolved intergrowths surrounded by sphene (spots 2-3). Spot 1 is titanhematite having MnO content similar to spot 3 of the sphene. In spot 1, it is obvious that V^{3+} follows Fe^{3+} rather than Fe^{2+} , while Mn^{2+} follows Fe^{2+} rather than Fe^{3+} . The spot is composed of 83% hematite, 15.42% ilmenite, 0.43% pyrophanite, and 0.04% rutile. Spot 4 is ferrilmenite with a relatively higher MnO content (3.4%). The spot consists of 87.44% ilmenite, 7.23% pyrophanite, 2.8% hematite, 0.6% geikielite, and 0.27% rutile.

Spots 8-10 in grain (3) seem to be ilmenite with relatively higher MnO content (Table V). This grain may indicate that both FeO and MnO are replaced by SiO_2 and CaO while the TiO_2 content remains stable to form sphene replacing ilmenite. The comparison of MnO content of spot 11 with the MnO content of spots 8-10 reflects that MnO is lost during the early stages of ilmenite alteration during the leaching of Fe^{3+} . Also, it is detected that the Cr_2O_3 content is relatively much higher in the sphene spots than in ilmenite spots which ensures that Cr_2O_3 does not follow TiO_2 content. These 3 last grains reflect the association of some ilmenite grains within the obtained final ilmenite concentrate with the sphene which may responsible for the increment of the SiO_2 and CaO content of the concentrate. Also, the ilmenite component associated to or replaced by sphene is characteristic with a relatively higher content of pyrophanite and hence MnO.

VI. CONCLUSION

The obtained Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrate from east Rosetta area contains several mineral textures. The homogeneous ilmenite represents 63wt% of the detected ilmenite varieties. Some of the homogeneous ilmenite grains are characterized by more MgO than MnO content, while the opposite occurs in the other grains. The reason for this is the presence of geikielite and pyrophanite solid solutions in different contents. In the homogeneous ilmenite grains the contents of MgO and MnO range between 0.0 and 3.1wt% and

0.4 and 6.1wt% respectively. Some of the detected homogeneous ferrilmenite grains are associated with the bulk ilmenite grains (2wt%). The included dissolved Fe_2O_3 ranges between 7.3 and 22.8wt%. Their MgO, Al_2O_3 , and Cr_2O_3 contents are relatively higher. The detected hematite-ilmenite exsolved intergrowth represents 21.4wt%, and may show 1 or 2 distinct generations of exsolutions.

Some minor composite grains are detected in the concentrate under examination. Each of them consists of two parts, one of them is titanhematite-ferrilmenite and the other ferrilmenite-titanhematite. The Fe_2O_3 contents of the ferrilmenite exsolved intergrowth of the different hematite-ilmenite grains varies and ranges between 0.02 and 17wt%. In some ferrilmenite components, the MnO ranges between 1.5 and 8.6wt%. In the composite ilmenite-hematite grains, the content of both MnO and MgO is relatively lower and can be also distributed homogeneously through the analyzed spots.

In the titanhematite components, the TiO_2 content ranges between 5.8 and 23.8wt%. The TiO_2 content rarely attains relatively greater value, 30.88wt%, where an individual amount of TiO_2 is postulated to occur with the ilmenite component within the titanhematite. The content of the associated MnO is relatively lower, i.e. 0.3-1.9wt%, in comparison with those of the ferrilmenite bodies. It is very low in the titanhematite of the detected composite grains. The solubility of MnO with ilmenite seems to be a relatively greater than with hematite. Both MgO and MnO are positively correlated with FeO rather than Fe_2O_3 . It was also detected that V_2O_3 follows TiO_2 in spots of ferrilmenite and Fe_2O_3 rather than TiO_2 or FeO in spots of titanhematite.

In the investigated hematite-ilmenite exsolved intergrowthed grains, the Cr_2O_3 and Al_2O_3 contents of all the analyzed spots for the 2 exsolved components range between 0 and 1.2wt% and 0 and 3.2wt% respectively. Relatively greater content is present in the titanhematite components. In some titanhematite components, it was detected that the mechanism of leaching Fe_2O_3 is associated with the presence of molecular water which seems to be recycled and the associated SiO_2 and/or Al_2O_3 are enriched and finally precipitated inside spots and cracks. Generally, it was noticed that the presence of molecular water is important in the alteration process of ilmenite or some associated silicate mineral impurities. The partially altered ilmenite grains represent 7.34wt% and contain a relatively higher MnO content in their ilmenite components. The presence of sphene in the obtained ilmenite concentrate may be responsible for the recorded amounts of SiO_2 and CaO and maybe for some of the recorded Cr_2O_3 content.

As a final conclusion it is obvious that a considerable number of ilmenite grains contained in the final obtained high-purity ilmenite concentrate (more than 99wt% ilmenite) have exsolved intergrowthed components containing relatively higher quantities of Fe_2O_3 , Cr_2O_3 , SiO_2 , and CaO. These intergrowths may be responsible for the relatively higher values of the recorded impurity oxides and hence the relatively lower TiO_2 and higher Fe_2O_3 and Cr_2O_3 content, for most of the obtained Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrates. Magnetic separation treatment, grain size differentiation, or both, of the

obtained ilmenite concentrate may improve the marketable specifications of the obtained ilmenite concentrate.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. M. El Shazly, "Classification of Egyptian Mineral Deposits," *Egyptian Journal of Geology*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–20, 1957.
- [2] M. I. Moustafa, "Mineralogy and beneficiation of some economic minerals in the Egyptian black sands," Ph.D. dissertation, Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt, 1999.
- [3] M. I. Moustafa, "Separation of economic minerals and discovery of zinc, lead and mercury minerals in the Egyptian black sands," in *The Third International Conference of the Geology of Africa*, Assiut, Egypt, 2003, pp. 153–171.
- [4] M. I. Moustafa, "Separation of economic minerals and discovery of zinc, lead and mercury minerals in the Egyptian black sands," in *The Fifth International Conference of the Geology of Africa*, Assiut, Egypt, 2007, pp. 63–78.
- [5] A. A. Mahessar *et al.*, "Sediment Transport Dynamics in the Upper Nara Canal Off-taking from Sukkur Barrage of Indus River," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6563–6569, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3924>.
- [6] N. P.H. Padmanabhan, T. Sreenivas, and N. K. Rao, "Processing of Ores of Titanium, Zirconium, Hafnium, Niobium, Tantalum, Molybdenum, Rhenium, and Tungsten: International Trends and the Indian Scene," *High Temperature Materials and Processes*, vol. 9, no. 2–4, pp. 217–248, Jul. 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1515/HTMP.1990.9.2-4.217>.
- [7] R. X. Sinha, *Industrial minerals*. Oxford, UK: Metal Bulletin Books, 1982.
- [8] E. E. El-Hinnawi, "Mineralogical and geochemical studies on Egyptian (U.A.R.) black sands," *Beitrag zur Mineralogie und Petrographie*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 519–532, Nov. 1964, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01104489>.
- [9] N. Z. Boctor, "Mineralogical study of the opaque minerals in Rosetta-Damietta black sands," M.S. thesis, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt, 1966.
- [10] N. M. Hammoud, "Concentration of monazite from Egyptian black sands, employing industrial techniques," M.S. thesis, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt, 1966.
- [11] N. M. S. Hammoud, "A process for recovery of low chromium high grade ilmenite from north Egyptian beach deposits," in *Proceedings, 11th Indust. Mineral Process Conference*, Sardegna, Italy, 1975.
- [12] M. A. Mikhail, "Distribution and sedimentation of ilmenite in black sands, west of Rosetta," M.S. thesis, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt, 1971.
- [13] A. A. Dewedar, "Comparative studies on the heavy minerals in some black sands deposits from Sinai and east Rosetta with contribution to the mineralogy and economics of their garnets," Ph.D. dissertation, El Menoufia University, Shebin El Koum, Egypt, 1997.
- [14] A. A. El-Kammar, A. A. Ragab, and M. I. Moustafa, "Geochemistry of economic heavy minerals from Rosetta black sand of Egypt," *Journal of King Abdulaziz University: Earth Sciences*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 69–97, 2011, <https://doi.org/10.4197/Ear.22-2.4>.
- [15] A.-A. M. Abdel-Karim, S. M. Zaid, M. I. Moustafa, and M. G. Barakat, "Mineralogy, chemistry and radioactivity of the heavy minerals in the black sands, along the northern coast of Egypt," *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, vol. 123, pp. 10–20, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2016.07.005>.
- [16] A.-A. M. Abdel-Karim, M. I. Moustafa, A. H. El-Afandy, and M. G. Barakat, "Mineralogy, Chemical Characteristics and Upgrading of Beach Ilmenite of the Top Meter of Black Sand Deposits of the Kafr Al-Sheikh Governorate, Northern Egypt," *Acta Geologica Sinica - English Edition*, vol. 91, no. 4, pp. 1326–1338, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-6724.13364>.
- [17] M. A. M. Mahmoud, "The Environmental and Radiological Impacts in Abu Ghalaga Ilmenite Mine, South Eastern Desert, Egypt," *International Journal of Mining Science*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 10–19, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.20431/2454-9460.0701002>.
- [18] A. M. Ramadan, M. Farghaly, W. M. Fathy, and M. M. Ahmed, "Leaching and kinetics studies on processing of Abu-Ghalaga ilmenite ore," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 46–53, 2016.
- [19] H. Awad *et al.*, "Mineralogy and Radioactivity Level of the New Occurrence of Ilmenite Bearing Gabbro at Abu Murrat, Northeastern Desert, Egypt," *Romanian Journal of Physics*, vol. 67, Mar. 2022, Art. no. 803.
- [20] M. I. Moustafa, M. A. Tashkandi, and A. M. El-Sherif, "Detecting Mineral Resources and Suggesting a Physical Concentration Flowsheet for Economic Minerals at the Northern Border Region of Saudi Arabia," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8617–8627, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4894>.
- [21] G. T. R. Droop, "A general equation for estimating Fe³⁺ concentrations in ferromagnesian silicates and oxides from microprobe analyses, using stoichiometric criteria," *Mineralogical Magazine*, vol. 51, no. 361, pp. 431–435, Sep. 1987, <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.1987.051.361.10>.
- [22] W. Uytendogaardt and E. A. J. Burke, *Tables for Microscopic Identification of Ore Minerals*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier, 1971.
- [23] V. P. Ramadohr, "Die beziehungen von Fe-Ti-erzen aus magmatischen gesteinen," *Bulletin De La Commission Geologique De Finlande*, no. 173, pp. 1–18, 1956.
- [24] J. R. Balsley and A. F. Buddington, "Iron-titanium oxide minerals, rocks, and aeromagnetic anomalies of the Adirondack area, New York," *Economic Geology*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 777–805, Nov. 1958, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.53.7.777>.
- [25] D. I. Groves, S. E. Ho, N. M. S. Rock, M. E. Barley, and M. T. Muggerridge, "Archean cratons, diamond and platinum: Evidence for coupled long-lived crust-mantle systems," *Geology*, vol. 15, no. 9, pp. 801–805, Sep. 1987, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1987\)15<801:ACDAPE>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1987)15<801:ACDAPE>2.0.CO;2).
- [26] S. J. Barnes and V. Y. Kunilov, "Spinels and Mg Ilmenites from the Noril'sk 1 and Talnakh Intrusions and Other Mafic Rocks of the Siberian Flood Basalt Province," *Economic Geology*, vol. 95, no. 8, pp. 1701–1717, Dec. 2000, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.95.8.1701>.
- [27] M. I. Pownceby, "Alteration and associated impurity element enrichment in detrital ilmenites from the Murray Basin, southeast Australia: a product of multistage alteration," *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 243–258, Mar. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08120090903521705>.
- [28] G. Pe-Piper, D. J. W. Piper, and L. Dolansky, "Alteration of Ilmenite in the Cretaceous Sandstones of Nova Scotia, Southeastern Canada," *Clays and Clay Minerals*, vol. 53, no. 5, pp. 490–510, Oct. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1346/CCMN.2005.0530506>.
- [29] D. P. Svisero and N. Z. Boctor, "Iron-titanium oxide and sulfide minerals in carbonatite from Jacupiranga, Brazil," *Annual report of the director of the geophysical laboratory*, vol. 77, pp. 876–880, 1978.
- [30] R. H. Mitchell, "Manganoan magnesian ilmenite and titanite clinohumite from the Jacupiranga carbonatite, Sao Paulo, Brazil," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 63, no. 5–6, pp. 544–547, Jun. 1978.
- [31] D. S. Rao and D. Sengupta, "Electron Microscopic Studies of Ilmenite from the Chhatrapur Coast, Odisha, India, and Their Implications in Processing," *Journal of Geochemistry*, vol. 2014, Jul. 2014, Art. no. e192639, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/192639>.
- [32] J. C. Gaspar and P. J. Wyllie, "Ilmenite (high Mg,Mn,Nb) in the carbonatites from the Jacupiranga Complex, Brazil," *American Mineralogist*, vol. 68, no. 9–10, pp. 960–971, Oct. 1983.
- [33] E. M. Khairy, M. K. Hussien, F. M. Nakhla, and S. S. Tawil, "Analysis and composition of Egyptian ilmenite ores from Abu Ghalaga and Rosetta," *Journal of Geology, United Arab Republic*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 1964.
- [34] E. Z. Basta and M. A. Takla, "Mineralogy and Origin of Abu Ghalaga Ilmenite Occurrence, Eastern Desert," *Journal of Geology*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 87–124, 1968.

- [35] M. E. Hilmy, M. L. Kabesh, G. S. Saleeb-Roufaiel, and A. M. Bishady, "Investigations on some mineral deposits in Um Rus area, Eastern Desert," *Journal of Geology, United Arab Republic*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 127-134, 1968.
- [36] E. Z. Basta, "New Data on the System Fe₂O₃- FeTiO₃-TiO₂ (Ferri-Ilmenite and Titanom-agnetite)," *Proceeding Egyptian Academic Science*, vol. 14, pp. 1-15, 1959.
- [37] E. F. Stumpfl, "Contribution to the study of ore minerals in some igneous rocks from Assynt," *Mineralogical magazine and journal of the Mineralogical Society*, vol. 32, no. 253, pp. 767-777, Jun. 1961, <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.1961.032.253.03>.
- [38] A. B. Edwards, *Textures of the ore minerals and their significance*. Melbourne, VIC, Australia: Australasian Institute of Mining and Metallurgy, 1947.
- [39] P. Ramdohr, *The Ore Minerals and Their Intergrowths*. Oxford, England: Pergamon Press, 1980.
- [40] N. K. Rao and G. V. U. Rao, "Intergrowths in ilmenite of the beach sands of Kerala," *Mineralogical magazine and journal of the Mineralogical Society*, vol. 35, no. 269, pp. 118-130, Mar. 1965, <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.1965.035.269.14>.
- [41] N. S. Hammoud, "Electrical separation in upgrading Egyptian beach zircon and rutile concentrates," in *XIIIth International Mineral Processing Congress*, Sao Paulo, Brazil, 1977, pp. 100-124.
- [42] E. M. Kara, M. Meghachou, and N. Aboubekr, "Contribution of Particles Size Ranges to Sand Friction," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 497-501, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.361>.

A Spatiotemporal Approach in Detecting and Analyzing Hydro-climatic Change in Northwest Algeria

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Abstract—Understanding climatic behavior, particularly that of semi-arid regions, is essential in order to optimize water resources management and provide protection from climatic risks. Water resources have great socio-economic and environmental importance. This paper focuses on the statistical analysis of the rainfall regime of northwest Algeria and estimates its spatial distribution and temporal variation. To this end, time series and principal component analysis were performed on rainfall series recorded from 1913 to 2009, representing the annual precipitation from thirty meteorological stations to discover patterns and trends in the studied region. Furthermore, the applied spectral analysis of the time series reveals the existence of a period of approximately 97 years at all stations. ArcGIS along with statistical and analytical tools like SPSS and XLSTAT were utilized in this study of the climatic behavior in northwest Algeria.

Keywords—rainfall series; statistics analysis; cartography; spectral analysis; climate variability

I. INTRODUCTION

Learning about climatic behavior in a region improves hydraulic constructions and plays a critical part in the management of water resources in various term lengths [1]. Researchers are trying to answer questions such as if there is there a climate change in the study region and how can the existence of any change be confirmed. In response to these complex questions, a verification of climate change parameters is required, such as the temporal homogeneity of hydro-meteorological time series, in particular stating the presence of trends in the case of annual rainfall series. Numerous studies analyze the variability of precipitation in the Mediterranean Basin and African regions. Linear trends from 1901–2005 show high spatial variability [2]. In comparison to other regions, positive annual precipitation trends were detected in North and South America, the Eurasian continent, and Australia. On the other hand, several observations were made concerning a significant decrease in annual totals in Western Africa, Sahel, the Western Coast of South America, and the

Mediterranean Basin [2]. In the zone of Sahel, there are several indicators of decreasing trend in rainfall series from 1970 to 1990 [3-7]. Consequently, it was observed that alteration in climatic parameters can result in modification of the hydrological cycle which affects the quantity and quality of rainfall and water resources [8]. The drought affected other countries around the Gulf of Guinea in the late '60s [9-11] and altered the rainfall regime of Sahel from 1990 to 2007, increasing it by 10% in comparison with the rainfall regime of the 1970–1989, but it was still lower than the 1950–1989 average (a 20-year wet period (1950-1969) and 20-year dry period (1970-1989)). While the rainfall deficit continued in Western Sahel, Central Sahel gradually recorded more wet years beginning from the late 1990s, but the recovery was considerably limited (1990-2007). As a conclusion, there are numerous differences between Western and Central Sahel regarding the inter-annual variability pattern and the seasonal cycle.

In Mediterranean regions, several researchers have observed a decrease in annual precipitation. Yearly and seasonal precipitation series from 32 stations from 1833 to 1996 were examined in [12]. Declining trends in several yearly series were noticed, which were remarkable, considering the statistics, only in Southern Italy. On a seasonal basis, a declining trend was significant only during spring in Southern Italy and autumn in Northern Italy. In Southern Italy (Calabria), statistical analysis of annual and seasonal precipitation on 109 series with over 50 years of processed data was performed in [13]. The rainfall data segment was first calculated following a pre-whitening technique to lower the autocorrelation of the rainfall series. The study showed a decreasing trend for annual and winter fall rainfall and an increasing trend for summer rainfall. In addition, raised percentages of rainfall series show breaks during the 1960-1970 period. Nonetheless, the analysis on parts of the Mediterranean area shows that the surging progression is a non-considerable reduction in precipitation or a lack of linear trend during the last century or a shorter period [14-16].

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A study of the changes in data series of climate variables at annual and monthly scales in the western part of the French Mediterranean area showed that annual precipitation was too low [17]. Moreover, the study stated that monthly rainfalls were decreasing in June and increasing in November throughout the area. The changes in precipitation of the Balearic Islands (Spain) were studied in [18], considering the daily time series from the 1951-2006 period, confirming a negative trend of annual precipitation. An abrupt decrease in a year's rainfall of 65mm has been identified in the time series around 1980.

In the current study, spatiotemporal analysis of precipitation with a set of statistical methods is used to recognize trends and identify break dates and spatial patterns of precipitation variability of the southern Mediterranean region. For this purpose, a series representing the total annual precipitation of approximately 30 stations in Western Algeria, with the recorded data spreading over a period of 97 years (1913-2009) were examined. The data were analyzed with the use of the Spearman test for the detection of trends, the Mann-Kendall and Pettitt tests for the detection and localization of these trends, spectral analysis to study the nature of the variations, and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to identify regions of consistent precipitation variability [8].

II. STUDY AREA AND PRECIPITATION DATA

The considered region extends between the meridians -2° West and 1° east, and between the North $36^{\circ}33'$ and $33^{\circ}91'$. It includes the catchments of Cheliff (01), Oraneese coast (04), Mactan (11), and Tafna (16) (the numbers in parentheses indicate catchment codes). The area is bordered in the north by the Mediterranean Sea, in the west by the Algerian-Moroccan borders, in the south by high plains, and in the east by the mountainous massif of Ouarsenis.

In Algeria, the climate of the northwest is affected by diverse factors, such as the atmospheric circulation and topography. From December to February, the winds are directed west-northwest. These winds must cross the narrow arm of the sea that distinguishes the study area from Spain, to access northwestern Algeria. Before leaving Spain, the winds discharge part of their moisture on the high peaks of the Sierra Nevada. The air masses do not have enough time to accumulate sufficient water vapor and reach northwestern Algeria relatively dry. During their journey over the Mediterranean Sea, the water-laden easterly winds favor the appearance of heavy precipitation, but this occurs rarely during the winter. Heterogeneity characterizes the area. West Tellian Atlas has a fragmented relief. The high west plains are arid steppes.

In Morocco, the Middle Atlas Rif Ridge protects northwestern Algeria. It exposes a complex topography with a split mountainous character, which increases the areas of shelter while the exposure to sea influences and disturbs flows. Figure 2 shows the location and geographical features of the region. The aforementioned factors contribute to the lowering of the precipitation and consequently to the surface and subsurface water resources.

The atmospheric circulation forms the climate of northwest Algeria and is composed of cells with latitudinal extensions. Among these cells, we can mention the following:

- The Azores High, a zone with permanent high pressure that grows in the middle of the Atlantic, in the region of the Azores Islands. Its propagation to the Maghreb area deflects the meteorological troubles towards Europe.
- The Saharan anticyclone is much more stable than the previous anticyclone from the general circulation point of view.

Irregularity is the most important index of precipitation: spatial and temporal irregularity from one region to another, eminently an inter-annual irregularity. Sometimes, heavy rainfalls cause catastrophic floods. Most of the region has precipitation totals between 200 and 800mm. The southwestern zone is the driest, with the lowest annual rate of 100mm. Another significant aspect is the low number of rainy days (between 14% and 21%).

The rainfall data were provided by the National Agency of Hydraulic Resources (ANRH). The original database comprises daily precipitation records from 30 stations distributed throughout the area, covering various periods with more than 97 years of observations. Analysis of precipitation variability requires long data sets in excellent condition. In addition, analyzing the spatial distribution of a general term in all stations should be chosen carefully. For this reason, we had to balance the length of the periods and the number of included stations. The number of missing data records influences precipitation analysis, so only series with $< 10\%$ missing values were maintained.

Fig. 1. Elevation map of western Algeria with principal mountains (2020).

The quality controls on the selected data sets had two main steps, the first of which was to discover possible errors and suspect precipitation records. In the second step, the data sets were subject to a homogeneity test. Data homogenization helps conceive observations conditionally, so the temporal variations of the adjusted data are only brought in by the climatic processes. The most frequent causes of the lack of homogeneity of the climatic data are the changes in the location of the stations, alterations in screen designs, or environmental changes around the station. The cumulative residuals had to be tested to detect such anomalies in the series. The test allows for a qualitative evaluation at a given significance level of the

homogeneity of the precipitation series concerning the confirmed homogeneous series by comparing the packed residuals of linear regression with an elliptical confidence interval (Bois ellipse). Only series that did not show heterogeneities were selected. Finally, 30 annual precipitation time series passed the above described quality control, which were also acceptably distributed throughout the study area, covering the 1913–2009 time period, and missing less than 10% values (Figure 2). The missing values were interpolated by linear regression based on a series from adjacent stations. Linear regression equations were established separately with complete series of 1 or 4 adjacent stations as independent variables and incomplete series as the dependent variable. The relative error in evaluating the interpolation was obtained by averaging 5 relative errors calculated from 5 observed and predicted values near the missing data. The linear regression equation with the lowest relative error rate was the chosen equation for predicting the missing data. The maximum relative error did not exceed 15%.

III. METHODOLOGY

Several parametric and nonparametric tests were used for trend detection. Parametric trend tests are more cumbersome than nonparametric tests, which require independent and properly distributed data. In contrast, nonparametric tests require only independent data and may allow for outliers. To detect trends in the precipitation time series, we decided to use nonparametric tests that overcome the obstacles of other methods. Mann–Kendall test [19, 20] and Spearman’s test are widely used to detect trends in time series. Their efficiency and power have been proven significant in similar applications [21]. Additionally, when implemented in a sequential version, the Mann-Kendall test positions itself notably well in synchronization with the trend appearance. To reinforce the results of both tests, we performed another nonparametric test, the Pettitt test, which can detect the breakpoint of serial average at any level of significance. It designates a highly precise magnitude of the detected trend. Spectral analysis helps determine the periodicities in the precipitation time series [22]. Afterward, principal component analysis is applied to deduce a spatiotemporal regionalization of the precipitation variability.

Fig. 2. Station positions in the study area.

IV. SPEARMAN’S TEST

Spearman’s test is a rank-based nonparametric statistical test that can be used to detect monotonic trends in a time series [23, 24]. The Spearman test was used to analyze hydro-meteorological trends in [25-27].

For a given sample of data ($X_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N$), the null hypothesis H_0 states that all X_i are independent and identically distributed. The alternative hypothesis is that X_i increases or decreases with i , i.e. there is a trend. The test’s statistics are given as [24]:

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6}{N(N^2-1)} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - i)^2 \quad (1)$$

where y_i is the rank of the i -th observation X_i in a sample of size N .

The diffusion of this statistic is asymptotically correct under the null hypothesis with the mean and variance of (2) and (3):

$$E(r_s) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{var}(r_s) = \frac{1}{N-1} \quad (3)$$

The exceedance probability a_1 is computed using the normal cumulative distribution function with zero mean and variance $\text{var}(r_s)$:

$$a_1 = P(|u| > |u(r_s)|) \quad (4)$$

$$u(r_s) = r_s \sqrt{N-1} \quad (5)$$

Then, the null hypothesis is adopted or not at a significance level of 0 depending on whether $a_1 > a_0$ or $a_1 < a_0$. Significant values of $|r_s|$ show a decreasing or increasing trend.

V. MANN–KENDALL TEST

The Mann–Kendall test is also a rank-based nonparametric test which associates a number n_i to each x_i where x_i is the number of elements, such that $i > j$, and $x_i > x_j$. Mann-Kendall statistic is:

$$t = \sum_{i=1}^N y_i \quad (6)$$

Under the null hypothesis, the statistic is, for a large sample, normally distributed with mean and variance assigned by:

$$E(t) = \frac{N(N-1)}{4} \quad (7)$$

$$E(t) = \frac{N(N-1)}{4} \quad (8)$$

Its reduced form is:

$$U(t) = \frac{t-E(t)}{\sqrt{\text{var}(t)}} \quad (9)$$

The null hypothesis is unacceptable for high values of the reduced statistic. Positive values of $U(t)$ indicate increasing trends, while negative values show decreasing trends. When testing either increasing or decreasing monotonic trends at a significance level, the null hypothesis was rejected for an absolute value of $U(t)$ greater than $U_{1-\alpha/2}$, and $U_{1-\alpha/2}$ is the critical value obtained from the standard normal cumulative distribution tables. In this research, a significance level of 0.05

was applied. The sequential version of the test (in a forward and a backward sense) enables us to identify the start to trend within the data series. Note that $U(t)$ is the forward sequence. The backward sequence $U'(t)$ is studied with the same function but with the opposite data series. In the absence of any trend, the graphical representation of the curves $U(t)$ and $U'(t)$ overlap many times. When the null hypothesis is rejected (i.e. when any of the points in $U(t)$ exceeds the confidence interval ± 1.96), an increasing or decreasing trend is indicated. The test statistic applied in this study allows finding the approximate moment of the appearance of the trend by locating the intersection of the curves $U(t)$ and $U'(t)$. A point of intersection with the confidence interval shows a point of change. The parts of the curves ahead of the confidence lines show the time domain of a sudden change. Detailed descriptions of this nonparametric test can be found in [24].

VI. PETTITT TEST

The Pettitt test is a nonparametric test derived from the Mann–Whitney test [28]. The absence of a break constitutes the null hypothesis. Pettitt defines the variable $U_{t,N}$ as:

$$U_{t,N} = \sum_{i=1}^t \sum_{j=i+1}^N \text{Sgn}(z) \quad (10)$$

$$Z = X_i - X_j \quad (11)$$

where $\text{Sgn}(z) = 1$ if $z > 0$, 0 if $z = 0$ and -1 if $z < 0$.

He suggested testing the null hypothesis by using the statistic K_N defined by the maximum value of $U_{t,N}$ for $t=1, \dots, N-1$. From the rank theory, Pettitt demonstrates that if k indicates a value of the K_N series, under the null hypothesis, the exceedance probability of the k value is given by:

$$\text{Prob}(K_N > k \approx 2 \exp(-6K^2/(N^3 + N^2))) \quad (12)$$

For a type I error α , if the exceedance probability estimated is less than α , the null hypothesis is rejected. The time series demonstrate a trend at time t where the K_N appears.

VII. PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

PCA is a classical factorial procedure. It changes several (possibly) correlated variables (here, the annual precipitation stations) into a (smaller) number of synthetic uncorrelated variables called Principal Components (PCs). Every time series (factor score) is linked to a component. PCA ensures the detection of coherent and recurring modes in the total domain. Rotation methods allow us to improve the interpretability of the results through a linear transformation of the PC. Compared to the non-rotated solution, orthogonal rotations (preserving the correlation between the PCs) are less affected by the domain form, and the instability of the subdomain (the fact that the PCA is performed only on a part of the field leads to different results from those of the PCA of the entire field) and the sampling errors between the PCs. Varimax is the most commonly used rotation [29]. Its goal is to maximize the variance of the factorial weights between each component for a given variable, increasing the segregation between the various PCs.

VIII. SPECTRAL ANALYSIS

The spectral density takes the frequency content of a stochastic process and allows the identification of periodicities. The spectral density function resembles the passage from a temporal mode to a frequency mode by a Fourier modification of the autocorrelation function. The interpretation of the spectral density function, $S(f)$, through the recognition of the different peaks indicating periodic phenomena, leads to the characterization of the system:

$$S(f) = 2[1 + 2 \sum_{k=1}^m D(k)r(k) \cos(2\pi fk)] \quad (13)$$

$$D(k) = \frac{(1 + \cos \frac{k}{m})}{2} \quad (14)$$

where $j=1$ to m , f is the frequency and $D(k)$ ensures that the estimated values $S(f)$ are not biased (Tukey filter). $r(k)$ is the autocorrelation function expressed by:

$$r(k) = \frac{C(k)}{C(0)} \quad (15)$$

$$C(k) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^{n-k} (x_t - \bar{X})(x_{t+k} - \bar{X}) \quad (16)$$

where k is the time lag ($k = 1 \dots m$), n is the length of the time series, x is a single event, \bar{X} is the mean of the events and m is the cutting point. The cutting point is usually determined based on the interval of the analysis and the given circumstances.

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Temporal Analysis

Spearman and Mann–Kendall tests were applied to the data series of annual rainfalls of the 30 selected stations and a significantly decreasing trend was detected at a significance level of 5% for 29 stations (Figure 3). Only the Ghriba station, in the eastern zone of the studied domain, presents a significantly increasing trend at a 5% level. In the region, this station is behind an isolated station.

Fig. 3. Trends in annual total precipitation during 1914–2004 detected by the Mann–Kendall method.

The curves overlap (e.g. Figure 4(a) for Mostaganem 1 station) and the statistical values do not surpass the limits of the critical significance levels, except for the series of Youb that present significant statistical variations, indicating the presence of dry periods. The intersection point between both curves (forward and backward) within the confidence interval demonstrates the change point that compares to the break date.

The graph in Figure 4(b) shows the forward and backward results of the test for the Youb station. The intersection of the two curves marks a change that occurred in 1955. The evident results obtained previously and the location of the break years in different levels of significance is provided by analyzing the whole series with the Pettit Test. Evidently, the results show that an abrupt change (decrease in rainfall) within the time series is observed mainly from the end of the 1940s until the beginning of the 1950s. For 6 stations, the beginning of the trend was detected between 1953 and 1980, 26 stations led to a very significant decreasing trend between 1975 and 1996, and the others appeared to be stationary and confirmed the previous results. Hence, the presence of a rainfall deficit is evident in the eastern zone from the beginning of the 1930s and accentuated during the 1950s and 1970s by its extension to the whole region.

Fig. 4. Mann-Kendall progressive test applied to stations: (a) Mostaganem I, (b) Youb.

Trends can be detected using Pettitt's and Mann-Kendall's tests. However, these tests cannot find more than one break date. This represents the drawback of these tests when investigating rainfall time series, which could have multiple increasing and decreasing trends and/or breaks, specifically for long series. When the number of stations used is not very large, a limit is triggered by the difficulty of interpreting the results on a regional scale. These results suggest that further investigation is needed. We tried to perform spectral density analysis to seek possible periodicities and supplementary PCA was carried out, and regionalization of rainfall variability was performed.

B. Spatiotemporal Rainfall Variability

PCA was applied with the stations as variables and the 97 annual precipitation values. The analysis without and with

rotation underlines that the first 4 components account for most of the total variance (57.8%), as shown in Table I.

TABLE I. EXPLAINED VARIANCES BY THE FOUR FIRST PCs BEFORE AND AFTER ROTATION (F: FACTORS)

	PC (without rotation)				RPC (rotated)			
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F1	F2	F3	F4
Variance %	45.988	6.575	5.250	4.830	29.292	14.156	5.049	14.147
Cumulative variance %	45.988	52.563	57.813	62.643	29.292	43.448	48.496	62.643

The first component accounts for a large part of the variance (45.988%). It describes the inter-annual variability of the precipitation for the whole region (opposing humid and dry years). All stations are correlated positively with this component, considering varying coefficients between 0.85 and 0.2. The greatest coefficients are noted in the deepest region (Figure 5). The objective of the test here is to identify regions with the same variation mode. This geographical consistency can be justified by the large homogeneity of the weather regimes (winter rains and summer drought), but it denotes that a long stretch of years presents large deficits or excesses over the whole region. The observation complies with the result that is found by the nonparametric statistical test of trend detection, as shown above.

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of the first PC (PC1) fields in the area of study (PCA without rotation).

Fig. 6. Temporal factorial scores of PC1 without rotation. The straight line represents the chronicle trend.

The time series of the amplitudes of the first component (Figure 6) highlights wet years (1927, 1933, and 1950) and the succession of dry years that most stations of the region recorded. A decreasing trend with a significant determination

coefficient of 0.2287 is clear starting from the end of 1975 to 2007 (with an absolute minimum in 1981).

The following components (Figure 7) account for smaller proportions of the variance. The second component accounts for only 6.575% of the variance (Table I). It shows opposite amplitudes between parts of the eastern region correlated positively (heavy rainfall) and the west and southwest (areas affected by the Foehn phenomenon. The distance from the sea influences the rainfall flows and, therefore these areas have low rainfall). The third component shows 5.25% of the variance. It represents the southwest and southern parts to the north and center of the study area. The first component accounts for the largest amount of total variance, however, some stations are correlated with this component. We performed a rotation of the factorial axes according to the Varimax method. Varimax orthogonal rotation is the option used to avoid some of the domain shape dependences [29] and to obtain a stable and physically meaningful pattern. The principle is to determine the components that correlate best with the variables [16, 30].

Fig. 7. Spatial distribution of (a) PC2 and (b) PC3 fields in the study area (PCA without rotation).

We retained the first 4 components accounting for 62.643% of the variance. The percentage of variance demonstrated by the eigenvalues is different from the PCA without rotation, with less variance demonstrated by the first component and more variance detailed by the other models. The first component shows the western and central parts of the region (coastal plains). The stations most related to this component are those with elevations between 5 and 215m. The eastern region is known for its low relief and low precipitation (annual rainfall <500mm) with a weakly explained variability (variation coefficients <0.30), see Figure 8(a).

The second component characterizes the eastern part of the study area (Dahra Mountains). This region is well-watered, expressing the simultaneous influence of topography and

atmospheric circulation on rainfall (Figure 8(b)). The third component characterizes the variability of the western part of the study region (Figure 8(c)). The fourth component represents the Tellian Plateau and the high plains in the east, characterized by weak rainfall with a low estimate of 450mm and a very sporadic character due to the shelter effect that reduces the influence of the rainy systems covering the west and northwest (Figure 8(d)).

Fig. 8. Spatial distribution of (a) PC1, (b) PC2, (c) PC3, (d) PC4 fields in the study area (PCA with Varimax rotation).

The time series associated with the first component (Figure 9(a)) reflect an evolution mode identical to the one described by the PCA component without rotation, with some differences like excesses, less accentuated from 1918 to 1953 in contrast with the other three PCs.

C. Spectral Analysis

It should be noted that the semi-arid character of northern Algeria, particularly the western zone, is partly defined by the changes in the general atmospheric circulation. Several studies connect precipitation compression to the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), which impacts the Mediterranean climate [31-36]. The phenomenon is studied quantitatively by the NAO index, which describes a normalized pressure difference between the measurements made in the Azores and Iceland. The index differs from year to year, but also shows a tendency to stagnate in one phase during long intervals [37]. Recently, its sign changed, mainly because of two concurrent trends observed during winter over the last three decades, leading towards a positive phase. These winters are related to higher than usual pressure in the subtropics and lower pressure in the Arctic. Thus, winters are dry and warm in Southern Europe, wet and warm in Northern Europe, and dry and cold in Greenland. On the other hand, during the negative periods of the NAO, winters are usually cold in Northern Europe, wet and humid in Southern Europe, and milder in Greenland. Climate anomalies combined with the NAO have effects on rainfall in North Africa, as demonstrated in [38-42]. The periodicity demonstrated for this part of the study area can also be tuned to the 25 years of the positive observed phase of the NAO (as it was a depiction of the correlation analysis).

Fig. 9. Temporal evolution of the annual NAO index and the factorial scores PC1.

Thus, a study taking into account the observation period of 2005–2011 could reveal that the negative phase of NAO led to increased precipitation. From the middle of 1970's to 2000, the NAO annual index enters a positive phase, and the regional precipitation regime, represented by the first component, presents a decreasing trend. Furthermore, a negative association (Pearson's $r = 0$, Pearson's $r = 0.209$) was found

between the first component and NAO during 1975–2000. The association will be clear on a seasonal scale, as the NAO phenomenon affects winter precipitation.

X. CONCLUSION

The use of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) allowed us to identify 4 significant geographical regions with coherent precipitation variability showing the influence of two regimes in the investigated area: a central zone from the north toward the south of Algeria that is affected by the rainfall deficit and two lateral zones registering no deficits. The reliefs of the analyzed area are essential to the high mountain plateau type, and the noticed phenomena are less dependent on the intrinsic characteristics of the domain. However, this would require a considerable change of the meteorological variations over a wider area, determining the transit corridors of the rainy currents. It precedes the unique effect of the approach of Moroccan Atlas mountain range. The central region of the domain becomes the most targeted for climate change. Nonparametric statistical tests of the annual precipitation series show a weak trend at most of the studied stations in Algeria. The result is in line with the results received in several trend analysis studies. One of the suggested recommendations to describe wet and dry sequences precisely is the analysis of precipitation time scales over the years, which enable the study of possible changes in rainy and dry times.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. A. Mahessar *et al.*, "Rainfall Analysis for Hyderabad and Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6597–6602, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3923>.
- [2] M. Iturbide *et al.*, "An update of IPCC climate reference regions for subcontinental analysis of climate model data: definition and aggregated datasets," *Earth System Science Data*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 2959–2970, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-2959-2020>.
- [3] R. Mahmood, S. Jia, and W. Zhu, "Analysis of climate variability, trends, and prediction in the most active parts of the Lake Chad basin, Africa," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 9, no. 1, Apr. 2019, Art. no. 6317, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-42811-9>.
- [4] S. Taibi, M. Meddi, D. Souag, and G. Mahe, "Evolution et regionalisation des precipitations au nord de l'Algerie (1936–2009)," in *Climate and land surface changes in hydrology*, Gothenburg, Sweden, Jul. 2013, vol. 359, pp. 191–197.
- [5] P. Hubert and J.-P. Carboneil, "Approche statistique de l'aridification de l'Afrique de l'Ouest," *Journal of Hydrology*, vol. 95, no. 1, pp. 165–183, Nov. 1987, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694\(87\)90123-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694(87)90123-5).
- [6] P. Hubert, J. P. Carboneil, and A. Chaouche, "Segmentation des series hydrometeorologiques — application a des series de precipitations et de debits de l'afrique de l'ouest," *Journal of Hydrology*, vol. 110, no. 3, pp. 349–367, Oct. 1989, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694\(89\)90197-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1694(89)90197-2).
- [7] A. Gustard, "Variations spatio-temporelles des regimes pluviometriques et hydrologiques en Afrique centrale du debut du sie`cle a` nos jours," in *FRIEND'97: Regional Hydrology: Concepts and Models for Sustainable Water Resource Management*, Wallingford, OXF, UK: International Association of Hydrological Sciences, 1997, pp. 257–263.
- [8] S. R. Samo, N. Bhatti, A. Saand, M. A. Keerio, and D. K. Bangwar, "Temporal Analysis of Temperature and Precipitation Trends in Shaheed Benazir Abad Sindh, Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2171–2176, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1388>.
- [9] B. Alves, D. B. Angnuureng, P. Morand, and R. Almar, "A review on coastal erosion and flooding risks and best management practices in West Africa: what has been done and should be done," *Journal of*

- Coastal Conservation*, vol. 24, no. 3, Jun. 2020, Art. no. 38, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-020-00755-7>.
- [10] Z. Nouaceur, "La reprise des pluies et la recrudescence des inondations en Afrique de l'Ouest sahelienne," *Physio-Geo. Geographie physique et environnement*, vol. 15, pp. 89–109, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.4000/physio-geo.10966>.
- [11] M. Sidibe, "Past and future hydroclimatic variability over West and Central Africa and their teleconnections," Ph.D. dissertation, Coventry University, Coventry, England, 2019.
- [12] P. Coratza and C. Parenti, "Controlling Factors of Badland Morphological Changes in the Emilia Apennines (Northern Italy)," *Water*, vol. 13, no. 4, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 539, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13040539>.
- [13] A. Greco, D. L. De Luca, and E. Avolio, "Heavy Precipitation Systems in Calabria Region (Southern Italy): High-Resolution Observed Rainfall and Large-Scale Atmospheric Pattern Analysis," *Water*, vol. 12, no. 5, May 2020, Art. no. 1468, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12051468>.
- [14] H. B. Abubakar, S. W. Newete, and M. C. Scholes, "Drought Characterization and Trend Detection Using the Reconnaissance Drought Index for Setsoto Municipality of the Free State Province of South Africa and the Impact on Maize Yield," *Water*, vol. 12, no. 11, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 2993, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12112993>.
- [15] Y. Ban, P. Zhang, A. Nascetti, A. R. Bevington, and M. A. Wulder, "Near Real-Time Wildfire Progression Monitoring with Sentinel-1 SAR Time Series and Deep Learning," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 10, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 1322, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-56967-x>.
- [16] A. Douguedroit and C. Norrant, "Annual and Seasonal Century Scale Trends of the Precipitation in the Mediterranean Area During the Twentieth Century," in *Mediterranean Climate: Variability and Trends*, H.-J. Bolle, Ed. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2003, pp. 159–163.
- [17] A. J. O'Donnell, M. Renton, K. J. Allen, and P. F. Grierson, "Tree growth responses to temporal variation in rainfall differ across a continental-scale climatic gradient," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 16, no. 5, 2021, Art. no. e0249959, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0249959>.
- [18] V. Homar, C. Ramis, R. Romero, and S. Alonso, "Recent trends in temperature and precipitation over the Balearic Islands (Spain)," *Climatic Change*, vol. 98, no. 1, Sep. 2009, Art. no. 199, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-009-9664-5>.
- [19] H. B. Mann, "Nonparametric Tests Against Trend," *Econometrica*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 245–259, 1945, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1907187>.
- [20] M. G. Kendall, *Rank correlation methods*. London, UK: Griffin, 1948.
- [21] V. Totaro, A. Gioia, and V. Iacobellis, "Numerical investigation on the power of parametric and nonparametric tests for trend detection in annual maximum series," *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 473–488, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-24-473-2020>.
- [22] P. Pathak, A. Kalra, S. Ahmad, and M. Bernardez, "Wavelet-Aided Analysis to Estimate Seasonal Variability and Dominant Periodicities in Temperature, Precipitation, and Streamflow in the Midwestern United States," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 30, no. 13, pp. 4649–4665, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-016-1445-0>.
- [23] E. L. Lehmann and H. J. D'Abrera, *Nonparametrics: Statistical methods based on ranks*. Oxford, England: Holden-Day, 1975.
- [24] P. Sneyers, *Sur l'analyse statistique des séries d'observations*. Geneva, Switzerland: OMM, 1990.
- [25] P. J. Pilon, R. Condie, and K. D. Harvey, "Consolidated Frequency Analysis Package, 1985," in *Cfa User Manual for Version 1: Dec Pro Series*, Ottawa, Canada: Environment Canada, Water Resources Branch, 1985.
- [26] A. I. McLeod, K. W. Hipel, and F. Comancho, "Trend Assessment of Water Quality Time Series," *Journal of the American Water Resources Association*, vol. 19, pp. 537–547, Aug. 1983, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-1688.1983.tb02768.x>.
- [27] K. W. Hipel and A. I. McLeod, *Time Series Modelling of Water Resources and Environmental Systems*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier, 1994.
- [28] A. N. Pettitt, "A Non-Parametric Approach to the Change-Point Problem," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series C (Applied Statistics)*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 126–135, 1979, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2346729>.
- [29] M. B. Richman, "Rotation of principal components," *Journal of Climatology*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 293–335, 1986, <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.3370060305>.
- [30] P. Camberlin, "Les précipitations dans la corne orientale de l'Afrique : climatologie, variabilité et connexions avec quelques indicateurs océano-atmosphériques," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Burgundy, Dijon, France, 1994.
- [31] M. Beniston, M. Rebetez, F. Giorgi, and M. R. Marinucci, "An analysis of regional climate change in Switzerland," *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, vol. 49, no. 3, pp. 135–159, Sep. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00865530>.
- [32] I. F. Trigo, T. D. Davies, and G. R. Bigg, "Decline in Mediterranean rainfall caused by weakening of Mediterranean cyclones," *Geophysical Research Letters*, vol. 27, no. 18, pp. 2913–2916, 2000, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2000GL011526>.
- [33] R. M. Trigo *et al.*, "The Impact of North Atlantic Wind and Cyclone Trends on European Precipitation and Significant Wave Height in the Atlantic," *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, vol. 1146, no. 1, pp. 212–234, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1446.014>.
- [34] N. C. Nebout, V. Bout-Roumzeilles, I. Dormoy, and O. Peyron, "Secheresses recurrentes en Mediterranee au cours des derniers 50 000 ans," *Science et changements planétaires / Secheresse*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 210–216, Apr. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1684/sec.2009.0181>.
- [35] A.-E. Briciu and D. Mihaila, "Wavelet analysis of some rivers in SE Europe and selected climate indices," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, vol. 186, no. 10, pp. 6263–6286, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-014-3853-z>.
- [36] C. Sun, J. Li, R. Ding, and Z. Jin, "Cold season Africa–Asia multidecadal teleconnection pattern and its relation to the Atlantic multidecadal variability," *Climate Dynamics*, vol. 48, no. 11, pp. 3903–3918, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-016-3309-y>.
- [37] J. W. Hurrell, "Decadal Trends in the North Atlantic Oscillation: Regional Temperatures and Precipitation," *Science*, vol. 269, no. 5224, pp. 676–679, Aug. 1995, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.269.5224.676>.
- [38] P. J. Lamb, "Chapter 5: West Africa," in *Teleconnections Linking Worldwide Climate Anomalies. Scientific Basis and Societal Impact*, M. H. Glantz, R. W. Katz, and M. Nicholls, Eds. New York, NY, USA: Cambridge University Press, 1991.
- [39] A. Khaldi, "Impacts de la secheresse sur le regime des ecoulements souterrains dans les massifs calcaires de l'Ouest Algerien Monts de Tlemcen - Saïda," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Oran, Oran, Algeria, 2005.
- [40] M. M. Meddi, A. A. Assani, and H. Meddi, "Temporal Variability of Annual Rainfall in the Macta and Tafna Catchments, Northwestern Algeria," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 24, no. 14, pp. 3817–3833, Nov. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-010-9635-7>.
- [41] L. Brandimarte, G. Di Baldassarre, G. Bruni, P. D'Odorico, and A. Montanari, "Relation Between the North-Atlantic Oscillation and Hydroclimatic Conditions in Mediterranean Areas," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 1269–1279, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-010-9742-5>.
- [42] A. N. Laghari, W. Rauch, and M. A. Soomro, "A Hydrological Response Analysis Considering Climatic Variability: Case Study of Hunza Catchment," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 2981–2984, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2056>.

Some Mineralogical Characteristics of the Egyptian Black Sand Beach Ilmenite Part II: Rutile-Ilmenite and the Various Titanhematite Grains

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Abstract-In addition to the grains of homogeneous ilmenite, ferriilmenite, hematite-ilmenite exsolved intergrowths, and the partially altered ilmenite grains, other textures are detected in the separated ilmenite concentrate. The grains of rutile-ilmenite exsolved intergrowth represent 0.8% of the detected ilmenite grains. The ilmenite component of this intergrowth is detected to be ferriilmenite associated with geikielite, pyrophanite, and rutile, with Cr_2O_3 content ranging between 0 and 0.5%. The exsolved rutile is ferriferrous rutile composed of rutile, hematite, geikielite, and pyrophanite, its Cr_2O_3 content ranging between 0 and 0.4%. The detected individual titanhematite grains represent 4.4% and include 3 textures arranged, in a decreasing order of abundance, as: ilmenite-hematite, rutile-hematite, and rutile-ilmenite-hematite exsolution intergrowths. MgO and MnO have minimum values and they do not follow Fe_2O_3 . In some homogeneous titanhematite or exsolved rutile-hematite, Fe_2O_3 content may be replaced with SiO_2 . In all titanhematite intergrown textures, the Cr_2O_3 content ranges between 0 and 0.1%. Only in the case of the titanhematite host with exsolved rutile, the contained MgO ranges between 1.2 and 5.3%. Some ferromagnetic titanhematite grains separated with the fraction of magnetite are detected. In these grains, the Cr_2O_3 , MgO, and MnO contents range between 0-0.2, 0-3, and 0-1.4% respectively. Several varieties of chromite and chromspinel mineral grains are found and represent 1.1% of the detected bulk ilmenite grains. In these grains, the Cr_2O_3 , MgO, V_2O_5 , and Al_2O_3 contents range between 16.69-56.72%, 0.54-17.33%, 0.14-0.58%, and 1.33-38.79% respectively. Although they are rarely met in the ilmenite concentrate, the relatively finer grain sizes could lead to the separation of some with ilmenite fraction rather than with the ferromagnetic one. It is concluded that the problem of high Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 contents of the Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrate is not only a mineralogical problem, but also an ore-dressing one.

Keywords-black sands; beach ilmenite; ferriferrous rutile; titanhematite; martitization; exsolved intergrowth

I. INTRODUCTION

The placer deposits are very important sources of many economic minerals. The Egyptian black sands extend along the northern coastal stretch between Abu Qir to the west and Rafah to the east. These deposits contain 6 economic minerals:

ilmenite, magnetite, garnet, zircon, rutile, and monazite. They are present either as beach sediments or as coastal sand dunes. Ilmenite alone reaches up more than 50% of the total. However, the original amount of materials transported by the river may be related to several variables such as the flow type and the sediment load [1]. Most ilmenite grains are found in fine and very fine sand-sized grains. In fact, the original grain size may affect the rate of mineral alteration [2]. The grain size becomes relatively coarser on moving from Rosetta to the west to Rafah to the east due to drifting by alongshore currents. Ilmenite also occurs in massive rock formations in the form of titaniferous ore, associated with hematite and magnetite [3]. Among the titanium minerals, only ilmenite, leucocoxene, and rutile have significant importance [4-7]. The ilmenite ore is the main source for the production of metallic titanium and titanium containing compounds. The mineralogy of the Egyptian beach ilmenite has been studied in [8-15] among others. Many authors reported the relatively lower TiO_2 content and relatively higher Fe_2O_3 and Cr_2O_3 contents and others reported the diversity of the mineralogical textures inside ilmenite grains.

In the Egyptian black sand, the ilmenite content varies from less than 1% in the raw beach sand up to more than 50% in the naturally highly concentrated surficial black sands. Most of the obtained Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrates are characterized by a relatively lower TiO_2 content (44-46% of ilmenite's beach sand and 46-49% of ilmenite's sand dunes) and relatively greater Cr_2O_3 content (0.1-0.4%). Also, they have a relatively lower $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ratio and relatively higher MgO and MnO contents. Authors in [16] explained that the general break-even grade for ilmenite is considered to be 47 to 48% TiO_2 , a rise in the ratio from 51% to 54% TiO_2 will, however, double profits.

The trace element concentrations of ilmenite grains show enrichment in Cr and V contents indicating that these elements are probably hosted by ilmenite [8]. The Cr_2O_3 content is negligible in the lattice of the Egyptian beach ilmenite and hematite. However, up to 0.36% Cr_2O_3 was recorded in the whole concentrate analysis that could be due to accessory Cr-

spinel minerals. The V content in the Egyptian ilmenite (av. 0.3%), which probably affects the pigment brightness, is relatively high [17]. Hydrometallurgical and/or pyrometallurgical processes for converting the Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrate into a marketable product are investigated in [18-19]. The separation procedures of ilmenite and other economic mineral concentrates of the Egyptian beach sand and other deposits are explained in [15, 20]. To detect the reasons of the relatively higher Cr_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 content in addition to the relatively lower TiO_2 content of most of the obtained Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrates, most of the contained mineral textures within the ilmenite concentrate, associated with the other obtained magnetic fractions, will be investigated. Knowing such reasons, the process of ilmenite separation, the chemical specification of the obtained ilmenite concentrate, and its corresponding marketable value can be improved.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A bulk sample of about 1000 tons was collected from the surficial naturally highly concentrated beach black sand at the Mediterranean coast, 7 km east of the Rosetta estuary. The sample represents the raw sand in a 2 km stretch with variable width of a few meters to 20 m. The sand was manually scraped from the mantle to a depth ranging between 10-30 cm. Using the difference in physical characteristics between the various economic minerals, the collected surficial naturally highly concentrated beach raw sand was processed using the following equipment: Full- and Half-size Wilfley shaking tables for wet-gravity concentration, Carpc (HP 167) high-tension roll-type electrostatic separator for electrostatic separation, Reading cross-belt magnetic separator, and the Carpc (MIH 13-231-100) industrial high intensity induced roll dry magnetic separator for magnetic separation. Finally, a bulk conductor ilmenite fraction was obtained and was subjected to the refining magnetic stage using the Reading cross-belt magnetic separator, after which an ilmenite concentrate assaying 99.5% ilmenite grains was obtained.

Four polished sections were prepared from 4 small representative samples and were studied under the reflected microscope and Cameca SX-100 microprobe instrument. They were taken from the obtained final ilmenite concentrate (including 2 obtained magnetic fractions of the reading separator), a representative sample of the obtained ferromagnetic fraction, a representative sample of all the other obtained magnetic fractions of the separator, and finally a representative sample of the obtained nonmagnetic fraction of the separator.

The investigation of the different ilmenite grains was carried out by a Cameca SX-100 electron microprobe analyzer (EMPA), from the Institute of Mineralogy and Crystal Chemistry, Stuttgart University, Germany. The microprobe instrument is equipped with 3 Wavelength Dispersive Spectrometers (WDSs) and an Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (EDS). The whole surface of the polished sections was examined by Back Scattered Electron (BSE) images, so that ilmenite grains with $10\mu\text{m}$ size or even smaller could be detected. The analytical conditions were 15 kV accelerating voltage, 15 nA electron current, 180 s counting time for each

analyzed spot in the investigated grains, and 1 to $4\mu\text{m}$ diameter of the focused electron beam. The following standards were used: diopside for Mg and Ca, albite for Na, corundum for Al, orthoclase for Si and K, rutile for Ti, rhodonite for Mn, Fe_2O_3 for Fe, Cr_2O_3 for Cr, V for V, and sphalerite for Zn. $K\alpha$ lines were used for analysis. Also, a stereoscopic binocular microscope, a reflected-light polarizing microscope, Jones riddle splitters of various sizes, and containers of various sizes are used.

III. CALCULATION

The calculation of Fe^{3+} content, the molecular formula of the contained ilmenite mineral components of the studied individual ilmenite grains, the methods of calculation of the different mineral components of the analyzed spots composed mainly of ferriilmenite and/or titanhematite with or without individual TiO_2 (rutile), and the calculation of different mineral components of the analyzed ferriferous rutile are as those of [21].

IV. RESULTS

Homogeneous ilmenite, homogeneous ferriilmenite, hematite-ilmenite exsolved intergrown grains, and the partially altered ilmenite varieties are discussed in [21], while the remaining ilmenite textures are investigated in this paper. Various mineral textures are detected and analyzed. 41 analyzed spots within 7 grains of rutile-ilmenite exsolved intergrown grains are investigated. Several ilmenite grains were detected to enclose rutile exsolution lamellae that are frequently undulating and arranged in one direction and to somewhat similar to what is called "Blitz structure" described in [22]. However, the texture is clearer under crossed nicols and with colored images. The ilmenite chemical molecular formula and the corresponding mineral component fractions are calculated. The detected individual titanhematite grains represent 4.4%. 53 analyzed spots within 8 titanhematite grains were investigated. Normal hematite (pure Fe_2O_3), showing well-defined optical properties under the reflected light is very rare. Titanhematite is slightly greyish white, showing a relatively lower reflectivity and is strongly anisotropic from bright slightly greyish white with pale yellowish tint to dull grey with faint bluish tint, rarely showing red internal reflections. However, titanhematite (Ti-rich hematite) is slightly darker and more greyish white than the primary and secondary hematite formed by martitization of magnetite or by the alteration of ilmenite. The ilmenite-hematite exsolution intergrowth is much less common than the hematite-ilmenite exsolution intergrowth. However, it is considered the most common exsolution intergrowth in the host titanhematite grains. In the present study, the host titanhematite mineral grain encloses exsolved lamellae of ferriilmenite oriented with their long axes parallel to the (0001) plane (Figure 1(1)).

On the other hand, some titanhematite grains contain 2 distinct size classes of ferriilmenite exsolution lamellae, an ordinary and a coarse type of intergrowth. In both cases, relatively finer ferriilmenite exsolution bodies are observed between the coarser bodies. Also, the very coarse ferriilmenite exsolution bodies may in turn contain very fine lamellae of titanhematite (Figure 1(2)). The same phenomenon was

observed in [23]. In rare cases, twinned ferriilmenite-titanhematite individual components are observed where the exsolved ferriilmenite lamellae are arranged parallel to the (0001) plane of the host titanhematite in each component which has different oriented direction (Figure 1(3)). Also, some rare composite grains, consisting of differently oriented titanhematite grains are observed with exsolutions of ferriilmenite parallel to their basal planes (Figure 1(4)). Sometimes narrow rims or small parts of homogenous ilmenite occur on the borders of these titanhematite grains. Some of these titanhematite grains can also contain fine exsolution lamellae of rutile parallel to one or more of its (224 $\bar{3}$) directions.

Fig. 1. Various ferrilmenite-titanhematite exsolved intergrowth samples, sometimes including rutile exsolved bodies: (1) Ferrilmenite-titanhematite exsolution intergrowth with the exsolved ferriilmenite lamellae parallel to the (0001) plane of titanhematite. Reflected light, $\times 100$. (2) Two different sizes of exsolved ferriilmenite in the host titanhematite. The relatively coarser exsolved ferriilmenite lamellae contain very fine exsolved lamellae of titanhematite. Reflected light, $\times 100$. (3) Two twinned ferriilmenite-titanhematite exsolution intergrowths. The exsolved ferriilmenites show different oriented directions in relation to each other. Reflected light, $\times 100$. (4) Granular aggregates of differently oriented titanhematite crystals, each of them containing exsolved ferriilmenite lamellae parallel to its basal plane. Some of them also contain fine lamellae of exsolved rutile. Reflected light, $\times 100$. (5) Titanhematite (greyish white) with rutile exsolutions (light grey) parallel to the (224 $\bar{3}$) direction. Reflected light, $\times 100$. (6) Ferrilmenite-titanhematite exsolution intergrowth associated with exsolved rutile needles. The exsolved ferriilmenite (dark grey) is parallel to the (0001) direction, while the exsolved rutile (light grey) is parallel to the (224 $\bar{3}$) direction. Reflected light, $\times 100$.

The second common exsolution intergrowth in the host titanhematite is rutile-titanhematite intergrowth. A considerable number of the detected titanhematite grains are not free of rutile exsolved lamellae. Fine needles of exsolved rutile were observed in up to 6 directions parallel to the (224 $\bar{3}$) planes of the titanhematite (Figure 1(5)). The third common exsolution intergrowth in the host titanhematite is rutile-ilmenite-hematite exsolution intergrowth. In this case, some of titanhematite grains contain exsolved ferriilmenite lamellae which are pod-shaped or spindle-shaped and are oriented in one direction parallel to the (0001) plane of the titanhematite. The exsolved ferriilmenite lamellae are associated with the exsolved fine needles of rutile which are arranged along 1, 2 to 6 directions, parallel to the (224 $\bar{3}$) planes of the titanhematite, and are much more elongated than the exsolved ferriilmenite (Figure 1(6)). In most cases, the exsolved rutile needles cut the grain from side

to side and are oblique to the direction of the ferriilmenite lamellae. The corresponding different mineral component fractions of the all the analyzed spots are calculated.

Finally, 49 analyzed spots within 6 grains of ferromagnetic titanhematite associated with magnetite in its ferromagnetic fraction were detected. The hematite chemical formula and the corresponding mineral component fractions were calculated. Some of analyzed spots are corresponding to impurities of silica, calcite, altered silicate minerals, and pseudobrookite. The analyzed oxides of the detected spots include TiO_2 , FeO , Fe_2O_3 , Cr_2O_3 , MnO , MgO , Al_2O_3 , V_2O_5 , ZnO , SiO_2 , and CaO .

V. DISCUSSIONS

A. Rutile-Ilmenite Exsolution Intergrowth (0.8%)

The rutile exsolutions in ilmenite are far less common than in titanhematite. These intergrowths of exsolved rutile are possibly the result of unmixing of a rutile-ilmenite solid solution, which must be very limited as the observed rutile lamellae are very few in number, extremely fine, while the intergrowth is very rare [14, 23-24]. This is in accordance with the results obtained in [25] for synthetic preparations, that not more than 6% TiO_2 can exist in solid solutions in ilmenite at 1050°C. However, 6 grains were detected for this exsolution intergrowth and their chemical compositions were investigated with the microprobe. It is noticed that the content of the exsolved rutile is relatively higher than that recorded in previous studies.

Fig. 2. BSE images of various rutile-ilmenite exsolved intergrowth grains.

Spots 2, 3 of grain (1) of Figure 2 (Table I), are ferrillmenite with considerable amounts of geikielite and minor pyrophanite and rutile in solid solutions. In these spots, the first method (M1) of calculation is used to calculate the different mineral fractions of the two spots. Then, the mineral components of the two spots are: Spot 2: 64.42% ilmenite, 22.9% hematite, 11.03% geikielite, 1.28% pyrophanite, and 0.16% rutile and spot 3: 66.11% ilmenite, 21.60% hematite, 10.14% geikielite, 1.28% pyrophanite, and 0.15% rutile.

Spot 1 of grain (1) of Figure 2 (Table II) is titanhematite with considerable amounts of rutile and geikielite. It is composed of 69.48% hematite, 11.63% geikielite, 1.7% pyrophanite, and 16.9% rutile. Spot 4 is mostly ilmenite. Spots

5-7 of grain (2) of Figure 2 (Table II) are ferrirous rutile composed mostly of rutile with considerable amounts of hematite (Fe₂O₃), ranging between 21.91% and 33.86%, geikielite, and pyrophanite mineral components. In these spots, the third method (M3) of calculation is used to calculate the different mineral fractions. Their mineral components are: Spot 5: 33.86% hematite, 6.09% geikielite, 0.64% pyrophanite, and 58.59% rutile, spot 6: 27.62% hematite, 4.18% geikielite, 0.53% pyrophanite, and 67.21% rutile, and spot 7: 21.91% hematite, 2.42% geikielite, 0.43% pyrophanite, and 73.22% rutile. It is obvious that the content of TiO₂ (rutile) decreases as the content of geikielite and pyrophanite increases. The same relation is detected between the exsolved rutile and the mixed hematite inside it.

TABLE I. MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND MOLECULAR FORMULAE OF THE ANALYZED SPOTS FOR THE RUTILO-ILMENITE EXSOLVED INTERGROWN GRAINS OF FIGURES 2, 3

Grains	Spot	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₅	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Total	Fe ²⁺	Fe ³⁺	Other cations	Ti	O	Gek	Pyr	Ilm	H	R	Total
Fig. 2 (1)	2	0.00	3.70	0.60	0.00	0.10	50.60	0.20	0.50	0.40	42.20	98.30	30.50	22.30	100.50	0.63	0.41	0.19	0.78	3	11.03	1.28	64.42	22.90	0.16	99.79
	3	0.00	3.40	0.60	0.00	0.10	50.20	0.20	0.50	0.40	42.20	97.50	31.30	21.00	99.60	0.65	0.39	0.17	0.79	3	10.14	1.28	66.11	21.60	0.15	99.27
	4	0.70	0.20	0.40	0.10	0.00	41.10	0.10	0.60	0.50	52.50	96.30	41.10	0.00	96.30	0.90	0.00	0.07	1.03	3	0.60	0.85	86.80	0.60	5.89	94.74
Fig. 2 (2)	2	0.00	5.10	0.70	0.00	0.00	53.30	0.40	0.40	0.20	32.80	93.00	19.60	37.50	96.70	0.42	0.72	0.27	0.63	3	15.21	1.49	41.40	38.10	0.13	96.32
	3	0.00	9.30	0.80	0.00	0.10	47.80	0.40	0.40	0.20	36.20	95.30	15.00	36.40	98.90	0.30	0.66	0.42	0.66	3	27.73	1.70	31.68	37.00	0.23	98.35
	4	0.00	9.00	0.60	0.00	0.00	45.40	0.40	0.40	0.20	38.90	94.90	18.30	30.10	97.90	0.37	0.55	0.40	0.71	3	26.84	1.28	38.65	30.70	0.13	97.59
Fig. 2 (3)	1	0.00	0.60	1.00	0.00	0.00	50.80	0.30	0.60	0.30	44.70	98.30	38.10	14.10	99.70	0.81	0.27	0.08	0.85	3	1.79	2.13	80.47	14.70	0.02	99.10
	2	0.00	3.10	0.60	0.00	0.10	48.60	0.30	0.60	0.30	46.10	99.80	35.30	14.90	101.30	0.72	0.27	0.16	0.85	3	9.24	1.28	74.55	15.50	0.15	100.73
	3	0.00	1.70	0.90	0.00	0.00	49.30	0.30	0.70	0.30	46.40	99.70	37.70	13.00	101.00	0.78	0.24	0.12	0.87	3	5.07	1.91	79.62	13.60	0.05	100.26
	4	0.00	5.70	0.50	0.00	0.00	45.20	0.30	0.60	0.40	46.80	99.50	31.30	15.50	101.00	0.63	0.28	0.25	0.85	3	17.00	1.06	66.11	16.20	0.12	100.49
	5	0.00	5.60	0.60	0.00	0.00	45.60	0.20	0.60	0.40	47.30	100.30	32.00	15.10	101.90	0.64	0.27	0.25	0.85	3	16.70	1.28	67.58	15.70	0.06	101.32
Fig. 2 (4)	1	0.00	3.80	0.60	0.00	0.00	54.00	0.10	0.60	0.10	35.20	94.30	24.20	33.00	97.60	0.52	0.63	0.20	0.67	3	11.33	1.28	51.11	33.20	0.07	96.99
	2	0.00	7.10	1.10	0.00	0.00	44.60	0.10	0.40	0.00	43.00	96.40	24.90	21.90	98.60	0.51	0.40	0.31	0.79	3	21.17	2.34	52.59	22.00	0.05	98.15
Fig. 2 (5)	1	0.00	9.10	0.30	0.00	0.10	37.00	0.10	0.70	0.40	49.20	96.80	27.60	10.40	97.90	0.56	0.19	0.37	0.89	3	27.14	0.64	58.29	10.90	0.15	97.11
	2	0.00	9.80	0.40	0.00	0.10	36.50	0.10	0.70	0.30	49.90	97.90	27.00	10.60	98.90	0.54	0.19	0.39	0.89	3	29.22	0.85	57.02	11.00	0.10	98.19
	3	0.00	9.10	0.40	0.00	0.00	36.50	0.10	0.70	0.40	50.20	97.30	28.40	8.90	98.20	0.57	0.16	0.37	0.91	3	27.14	0.85	59.98	9.40	0.13	97.50
	4	0.00	9.80	0.40	0.00	0.00	35.30	0.10	0.60	0.30	51.10	97.50	28.00	8.00	98.30	0.56	0.14	0.39	0.92	3	29.22	0.85	59.14	8.40	0.10	97.71
	5	0.00	7.70	0.40	0.00	0.00	35.00	0.10	0.80	0.50	52.80	97.30	33.30	1.80	97.50	0.68	0.03	0.32	0.97	3	22.96	0.85	70.33	2.40	0.08	96.62
	6	0.00	12.00	0.50	0.00	0.10	31.90	0.10	0.50	0.20	53.00	98.30	25.80	6.90	98.90	0.50	0.12	0.45	0.93	3	35.78	1.06	54.49	7.20	0.21	98.75
	7	0.00	7.30	0.30	0.00	0.00	34.70	0.10	0.70	0.50	53.30	97.00	34.60	0.10	97.00	0.71	0.00	0.30	0.99	3	21.77	0.64	73.08	0.70	0.03	96.21
	8	0.00	7.70	0.30	0.00	0.00	34.20	0.10	0.60	0.30	53.80	97.10	34.20	0.00	97.10	0.70	0.00	0.31	0.99	3	22.96	0.64	72.23	0.40	0.29	96.52
Fig. 2 (6)	1	0.00	0.00	3.50	0.10	0.00	43.30	0.00	0.20	0.00	48.70	95.80	40.00	3.60	96.20	0.88	0.07	0.09	0.96	3	0.00	7.44	84.48	3.60	0.22	95.74
	2	0.00	0.10	5.00	0.00	0.00	41.40	0.00	0.30	0.00	49.50	96.20	39.30	2.30	96.40	0.86	0.05	0.12	0.97	3	0.30	10.63	83.00	2.30	0.09	96.32
	3	0.00	0.00	3.60	0.00	0.00	44.20	0.00	0.40	0.00	49.50	97.70	40.90	3.70	98.00	0.88	0.07	0.09	0.96	3	0.00	7.65	86.38	3.70	0.04	97.77
	4	0.00	0.00	3.30	0.00	0.10	43.90	0.00	0.30	0.00	49.50	97.20	41.10	3.10	97.50	0.89	0.06	0.08	0.97	3	0.00	7.02	86.80	3.10	0.10	97.02
	5	0.00	0.00	4.80	0.10	0.00	41.30	0.00	0.30	0.00	49.50	96.10	39.60	2.00	96.30	0.87	0.04	0.12	0.98	3	0.00	10.20	83.64	2.00	0.04	95.88
	6	0.00	0.00	3.40	0.00	0.10	43.50	0.00	0.40	0.00	49.50	97.00	41.00	2.80	97.20	0.89	0.06	0.09	0.97	3	0.00	7.23	86.59	2.80	0.07	96.69
	7	0.00	0.00	4.40	0.10	0.10	42.20	0.00	0.30	0.00	50.10	97.20	40.40	1.90	97.30	0.88	0.04	0.11	0.98	3	0.00	9.35	85.32	1.90	0.18	96.76
Fig. 3	1	0.00	0.00	3.60	0.10	0.10	47.10	0.00	0.60	0.00	44.80	96.30	36.40	11.90	97.50	0.79	0.23	0.10	0.88	3	0.00	7.65	76.88	11.90	0.20	96.63
	2	0.00	0.10	3.40	0.10	0.10	43.70	0.00	0.60	0.00	48.90	96.90	40.20	3.90	97.30	0.87	0.08	0.10	0.96	3	0.30	7.23	84.90	3.90	0.19	96.52
	3	0.00	0.00	4.20	0.00	0.00	43.00	0.00	0.50	0.10	48.80	96.70	39.50	3.90	97.10	0.86	0.08	0.11	0.96	3	0.00	8.93	83.42	4.00	0.06	96.41
	4	0.00	0.10	4.10	0.10	0.10	42.70	0.00	0.50	0.00	49.10	96.60	39.70	3.40	97.00	0.86	0.07	0.11	0.96	3	0.30	8.72	83.85	3.40	0.29	96.55
	5	0.00	0.10	4.40	0.20	0.00	43.10	0.00	0.50	0.00	49.20	97.60	39.50	4.10	98.00	0.85	0.08	0.12	0.96	3	0.30	9.35	83.42	4.10	0.27	97.45
	6	0.40	0.10	4.00	0.40	0.10	41.10	0.00	0.60	0.00	49.30	96.00	40.10	1.10	96.10	0.88	0.02	0.13	0.97	3	0.30	8.50	84.69	1.10	0.02	94.62
	7	0.00	0.00	4.30	0.00	0.00	42.00	0.00	0.50	0.00	49.40	96.30	40.10	2.20	96.50	0.88	0.04	0.11	0.97	3	0.00	9.14	84.69	2.20	0.05	96.08
	8	0.00	0.10	4.40	0.10	0.10	42.00	0.00	0.50	0.00	49.50	96.70	39.70	2.60	97.00	0.87	0.05	0.12	0.97	3	0.30	9.35	83.85	2.60	0.23	96.33
	9	0.00	0.10	3.80	0.00	0.20	41.40	0.00	0.60	0.00	49.50	95.50	40.50	1.00	95.60	0.89	0.02	0.10	0.98	3	0.30	8.08	85.54	1.00	0.15	95.07
	10	0.00	0.00	4.00	0.00	0.10	43.50	0.00	0.50	0.10	49.60	97.90	40.40	3.40	98.20	0.87	0.07	0.10	0.96	3	0.00	8.50	85.32	3.50	0.18	97.50
	11	0.00	0.00	3.90	0.00	0.10	42.90	0.00	0.60	0.30	50.00	97.80	40.80	2.30	98.10	0.88	0.04	0.11	0.97	3	0.00	8.29	86.17	2.60	0.22	97.29
	12	0.10	0.10	3.70	0.10	0.10	39.40	0.00	0.50	0.00	50.40	94.50	39.40	0.00	94.50	0.88	0.00	0.11	1.01	3	0.30	7.87	83.21	0.00	2.24	93.62
	13	0.30	0.10	3.20	0.10	0.00	39.50	0.00	0.60	0.00	50.60	94.30	39.50	0.00	94.30	0.88	0.00	0.10	1.02	3	0.30	6.80	83.42	0.00		

TABLE II. CALCULATED DIFFERENT MINERAL COMPONENT FRACTIONS OF EACH ANALYZED SPOT OF OF THE RUTILO-ILMENITE EXSOLVED INTERGROWN GRAINS OF FIGURES 2, 3

Grain	Spot	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Gek	Pyr	H	R	Total
Fig. 2 (1)	1	0.20	3.90	0.80	0.10	0.00	59.10	1.30	0.70	2.50	25.50	94.10	11.63	1.70	69.48	16.90	99.71
	5	0.00	2.00	0.30	0.00	0.00	30.10	0.10	0.50	0.30	63.00	96.40	6.09	0.64	33.86	58.59	99.18
	6	0.00	1.40	0.20	0.00	0.10	24.50	0.10	0.60	0.30	70.30	97.40	4.18	0.53	27.62	67.21	99.54
	7	0.00	0.80	0.20	0.00	0.00	19.30	0.10	0.50	0.30	75.00	96.40	2.42	0.43	21.91	73.22	97.97
Fig. 2 (2)	5	0.00	1.60	0.10	0.00	0.10	19.20	0.20	0.60	0.10	75.10	97.00	4.82	0.27	21.59	71.78	98.46
	6	0.00	0.50	0.10	0.10	0.00	7.30	0.00	0.80	0.10	88.50	97.40	1.56	0.2	8.23	87.41	97.4
Fig. 2 (3)	6	0.00	0.10	0.40	0.00	0.00	23.20	0.30	0.80	0.40	70.90	96.20	0.42	0.82	26.44	70.21	97.89
	7	0.00	0.70	0.30	0.00	0.00	19.50	0.20	0.70	0.20	75.40	97.20	2.17	0.6	22.11	73.69	98.56
Fig. 2 (4)	3	0.00	1.50	0.30	0.00	0.00	25.20	0.00	0.60	0.00	68.20	95.90	4.38	0.71	28.07	64.91	98.07
	4	0.00	0.70	0.10	0.00	0.00	17.20	0.00	0.70	0.10	78.80	97.60	2.17	0.14	19.16	77.33	98.8
	5	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	1.20	0.00	0.60	0.00	96.30	98.20	0.05	0.12	1.37	96.18	97.72
	6	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	1.20	0.00	0.70	0.00	96.60	98.60	0.05	0.02	1.34	96.54	97.95
Fig. 2 (5)	9	0.00	5.60	0.20	0.00	0.00	21.80	0.10	0.70	0.20	68.70	97.30	16.55	0.48	24.53	57.5	99.07
	10	0.00	4.80	0.20	0.00	0.00	20.60	0.00	0.80	0.30	71.20	97.90	14.24	0.36	23.24	61.61	99.45
	11	0.00	4.10	0.30	0.00	0.00	19.00	0.00	0.80	0.30	73.00	97.50	12.27	0.57	21.38	64.54	98.76
	12	0.00	4.10	0.20	0.00	0.00	18.50	0.10	0.80	0.20	73.70	97.60	12.11	0.52	20.81	65.43	98.87
	13	0.00	2.80	0.10	0.00	0.10	16.40	0.00	0.80	0.20	77.40	97.80	8.25	0.25	18.48	71.77	98.76
	14	0.00	3.60	0.20	0.00	0.00	15.70	0.00	0.80	0.20	77.70	98.20	10.65	0.33	17.66	70.5	99.14
	15	0.00	3.10	0.20	0.00	0.10	12.90	0.00	0.80	0.10	80.60	97.80	9.17	0.37	14.53	74.33	98.39
Fig. 2 (6)	8	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	25.40	0.00	0.50	0.00	69.80	95.90	0.12	0.28	28.23	69.57	98.2
	9	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.00	16.30	0.50	0.50	0.00	72.10	90.10	0.45	0.49	18.57	71.54	91.05
	10	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	6.10	0.00	0.60	0.00	91.80	98.80	0.17	0.21	6.85	91.62	98.85
	11	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.10	5.30	0.00	0.70	0.00	93.50	99.70	0.1	0.11	5.95	93.34	99.5
Fig. 3	14	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	23.30	0.00	1.10	0.10	71.90	96.50	0.21	0.21	25.96	71.62	98
	15	1.20	0.20	0.20	0.90	0.10	7.20	1.00	1.00	0.00	80.40	92.20	0.69	0.47	9	79.7	89.86
	16	1.80	0.40	0.20	1.20	0.00	6.10	1.40	1.00	0.00	81.20	93.40	1.19	0.41	8.22	80.19	90.02
	17	0.40	0.30	0.10	0.40	0.00	9.70	1.20	1.10	0.00	81.30	94.50	0.8	0.27	11.94	80.61	93.63
	18	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	12.10	0.00	0.90	0.10	83.20	96.50	0.26	0.07	13.53	83.02	96.88
	19	1.40	0.30	0.20	1.00	0.00	4.10	1.20	1.10	0.00	83.60	92.70	0.84	0.36	5.69	82.84	89.73
	20	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.20	0.00	9.50	0.10	1.00	0.00	85.50	96.50	0.43	0.06	10.6	85.23	96.32
	21	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.20	0.00	9.20	0.00	0.90	0.00	86.40	96.80	0.17	0.11	10.28	86.26	96.83
	22	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	9.60	0.00	0.90	0.00	86.70	97.50	0.29	0.09	10.75	86.46	97.58
	23	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	6.90	0.10	1.10	0.00	88.70	97.10	0.2	0.16	7.73	88.5	96.59
	24	0.10	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.00	6.60	0.00	1.00	0.00	89.00	96.90	0.27	0.08	7.32	88.76	96.42
	25	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.80	0.00	0.90	0.00	90.70	97.60	0.4	0.07	6.43	90.38	97.28
	26	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00	4.10	0.00	1.00	0.00	90.80	96.10	0.12	0.14	4.59	90.67	95.53
	27	0.10	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00	5.10	0.20	1.10	0.10	91.20	97.90	0.11	0.22	5.91	90.97	97.21
	28	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.00	4.70	0.00	0.90	0.00	91.40	97.30	0.29	0.14	5.24	91.14	96.81
	29	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.10	0.00	4.80	0.00	1.00	0.00	92.30	98.20	0.07	0.13	5.32	92.15	97.66
	30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	3.90	0.00	0.90	0.00	93.20	98.10	0.13	0.03	4.36	93.1	97.62
31	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.00	3.40	0.00	0.90	0.10	93.60	98.10	0.06	0.13	3.79	93.48	97.46	

TABLE III. ORIGINAL MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF SOME SPOTS OF GRAINS FROM FIGURES 2, 3

Grains	Spots	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total
Fig. 2(2)	1	46.36	7.92	0.20	10.20	0.01	13.55	11.23	0.11	0.00	4.62	94.21
	32	23.65	18.77	0.14	0.66	0.03	15.91	17.12	0.26	0.03	13.96	90.53
Fig. 3	33	7.24	0.82	0.36	1.21	0.04	16.44	2.59	0.71	0.13	41.55	71.10
	34	7.77	1.41	0.85	1.25	0.02	15.35	3.75	0.54	0.06	43.36	74.36
	35	1.02	0.24	1.02	0.75	0.00	18.48	0.73	0.57	0.48	46.78	70.06
	36	3.63	0.85	0.28	1.51	0.00	14.80	2.04	0.67	0.03	47.65	71.45
	37	7.70	0.68	0.32	3.50	0.12	9.95	2.22	0.57	0.08	50.96	76.09
	38	4.96	0.90	0.55	2.17	0.00	10.43	1.64	0.60	0.02	52.53	73.80
	39	7.29	1.00	0.18	0.63	0.03	5.69	3.64	0.71	0.01	56.14	75.31

Spot 1 of grain 2 of Figure 2 (Table III) is a definite silicate mineral composed of Fe, Ca, Mg, Ti, and Al-silicate. Spots 2-4 (Figure 2, Table I), are mixtures of several mineral components. Using the same method of calculation with (M1), the various mineral components of spots 2- 4 of grain (2) are: Spot 2: 41.40% ilmenite, 38.10% hematite, 15.21% geikielite, 1.49% pyrophanite, and 0.13% rutile. Spot 3: 31.68% ilmenite, 37% hematite, 27.73% geikielite, 1.70% pyrophanite, and

0.23% rutile. Spot 4: 38.65% ilmenite, 30.70% hematite, 26.84% geikielite, 1.28% pyrophanite, and 0.13% rutile. It is obvious that the ilmenite component in these spots is partially altered into hematite and the detected exsolved rutile bodies. It is obvious that the lightness of spot area is determined according to the amount of hematite component. As the hematite % increases, the lightness increases (spots 2 and 3), and vice versa (spot 4).

Spots 5 and 6 of grain (2) of Figure 2 (Table II) are ferriiferous rutile composed mostly of rutile with considerable amounts of hematite in solid solution, ranging between 8.23 and 21.59%. Using the M3 method of calculation, the mineral components for each of the two spots are: Spot 5: 21.59% hematite, 4.82% geikielite, 0.27% pyrophanite, and 71.78% rutile and spot 6: 8.23% hematite, 1.56% geikielite 0.20%, pyrophanite, and 87.41% rutile. Spots 1-5 of grain (3) of Figure 2 (Table I) are ferriilmenite with Fe_2O_3 content ranging between 13.60 and 16.20%. Both spots 6-7 of Figure 2 are ferriiferous rutile (Table II).

Spots 1 and 2 of grain (4) of Figure 2 are ferriilmenite (Table I), spots 3 and 4 are ferriiferous rutile, and spots 5 and 6 are rutile with minor Fe_2O_3 content (Table II). Using the M1 method of calculation, the mineral components of spots 1 and 2 are: Spot 1: 51.11% ilmenite, 33.20% hematite, 11.33% geikielite, 1.28% pyrophanite, and 0.07% rutile. Spot 2: 52.59% ilmenite, 22%, hematite, 21.17% geikielite, 2.34% pyrophanite, and 0.05% rutile. These two spots are solid solutions of ilmenite, hematite, geikielite, pyrophanite, and traces of rutile. It is obvious that both Mg and Mn follow FeO and not Fe_2O_3 , hence as the content of hematite decreases, as the content of geikielite and/or pyrophanite increases. Geikielite and pyrophanite are mixed easier with ilmenite than with hematite. Spots 3 and 4 are rutile mixed with hematite, ranging between 19.16 and 28.07%.

Spots 5 and 6 are mostly rutile with minor hematite, which ranges between 1.34 and 1.37%. It is obvious that the relatively larger and darker rutile exsolved intergrowths are composed mostly of rutile (more than 95% TiO_2), while the relatively smaller ones are mainly ferriiferous rutile with considerable amounts of mixed hematite (Figure 2, Table II). Spots 1-6 of grain (5) of Figure 2 are ferriilmenite, 7 and 8 are ilmenite (Table I). All the iron of spot 8 is ferrous iron. It is obvious that most of ferriilmenite containing exsolved intergrowths of rutile contain a considerable amount of MgO as geikielite. Spots 9-15 are ferriiferous rutile mixed with hematite, geikielite, and pyrophanite in solid solution (Table II). Using the same method of calculations of (2) and (3) grains, and converting all analyzed iron as FeO to Fe_2O_3 to be calculated as hematite, the mineral components composed for each spot are shown in Table II. Spots 1-7 of grain (6) of Figure 2 (Table I) are ferriilmenite with Fe_2O_3 content ranging between 1.9 and 3.7%. Spots 10 and 11 are ferriiferous rutile. Spots 8 and 9 are ilmenite altered to rutile and hematite (Table II). Spot 9 is located beside the edge of the grain. The activity of water seems to be relatively greater hence a partial leaching of hematite component occurred. The total oxide sum of this spot is 91.05%, which reflects the existence of molecular water (Table II).

Spots 1-13 of the grain of Figure 3 (Table I) are composed mainly of ilmenite and pyrophanite with minor amounts of hematite and other mineral components. Spots from 1 to 11, are ferriilmenite with Fe_2O_3 content ranging between 1 and 11.90%. Spots 12 and 13 are ilmenite, in which most of the mixed Fe_2O_3 is leached out. All the iron content is ferrous iron. Some molecular water is included in these two spots. The

analyzed total oxide sum of the two spots is 94.3 and 94.5% respectively (Table I).

Fig. 3. BSE image of a composite ilmenite grain. Spots 1-13 are composed of ilmenite enriched with MnO content. Spots 14-31 are ilmenite altered to rutile and hematite, and spots 32-39 are alterations of a definite silicate mineral.

Spots 14-31 are ilmenite altered to rutile and hematite. They are composed mainly of rutile and hematite mineral components (Table II). Spots 15, 16, and 19 are in the neighborhood of voids where the activity of molecular water is relatively higher. Spots 32-39 are an alteration of a definite silicate mineral, Mg Fe Al-silicate, attached with ilmenite altered to rutile and hematite (Table III). The hematite component is partially leached leaving the remaining rutile associated with the products of the altered silicate mineral. Most of these last spots contain molecular and/or structural water.

B. Titanhematite (4.4%)

Authors in [26] explained that hematite is not so widely distributed in magmatic rocks, as it is known from the literature. Authors in [27] showed that hematite is almost wholly Fe_2O_3 and subtitanhematite is Fe_2O_3 with 1.5 to 5% TiO_2 as $\text{FeO}\cdot\text{TiO}_2$ or TiO_2 or both while titanhematite is Fe_2O_3 with 5-10% TiO_2 as $\text{FeO}\cdot\text{TiO}_2$ up to about 13% plus excess TiO_2 up to about 3% in solid solution. Titanhematite or white ilmenite is hematite containing a maximum of 10% FeTiO_3 in solid solution. If the FeTiO_3 -content exceeds 10%, oriented intergrowths of ilmenite and Ti-hematite may be formed [28]. A number of fabrics in which the titanhematite is considered as the major component (the host mineral) have been observed. These include the following arranged in decreasing order of abundance:

1) Ilmenite-Hematite Exsolution Intergrowth

The intergrowth was called ilmeno-hematite where micro intergrowths of ferriilmenite or hemoilmenite are enclosed in the titanhematite host [27]. Although ferriilmenite exsolution bodies are found in two different sizes in the host titanilmenite, they cannot be considered as two distinct generations. Many of

the relatively larger ferriilmenite exsolution lamellae are observed to have coalesced, are frequently irregular, and seem to grade into smaller bodies. So, the ferriilmenite-titanhematite intergrowth may be interpreted as a result of unmixing of an original ilmenite-hematite solid solution and most of the relatively larger ferriilmenite exsolution lamellae that seem to have grown in situ by diffusion.

2) Rutile-Hematite Exsolution Intergrowth

Such intergrowth is called as rutilohematite where microintergrowths of rutile or exsolved rutile grains are enclosed in the titanhematite host [27]. A few exsolved rutile needles cut the host titanhematite grains from side to side, suggesting that most of them represent the unmixing of excess TiO_2 originally dissolved in the Fe_2O_3 solid solution. The same intergrowth was observed in [29] in metamorphosed beach sands.

3) Rutile-Ilmenite-Hematite Exsolution Intergrowth

This intergrowth was called as ilmenorutilohematite where exsolved micro intergrowths of ferriilmenite or hemoilmenite and rutile are enclosed in the host titanhematite [27]. Such type of exsolved intergrowth was observed in the sands of Lake Oulu, Finland [30]. The exsolved ferriilmenite lamellae had short, more spindle-shaped bodies parallel to the (0001) plane of titanhematite while the exsolved rutile needles were common in at least 6 directions. Authors in [29] recorded the same type of intergrowth, but the exsolved rutile lamellae were found in the typical Blitz texture. Authors in [31] believed that the rutile lamellae are of an earlier generation than the ferriilmenite exsolution bodies. However, authors in [25] concluded that the unmixing of the ilmenite-hematite solid solution to ferriilmenite and titanhematite started before the separation of the excess TiO_2 as rutile. Authors in [14] agreed with this conclusion, since the rutile lamellae are observed to cut the ferriilmenite exsolutions, i.e. they are, therefore, of later origin. On the other hand, authors in [32] explained the development of the rutile exsolutions as a result of the partial oxidation (under high oxidation potential) of FeTiO_3 in a mixed crystal lying near the Fe_2O_3 - FeTiO_3 join, on the TiO_2 side of the system FeO - Fe_2O_3 - TiO_2 to hematite and rutile:

The resulting rutile is then dissolved at sufficient temperatures in the FeTiO_3 - Fe_2O_3 solid solution (especially on the Fe_2O_3 side). Later unmixing of the rutile in solid solution takes place. We believe that the exsolved rutile lamellae are of later origin and are the result of the unmixing of the excess TiO_2 , originally dissolved in the FeTiO_3 - Fe_2O_3 solid solution. The frequency of these exsolved rutile lamellae is very low compared with the exsolved ferriilmenite lamellae and some of them were detected to cut the ferriilmenite exsolutions.

The microprobe findings of some titanhematite grains of different fabrics are: In grain (1), all the analyzed 6 spots of Figure 4 (Tables IV, V) are mainly Fe_2O_3 with only minor portions of TiO_2 . The grain is most probably hematite. In grain (2), the analyzed 5 spots (Figure 4, Tables IV, V) are composed of hematite. The V_2O_5 content ranges between 0.18 and 0.2%. Spots 1-4 of grain (3), (Figure 4, Tables IV, V) are hematite

with minor TiO_2 . The V_2O_5 content of these spots ensures that V_2O_5 follows Fe_2O_3 rather than FeO . Also, the negligible content of MgO and MnO ensures that these two oxides do not follow Fe_2O_3 . Spot 5 is silica which is recorded along the edges of grain (3), (Figure 4, Table VIII). This may reflect the ability of silica to replace Fe_2O_3 . Spots 6-7 are calcite, where the remaining percentage of each spot is detected to be carbon (Figure 4, Table VIII).

Fig. 4. BSE images of various titanhematite exsolved intergrown grains.

Spots 1 and 2 of grain (4) of Figure 4 (Tables IV, V) are ilmenite. Spot 3 is hematite altered to goethite. Spots 4-13 are hematite altered to goethite where the analyzed total oxide sum decreases by about one tenth of the analyzed value of Fe_2O_3 content which corresponds the content of structural water (OH) necessary for converting hematite to goethite (FeOOH), (Figure 4, Tables IV, V). In these spots, V_2O_5 content ranges between 0.69 and 0.78%. It follows Fe_2O_3 , which ranges between 87.06 and 89.99%. TiO_2 content ranges between 0.81 and 1.22%. Spots 1-5 of grain (5) of Figure 4 (Tables IV, V) are titanhematite. MgO and MnO contents range between 0.06 and 0.09% and 0.16 and 0.28% respectively. TiO_2 content ranges between 8.29 and 9.15%, while the FeO content ranges between 6.99 and 7.83%. The recorded TiO_2 content seems to be related to the contained ilmenite. Spots 6-14 have total oxide sum ranging between 93.2 and 96.77%. TiO_2 content ranges between 24.05 and 45.73%, while the Fe_2O_3 content ranges between 50.59 and 5.78%. At spot 6, the TiO_2 content is 24.05% while the Fe_2O_3 content is 50.59%. On the other hand, at spot 14, the TiO_2 content is 45.73%, while the Fe_2O_3 content is 5.78%. There is an obvious reverse relation between TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 inside each spot. Also, it is noticed that although the spots 12, 14 are located at the same exsolved intergrowth lamella, they have widely varying contents of TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 , while the analyzed total oxide sum is almost the same: 93.67 and 93.20% respectively. Also, the MnO and MgO contents are negligible which may indicate the absence of ferrous iron. In fact, spots 6-14 are ilmenite alteration mixtures of rutile and hematite or some of spots are pseudobrookite of the Fe_2TiO_5

type, mixed with an individual TiO_2 phase, most probably rutile, and maybe also Fe_2O_3 .

In grain (6) of Figure 4 (Tables IV, V), spots 1-6 are titanhematite. The FeO content ranges between 1.9 and 7.86% which corresponds to the analyzed content of TiO_2 : 2.17-8.82%, indicating the content of ilmenite. Spots 7-13 do not give acceptable results using the ilmenite program (Figure 4, Table VIII). Spots 7-8 are made from a CaFeAl -silicate mineral. The area of spot 8 is darker than that of spot 7 due to the alteration of the silicate mineral and an enrichment of the content of SiO_2 (Table VIII). Spot 13 is silica. In spots 9-12 of grain (6), the silica ranges between 5.57 and 90.85%, while TiO_2 ranges between 94.98 and 8.51%. It is obvious that the titanhematite of spot 9 is replaced by SiO_2 , while the contained TiO_2 remained. Spots 10-12 are most probably rutilo-hematite (spots 10, 11), or ferriferous rutile (spot 12), where Fe_2O_3 is replaced by SiO_2 . The analyzed total oxide sum of some spots may be greater than 100%, due to the irregularity and the voids of the measured spot surface.

In grain (7) of Figure 4 (Tables IV, V), spots 1-3 may be the result of high temperature alteration of ilmeno-hematite fabric, producing a mixture of hematite and rutile in solid solution. Spots 4-8 do not give acceptable results using the ilmenite program (Table V). These spots have TiO_2 content ranging between 62.23 and 82.42%. By converting the analyzed FeO content into Fe_2O_3 , the obtained values range between 15.22 and 34.83% and the corresponding total oxide sum of these spots ranges between 98.03 and 98.94%, respectively (Table V). There is a distinct reverse relation between TiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 at these spots. These spots are most probably pseudorutile or mixtures of rutile and hematite obtained by the alteration of contained ilmenite exsolved intergrowth.

In grain (8), spots 1-2 (Figure 4, Tables IV, V) are hematite and rutile in solid solution. Spots 3-6 do not give acceptable results using the ilmenite program. Spots 3-5 have TiO_2 content ranging between 63.66 and 64.72%. By converting the analyzed FeO content into Fe_2O_3 , the obtained values range between 25.94 and 33.24% (Table VIII). These spots are ferriferous rutile or pseudorutile obtained by the alteration of contained ilmenite exsolved intergrowth, as the last grain (7). Spot 6 is a definite silicate mineral (Table VIII) MgFeAl -silicate, with some of contained structural and/or molecular water.

4) Ferromagnetic Titanhematite

All the analyzed 6 grains (Figure 5, Tables VI, VII), are separated within the ferromagnetic fraction associated with magnetite and titanomagnetite grains. They are not contained within the final bulk ilmenite concentrate. In these grains, spot 5 of (4), spots 1-5 and 11 of (5), and spots 13, 14 of (6) do not give acceptable results. The other investigated spots (Figure 5, Tables VI, VII), of the grains are:

Grain (1): Spots 1-6 are martitized magnetite. In spot 1, the recorded contents of SiO_2 , MgO , CaO , and Al_2O_3 may be remnants of altered silicate mineral inclusions.

Grain (2): Spots 1, 2 are hematite while spots 3, 4 are remnants of magnetite.

Grain (3): Spots 1-5 (Figure 5) are titanomagnetite with TiO_2 content ranging between 13.67 and 17.03%. Spots 6-11 are titanhematite with TiO_2 content ranging between 22.93 and 26.5%. Spots 12, 13 are most probably pseudobrookite (Table VIII), while spot 14 is ferriilmenite.

Grain (4): Spots 1, 2 are pseudobrookite, while spot 5 is calcite (Table VIII). Spots 3, 4 are titanhematite after titanomagnetite.

Grain (5): Spots 1-5 are rutile (Table VII). Spots 6-8 are martitized titanomagnetite with TiO_2 content ranging between 8.77 and 9.55%. Spots 9, 10 are martitized titanomagnetite with relatively higher content of TiO_2 , which ranges between 17.8 and 19.54%. Spot 11 is martitized titanomagnetite into titanhematite and most of Fe_2O_3 content is leached (Table VIII). The recorded SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 are due to the increased water activity during the alteration and leaching of titanhematite.

Grain (6): Spots 1-9 are martitized titanomagnetite with TiO_2 content ranging between 13.43 and 24.37% (Tables VI, VII). Spots 10-12 are ilmenite (Tables VI, VII), spot 13 is leached ilmenite, and spot 14 is calcite (Table VIII).

Fig. 5. BSE images of various ferromagnetic titanhematite grains. They are most probably produced by the process of martitization after titanomagnetite.

TABLE IV. MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND MOLECULAR FORMULAE OF THE ANALYZED SPOTS OF THE VARIOUS TITANHEMATITE EXSOLVED INTERGROWN GRAINS OF FIGURE 4

Grain	Spot	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₅	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₅	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Ferrous Fe	Ferric Fe	Other cations	Ti	O
Fig. 4 (1)	1	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	88.88	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.35	89.36	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.40	98.29	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.35	99.18	0.01	1.98	0.01	0.01	3
	2	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.01	0.00	88.89	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.14	89.18	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.05	98.70	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.14	99.04	0.00	1.99	0.01	0.00	3
	3	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	88.89	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.23	89.27	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.11	98.64	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.23	99.12	0.00	1.99	0.01	0.00	3
	4	0.10	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	89.27	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.24	89.71	0.10	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.28	98.86	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.24	99.59	0.01	1.98	0.01	0.00	3
	5	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.00	89.41	0.00	0.03	0.06	0.26	89.88	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.00	0.08	99.25	0.00	0.03	0.06	0.26	99.80	0.00	1.99	0.01	0.01	3
	6	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	91.23	0.00	0.02	0.05	0.33	91.70	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.22	101.11	0.00	0.02	0.05	0.33	101.80	0.00	1.99	0.00	0.01	3
Fig. 4 (2)	1	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.05	87.74	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.17	88.19	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.05	0.07	97.40	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.17	97.92	0.00	1.99	0.01	0.00	3
	2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	88.34	0.01	0.19	0.04	0.17	88.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.12	98.01	0.01	0.19	0.04	0.17	98.57	0.00	1.99	0.01	0.00	3
	3	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.00	88.53	0.00	0.18	0.04	0.42	89.23	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.31	98.01	0.00	0.18	0.04	0.42	99.02	0.01	1.98	0.01	0.01	3
	4	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	89.05	0.00	0.19	0.02	0.42	89.76	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.31	98.60	0.00	0.19	0.02	0.42	99.61	0.01	1.98	0.01	0.01	3
	5	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.04	90.03	0.00	0.20	0.03	0.35	90.72	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.23	99.76	0.00	0.20	0.03	0.35	100.68	0.01	1.98	0.01	0.01	3
Fig. 4 (3)	1	0.33	0.24	0.04	0.09	0.00	86.44	0.30	0.36	0.12	1.49	89.43	0.33	0.24	0.04	0.09	0.00	1.14	94.77	0.30	0.36	0.12	1.49	98.90	0.03	1.90	0.06	0.03	3
	2	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.14	87.04	0.01	0.31	0.03	1.22	88.87	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.14	0.85	95.76	0.01	0.31	0.03	1.22	98.43	0.02	1.94	0.02	0.02	3
	3	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.05	87.39	0.03	0.31	0.05	1.20	89.14	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.95	96.03	0.03	0.31	0.05	1.20	98.73	0.02	1.94	0.02	0.02	3
	4	0.02	0.00	0.07	0.04	0.00	87.56	0.03	0.34	0.06	0.99	89.11	0.02	0.00	0.07	0.04	0.00	0.81	96.39	0.03	0.34	0.06	0.99	98.74	0.02	1.95	0.02	0.02	3
Fig. 4 (4)	1	0.00	0.05	2.77	0.03	0.07	42.44	0.00	0.41	0.05	49.90	95.71	0.00	0.05	2.77	0.03	0.07	41.90	0.60	0.00	0.41	0.05	49.90	95.77	0.92	0.01	0.08	0.99	3
	2	0.03	0.07	2.88	0.00	0.00	43.09	0.00	0.37	0.03	49.87	96.35	0.03	0.07	2.88	0.00	0.00	41.86	1.37	0.00	0.37	0.03	49.87	96.49	0.92	0.03	0.08	0.98	3
	3	5.64	0.96	0.06	0.11	0.00	73.79	0.84	0.77	0.08	0.86	83.10	5.64	0.96	0.06	0.11	0.00	5.60	75.75	0.84	0.77	0.08	0.86	90.67	0.13	1.60	0.34	0.02	3
	4	0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.00	79.32	0.02	0.74	0.08	0.97	81.44	0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.96	87.06	0.02	0.74	0.08	0.97	90.14	0.02	1.93	0.04	0.02	3
	5	0.16	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.00	79.63	0.04	0.78	0.11	0.94	81.75	0.16	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.00	0.90	87.46	0.04	0.78	0.11	0.94	90.49	0.02	1.93	0.04	0.02	3
	6	0.16	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.07	79.73	0.07	0.72	0.05	1.22	82.15	0.16	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.07	1.04	87.43	0.07	0.72	0.05	1.22	90.89	0.03	1.92	0.05	0.03	3
	7	0.24	0.06	0.00	0.04	0.00	80.37	0.08	0.70	0.03	0.81	82.31	0.24	0.06	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.86	88.33	0.08	0.70	0.03	0.81	91.13	0.02	1.93	0.04	0.02	3
	8	0.31	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.03	80.84	0.09	0.78	0.03	0.81	83.06	0.31	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.03	0.82	88.91	0.09	0.78	0.03	0.81	91.94	0.02	1.93	0.05	0.02	3
	9	0.12	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.00	80.94	0.07	0.75	0.08	0.82	82.90	0.12	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.00	0.72	89.12	0.07	0.75	0.08	0.82	91.80	0.02	1.94	0.04	0.02	3
	10	0.21	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.08	80.98	0.09	0.69	0.06	0.98	83.19	0.21	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.08	0.95	88.91	0.09	0.69	0.06	0.98	92.07	0.02	1.92	0.05	0.02	3
	11	0.21	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.04	81.18	0.04	0.69	0.04	1.12	83.39	0.21	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.04	1.13	88.94	0.04	0.69	0.04	1.12	92.28	0.03	1.92	0.04	0.02	3
	12	0.14	0.04	0.01	0.04	0.00	81.60	0.05	0.73	0.08	0.83	83.51	0.14	0.04	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.80	89.77	0.05	0.73	0.08	0.83	92.48	0.02	1.94	0.04	0.02	3
	13	0.20	0.04	0.08	0.06	0.00	81.83	0.05	0.74	0.08	0.91	84.00	0.20	0.04	0.08	0.06	0.00	0.83	89.99	0.05	0.74	0.08	0.91	92.99	0.02	1.93	0.05	0.02	3
Fig. 4 (5)	1	0.00	0.09	0.22	0.02	0.07	80.70	0.06	0.28	0.12	8.29	89.85	0.00	0.09	0.22	0.02	0.07	6.99	81.89	0.06	0.28	0.12	8.29	98.03	0.16	1.65	0.03	0.17	3
	2	0.00	0.06	0.16	0.01	0.05	80.97	0.03	0.33	0.09	8.53	90.22	0.00	0.06	0.16	0.01	0.05	7.35	81.79	0.03	0.33	0.09	8.53	98.40	0.16	1.65	0.02	0.17	3
	3	0.00	0.09	0.28	0.00	0.07	80.69	0.05	0.33	0.10	8.61	90.20	0.00	0.09	0.28	0.00	0.07	7.24	81.60	0.05	0.33	0.10	8.61	98.35	0.16	1.64	0.03	0.17	3
	4	0.00	0.09	0.17	0.01	0.04	81.00	0.07	0.29	0.06	8.78	90.50	0.00	0.09	0.17	0.01	0.04	7.52	81.63	0.07	0.29	0.06	8.78	98.66	0.17	1.64	0.02	0.18	3
	5	0.00	0.09	0.20	0.00	0.05	80.38	0.06	0.28	0.05	9.15	90.25	0.00	0.09	0.20	0.00	0.05	7.83	80.60	0.06	0.28	0.05	9.15	98.31	0.18	1.62	0.02	0.18	3
	6	0.01	0.04	0.09	0.00	0.01	67.02	0.04	0.29	0.06	24.05	91.60	0.01	0.04	0.09	0.00	0.01	21.48	50.59	0.04	0.29	0.06	24.05	96.66	0.48	1.02	0.02	0.49	3
	7	0.00	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.00	66.36	0.02	0.37	0.09	24.90	91.88	0.00	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.00	22.25	49.01	0.02	0.37	0.09	24.90	96.77	0.50	0.99	0.02	0.50	3
	8	0.00	0.04	0.08	0.00	0.00	62.34	0.03	0.43	0.05	28.10	91.07	0.00	0.04	0.08	0.00	0.00	25.13	41.34	0.03	0.43	0.05	28.10	95.20	0.57	0.84	0.02	0.57	3
	9	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.00	0.00	60.87	0.02	0.44	0.09	29.28	90.77	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.00	0.00	26.27	38.44	0.02	0.44	0.09	29.28	94.61	0.60	0.79	0.02	0.60	3
	10	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	59.09	0.04	0.39	0.11	30.96	90.66	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	27.77	34.80	0.04	0.39	0.11	30.96	94.14	0.63	0.72	0.02	0.64	3
	11	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.01	55.15	0.04	0.39	0.08	35.16	90.93	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.01	31.53	26.25	0.04	0.39	0.08	35.16	93.55	0.72	0.54	0.02	0.72	3
	12	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.03	53.60	0.04	0.48	0.07	37.13	91.42	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.03	33.31	22.55	0.04	0.48	0.07	37.13	93.67	0.76	0.46	0.02	0.76	3
	13	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.00	50.91	0.01	0.45	0.06	42.49	93.99	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.00	38.13	14.19	0.01	0.45	0.06	42.49	95.40	0.85	0.28	0.01	0.85	3
	14	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	46.28	0.02	0.47	0.08	45.73	92.62	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	41.08	5.78	0.02	0.47	0.08	45.73	93.20	0.93	0.12	0.01	0.93	3
Fig. 4 (6)	1	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02		88.60	0.00		0.03	2.17	90.83	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00	1.90	96.32	0.00	0.00	0.03	2.17	100.45	0.04	1.91	0.00	0.04	3
	2	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.01		88.18	0.00		0.03	2.38	90.64	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.01	0.00	2.09	95.64	0.00	0.00	0.03	2.38	100.19	0.05	1.90	0.00	0.05	3
	3	0.30	0.00																										

TABLE V. CALCULATED DIFFERENT MINERAL COMPONENT FRACTIONS OF THE SPOTS OF THE VARIOUS TITANHEMATITE EXSOLVED INTERGROWN GRAINS OF FIGURE 4

Grain	Spot	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Method	Gek	Pyr	Ilm	H	R	Total
Fig. 4 (1)	1	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.40	98.29	0.00	0.03	0.02	0.35	99.18	M2	0.00	0.00	0.66	98.41	0.00	99.07
	2	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.05	98.70	0.00	0.04	0.06	0.14	99.04	M1	0.00	0.12	0.11	98.76	0.01	99.00
	3	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.11	98.64	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.23	99.12	M1	0.04	0.10	0.23	98.64	0.03	99.03
	4	0.10	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.28	98.86	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.24	99.59	M2	0.07	0.00	0.36	99.04	0.00	99.47
	5	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.06	0.00	0.08	99.25	0.00	0.03	0.06	0.26	99.80	M1	0.10	0.05	0.16	99.31	0.08	99.70
	6	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.22	101.11	0.00	0.02	0.05	0.33	101.80	M1	0.01	0.14	0.47	101.16	0.00	101.78
Fig. 4 (2)	1	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.05	0.07	97.40	0.00	0.20	0.00	0.17	97.92	M1	0.00	0.07	0.15	97.40	0.05	97.67
	2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.12	98.01	0.01	0.19	0.04	0.17	98.57	M1	0.00	0.00	0.26	98.05	0.03	98.35
	3	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.31	98.01	0.00	0.18	0.04	0.42	99.02	M1	0.02	0.06	0.66	98.05	0.02	98.82
	4	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.31	98.60	0.00	0.19	0.02	0.42	99.61	M1	0.00	0.15	0.65	98.62	0.00	99.42
	5	0.02	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.23	99.76	0.00	0.20	0.03	0.35	100.68	M1	0.00	0.08	0.49	99.79	0.04	100.41
Fig. 4 (3)	1	0.33	0.24	0.04	0.09	0.00	1.14	94.77	0.30	0.36	0.12	1.49	98.90	M2	0.73	0.09	1.82	95.57	0.00	98.22
	2	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.14	0.85	95.76	0.01	0.31	0.03	1.22	98.43	M1	0.02	0.14	1.79	95.80	0.19	97.95
	3	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.95	96.03	0.03	0.31	0.05	1.20	98.73	M1	0.02	0.08	2.02	96.12	0.08	98.32
	4	0.02	0.00	0.07	0.04	0.00	0.81	96.39	0.03	0.34	0.06	0.99	98.74	M1	0.00	0.14	1.70	96.47	0.02	98.34
Fig. 4 (4)	1	0.00	0.05	2.77	0.03	0.07	41.90	0.60	0.00	0.41	0.05	49.90	95.77	M1	0.15	5.88	88.50	0.65	0.11	95.29
	2	0.03	0.07	2.88	0.00	0.00	41.86	1.37	0.00	0.37	0.03	49.87	96.49	M2	0.21	6.12	88.34	1.46	0.00	96.13
	3	5.64	0.96	0.06	0.11	0.00	5.60	75.75	0.84	0.77	0.08	0.86	90.67	M2	2.86	0.12	0.00	82.95	0.00	85.93
	4	0.20	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.96	87.06	0.02	0.74	0.08	0.97	90.14	M2	0.14	0.04	1.62	87.36	0.00	89.16
	5	0.16	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.00	0.90	87.46	0.04	0.78	0.11	0.94	90.49	M2	0.05	0.05	1.67	87.77	0.00	89.54
	6	0.16	0.04	0.04	0.07	0.07	1.04	87.43	0.07	0.72	0.05	1.22	90.89	M2	0.10	0.07	2.11	87.60	0.00	89.89
	7	0.24	0.06	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.86	88.33	0.08	0.70	0.03	0.81	91.13	M2	0.16	0.00	1.33	88.72	0.00	90.21
	8	0.31	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.03	0.82	88.91	0.09	0.78	0.03	0.81	91.94	M2	0.17	0.13	1.19	89.34	0.00	90.83
	9	0.12	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.00	0.72	89.12	0.07	0.75	0.08	0.82	91.80	M2	0.06	0.11	1.38	89.42	0.00	90.97
	10	0.21	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.08	0.95	88.91	0.09	0.69	0.06	0.98	92.07	M2	0.05	0.04	1.75	89.24	0.00	91.08
	11	0.21	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.04	1.13	88.94	0.04	0.69	0.04	1.12	92.28	M2	0.02	0.00	2.09	89.21	0.00	91.33
	12	0.14	0.04	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.80	89.77	0.05	0.73	0.08	0.83	92.48	M2	0.11	0.02	1.43	90.04	0.00	91.59
	13	0.20	0.04	0.08	0.06	0.00	0.83	89.99	0.05	0.74	0.08	0.91	92.99	M2	0.11	0.17	1.41	90.29	0.00	91.98
Fig. 4 (5)	1	0.00	0.09	0.22	0.02	0.07	6.99	81.89	0.06	0.28	0.12	8.29	98.03	M1	0.26	0.47	14.76	82.07	0.10	97.66
	2	0.00	0.06	0.16	0.01	0.05	7.35	81.79	0.03	0.33	0.09	8.53	98.40	M1	0.19	0.34	15.53	81.90	0.06	98.02
	3	0.00	0.09	0.28	0.00	0.07	7.24	81.60	0.05	0.33	0.10	8.61	98.35	M1	0.28	0.58	15.28	81.74	0.07	97.96
	4	0.00	0.09	0.17	0.01	0.04	7.52	81.63	0.07	0.29	0.06	8.78	98.66	M1	0.26	0.37	15.89	81.75	0.05	98.32
	5	0.00	0.09	0.20	0.00	0.05	7.83	80.60	0.06	0.28	0.05	9.15	98.31	M1	0.26	0.43	16.54	80.71	0.05	97.99
	6	0.01	0.04	0.09	0.00	0.01	21.48	50.59	0.04	0.29	0.06	24.05	96.66	M1	0.12	0.19	45.37	50.69	0.00	96.36
	7	0.00	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.00	22.25	49.01	0.02	0.37	0.09	24.90	96.77	M1	0.04	0.23	47.00	49.12	0.02	96.40
	8	0.00	0.04	0.08	0.00	0.00	25.13	41.34	0.03	0.43	0.05	28.10	95.20	M1	0.10	0.18	53.07	41.42	0.00	94.78
	9	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.00	0.00	26.27	38.44	0.02	0.44	0.09	29.28	94.61	M1	0.01	0.14	55.47	38.55	0.00	94.18
	10	0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	27.77	34.80	0.04	0.39	0.11	30.96	94.14	M1	0.02	0.10	58.66	34.94	0.02	93.74
	11	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.01	31.53	26.25	0.04	0.39	0.08	35.16	93.55	M1	0.00	0.17	66.59	26.37	0.03	93.15
	12	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.03	33.31	22.55	0.04	0.48	0.07	37.13	93.67	M1	0.00	0.14	70.34	22.66	0.03	93.18
	13	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.01	0.00	38.13	14.19	0.01	0.45	0.06	42.49	95.40	M1	0.05	0.09	80.54	14.26	0.01	94.96
	14	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.00	41.08	5.78	0.02	0.47	0.08	45.73	93.20	M1	0.04	0.04	86.76	5.88	0.02	92.73
Fig. 4 (6)	1	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02		1.90	96.32	0.00		0.03	2.17	100.45	M1	0.00	0.04	4.02	96.34	0.03	100.43
	2	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.01		2.09	95.64	0.00		0.03	2.38	100.19	M1	0.00	0.09	4.41	95.67	0.01	100.18
	3	0.30	0.00	0.00	0.21		3.00	93.26	0.00		0.03	3.24	100.04	M2	0.00	0.00	6.15	93.41	0.00	99.56
	4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02		2.43	93.82	0.00		0.04	2.72	99.03	M1	0.00	0.00	5.13	93.86	0.02	99.02
	5	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.03		7.86	83.30	0.00		0.04	8.82	100.09	M1	0.04	0.04	16.60	83.35	0.03	100.06
	6	0.53	0.00	0.04	0.02		7.35	83.83	0.00		0.03	7.55	99.33	M2	0.00	0.09	14.25	84.54	0.00	98.88
Fig. 4 (7)	1	0.00	5.25	1.01	0.00		9.06	60.38	0.53		0.03	21.61	97.87	M1	15.66	2.15	19.13	60.94	0.04	97.91
	2	0.00	3.82	0.73	0.01		19.77	40.54	0.50		0.06	30.38	95.80	M1	11.39	1.54	41.75	41.10	0.04	95.82
	3	0.00	2.96	0.53	0.01		23.24	36.54	0.43		0.00	32.30	96.00	M1	8.81	1.12	49.08	36.98	0.04	96.03
	4	0.00	1.26	0.28	0.02		31.35	0.00	0.19		0.00	62.23	95.33	M3	3.76	0.58	0.00	35.03	59.43	98.80
	5	0.00	0.96	0.20	0.03		23.93	0.00	0.17		0.02	70.07	95.37	M3	2.86	0.43	0.00	26.78	67.95	98.01
	6	0.01	1.35	0.31	0.01		24.06	0.00	0.17		0.00	70.37	96.27	M3	4.01	0.65	0.00	26.91	67.37	98.95
	7	0.00	0.90	0.23	0.01		16.52	0.00	0.09		0.05	78.69	96.49	M3	2.68	0.49	0.00	18.50	76.65	98.33
	8	0.00	0.71	0.20	0.01		13.70	0.00	0.08		0.00	82.42	97.12	M3	2.11	0.43	0.00	15.30	80.80	98.64
Fig. 4 (8)	1	0.00	1.19	0.62	0.00		24.61	37.64	0.52		0.00	30.43	95.02	M1	3.56	1.32	51.98	38.16	0.02	95.03
	2	0.02	1.76	1.12	0.01		27.88	28.24	0.44		0.03	35.74	95.23	M1	5.25	2.38	58.89	28.71	0.00	95.23

TABLE VI. MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND MOLECULAR FORMULAE OF THE SPOTS OF THE FERROMAGNETIC TITANHEMATITE EXSOLVED INTERGROWN GRAINS OF FIGURE 5

Grains	Spot	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Ferrous Fe	Ferric Fe	Other cations	Ti	O	
Fig. 5 (1)	1	6.66	0.49	0.03	0.15	0.01	78.05	2.09	0.29	0.04	0.20	88.00	6.66	0.49	0.03	0.15	0.01	7.03	78.90	2.09	0.29	0.04	0.20	95.88	0.16	1.57	0.37	0.00	3	
	2	0.51	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.17	86.16	0.08	0.27	0.04	0.57	87.86	0.51	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.17	0.88	94.74	0.08	0.27	0.04	0.57	97.32	0.02	1.94	0.04	0.01	3	
	3	0.38	0.05	0.00	0.03	0.00	88.97	0.04	0.29	0.03	0.11	89.90	0.38	0.05	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.43	98.36	0.04	0.29	0.03	0.11	99.73	0.01	1.97	0.03	0.00	3	
	4	0.29	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.01	89.02	0.00	0.26	0.02	0.18	89.84	0.29	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.40	98.45	0.00	0.26	0.02	0.18	99.68	0.01	1.97	0.02	0.00	3	
	5	0.80	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	89.19	0.00	0.30	0.07	0.33	90.71	0.80	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	1.23	97.72	0.00	0.30	0.07	0.33	100.4	0.03	1.94	0.04	0.01	3	
	6	0.12	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.00	89.67	0.00	0.29	0.07	0.24	90.48	0.12	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.26	99.34	0.00	0.29	0.07	0.24	100.4	0.01	1.98	0.02	0.00	3	
	7	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	94.07	0.00	0.28	0.03	0.23	94.62	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	104.2	0.00	0.28	0.03	0.23	105.0	0.00	1.98	0.01	0.00	3	
Fig. 5 (2)	1	0.06	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.00	87.62	0.01	0.06	0.09	0.89	88.83	0.06	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.76	96.50	0.01	0.06	0.09	0.89	98.47	0.02	1.96	0.01	0.02	3	
	2	0.06	0.01	0.23	0.00	0.00	88.24	0.00	0.05	0.03	0.22	88.84	0.06	0.01	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.02	98.01	0.00	0.05	0.03	0.22	98.63	0.00	1.99	0.01	0.00	3	
	3	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.12	92.38	0.00	0.12	0.01	0.35	93.16	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.12	0.01	102.6	0.00	0.12	0.01	0.35	103.4	0.00	1.98	0.01	0.01	3	
	4	0.00	0.02	0.19	0.00	0.09	92.78	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.27	93.41	0.00	0.02	0.19	0.00	0.09	0.07	103.1	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.27	103.7	0.00	1.99	0.01	0.01	3	
Fig. 5 (3)	1	0.02	2.63	0.81	0.00	0.05	76.05	2.50	0.70	0.07	13.6	96.51	0.02	2.63	0.81	0.00	0.05	6.78	76.96	2.50	0.70	0.07	13.6	104.2	0.14	1.41	0.26	0.25	3	
	2	0.08	2.42	0.93	0.01	0.00	74.54	0.93	0.75	0.00	14.8	94.48	0.08	2.42	0.93	0.01	0.00	8.18	73.72	0.93	0.75	0.00	14.8	101.8	0.17	1.39	0.20	0.28	3	
	3	0.04	2.19	0.79	0.02	0.13	71.90	1.64	0.75	0.03	16.2	93.76	0.04	2.19	0.79	0.02	0.13	9.85	68.94	1.64	0.75	0.03	16.2	100.6	0.21	1.31	0.22	0.31	3	
	4	0.08	2.13	0.86	0.00	0.14	73.17	1.50	0.71	0.00	16.3	94.93	0.08	2.13	0.86	0.00	0.14	9.98	70.20	1.50	0.71	0.00	16.3	101.9	0.21	1.32	0.21	0.31	3	
	5	0.05	2.32	0.98	0.00	0.18	72.44	1.23	0.71	0.04	17.0	94.97	0.05	2.32	0.98	0.00	0.18	10.0	69.26	1.23	0.71	0.04	17.0	101.8	0.21	1.30	0.21	0.32	3	
	6	0.12	0.83	0.20	0.03	0.15	66.73	1.30	0.87	0.08	22.9	93.23	0.12	0.83	0.20	0.03	0.15	18.9	53.11	1.30	0.87	0.08	22.9	98.54	0.41	1.04	0.12	0.45	3	
	7	0.06	1.28	0.15	0.01	0.09	65.40	1.98	0.85	0.02	23.8	93.69	0.06	1.28	0.15	0.01	0.09	19.0	51.53	1.98	0.85	0.02	23.8	98.84	0.41	1.00	0.16	0.46	3	
	8	0.08	0.89	0.20	0.01	0.09	65.09	1.53	0.91	0.02	24.1	93.01	0.08	0.89	0.20	0.01	0.09	19.9	50.15	1.53	0.91	0.02	24.1	98.02	0.43	0.98	0.13	0.47	3	
	9	0.07	1.29	0.45	0.01	0.05	64.66	1.16	0.84	0.01	25.7	94.30	0.07	1.29	0.45	0.01	0.05	20.4	49.12	1.16	0.84	0.01	25.7	99.21	0.44	0.95	0.14	0.50	3	
	10	0.10	0.92	0.30	0.03	0.09	65.40	1.10	0.87	0.06	26.1	95.04	0.10	0.92	0.30	0.03	0.09	21.6	48.64	1.10	0.87	0.06	26.1	99.90	0.46	0.94	0.12	0.50	3	
	11	0.06	1.65	0.36	0.00	0.16	61.06	2.94	0.93	0.04	26.5	93.69	0.06	1.65	0.36	0.00	0.16	20.4	45.09	2.94	0.93	0.04	26.5	98.19	0.44	0.87	0.21	0.51	3	
	14	0.06	0.34	0.16	0.01	0.00	47.19	0.49	1.01	0.04	44.3	93.65	0.06	0.34	0.16	0.01	0.00	39.1	8.90	0.49	1.01	0.04	44.3	94.54	0.87	0.18	0.06	0.89	3	
	Fig. 5 (4)	3	0.14	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.00	85.83	0.01	0.32	0.09	4.28	90.77	0.14	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.00	3.87	91.06	0.01	0.32	0.09	4.28	99.86	0.09	1.81	0.02	0.09	3
		4	0.02	0.04	0.07	0.00	0.00	86.01	0.00	0.35	0.10	3.97	90.57	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.00	0.00	3.47	91.70	0.00	0.35	0.10	3.97	99.73	0.08	1.83	0.02	0.08	3
Fig. 5 (5)	6	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01		84.72	0.00		0.01	8.77	93.53	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	7.90	85.35	0.00	0.00	0.01	8.77	102.0	0.17	1.66	0.00	0.17	3	
	7	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00		83.29	0.00		0.00	9.55	92.86	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	8.56	83.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	9.55	101.1	0.19	1.63	0.00	0.19	3	
	8	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.04		82.65	0.02		0.02	9.41	92.14	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	8.43	82.47	0.02	0.00	0.02	9.41	100.3	0.18	1.63	0.00	0.19	3	
	9	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03		77.55	0.00		0.01	17.8	95.43	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.00	15.9	68.39	0.00	0.00	0.01	17.8	102.2	0.34	1.31	0.00	0.34	3	
10	0.28	0.05	0.00	0.03		73.08	0.06		0.02	19.5	93.07	0.28	0.05	0.00	0.03	0.00	17.7	61.44	0.06	0.00	0.02	19.5	99.21	0.39	1.21	0.02	0.39	3		
Fig. 5 (6)	1	0.04	2.99	1.39	0.02	0.28	73.61	1.82	0.47	0.03	13.4	94.07	0.04	2.99	1.39	0.02	0.28	5.12	76.10	1.82	0.47	0.03	13.4	101.6	0.11	1.43	0.28	0.25	3	
	2	0.02	2.25	1.03	0.08	0.13	72.32	1.14	0.43	0.05	16.5	94.03	0.02	2.25	1.03	0.08	0.13	9.68	69.60	1.14	0.43	0.05	16.5	100.9	0.20	1.32	0.20	0.32	3	
	3	0.08	2.43	0.99	0.04	0.21	71.22	1.49	0.46	0.05	18.0	95.06	0.08	2.43	0.99	0.04	0.21	10.7	67.14	1.49	0.46	0.05	18.0	101.7	0.23	1.26	0.22	0.34	3	
	4	0.01	2.10	1.06	0.04	0.14	69.14	1.09	0.51	0.02	18.5	92.63	0.01	2.10	1.06	0.04	0.14	11.7	63.82	1.09	0.51	0.02	18.5	99.00	0.25	1.24	0.19	0.36	3	
	5	0.03	1.74	0.73	0.01	0.14	69.80	0.81	0.50	0.03	19.7	93.56	0.03	1.74	0.73	0.01	0.14	13.8	62.16	0.81	0.50	0.03	19.7	99.77	0.30	1.20	0.15	0.38	3	
	6	0.06	1.56	0.61	0.03	0.00	70.56	0.44	0.53	0.00	20.4	94.24	0.06	1.56	0.61	0.03	0.00	15.0	61.69	0.44	0.53	0.00	20.4	100.4	0.32	1.19	0.12	0.39	3	
	7	0.00	2.03	1.18	0.02	0.21	67.25	1.27	0.52	0.05	22.0	94.62	0.00	2.03	1.18	0.02	0.21	14.8	58.22	1.27	0.52	0.05	22.0	100.4	0.31	1.11	0.19	0.42	3	
	8	0.23	2.42	0.76	0.01	0.12	63.46	0.99	0.48	0.08	22.9	91.53	0.23	2.42	0.76	0.01	0.12	15.7	52.99	0.99	0.48	0.08	22.9	96.82	0.34	1.04	0.20	0.45	3	
	9	0.01	1.88	0.94	0.00	0.18	63.04	1.04	0.52	0.00	24.3	91.97	0.01	1.88	0.94	0.00	0.18	17.4	50.62	1.04	0.52	0.00	24.3	97.02	0.38	1.00	0.17	0.48	3	
	10	0.03	0.89	0.34	0.03	0.00	44.02	0.41	0.64	0.00	47.7	94.11	0.03	0.89	0.34	0.03	0.00	41.0	3.32	0.41	0.64	0.00	47.7							

It was noticed that the ilmenite enriched with relatively higher content of MgO and individual TiO₂ is unstable and alters partially into rutile and hematite. Increased TiO₂ content leads to the exsolution of rutile bodies. The difference in the geometry of the associated mixed mineral crystal structures and their corresponding contents inside the rutile-ilmenite exsolved intergrowth in addition to the prevailing physical conditions may be responsible of the different obtained textures of such intergrowth.

The titanhematite intergrowth includes 3 fabrics arranged in a decreasing order of abundance as: ilmenite-hematite, rutile-hematite, and rutile-ilmenite-hematite. The TiO₂ content attains up to 9.15%. Both MgO and MnO have minimum values and

do not follow Fe₂O₃. In the titanhematite host, MgO ranges between 0 and 0.2%, while MnO ranges between 0 and 0.3%. Only in the case of exsolved rutile within the titanhematite host, the titanhematite host contained MgO ranges between 1.2 and 5.3%, while the MnO content ranges between 0.5 and 1.1%. The exsolved rutile MgO content ranges between 0.6 and 1.3%, while the MnO content ranges between 0.2 and 0.7%.

It was found that the contained exsolved ilmenite may be altered into pseudorutile or mixed rutile and hematite fabric. In some homogeneous titanhematite or mixed rutile-hematite, the Fe₂O₃ content can be replaced with SiO₂. In all types of the titanhematite intergrowth, the Cr₂O₃ contents range between 0 and 0.1%.

TABLE VII. CALCULATED DIFFERENT MINERAL COMPONENT FRACTIONS OF THE SPOTS OF THE VARIOUS FERROMAGNETIC TITANHEMATITE EXSOLVED INTERGROWN GRAINS OF FIGURE 5

Grain	Spot	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total	Method	Gek	Pyr	Ilm	H	R	Total	
Fig. 5 (1)	1	6.66	0.49	0.03	0.15	0.01	7.03	78.90	2.09	0.29	0.04	0.20	95.88	M2	1.47	0.07	0.00	90.24		91.77	
	2	0.51	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.17	0.88	94.74	0.08	0.27	0.04	0.57	97.32	M2	0.01	0.00	1.07	95.33		96.40	
	3	0.38	0.05	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.43	98.36	0.04	0.29	0.03	0.11	99.73	M2	0.15	0.00	0.03	98.94		99.12	
	4	0.29	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.40	98.45	0.00	0.26	0.02	0.18	99.68	M2	0.10	0.07	0.15	98.91		99.22	
	5	0.80	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	1.23	97.72	0.00	0.30	0.07	0.33	100.47	M2	0.00	0.05	0.58	98.88		99.51	
	6	0.12	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.26	99.34	0.00	0.29	0.07	0.24	100.40	M2	0.03	0.11	0.31	99.58		100.03	
	7	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	104.29	0.00	0.28	0.03	0.23	105.04	M1	0.01	0.00	0.42	104.32	0.00	104.76	
Fig. 5 (2)	1	0.06	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.76	96.50	0.01	0.06	0.09	0.89	98.47	M2	0.00	0.24	1.46	96.74		98.44	
	2	0.06	0.01	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.02	98.01	0.00	0.05	0.03	0.22	98.63	M2	0.01	0.49	0.00	97.99		98.50	
	3	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.12	0.01	102.61	0.00	0.12	0.01	0.35	103.41	M1	0.00	0.41	0.03	102.62	0.11	103.17	
	4	0.00	0.02	0.19	0.00	0.09	-0.07	103.16	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.27	103.72	M2	0.06	0.41	0.01	103.14		103.63	
Fig. 5 (3)	1	0.02	2.63	0.81	0.00	0.05	6.78	76.96	2.50	0.70	0.07	13.67	104.20	M1	7.85	1.72	14.31	79.54	0.04	103.45	
	2	0.08	2.42	0.93	0.01	0.00	8.18	73.72	0.93	0.75	0.00	14.83	101.84	M2	7.21	1.98	17.11	74.70		101.00	
	3	0.04	2.19	0.79	0.02	0.13	9.85	68.94	1.64	0.75	0.03	16.27	100.65	M1	6.52	1.68	20.79	70.61	0.12	99.72	
	4	0.08	2.13	0.86	0.00	0.14	9.98	70.20	1.50	0.71	0.00	16.34	101.94	M1	6.36	1.83	21.09	71.70	0.06	101.03	
	5	0.05	2.32	0.98	0.00	0.18	10.09	69.26	1.23	0.71	0.04	17.03	101.89	M1	6.92	2.07	21.32	70.53	0.13	100.97	
	6	0.12	0.83	0.20	0.03	0.15	18.93	53.11	1.30	0.87	0.08	22.93	98.54	M1	2.48	0.43	39.98	54.49	0.02	97.39	
	7	0.06	1.28	0.15	0.01	0.09	19.02	51.53	1.98	0.85	0.02	23.85	98.84	M1	3.81	0.31	40.16	53.54	0.03	97.85	
	8	0.08	0.89	0.20	0.01	0.09	19.95	50.15	1.53	0.91	0.02	24.18	98.02	M1	2.67	0.43	42.14	51.70	0.01	96.95	
	9	0.07	1.29	0.45	0.01	0.05	20.45	49.12	1.16	0.84	0.01	25.76	99.21	M1	3.84	0.95	43.19	50.29	-0.01	98.26	
	10	0.10	0.92	0.30	0.03	0.09	21.62	48.64	1.10	0.87	0.06	26.18	99.90	M1	2.74	0.63	45.66	49.80	0.00	98.83	
	11	0.06	1.65	0.36	0.00	0.16	20.47	45.09	2.94	0.93	0.04	26.50	98.19	M1	4.92	0.75	43.23	48.07	0.09	97.07	
	14	0.06	0.34	0.16	0.01	0.00	39.18	8.90	0.49	1.01	0.04	44.35	94.54	M2	1.02	0.34	82.63	9.49		93.48	
	Fig. 5 (4)	3	0.14	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.00	3.87	91.06	0.01	0.32	0.09	4.28	99.86	M2	0.13	0.05	7.91	91.29		99.38
		4	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.00	0.00	3.47	91.70	0.00	0.35	0.10	3.97	99.73	M2	0.11	0.14	7.26	91.92		99.42
Fig. 5 (5)	1	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02		0.46	0.00	0.00		0.02	100.16	100.67		0.00	0.00		0.53	100.16	100.69	
	2	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03		0.44	0.00	0.00		0.02	99.91	100.44		0.01	0.05		0.51	99.88	100.45	
	3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.55	0.00	0.00		0.05	99.88	100.47		0.00	0.01		0.65	99.87	100.53	
	4	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.09		0.51	0.00	0.00		0.03	99.57	100.33		0.00	0.00		0.59	99.57	100.16	
	5	0.14	0.01	0.00	0.07		0.51	0.00	0.00		0.04	99.66	100.42		0.02	0.00		0.60	99.64	100.27	
	6	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	7.90	85.35	0.00	0.00	0.01	8.77	102.06	M2	0.00	0.00	16.66	85.40		102.06	
	7	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	8.56	83.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	9.55	101.15	M1	0.05	0.00	18.08	83.02	0.00	101.15	
	8	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	8.43	82.47	0.02	0.00	0.02	9.41	100.38	M1	0.00	0.00	17.79	82.50	0.05	100.34	
	9	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.00	15.99	68.39	0.00	0.00	0.01	17.80	102.27	M1	0.01	0.03	33.77	68.40	0.00	102.21	
	10	0.28	0.05	0.00	0.03	0.00	17.78	61.44	0.06	0.00	0.02	19.54	99.21	M2	0.16	0.00	36.93	61.86		98.95	
Fig. 5 (6)	1	0.04	2.99	1.39	0.02	0.28	5.12	76.10	1.82	0.47	0.03	13.43	101.67	M1	8.92	2.96	10.81	77.94	0.28	100.90	
	2	0.02	2.25	1.03	0.08	0.13	9.68	69.60	1.14	0.43	0.05	16.59	100.98	M1	6.71	2.20	20.43	70.78	0.23	100.35	
	3	0.08	2.43	0.99	0.04	0.21	10.79	67.14	1.49	0.46	0.05	18.08	101.77	M1	7.25	2.11	22.80	68.68	0.17	101.00	
	4	0.01	2.10	1.06	0.04	0.14	11.70	63.82	1.09	0.51	0.02	18.53	99.00	M1	6.26	2.24	24.71	64.93	0.19	98.33	
	5	0.03	1.74	0.73	0.01	0.14	13.85	62.16	0.81	0.50	0.03	19.78	99.77	M1	5.20	1.56	29.25	63.00	0.12	99.12	
	6	0.06	1.56	0.61	0.03	0.00	15.04	61.69	0.44	0.53	0.00	20.46	100.40	M2	4.65	1.29	31.72	62.13		99.80	
	7	0.00	2.03	1.18	0.02	0.21	14.84	58.22	1.27	0.52	0.05	22.09	100.44	M1	6.07	2.52	31.34	59.54	0.25	99.71	
	8	0.23	2.42	0.76	0.01	0.12	15.77	52.99	0.99	0.48	0.08	22.99	96.82	M2	7.21	1.61	32.98	54.26		96.06	
	9	0.01	1.88	0.94	0.00	0.18	17.48	50.62	1.04	0.52	0.00	24.37	97.02	M1	5.60	1.99	36.92	51.66	0.17	96.34	
	10	0.03	0.89	0.34	0.03	0.00	41.03	3.32	0.41	0.64	0.00	47.76	94.44	M1	2.65	0.72	86.65	3.73	0.01	93.77	
	11	0.35	0.08	0.19	0.19	0.16	39.40	0.00	0.39	0.59	0.16	49.21	90.16	M2	0.23	0.39	83.21	0.54	5.05	89.43	
	12	0.05	0.76	0.23	0.03	0.00	42.84	1.50	0.34	0.60	0.00	49.38	95.74	M1	2.28	0.49	90.47	1.84	0.00	95.07	

TABLE VIII. ORIGINAL MICROPROBE CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF SOME SPOTS OF THE GRAINS FROM FIGURES 4, 5

Grain	Spot	SiO ₂	MgO	MnO	CaO	ZnO	FeO	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₃	Cr ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Total
Fig. 4 (3)	5	96.02	0.16	0.00	0.04	0.00	1.72	0.00	0.81	0.03	0.00	0.36	99.14
	6	0.32	0.03	0.22	54.49	0.67	2.33	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.05	0.11	58.25
	7	0.21	0.00	0.10	55.49	0.72	1.96	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.07	58.59
Fig. 4 (6)	7	37.45	0.01	0.18	23.10		14.45	0.00	22.45		0.04	0.10	97.78
	8	49.84	0.04	0.19	19.54		10.26	0.00	19.14		0.03	0.09	99.13
	9	90.85	0.00	0.00	0.16		1.13	0.00	0.03		0.01	8.51	100.68
	10	85.10	0.13	0.00	0.07		0.78	0.00	0.90		0.02	17.19	104.19
	11	63.75	0.91	0.00	0.19		2.25	0.00	1.71		0.00	28.06	96.87
	12	5.57	0.02	0.00	0.11		1.29	0.00	0.68		0.03	94.98	102.69
Fig. 4 (8)	13	93.90	0.17	0.00	1.28		1.21	0.00	3.08		0.03	0.09	99.75
	3	0.00	0.57	0.29	0.02		29.92	0.00	0.22		0.04	63.66	94.72
	4	0.00	1.05	0.69	0.01		28.45	0.00	0.23		0.00	64.72	95.15
	5	0.01	0.63	0.50	0.00		23.35	0.00	0.18		0.00	69.55	94.22
Fig. 5 (3)	6	50.05	3.08	0.12	0.30		11.12	0.00	21.99		0.00	1.67	88.33
	12	0.00	1.9	0.5	0.00	0.1	53.4	0.0	3.5	0.8	0.0	33.4	93.8
Fig. 5 (4)	13	0.0	1.4	0.3	0	0.1	53.5	0.0	2.5	0.9	0.0	35.8	94.6
	1	0.89	0.03	0.00	0.10	0.00	57.48	0.00	0.64	0.47	0.11	31.91	91.62
	2	0.93	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.00	63.20	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.07	26.75	91.39
Fig. 5 (5)	5	0.34	0.10	0.09	54.08	0.62	1.98	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.30	57.53
	11	11.57	1.24	0.04	0.20		2.83	0.00	8.35		0.00	58.65	82.88
Fig. 5 (6)	13	0.03	0.60	0.25	0.01	0.03	37.93	0.00	0.25	0.59	0.00	56.80	96.50
	14	1.27	0.23	0.04	44.53	0.29	4.51	0.00	0.06	0.10	0.02	5.94	57.00

Some ferromagnetic titanhematite varieties separated from the fraction of magnetite are detected. They are produced by the martitization of titanomagnetite. Their TiO₂ content attains up to 24.37%. In these grains, the contents of Cr₂O₃, MgO, and MnO range between 0.0-0.2, 0.0-3, and 0.0-1.4% respectively. In fact, some of the exsolved intergrown textures included within the grains of the ilmenite concentrate contain relatively higher values of Cr₂O₃ content, their distribution is relatively lower, and they are the only reason for the increased Cr₂O₃ content in the obtained ilmenite concentrate. In fact, several varieties of chromite and chromspinel mineral grains are found and represent 1.1% of the detected bulk ilmenite grains. In these grains, the contents of Cr₂O₃, MgO, V₂O₃, and Al₂O₃ range between 16.69-56.72, 0.54-17.33, 0.14-0.58, and 1.33-38.79% respectively.

Although it is rarely met with one of these high chromium grains within the ilmenite concentrate, the relatively finer grain sizes of most of them could lead to the separation for some of them to ilmenite rather than to separated ferromagnetic fractions. Especially with the current used types of magnetic separators. Hence, the problem of high Cr₂O₃ content of the Egyptian beach ilmenite concentrate is an ore dressing problem rather than a mineralogical one.

One of the most important conclusions is that in the case of the ilmenite of the El Burullus-Baltim sand dunes, it is expected that a considerable fraction of ilmenite can be obtained with relatively lower Cr₂O₃ content. The reason for this is that most of the heavy and economic interesting minerals are concentrated in relatively coarser grain sizes than those of beach sediments. So, the associated relatively finer chromite and chromspinel grains will be in minimum contents.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. A. Mahessar *et al.*, "Sediment Transport Dynamics in the Upper Nara Canal Off-taking from Sukkur Barrage of Indus River," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6563–6569, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3924>.
- [2] E. M. Kara, M. Meghachou, and N. Aboubekr, "Contribution of Particles Size Ranges to Sand Friction," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 497–501, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.361>.
- [3] N. P.H. Padmanabhan, T. Sreenivas, and N. K. Rao, "Processing of Ores of Titanium, Zirconium, Hafnium, Niobium, Tantalum, Molybdenum, Rhenium, and Tungsten: International Trends and the Indian Scene," *High Temperature Materials and Processes*, vol. 9, no. 2–4, pp. 217–248, Jul. 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1515/HTMP.1990.9.2-4.217>.
- [4] A. Stwertka, *A guide to the elements*. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press, 1998.
- [5] F. Habashi, *Principles of Extractive Metallurgy: Pyrometallurgy*. Oxford, UK: Gordon and Breach, 1993.
- [6] E. Barbara and S. Hawkins, Eds., "Thorium and Thorium Compounds to Vitamins," in *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*, vol. A27, 1996, pp. 95–122.
- [7] T. S. Mackey, "Upgrading ilmenite into a high-grade synthetic rutile," *JOM*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 59–64, Apr. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03220676>.
- [8] A.-A. M. Abdel-Karim, S. M. Zaid, M. I. Moustafa, and M. G. Barakat, "Mineralogy, chemistry and radioactivity of the heavy minerals in the black sands, along the northern coast of Egypt," *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, vol. 123, pp. 10–20, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2016.07.005>.
- [9] A.-A. M. Abdel-Karim, M. I. Moustafa, A. H. El-Afandy, and M. G. Barakat, "Mineralogy, Chemical Characteristics and Upgrading of Beach Ilmenite of the Top Meter of Black Sand Deposits of the Kafr Al-Sheikh Governorate, Northern Egypt," *Acta Geologica Sinica*, vol. 91, no. 4, pp. 1326–1338, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-6724.13364>.
- [10] A. A. Dewedar, "Comparative studies on the heavy minerals in some black sands deposits from Sinai and east Rosetta with contribution to the mineralogy and economics of their garnets," Ph.D. dissertation, El Menoufia University, Shibin El Kom, Egypt, 1997.
- [11] A. A. El-Kammar, A. A. Ragab, and M. I. Moustafa, "Geochemistry of economic heavy minerals from Rosetta black sand of Egypt," *Journal of King Abdulaziz University: Earth Sciences*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 69–97, 2011, <https://doi.org/10.4197/Ear.22-2.4>.

- [12] N. M. Hammoud, "Concentration of monazite from Egyptian black sands, employing industrial techniques," M.S. thesis, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt, 1966.
- [13] N. M. S. Hammoud, "A process for recovery of low chromium high grade ilmenite from north Egyptian beach deposits," in *Proceedings, 11th Indust. Mineral Process Conference*, Sardegna, Italy, 1975.
- [14] M. A. Mikhail, "Distribution and sedimentation of ilmenite in black sands, west of Rosetta," M.S. thesis, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt, 1971.
- [15] M. I. Moustafa, "Mineralogy and beneficiation of some economic minerals in the Egyptian black sands," Ph.D. dissertation, Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt, 1999.
- [16] R. M. Tyler and R. C. A. Minnitt, "A review of sub-Saharan heavy mineral sand deposits : implications for new projects in southern Africa," *Journal of the Southern African Institute of Mining and Metallurgy*, vol. 104, no. 2, pp. 89–99, Mar. 2004, https://doi.org/10.10520/AJA0038223X_2869.
- [17] M. A. Mandour, T. Chernet, and M. I. Moustafa, "Applied mineralogical studies on Egyptian sand ilmenite concentrates," in *Seventh Biennial Sgs Meeting on Mineral Exploration and Sustainable Development*, Athens, Greece, 2003, pp. 903–906.
- [18] M. F. R. Fouda, R. S. Amin, H. I. Saleh, A. A. Labib, and H. A. Mousa, "Preparation and characterization of nanosized Titania prepared from beach black sands broad on Mediterranean Sea Coast in Egypt Via reaction with acids," *Australian Journal of Basic Applied Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 4540–4553, 2010.
- [19] N. A. El-Hussiny, T. A. Lasheen, and M. E. H. Shalabi, "Kinetic reduction of Rosetta ilmenite with coke Breeze and Beneficiation of the product," *The Journal of ORE DRESSING*, vol. 10, no. 20, pp. 16–23, Jan. 2008.
- [20] M. I. Moustafa, M. A. Tashkandi, and A. M. El-Sherif, "Detecting Mineral Resources and Suggesting a Physical Concentration Flowsheet for Economic Minerals at the Northern Border Region of Saudi Arabia," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8617–8627, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4894>.
- [21] M. I. Moustafa, "Some Mineralogical Characteristics of the Egyptian Black Sand Beach Ilmenite: Homogeneous Ilmenite and Titanhematite-Ferriilmenite Grains-Part I," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 9614-9631, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5296>.
- [22] E. F. Stumpfl, "Erzmikroskopische untersuchungen an schwermineralien in sanden," *Geol.Jarb.*, vol. 73, pp. 685–723, 1958.
- [23] E. Z. Basta and M. A. Takla, "Mineralogy and Origin of Abu Ghalaga Ilmenite Occurrence, Eastern Desert," *Journal of Geology*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 87–124, 1968.
- [24] N. K. Rao and G. V. U. Rao, "Intergrowths in ilmenite of the beach sands of Kerala," *Mineralogical magazine and journal of the Mineralogical Society*, vol. 35, no. 269, pp. 118–130, Mar. 1965, <https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.1965.035.269.14>.
- [25] E. Z. Basta, "New Data on the System Fe₂O₃- FeTiO₃-TiO₂ (Ferri-Ilmenite and Titanom-agnetite)," *Proceeding Egyptian Academic Science*, vol. 14, pp. 1–15, 1959.
- [26] P. Ramdohr, *Die Erzminerale in gewöhnlichen magmatischen Gesteinen*. Berlin, Germany: Verlag der Wissenschaften, 1940.
- [27] J. R. Balsley and A. F. Buddington, "Iron-titanium oxide minerals, rocks, and aeromagnetic anomalies of the Adirondack area, New York," *Economic Geology*, vol. 53, no. 7, pp. 777–805, Nov. 1958, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gsecongeo.53.7.777>.
- [28] W. Uytendogaardt, *Tables for microscopic identification of ore minerals*, Second Edition. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier, 1971.
- [29] S. E. Haggerty, "Oxide textures; a mini-atlas," *Reviews in Mineralogy and Geochemistry*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 129–219, Jan. 1991.
- [30] P. Ramdohr, *The Ore Minerals and Their Intergrowths*. Oxford, UK: Pergamon Press, 1980.
- [31] A. B. Edwards, *Textures of the ore minerals and their significance*. Melbourne, VIC, Australia: Australasian Institute of Mining and Metallurgy, 1947.
- [32] P. Ramdohr, *Die Beziehungen von Fe-Ti-Erzen aus magmatischen Gesteinen*. Valtioneuvoston kirjapaino, 1956.

Road Segmentation in High-Resolution Images Using Deep Residual Networks

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Abstract-Automatic road detection from remote sensing images is a vital application for traffic management, urban planning, and disaster management. The presence of occlusions like shadows of buildings, trees, and flyovers in high-resolution images and misclassifications in databases create obstacles in the road detection task. Therefore, an automatic road detection system is required to detect roads in the presence of occlusions. This paper presents a deep convolutional neural network to address the problem of road detection, consisting of an encoder-decoder architecture. The architecture contains a U-Net with residual blocks. U-Net allows the transfer of low-level features to the high-level, helping the network to learn low-level details. Residual blocks help maintain the network's training performance, which may deteriorate due to a deep network. The encoder and decoder structures generate a feature map and classify pixels into road and non-road classes, respectively. Experimentation was performed on the Massachusetts road dataset. The results showed that the proposed model gave better accuracy than current state-of-the-art methods.

Keywords-U-network; residual block; encoder; decoder

I. INTRODUCTION

Remote Sensing (RS) is one of the most essential applications. It is related to the analysis and identification of features by measuring the physical parameters of an object at some distance with the help of electromagnetic radiation. Target discrimination is possible using different characteristics of sensors such as temporal, spatial, and spectral [1]. Due to the improvements in RS technology, high-resolution images with adequate spectral and temporal information are available for different applications such as disaster management, water source, land utilization, marine, glacier monitoring, urban city planning, etc. These high-resolution images are considered a primary database for automatic road extraction methods.

Automatic road detection from remotely sensed images is an essential task for many applications such as urban planning, geographic information systems, map updates, and automatic vehicle navigation [2]. Various methods to address the problem of road detection have been presented, but it is still a challenging task due to the presence of occlusions, building shadows, and complex backgrounds in high-resolution images.

These noise elements result in a false and discontinuous segmentation of roads. Manual road detection is time-consuming, complex, and involves human interpretation. Artificial intelligence and deep learning have made automatic road detection more efficient and accurate than manual methods. Road detection methods are of two types: road detection and centerline extraction [3]. The main objective of a road detection system is to detect road pixels from RS images, while centerline extraction locates the skeleton of a road using mathematical morphological operations. The RS characteristics of the roads depend on weather conditions and sensors. Road features are classified into geometric, functional, topological, and contextual [4]. Geometric features are continuous and include the length-to-width ratio of roads, where the width is always narrower than the length. Functional features constitute connectivity in different areas. Characteristics of road intersections and continuity in length without interruption are called topological features. Contextual features include the shadows of trees, buildings, and flyovers. Some road detection methods used multiple features to improve the segmentation accuracy. But it is complex to identify all the features due to occluded high-resolution images.

Figure 1 shows a general block diagram of road extraction from remote sensing images. Several road datasets are available, including high-resolution satellite images with two classes: roads and non-roads [4]. The Massachusetts road dataset [5] has 1124 VHR images with 1500×1500 resolution. As a model's performance depends on the data quality, the preprocessing step ensures that the model receives correct data in a suitable format. The filtering technique helps to remove unwanted data from the image. Thresholding and binarization methods are used for grayscale conversion and normalization. The extraction of road features helps to produce different road aspects (geometric, radiometric, and contextual). In the classification technique, each pixel in an image is categorized in the road or non-road class. Various supervised or unsupervised methods are used for classification. Model accuracy can be evaluated using precision, recall, and IoU score. The segmented map represents the output of the model containing only the road pixels of the image.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of road extraction from remote sensing images.

II. RELATED WORKS

Road detection from remote sensing images can be addressed using manual and automatic techniques. Currently, it is based on a manual process that is tedious and requires human intervention, while its accuracy depends upon the interpreter's skills. Automatic methods are more structured and economic. A neural network classifier approach was proposed in [6] to discriminate road and non-road pixels from IKONOS images. The accuracy of segmentation was improved using texture and spectral information. This method used a backpropagation neural network and a Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) for the detection of road pixels. A backpropagation neural network with GLCM features for semantic segmentation was proposed in [7], where its functionality was optimized by incorporating homogeneity, contrast, and entropy.

Many computer vision applications use deep neural networks and mark state-of-the-art performance. Several studies applied deep neural networks to the semantic segmentation of roads, using different algorithms like U-Net, fully convolutional networks, CasNet, and deep Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for the semantic segmentation of remotely sensed images. A CNN approach to detect roads from noisy labeled samples was proposed in [8]. This algorithm generated the training labels and used texture descriptors to obtain road areas, using a combination of the supervised and unsupervised methods for post- and pre-training respectively. A novel cascade end-to-end CNN was presented in [3] to detect roads and their centerlines from high-resolution images. This study used two networks for the semantic segmentation of road pixels. The first network detected road pixels and generated a feature map. At the same time, the second network was cascaded with the first one to generate the centerline of the road area. This method marked the fastest computation time compared to existing networks. Deep residual U-nets were proposed in [9-10], using the U-net architecture [11] with skip connections and residual blocks. The skip connection helps to propagate the information from encoder to decoder and improves the segmentation result with fewer network parameters.

A linear integral convolutional algorithm was used in [12] to label road pixels using probability maps generated by CNN. Post-processing was performed using the linear convolutional algorithm to join the road labels, overcoming the limitation of spectral intensity variation in high-resolution images. CNN shows improved performance in semantic segmentation. An early fusion model using a VGG-16-based CNN was proposed in [13] for the classification and detection of 16 classes, showing better training and test validity. A fully CNN for automatic road extraction was presented in [14], using ResNet-34 on the encoder and basic U-Net on the decoder. The encoder was pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset and used a data augmentation technique to increase the dataset size. In [15], semantic segmentation was proposed using an eleven-layered CNN and images of the San Francisco bay area for road detection. The result was compared using average and max pooling and showed that CNN is a suitable method for remote sensing image analysis. A pre-trained CNN model was used in [16] for segmentation, proposing transfer learning using CNN. In [17], the conditional random field and landscape metrics were utilized with a deep CNN, where over-segmented roads were removed using landscape metric thresholding.

Unsupervised techniques such as the knowledge-based method, mean shift, graph theory, and mathematical morphology have been used to address the problem of semantic segmentation from remotely sensed images. In [18], semi-automatic road detection was presented using a mean shift. The seed points were prescribed in the images in advance by the user. Then, road and non-road segments were classified using the thresholding technique and the seed points were connected to generate a road network. Some studies used knowledge-based methods for road detection. The structural element can be evaluated using the energy function, which results in object detection, and the road tracker algorithm can be applied to gray-level images to find long ribbons, but this method is not suitable for occluded remote sensed images [19]. The toe-finding algorithm has been used to detect road footprints, eliminating non-road segments, but had over-segmentation limitations and was also sensitive to shadows and occlusions in an image [20].

In [21], morphological operations were used for the segmentation of the image and restored the road area by filtering out noise elements. This method resulted in discontinuous segmentation, and some road gaps existed in output. In [22], the multiscale retinex algorithm was used to enhance a high-resolution image, a canny operator was used for edge detection, and the skeleton of the road was detected using morphological operations. Mathematical morphology gives results for road segmentation, but accuracy depends on the size and shape of the road. There are no fixed road construction standards, as it varies from region to region. Therefore, integrating mathematical morphology with other techniques can help improve the overall result.

III. METHODOLOGY

This paper proposes a road segmentation architecture to extract roads from remotely sensed images. The main challenge was to identify design components that regulate the performance of the road segmentation architecture. This model

was established using U-Net and residual blocks [23]. The U-Net architecture consists of a contraction and an expansion path, which help to propagate the feature map in all possible ways from the encoder to the decoder. Therefore, the network accuracy can be improved using low-level details and high-level semantic information. The residual block introduces identity mapping in the network, facilitates smooth training, and helps to prevent the problem of vanishing gradients. Another task was to preprocess the high-resolution satellite images to produce the dataset to train and test the network.

A. Network Architecture

Road detection from remote sensing images is a semantic segmentation task, and U-Net is the best-suited architecture. The proposed model was inspired by the U-Net architecture. Figure 2 shows the detailed flow chart of the Deep Res-UNet. The architecture consists of three parts: the encoder, the decoder, and the bridge.

Fig. 2. Network architecture of the proposed model.

An input image sized 256×256 pixels is considered at the encoder's input. Four residual blocks with a 3×3 filter are implemented in the encoder part. The filter sizes of the residual blocks are respectively 16, 32, 64, and 128. An additional residual block with a filter size of 256 is connected between the encoder and the decoder, forming the bridge. The encoder helps to extract road features and generates feature maps, while the decoder classifies each pixel into a specific class. The encoder path uses the typical architecture of a convolutional network. It consists of repeated 3×3 convolutional layers followed by an Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) [24]. It also carries out a 2×2 max pooling operation with a stride of 2. The max pooling operation is required for the downsampling of the feature map and size reduction. Each residual block in the encoding part is connected to the decoding part using concatenation. The residual block consists of identity mapping, which represents connections between the input and output of the residual module. The proposed architecture replaces the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) with an Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) and adds the BN layer [25] after each convolutional layer. The ELU activation function is defined as:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x, & x > 0 \\ \alpha(e^x - 1), & x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The ELU and BN layers have become widely used components in CNN due to their high performance during network training. The number of kernels per output layer was set to 1. The sigmoid function, shown in (2), was used for classification instead of softmax:

$$\text{sigmoid} = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \quad (2)$$

The classification cross-entropy was minimized using the Adam optimizer. Cross entropy is used to represent the difference between the distribution of input data and the distribution obtained from model training. Convolutional and upsampling operations were carried out in the decoder path. Each decoder module first performs the up convolutional operation with a feature map provided by the concatenation path, doubling the size of the feature map and improving the resolution. The same size of the input and output images can be ensured by upsampling. Then, 3×3 convolutional operation was carried out with the ELU activation function. The filter size of a convolutional layer in the decoder is 128, 64, 32, and 16 respectively. The last layer is 1×1 convolutional and is used to map 128 component feature vectors to their desired classes. This layer uses a sigmoid as an activation function. Table I shows the details of the network layers.

TABLE I. SIZE OF NETWORK LAYERS

	Unit Level	Conv. Layer	Filter	Stride	Output Size
Input					$256 \times 256 \times 3$
Encoding	Level 1	Conv 1	$3 \times 3 / 16$	2	$256 \times 256 \times 16$
		Conv 2	$3 \times 3 / 16$	2	$256 \times 256 \times 16$
	Level 2	Conv 3	$3 \times 3 / 32$	2	$128 \times 128 \times 32$
		Conv 4	$3 \times 3 / 32$	2	$128 \times 128 \times 32$
	Level 3	Conv 5	$3 \times 3 / 64$	2	$64 \times 64 \times 64$
		Conv 6	$3 \times 3 / 64$	2	$64 \times 64 \times 64$
	Level 4	Conv 7	$3 \times 3 / 128$	2	$32 \times 32 \times 128$
		Conv 8	$3 \times 3 / 128$	2	$32 \times 32 \times 128$
Bridge	Level 5	Conv 9	$3 \times 3 / 256$	1	$16 \times 16 \times 256$
		Conv 10	$3 \times 3 / 256$	1	$16 \times 16 \times 256$
Decoder	Level 6	Conv 11	$3 \times 3 / 128$	2	$32 \times 32 \times 128$
		Conv 12	$3 \times 3 / 128$	2	$32 \times 32 \times 128$
	Level 7	Conv 13	$3 \times 3 / 64$	2	$64 \times 64 \times 64$
		Conv 14	$3 \times 3 / 64$	2	$64 \times 64 \times 64$
	Level 8	Conv 15	$3 \times 3 / 32$	2	$128 \times 128 \times 32$
		Conv 16	$3 \times 3 / 32$	2	$128 \times 128 \times 32$
	Level 9	Conv 17	$3 \times 3 / 16$	2	$256 \times 256 \times 16$
		Conv 18	$3 \times 3 / 16$	2	$256 \times 256 \times 16$
Output		Conv 19	1×1	1	$256 \times 256 \times 16$

IV. EXPERIMENT

A. Dataset and Preprocessing

The Massachusetts dataset was used, where each image contains $3 \times 1500 \times 1500$ pixels. The dataset consists of 1711 aerial images, and covers around 2600 km^2 . The dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing sets. The experimental procedure used 1191 images for training, 109 images for validation, and 273 images for testing. Figure 3 shows some samples of cropped satellite images with ground-truth labels. As the size of the original image is too large, it

would be resource intensive to feed it in the first layer, and the input image was cropped into 256×256 to avoid it. All the cropped images were then processed with the data augmentation technique to increase the number of images. This was carried out using random rotation and vertical and horizontal flips. The data augmentation technique helps to prevent the model from overfitting.

B. Implementation Details

The implementation was carried out on the TensorFlow platform. A deep learning framework requires lots of memory and high-performance machines. The proposed method was

implemented on an NVIDIA GPU with 24GB of memory. The Adam optimizer was used during training and the learning rate was set to 0.0001 to reduce the errors during training and improve performance. Semantic segmentation is a binary classification problem. The binary cross entropy was used as a loss function:

$$L(y, p(y)) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N (y * \log p(y)) + (1 - y) \times \log(1 - p(y)) \quad (3)$$

where $p(y)$ is the predicted value, y is the true label, and N is the number of samples.

Fig. 3. Cropped satellite images with ground truth labels.

C. Evaluation Metrics

The qualitative performance of the model was assessed using the Intersection over Union (IoU), Completeness (COM), Correctness (COR), and F1 score. The IoU expresses the correctness of generated maps and is the ratio of intersection over the predicted map and ground-truth labels to a total area of the ground-truth labels and predicted map. The IoU can be calculated using the union operation. COM measures the percentage of areas matched on the reference map. COR measures the percentage of the matched road area in the segmentation map, and F1 defines the overall metric by combining COM and COR.

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{Area of Overlap}}{\text{Area of union}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{COM} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{COR} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (6)$$

The proposed model was trained from scratch without using any pre-trained modules. Table II shows the results of the proposed architecture and mentions the external accuracy results from [9]. This network uses skip connections and dense blocks. The results showed that the IoU score on the Massachusetts road dataset was 74.47%. Figure 4 shows the IoU and loss graphs of the proposed model. The COR metric was 96.42% and IoU was 81.57%. There were two problems associated with the ground-truth labels: sometimes, an area in an image was marked as a road but it was not. Some side or local roads were incorrectly labeled in the ground-truth image. The first problem increases the difficulty of extracting precise edges for the road networks. Figure 5 represents the flow chart of the proposed model.

TABLE II. RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

	Accuracy Metric			
	COR	COM	IoU	F1 score
Proposed model	96.42%	81.03%	81.57%	88.02%
External accuracy [9]	78.25%	70.41%	74.47%	74.07%

Fig. 4. IoU and loss metrics of the proposed model.

Fig. 5. Flow chart of the proposed model.

D. Comparison with Other Algorithms

The proposed architecture was compared with state-of-the-art models to test its validity. U-Net, FCN, and SegNet models

were considered and trained on the Massachusetts road dataset by keeping the same hyperparameters, as they are used extensively in semantic segmentation. The U-Net architecture was proposed for medical image segmentation, implementing a four-layer U-Net architecture using skipped connections without identity mapping [11]. A basic 7-layer FCN algorithm was implemented to assess accuracy, which was proposed for semantic segmentation in [26]. The SegNet model was introduced for multiscale segmentation [27]. The proposed model was used as is, following the encoder and decoder architecture with pixel-wise labeling and using pooling indices for the maximum pooling feature map at the decoder. Table III shows the qualitative performance of the models for the road extraction task using COR, COM, IoU, and F1 scores. The bold and underlined values indicate the best and second-best scores per metric respectively. The proposed model had 96.42% COR and 81.57% IoU values. The proposed model's IoU was about 5% higher than the U-Net's, showing that the more supervised information in the proposed model helps extracting roads more precisely. The COR metric of the proposed model is nearly 8% higher than that of SegNet.

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF RESULTS

Model	COR	COM	IoU	F1 Score	Detection time (s)
Proposed model	96.42%	81.03%	81.57%	88.02%	11.331s
Segnet [27]	88.25%	76.92%	71.03%	82.13%	14.528s
Unet [11]z	93.31%	79.03%	77.49%	85.54%	11.432s
FCN [26]	83.13%	75.16%	68.66%	78.80%	9.144s

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 6-8 show the IoU and loss graphs of the SegNet, U-Net, and FCN models, and Figure 9 shows a chart of their performance.

Fig. 6. IoU and loss of SegNet.

The proposed model used more skip connections in the encoder and decoder to improve the performance of U-Net and propagate the feature map in all possible ways. Identity mapping between the input and output of each residual block improves the network's generalization ability and enables the

identification of deep features. The SegNet model showed 71.03% IoU and 82.02% F1 scores. The U-Net achieved the second highest performance in IoU and COR and had an 85.54% F1 score. FCN had the lowest IoU and F1 scores but had the least detection time compared to the other three models. Figure 10 shows sample results for road detection with original, ground-truth, predicted, and threshold images.

Fig. 7. IoU and loss of U-Net.

Fig. 8. IoU and loss of FCN.

Fig. 9. Chart of models performance.

Fig. 10. Road detection results: (a) original, (b) ground-truth, (c) predicted, and (d) threshold images.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a deep convolutional ResUnet architecture, using CNN to extract road areas from remotely sensed images. The deep convolutional encoder-decoder architecture serves as the foundation of the network. Data augmentation techniques were used to improve the performance of the network. The encoder helps to generate a feature map, and the decoder classifies each pixel into a particular class. A simulation was carried out on the Massachusetts road dataset. The proposed architecture was compared with other state-of-the-art models. The results showed that the proposed network outperforms SegNet, U-Net, and FCN. The proposed algorithm is robust against occlusions of shadows in the image and can be used to detect roads in forests and farms. It could also be helpful in land analysis and urban planning. The proposed model can be used for the automatic generation of road maps from different datasets. At first, some pre-processing techniques, like cropping and thresholding, need to be carried out on the input data set. These images can be applied as input to the proposed model to generate a road map. In the future, different optimization techniques and activation functions along with different datasets can be used to improve segmentation results.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. R. Navalgund, V. Jayaraman, and P. S. Roy, "Remote sensing applications: An overview," *Current Science*, vol. 93, no. 12, pp. 1747–1766, 2007.
- [2] A. A. Daptardar, "Introduction to Remote Sensors and Image Processing and its Applications," *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology*, Special Issue-IDEAS-2013, pp. 107–114, 2013.
- [3] G. Cheng, Y. Wang, S. Xu, H. Wang, S. Xiang, and C. Pan, "Automatic Road Detection and Centerline Extraction via Cascaded End-to-End Convolutional Neural Network," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 3322–3337, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2017.2669341>.

- [4] W. Wang, N. Yang, Y. Zhang, F. Wang, T. Cao, and P. Eklund, "A review of road extraction from remote sensing images," *Journal of Traffic and Transportation Engineering (English Edition)*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 271–282, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtte.2016.05.005>.
- [5] V. Mnih, "Machine Learning for Aerial Image Labeling," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada, 2013.
- [6] A. Kirthika and A. Mookambiga, "Automated road network extraction using artificial neural network," in *2011 International Conference on Recent Trends in Information Technology (ICRTIT)*, Chennai, India, Jun. 2011, pp. 1061–1065, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRTIT.2011.5972323>.
- [7] A. N. Saeed, "A Machine Learning based Approach for Segmenting Retinal Nerve Images using Artificial Neural Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 5986–5991, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3666>.
- [8] V. Mnih and G. E. Hinton, "Learning to Detect Roads in High-Resolution Aerial Images," in *Computer Vision – ECCV 2010*, Heraklion, Greece, 2010, pp. 210–223, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-15567-3_16.
- [9] J. Xin, X. Zhang, Z. Zhang, and W. Fang, "Road Extraction of High-Resolution Remote Sensing Images Derived from DenseUNet," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 11, no. 21, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 2499, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11212499>.
- [10] T. Alshaikhli, W. Liu, and Y. Maruyama, "Automated Method of Road Extraction from Aerial Images Using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 22, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 4825, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9224825>.
- [11] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, "U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation," in *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2015*, Munich, Germany, 2015, pp. 234–241, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24574-4_28.
- [12] P. Li *et al.*, "Road network extraction via deep learning and line integral convolution," in *2016 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (IGARSS)*, Beijing, China, Jul. 2016, pp. 1599–1602, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS.2016.7729408>.
- [13] S. Nuanmeesri, "A Hybrid Deep Learning and Optimized Machine Learning Approach for Rose Leaf Disease Classification," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7678–7683, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4455>.
- [14] A. V. Buslaev, S. S. Seferbekov, V. I. Iglovikov, and A. A. Shvets, "Fully Convolutional Network for Automatic Road Extraction from Satellite Imagery," in *2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW)*, Salt Lake City, UT, USA, 2018, pp. 4321–4324.
- [15] S.-H. Wang, J. Sun, P. Phillips, G. Zhao, and Y.-D. Zhang, "Polarimetric synthetic aperture radar image segmentation by convolutional neural network using graphical processing units," *Journal of Real-Time Image Processing*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 631–642, Jul. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11554-017-0717-0>.
- [16] L. Loyani and D. Machuve, "A Deep Learning-based Mobile Application for Segmenting Tuta Absoluta's Damage on Tomato Plants," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7730–7737, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4355>.
- [17] T. Panboonyuen, K. Jitkajornwanich, S. Lawawirojwong, P. Srestasathien, and P. Vateekul, "Road Segmentation of Remotely-Sensed Images Using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks with Landscape Metrics and Conditional Random Fields," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 9, no. 7, Jul. 2017, Art.no 680, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9070680>.
- [18] Z. Miao, B. Wang, W. Shi, and H. Zhang, "A Semi-Automatic Method for Road Centerline Extraction From VHR Images," *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 1856–1860, Aug. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2014.2312000>.
- [19] J. Shen, X. Lin, Y. Shi, and C. Wong, "Knowledge-Based Road Extraction from High Resolution Remotely Sensed Imagery," in *2008 Congress on Image and Signal Processing*, Sanya, China, Feb. 2008, vol. 4, pp. 608–612, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CISP.2008.519>.
- [20] J. Hu, A. Razdan, J. C. Femiani, M. Cui, and P. Wonka, "Road Network Extraction and Intersection Detection From Aerial Images by Tracking Road Footprints," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 45, no. 12, pp. 4144–4157, Sep. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2007.906107>.
- [21] M. M. Awad, "A Morphological Model for Extracting Road Networks from High-Resolution Satellite Images," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 2013, Feb. 2013, Art. no e243021, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/243021>.
- [22] Z. Ma, J. T. Wu, Z. H. Luo, Z.H., "Road extraction from RS image based on level set method" presented at the 13th National Academic Conference on Image and Graphics, Nanjing, China, 2006.
- [23] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition," *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Jun. 2016, pp. 770–778, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.90>.
- [24] D.-A. Clevert, T. Unterthiner, and S. Hochreiter, "Fast and Accurate Deep Network Learning by Exponential Linear Units (ELUs)." arXiv, Feb. 22, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1511.07289>.
- [25] S. Ioffe and C. Szegedy, "Batch Normalization: Accelerating Deep Network Training by Reducing Internal Covariate Shift," in *Proceedings of the 32nd International Conference on Machine Learning*, Lille, France, Jun. 2015, pp. 448–456.
- [26] E. Shelhamer, J. Long, and T. Darrell, "Fully Convolutional Networks for Semantic Segmentation," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 640–651, Apr. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2016.2572683>.
- [27] V. Badrinarayanan, A. Kendall, and R. Cipolla, "SegNet: A Deep Convolutional Encoder-Decoder Architecture for Image Segmentation," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 39, no. 12, pp. 2481–2495, Sep. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2016.2644615>.

Effect Change Concrete Slab Layer Thickness on Rigid Pavement

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Abstract-Years of research have been devoted to developing a tool to model and analyze the behavior of rigid pavements. A major component of the new design approaches is the three-dimensional Finite Element Method (FEM), which caused a breakthrough in rigid pavement analysis. The current study used FEM to analyze a rigid pavement composed of a concrete slab layer and a subgrade. The impact of the depth of the concrete slab layer on vertical stresses and displacements was studied with the ABAQUS software. Three different thicknesses were chosen, 20, 25, and 28cm, while the thickness of the remaining paving layers remained unchanged. According to the study results, the top of the concrete slab layer had an increase in stress of approximately 88% when its thickness increased from 20 to 28cm, whereas the top of the subgrade layer had a decrease of about 21% in stress. The change in vertical stress at the top of the subgrade layer was 46% for a thickness of 20-25cm and 14.8% for 25-28cm. The percent of the reduction in vertical stress at the top of the concrete slab layer was 13.2% and 1.8% for thicknesses of 20-25 and 25-28cm respectively. Vertical displacement in the middle of the horizontal distance under the tire print was reduced by 14%, 12%, and 24% when the concrete slab layer increased from 20 to 25, from 25 to 28, and from 20 to 28cm respectively.

Keywords-rigid pavement; ABAQUS; concrete slab thickness; finite element method

I. INTRODUCTION

Rigid pavements are complicated structural systems made up of a variety of concrete slabs connected by longitudinal and transverse joints that may or may not contain dowel bars. Many design approaches to determine required pavement thicknesses have been established [1]. Analytical solutions developed from closed-form formulas to complicated derivations can be used to determine stress and strain on rigid pavements. Finite Element (FE) modeling is useful to simulate the structural reaction of pavements under the influence of various loading conditions and is effective in solving partial and integral differential equations [2-4]. FEM was developed as a numerical approach to solve numerous engineering and applied science issues [5]. Many techniques with various computational costs may be implemented in ABAQUS, a software widely used for FEM analysis [6], as it can solve problems with static, harmonic, and

transient dynamic loading as well as thermal gradient conditions in two and three dimensions [7]. Linear and nonlinear elastic, viscoelastic, plastic, and modified elastic materials can be represented.

Several studies used three-dimensional (3D) FE models to investigate the behavior of rigid pavements. Various FE models have been proposed to analyze the behavior of concrete pavement systems. In [8], the tension in rigid runway pavement was studied showing that wider wheel arrangements cause less stress by aircraft load. Computational modeling of a rigid pavement with load applied to the slab's edge was conducted in [1] using FEM. There were no significant variations in stresses at the research control point between modeling a system with three slabs with dowels and modeling an isolated slab for slab sizes frequently used in basic concrete pavements ($L \geq 3.5m$). An analysis of a dowel-jointed concrete pavement using a 3D FE model was carried out in [9], observing that voids beneath the joint increased the vertical displacement of the concrete slab and vertical stress at the concrete/dowel bar interface, potentially leading to concrete crushing and dowel loosening. In [2], ABAQUS was used to investigate the pavement response under the effect of some model parameters, and a comparison with field measurements confirmed the findings. The stress and strains on the concrete slabs were found to minimize by increasing the thickness of the slab. Stress reduction is especially noticeable in the joints. In [11], ABAQUS was employed to model rigid pavements and investigate how varied pavement layer thicknesses, such as base course material and slab thickness, affected the critical pavement reactions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Pavement Model

This study modeled the concrete slab and subgrade using a 3D FE mesh. A conventional pavement section was used, consisting of a concrete slab and a subgrade, to investigate the effect of the thickness of the concrete slab layer on the performance of the rigid pavement layers, with a fixed subgrade depth thickness. The geometries and the mechanical properties of the materials examined were the elastic modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν . The data of the adopted model were:

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- Concrete slab layer of 4.50×5.00m, $h=200\text{mm}$
- $E_c=26000\text{MPa}$, $\nu=0.17$
- Subgrade of 4.50×5.00m, $h=3.00\text{m}$.
- $E=34\text{MPa}$, $\nu=0.35$

Figure 1 shows the geometrical model.

TABLE I. LAYER THICKNESSES

Layer	Layer name	Thickness		
		Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
1	Concrete slab	180 mm	200 mm	250 mm
2	Subgrade	3 m	3 m	3 m

Fig. 1. 3-D model, geometry.

B. Mesh Size Distribution in the Model

The mesh size was optimized to achieve a balance between computation time and calculation stability [4]. A fine mesh of 10×10cm was required in the concrete slab. However, a somewhat coarse mesh of 30×30cm was chosen for the soil foundation, without affecting the accuracy of the stress and displacement predictions. Figure 2 shows the model's FE mesh.

Fig. 2. Mesh size distribution for the model.

C. Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions were chosen to be as close as possible to the actual boundary conditions. The peripheric and bottom limitations were defined using the boundary conditions. For boundary conditions, the lower surfaces were considered completely fixed against all degrees of freedom [10]. For all pavement geometry models, the edges can move in the vertical (z) direction. No movement was considered in the horizontal directions for the four sides of the model during FEM analysis. Figure 3 shows these boundary conditions.

Fig. 3. The boundary conditions of the model.

D. Load Representation

The load was characterized as static, which is the most favorable state for calculating stresses, and the equivalent contact area was used in the load configuration, which is a common technique of representing pavement loads [3]. The single axle, with a single wheel, and a 690kPa pressure of the tire was adopted in the analysis. The use of a square footprint resulted in an improved agreement with FE meshing. Figure 4 shows the wheel load configurations, and Table II presents footprint dimensions.

Fig. 4. Wheel load configurations.

TABLE II. FOOTPRINT DIMENSIONS [3]

Wheel load	Dimensions "b" (mm)
Single wheel load (SAL)	332

E. Interaction Modeling Techniques

Interactions between contact surfaces were established in the FE model. The interactions had many features that are necessary for the solution's appropriate convergence and were determined by the physical relationship between its components [3].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The distributions of stresses and displacements were studied to properly exploit and develop the results of 3D modeling. Figure 5 shows the collected results of stresses and their vertical distribution from the FE model analysis used in this study for case 1, while Figure 6 shows the vertical displacement distribution within the pavement layers. Figures 7-10 show the collected results of stresses and vertical displacement distribution within pavement layers for cases 2 and 3.

Fig. 5. Stress distribution within pavement layers, case 1.

Fig. 6. Vertical displacement distribution within pavement layers, case 1.

Fig. 7. Stress distribution within pavement layers, case 2.

Fig. 8. Vertical displacement distribution within pavement layers, case 2.

concrete slab layer under the tire print, which is about 75% of the applied pressure. This was reduced to 190kPa at the top of the subgrade layer, which is about 28% of the applied pressure. In case 2, vertical stress increased to 598kPa at the top of the concrete slab layer, which is approximately 87% of the applied pressure, and reduced to 163kPa at the top of the subgrade layer, which is approximately 24% of the applied pressure. In case 3, vertical stress increased to 610kPa and 150kPa at the top of the concrete slab and subgrade layers (approximately 88% and 22% of the applied pressure) respectively.

Fig. 9. Stress distribution within pavement layers, case 3.

Fig. 10. Vertical displacement distribution within pavement layers, case 3.

TABLE III. STRESS LEVELS BETWEEN THE INTERFACED LAYERS

Layer name	Vertical Stress (σ_{33}), Pa		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Top of concrete slab layer	519652	598887	610052
Top of subgrade	190376	163143	150807

The results of this study indicate that the stress levels at the top of the concrete slab layer increased by approximately 88% when the thickness of this layer increased from 20 to 28cm, while the stress levels at the top of the subgrade layer reduced by approximately 21%. Figure 11 illustrates how the stress level increased with the increasing thickness of the concrete slab layer. Additionally, as the thickness of the concrete slab layer increases, the vertical stresses below the tire print at shallow depths vary slightly. However, at large horizontal distances and depths, the variation is negligible.

Figure 12 shows the vertical displacement along with the horizontal distance for all cases on top of the concrete slab layer under the center of the inner wheel. The vertical displacement in the middle of the horizontal distance under the

Table III shows the values of vertical stresses (σ_{33}) in the pavement system when applying a pressure of 690kPa. In case 1, vertical stress of 519kPa was concentrated on the top of the

tire print decreased by 14%, 12%, and 24% when the concrete slab layer increased from 20 to 25cm, 25 to 28cm, and 20 to 28cm respectively. However, the vertical displacement at the edge of the concrete slab layer increased by about 26% when the thickness of this layer increased from 20 to 28 cm.

Fig. 11. Vertical stress vs depth.

Fig. 12. Vertical displacement on the top of the concrete slab layer.

IV. CONCLUSION

The main conclusions drawn from on the results of this study are:

- The percentage of deformation in the middle of the horizontal distance under the tire print decreases by 14%, 12%, and 24% as the thickness increases from 20 to 25cm, 25 to 28cm, and 20 to 28cm respectively. This indicates that the concrete slab layer is mainly responsible for this reduction in deformation in the pavement structure.
- For concrete slab layer thicknesses of 20, 25, and 28cm, the vertical stress at the top of the concrete slab layer is 519, 598, and 610kPa respectively, and it reduces to 190, 163, and 150kPa on the top of the subgrade layer, which is equivalent to approximately 28%, 24%, and 22% of the applied stress at the top. Since the stresses in the layer under the concrete slab layer decrease as the thickness of the concrete slab layer increases, the stresses above the subgrade therefore decrease.
- The maximum value of vertical stress is 610.052Pa at the top of the concrete slab layer when the concrete slab layer is

28cm, while the minimum vertical stress is 100.152 at the top of the subgrade layer when the concrete slab layer is 25cm.

- The analysis clearly shows that the vertical stress at the top of the concrete slab layer increases as the vertical depth of the concrete slab layer increases.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. M. H. López, E. T. Piusseaut, E. A. R. Veliz, and C. A. R. Morfa, "3D-FE of jointed plain concrete pavement over continuum elastic foundation to obtain the edge stress," *Revista de la Construcción - Journal of Construction*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 5–18, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.7764/RDLC.19.1.5-18>.
- [2] M. Zokaie, M. Fakhri, and S. Rahimnezhad, "A Parametric Study of Jointed Plain Concrete Pavement Using Finite Element Modeling," *Modern Applied Science*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 75–84, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5539/mas.v11n11p75>.
- [3] Y. H. Huang, *Pavement Analysis and Design*, 2nd ed. Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA: Pearson Education, 2004.
- [4] M. Zdiri, N. Abriak, J. Neji, and M. B. Ouezdou, "Modelling of the Stresses and Strains Distribution in an RCC Pavement Using the Computer Code 'Abaqus,'" *Electronic Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 9, pp. 37–44, Jun. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.56748/ejse.9116>.
- [5] A. S. Mahdi and S. D. Mohammed, "Experimental and Numerical Analysis of Bubbles Distribution Influence in BubbleDeck Slab under Harmonic Load Effect," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6645–6649, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3963>.
- [6] A. A. Abdulhussein and M. H. Al-Sherrawi, "Experimental and Numerical Analysis of the Punching Shear Resistance Strengthening of Concrete Flat Plates by Steel Collars," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7853–7860, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4497>.
- [7] W. Uddin, R. M. Hackett, A. Joseph, Z. Pan, and A. B. Crawley, "Three-Dimensional Finite-Element Analysis of Jointed Concrete Pavement with Discontinuities," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 1482, pp. 26–32, 1995.
- [8] M. R. K. Manesh, M. M. S. Babaki, A. P. Tavandasthi, "Examining the Effect of Weight and the Arrangement of Aircrafts' Wheels on Roller-Compacted Concrete (RCC) Pavement Design of Runways Using Finite Element Method," *Current World Environment*, vol. 10, Special Issue 1, Apr. 2015.
- [9] Sii, How Bing (Perry), "Three-dimensional finite element analysis of concrete pavement on weak foundation," Ph.D. dissertation, Griffith University, Queensland, Australia, 2015.
- [10] M. a. S. Hadi and M. H. Al-Sherrawi, "The Influence of Base Layer Thickness in Flexible Pavements," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7904–7909, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4573>.
- [11] M. Rahman and N. Murshed, "Sensitivity of Rigid Pavement Responses to Pavement Layer Thickness Due to Wheel Load: A Nonlinear Finite Element Study," *Trends in Transport Engineering and Applications*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2014.

An Experimental Study on the Socketed Pile in Soft Rock

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Abstract-Pile foundation systems are used in India in many projects such as metro and railways, flyovers, and multi-story buildings. The pile transfers superstructure load to the substructure, i.e. to rock layers by means of skin resistance and end-bearing resistance. In this study, an attempt is made to observe the performance of socketed piles in soft rock. A series of socketed small-scale model pile load laboratory studies have been conducted using the loading frame. Load tests were performed on a model steel pile to calculate its axial load-bearing capability at various socket depths. An unconfined compression test was performed on pseudo-rock variations to find out the properties of the soft rock used. The results showed the ability of the drilled pile to enhance the strength of the pseudo rock. An attempt was also made to calculate the optimum depth for the socketed pile in soft rock.

Keywords-pile foundation; socketed depth; settlement; axial load; model pile

I. INTRODUCTION

Utilization of socketed piles is one economical method which has been used to transfer heavy loads to the rock strata. Rock socketed piles are drilled into the rock and then filled with steel and concrete. These piles are designed to carry heavy loads by base resistance and side skin resistance. Broad diameter cast in situ piles are used to hold massive loads of super-structures. Almost in every construction project, 1000mm to 1200mm diameter piles are used. As these piles are built for heavy loads, they are basically to be lowered to the rock surface and need to be inserted into the rock [1]. The socket in the rock layer is absolutely necessary when the piles rest just on a rock at shallow depths. Boring in rock would have almost no challenge, except for occasional water pipes and boulders [2-5]. Rock sockets will pose several functional issues, usually ranging from rock classification to socket depth and actual terminating standards. Authors in [6] carried out a field pile load test by using Osterberg-cell which measures the skin friction of the pile. Authors in [7] carried out experimental investigations on the shaft friction of rock socketed piles using direct shear tests. Authors in [8] conducted numerical and experimental tests on model piles with good agreement between them. The method of [9] was applied to the field load-

displacement curve to obtain the ultimate pile load. Authors in [10] presented a scale of strength and the corresponding N values for weak rock and soils. Authors in [11] introduced the chiseling energy criteria applicable for rocks of the Mumbai region. Authors in [12] suggested that almost every load, including its subsequent settlement and the corresponding magnitude, was also drawn towards the applied load. Authors in [13] investigated the case of piles in elasto-plastic rocks using finite element analysis.

Author in [14] strongly advocated the use of axisymmetric values of loads to define failure. Authors in [15] reviewed some of the methods of socket design. In their review, they recommended a range of bond values for piles socketed in shale rock. The author in [16] applied neural network modeling to compute the maximum load for a driven pile in cohesionless soil. Authors in [17] developed analytical solutions for the calculation of load-displacement response for axially loaded piles in rock. Authors in [18] proposed a simple geomechanical model for calculating the settlements of foundations in soft rock masses which showed good agreement with the field data. Authors in [19] carried out experimental studies for bond strength in rock socketed piers and stated that sidewall shear resistance essentially behaved in a non-brittle manner, i.e. it did not decrease even after the pile-rock bond was broken. Authors in [20] presented charts for rock socket design based on finite element analysis of an elastic pile resting on the elastic socket. Roughness classification and specification are shown in Table I. Authors in [21] proposed a design process for socketed pile in a soft rock complying with the defined settlement requirements and providing an appropriate factor of safety. Authors in [22] proposed a design method, which used parameters based on a wide range of theoretical, laboratory, and field investigations.

II. PILE SOCKETING

If the diameter of the pile is 1.2m, the rock socket is to be completed by breaking the hard rock for a length of 1.2m. For chiseling in hard rock, whose crushing strength is 1000kg/cm², more time is required. Each of these components may cause serious damage to a rock mass. The load is carried by the pile

on the rock by point bearing. This makes necessary to socket the pile through the rock by breaking across the weak rock and by cutting down the hard rock for an appropriate depth generally to get the flat surface of the rock. This appropriate depth can vary between 200 and 400mm [23]. Also, if the soft or medium rocks precede the hard rock, each length of the socket can be considered from the level where soft rock has an N value higher than 50. There are variations in the form of the rock almost every time. It can be weathered rock, soft rock, or hard rock. Firstly, rock layer classification must be conducted. For this reason, we refer to field test reports such as RQD and SPT [24, 25]. For larger constructions like flyover and high-rise buildings, soil study must be conducted beneath every pier position. Hence, the above-mentioned studies are crucial to be performed for every pier site. [26-28].

TABLE I. ROUGHNESS CLASSIFICATION OF ROCK SOCKETS [18]

Roughness classification	Specification
R1	Soft socket, grooves less than 1mm deep
R2	Depth of grooves 1 to 4mm, spacing 50mm to 200mm, width > 2mm
R3	Depth of grooves 4 to 10mm, spacing 50mm to 200mm, width > 5mm
R4	Depth of grooves > 10mm, spacing 50mm to 200mm, width > 10mm

III. TECHNIQUES FOR ASSESSING SOCKETED PILE LENGTH IN ROCK

There are two different techniques used for the calculation of the socketed depth of piles in rock.

A. On the basis of Uniaxial Compression Strength Method

Rock socketed pile is primarily executed to make use of the complete structural strength of the pile. Sockets are built to hold the axial load through the side friction and the base resistance. It is important to gather all the information described above. In this regard, the elemental composition of the rock at the foundation stage should also be collected for the detection of chemical components influencing the capacity of the pile. The safe load-carrying capabilities of the socketed pile can be determined by the uniaxial compression strength of the rock.

B. Determination by the Energy Criteria Method

The configuration of the rock socket depth of the pile in the rock can be determined based on energy criteria. Rock socketing standards have a great deal of significance in weathered/soft rock. Core recovery ratio/rock content classification is the optimal measure to assess the rock type. It's hard to have the cores in the weathered/soft rock. The approach proposed in [10] is commonly used to determine the depth of the socket of the piles in soft-rock to obtain the ability of the pile and its structural strength. N values are used to describe the rock type and its shear strength. In fact, another technique uses a chisel to decide the form of the rock and the depth of the socket. The key points to be considered in the chisel energy system are the weight of the chisel, the number of blows, and the penetration into the rock for a predetermined number of blows. While this method appears to be more realistic and

rational, it has many disadvantages, such as the strength of the chisel, the chisel dropping into the bentonite mixture, the mass of the chisel, and its type. Chisel energy is measured based on the findings of the load test carried out in those regions.

C. Steps to Follow During Rock Socketing

Other than drilling the rock up to the necessary depth in the rock socket, certain more important functional considerations need to be noticed. The heavy chiseling of high torque drilling can create vibrations during the rock socket operation. Such vibrations can allow the soil strata to destabilize the rock base and the pile would lose the resistance component of these levels. Therefore, better care must be taken to minimize disturbances. Rock socketing requires a longer time and often disturbs the layers by laying the rock strata. This disruption would allow the fine particles to break down and settle down at the bottom. In order to clear these small pieces and other boulders, the borehole must be thoroughly washed with a clean bentonite solution prior to the concreting process.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Rock socketed pile load testing is an experiment to be performed in the lab with the intention of providing more data on the load transfer behavior in socketed piles with varying L/D ratios. The typical sub-surface profile of soft-rock socketed pile is shown in Figure 1. After the application of P downward axial load on the top of the pile, equal and opposite reaction is developed at the pile in the upward direction. Q base is the base resistance. The length of the weathered stratum and the length of the soft-rock stratum represent the skin friction in different layers.

Fig. 1. Typical sub-surface profile of the rock socketed pile.

A. Model Pile Material and Tank

A stainless steel hollow pipe was used, having two different diameters of 60mm and 80mm and a length 600mm. The steel tank is made up of mild steel material whose dimensions are 1000×1000×1000mm and 6mm thickness. The front side of the tank is made up of a Perspex sheet to observe failure patterns during testing. The tank can be moved in the x and y directions under the load frame in order to apply centric and eccentric loading.

B. Developing of Pseudo-rock Socket

For pseudo-rock formation cement, sand, bentonite, and water were used. Model rock specimens were developed, although their strengths varied widely. Table II provides the description of the ingredient proportions for pseudo-rock. The percentage of sand and water were kept constant and the percentage of cement and bentonite increased and decreased simultaneously. Unconfined compressive strengths, as shown in Figure 2, were determined by the Compression Testing Machine (CTM) after 28 days of curing.

Fig. 2. Testing of mortar cube and cylinder in the CTM.

TABLE II. MORTAR CUBE TEST RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT BENTONITE PERCENTAGES

Mix	Cement (%)	Bentonite (%)	Sand (%)	Water (%)	Avg. UCS (MPa)
M1	17.97	4.5	67.41	10.11	19.3
M2	15.73	6.74	67.41	10.11	16.7
M3	13.48	8.98	67.41	10.11	9.5
M4	11.23	11.23	67.41	10.11	4.7
M5	8.9	13.48	67.41	10.11	3.4
M6	6.74	15.73	67.41	10.11	1.9
M7	4.5	17.97	67.41	10.11	1.2

V. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A hydraulic jack attached to the frame's bottom allowed the gradual application of axial load to the pile head throughout the experiment. A load cell was attached between the hydraulic jack and the loading frame. Therefore, two Linear Variable Differential Transformers (LVDTs) were installed on the wing plates, fastened to the opposing sides of the pile cap to measure the movement of the pile head. The whole assembly, including the hydraulic jack, has a capacity of 30kN. An initial load of 0.2kN was applied before initiating any load increments. Loads were applied in increments of 0.25kN up to 1kN, thereafter at 1kN increments until failure or 30kN whichever was earlier. A digital displacement monitor linked to the LVDTs recorded movement readings when each load was applied. We kept increasing the load until the rate of change in the pile

movement was minimal. The schematic view of the experimental setup and the actual pile load test setup are presented in Figure 3 and 4 respectively. L/D ratios 1 to 7 were used for the testing program, where D is the diameter of the pile and L is the socketed length of the pile. Details of the testing program for 60mm diameter pile and 80mm diameter pile are given in Tables III and IV respectively. Different unconfined strengths of soft rock were used.

Fig. 3. Schematic view of the experimental setup (1= loading frame, 2= hydraulic jack, 3= LVDT, 4= load cell, 5= model pile, 6 = metal tank, 7 = pseudo rock, 8 = pressure indicator, 9 = hydraulic pump).

Fig. 4. Actual pile load test set-up with LVDT and load cell.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The behavior of load-settlement curves is discussed in this section. Based on the experimental results, the load-settlement response and the load transfer mechanism along the depth of the pile are discussed. All the piles were gradually loaded until failure to obtain their axial load-carrying capacities. Two different diameter piles were used in the testing program. The load vs displacement curves for the 60mm diameter piles are shown in Figure 5. A number of experimental model studies were carried out to determine the impact of the socket depth on the behavior of the in situ cast piles. Seven sets of experiments with different socket lengths of 1D, 2D, 3D, 4D, 5D, 6D, and 7D, where D is the diameter of the pile in pseudo rock were used in the testing program. With the help of the load settlement curve, the ultimate pile capacity was calculated.

TABLE III. DETAILS OF MODEL SOCKETED PILE LOAD TESTS ON SOFT ROCK FOR 60mm DIAMETER PILE

Test no.	Pile no	L/D	Socket length (mm)	Avg. UCS (MPa)
1	P1	1	60	9.45
2	P2	2	120	9.43
3	P3	3	180	9.36
4	P4	4	240	9.40
5	P5	5	300	9.21
6	P6	6	360	9.64
7	P7	7	420	9.33

TABLE IV. DETAILS OF MODEL SOCKETED PILE LOAD TESTS ON SOFT ROCK FOR 80mm DIAMETER PILE

Test no.	Pile no.	L/D	Socket length (mm)	Avg. UCS (MPa)
1	P1	1	80	9.30
2	P2	2	160	9.45
3	P3	3	240	9.46
4	P4	4	320	9.40
5	P5	5	400	9.31
6	P6	6	480	9.54
7	P7	7	560	9.43

Fig. 5. Comparison of load vs. settlement curves for 1D -7D socketed piles for 60mm pile diameter.

Fig. 6. Comparison of load vs. settlement curves for 1D -7D socketed piles for 80mm pile diameter.

The load was applied incrementally up to 30kN and the corresponding vertical displacements were recorded. For 1D, 2D, 3D, 4D, 5D, 6D, and 7D socketed depths, the observed axial pile capacities by the double tangent method were 6.2kN, 9.1kN, 11.2kN, 12.8kN, 15.3kN, 16kN, and 16.6kN respectively. The load vs displacement curves for 80mm diameter piles are shown in Figure 6. The loads were applied and the corresponding vertical displacements were recorded.

For 1D, 2D, 3D, 4D, 5D, 6D, and 7D socketed depths, the axial pile capacities were 10.8kN, 14.1kN, 17.25kN, 21.1kN, 24.15kN, 26.1kN, and 27.9kN respectively.

The compression measurements on the model piles demonstrate that the pile resistance increases as the depth of the socket increases, which is essentially due to the friction between the pile and the socketed rock. Up to a length of 4D to 5D of socket depth, the capacity of the pile was observed to increase considerably, but after 5D socket length, the improvement in the pile capacity was marginal. This marginal increase in strength was caused by the decrease in strength of the material and low pile stiffness. So, it can be concluded that 5D of the length of socket is the optimum depth of the socketed pile in soft-rock. This is consistent with the observations of [7, 11].

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, an effort has been made to analyze the minimum depth of the socketed pile in soft rocks. The behavior of piles in the soft rock was studied through an elaborate laboratory program, with varying socket lengths. A large number of pseudo rock samples using cement and bentonite were made by changing the proportions of cement and bentonite (7 mixes, termed as M1-M7, having UCS values of up to 19.3MPa were prepared and tested). The present study demonstrated that the behavior of socketed piles can be successfully modeled in a soft rock. The results of the present model study and the reported data in the literature are in accordance. The conclusions of the experimental program are:

- UCS strengths were found to decrease as the proportion of bentonite increased in the pseudo-rock.
- Pile capacity increases dramatically for socket length up to 5D, but this is minimal above a length of 5D.
- As the diameter of the pile increases, the ultimate load capability of the pile also increases.
- The experimental results indicate that when the diameter of the pile increases by 35%, the loading capacity at the top of the pile increases by around 50%.

It should be noted that the conclusions shown above are based on laboratory testing with a 1-g model. Because the behavior of piles in rock is stress-dependent, which is not properly simulated in 1-g model testing, full-scale/centrifuge test data under axial loading are necessary to verify the above-mentioned conclusions. Therefore, these results may be very useful as both a firsthand description and as a resource for numerical verification.

REFERENCES

[1] T. Sadeghian and M. E. Babadi, "Earthquake prediction modeling using dynamic changes (Case Study: Alborz Region)," *International Journal of Engineering*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 355-366, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5829/ije.2021.34.02b.07>.

[2] H. Zare, H. G. Taleghani, and J. Khanjani, "Efficient Removal of Copper Ion from Aqueous Solution using Crosslinked Chitosan Grafted with Polyaniline," *International Journal of Engineering*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 305-312, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5829/ije.2021.34.02b.01>.

- [3] M. E. Ergin and H. O. Tezcan, "Planned Special Event Travel Demand Model Development," *International Journal of Engineering*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 336–347, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5829/ije.2021.34.02b.05>.
- [4] V. Maralapalle, R. Hegde, R. Dasgupta, and W. Shaikh, "Experimental Investigation on Behavior of Piled-Raft Foundation," *International Journal for Science and Advance Research In Technology*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 666–670, Jan. 2017.
- [5] V. Maralapalle, M. Muntazir, A. Aahad, K. Mubariz, and B. Sakib, "Analysis and Design of pile foundation for G+20 Residential Building," *International Journal for Science and Advance Research In Technology*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 737–743, Jun. 2019.
- [6] F. M. Abdrabbo, R. M. El-Hansy, and T. M. Abdel-Aziz., "Study on the Osterberg-cell procedure for pile testing," in *Proceedings of the Tenth International Conference on Computer Methods and Advances in Geomechanics*, Tuscon, AZ, USA, Jan. 1991.
- [7] S. S. Basarkar, "Analytical and experimental studies on rock socketed piles in Mumbai region," Ph.D. dissertation, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Bombay, India, 2004.
- [8] B. Benmokrane, K. S. Mouchaorab, and G. Ballivy, "Laboratory investigation of shaft resistance of rock-socketed piers using the constant normal stiffness direct shear test," *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 407–419, Jun. 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1139/t94-048>.
- [9] F. K. Chin, "Estimation of the ultimate load of piles from tests not carried to failure," in *2nd Southeast Asian Conference on Soil Engineering*, Singapore, Singapore, Jun. 1970, pp. 81–92.
- [10] K. W. Cole and M. A. Stroud, "Rock socket piles at Coventry Point, Market Way, Coventry," *Geotechnique*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 47–62, Mar. 1976, <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1976.26.1.47>.
- [11] K. R. Datye and D. Karandikar, "Bored piling in Bombay region," in *International Geotechnical Seminar on Deep Foundations on Bored and Auger Piles*, Rotterdam, Netherlands, 1988, pp. 315–323.
- [12] L. Decourt, "Behavior of Foundations under Working Load Conditions," in *11th Pan-American Conference on Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, Foz do Iguacu, Brazil, Aug. 1999, pp. 453–488.
- [13] I. B. Donald, H. K. Chiu, and S. W. Sloan, "Theoretical analyses of rock socketed piles," in *International Conference on Structural Foundations on Rock*, Sydney, NSW, Australia, Dec. 1980, vol. 1, pp. 303–316.
- [14] W. G. K. Fleming, "A new method for single pile settlement prediction and analysis," *Géotechnique*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 411–425, Sep. 1992, <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1992.42.3.411>.
- [15] C. F. Freeman, D. Klajnerman, and G. D. Prasad, "Design of Deep Socketed Caissons Into Shale Bedrock," *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 105–114, Feb. 1972, <https://doi.org/10.1139/t72-008>.
- [16] M. A. A. Kiefa, "General Regression Neural Networks for Driven Piles in Cohesionless Soils," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 124, no. 12, pp. 1177–1185, Dec. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(1998\)124:12\(1177\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(1998)124:12(1177)).
- [17] F. H. Kulhawy, "Geomechanical Model for Rock Foundation Settlement," *Journal of the Geotechnical Engineering Division*, vol. 104, no. 2, pp. 211–227, Feb. 1978, <https://doi.org/10.1061/AJGEB6.0000582>.
- [18] J. K. Kodikara and I. W. Johnston, "Analysis of compressible axially loaded piles in rock," *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 427–437, 1994, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nag.1610180606>.
- [19] B. Ladanyi and D. Domingue, "An analysis of bond strength for rock socketed piers," in *International Conference on Structural Foundations on Rock*, Sydney, NSW, Australia, Dec. 1980, vol. 1, pp. 363–373.
- [20] P. J. N. Pells and R. M. Turner, "Elastic solutions for the design and analysis of rock-socketed piles," *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 481–487, Aug. 1979, <https://doi.org/10.1139/t79-054>.
- [21] R. K. Rowe and H. H. Armitage, "A design method for drilled piers in soft rock," *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 126–142, Feb. 1987, <https://doi.org/10.1139/t87-011>.
- [22] A. F. Williams, I. W. Johnston, and I. B. Donald, "The design of socketed piles in weak rock," in *International Conference on Structural Foundations on Rock*, Sydney, NSW, Australia, Dec. 1980, pp. 327–347.
- [23] N. Mangi, D. K. Bangwar, H. Karira, S. Kalhor, and G. R. Siddiqui, "Parametric Study of Pile Response to Side-by-Side Twin Tunneling in Stiff Clay," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5361–5366, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3290>.
- [24] T. A. Rind, H. Karira, A. A. Jhatial, S. Sohu, and A. R. Sandhu, "Particle Crushing Effect on The Geotechnical Properties of Soil," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4131–4135, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2730>.
- [25] A. H. Bhatto *et al.*, "Mohr-Coulomb and Hardening Soil Model Comparison of the Settlement of an Embankment Dam," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4654–4658, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3034>.
- [26] V. C. Maralapalle and R. Hegde, "Model studies on effect of pseudo-rock-socket strength on resistance of friction-only piles," *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*, vol. 34, Oct. 2022, Art. no. 101089, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jestech.2021.101089>.
- [27] R. U. Kulkarni and D. M. Dewaikar, "Analysis of rock-socketed piles loaded in axial compression in Mumbai region based on load transfer characteristics," *International Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 261–269, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19386362.2017.1343262>.
- [28] S. Rezazadeh and A. Eslami, "Empirical methods for determining shaft bearing capacity of semi-deep foundations socketed in rocks," *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1140–1151, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrmge.2017.06.003>.

PV and Wind Energy Conversion Exploration based on Grid Integrated Hybrid Generation Using the Cuttlefish Algorithm

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Abstract-This paper focuses on the exploration of grid integrated hybrid generation comprising of Photovoltaic (PV) and Wind Energy Conversion Systems (WECSs) using the Cuttlefish Algorithm (CFA). PV and wind energies are opposite because sunny days are normally calm, and strong winds frequently occur on cloudy days or at night. Hence, a hybrid PV and wind power system is more reliable than either individual source in terms of delivering uninterrupted power. The regulation of the DC voltage is the key issue in this configuration. The conventional PI controller is inaccurate in regulating the DC voltage. The PI controller gain tuning using optimization techniques provides good DC voltage regulation and less Total Harmonic Distortion (THD). Hence, CFA is proposed for the tuning of PI gains. The performance parameters such as DC voltage regulation and THD of CFA are analyzed.

Keywords-photovoltaic; wind energy conversion system; PWM; PI; AWT; PR; PSO; CFA

I. INTRODUCTION

The quick advancement of power electronics has increased the amount of solar and wind energy applications. Solar energy and wind energy are generally considered to be incompatible with one another due to the fact that calm winds are more typical on cloudy days or at night, whereas sunny days typically include calm conditions. As a result, a hybrid PV and wind power system is more reliable than any independent source in terms of delivering continuous electricity. Conventionally, a large energy storing battery bank [1] is adopted to reliably supply power and maximize power from PV arrays or wind turbines [1, 18], both of which are intermittent. The battery is not an environmentally friendly product, it is

expensive, has a limited life cycle, it is large and heavy [2], and, pollutes the environment with chemical waste. As a consequence, it is fairly usual practice to link renewable energy sources like solar or wind to the main power grid directly. The integration of wind and solar power hybrids into the grid system is an area that is explored in this study.

II. MODELING OF THE HYBRID GENERATION SYSTEM

The structure of the projected PV and wind based hybrid renewable generation power system is depicted in Figure 1 and its comprehensive stipulations are listed in Table I [3].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of a hybrid generation system connected to the grid.

The block diagram of the hybrid renewable generation power system including WEC, PV, inverter, and grid is depicted in Figure 1. The wind energy based power is

converted to the dc supply and then the PV supply is integrated [4]. The combined voltage at the dc link is converted to ac supply using a standard inverter for the integration of the ac power grid. The filter is used between the inverter and the grid for obtaining quality signal. Two converters are brought together to form a back-to-back converter. The connection between a Grid Side Converter (GSC) and a Machine Side Converter is made via a DC-bus capacitor (MSC) [3]. The vector control method is utilized so that the VSI can be controlled. The vector control is constructed using two different loops. The first loop is responsible for regulating the DC-link voltage and the second loop is in charge of controlling the amount of the current that is injected. When compared to the voltage loop, the current loop is intended to react more quickly to any disturbance that may occur [3].

Wind turbines generate mechanical power by capturing wind [11], as shown in (1):

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2} \pi \rho R^2 C_p(\beta, \lambda) v^3 \quad (1)$$

where R and ρ denote the radius of blades and air density, β is the pitch angle, and λ the tip-speed ratio. The wind speed is denoted by v . C_p represents the utilization coefficient of wind energy [11]. Equation (2) expresses the wind turbine mechanical acting torque [11]:

$$T_m = \frac{P_m}{\omega_m} = \frac{1}{2} \pi \rho R^3 C_p(\beta, \lambda) v^2 / \lambda \quad (2)$$

where $\omega_m = \frac{R}{\lambda v}$ denotes the mechanical angular velocity. The PMSG is a type of power conversion machinery that converts mechanical energy to electrical energy. The Park transformation, also known as dq transformation, is used to transform the time varying quantities into DC quantities.

Equations (3) and (4) present the voltage expression of PMSG in a 2-phase rotating d-q axis system [3]:

$$L_{sd} \frac{dI_{sd}}{dt} = -R_s I_{sd} + \omega_e L_{sq} I_{sq} + V_{sd} \quad (3)$$

$$L_{sq} \frac{dI_{sq}}{dt} = -R_s I_{sq} - \omega_e L_{sd} I_{sd} - \omega_e \psi + V_{sq} \quad (4)$$

where V_{sd} and V_{sq} are the stator voltages in the d-q components and I_{sd} and I_{sq} are the d and q current components in the rotor flux. The stator resistance is denoted by R_s . L_{sd} and L_{sq} are the equal inductances of stator d-q axis in the surface mounted PMSG. ω_e and ψ denote the electrical angular speed and permanent magnet chain respectively.

Equation (5) represents the electromagnetic torque of PMSG [11]:

$$T_e = 1.5 n_p [(L_{sd} - L_{sq}) I_{sd} I_{sq} + \psi I_{sq}] \quad (5)$$

Equation (6) expresses the mechanical properties of a system that employs a dynamic one-mass model:

$$T_m = J \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} + B \omega_m + T_e \quad (6)$$

The transmission system's moment of inertia and the coefficient of self-damping are denoted by J and B respectively.

The PV array is depicted in Figure 1, where N_s represents the number of cells connected in series and N_p the number of modules connected in parallel. In this particular instance, the array denoted by I_{pv} can be written as:

$$I_{pv} = N_p I_p - N_p I_s \left[\exp \left[\alpha \left(\frac{V_{PV}}{N_s} + \frac{R_s I_{PV}}{N_p} \right) \right] - 1 \right] - \frac{N_p}{R_{sh}} \left(\frac{V_{PV}}{N_s} + \frac{R_s I_{PV}}{N_p} \right) \quad (7)$$

Considering zero sequence components in a 3-phase system is not necessary because there is no circulation path. Equation (8) depicts the three-phase balanced voltage:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{ga} \\ V_{gb} \\ V_{gc} \end{bmatrix} = V_m \begin{bmatrix} \sin \omega t \\ \sin(\omega t + 120^\circ) \\ \sin(\omega t - 120^\circ) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Control systems make it possible to improve the effectiveness as well as the quality of the electricity that is generated by a wind energy conversion system. They are closed-loop feedback systems that control switching elements in active power conversion stages. Initially, the rotational speed of the generator can be sensed and controlled using an active rectifier and a Proportional Integral (PI) controller. Also, the grid-side inverter PWM signal can be used to regulate the system. It can be adopted to keep the DC link at a constant voltage [13-17], which will decouple the grid from power fluctuations caused by wind variations.

Fig. 2. Overall control block illustration for MSC. (a) Reference generation of I_q . (b) Control block illustration.

The overall control method for the PMSG [1, 4, 9-12] based wind energy power system is depicted in Figure 2. The reference torque is generated in a torque control scheme by measuring the generator speed. The Park transformation is used to convert the measured 3-phase current in the stator into a d-q component. Thus, the stator current is equal to the q-axis component. Thus, torque is controlled by only changing the stator current in the q-axis direction. It is determined whether the measured d-q stator currents are greater than the reference

d-q currents in the stator, and the difference is connected to the PI controllers [8], which produce the stator reference voltages in the d-q components. The reference voltages in stator of d-q components are transformed to the reference 3-phase stator voltages V_a , V_b , and V_c and are sent to the PWM, which generates the converter switching pulses.

Fig. 3. Control block diagram of the GSC.

The GSC's role is to ensure that the dc-link voltage stays the same all the time [5]. Figure 3 depicts the block diagram of the control of GSC. The current reference (I_{dg_ref}) is generated using the PI+AWT method. The GSC output current is converted from abc signal to dq signal and the components of this current are compared with the reference currents I_{dg_ref} and I_{qg_ref} . This design is made up of one outer voltage loop and two inside current loops, which are connected. The dc-link voltage loop provides the reference d-axis component of grid current. It is necessary to match the reference and measured dc-link voltages, and vector control is used to handle errors. The reference d-axis grid current is produced by the PI+AWT controller. The inner Proportional-Resonant (PR) controller produces the d-q axis grid voltage from the d-axis reference grid current and the actual d-axis grid current. Park transformation is adopted to convert the d-q voltage components into natural abc grid components. The actual 3-phase abc grid voltage components are then sent to the PWM generator, which generates the firing pulses to the VSC. Figure 4 depicts the PR controller's block diagram. The PR control method has a high gain at the resonant frequency, which ensures that a little steady-state inaccuracy is presented between the actual and the reference signal. The PR controller is composed of a proportional and a resonant term.

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the PR current controller.

III. CUTTLEFISH OPTIMIZATION SCHEME

Cuttlefish is a species of mollusk and it is well-known for its ability to change color in such a way that it either blends in with its surroundings or puts on a spectacular show. The

program is designed to function in a manner analogous to the color-changing systems that are present in cuttlefish. The patterns and colors that can be observed on cuttlefish are the result of light being reflected off of the several layers of cells within the animal, including chromatophores, leucophores, and iridophores. Reflection and visibility are both taken into consideration by the CFA as important activities. The visibility process replicates the visibility of matching patterns, whereas the reflection process models the mechanism that controls how the light is reflected. The patterns and colors that may be seen in cuttlefish are the results of light being reflected from multiple layers of cells. The complete steps of the CFO algorithm are depicted in the flowchart of Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the CFO algorithm.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performance of proposed grid-connected HRES is analyzed using the MATLAB simulation results. The proposed work was simulated in 4 cases: constant wind speed and

irradiation, variable wind speed and constant irradiation, constant wind speed and variable irradiation, and variable wind speed and variable irradiation. The PR controller was adopted as the current controller. The CFA was adopted for dc voltage regulation and its performance was compared with conventional controllers', such as the AWT controller and the PSO algorithm. The simulation parameters are listed in Table I [7].

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Description	Value
PMSM parameters	
Stator phase resistance R_s	2.8750Ω
L_d (H), L_q (H)	8.5mH, 8.5mH
Inertia (kg.m ²)	0.0019
Friction factor (N.m.s)	0.001
No. of poles	4
Flux linkage	0.175 v.s
DC link parameters	
DC link capacitor	4700 μF
Reference DC voltage	800V
GSC parameters	
Switches	IGBT
Switching frequency	7000Hz
Filter inductance	6 mH
Grid parameters	
Voltage	400V (r.m.s)
Frequency	50 Hz
Source resistance	0.01Ω
Source inductance	2μH
Turbine parameters	
Reference wind speed	12m/s
Reference voltage	1.2 p.u
PV Parameters	
Open Circuit Voltage V_{oc}	43.5 V
Short Circuit Current I_{sc}	2.783 A

A. Case 1: Constant Wind Speed and Irradiation

In this case, the wind speed value was set at 12m/s and the PV irradiation was maintained constant and equal to 1000W/m² throughout the simulation as shown in Figures 6 and 7 respectively.

Fig. 6. Constant wind speed.

Fig. 7. Constant PV irradiation.

The CFA response curves are presented in Figure 8. The DC link voltage when using the CFA algorithm has a value of 800V and it is tracking the reference voltage after 0.06s. All the

grid voltages are sinusoidal in nature and balanced. The response curves of the grid voltage and current are also presented in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Response curves of CFA (case 1): (a) DC link Voltage, (b) grid Voltage, (c) grid current.

B. Case 2: Variable Wind Speed and Constant Irradiation

In this case, the variable wind speed depicted in Figure 9 was applied. The wind speed was 12m/s from 0 to 0.2s, it reduced to 8m/s at 0.2s, changed to 10m/s at 0.5sec, and changed back to the initial value at 0.8s.

Fig. 9. Variable wind speed.

Fig. 10. Response curves of CFA (case 2): (a) DC link Voltage, (b) grid Voltage, (c) grid current.

The response curves using CFO are presented in Figure 10. The DC link voltage using the CFA algorithm has a value of 800V and it is tracking the reference voltage after 0.06s. All the grid voltages are in sinusoidal nature and balanced. The response curves of the grid voltage and current are also presented in Figure 10.

C. Case 3: Constant Wind Speed and Variable Irradiation

In this case, the change of PV irradiation is applied as illustrated in Figure 11. A constant irradiation of 1000W/m² is applied from 0 to 0.5s, it is then reduced to 700W/m², and is again 1000W/m² at 0.8s. The response curves using CFO are presented in Figure 12. The DC link voltage using CFA algorithm has a value of 800V and it is tracking the reference voltage after 0.06s as depicted in Figure 12(a). All the grid voltages are sinusoidal in nature and balanced. The response curves of grid voltage and current are also presented in Figure 12.

Fig. 11. Variable PV irradiation.

Fig. 12. Response curves of CFA (case 3): (a) DC link Voltage, (b) grid Voltage, (c) grid current.

D. Case 4: Variable Wind Speed and Variable Irradiation

In this case, variable wind speed as depicted in Figure 6 and variable PV irradiation as illustrated in Figure 11 are applied. The response curves using CFO are presented in Figure 13. The DC link voltage using CFO algorithm has a value of 800V and it is tracking the reference voltage after 0.06s as depicted in Figure 13. All the grid voltages are sinusoidal in nature and balanced. The response curves of grid voltage and current are also presented in Figure 13.

Further, comparative performance analysis was conducted with THD. The FFT spectrum using the PI+AWT controller, the PSO algorithm, and CFA are presented in Figure 14. The THD when using the PI+AWT controller, PSO, and CFA is 1.97%, 1.62%, and 1.56% respectively. The proposed

controller (CFA) performed better than the PI+AWT controller and the PSO algorithm. The comparative performance indices are listed in Table II. It is observed that the CFA has performed well in regulating the dc voltage. The dc voltage reached the reference voltage at 0.04s which is less compared than the time it took in both PI+AWT and PSO.

Fig. 13. Response curves of CFA (case 4): (a) DC link Voltage, (b) grid Voltage, (c) grid current.

Fig. 14. THD comparison. FFT spectrum of grid current using (a) AWT controller, (b) PSO algorithm, (c) CFA.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

Controller	DC voltage settling time (s)	% THD in current signal
AWT	0.15	1.97
PSO	0.1	1.62
CFA	0.04	1.56

V. CONCLUSION

The concept of hybrid solar and wind power generation was described in detail in this paper, and the training procedure of a

CFA-based optimization algorithm is presented. From the results, it is realized that the CFA performed better than PI+AWT and PSO. Optimum DC voltage regulation is achieved with the use of the CFA algorithm. In order to demonstrate the applicability of the suggested controller, simulations were carried out in MATLAB/SIMULINK.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y.-M. Chen, Y.-C. Liu, S.-C. Hung, and C.-S. Cheng, "Multi-Input Inverter for Grid-Connected Hybrid PV/Wind Power System," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 1070–1077, Feb. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPEL.2007.897117>.
- [2] J. B. V. Subrahmanyam, P. Alluvada, Bandana, K. Bhanupriya, and C. Shashidhar, "Renewable Energy Systems: Development and Perspectives of a Hybrid Solar-Wind System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 177–181, Feb. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.104>.
- [3] A. F. Tazay, A. M. A. Ibrahim, O. Noureldeen, and I. Hamdan, "Modeling, Control, and Performance Evaluation of Grid-Tied Hybrid PV/Wind Power Generation System: Case Study of Gabel El-Zeit Region, Egypt," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 96528–96542, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2993919>.
- [4] A. V. P. Kumar, A. M. Parimi, and K. U. Rao, "Investigation of small PMSG based wind turbine for variable wind speed," in *2015 International Conference on Recent Developments in Control, Automation and Power Engineering (RDCAPE)*, Noida, India, Mar. 2015, pp. 107–112, <https://doi.org/10.1109/RDCAPE.2015.7281378>.
- [5] N. A. Orlando, M. Liserre, R. A. Mastromauro, and A. Dell'Aquila, "A Survey of Control Issues in PMSG-Based Small Wind-Turbine Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 1211–1221, Dec. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TII.2013.2272888>.
- [6] G. Mustafa, M. H. Baloch, S. H. Qazi, S. Tahir, N. Khan, and B. A. Mirjat, "Experimental Investigation and Control of a Hybrid (PV-Wind) Energy Power System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6781–6786, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3964>.
- [7] W. M. Amutha, Renugadevi, and V. Rajini, "A Novel Fused Converter for Hybrid Power Systems," *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 984–985, pp. 744–749, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.984-985.744>.
- [8] J. Biela, D. Hassler, J. Schönberger, and J. W. Kolar, "Closed-Loop Sinusoidal Input-Current Shaping of 12-Pulse Autotransformer Rectifier Unit With Impressed Output Voltage," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 249–259, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPEL.2010.2052633>.
- [9] X. Zeng, T. Liu, S. Wang, Y. Dong, and Z. Chen, "Comprehensive Coordinated Control Strategy of PMSG-Based Wind Turbine for Providing Frequency Regulation Services," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 63944–63953, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2915308>.
- [10] M. Benchagra, M. Maaroufi, and M. Ouassaid, "Study and analysis on the control of SCIG and its responses to grid voltage unbalance," in *2011 International Conference on Multimedia Computing and Systems*, Quarzazate, Morocco, Apr. 2011, pp. 1–5, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICMCS.2011.5945737>.
- [11] J. Liu, C. Zhao, and Z. Xie, "Power and Current Limiting Control of Wind Turbines Based on PMSG Under Unbalanced Grid Voltage," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 9873–9883, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3049839>.
- [12] A. Mittal and L. Taylor, "Optimization of Large Wind Farms Using a Genetic Algorithm," in *ASME 2012 International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition*, Houston, TX, USA, Nov. 2012, vol. 7, <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2012-87816>.
- [13] V. Narasimhulu, D. V. Ashok Kumar, and Ch. Sai Babu, "Computational intelligence based control of cascaded H-bridge multilevel inverter for shunt active power filter application," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-019-01660-0>.
- [14] V. Narasimhulu, D. V. Ashok Kumar, and Ch. Sai Babu, "Fuzzy Logic Control of SLMMC-Based SAPF Under Nonlinear Loads," *International Journal of Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 428–437, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40815-019-00622-0>.
- [15] M. Heidari, "Improve the Power Quality of Wind Power Plant by Modifying the Theory of Instantaneous Active and Reactive Power," *International Journal Of Renewable Energy Research*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 722–731, Sep. 2015.
- [16] V. Narasimhulu, D. V. Ashok Kumar, and Ch. Sai Babu, "Recital analysis of multilevel cascade H-bridge based active power filter under load variation," *SN Applied Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 12, Nov. 2019, Art. no. 1621, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-019-1669-8>.
- [17] V. Narasimhulu and K. Jithendra Gowd, "Performance Analysis of Single-Stage PV Connected Three-Phase Grid System Under Steady State and Dynamic Conditions," in *Cybernetics, Cognition and Machine Learning Applications*, Singapore, 2021, pp. 39–46, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-33-6691-6_5.
- [18] N. Regis, C. M. Muriithi, and L. Ngoo, "Optimal Battery Sizing of a Grid-Connected Residential Photovoltaic System for Cost Minimization using PSO Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4905–4911, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3094>.

One-dimensional Site Response Analysis and Liquefaction Evaluation of Can Tho City, Vietnam

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Abstract-Can Tho is the biggest city in the Mekong River Delta, one of the five national central cities in Vietnam. However, it has not been studied regarding seismic hazard estimation. For this purpose, one-dimensional nonlinear site response analysis of this city was performed in this paper. The measured in-situ profiles and corresponding geotechnical site investigation and laboratory test data were utilized to develop the site model for site-specific ground response analysis. A suite of earthquake records compatible with the Vietnam rock design spectrum (TCVN 9386:2012) was used as input ground motions at the bedrock. The results show that Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) increases from the bedrock to the surface. Maximum PGA is 0.083g for O Mon district (P1) and 0.073g for Cai Rang district (P2). The maximum shear strain is reported to be 0.35% for P1 and 0.45% for P2. The recommended amplification factors are 1.7 for P1 and 1.9 for P2. Even though Can Tho city is composed of soft layers, liquefaction is unlikely to occur.

Keywords-response spectra; one-dimensional nonlinear site response analysis; peak ground acceleration; shear strain; liquefaction assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

Seismic hazard assessment plays an important role in the sustainable development of urban infrastructure. Site response analysis and evaluating soil liquefaction potential is commonly used for that purpose. A total of 1645 earthquakes recorded in Vietnam with magnitude (M_L) of 3.0 or higher were considered in [1, 2]. In the 20th century, up to 90% of earthquakes occurred in northern Vietnam because that area lies on Indochina and South China faults [3]. The studies on seismic effects in southern Vietnam are almost non-existent. In recent years, several earthquakes have been recorded in south Vietnam, such as the earthquake that occurred on the coast of Vung Tau province in 2005, with $M_L = 4.5$, shaking the whole Ho Chi Minh City, the earthquake at the coast of Binh Thuan province in 2020, with $M_L = 4.7$. These earthquakes are related to the Thuan Hai – Minh Hai fault, which has a closet distance of about 45km from Can Tho city. There is a need for studies that assess the effects of earthquakes on the southern region of Vietnam, especially in large cities with dense population.

Regarding the central of Can Tho city, and to the best of our knowledge, no studies have been conducted on one-dimensional site response analysis and evaluation of ground behavior under earthquake effects. Can Tho is one of the 5 biggest cities in Vietnam, with nearly 1.3 million residents (2019). Can Tho is also the capital of the Southwest region and the economic center of the Cuu Long River Delta. The stratigraphy is mainly clay and sandy clay with large thickness, interspersed with fine sand layers with a thin thickness and deep. The groundwater level is shallow and changes seasonally due to the interlaced system of canals. This study aims to perform site response analysis and then propose design spectra for the ground in the area of Can Tho city. Two site classes, C and D, and 15 earthquakes, were adopted in this research. Also, the liquefaction assessment of this city is evaluated.

Fig. 1. Central of Can Tho city and investigated sites.

II. INVESTIGATED SOIL PROFILES

Figure 1 shows the two investigated soil profiles of Can Tho city considered in this study. These profiles represent site class C (O Mon district, named P1) and D (Cai Rang district, named P2) according to the Vietnam code [4]. The typical soil stratigraphy includes fill, clay or sandy clay/clayey sand, and gravel. The groundwater level is 0.6m and 2.2m depth for the soil profiles of P1 and P2. Details of the soil properties and shear wave velocity is presented in Tables I-II and Figure 2.

TABLE I. SOIL PROPERTIES OF P1

No	Material type	Thickness (m)	Depth (m)	Density (kg/m ³)	Shear wave velocity (m/s)
1	Fill	1.3	1.3	1500	100
2	Sandy clay	5.1	6.4	1570	100
3	Clay	6.2	12.6	1940	214
4	Clay	4.8	17.4	1940	219
5	Clayey sand	5.3	22.7	2000	259
6	Clay	3	25.7	2000	263

TABLE II. SOIL PROPERTIES OF P2

No	Material type	Thickness (m)	Depth (m)	Density (kg/m ³)	Shear wave velocity (m/s)
1	Fill	1.2	1.2	1500	100
2	Sandy clay	1.4	2.6	1680	100
3	Clay	6.8	9.4	1650	100
4	Clay	6.5	15.9	1790	141
5	Sandy clay	7.8	23.7	1720	209
6	Clay	5.7	29.4	1950	214

Fig. 2. Shear wave velocity profiles.

III. INPUT GROUND MOTIONS

The critical unknown in site response analysis is earthquake ground excitation. Due to the lack of available earthquake records in Can Tho city, ground motions recorded in other regions, but with similar characteristics to those likely to occur in Vietnam are selected. The recorded ground motions were selected from the NGA-west2 database (<https://ngawest2.berkeley.edu/>). The ground motions with the following features were selected:

- Range of moment magnitudes M_L 5.5-7.0.
- Rupture distance R_{rup} : 0.92-85.17km.
- Time-averaged shear-wave velocity to a depth of 30m (V_{S30}): 760-1500m/s.

A total of 15 motions with Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) ranging from 0.04g to 0.25g were selected from 12 earthquake events, as shown in Table III. The ground motions were scaled to the representative shaking intensity levels of each analyzed district, in which PGA levels at P1, and P2 were scaled to 0.0546g, and 0.0515g respectively. Also, the mean response spectrum of selected ground motions was matched closely to the spectrum of site class A of the Vietnam design code (MoC, 2012), as shown in Figure 3. These motions were also used in [1, 2].

Fig. 3. Input motions and design response spectra (a) P1, (b) P2.

TABLE III. SELECTED EARTHQUAKE EVENTS [1, 2]

Event	Year	Station	M_w	Mechanism	R_{rup} (km)	V_{S30} (m/s)
San Fernando	1971	Pasadena - Old Seismo Lab	6.61	Reverse	21.5	969.07
Whittier Narrows-01	1987	Pasadena - CIT Kresge Lab	5.99	Reverse	18.12	969.07
Loma Prieta	1989	Piedmont Jr High School Grounds	6.93	Reverse oblique	73	895.36
Loma Prieta	1989	Point Bonita	6.93	Reverse oblique	83.45	1315.92
Loma Prieta	1989	SF - Pacific Heights	6.93	Reverse oblique	75.96	1249.86
Loma Prieta	1989	So. San Francisco_ Sierra Pt.	6.93	Reverse oblique	63.15	1020.62
Northridge-01	1994	LA - Wonderland Ave	6.99	Reverse	20.29	1222.52
Northridge-01	1994	Vasquez Rocks Park	6.99	Reverse	23.64	996.43
Chi-Chi_Taiwan-05	1999	TTN042	6.20	Reverse	85.17	845.34
Umbria-03_Italy	1984	Gubbio	5.60	Normal	15.72	922
Kobe_Japan	1995	Kobe University	6.90	Strike slip	0.92	1043
Chi-Chi_Taiwan-05	1999	HWA002	6.20	Reverse	45.03	789.18

IV. ONE-DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS

One-dimensional (1D) nonlinear analysis was performed using DEEPSOIL v7.0 [5-9]. The most widely used pressure-dependent hyperbolic, the Modified Kodner-Zelasko (MKZ) model [10], implemented in DEEPSOIL, was used. Darendeli model [11] was employed to generate the dynamic properties of soil layers. The variables required to generate the nonlinear curves for each layer are the coefficient of lateral earth pressure (K_0), Plasticity Index (PI), number and frequency of cycles (N), loading frequency (f), and the Over Consolidation Ratio (OCR). Due to the unavailability of site-specific index properties, PI and OCR were taken as 0 and 1 respectively. N and f were set to 10 and 1 as recommended in [11], whereas K_0 was specified as 0.5. Figure 4 presents a flowchart of the site response and liquefaction evaluation procedure implemented in this study. The flowchart illustrates that a suite of nonlinear site response analyses are used to determine the site-specific spectral shapes, PGA, and maximum shear strain profiles of the P1 and P2 areas. Moreover, the proposed response spectra resulting from this study provide insights into the discrepancies between the design and site-specific spectra. The Cyclic Stress

Ratio (CSR) was also obtained from 1D site response analysis and was used for the liquefaction evaluation purpose.

Fig. 4. Response spectra comparison of the surface, input motion, and bedrock design.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5(a) shows the PGA along with the depth of P1 and P2 soil profiles. PGA increases from the bedrock to the surface except at the 2.5 – 7.5m depth. The decrease at that depth can be attributed to a significant thickness of the soft soil. Surface PGAs are 0.083g at P1 and 0.073g at P2. Shear strain profiles are shown in Figure 5(b). The shear strain of P1 and P2 reached 0.35% and 0.45% respectively. The maximum value of shear strain occurs at the approximate position of the boundary between the soil layers with a significant shear wave velocity difference.

Fig. 5. PGA and shear strain profiles.

Figure 6 presents the surface response spectra for P1 and P2. The average response spectrum of the input earthquakes and the design spectrum according to the Vietnamese code (bedrock) are also shown. The maximum values of spectra acceleration of P1 and P2 are at periods of 0.4s and 0.3s respectively. Figure 7 depicts the proposed surface response spectra against the calculated and design ones. The proposed surface response spectra were computed based on [12]:

$$S = \frac{I_{soil}}{I_{rock}} \quad (1)$$

where S is the soil factor and I_{soil} and I_{rock} are the spectral acceleration index of soil and rock respectively:

$$I_{soil \text{ or } rock} = \int_{0.05}^{2.5} Sa(T) \quad (2)$$

S was 1.7 and 1.9 for P1 (site class C) and P2 (site class D). In the Vietnam design code [4], these values are 1.15 and 1.35 for site class C and site class D.

Fig. 6. Response spectra comparison of the surface, input motion, and bedrock design.

Fig. 7. Response spectra comparison of the calculated surface, proposed surface, and bedrock design.

In this study, the empirical correlation proposed in [13] is used to assess the liquefaction potential of the soil, which relates V_{S1} to CCR as follows:

$$CRR = \left\{ a \left(\frac{K_c V_{S1}}{100} \right)^2 + b \left(\frac{1}{V_{S1}^* - K_c V_{S1}} - \frac{1}{V_{S1}^*} \right) \right\} MSF \quad (3)$$

where $a = 0.022$, $b = 2.8$, K_c = correction factor for high value of V_{S1} caused by cementation, MSF is the Magnitude Scaling Factor, and $V_{S1} = V_S$ corrected for the effect of overburden pressure. They are determined as follows:

$$MSF = \left(\frac{M_w}{7.5} \right)^{-2.56} \quad (4)$$

$$V_{S1} = V_S \left(\frac{P_a}{\sigma'_v} \right)^{0.25} \quad (5)$$

where M_w is the moment magnitude, P_a is the atmospheric pressure, σ'_v is the effective overburden stress (kPa), and V_{S1}^* is the critical value of V_{S1} that separates the contractive and dilative behavior of soil. The recommended V_{S1}^* value is dependent on the Fines Content (FC) as follows:

- $V_{S1}^* = 215\text{m/s}$ for sand and gravels with $FC \leq 5\%$.
- $V_{S1}^* = 215 - 0.5(FC - 5)\text{m/s}$ for sand and gravel with $5\% < FC < 35\%$.
- $V_{S1}^* = 200\text{m/s}$ for sand and gravels with $FC \geq 35\%$

For a conservative estimate, $FC \leq 5\%$ and $V_{S1}^* = 215\text{m/s}$ are used. V_{S1} based on the measured V_S profiles are shown in Figure 8. Liquefaction potential assessment for Can Tho city area was performed utilizing the maximum CSR calculated from the nonlinear site response analyses presented in Section IV and the CSR presented in this section.

Because not the entire soil profile is susceptible to liquefaction, liquefaction potential was assessed only for the fill, sandy clay layer with $V_{S1}^* < 215\text{m/s}$. The averaged results from the input motions are shown in Figure 9. The liquefaction assessment shows that even though the soil profiles at Can Tho city are composed of soft layers, liquefaction is unlikely to occur due to the low seismic hazard of the region. It should also be noted that the assessment is based on the significantly conservative estimate that even layers with clay content are susceptible to liquefaction.

Fig. 8. Overburden stress-corrected shear wave velocity V_{S1} profiles.

Fig. 9. Overburden stress-corrected shear wave velocity V_{S1} profiles.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study evaluates the behavior of the ground under earthquake loading at the center of Can Tho city, Vietnam. A total of 15 recorded input motions and two investigated soil profiles were considered and one-dimensional nonlinear ground analysis and liquefaction potential assessment were performed. The following conclusions were drawn:

- PGA increases from the bedrock to the surface. The maximum values of PGA are 0.083g for P1 (site class C) and 0.073g for P2 (site class D).
- The maximum shear strain occurs at the boundary between two soil layers with a large difference in shear wave velocities. The maximum values of the shear strain are 0.35% for P1 and 0.45% for P2.
- Design response spectra are proposed in this study area. The recommended soil factor is 1.7 for P1 and 1.9 for P2.
- The liquefaction potential is assessed using the empirical liquefaction triggering chart based on the in-situ measured V_S . The results demonstrated that there is no liquefaction susceptibility in Can Tho city.

REFERENCES

- [1] V.-Q. Nguyen, M. Aaqib, D.-D. Nguyen, N.-V. Luat, and D. Park, "A Site-Specific Response Analysis: A Case Study in Hanoi, Vietnam," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 11, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 3972, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10113972>.
- [2] N.-L. Tran, M. Aaqib, B.-P. Nguyen, D.-D. Nguyen, V.-L. Tran, and V.-Q. Nguyen, "Evaluation of Seismic Site Amplification Using 1D Site Response Analyses at Ba Dinh Square Area, Vietnam," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2021, Aug. 2021, Art. no. e3919281, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/3919281>.
- [3] T. V. Hung, "Study on earthquake ground motion prediction and its application to structural response of bridge in Vietnam," Ph.D. dissertation, Waseda University, Tokyo, Japan, 2012.
- [4] *TCVN 9386:2012 - Design of structures for earthquake resistances*. Hanoi, Vietnam: MoC, 2012.
- [5] Y. M. A. Hashash, *Deeppsoil User Manual*. Champaign, IL, USA: University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, 2016.
- [6] A. Behshad and M. R. Shekari, "Seismic Performance Evaluation of Concrete Gravity Dams with Penetrated Cracks Considering Fluid-Structure Interaction," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2546–2554, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1729>.
- [7] T. Nagao, "Maximum Credible Earthquake Ground Motions with Focus on Site Amplification due to Deep Subsurface," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 6873–6881, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3991>.
- [8] A. Razmyar and A. Eslami, "Geotechnical Characterization of Soils in the Eastern and Western Areas of Tehran," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1802–1810, Aug. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1200>.
- [9] S. Sadiq, Q. van Nguyen, H. Jung, and D. Park, "Effect of Flexibility Ratio on Seismic Response of Cut-and-Cover Box Tunnel," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2019, Jul. 2019, Art. no. e4905329, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4905329>.
- [10] N. Matasović and M. Vucetic, "Cyclic Characterization of Liquefiable Sands," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 119, no. 11, pp. 1805–1822, Nov. 1993, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1993\)119:11\(1805\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1993)119:11(1805)).
- [11] M. B. Darendeli, "Development of a new family of normalized modulus reduction and material damping curves," Ph.D. Dissertation Ph.D. dissertation, University of Texas at Austin, Austin, TX, USA, 2001.
- [12] J. Rey, E. Faccioli, and J. J. Bommer, "Derivation of design soil coefficients (S) and response spectral shapes for Eurocode 8 using the European Strong-Motion Database," *Journal of Seismology*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 547–555, Oct. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1021169715992>.
- [13] R. D. Andrus and K. H. Stokoe II, "Liquefaction Resistance of Soils from Shear-Wave Velocity," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 126, no. 11, pp. 1015–1025, Nov. 2000, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(2000\)126:11\(1015\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2000)126:11(1015)).

A Novel Blind Image Source Separation Using Hybrid Firefly Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm

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Abstract—Signal and image separation are extensively used in numerous imaging applications and communication systems. In this paper, a novel Blind Source Separation (BSS) approach, based on the Hybrid Firefly Particle Swarm Optimization (HFPSO), is proposed for separating mixed images. This approach processes the observed source without any prior knowledge about the model and the statistics of the source signal. The proposed method presents high robustness against local minima and converges quickly to the global minimum. Via numerical simulations, the proposed approach is tested and validated in comparison with standard Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Robust Independent Component Analysis (RobustICA), and Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithms. The obtained results show that the presented technique outperforms the existing ones in terms of quality of image separation, the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM). Moreover, the obtained results demonstrate that our approach provides also promising results in image separation from noisy mixtures.

Keywords—blind image separation; hybrid firefly particle swarm optimization; PSNR; SSIM

I. INTRODUCTION

Blind Source Separation (BSS) is a signal processing approach that was first proposed in the late '80s [1]. The BSS refers to the separation of unknown signals that are mixed in an unknown manner. It has been an important topic in many applications of signal processing, such as medical imaging, communication systems, speech processing, image processing, etc. [2, 3]. Unlike speech signals, it is well known that images cannot easily satisfy the constraints of the BSS method. During the past three decades, most research studies on the BSS

problem have been focused on speech separation. Nowadays, researchers are more interested in blind image separation due to its importance in many real-world applications.

Generally, the Independent Component Analysis (ICA) approach has been considered as a solution to many BSS problems [4]. This approach lies in the fact that the assumption of statistical independence and the non-Gaussian restraint among the sources does not hold in image mixing conditions. However, the ICA approach faces some limitations and drawbacks, i.e. it is not able to separate the signals if the number of sensors is less than the number of sources. Furthermore, the local minima problem is another limitation of the ICA method in many applications. In order to overcome the drawbacks of ICA approach, many optimization methods have been developed, based on evolutionary algorithms. These algorithms have been extensively used for tackling BSS problems [5-8]. By using Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), a blind separation method based on reducing mutual information has been introduced in [5]. Using GA, the blind separation problem is also investigated in [6] based on high order statistics of kurtosis. In the same context, a cost function based on the feature distance and kurtosis was proposed to solve BSS problems using PSO and GA [7]. Besides, the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm was applied in [8] to solve BSS problem using a combination of many types of the cost function.

Most previous studies have discussed blind speech separation. However, in this study, a novel separation approach using a modified version of the Hybrid Firefly Particle Swarm Optimization (HFPSO) algorithm will be used to separate image mixtures. To evaluate the performance of the proposed

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hybrid method, we present a fair comparison with other works where four examples are illustrated under noisy and noiseless conditions.

II. ONE-DIMENSIONAL BLIND SIGNAL SEPARATION PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Assume that $S_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are unknown signals that are independent and feasible. The source signals are linearly blinded with each other by the mixing matrix A as:

$$X = A.S \quad (1)$$

A linear instantaneous blind image separation algorithm is the one suggested in this paper for image separation. This indicates that the constant random coefficients are present in the mixing model. This relation in a noisy environment will be:

$$X = A.S + n \quad (2)$$

where the additive noise signal is denoted by n . The objective separation is to estimate the unmixing matrix W without any knowledge about the mixing matrix A . The unmixing matrix is used to approximate the original source signals using the following equation.

$$Y = W.X \quad (3)$$

where Y represents an estimate of source signal S . It is obvious that the estimated signals involved in Y assuming $W = A^{-1}$ are the exact same as the original sources S .

III. PREPROCESSING PROCEDURES OF THE SEPARATION PROBLEM

To prevent using a difficult optimization approach, the preprocessing phase should be completed in the first step of the separation procedure. The signals are centered and whitened during the preprocessing stage. In order to produce the observed signals with zero mean value, centering is conducted by subtracting the average values $M_i = E_i(X_i)$ from the observed signals. With a linear transmission, whitening transforms the mixed signals into white uncorrelated and with unit variance signals. The identity matrix of the whitened covariance matrix X is given by [9]:

$$E\{\tilde{X}.\tilde{X}^T\} = I \quad (4)$$

To obtain the whitened mixed signals, the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) algorithm is used. The eigenvectors of the covariance matrix of the observed signals are employed as follows:

$$\tilde{X} = UV^{-\frac{1}{2}}U^T X = UV^{-\frac{1}{2}}U^T A.S = \text{diag}\left(V_1^{-\frac{1}{2}} \dots V_m^{-\frac{1}{2}}\right) \quad (5)$$

where V is a diagonal eigenvalue matrix and U is the orthogonal eigenvector matrix. It is important to note that applying the whitening stage will result in an orthogonal new mixing matrix and a reduction in the number of parameters that must be evaluated throughout the optimization phase.

IV. OVERVIEW OF PSO AND FIREFLY ALGORITHMS

A. Partial Swarm Optimization (PSO)

PSO was proposed in [10]. The motions of bird and fish swarms in pursuit of food or fleeing from perceived threats served as the model's inspiration. PSO algorithm has outperformed many other search methods due to its ability to find results quickly, requiring fewer parameters, while being less likely to become trapped at local optima. PSO begins with a collection of random solutions known as particles, with a group of particles being referred to as a crowd or flock. Mathematically, initialization of the i th particle is determined by $x_i = l_b + \text{rand}(u_b - l_b)$, where l_b and u_b are the lower and upper bounds. Each particle in the solution space is first assigned a random value as part of the search process. Each particle's position will be modified at each iteration based on its best position p_1 and the best positions of the other particles in its topological neighborhood $gbest$. The velocity vector v_i^t will be added to find the new position. PSO is an iterative process, and at each iteration v_i^t and x_i are defined respectively according to the following rules:

$$v_i^t = wv_i^{t-1} + R_1C_1(pbset_i - x_i) + R_2C_2(gbest - x_i) \quad (6)$$

$$x_i^t = x_i^{t-1} + v_i^t \quad (7)$$

where w represents the inertia weight which is significant in the exploration/exploitation process, v_i^t and x_i^t indicate the velocity and the position of the i th particle at iteration t , $pbset_i$ and $gbest$ stand for the location of the best solution so far discovered by the i th particle and the best overall solution respectively. Two random numbers, R_1 and R_2 , were produced from a uniformly distributed range $[0, 1]$ Since C_1 is multiplied by the distance to each particle's optimal position and C_2 is multiplied by the distance to the optimal position for all particles, C_1 and C_2 are the cognition and social learning components respectively.

B. Firefly Algorithm (FA)

FA was first developed in [11, 12]. FA is known as a metaheuristic optimization technique which is inspired by the natural behavior of fireflies [11-14]. The algorithm considers randomly generated solutions as fireflies, and brightness is assigned based upon their performance on the objective function. One of the rules used to construct the algorithm is that a firefly will be attracted to a brighter firefly, and if there is no brighter firefly, it will move randomly. The inverse square law is used to calculate the amount of light (I) at a given distance (r) from a light source. As a result, as distance rises, light intensity diminishes. In addition, light weakens and loses intensity as distance rises due to absorption by the air. Due to these factors, fireflies can typically be seen from only a few hundred meters away, which is a sufficient range for them to communicate. As a result, flashing light may be expressed as the objective function to be improved, which offers a new population-based optimization method [11, 12]. According to the inverse square law, a light intensity $I(r)$ at r distance from a light source I_s can be estimated by:

$$I(r) = \frac{I_s}{r^2} \quad (8)$$

Light is absorbed in an environment with a constant light absorption coefficient $\gamma \in [0, \infty]$. As a result, one can use the following equation to build a Gaussian:

$$B(r) = B_0 e^{-\gamma r^2} \quad (9)$$

A firefly's attraction at a distance r is $B(r)$, while its attractiveness at $r = 0$ is B_0 . Suppose i and j are two fireflies with positions $X_i(x_i, y_i)$ and $X_j(x_j, y_j)$ respectively. The Euclidean distance r_{ij} between two fireflies is computed by:

$$r_{ij} = \|X_i - X_j\| = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \quad (10)$$

The new position X_i of the less brilliant firefly i and its migration toward the more brilliant firefly j , is calculated by:

$$X_i = X_i + B_0 e^{-\gamma r_{ij}^2} (x_j - x_i) + \alpha \epsilon_i \quad (11)$$

where ϵ_i is a vector of random variables drawn from the Gaussian distribution and $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is a randomization parameter [15, 16].

$$w = w_i - \left(\frac{w_i - w_f}{iteration_{max}} \right) \times iteration \quad (12)$$

$$f(i, t) = \begin{cases} \text{true, if } fitness(\text{particle}_i^t) \leq gbest^{t-1} \\ \text{true, if } fitness(\text{particle}_i^t) > gbest^{t-1} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$V_i(t + 1) = X_i(t + 1) - X_{i_temp} \quad (14)$$

where:

$$X_i(t + 1) = X_i(t) + B_0 e^{-\gamma r_{ij}^2} (X_i(t) - gbest^{t-1}) + \alpha \epsilon_i,$$

w is the inertia weight, w_i and w_f are the initial and final values of the linear decreasing inertia weight respectively.

V. THE PROPOSED SEPARATION APPROACH

The proposed separation approach is presented in this section. The newly developed BSS system is used here in order to solve issues with multiple image source separation. Our technique is based on the HFPSO algorithm [17]. This hybridization makes allow combining the search power PSO with the optimization capabilities of FA. This approach makes use of both algorithms' characteristics and seeks to find a balance between exploration and exploitation [17]. Basically, our approach has been implemented in 4 stages (See Figure 1): In the first stage, the input image sources decomposed into 1-D signals are mixed. After that, HFPSO algorithm is used to unmix the output signals. Then, (3) is used to estimate the output signals and the estimated output signals were transformed into images. In the last stage, the effectiveness of the BSS system is assessed.

A. Hybrid Firefly and PSO (HFPSO)

PSO is typically utilized in the global search in the proposed hybrid combination of two algorithms because it offers quick convergence in exploration. Furthermore, FA is frequently employed in local search since it offers exploitation fine-tuning. Studies on inertia weight that are dynamically modified and take improvements over prior personal bests have been successful [16]. The main objective of HFPSO is to benefit from the advantages of FA and PSO algorithms [17]. Exploration will benefit from the PSO algorithm, and the FA will look after local search. The inertia weight will be dynamically updated. The initialization of all the parameters is the first step in the HFPSO algorithm. Particle locations and velocities are initialized to random values in the predetermined ranges. Fitness, global best ($gbest$), and individual best ($pbest_i$) will then be computed. The particle's fitness in the current stage and in the previous iteration will be compared according to (13). The FA will assume control and local search will begin if the particle fitness value is the same or improved; otherwise, the PSO algorithm proceeds in accordance with (6). If the FA algorithm is in use, then (11) and (14) will be used to determine position and the velocity. The ranges of position and velocity for each firefly and each particle are checked in the following step. The process will be stopped if the maximum number of iterations is reached and the output will be $gbest$ and its fitness value.

B. Evaluation of the Objective Function

The fitness function suggested in this paper is based upon mutual information and kurtosis. Kurtosis is a crucial component of BSS. It is used here to sort the independent components and to measure the non-Gaussianity of signals. The degree of dependence between the components is measured with mutual information. The later must be kept to a minimum in order to have independent components. The definition of the mutual information is:

$$I(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n H(y_i) - H(Y) \quad (15)$$

where $H(y_i) = -E \cdot \log(p_{y_i}(y_i))$ and $H(Y) = -E \cdot \log(p_Y(y))$ are the entropies of the estimated original signals, E denotes the expectation operator, and $p_Y(y)$ the density of the kurtosis y . By using the following formula, the kurtosis of the estimated original signals can be calculated:

$$Kurt(y) = \sum_{i=1}^n |E(y_i^4) - 3E^2(y_i^2)| \quad (16)$$

The fitness function can be expressed by:

$$J = I(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) + Kurt(y) \quad (17)$$

When the fitness function J is maximized, the estimated signals are mutually independent.

Fig. 1. Diagram of the proposed method.

C. BSS using HFPSO Algorithm

In this part, the HFPSO algorithm will be used to determine the coefficient for the separating matrix W . By maximizing the objective function given in (17), the optimization technique seeks to identify the coefficients that will result in estimated signals that are independent. The dimension D of the optimization procedure is the same as the number of coefficients in the separation matrix. The iterative process of Figure 2 can be used to implement the HFPSO-based BSS algorithm.

```

01: Initialize  $t = 0$ ;
02: A random initial set of parameters is used to construct an
    initial population of size using the parameters  $\{W_{i=1}^{pop}\}$  and
     $\{v_{i=1}^{pop}\}$ ;
03: Each fitness particle,  $\{W_{i=1}^{pop}\}$  evaluated using (17);
04: if fitness $\{W_{i=1}^{pop}\} > pbest_i$  according to (13) then
05:    $W_{i,temp} = W_i$ ;
06:    $W_i = W_i + B_0 e^{-\gamma r_{ij}^2} (W_j - W_i) + \alpha \epsilon_i$ ;
07:    $V_i(t+1) = W_i(t+1) - W_{i,temp}$ 
08: else
09: Update  $w$  using (12);
10:  $v_i^t = w v_i^{t-1} + R_1 C_1 (pbest_i - W_i) + R_2 C_2 (gbest - W_i)$ ;
11:  $W_i = W_i + v_i^t$ ;
12:  $t = t + 1$ ;
13: Repeat steps 2 until convergence is reached;
14: Output the panicle  $W$  with the best fitness value and
    compute the separated signals  $y = W \cdot X$ .
15: Separated signals transformed into images.
  
```

Fig. 2. Pseudocode of the HFPSO BSS algorithm.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this section, some computer simulations were carried out in order to assess the effectiveness and compare the performance of the proposed approach against PSO, ABC, and RobustICA [18]. In all the conducted experiments, four benchmark images ("Ily", "Parrot", "Barbara" and "Einstein") were used. During initialization, the sensors and sources are set to 2 elements each. The 2×2 mixing matrix A is randomly chosen as follows:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0.6 & -0.4 \\ -0.4 & 0.6 \end{bmatrix}$$

A. Parameters Settings

The different parameter initialization values for the proposed HFPSO approach are: The population pop size is fixed to 50, the problem has a dimension of 4 ($D = 4$), minimum velocity $v_{min} = -v_{max}$, maximum velocity $v_{max} = 0.1$, search range $(x_{max} - x_{min})$, inertia weight $w_i = 0.9$, and $w_f = 0.5$, $C_1 = 1.49$, $C_2 = 1.495$, $\beta_0 = 0$, $\gamma = 1$, and $\alpha_0 = 0.5$.

B. Performance Evaluation

In this paper, two performance indices have been used to assess the effectiveness of the proposed method, the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM). The PSNR is defined by [19]:

$$PSNR(f, g) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{255^2}{MSE(f, g)} \right) \quad (18)$$

where MSE is the mean squared error which is calculated by

$$MSE(f, g) = \frac{1}{M \times N} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^N (f_{ij} - g_{ij})^2 \quad (19)$$

where f is the original image, g is the reconstructed image and the size of the images is $M \times N$.

The SSIM index is defined as [20, 21]:

$$SSIM(f, g) = \frac{(2\mu_i \mu_{rec} + c_1)(2\sigma_i \sigma_{rec} + c_2)}{(\mu_i^2 + \mu_{rec}^2 + c_1)(\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_{rec}^2 + c_1)} \quad (20)$$

where rec and i for the reconstructed and original images, respectively, and σ_{rec} and σ_i are the mean standard deviations of the original and reconstructed images. The positive constants c_1 and c_2 are used to avoid a null denominator. We choose specifically in this paper $c_1 = (K_1 L)^2$ and $c_2 = (K_2 L)^2$, where $K_1 = 0.01$, $K_2 = 0.03$ and $L = 255$.

In order to assess the performance of the proposed approach, three different simulations were conducted. The obtained results are presented in Figures 3 and 4 for the noise-free case and in Figure 5 for the noisy case. For noisy mixtures, we assumed that the mixed images are corrupted by an additive white Gaussian noise with SNR equal to 5dB. We list in the upper-left part of each Figure the used grayscale benchmark images ("Bear Lake Lighthouse" and "Henry David Thoreau" images for Figure 3, "Charlie Chaplin" and "Albert Einstein" images for Figures 4 and 5). These test images were marked as Public Domain or CC0 and are free to use [22]. The sizes of all test images are 256×256 . The mixtures of each pair of images appear always in the upper-right part of the presented Figures. As a result of the experiments, the separated images from RobustICA, PSO, ABC, and the proposed approach are listed in the second and third rows of these Figures. For the noise-free case, Figure 3 shows the experimental results with "Bear Lake Lighthouse" and "Henry David Thoreau" images, while the obtained results for "Charlie Chaplin" and "Albert Einstein" images are presented in Figures 4 and 5.

It is illustrated in Figures 3 and 4 and can be seen from the obtained results for the noise-free scenario, that the proposed approach performs better than RobustICA, PSO, and ABC. In fact, we can observe that the separated images using our method have a better quality compared to those separated by other methods. PSO and ABC provide acceptable results as well (see Figures 3(d), 3(e), 4(d) and 4(e)). It can be observed also that the separation quality of the RobustICA method is relatively poor. In order to evaluate quantitatively the effectiveness of the introduced approach and compare its separation performance against RobustICA, PSO, and ABC methods, the PSNR and SSIM indices were used. For instance, the numerical metrics obtained from different separation methods are reported below subfigures (c), (d), (e) and (f) of Figures 3 and 4. From this, we can observe that the visual improvements of the proposed separation method are consistent with the reported numerical results.

Fig. 3. Results of separating mixtures of noise-free images (a) original images. From left to right: "Bear Lake Lighthouse" and "Henry David Thoreau", (b) mixed images, (c) RobustICA, (d) PSO, (e) ABC, (f) proposed.

Fig. 4. Results of separating mixtures of noise-free images: (a) Original images. From left to right: "Charlie Chaplin" and "Albert Einstein", (b) mixed images (c) RobustICA, (d) PSO, (e) ABC, (f) proposed.

Fig. 5. Results of separating mixtures at noise level 5dB (a) Original images, (b) mixed images, (c) RobustICA, (d) PSO, (e) ABC, (f) proposed.

TABLE I. PSNR (DB) FOR THE PROPOSED APPROACH, ABC, PSO AND ROBUSTICA ALGORITHMS AT DIFFERENT NOISE LEVELS

Separation method	Proposed	ABC	PSO	RobustICA
SNR = ∞				
Charlie Chaplin	31.7251	16.5566	20.2721	3.2623
Albert Einstein	21.5259	21.1023	18.3893	5.8787
SNR = 5dB				
Charlie Chaplin	26.9971	15.4666	19.1798	2.1783
Albert Einstein	19.2665	19.1782	15.9317	5.0329
SNR = 0dB				
Charlie Chaplin	21.5486	12.5340	17.2280	2.744
Albert Einstein	14.9109	13.8784	12.7259	5.6871
SNR = -5dB				
Charlie Chaplin	17.1398	13.3876	17.0051	2.3869
Albert Einstein	11.0998	11.0006	11.0156	5.1287

Now, we will show the results of separation process at different noise levels (SNR = ∞, 5, 0, and -5 dB). According to Figure 5, for noisy images at SNR=5dB, it can be observed that our method still provides acceptable separation quality despite the presence of additive white Gaussian noise (See Figure 5(f)). However, the RobustICA is highly affected by noise and provides therefore much poorer quality than PSO and ABC. This is well illustrated in Figure 5(c)-(e). Further numerical results are summarized in Tables I and II. Here the test images are only "Charlie Chaplin" and "Albert Einstein", since the

other cases give similar conclusions. For all noise levels, Table I indicates that the PSNR of the resulting images by the proposed method is the best. In addition, as illustrated in Table II, our approach achieves also the highest SSIM results for the considered noise levels. In summary, it can be shown that the proposed method produces higher quality and efficiency compared to the RobustICA, PSO, and ABC approaches in terms of PSNR and SSIM indices. This indicates that our approach has strong separation capability.

TABLE II. SSIM FOR THE PROPOSED APPROACH, ABC, PSO AND ROBUSTICA ALGORITHMS AT DIFFERENT NOISE LEVELS

Separation method	Proposed approach	ABC algorithm	PSO	RobustICA
SNR = ∞				
Charlie Chaplin	0.9825	0.6650	0.8788	-0.2733
Albert Einstein	0.7790	0.7090	0.6466	-0.0893
SNR = 5dB				
Charlie Chaplin	0.8298	0.5677	0.8088	-0.2988
Albert Einstein	0.7070	0.6914	0.5827	-0.0947
SNR = 0dB				
Charlie Chaplin	0.6514	0.4402	0.6276	-0.2923
Albert Einstein	0.6109	0.5502	0.4453	-0.0767
SNR = -5dB				
Charlie Chaplin	0.6084	0.5464	0.5938	-0.2994
Albert Einstein	0.3049	0.3008	0.3036	-0.0898

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper addressed the blind source separation problem by introducing a novel image separation approach based on a hybrid firefly and particle swarm optimization algorithm. The performance of the proposed approach has been assessed and tested against PSO, RobustICA, and ABC methods using different benchmark images. The simulation results demonstrate that our approach is more effective at separating noiseless source images from their observed mixture than other methods. In addition, the proposed technique still provides acceptable separation quality in noisy situation. As a future perspective, it will be good to examine multi-objective optimization for more than two sources.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Herault, C. Jutten, and B. Ans, "Detection de grandeurs primitives dans un message composite par une architecture de calcul neuromimetique en apprentissage non supervise," in *10^e Colloque sur le traitement du signal et des images*, Nice, France, Jan. 1985, pp. 1017–1022.
- [2] G. D. Pelegrina, L. T. Duarte, and C. Jutten, "Blind source separation and feature extraction in concurrent control charts pattern recognition: Novel analyses and a comparison of different methods," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 92, pp. 105–114, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2015.12.017>.
- [3] H. Buchner, E. Petersen, M. Eger, and P. Rostalski, "Convolutional blind source separation on surface EMG signals for respiratory diagnostics and medical ventilation control," in *2016 38th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, Orlando, FL, USA, Dec. 2016, pp. 3626–3629, <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2016.7591513>.
- [4] F. J. Theis, "Uniqueness of complex and multidimensional independent component analysis," *Signal Processing*, vol. 84, no. 5, pp. 951–956, May 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sigpro.2004.01.008>.
- [5] S. Mavaddaty and A. Ebrahimzadeh, "Blind signals separation with genetic algorithm and particle swarm optimization based on mutual information," *Radioelectronics and Communications Systems*, vol. 54, no. 6, Jul. 2011, Art. no. 315, <https://doi.org/10.3103/S0735272711060045>.
- [6] S. Mavaddaty and A. Ebrahimzadeh, "Evaluation of Performance of Genetic Algorithm for Speech Signals Separation," in *2009 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Control, and Telecommunication Technologies*, Bangalore, India, Sep. 2009, pp. 681–683, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACT.2009.173>.
- [7] Y. Yang, X. Wang, and D. Zhang, "Blind Source Separation Research Based on the Feature Distance Using Evolutionary Algorithms," *International Journal of Acoustics and Vibrations*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 276–281, Dec. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.20855/ijav.2014.19.4360>.
- [8] L. Chen, L. Y. Zhang, and Y. J. Guo, "Blind Image Separation Method Based on Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm," *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 468–471, pp. 583–586, 2012, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.468-471.583>.
- [9] S. Mavaddati, "Blind Voice Separation Based on Empirical Mode Decomposition and Grey Wolf Optimizer Algorithm," *Iranian Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 330–342, Sep. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.22068/IJEEE.15.3.330>.
- [10] J. Kennedy and R. Eberhart, "Particle swarm optimization," in *Proceedings of ICNN'95 - International Conference on Neural Networks*, Aug. 1995, vol. 4, pp. 1942–1948, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICNN.1995.488968>.
- [11] X.-S. Yang, "Firefly Algorithms for Multimodal Optimization," in *Stochastic Algorithms: Foundations and Applications*, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 169–178, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-04944-6_14.
- [12] X.-S. Yang, "Firefly algorithm, stochastic test functions and design optimisation," *International Journal of Bio-Inspired Computation*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 78–84, Nov. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBIC.2010.032124>.
- [13] N. M. Okasha, "Reliability-Based Design Optimization of Trusses with Linked-Discrete Design Variables using the Improved Firefly Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 964–971, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.675>.
- [14] M. F. Masouleh, M. A. A. Kazemi, M. Alborzi, and A. T. Eshlaghy, "A Genetic-Firefly Hybrid Algorithm to Find the Best Data Location in a Data Cube," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 1187–1194, Oct. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.702>.
- [15] A. Nickabadi, M. M. Ebadzadeh, and R. Safabakhsh, "A novel particle swarm optimization algorithm with adaptive inertia weight," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 3658–3670, Jun. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2011.01.037>.
- [16] M. Taherkhani and R. Safabakhsh, "A novel stability-based adaptive inertia weight for particle swarm optimization," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 38, pp. 281–295, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2015.10.004>.
- [17] İ. B. Aydılek, "A hybrid firefly and particle swarm optimization algorithm for computationally expensive numerical problems," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 66, pp. 232–249, May 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2018.02.025>.
- [18] V. Zarzoso and P. Comon, "Robust Independent Component Analysis by Iterative Maximization of the Kurtosis Contrast With Algebraic Optimal Step Size," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 248–261, Oct. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNN.2009.2035920>.
- [19] L. C. Chan and P. Whiteman, "Hardware-Constrained Hybrid Coding of Video Imagery," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. AES-19, no. 1, pp. 71–84, Jan. 1983, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAES.1983.309421>.
- [20] Z. Wang, A. C. Bovik, H. R. Sheikh, and E. P. Simoncelli, "Image quality assessment: from error visibility to structural similarity," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 600–612, Apr. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2003.819861>.
- [21] N. Diffellah, Z. E. Baarir, F. Derraz, and A. Taleb-Ahmed, "A Global Variational Filter for Restoring Noised Images with Gamma Multiplicative Noise," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4188–4195, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2737>.
- [22] "Free-Images.com - Free Public Domain Images." <https://free-images.com>.

Performance Analysis of Ultrathin Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ Solar Cells with Backwall Superstrate Configuration Using AMPS-1D

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Abstract-This study used AMPS-1D to perform numerical simulations and model the behavior of back-wall superstrate solar cells based on Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) thin films to investigate optimal conditions and obtain maximum efficiency. The effects of absorber thickness and density of interface defects were examined along with the work function of the transparent conductive oxide (W_{TCO}) to investigate their influence on the output parameters. Measurements of device performance (J-V) and Quantum Efficiency (QE) showed that the performance of the cell improved as the thickness of the CIGS layer decreased because photons were absorbed near the junction. The device achieved an efficiency of 16.4% using an optimal thickness for the CIGS layer on the order of 0.3 μ m, defect densities in the range of 10^{13} - 10^{15} cm⁻³, doping concentration of the n-TCO back contact on the order of 10^{19} cm⁻³, and W_{TCO} in the range of 4.5-5.2eV. These results show that the generated electron-hole pairs had a high probability of separation and demonstrate the potential of this device structure.

Keywords-Cu(In,Ga)Se₂; thin films solar cells; backwall superstrate; transparent conductive oxide; device modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) is regarded as one of the most promising semiconductors for use in thin-film photovoltaic applications [1, 2], due to its sizeable optical coefficient in the range of the solar spectrum and its electrical and optical properties, which vary depending on the preparation condition and the production technique [3, 4]. The production of this semiconductor using various techniques and different types of substrates was examined in [5, 6]. Higher efficiency of CIGS thin film solar cells was achieved recently, with values exceeding 23.4%, from devices in the typical substrate cell configuration [1, 7], wherein the first step of device fabrication,

the molybdenum layer was deposited as a back contact layer on Soda-Lime Glass (SLG), followed by the deposit of the p-CIGS absorber layer. Then, the n-type buffer layer grew on top of the CIGS to form the crucial p-n junction [8] that completes the structure of the solar cell. Next, a thin layer of high resistance intrinsic (i-ZnO) was applied to the front window, followed by a thin layer, to form the front electrode while ensuring the optimal transmission of solar spectrum photons. The device was finished by depositing the collecting grid [9] and illuminated through the TCO window layer [10, 11]. The best performances were obtained by depositing 20-50nm of the CdS buffer layer on top of the CIGS absorber layer, whose thickness was around 2-3 μ m [12-14]. The economic aspect remains critical in the industrial development of CIGS technology [14], and it is necessary to reduce its production cost. One of the drawbacks of this process remains the use of rare elements, such as Indium and Gallium [11, 12]. In this context, this study investigated the development of low-cost and environmentally friendly photovoltaic cells. Reducing the thickness of the CIGS has the eventual benefit of reducing costs, while fast fabrication and limiting the use of rare elements can achieve higher manufacturing throughput [15-17].

The back-wall superstrate configuration of CIGS photovoltaic devices has the potential for better light harvesting than the substrate cell structure [17-19]. In this structure, the manufacturing sequences are reversed concerning the substrate configuration. In the first step, the absorber layer is deposited onto the TCO window layer and illumination comes from the back region. Hence, a wide band gap transparent back contact is required in the structure [20]. In addition, the critical absorber buffer interdiffusion is restricted [1, 2]. This study focused on an original back-wall superstrate solar cell of the

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type SLG/n-SnO₂:F/p-CIGS/n-In₂Se₃/i-ZnO/Mo. The CIGS-based cell eliminates the need for transparent encapsulation due to the collection grids at both the cell and the module productions and the requirement for toxic cadmium sulfide (CdS) used in conventional cells [1]. Developing solar cells with high conversion efficiency and based on hetero-structures requires knowledge of the effects that limit their photovoltaic performance, in particular the phenomenon of diffusion and recombination at the interfaces and in the volume of the material of the different layers of the device.

The CIGS-based back-wall superstrate solar cell's behavior has been the subject of considerable theoretical modeling efforts in this area. This study investigates the main parameters likely to be involved in the optimization of the photovoltaic performance of the cells studied using AMPS-1D [21, 22], proposing indicative design parameters for the back-wall superstrate solar cell. Therefore, this study focuses on the investigation of the properties of the absorber layer with different thicknesses, densities of interface defects (N_{ii}), and the TCO/absorber interface that may limit current transport in the cell, aiming to examine the limits of the device and determine the most favorable parameters. The best obtained efficiency was 16.4%, showing the prospects of this structure. The simulations results were found to be in good agreement with the values reported in [2] and allowed the verification of the proposed AMPS parameters. However, the main motive of this study was to examine the trends of device performance rather than predict optimum values.

II. DETAILS OF THE SIMULATED SOLAR CELL

The AMPS-1D software was used to evaluate the performance of the device as the design of the absorber layer varied. The numerical modeling of the semiconductor device was based on the simultaneous resolution of the Poisson and the continuity equations for the holes and electrons [23, 24]. AMPS-1D solves three coupled differential equations in suitable limit conditions and then evaluates the electrostatic potential and the quasi-Fermi level for holes and electrons at any point in the device [25, 26]. Once these variables are identified according to the depth, it is easy to evaluate the carrier concentrations, electric fields, current density-voltage characteristics (J - V), Quantum Efficiency (QE) curves, and the photovoltaic output parameters open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), fill factor (FF), and efficiency (η) [6]. These parameters describe the performance of solar cells [25, 27]. Modeling solar cells has the advantage that all device and material properties are well restricted as they are input parameters of the model. Therefore, trend assessment and quantified changes in J - V or QE measurements are probable.

The chosen back-wall solar cell structure consists of a stack of thin layers: SLG/SnO₂:F/p-CIGS/n-In₂Se₃/i-ZnO/Mo. The TCO layer is required to form the front electrode while ensuring the optimal transmission of the solar spectrum photons. SnO₂ was chosen for its excellent conductivity, as it is a wide-gap semiconductor [28]. The thin layer of In₂Se₃ was deposited on the CIGS absorber layer, which is involved in the formation of the p-n junction and also protects the surface of the CIGS. Figure 1 shows the proposed CIGS solar cell. The interface recombination velocities were fixed at 10⁷ cm/s and

the light reflection of the rear and the front contacts were assumed to be 1 and 0.1 respectively. AM 1.5D solar radiation was used as the illumination source, corresponding to a power of 1000W/m². The electrical and optical properties of the CIGS layer were incorporated using the close-spaced vapor transport technique [21]. Table I shows the parameters of each semiconductor of the typical cell used in the simulation, as reported in the literature.

Fig. 1. Basic structures of back-wall superstrate device.

TABLE I. BASELINE PARAMETERS USED FOR THE BACKWALL SUPERSTRATE CIGS SOLAR CELLS IN THE SIMULATIONS

Parameters	i-ZnO	In ₂ Se ₃	CIGS	SnO ₂ :F
Layer thickness: d (nm)	50	50	variable	300
Dielectric constant: ϵ_r	9	10	13.6	9
Effective conduction band density: N_C (cm ⁻³)	2.2×10^{18}	2.2×10^{18}	2.2×10^{18}	2.2×10^{18}
Effective valence band density: N_V (cm ⁻³)	1.8×10^{19}	1.8×10^{19}	1.8×10^{19}	1.8×10^{19}
Doping concentration: (N_A) (cm ⁻³)	/	/	2×10^{16}	/
Doping concentration: (N_D) (cm ⁻³)	1×10^{14}	1×10^{16}	/	1×10^{19}
Band gap: E_g (eV)	3.30	2.40	1.20	3.6
Electron affinity: χ (eV)	4.00	3.80	4.10	4.00
Electron mobility: μ_e (cm ² /V.s)	100	50	50	100
Hole mobility: μ_h (cm ² /V.s)	25	12	12	25
Defect density: N_{DG}/N_{AG} (cm ⁻³)	1.5×10^{14}	1.5×10^{17}	1×10^{12}	1.5×10^{14}
Capture cross-section electrons: σ_e (cm ²)	1×10^{-13}	1×10^{-17}	1×10^{-13}	1×10^{-13}
Capture cross-section holes: σ_h (cm ²)	1×10^{-15}	1×10^{-12}	1×10^{-15}	1×10^{-15}

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Effect of the CIGS Absorber Layer Thickness

Several studies focused on reducing the thickness of the absorber layer without affecting solar cell performance. A simulation of the J - V characteristic was obtained by varying the thickness of the p-CIGS layer in the structure between 0.05 and 2 μ m to obtain the optimal results for the back-wall superstrate configuration cells. Figure 2 shows the variation of the current density as a function of the bias voltage for different thicknesses of the absorber layer.

Fig. 2. Current-voltage characteristics of the solar cell with different thicknesses of CIGS absorber.

The absorber's thickness significantly influences the performance of the photovoltaic cell. The results showed that the variation and reduction of $d(\text{CIGS})$ from 2 to $0.3\mu\text{m}$ lead to an increase of J_{sc} from 20.19 to $36.42\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$. This means that the power provided by the cell increases as the thickness of the CIGS layer decreases and the efficiency is lost due to the parasitic losses, including higher series resistance. The thickness of the CIGS layer affects the quantum efficiency of the solar cell, as shown in Figure 3, and the active layer affects the short wavelength. For the thick absorber layer, the photo-generation process is produced far from the back contact region and, therefore, not near the electric field of the space charge region (ZCE).

Fig. 3. The quantum efficiency of the device with different absorber thicknesses.

The generation probability in a thin absorber less than $0.5\mu\text{m}$ is very high and, therefore, produces photocarriers close to the electric field. This is partly due to a considerable absorption loss in the rear region of the CIGS absorber layer. Another probable explanation is that the diffusion length of the minority carrier layer in a thinner absorber layer is similar to its thickness. As a result, $QE(\lambda)$ at a short wavelength is improved without a significant decrease in efficiency, and the parasitic absorption in the buffer layer is prevented, as shown in Figure 3. The optimal absorber layer thickness was approximately $0.25\text{-}0.5\mu\text{m}$ in this case, which reduces the thickness of the

absorber layer and has the eventual benefit of reducing the cost of manufacture due to the reduced material usage.

B. Effect of Absorber Thickness on Photovoltaic Parameters

Figure 4 illustrates the influence of the thickness of the CIGS on the photovoltaic parameters of the cell (J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF , and η). It can be noted that the voltage V_{oc} is practically constant when reducing the thickness of the p-CIGS absorber layer from 2 to $0.25\mu\text{m}$. The current density of J_{sc} strongly depends on the thickness of the p-CIGS absorber, and it increases with decreasing thickness. The efficiency of cell structure also increases rapidly because the photons are absorbed close to the p-CIGS/n- In_2Se_3 junction and the generated photocarriers have a high probability of being separated. For absorber thickness greater than $0.5\mu\text{m}$, the photons are absorbed away from the electric field, so that V_{oc} and J_{sc} decrease as the thickness of the absorber increases up to $2\mu\text{m}$. Reducing V_{oc} and J_{sc} results in a reduction in conversion efficiency (η). This is probably due to imperfections in the thick absorber, which allowed the emergence of many defects. When the absorber thickness is reduced below $0.25\mu\text{m}$, the performance of the device begins to deteriorate due to incomplete optical absorption. A maximum cell conversion efficiency of 16.4% was obtained for a thickness in the range of 0.25 to $0.5\mu\text{m}$ for the CIGS absorber.

Fig. 4. The dependence of solar cell performance on CIGS thickness with different $N_d(\text{TCO})$.

C. Effect of the Density of Defects N_{it} of the Absorber Layer on the Performance of the Cell

Figure 5 shows the effect of the concentration of the absorber layer defects on the photovoltaic parameters (J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF , and η) with various doping concentrations of the TCO layer. The results showed that high efficiency is achieved when the defect density is in the range of 10^{12} to 10^{15}cm^{-3} , because the barrier that causes the recombination is not produced at the CIGS/ In_2Se_3 interface, and J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF , and η are practically constant. On the other hand, when the concentration of the

absorber layer defects is more significant than 10^{15}cm^{-3} , the variation of V_{oc} , J_{sc} , and FF becomes very significant, affecting the cell's performance. These parameters decrease sharply as a result of the formation of a barrier in the face of the photogenerated electrons. A strongly doped layer of TCO is also preferred to shove the electrons photogenerated inward the bulk of the absorber.

Fig. 5. The photovoltaic parameters as a function of CIGS density defect with different N_d (TCO).

D. Effect of the Back TCO/CIGS Contact Region

The development of a high-quality TCO back-contact while maintaining the efficiency of light transmission throughout the top CIGS layer is essential to obtain a high efficiency of the back-wall solar cells. The TCO work function (W_{TCO}) of the back contact region was a means factor in affecting the back-wall solar cell performance. Figure 6 shows the dependence of the performance of the $\text{SnO}_2:\text{F}/\text{p-CIGS}/\text{n-In}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{i-ZnO}/\text{Mo}$ solar cell on the variation of W_{TCO} . It can be seen that V_{oc} , FF , and η increase with W_{TCO} of the back SLG/ $\text{SnO}_2:\text{F}/\text{p-CIGS}$ surface. It is necessary to use a suitable work function of the back TCO to have ohmic contact in the back contact and reduce the barrier recombination. Furthermore, when W_{TCO} is higher than 5.2eV, the potential barriers of the TCO/p-CIGS Schottky contact are effectively elevated than the crucial n- $\text{In}_2\text{Se}_3/\text{p-CIGS}$ junction and the TCO/p-CIGS contact, and the p-CIGS/n- In_2Se_3 junction will have potential barriers on the contrary course of action. In that event, overlapping the space charge region involving the two junctions would induce a drop in the device performance. The back contact resistance depends on the barrier potential (Φ_b) and N_d (TCO). A low height barrier (Φ_b) and a high concentration of N_d are needed to have low resistance and ohmic contacts and avoid the depletion zone created at the TCO/CIGS interface. The simulation results confirm that the N_d (TCO) is required to be in the range of 10^{19}cm^{-3} , to obtain high performance and induce the increase of the $QE(\lambda)$, as shown in Figure 7, due to the decrease of recombination at the TCO/CIGS interface.

Fig. 6. The dependence of solar cell performance on W_{TCO} with different N_d (TCO).

Fig. 7. The dependence of the quantum efficiency on the N_d (TCO).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the performance of back-wall superstrate solar cells using AMPS-1D software with a modified absorber layer. Based on the results, the thickness of the absorber layer, the densities of interface defects (N_{it}), and the work function of the back transparent conductive oxide on the performance of the CIGS back-wall superstrate cell structure. To improve conversion efficiency, the CIGS absorber thickness must be thinner as possible (0.25 μm -0.5 μm), because the photons will be captured in the area of the junction, and the generated electron-hole pairs will have a high probability of being split apart because there will be a gap between them. However, the results of the simulation demonstrated that even a high density of defects does not prevent a structure from achieving exceptional levels of performance. The N_{it} of the absorber layer was in the range of 10^{12} - 10^{15}cm^{-3} . The optimized conditions were the doping concentration of the n-TCO back contact N_d on the order of 10^{19}cm^{-3} and W_{TCO} between 4.6-5.2eV. The CIGS back-wall superstrate solar cell with an absorber layer thickness of 0.3 μm showed the best efficiency of 16.4%.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Ni, J. M. Liu, Z. Q. Li, Q. Shen, Y. Z. Feng, and X. D. Feng, "Simulation of graded bandgap on backwall superstrate CIGS solar cells with MoOx electron reflection layer," *Materials Research Express*, vol. 6, no. 11, Jul. 2019, Art. no. 116441, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2053-1591/ab4c5c>.
- [2] J. K. Larsen, H. Simchi, P. Xin, K. Kim, and W. N. Shafarman, "Backwall superstrate configuration for ultrathin Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 104, no. 3, Jan. 2014, Art. no. 033901, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4862651>.
- [3] S. M. Ho, "Fabrication of Cu₄SnS₄ Thin Films: A Review," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 6161–6164, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3663>.
- [4] C. Zhang *et al.*, "High efficiency CIGS solar cells on flexible stainless steel substrate with SiO₂ diffusion barrier layer," *Solar Energy*, vol. 230, pp. 1033–1039, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2021.11.006>.
- [5] S. E. T. Moghaddam and S. M. Kankanani, "Numerical Simulation of a Mechanically Stacked GaAs/Ge Solar Cell," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1611–1614, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.935>.
- [6] W. S. Liu, H. C. Hu, N. W. Pu, and S. C. Liang, "Developing flexible CIGS solar cells on stainless steel substrates by using Ti/TiN composite structures as the diffusion barrier layer," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 631, pp. 146–152, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2014.12.189>.
- [7] M. D. Heinemann *et al.*, "Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ superstrate solar cells: prospects and limitations," *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 1228–1237, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.2536>.
- [8] C. H. Huang, "Effects of junction parameters on Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells," *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 779–783, Feb. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpcs.2007.07.118>.
- [9] A. Mavlonov *et al.*, "Superstrate-type flexible and bifacial Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ thin-film solar cells with In₂O₃:SnO₂ back contact," *Solar Energy*, vol. 211, pp. 725–731, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2020.10.019>.
- [10] T. Nakada, "Microstructural and diffusion properties of CIGS thin film solar cells fabricated using transparent conducting oxide back contacts," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 480–481, pp. 419–425, Jun. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2004.11.142>.
- [11] X. Li, A. Kanevce, J. V. Li, and I. Repins, "The impact of front contact ZnO:Al/Zn_{1-x}MgxO layer on Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ thin-film solar cells," *physica status solidi c*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 1703–1705, 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssc.200983225>.
- [12] A. Chirilă *et al.*, "Highly efficient Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells grown on flexible polymer films," *Nature Materials*, vol. 10, no. 11, pp. 857–861, Nov. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat3122>.
- [13] P. Jackson, R. Wuerz, D. Hariskos, E. Lotter, W. Witte, and M. Powalla, "Effects of heavy alkali elements in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells with efficiencies up to 22.6%," *physica status solidi (RRL) – Rapid Research Letters*, vol. 10, no. 8, pp. 583–586, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssr.201600199>.
- [14] M. Paire, L. Lombez, J.-F. Guillemoles, and D. Lincot, "Toward microscale Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells for efficient conversion and optimized material usage: Theoretical evaluation," *Journal of Applied Physics*, vol. 108, no. 3, Aug. 2010, Art. no. 034907, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3460629>.
- [15] D. L. Young *et al.*, "Improved performance in ZnO/CdS/CuGaSe₂ thin-film solar cells," *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp. 535–541, 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.516>.
- [16] T. Nakada, Y. Hirabayashi, T. Tokado, D. Ohmori, and T. Mise, "Novel device structure for Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ thin film solar cells using transparent conducting oxide back and front contacts," *Solar Energy*, vol. 77, no. 6, pp. 739–747, Dec. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2004.08.010>.
- [17] F.-J. Haug, D. Rudmann, H. Zogg, and A. N. Tiwari, "Light soaking effects in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ superstrate solar cells," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 431–432, pp. 431–435, May 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6090\(03\)00187-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6090(03)00187-1).
- [18] M. D. Heinemann *et al.*, "Advantageous light management in Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ superstrate solar cells," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 150, pp. 76–81, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2016.02.005>.
- [19] S. Ikeda, R. Kamai, S. Min Lee, T. Yagi, T. Harada, and M. Matsumura, "A superstrate solar cell based on In₂(Se,S)₃ and CuIn(Se,S)₂ thin films fabricated by electrodeposition combined with annealing," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 95, no. 6, pp. 1446–1451, Jun. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2010.11.006>.
- [20] M. D. Heinemann *et al.*, "The Importance of Sodium Control in CIGSe Superstrate Solar Cells," *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 378–381, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPHOTOV.2014.2360332>.
- [21] A. Mouhoub, A. Bouloufa, K. Djessas, and A. Messous, "Analytical modeling and optimization of original bifacial solar cells based on Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ thin films absorbers," *Superlattices and Microstructures*, vol. 122, pp. 434–443, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spmi.2018.06.068>.
- [22] A. Mouhoub, A. Bouloufa, K. Djessas, and A. Messous, "Device modeling approach and simulation of the effect of the ODC thin layer on bifacial solar cells based on CuIn_{1-x}GaxSe₂ thin films absorbers," *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*, vol. 144, p. 109520, Sep. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpcs.2020.109520>.
- [23] A. Morales-Acevedo, N. Hernández-Como, and G. Casados-Cruz, "Modeling solar cells: A method for improving their efficiency," *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, vol. 177, no. 16, pp. 1430–1435, Sep. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mseb.2012.01.010>.
- [24] C. H. Huang, "Effects of Ga content on Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells studied by numerical modeling," *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 330–334, Feb. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpcs.2007.07.093>.
- [25] I. Bouchama, K. Djessas, F. Djahli, and A. Bouloufa, "Simulation approach for studying the performances of original superstrate CIGS thin films solar cells," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 519, no. 21, pp. 7280–7283, Aug. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2011.01.182>.
- [26] A. Bouloufa, K. Djessas, and D. Todorovic, "Structural and optical properties of Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ grown by close-spaced vapor transport technique," *Materials Science in Semiconductor Processing*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 82–87, Feb. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mssp.2009.07.010>.
- [27] M. Nerat, F. Smole, and M. Topič, "A simulation study of the effect of the diverse valence-band offset and the electronic activity at the grain boundaries on the performance of polycrystalline Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ solar cells," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 519, no. 21, pp. 7497–7502, Aug. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsf.2010.12.100>.
- [28] T. B. Nasrallah, D. Mahboub, M. Jemai, and S. Belgacem, "Temperature Effect on Al/p-CuInS₂/SnO₂(F) Schottky Diodes," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4695–4701, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3072>.

The Effect of Adding Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPS) on the Hardened Properties of Concrete

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Abstract-This study investigated the possibility of producing lightweight concrete using Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPS), using one reference and five light concrete mixes by replacing coarse aggregates with EPS grains in five volumetric ratios: 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100%. The properties of hardened concrete of all mixed specimens, such as compressive strength, flexural strength, and density, were evaluated. The results showed that the addition of EPS caused an apparent reduction in the mechanical properties of concrete. The compressive strength at 28 days of curing ranged from 13.6 to 1.96MPa, while the rupture modulus ranged from 2.26 to 0MPa. Adding EPS grains as coarse aggregates led to a decrease in the concrete's weight. Replacing the coarse aggregates with EPS grains resulted in lightweight concrete with a density of 1086.5kg/m³.

Keywords-lightweight concrete (LWC); coarse aggregates; Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPS); properties of hardened concrete

I. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is an artificial material used to construct various civil engineering structures [1]. Concrete is the most commonly used substance in construction and can be used as stand alone mass concrete, reinforced concrete, or prestressed concrete when combined with steel [2]. For every ton of cement produced, one ton of carbon dioxide (CO₂) is emitted into the atmosphere. Cement manufacturing is responsible for 5% of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [3]. Cement production produces a significant amount of CO₂ and requires a large amount of energy during the manufacturing process. Given that Pakistan is already facing an energy crisis, the high energy consumption in cement production puts additional pressure on its energy sector. As a result, the price of cement is rising daily. Furthermore, waste disposal and the restoration of concrete components after demolition have negative environmental consequences. As a result, the use of this waste reduces cement manufacturing and energy consumption while also helping protect the environment [4]. One of the drawbacks of traditional concrete is its high self-weight. The density of regular concrete ranges between 2200 and 2600kg/m³ making it an uneconomical structural material. Several attempts have been made in the past to reduce the self-weight of concrete to

increase its efficiency. Lightweight Concrete (LWC) is a type of concrete with a density ranging from 300 to 1850kg/m³ [5].

Since LWC was first used approximately two thousand years ago, several lighter structures were built, particularly in the Mediterranean region. The three most important structures built during the Roman Empire are the Colosseum, the Port of Cosa, and the Pantheon Dome [6]. The use of LWC in buildings, structural and non-structural, as construction material must have specific characteristics that meet the requirements of strength and performance for the application. Before using any material in construction, there is a need to study its mechanical properties to determine its suitability [7]. Due to its low density, which offers tremendous benefits by reducing the cross sections of the components, there is an increase in the demand for LWCs in many modern architectural constructions [7]. There are two categories of lightweight aggregates: natural, such as diatomite, volcanic cinders, etc., and industrial such as expanded shale, clay, and slate. Polystyrene is an industrial material with a density less than 300kg/m³ and no absorption properties [8-9]. Polystyrene has a closed cell structure, is stable, has low density, and is not absorbent or hydrophobic [10-11]. Concrete can be used for all parts of a building (structural and non-structural) as a very lightweight material by altering the percentage ratio of its aggregates [12-13].

Unlike lightweight industrial aggregates, polystyrene is commercially available everywhere. Most polystyrene manufacturing facilities are located in Europe and Russia [14]. The effects of adding EPS to cement mortar and concrete have not been extensively studied. This addition leads to a decrease in the density and mechanical properties of both cement mortar and concrete [15-16]. Ultra-high-performance concrete and EPS beads composite sandwich plates were investigated in [17], examining the use of these sandwich plates in high-rise structures. Because of their low density and high compressibility, EPS beads are frequently used as filling materials in earthquake buffers [18-20]. This study aimed to investigate the production of LWC using EPS as coarse aggregate, carrying out several tests to examine the effect of adding EPS as coarse aggregate with different volume percentages on the properties of the new LWC.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Cement

All specimens were cast using Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) Type I throughout the experiment. This kind of cement complies with the Iraqi specification 5/2019 [19]. Table I shows its physical attributes and chemical composition.

B. Fine Aggregates

Sand from the Al-Ekhadir area (Karbala city) was used as fine aggregates, as shown in Figure 1. This sand is classified as zone 2 and meets the physical and chemical requirements of the Iraqi standard 45/1984 [20], as shown in Table II.

Fig. 1. Fine aggregates (left) and coarse aggregates (right).

C. Coarse Aggregates

Natural gravel from the Al-Nibae region with a nominal aggregate size of 5-10mm, shown in Figure 1, was used as coarse aggregates in all mixes. Table III shows that the physical and chemical parameters of the coarse aggregates comply to the Iraqi standard 45/1984 [20].

D. Water

Potable (tap) water, obtained from the laboratory, was used for mixing and curing. This water meets the requirements of the Iraqi standard 1703 [21].

E. Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPS)

This study used spherical-shaped EPS beads with a maximum nominal size of 10mm to replace coarse aggregates. Table IV depicts the gradient and physical properties of EPS beads, shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Expanded Polystyrene Beads (EPS).

F. Superplasticizer (SP)

A superplasticizer called Sika ViscoCrete 5930, which complies with the ASTM C494 type G [22] criteria, was used in the adjusted mixes, and Table V shows its features.

TABLE I. PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF CEMENT

Physical properties	Test result	Limits of IQS 5/2019 [19]
Setting time:		
-Initial setting (min)	106	45 min
-Final setting (hrs.)	4.83	00 hrs. max
Comp. Str. (MPa):		
2-days	11.25	Min. 10
28-days	33.31	Min. 32.5
Chemical properties		
Oxide composition	Result	Limits of IQS 5/2019 [19]
(SiO ₂)	21.62	No limited
(Al ₂ O ₃)	5.94	No limited
(Fe ₂ O ₃)	3.32	No limited
(CaO)	61.55	No limited
L.S.F. %	0.86	No limited
(MgO)	2.85	Max. 5
Sulfate (SO ₃ %)	C ₃ A<5%	Not applicable
	C ₃ A >5%	2.25
(L.O.I.)	1.07	Max. 4
(I.R.)	0.88	Max. 5
(C ₃ S)	35.11	No limited
(C ₂ S)	35.07	No limited
(C ₃ A)	10.13	No limited
(C ₄ AF)	10.09	No limited

TABLE II. FINE AGGREGATES SIEVE ANALYSIS

Sieve Size (mm)	Passing %	Limits of [20] (Zone 2)
10	100	100
4.75	92	90-100
2.63	85	75-100
1.18	56	55-90
0.6	42	35-59
0.3	13	8-30
0.15	5	0-10
Physical and chemical properties		
Physical characteristics	Test results	Limits of Iraqi standards
Specific gravity	2.5	-----
(SO ₃ %)	0.4%	0.5% (max)
Absorption (%)	0.7%	-----

TABLE III. COARSE AGGREGATE'S PROPERTIES

Sieve Size (mm)	Test Results	Limits of [20]
14	100	90-100
10	75.1	50-85
5	1.2	0-10
2.36	--	No limited
SO ₃ % content	0.092	Max. 0.1%

TABLE IV. SIEVE ANALYSIS AND PROPERTIES OF EPS

Sieve Size	Passing %	ASTM C330
12.5mm	100	100
9.5mm	91	80-100
4.75mm	6.5	5-40
2.36mm	1.5	0-20
Specific gravity	--	--
Water absorption	0	--
Maximum particle size (mm)	10	--

TABLE V. PROPERTIES OF SUPERPLASTICIZER [23]

Density	1.08 kg/l
pH	8.0 ±1.0
Chloride content	NIL (EN934-2)

III. MOLDS, MIXING, AND CASTING

Three 100×100×400mm prism samples were produced for each group of 7, 14, and 28 days of curing to test the flexural strength and three 100×100×100mm cube samples with ages 7, 14, and 28 days were constructed to test compressive strength. Before placing the materials, the internal surface of the mixer was cleaned and wet. To ensure even dispersion of the polystyrene, the raw materials were first thoroughly combined and dried for about 3 minutes. Afterward, water was gradually added while mixing to produce a smooth and flowing liquid. The mixing process was extended for 3 minutes to create a uniform and consistent concrete. This process was performed in the concrete laboratory of Baghdad University's College of Engineering. All concretes were blended using a planetary mixer, shown in Fig. 4. The mixture was poured into oiled molds, which were then vibrated on a vibrating table for 1 minute to improve compaction and reduce air bubbles. The samples were demolded after 24 hours and placed in water for curing before testing.

Fig. 3. Mixing of concrete.

IV. CONCRETE MIX

This study used 1 reference and 5 different concrete mixes to create the samples. Concrete was produced with a water/cement ratio of 0.45 and a coarse aggregate ratio of 1:1.6:3.12, by weight, of OPC. Table VI shows the details of the samples.

TABLE VI. MIX OF 1m³ OF CONCRETE

Mix Code	R	E20%	E40%	E60%	E80%	E100%
Cement (kg/m ³)	401	401	401	401	401	401
SP (kg/m ³)	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
Fine aggregates (kg/m ³)	643	643	643	643	643	643
Coarse aggregates (kg/m ³)	1254	1002	753	501	250	0
EPS (kg/m ³)	0	2	4	6	8	10
Water (kg/m ³)	180	180	180	180	180	180

V. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Density

The quantity and density of lightweight aggregates are two of the most crucial elements in regulating a variety of physical properties in LWC. Due to the low density of polystyrene, the density of LWC falls as polystyrene volume increases [24-25]. Table VII shows the densities of the samples and Figure 4 shows their density variation with age.

TABLE VII. DENSITY TEST RESULTS

Mix Code	7 days	14 days	28 days
R	2550	2573	2589
E20%	2266	2283	2295
E40%	1944	1975	1984.5
E60%	1615	1627	1635
E80%	1356.5	1400	1422.5
E100%	1035	1055.5	1086.5

Fig. 4. Variation of density with age

B. Compressive Strength

According to Figure 5, the compressive strength gets stronger with curing time. This rise is the result of the cement hydration process becoming more advanced with time. Figure 6 and Table VIII both provide a comparison of the compressive strengths of several specimens at 7, 14, and 28 days of age.

TABLE VIII. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH TEST RESULTS

Mix Code	7 days	14 days	28 days
R	25.7	33.11	42.4
E20%	9.67	10.12	13.6
E40%	6.04	9.29	10.88
E60%	3.47	3.62	4.08
E80%	3.42	3.62	3.86
E100%	1.36	1.81	1.96

Fig. 5. Variations of compressive strength with age per sample.

Figure 6 shows that the concrete containing EPS had a decrease in compressive strength when the P/Agg ratio reached 20% or higher. As EPS increased, the compressive strength decreased. In the case of higher-density concrete mixes, those that contained less polystyrene typically had higher strengths, but compressive strength decreased when the polyester content was greater than 80% of the aggregate. This is because the polystyrene fills in the gaps left by the absence of coarse aggregates. In addition, the compressive strength of

polystyrene is lower than that of coarse aggregates. Similar to the conventional concrete, it is evident that strength declines as polystyrene content increases. Figure 6 shows the variation in compressive strength per sample and Figure 7 shows the compressive strength test procedure.

Fig. 6. Variation of compressive strength with polystyrene content %.

Fig. 7. Compressive strength test.

C. Flexural Strength

Figure 8 shows that all prisms made of concrete mixtures exhibited a steady increase in flexural strength over time. Figure 8 and Table IX show a comparison of the variance in flexural strength values with different polystyrene content percentages at 7, 14, and 28 days of age.

Fig. 8. Variation of flexural strength with age.

TABLE IX. RESULTS OF FLEXURAL STRENGTH TESTS

Mix Code	7 days	14 days	28 days
R	3.72	3.85	6.01
E20%	1.13	1.52	2.26
E40%	1.71	2.09	3.43
E60%	0.73	0.93	1.09
E80%	0.28	0.36	0.42
E100%	0	0	0

Figure 9 shows the change in flexural strength after 7, 14, and 28 days, and Figure 10 shows the flexural strength test procedure. Figure 9 shows that the flexural strength of concrete containing polystyrene decreased when the P/Agg ratio was 20% or higher. This could be because lower-density concrete has lower flexural strength as it contains higher amounts of polystyrene. Figure 9 illustrates how higher-density concrete mixes with lower amounts of polystyrene typically had a higher flexural strength. However, flexural strength decreased when polyester content was greater than 80% of the aggregates. This is because polystyrene fills in the gaps left by the absence of coarse aggregates and has lower flexural strength than coarse aggregates.

Fig. 9. Variation of flexural strength with polystyrene content %.

Fig. 10. Flexural strength test.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the compressive and flexural strengths of concrete with various proportions of EPS beads replacing coarse aggregates. The results showed that:

- As the polystyrene/aggregate ratio increases, lightweight concrete's compressive strength decreases.

- As the polystyrene/aggregate ratio increases, the density of the lightweight concrete mixes decreases. The lowest density value was 1086.5 kg/m³ for the total replacement of coarse aggregate with polystyrene (100%).
- As the polystyrene/aggregate ratio increases, the flexural strength of the lightweight concrete mixes decreases. The lowest value of flexural strength was 0Mpa for total replacement of coarse aggregates with polystyrene (100%).

Finally, recycling waste materials can help create new and environmentally friendly lightweight concrete for specific purposes.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Bheel, A. S. Memon, I. A. Khaskheli, N. M. Talpur, S. M. Talpur, and M. A. Khanzada, "Effect of Sugarcane Bagasse Ash and Lime Stone Fines on the Mechanical Properties of Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5534–5537, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3434>.
- [2] C. Oliko, C. K. Kabubo, and J. N. Mweru, "Rice Straw and Eggshell Ash as Partial Replacements of Cement in Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6481–6487, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3893>.
- [3] N. Bheel, R. A. Abbasi, S. Sohu, S. A. Abbasi, A. W. Abro, and Z. H. Shaikh, "Effect of Tile Powder Used as a Cementitious Material on the Mechanical Properties of Concrete," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4596–4599, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2994>.
- [4] S. Sohu, N. Bheel, A. A. Jhatial, A. A. Ansari, and I. A. Shar, "Sustainability and mechanical property assessment of concrete incorporating eggshell powder and silica fume as binary and ternary cementitious materials," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 29, no. 39, pp. 58685–58697, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-19894-5>.
- [5] A. W. Ali and N. M. Fawzi, "Production of Light Weight Foam Concrete with Sustainable Materials," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7647–7652, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4377>.
- [6] "Guide for Structural Lightweight-Aggregate Concrete," American Concrete Institute, Farmington Hills, MI, USA, ACI 213R-03, Sep. 2003.
- [7] "Guide for Structural Lightweight-Aggregate Concrete," American Concrete Institute, Farmington Hills, MI, USA, ACI 213R-87, 1987.
- [8] A. Short and W. Kinniburgh, *Lightweight concrete*, 3rd ed. London: Applied Science, 1978.
- [9] V. Sussman, "Lightweight Plastic-Aggregate Concrete," *ACI Journal*, pp. 321–323, Jul. 1975.
- [10] R. Sri Ravindrarajah and A. J. Tuck, "Properties of hardened concrete containing treated expanded polystyrene beads," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 273–277, Jan. 1994, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465\(94\)90039-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0958-9465(94)90039-6).
- [11] D. J. Cook, "Expanded Polystyrene Concrete," in *Concrete Technology and Design - New Concrete Materials*, vol. 1, London, UK: Surrey University Press, 1983, pp. 41–69.
- [12] S. H. Perry, P. H. Bischoff, and K. Yamura, "Mix details and material behaviour of polystyrene aggregate concrete," *Magazine of Concrete Research*, vol. 43, no. 154, pp. 71–76, Mar. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.1680/mac.1991.43.154.71>.
- [13] C. Bagon and S. Frondistou-Yannas, "Marine floating concrete made with polystyrene expanded beads," *Magazine of Concrete Research*, vol. 28, no. 97, pp. 225–229, Dec. 1976, <https://doi.org/10.1680/mac.1976.28.97.225>.
- [14] A. I. Al-Hadithi and M. K. M. Al-Ani, "Study Some Properties of Concrete Containing Industrial Styrobre and Modified by Polymer," *Anbar Journal of Engineering Sciences*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2016.
- [15] A. A. Mutar, A. I. Al-Hadithi, and B. A. Mahmood, "The Use of Polystyrene Waste in Concrete," *Journal of university of Anbar for Pure science*, vol. 7, no. 2, 2013.
- [16] A. M. Neville, *Properties of Concrete*, 3rd ed. London, UK: Pitman Publishing, 1981.
- [17] J. H. Lee, S. H. Kang, Y. J. Ha, and S. G. Hong, "Structural Behavior of Durable Composite Sandwich Panels with High Performance Expanded Polystyrene Concrete," *International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials*, vol. 12, no. 1, Feb. 2018, Art. no. 21, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40069-018-0255-6>.
- [18] J. G. Wang, W. Sun, and S. Anand, "Numerical investigation on active isolation of ground shock by soft porous layers," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 321, no. 3, pp. 492–509, Apr. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2008.09.047>.
- [19] R. J. Bathurst and S. Zarnani, "Earthquake Load Attenuation Using EPS Geofoam Buffers in Rigid Wall Applications," *Indian Geotechnical Journal*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 283–291, Dec. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40098-013-0047-5>.
- [20] O. L. Ertugrul, A. C. Trandafir, and M. Yener Ozkan, "Reduction of dynamic earth loads on flexible cantilever retaining walls by deformable geofoam panels," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 92, pp. 462–471, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2016.10.011>.
- [21] "Portland Cement," Iraqi Organization for Standardization and Quality Control, Standard 5/2019, 2019.
- [22] "Aggregate from Natural Sources for Concrete and Construction," Iraqi Specifications, Iraq, 45/1984, 1984.
- [23] "Water Used in Concrete," Iraqi Organization for Standardization and Quality Control, Standard 1703/1992, 1992.
- [24] "Standard Specification for Chemical Admixtures for Concrete," American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard /C494M-17, 2017.
- [25] "Sika ViscoCrete® -5930," Sika, 2015. Available: <https://egy.sika.com/content/dam/dms/egy01/e/Sika%20ViscoCrete%C2%AE%20-5930.pdf>.
- [26] "Testing concrete - Method for determination of compressive strength of concrete cubes," British Standards Institute, BS 1881-116:1989, Jan. 1983.
- [27] "Standard Test Method for Flexural Strength of Concrete Using Simple Beam with Two Points Loading," American Society for Testing and Materials, West Conshohocken, PA, US, Standard C293-86, 1986.
- [28] K. G. Babu and D. S. Babu, "Behaviour of lightweight expanded polystyrene concrete containing silica fume," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 755–762, May 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-8846\(02\)01055-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0008-8846(02)01055-4).
- [29] D. Saradhi Babu, K. Ganesh Babu, and T. H. Wee, "Properties of lightweight expanded polystyrene aggregate concretes containing fly ash," *Cement and Concrete Research*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1218–1223, Jun. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2004.11.015>.

An Original Approach for Translating Grafcet into C/Unix Code for Validation Purposes

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Abstract-This paper proposes an approach to simulate the function of the control part of a Grafcet model, translating it into C code in a Unix environment. First, the Grafcet/C generation schemes are established. The Grafcet model, described in graphic or text form, is transformed in an internal form and then to C code by a generation algorithm based on the previously found diagrams. The result is a program that simulates the operation of the automation in question and makes it possible to validate the functional specifications of sequential automation. This validation can be used for educational purposes, such as the learning of the Grafcet formalism, or corrective or evolutionary maintenance. Once the configuration, testing, and validation of the program are complete, it is possible to implement the object code on the microcontroller of the control system.

Keywords-C/Unix; Grafcet; process; sequential automation

I. INTRODUCTION

Equipment manufacturers and automation engineers responsible for automated industrial installations should master the programs that drive their installations to perform preventive [1, 2], corrective, adaptive, and evolutionary maintenance tasks [3]. These programs are often outsourced, use a variety of libraries, and depend not only on the problem to be solved but also on the past of their provider. Grafcet [4, 5] is a graphic formalism for describing automatisms, accepted by mechanical automation engineers who consider it to represent the right level of specification without much complexity. In an automated system, the control part is the image of the operative part that represents the automated machine. Simulation and validation of the operation of an automated system are necessary before its implementation in the actual installation. Simulating the operation of Grafcet is equivalent to translating it into appropriate languages, which generate programs with the same semantics. These programs have shown their usefulness for maintenance or educational purposes. This study chose C/Unix as the target language and system for the Grafcet translation. This choice was motivated by two reasons; the C language extended by the Unix libraries has all the necessary tools for the translation of Grafcet, and the required hardware and software configuration for the application is very simple, just a personal computer with a Linux distribution.

II. RELATED WORK

Several studies achieved to formalize Grafcet. In [6], Grafcet translation schemes were designed in the Occam2 language, which is executable on transputers, exploiting the possibilities of expressions of parallel tasks offered in Occam2 to express the respective representation in Grafcet. The resulting program could run on a parallel machine and simulate the actual operation of an automated system. This work could obtain the equivalent Occam2 program from a Grafcet in graphical or textual form. Being a parallel language, Occam2 possesses the necessary tools to translate Grafcet, but the resulting program can only be exploited if a parallel machine existed. Since parallel machines are only available in certain research laboratories or specific industrial settings, such a program may have limited use. In [7], a semi-coarse ontology was defined and tested by integrating it into an existing educational tool to teach Grafcet for use in programmable logic controllers. This ontology was OWL (Web Ontology Language) DL based, a specific decidable fragment of first-order logic applied to OWL markup language. The objective of this method was to complement previous studies and promote this type of technique in the formalization of Grafcet. The advantages of ontologies are numerous, as they make collaboration and sharing of knowledge easier, provide better reliability, and assure to handle automatically any input change without having to recompile the processing code. This approach was validated according to two criteria, accuracy and completeness. A new vision was adopted in [8], by proposing a systematic implementation of the control software in IEC 61499. This constituted a key advantage over previous Grafcet implementations because it allowed engineers to implement models distributed over several devices and also kept the initial centralized design. IEC 61499 has all the translation tools for most of the Grafcet elements. This work made it possible to systematically translate Grafcet and introduced several translation models. The disadvantages of this method lied in the fact that it was not possible to model the structuring mechanisms such as fences or forcing steps, and the macro-steps that could be implemented were limited to simple sequences.

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III. MOTIVATION FOR CHOOSING C LANGUAGE

Grafcet is a logical automatism description formalism that allows expressing competing processes. A language to translate Grafcet has to preferably be parallel [6] and/or real-time. The duration of the task's installation or its switching time is decisive in choosing such a language. C and Unix [9] were chosen due to their portability, universality, and control by most computer scientists. Its disadvantage lies in the fact that Unix is not quite real-time, because its slow temporal primitives were defined according to the only problems of the timeshare. C language is a High-Level Machine-Oriented Language (HLMOL) that allows defining bit-close fields, and expanded by Unix libraries can provide the illusion of simultaneous execution of tasks on uniprocessor machines, as shown by functions such as fork, wait, sleep, kill [9]. Pipes are the main means of communication between Unix processes [9]. Several synchronization means are available in Unix. This study used the wait function, which is the most basic mean of synchronization and can be used to synchronize a parent process on the termination of its children. Time management was carried out using the sleep() function, as the call to the sleep(*n*) function suspends the calling process for *n* seconds. Since the seconds are not useful for many real-time scenarios, the macro tempo() was used to allow timers in microseconds:

```
#define tempo(n){
    clock_t reveil = clock()+n;
    while(clock(<reveil) sleep(0);
}/*n in microseconds */
```

So, sleep(1) is equivalent to tempo(1000000). These timers were used in processes running in parallel and can limit the waiting time for certain events.

IV. SIMULATION SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Two subsystems constitute the simulation system [10]:

- Grafcet entry: this subsystem offers two possibilities:
 - Graphical input: Based on a graphical editor, allows any Grafcet to be entered graphically and outputs its image data structure.
 - Text entry: Rarely used in practice, except for maintenance purposes. It allows to enter the Grafcet as text, so requires a text analyzer that outputs the same data structure as the graphical editor.
- Translation of the Grafcet: This subsystem exploits the data structure from the entry and translates it into C. Two steps are possible:
 - Interpreter/simulator: A program that executes step-by-step the appropriate C sequences according to the data structure.
 - Generator: A program that creates a complete C code of all the Grafcet. Executing this code is the simulation of the automatism described by the Grafcet, as long as this code is not configured according to real I/O.

In both cases, translation requires defining the Grafcet/C generation schemes.

V. GRAFCET/C TRANSLATION SCHEMES

The definition of the translation schemes from Grafcet to C consists of finding for each Grafcet basic element a program scheme in C which has the same semantics. The elements of Grafcet are: simple transition, divergences (AND, OR), convergences (AND, OR), the stage, and the macro stage [10].

A. Preliminary Study [10]

Let's consider the following scenario:

- A rotating bar at a position *x*, *y* of the screen successive display in *x*, *y* of characters -, /, |, \, -, /, ...)
- In case of no overflows, pressing the arrow keys causes the bar to move down, left, right, and up respectively.
- If limits are exceeded, the above characters produce an audible signal, and the bar keeps rotating in the same place.
- Pressing the character "q" stops the scenario.
- Pressing any other character is ineffective.

Figure 1 shows the Grafcet of the above scenario.

Fig. 1. Grafcet associated with the rotating bar scenario.

Let EB and TB be the stages and transitions of the rotating bar branch, and EL and TL be the stages and transitions of the reading characters branch.

- | | |
|--------------------|--|
| Stages | E0: initial stage, beginning of the program.
EB1: rotating bar.
EB2: end of the rotating bar process.
EB3: Test of the character read in the pipe.
EB4: audible alarm.
EB5: moving the bar.
EB6: rest (sleep). |
| Transitions | EL1: read and test the read character.
EL2: sending a KILL and exit.
EL3: write ↓, ←, →, ↑ in the pipe.
EL4: rest (sleep).
S: end of the scenario.
T1: pressing any key to start both processes.
TB1: reception of a KILL signal.
TB2: read ↓, ←, →, ↑ in the pipe.
TB4: overcoming limits.
TB5: no overflows.
TB6 = 1; TB7 = 1
TL2: read ↓, ←, → or ↑ from the keyboard.
TL3: reading of the 'q' character of the keyboard.
TL4 = 1; TL5 = 1; TLF = 1. |

B. Principles of the Image Program

Once the program is launched, two processes are created and launched simultaneously (proc1, proc2). Proc1 is a standalone process associated with the rotating bar, while proc2 is associated with its movement and is under external influence. At some point, the two processes must act simultaneously on the coordinates x, y of the bar. A first solution is to create a critical section within each process to achieve mutual exclusion of both accesses [8]. A second solution would be to allow effective access to a single process, such as proc1, which will rotate and move the bar, proc2 reads the arrow characters, considered as the move commands of the bar, and sends them through a pipe to proc1 to use them to move the bar in the desired direction. The end of the scenario will take place when proc2 reads the "q" key. Table I shows the general processing algorithms of proc1 and proc2. This program, modeled in Grafcet, is the basis to deduce the basic translation schemes from Grafcet into C. These schemes were extended for industrial processes where the system entries can be numerous, simultaneous, and real-time. Therefore, push buttons and sensors were integrated.

TABLE I. PARALLEL RUNNING OF PROC1 AND PROC2

Proc1	Proc2
At each position of the bar: Display the bar Look in p[0] if a character is placed in the pipe. If yes the character is stored in cc1 and tested. If exceeding the limits, warning sound, otherwise move in the desired direction. Rotation of the bar.	Reads a cc character from the keyboard and test it. If cc ='q' then sends a SIGKILL to proc1 then EXIT. If cc ="↓", "←", "→" or "↑" then places cc in the inlet p[1] of the pipe; If cc is other, ignore cc.

C. Grafcet-C Translation Schemes

A simple transition is an external event that can arise at any time from a sensor, button, etc. Three cases exist to simulate it: keyboard, order box, and always concurrent. Keyboard input can be given as a simple scheme:

```
cc=getch()
```

In case of an order box, let boitcom be the port address of the command box, reading 8 to 16 digital inputs. By assimilating all the bits to zero in the absence of an entry, the scheme could be the following:

```
while(!(*boitcom)) sleep(0);
```

These diagrams are taken up and developed when a configuration language would cover the essential cases concerning the real-time management of arbitrary devices, which will be part of a realistic simulation. Meanwhile, the input from the control box can be simulated by programming the keys of the keyboard, associating a sequence of bits: for $i=1, \dots, 7$, command[0], ..., command[7], command[i]=1 when the receptivity i is true, and command[i]=0 when no receptivity is true. In an always occurrent case, $t=1$, which means that the sum of the internal and external receptivity conditions is 1. In this case, a comment is generated (*/* t=1 */*).

1) Divergences

- AND divergence:

```
while(!t) sleep(0);
rep=forkn(tab_fonc,nproc,tab_pid);
rep1=wait(&status);
while((rep1 !=-1) wait(&status);
```

where tab_fonc is an array of pointers to functions performed in the context of each process, nproc is the number of the created processes, tab_pid is the pid char of the created processes, and tab_fonc[i] is the pointer to the function executed by the process with the pid_tab_pid[i]. Forkn() details can be found in [9].

- OR divergence: The exclusive OR divergence is given by:

```
while(!t1&&!t2&&!t3... &&!tn)sleep(0);
switch(transition){
case t1 : p1();
case t2 : p2();
...
case tn : pn();
}
```

where pi() is the procedure executed for the transition ti and there is no priming of new paths. Inclusive OR is given by:

```
while(!t1&&!t2&&... &&!tn) sleep(0);
if(t1) p1();
if(t2) p2();
...
if(tn) pn();
/* the creative process enters the
zombie state */
rep1=wait(&status);
while (rep1 !=-1) wait(&status);
```

where pi() is the process creation procedure i. There is a boot of new paths. Two images are likely in the classical case of an input form: A general but expensive image (competition diagram), or an effective image applicable under certain conditions. In the case of an effective image, the alternative scheme is applicable if and only if the transitions are disjoint two by two.

The evaluation of this question in a generator is the subject of a decision procedure, which in case of difficulties may substitute, the absolute criterion above, one or more sufficient conditions easier to evaluate. For example, if two transitions occur as products of elementary conditions, they are disjoint if the same condition is present in the two transitions in opposite forms, such that: $T1 = x y z$ and $T2 = x \bar{y} z$. In the case of expectations with time-out, there is divergence with two issues, one of which carries the receptivity "event" and the other a receptivity "time limit". Since this can only be performed in excess, it is normal to consider the two as disjoint (in case of conjunction, the event is considered to have happened after the prescribed duration). The quality of the decision procedure thus directly governs the quality of the code, which may be inaccurate, correct but heavy, correct and effective, and even optimal for a perfect decision procedure. On the other hand, the generation with divergences must agree with the generation with convergences.

2) Convergences

- **AND Convergence:** Two cases arise: If pi has the same divergence as the origin, the synchronization is performed by wait(), while if they don't have the same origin, synchronization is mandatory. For each father process, synchro is a global variable. Initially, synchro is the number of incoming branches. Once it finishes, each process simulating an incoming branch must access synchro and decrement it. When synchro becomes null, it implies the end of all branches. As the access to synchro may be simultaneous, it must therefore be a critical section within each process, using either semaphores or locks [11]. This study used a method of choosing a process, called the coordinator, and took the one that simulates the most left incoming branch. When it finishes, the coordinator performs the following algorithm.

```

/* scheme associated with coordinator*/
/*only the coordinator accesses synchro*/
int rep ; char cc ;
...
/* as soon as it finishes, it
decrements synchro */
synchro-- ;
while(1){
    cc = ' ';
    dup(tube1[1]);
    close(tube1[1]);
    read(tube1[0],cc,1);
    if (cc=='f') synchro--;
    ...
    cc=' ';
    dup(tuben[1]);
    close(tuben[1]);
    read(tuben[0],cc,1);
    if (cc=='f') synchro--;
}/* finwhile */
/* synchro=0, le process p0 kills
all the other processes and makes
an exit */
rep=kill(pid1, SIGKILL);
rep=kill(pid2, SIGKILL);
...
rep=kill(pidn, SIGKILL);
exit();

```

Once it finishes, each other process associated with other branches should perform the following algorithm:

```

/* let's suppose the process number i,
other than the coordinator, sends the
character 'f' in the pipe */
dup(tubei[0]);
close(tubei[0]);
write(tubei[1],f,1);
/* infinite loop as wait */
for( ; ) sleep(0);

```

- **OR Convergence:** Exclusive OR comes down to the simple transition, while inclusive OR is discussed in the same way as the AND convergence.

3) The Stages

It executes within a process, and can be simulated by a message specifying it, possibly a time-dependent timer associated with it, encapsulated in an enn() procedure:

```

void enn()
printf("etape %d",num_etape);
tempo(duree) ;

```

4) The Macro Stage

The macro stage is translated using a procedure that is an image similar to the main program because it is a sub-Grafcet and militates a recursive generation.

5) Forcing

The diagrams can be implemented in the case where the automatism is modeled by a single Grafcet, which is a single connected component. They can be extended by adding the associated macros in the case of forcing or applied in the case of a hierarchy of Grafcets. The forcing function is an action of macro stage M. This is then called macroaction, and is a procedure using another Grafcet (slave). The functions associated with forcing operations are summarized below:

- **Freezing:** This operation consists of sending the signal SIGSTOP to the active stages of the given Grafcet.

```

void suspendre(g){
int i, rep ;
i=1 ;
while (i<= nbactif){
    rep=kill(pid[i],SIGSTOP);
    i++;
}
//nbactif = number of active stages
//pid : table of active pid

```

- **Disabling the slave Grafcet:** This operation is associated with a deactivate() procedure which consists of sending a SIGKILL signal to the active processes in the slave Grafcet given by g.
- **Put in initial situation:** This procedure consists of calling a subroutine that is analogous to the main program. This is similar to using the macro stage in the case of the normal operation of automation.
- **Put in any situation:** Two cases may arise, reactivate a previously suspended Grafcet, which would consist of sending the SIGCONT signal to the suspended process, or activate certain stages of the Grafcet in question where it would be necessary to put to true their input receptivities and launch the functions associated with them.

VI. NECESSARY CONFIGURATION FOR THE SYSTEM

The implementation of this system requires:

- A Unix or Linux or any multitasking system.
- A graphic screen for entering the Grafcet.
- A keyboard as input device and, if possible, a box of commands.
- Effectors: LEDs, bulbs, effectors.

The screen is divided into two windows. The first window (FEN1) is used to draw the currently active Grafcet (command part), while the second (FEN2) is specific to the messages that illustrate the actions carried out by the operative part. Initially,

the Grafcet is animated from the initial situation. The arrival of the transitions from the keyboard or the control box causes the evolution of the Grafcet, i.e. activation of the new stage or stages (following the transition), and deactivation of the stage or stages. Active stages will be highlighted in FEN1, showing their associated messages in FEN2. The command box allows making several entries at once, a case that can be tested for OR divergences and transitions whose branches run in parallel. Figure 2 shows a Grafcet and the corresponding C program.

Fig. 2. From Grafcet to C code.

VII. APPLICATION

Figures 3 and 4 show two industrial Grafcet examples that were used to validate the proposed method. The principle of validation of a Grafcet has two phases: static validation, respecting the conditions of good form, and dynamic validation of the execution.

A. Grafcet Good Form Conditions

A Grafcet is:

- Except: if for any situation accessible from E0, no step is reactivated.
- Living: If for any accessible situation from E0, a crossing sequence of any transition exists.
- Clean: If for any situation accessible for E0, there is a crossing sequence leading to E0.

B. Importance of the Preceding Properties for the Grafcet Evolution

If the Grafcet is safe, no step is reactivated during its possible evolutions. Reactivation is dangerous and can lead to errors. A living Grafcet will never block and will never find inert steps or transitions (unactivated steps, unsensitized transitions) at a certain stage of the evolution. If a Grafcet is clean, this implies possible re-initiation. This is a very important phenomenon for automation, as the initial step is considered a resting stage. The proposed method assumes:

- Transitions from the keyboard or the control box are always occurring (= 1), simulating well external or internal events.
- Simple steps: The considered Grafcet can easily be assimilated to the complete Grafcet that takes into account any type of transition or step. This method is effective for Grafcet validation.

The Grafcet shown in Figure 3 is not safe because there is a reactivation of step 2, in the case of crossing transition 5. The proposed method indicates it by a message and rejects it when meeting again step 2 within the normal operating cycle.

Fig. 3. Industrial Grafcet example1.

Fig. 4. Industrial Grafcet example2.

In Figure 4, transitions 2 and 3, are OR divergences. If they occur together, the OR of this divergence is inclusive and the Grafcet is clean, alive, and safe. If they do not occur together, the OR is exclusive, and one branch will be executed, but arriving at the AND convergence, transition 5 can be crossed only if steps 4 and 5 are both active and the transition is equal

to 1, which is not the case if the OR is exclusive. The proposed program reports a blockage in this case.

C. Compatibility of Simultaneous Actions and Correlation of Stages and Receptivity

A subsystem displaying the steps and associated actions would allow the user to know if the steps that have run simultaneously correspond to compatible actions, after observing the execution of the Grafcet. For example, two pumps, one operating while the other is at rest, should never appear together in two simultaneous actions in a Grafcet. Similarly, the action-receptivity correlation can be checked by consulting the transitions and the associated receptivity conditions (the symbol table contains all the information relating to the steps and transitions).

D. Search of Cycles

In principle, a cycle exists, outside the normal operating cycle, if there is a reactivation of at least one previous step. The proposed algorithm, as designed, rejects the Grafcet as soon as a previously activated stage is reactivated. A cycle within the normal cycle of operation can have dangerous consequences.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The proposed algorithm allows to translate a large number of Grafcets by compositions of the most elementary elements. On a practical level, this study created a Grafcet library of translation diagrams. This library was tested on several examples, is independent of the assumed internal form, takes into account the automatisms described by a single Grafcet, and can be extended to explicit macros and procedures relating to forcing processing used in the case of a Grafcets hierarchy. A program was developed that requires to start from a graphic editor or specialized analyzers to enter the Grafcet in an internal form to produce a C code whose execution will behave according to the entered Grafcet. Automatic production of the C code is based on the elementary translation schemes described. As a second step, after the test, validation, and configuration of the algorithm and the program, the object code can be implemented on the microcontroller of the actual control system, in particular explaining everything related to the execution configuration. The advantage of the proposed algorithm is that it can be widely used because it requires a simple hardware and software configuration as a microcomputer equipped with the Linux operating system is more than enough. Compared to other works, the proposed method can simulate any type of Grafcet and the various forcing treatments, and it presents precision and exhaustiveness. The only downside of the proposed method is that Unix is not quite real-time, but this approach can be assumed as complete by staying at the simulation stage. Future work would focus on translating Grafcet into Promela/SPIN.

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REFERENCES

- [1] O. A. Adebimpe, V. Oladokun, and O. E. Charles-Owaba, "Preventive Maintenance Interval Prediction: a Spare Parts Inventory Cost and Lost Earning Based Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 811–817, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.565>.
- [2] L. S. Tavassoli, N. Sakhavand, and S. S. Fazeli, "Integrated Preventive Maintenance Scheduling Model with Redundancy for Cutting Tools on a Single Machine," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6542–6548, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3903>.
- [3] M. A. Munir, M. A. Zaheer, M. Haider, M. Z. Rafique, M. A. Rasool, and M. S. Amjad, "Problems and Barriers Affecting Total Productive Maintenance Implementation," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4818–4823, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3082>.
- [4] B. M., *Comprendre Maîtriser Et Appliquer Le Grafcet*. Toulouse, France: Éditions Cépaduès, 2005.
- [5] Reeb Bernard, *Développement des grafcets : des machines simples aux cellules flexibles, du cahier des charges à la programmation / Bernard Reeb*, Nouvelle édition. Paris, France: Ellipses, 2011.
- [6] Z. Remaki, J. F. Ponsignon, M. Nekkache, "Schémas de traduction grafcet Occam2", presented at the 3rd Maghreb Congress on Artificial Intelligence and Software Engineering, Rabat, Morocco, 1994.
- [7] E. González, R. Marichal, and A. Hamilton, "Ontology-based approach to Basic Grafcet formalization," *Journal of the Chinese Institute of Engineers*, vol. 39, no. 8, pp. 946–953, Nov. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02533839.2016.1215939>.
- [8] O. Miguel-Escrig, J.-A. Romero-Pérez, B. Wiesmayr, and A. Zoitl, "Distributed implementation of Grafcets through IEC 61499," in *2020 25th IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, Vienna, Austria, Sep. 2020, vol. 1, pp. 402–409, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ETFA46521.2020.9212087>.
- [9] W. Stevens and S. Rago, *Advanced Programming in the UNIX Environment, 3rd Edition*, 3rd edition. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Addison-Wesley Professional, 2013.
- [10] Nacéra Benaouda and Abdelhafid Benaouda, "Translating Grafcet Specifications into C/Unix Program," presented at the IADIS International Conference Information Systems 2021, 2021, pp. 209–217.
- [11] M. Raynal, *Concurrent Programming: Algorithms, Principles, and Foundations*. Springer, 2013.

Exploring the Enhanced Performance of a Static Synchronous Compensator with a Super-Capacitor in Power Networks

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Abstract-The use of a super-capacitor as a storage device integrated with a Voltage source converter-based shunt-connected Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) is proposed for improving the STATCOM performance during sudden large disturbances in a power network. The super-capacitor was applied across the STATCOM capacitor during the disturbance condition. MATLAB simulations were carried out for the verification of a secondary function of the STATCOM like oscillation damping, transient stability improvement, and security of the power network with the storage device. The validation of the proposed super-capacitor was carried out in MATLAB.

Keywords-STATCOM; storage device; super-capacitor; transient stability; security

I. INTRODUCTION

Power demand is increasing in comparison to power production. To balance it, enlargement or modification of the power network is needed, which results in complex design and unsecure operation of the network. With this complex design, the network becomes very sensitive to various types of disturbance like faults, line switching, contingency, congestion, etc., leading to a decline in stability, security, and reliability of the power network [1-2]. Power network stability plays a very imperative role in securing the network operation. The instability in power network exhibits itself in various ways, such as frequency, angle, and speed deviations, and power and voltage oscillations. Power network stability status may be steady state, transient state, or dynamic. Transient stability is mainly affected by major disturbances. Proper power network devices are used to enhance stability and to increase security. Shunt-connected voltage source converter-based reactive power compensation devices are widely adopted to overcome voltage stability issues. However, to compensate the true power in the network, Super-Capacitors (SCs) with the additional benefit of storage are used [3-4].

In [5], a supplementary HVDC technology for STATCOM is considered for steady state and transient stability characteristics. In [6], a battery energy storage system was

taken as a package of storing elements and VSC to provide autonomous control of the active and reactive power injection to the grid. In [7], the transient stability margin of a power network connected STATCOM is determined using trajectory sensitivity analysis. A SC type energy storage system is used to enhance the transient state stability analysis of a grid connected wind turbine in [8]. A unified STATCOM and battery energy storage system is evaluated for the enhancement of dynamic, transient stability, and transmission competence in [9]. In [10], STATCOM is used for transient stability enhancement. Modelling of non-linear load with STATCOM is conducted in [11]. An ultra-capacitor is used with the STATCOM for power oscillation damping in [12]. In [13], a superconducting magnetic energy storage system with STATCOM is used for power system oscillation damping. In [14], steady state performance has been checked with STATCOM and an energy storage system. Sub-synchronous oscillations are mitigated with a superconducting magnetic energy storage system in [15]. In [16], rotor angle and voltage stability were studied during fault conditions with fault location identification. In [17], voltage stability assessment in real time was conducted. A brief summary of different FACTS controller types with a focus on STATCOM topologies and their control strategies was done in [18]. In all the above studies, focus was towards steady state, transient state, dynamic state stability, rotor angle stability, or mitigation of sub-synchronous oscillations of the network, which are conducted by using STATCOM or an energy storage system. Little focus has been given in the enhancement of STATCOM performance by connecting SC during various conditions. Very few researches tested SC with shunt FACTS devices under transient disturbances in multi-machine networks.

In this paper, a storage device (SC) is connected to the STATCOM capacitor for improving its secondary performance under sudden large disturbances in the power network. The short duration application of the SC during disturbance conditions is tested in MATLAB environment. The voltage source converter based STATCOM is designed to provide voltage support by reactive power control and to enhance

secondary functions, e.g. reduction in power oscillation damping and improvement in transient stability and security of the multi-machine network. The sudden large disturbances are created by three phase faults of 0.3 and 0.2s duration in a multimachine network. Comparative analysis of STATCOM with storage device and without storage devices is conducted. The results prove the improved STATCOM performance with the SC during the transient problem.

II. MODELLING OF THE POWER NETWORK

A multi-machine network during transient conditions is considered. A synchronous generator, two loads, and a transformer are connected with the STATCOM and the supercapacitor is connected in shunt. As case studies, three-phase faults are applied for transient conditions near the transformer.

A. Synchronous Generator

The synchronous generator is an electrical machine converting mechanical into electrical power. It is the chief driver of any power network. The synchronous generator plays a very important role in the monitoring of the power network at various conditions [10]. Model (1.1) of IEEE Task Force, with one equivalent damper winding on the q-axis with field circuit is represented as [11]:

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = \omega_B (S_m - S_{mo}) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dS_m}{dt} = \frac{1}{2H} [-D (S_m - S_{mo}) + T_m - T_e] \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dE'_q}{dt} = \frac{1}{T'_{do}} [-E'_q + (x_d - x'_d) i_d + E_{fd}] \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dE'_d}{dt} = \frac{1}{T'_{qo}} [-E'_d - (x_q - x'_q) i_q] \quad (4)$$

The electrical torque equation is given as:

$$T_e = E'_d i_d + E'_q i_q + (x'_d - x'_q) i_d i_q \quad (5)$$

where δ is the operating rotor angle, ω_B is the rated angular speed, S_m and S_{mo} represent the slip, H is the generator inertia constant, D is the damping coefficient, T_m and T_e represent the mechanical and electrical torque, E'_d and E'_q are the voltages for d and q axes, T'_{do} and T'_{qo} are the open circuit transient time constants for direct and quadrature axes, $x_d, x'_d, x_q, x'_q, i_d,$ and i_q are the reactances and currents of the said two axes, and E_{fd} is the output of the dynamic system.

B. Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM)

The STATCOM and the Static VAR compensator are members of the FACTS family which are shunt-connected devices. The STATCOM helps to control the power and enhances transient stability of power grids [1]. STATCOM can generate more reactive power than Static VAR compensator during voltage lower than the normal voltage regulation range. The STATCOM has the ability to provide more capacitive reactive power during fault conditions. STATCOM regulates both inductive and capacitive modes according to the action of injection or absorption of the reactive power [12, 13]. Reactive power variation is performed by the voltage source converter

coupled to the coupling transformer [14, 20]. The equivalent circuit of a STATCOM with a SC is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Equivalent circuit of STATCOM with an SC.

Mathematically, the active and reactive powers of the STATCOM are represented as:

$$P = \frac{V_1 V_2}{X} \sin \delta \quad (6)$$

$$Q = \frac{V_1 (V_1 - V_2 \cos \delta)}{X} \quad (7)$$

Figure 2 shows the control network block diagram of a STATCOM with an SC. It comprises of a phase locked loop which calculates the phase voltage and the three phase AC current for the direct-axis and quadrature-axis components, the measurement system for measuring the d and q components of the AC positive-sequence voltage, the currents to be controlled, the DC voltage V_{dc} , and the AC and DC voltage regulators for controlling reactive and active power flow respectively. The current regulator controls the magnitude and the phase by the Pulse Width Modulator converter. The SC is connected across V_{dc} .

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the control network of a STATCOM with an SC.

C. Super-Capacitor

An SC, also known as an ultra-capacitor, is an electrochemical double layer capacitor. The values of capacitance of the super-capacitor are orders of magnitude greater than the values of normal capacitors. SCs can deliver

bursts of energy since charging and discharging takes place rapidly. Using a single SC block, modeling can be done by connecting the SC's cell in series or parallel. Beside the energy storing capacity as an advantage, when the SC is combined with STATCOM, the performance of the network is enhanced with active power support to the network. The equivalent circuit for a single cell in the SC block is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. A single cell SC.

The voltage and current across the SC block are obtained by:

$$V_{cn} = \frac{v}{N_{series}} - i_n R_n \quad (8)$$

$$i_n = C_n \frac{dV_{cn}}{dt} \quad (9)$$

where V is the voltage across the block, N_{series} is the number of series cells, n is the branch number, i_n is the n^{th} branch current, R_n is the n^{th} branch resistance, and V_{cn} is the n^{th} branch voltage across the capacitor.

III. TEST NETWORK

In order to check the performance of the power network during transient condition, a 4-bus test network is considered (Figure 4). The test network consists of 3 generators, 2 loads, 1 transformer, 3 lines, and 4 buses. The basic test network is modeled in MATLAB/Simulink environment with the following parameters: The generators have 16,500MVA total generation capacity, the loads have 12,500MW loading, one 1000MVA transformer is used, a VSC based 100MVA STATCOM, 500KV Voltage, and a 100pF, 16V SC.

Fig. 4. Test network single line diagram.

IV. SIMULATION PERFORMANCE

Simulation performance is checked by applying 3-phase faults of 0.2 and 0.3s duration near bus 1, which implies a transient condition. Various parameters like rotor speed, stator voltage, true power, imaginary power, and voltages are monitored. Transient conditions or large disturbances result into very unbalanced network parameters and create tremendous oscillations in the network, upshots, or complete black-outs or total failures. It is better to prevent such types of failure by connecting some boosting or balancing elements. Flexible AC transmission system elements are power devices connected to the network for enhancement. A STATCOM shunt FACTS device is connected in the network at bus 4 to support the network during disturbance conditions.

Figure 5 displays the rotor speed of the generator connected to bus 1. A 3-phase fault is applied for 0.2 and 0.3s. The network without STATCOM and SC shows more oscillations and takes more time to return to the stable condition. As compared to the earlier condition, the connected STATCOM stabilizes rotor speed early, with fewer oscillations. The result of connecting the SC with the STATCOM is more impressive because it damps rotor speed oscillations in less settling time. Figure 5 indicates effective large fault duration condition and oscillation suppression by the SC-based STATCOM and thus, reduced settling time of the rotor speed.

Figure 6 depicts the Generator 1 terminal voltage without STATCOM and SC, with STATCOM and SC, and with STATCOM only. As the fault duration increases, the system becomes more prone to instability. With STATCOM and SC stator, the Voltage comes closer to 1pu earlier and thus the stability margin increases. During the transient period, the SC suppresses the oscillations and superior performance of the STATCOM is observed.

Fig. 5. Rotor speed, fault time (a) 0.2s, (b) 0.3s.

Fig. 6. Generator 1 terminal Voltage, fault time (a) 0.2s, (b) 0.3s.

Fig. 8. Reactive power, fault time: (a) 0.2s, (b) 0.3s.

Fig. 7. Active Power, fault time (a) 0.2s, (b) 0.3s.

Fig. 9. Network Voltage at bus 2, fault time (a) 0.2s, (b) 0.3s.

Active power and reactive power oscillation damping is more effectively done with STATCOM and SC as can be seen in Figures 7 and 8. Larger oscillations are observed in the 0.3s fault duration. STATCOM with SC real power oscillations are effectively damp out and settling time reduces with a large stability margin. Reactive power demand reduces and oscillations reduce as well.

Figure 9 exhibits the bus 2 Voltage oscillations, which are maintained at 1pu with the SC-based STATCOM combination. Figure 10 shows the V_{dc} variation with an SC. The DC voltage is maintained constant. Figure 11 shows the SC voltage variation during fault conditions.

Fig. 10. V_{dc} , fault time (a) 0.2s, (b) 0.3s.

Fig. 11. SC Voltage, fault time (a) 0.2s, (b) 0.3s.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the performance of the Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) is enhanced with the aid of a Super-Capacitor (SC). A multi-machine network was evaluated in MATLAB during the transient condition without STATCOM, with STATCOM and with both STATCOM and SC. A symmetrical 3-phase fault is applied for 0.2s as case study 1 in the network. It is observed that the oscillations are damped within 25, 12, and 105s without STATCOM, with STATCOM, and with STATCOM-SC respectively. With STATCOM-SC, the second peak reduces from 1.025 to 1.015pu. The primary function of a STATCOM is to maintain constant terminal voltage and bus voltage at 0.9 to 1pu, which is achieved by the proposed STATCOM-SC combination. Similarly for the case study 2, the fault duration is 0.3s, for which the responses of STATCOM-SC are drastically enhanced as network oscillations are damped quickly, peak time and Voltage variation are reduced, and the network quickly overcomes the issue.

It is observed that as the fault duration increases, the proposed STATCOM-SC model works more effectively. An additional benefit to true power compensation is the energy storage which is very essential for secured power network. The energy storage with STATCOM-SC enhances the transient performance of the network and reduces the damage to the equipment during sudden large disturbances, which have not been tested in the published research work. SCs are preferred for short duration applications of nearly 30 to 40s. In the simulations of the current study, the system was tested for 25 to 30s after the disturbance.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. G. Hingorani and L. Gyugyi, *Understanding FACTS: Concepts and Technology of Flexible AC Transmission Systems*, 1st ed. New York, NY, USA: Wiley-IEEE Press, 1999.
- [2] C. W. Taylor, *Power System Voltage Stability*. New York, NY, USA: McGraw-Hill, 1993.
- [3] P. Srithorn, M. Sumner, L. Yao, and R. Parashar, "A STATCOM with supercapacitors for enhanced power system stability," in *2008 4th IET Conference on Power Electronics, Machines and Drives*, York, UK, Apr. 2008, pp. 96–100, <https://doi.org/10.1049/cp:20080490>.
- [4] H. Xie, L. Angquist, and H.-P. Nee, "Design Study of a Converter Interface Interconnecting Energy Storage With the DC Link of a StatCom," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 2676–2686, Jul. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2011.2161677>.
- [5] P. Wang, Y. Wang, N. Jiang, and W. Gu, "A comprehensive improved coordinated control strategy for a STATCOM integrated HVDC system with enhanced steady/transient state behaviors," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 121, Oct. 2020, Art. no. 106091, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2020.106091>.
- [6] O. B. Adewuyi, R. Shigenobu, K. Ooya, T. Senjyu, and A. M. Howlader, "Static voltage stability improvement with battery energy storage considering optimal control of active and reactive power injection," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 172, pp. 303–312, Jul. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epr.2019.04.004>.
- [7] D. Chatterjee and A. Ghosh, "Improvement of transient stability of power systems with STATCOM-controller using trajectory sensitivity," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 531–539, Mar. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2010.12.005>.
- [8] M. Kenan Döşoğlu and A. B. Arsoy, "Transient modeling and analysis of a DFIG based wind farm with supercapacitor energy storage,"

- International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 78, pp. 414–421, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2015.12.020>.
- [9] Z. Yang, C. Shen, L. Zhang, M. L. Crow, and S. Atcitty, "Integration of a StatCom and battery energy storage," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 254–260, Feb. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1109/59.918295>.
- [10] M. M. N. Akhtar and V. K. Chandrakar, "Security Enhancement of Hybrid Source in the Grid with STATCOM," in *2019 3rd International conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA)*, Coimbatore, India, Jun. 2019, pp. 49–54, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICECA.2019.8821798>.
- [11] M. V. Wankhede and V. K. Chandrakar, "Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) for the improvement of the Electrical System performance with Non Linear load," *International Journal of Power Systems*, vol. 1, pp. 27–32, 2016.
- [12] K. Dayalal Joshi and V. Chandrakar, "Power oscillation damping using ultracapacitor and voltage source based FACTS controllers," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Electrical, Instrumentation and Communication Engineering (ICEICE)*, Karur, India, Apr. 2017, pp. 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEICE.2017.8191878>.
- [13] A. M. Raut, K. D. Joshi, and V. K. Chandrakar, "Damping of Power System Oscillation using STATCOM Integrated with SMES," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 119, no. 8, pp. 11–14, Jun. 2015.
- [14] P. Mahale, K. D. Joshi, and V. K. Chandrakar, "Static Synchronous Compensator (STATCOM) with Energy Storage," in *2009 Second International Conference on Emerging Trends in Engineering & Technology*, Nagpur, India, Sep. 2009, pp. 560–563, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICETET.2009.213>.
- [15] W. Gil-González, O. D. Montoya, and A. Garces, "Control of a SMES for mitigating subsynchronous oscillations in power systems: A PBC-PI approach," *Journal of Energy Storage*, vol. 20, pp. 163–172, Dec. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2018.09.001>.
- [16] H. F. Khan, A. H. Hanif, and N. Anwar, "Rotor Angle and Voltage Stability Analysis with Fault Location Identification on the IEEE 9 Bus System," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5259–5264, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3175>.
- [17] D. V. Ngo, K. V. Pham, D. D. Le, K. H. Le, and K. V. Huynh, "Assessing Power System Stability Following Load Changes and Considering Uncertainty," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2758–2763, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1892>.
- [18] R. Jadeja, S. Patel, and S. Chauhan, "STATCOM – A Preface to Power Quality in Power Systems Performance," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 895–905, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.603>.
- [19] A. Chakraborty, S. K. Musunuri, A. K. Srivastava, and A. K. Kondabathini, "Integrating STATCOM and Battery Energy Storage System for Power System Transient Stability: A Review and Application," *Advances in Power Electronics*, vol. 2012, Dec. 2012, Art. no. e676010, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/676010>.

Effectiveness of EPS Bead Size and Cement Proportions on the Strength and Deformation of Light-Weighted Soil

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Abstract-The current study investigates the deformation and strength of Light-Weighted Soil (LWS) comprised of silt, Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) beads, cement, and water. The EPS bead sizes employed in this study are 4, 5, and 6mm in diameter with densities of 0.011, 0.009, and 0.006g/cm³ and cement concentrations of 10% and 15%. The effects of different EPS bead sizes and cement proportions on the mechanical properties (strength and deformation) of LWS are evaluated by Unconfined Compression Strength (UCS) tests. The findings show that the EPS bead sizes significantly impact the strength and deformations of the LWS. The smaller the EPS bead size, the higher the observed strength, but, on the other hand, bigger EPS bead sizes have lower strength and higher ductility. It was also revealed that the strength of LWS is entirely dependent on the cement concentration. High cement content in the LWS has more strength and brittleness, but it is more prone to deformation. The cost can be decreased by increasing the EPS bead size, and thus the prescription of mixed soil can be enhanced. The use of EPS beads with a diameter of 4-6mm is recommended in the construction process, especially in backfill for retaining walls. Each EPS bead size provides advantages in different context, depending on engineering applications and field conditions.

Keywords-strength and deformation; expanded polystyrene beads; unconfined compression test; cement

I. INTRODUCTION

Light-Weighted Soil (LWS) comprises of silt, EPS beads, cement, and water and it has lower density than the ordinary

soil. LWS has good independence, hardness, flowability, strength, ductility, heat resistance, and water resistance. The disposal of EPS is a problem that many cities face. On its own, EPS does not harm or contaminate the soil, but because it takes hundreds of years to break down, it takes up too much space in landfills and reduces the usable area. Its lightweight nature and low density have impeded efforts to recycle EPS. Lightweight fill materials are utilized in a variety of ways. They can be used as fill over poor soils, backfill for retaining walls to minimize lateral loads, fill materials for slopes to decrease driving forces, and seismic buffers, among other applications. These solutions have tremendous engineering merits and can significantly cut project costs.

Authors in [1] simulated the mechanical properties of mixed LWS using indoor tests and ABAQUS finite element software and assessed its strength characteristics and deformation law. Authors in [2] reported that when the size of EPS particles was in the range of 1–5 mm, the permeability of the water increased as the EPS particle size rose, while the UCS of spherical EPS 1–3mm particles was higher than that of fractured and flaky EPS particles [2]. EPS soil combinations' compressive strength, unit weight, permeability, dynamic properties, creep qualities, and water absorption properties were examined in [3]. Authors in [4] reported that when the size of the EPS beads increases, the unconfined compressive strength of LWS is reduced. To reduce project expenses, the impact of EPS beads with a particle size bigger than 3mm on the shear strength of LWS was explored in [5]. The stress-

strain properties of EPS sand mixture specimens were investigated using Consolidated Drained (CD) triaxle compression trials, and it was revealed that increasing EPS content resulted in lower shear strength and increased volumetric strain [6]. Authors in [7] reported that the compressive strength of LWS decreases as the EPS increases. Furthermore, increasing the amount of EPS particles lowers the strength of LWS [7, 8]. The deformation of LWS is quick at the top of the sample and progressively declines to the bottom, according to the cyclic loading test and ABAQUS simulations of different blends of EPS and silty soil under varying confining pressure and cement contents [9, 10]. When the cement mixing ratio is increased, the mixed soil shear strength characteristics are comparable to those of general soil laboratory uniaxial and triaxle compression tests used to determine the relationship between stress and strain strengths. The triaxle test findings demonstrate that mixed soil's shear strength characteristics are very similar to ordinary soil only when the cement mixture is high [8]. Authors in [11] studied lightweight fill's unconfined compressive and shear strength and stiffness with regard to the cement-to-soil ratio. The compression strength of a lightweight blend is reduced by the formation of EPS particles. The most likely explanation is that the enlarged EPS beads have taken the place of the hydrate. In terms of composition, the porosity of the light mixture increases and the strength decreases as the percentage of light particles grows. When the cement percentage is reduced, the lightweight's compressive strength with various EPS sections varies only slightly [12]. Authors in [13] conducted triaxle and direct shear tests to investigate the shear strength characteristics. The soil friction angle was enhanced by combining 1mm EPS beads with fly ash.

The effect of various EPS geofoam densities and geofoam cell heights on the compressive strength was studied in [14, 15]. The density of EPS geofoam improves its compressive strength, whereas the compressive strength of EPS geofoam falls along with the cell height [16]. Light materials, such as EPS particles, are frequently used for mixing in a variety of earthworks in order to minimize the composite weight and reduce self-weight [15, 16]. The addition of cement solidification improves the engineering characteristics of waste soil, and the lightweight treatment reduces embankment settling [17, 18]. Additionally, the mechanical constitutive model of the lightweight mixture may be developed, and engineering applications can employ the calculated strengths and deformation of these lightweight additions [15, 21–24]. EPS is a type of plastic foam with several features, including light weight, pressure resistance, durability, and thermal insulation. It may be used to make LWS and is frequently employed in engineering constructions [20, 21]. Strength and deformability features are essential engineering properties of solidified soil as filling soil. Thus, focus is given on studying the basic mechanisms of artificially modified soil, such as compression deformability and shear strength. Many studies on LWS with EPS diameters up to 3mm have been reported, however, the mechanical properties of the mixed soil with EPS with diameters bigger than 3mm mixed with silty soil have yet to be thoroughly investigated. In the current investigation, laboratory experiments were conducted on silty soil mixed with

different sizes of EPS beads and cement proportions. This study aimed to discover silty soil blends with various EPS bead sizes employed in civil engineering applications such as backfilling.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Silty Soil

Silty soil was collected from the Yellow River Beach, which is adjacent to Zhengzhou City, Henan Province, China, as shown in Figure 1(a). The particles have a light-yellow color and uniform shape, as shown in Figure 1(b). The index characteristics and the gradation of silty soil are shown in Tables II and III. All particles passed through US standard sieve No. 40 (425 μ m). A total of 89.69% of the particles passed through the No. 200 (0.075mm) sieve. The gradation curve of silty soil is shown in Figure 1(c). According to the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS), this silt is classified as High Plasticity silt (MH). Its liquid limit is 52.63, which is greater than 50%, and the plasticity index (Ip) is 22.31 (greater than 7), and lies below the A-line in the plasticity chart.

Fig. 1. (a) Yellow river sample collection site, (b) collected sample (silty soil), (c) grain size distribution curve.

B. EPS Beads

Lightweight EPS insulation is created from solid polystyrene particles. Polystyrene, which makes up 90 to 96% of its makeup, is the main gradient. Three different sizes of EPS beads, i.e. 4, 5, and 6mm, were employed in this study. The beads are round and white. Table I displays the densities and sizes of the EPS beads. In [22] images of the EPS beads taken using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) can be seen.

TABLE I. SIZE OF EPS BEADS AND DENSITIES

Size of EPS beads (mm)	Density (g/cm ³)
4mm	0.011
5mm	0.009
6mm	0.006

C. Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC)

The curing agent used in this experiment is 32.5 composite OPC, which has a consistent quality, high strength, and quick-setting characteristics.

D. Sample Preparation and Mixed Ratio

The silty soil samples were first dried for 24h at 105°C in an oven. The following day, the dried samples were taken from the oven and were spread in a tray. They were carefully broken into pieces with a rubber hammer so that the structure of the silty soil could not be destroyed. Then, the pieces passed through a sieve and debris and unwanted materials were removed. Then, the cement was mixed into the dry silty soil. The silty soil's and cement's particles sizes are similar. Ordinary tap water was poured into the silt cement powder and they were mixed properly with a spatula for 2min until the admixture became homogenous. EPS beads of different sizes were put into the cement silt slurry and the admixture was mixed again for 5min. The mixture became non-homogenous because EPS beads are bigger than silt and cement particles [22]. The mixture was then sampled and the light-weighted samples were left for curing for 28 days. The specimens were ready for testing after the curing period. The mixing ratios are shown in Table IV.

TABLE II. INDEX PROPERTIES OF SILTY SOIL

Properties	Values
Density (g/cm ³)	1.49
Specific gravity G_s	2.72
Water content ω	99.5
Liquid limit w_L	52.63
Plastic limit w_p	30.32
Plasticity index I_p	22.31
Liquidity index I_L	3.10
Volumetric weight ($\gamma/\text{KN/m}^3$)	14.90
Pore ratio (e)	2.64

TABLE III. SIEVE ANALYSIS

Particle percentage (%)			
0.425-0.18mm	0.18-0.15mm	0.15-0.075mm	0.075-0.001mm
1.76	3.19	5.36	89.69

E. Test Plan

The UCS is commonly used in engineering applications and tests. Different mixing ratios were chosen and 3 samples were made for each mixing ratio. The sample size dimensions for the UCS test were 40mm diameter and 80mm height, with applied loading pressures of different stresses. The impact of several parameters on the deformation and strength of silt LWS were investigated, including EPS particle size, cement blending ratios, and EPS content. The ultimate axial strength without lateral pressure resistance was measured using unconfined compressive strength. A dial gauge and a proving ring are typically employed to check the compressive strength, as shown in Figure 2(a). The UCS test was performed, and the test technique was controlled by strain. The device can directly detect the stress and determine the strain based on the sample's height change. The axial stress and strain data were obtained for 2 cement mixing ratios (10% and 15%) and the effect of EPS bead diameter on LWS's deformation and strength properties was examined.

Fig. 2. (a) View of the large-size unconfined compression test apparatus, (b) specimen after the test.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Effects of Cement and EPS Bead Size on Stress and Strain Curves of Light-Weighted Soil

The stress-strain curves of samples with various EPS bead sizes are shown in Figures 3-4. The stress-strain curve swings to the right and downward with increasing cement and EPS content. This demonstrates that the production of LWS follows a distinct pattern. The samples with 4mm EPS bead, 15% cement content, and 1% EPS content had more strength and lower ductility than the samples with 5mm and 6mm EPS bead size with the same percentage of cement and EPS. Besides, EPS beads of bigger sizes have lower shear strength and higher ductility. When the mixing ratio is 15% and 10% cement, and

1% and 2% EPS, the density of 4mm is higher than that of other EPS beads. Due to the small size of the sample, the EPS beads and silty particles have close contact with each other, which enhances shear strength. On the other hand, the tiny holes in the EPS beads of 4mm particles make movement more difficult. When the shear stress exceeds the sample's strength, the 4mm samples are easily destroyed quickly due to energy dissipation, which explains the sample's reduced ductility. Furthermore, when the size and composition of EPS beads grow more significant, the strength falls, and the ductility increases. Moreover, when EPS, a material with lower strength and better ductility, substitutes silty soil in blends, the strength and ductility of the EPS-silt blends drop. Another factor contributing to the weakening of EPS-silty blends is the failure of EPS beads to connect with soil particles.

The stress-strain relationship curve comprises three phases. Before reaching the yield stress, the early load period expands with the strain, stress rises, and the stress-strain relationship gets closer to a linear connection. The linear relationship demonstrates that samples in an elastic state with no discernible breaks can theoretically be restored. As the load increases in the material plastic yield stage, new cracks are formed, and the existing cracks are improved. The strain growth rate is greater than the stress growth rate as the soil shrinks and expands. The stress-strain relationship fits the curve, and the stress rises to its maximum value. The third step is the fracture stage, in which the stress lowers dramatically, and the curve's slope becomes negative. Stress-strain curves of different EPS bead sizes and cement mixing are shown in Figures 3-5.

TABLE IV. MIXING RATIOS

Specimen	Serial number	Cement content (a _c) %	EPS content (a _e) %	EPS beads	Water content	Curing time
LWS	1	10%	1%, 2%	4mm	40	28
		10%	1%, 2%	5mm	40	
		10%	1%, 2%	6mm	40	
LWS	2	15%	1%, 2%	4mm	40	28
		15%	1%, 2%	5mm	40	
		15%	1%, 2%	6mm	40	
Silt					99.5	28

B. UCS of LWS and EPS Bead Size

The UCS comparison for different EPS particle sizes is shown in Figure 5. The UCS for the 4mm group is larger for a given additive content than it is for the other EPS bead sizes. It is evident that when the EPS particle size increases, the UCS of EPS-silty blends diminishes. For instance, the UCS of the 4, 5, and 6mm groups is 550.30kPa, 320.51kPa, and 221.41kPa respectively, when the EPS content is 1% and the cement percentage is 15%. As a result, samples with 4mm EPS particle size should have a denser microstructure than samples with other EPS sizes, resulting in increased strength. Furthermore, the UCS difference between the 5mm and 6mm groups is less than that between the 4mm and 5mm groups. The soil structure of the 4mm group is smaller due to the relatively tinier particle size. The soil particles in the 5mm and 6mm groups cannot be closely mixed with the EPS particles because the EPS particles are substantially more significant than the soil particles. Furthermore, the EPS with particle sizes of 5 and 6mm had the

most significant specific surface area and smooth surface, which reduced the effects of occlusion between soil particles, resulting in the weakest strength of all groups. The cost can be reduced by increasing the EPS size. Structural strength and prices drop as the EPS size increases. To reduce cost, practical projects should employ EPS beads with a diameter of 4-6mm, and material prescription can be adjusted.

C. Deformation of LWS with Different Cement Proportions and EPS Bead Sizes

LWS's confined stress-strain curve is comparable to other traditional soils. As the load and the size of the EPS beads grow larger, the modulus of deformation increases. The rate of development of light soil increased slowly at first and steadily dropped as stress increased, forming a curved dome shape. The turning point of the curve represents the strength of soil, particularly its ultimate strength.

Fig. 3. 15% cement mixed with (a) 1% (b) 2% EPS content.

The bigger the EPS particle size, the lower the strength of the mix. The strength of a mixed soil containing a significant amount of cement is superior to that of a mixed soil containing less cement. The LWS's strength was improved however, if the stress exceeds the mixed soil's strength, the mixed soil's structure will eventually disintegrate and collapse. The ratio of

EPS particle volume deformation to the total volumetric deformation decreased as the EPS particle size rose from 4 to 6mm, due to the fact that when EPS particle size increases, fewer EPS particles are incorporated into the system as a whole, which lowers the EPS particle deformation ratio.

Fig. 4. 10% cement mixed with (a) 1%, (b) 2% EPS content.

The number of EPS particles in a structure significantly impacts structural deformation. With more EPS content in the sample, the particular surface area grows greater, reducing the sample's consolidation strength. Under different stress conditions, increased EPS sizes dramatically increase soil deformation. The structural deformation of lightweight silt soil is significantly affected by the added EPS particles. The experiment revealed that the added EPS particles of various sizes significantly impact the silt LWS's shear strength and deformation characteristics. The strength and deformation variation characteristics of LWS with varied EPS bead sizes are diverse. For instance, the samples with 15% cement and 1% EPS contents of 4mm size have the highest shear strength and the lowest ductility. On the other hand, the samples with 10% cement and 2% EPS of 6mm have the lowest shear strength and the highest ductility as shown in Figures 3 and 4, and they all display multi-stage changes. The failure strain value increased dramatically as the size and quantity of the EPS particle content increased, the plastic zone expanded, but the strength decreased. Additionally, the changing rate of stress intensity decreased as the EPS size increased, resulting in the extension of the elastoplastic range.

Fig. 5. Unconfined compressive strength and EPS beads size of (a) 15% and (b) 10% cement with 1% and 2% EPS content.

According to the analysis of Figures 3-5, cement concentration has little impact on the failure strain of light silt soil, and the strain value difference between them at different mixing ratios is small. As a result, the effect of cement amount on the strain value of light silt soil can be ignored within a limited range of cement contents. The strength of the cementation created between the EPS particles and the consolidated soil in the lightweight silt soil is quite robust under high cement content conditions. Moreover, when the stress level rises, a brittle fracture is more likely to occur.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) test was utilized in this study to investigate the strength and deformation characteristics of Light Weighted Soil (LWS) comprised of EPS beads of various sizes, silty soil, cement, and water. From the experimental results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- As the EPS particle size rises, the strength of LWS does not. EPS beads easily adhere to silty particles to create an elastic body in the case of 4mm EPS size because there are more pores between the particles and they are closer in size. The silty particles and EPS beads are in close contact due to their small diameter, thus increasing shear strength.
- The engineering features of EPS-silty blends, such as ductility and deformation, increase with high loads and EPS

size. When the EPS particle size approaches 6mm, the UCS results drop. The UCS of EPS-silt mixes with 4mm EPS size is greater than all the other groups for a given additive concentration, but their ductility is lower.

- The dome shape of LWS has confined stress-strain relation curves that differ from typically modified silt, indicating that LWS is structural soil. When stress is less than strength, very minor deformation occurs. However, the soil structure rapidly degrades and collapses when stress exceeds strength.
- The cost can be reduced by using higher EPS bead size. Strength and price drop as the EPS size increases. To save money, practical projects like wall retaining should employ EPS beads with a diameter of 4 to 6mm, while material prescription can be adjusted.

REFERENCES

- [1] W. Q. Dai, X. Chen, and H. Q. Zhang, "Experiment and numerical simulation of dynamic behavior for cohesive soils," *Journal of Jilin University*, vol. 38, pp. 831–836, 2008.
- [2] S. Yamada, Y. Nagasaka, and N. Nishida, "Foamed particle light-weight soil with sand," *Soils and Foundations*, vol. 37, pp. 25–30, 1989.
- [3] H. Gao, J. Liu, and H. Liu, "Geotechnical properties of EPS composite soil," *International Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 69–77, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.3328/IJGE.2011.05.01.69-77>.
- [4] A. Kan and R. Demirboga, "Effect of cement and EPS beads ratios on compressive strength and density of lightweight concrete," *Indian Journal of Engineering and Materials Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 158–162, Apr. 2007.
- [5] T. Hou and G.-L. Xu, "Influence law of EPS size on shear strength of light weight soil," *Yantu Gongcheng Xuebao/Chinese Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 33, pp. 1634–1641, Oct. 2011.
- [6] A. Deng and Y. Xiao, "Measuring and Modeling Proportion-Dependent Stress-Strain Behavior of EPS-Sand Mixture," *International Journal of Geomechanics*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 214–222, Dec. 2010, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GM.1943-5622.0000062](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GM.1943-5622.0000062).
- [7] Y. Feng, "Experimental research on the compressive strength influencing factors of expanded polystyrene sheet silt mixed lightweight soil material," *Materials Research Innovations*, vol. 19, no. sup10, pp. S10-64, Dec. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1179/1432891715Z.0000000002089>.
- [8] A. A. H. Bhutto, S. Zardari, G. S. Bhurgri, M. A. Zardari, R. Bhanbhro, and B. A. Memon, "Post Construction and Long Term Settlement of an Embankment Dam Computed with Two Constitutive Models," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4750–4754, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3070>.
- [9] Y. Feng, Y. Chao, and P. Zhang, "Meso-Structure Deformation Mechanism of EPS Silt Mixed Lightweight Soil Material under Cyclic Loading," *Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 237–243, Jul. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11204-020-09660-5>.
- [10] A. H. Bhutto, G. S. Bhurgri, S. Zardari, M. A. Zardari, R. Bhanbhro, and B. A. Memon, "Numerical Analysis of Rapid Drawdown of an Embankment Dam," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5496–5500, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3211>.
- [11] Y. Feng and Y. B. Pei, "Study on the Stress and Strain of EPS Silt Light-Weight Soil by Laboratory Test," *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, vol. 580–583, pp. 499–502, 2014, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.580-583.499>.
- [12] H. Liu, A. Deng, and J. Chu, "Effect of different mixing ratios of polystyrene pre-puff beads and cement on the mechanical behaviour of lightweight fill," *Geotextiles and Geomembranes*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 331–338, Dec. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geotexmem.2006.05.002>.
- [13] W. Lu, J. Wang, and Y. Zhang, "Strength Characteristics of Cement Treated and Expanded Polystyrene Mixed Lightweight of Waste Soil from the Construction Site of a Yangtze River Bridge in China," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2020, May 2020, Art. no. e3640510, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/3640510>.
- [14] S. M. Nawghare and J. N. Mandal, "Effectiveness of Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) Beads Size on Fly Ash Properties," *International Journal of Geosynthetics and Ground Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 1, Mar. 2020, Art. no. 6, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40891-020-0189-3>.
- [15] A. H. Padade, S. Dutta, M. B. Nadaf, B. Ram Rathan Lal, and J. N. Mandal, "Expanded Polystyrene (EPS) Geofoam Unit Cells with Fly Ash," in *Geo-Chicago*, Chicago, IL, USA, Aug. 2016, pp. 35–43, <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784480144.004>.
- [16] E. Vitale *et al.*, "Chemo-mechanical behaviour of lightweight cemented soils," *Acta Geotechnica*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 933–945, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11440-019-00797-8>.
- [17] X. Zhao, G. Zhao, J. Li, and P. Zhang, "Unconfined compressive strength property and its mechanism of construction waste stabilized lightweight soil," *Geomechanics and Engineering*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 307–314, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.12989/gae.2019.19.4.307>.
- [18] W. Lu, L. Miao, J. Zhang, Y. Zhang, and J. Li, "Characteristics of Deformation and Damping of Cement Treated and Expanded Polystyrene Mixed Lightweight Subgrade Fill under Cyclic Load," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 1, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 167, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9010167>.
- [19] A. J. Puppala, P. Ruttanaporamakul, and S. S. C. Congress, "Design and construction of lightweight EPS geofoam embedded geomaterial embankment system for control of settlements," *Geotextiles and Geomembranes*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 295–305, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geotexmem.2019.01.015>.
- [20] H. M. Gao, X. Li, Z. H. Wang, A. W. Stuedlein, and Y. Wang, "Dynamic shear modulus and damping of expanded polystyrene composite soils at low strains," *Geosynthetics International*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 436–450, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgein.19.00029>.
- [21] W. Lu, Y. Zhang, W. Liu, C. Liu, and H. Wang, "Evaluation of Geomembrane Effect Based on Mobilized Shear Stress due to Localized Sinking," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2019, May 2019, Art. no. e4942578, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4942578>.
- [22] M. V. Silveira, A. V. Calheiros, and M. D. T. Casagrande, "Applicability of the Expanded Polystyrene as a Soil Improvement Tool," *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 6, Jun. 2018, Art. no. 06018006, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0002276](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0002276).
- [23] E. O. Ogunsona, K. L. Dagnon, and N. A. D'Souza, "Multi-Fold Enhancement in Compressive Properties of Polystyrene Foam Using Pre-delaminated Stearate Functionalized Layer Double Hydroxides," *Polymers*, vol. 12, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 8, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12010008>.
- [24] X. Ni, Z. Wu, W. Zhang, K. Lu, Y. Ding, and S. Mao, "Energy Utilization of Building Insulation Waste Expanded Polystyrene: Pyrolysis Kinetic Estimation by a New Comprehensive Method," *Polymers*, vol. 12, no. 8, Aug. 2020, Art. no. 1744, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym12081744>.

An Anisotropic Diffusion Adaptive Filter for Image Denoising and Restoration Applied on Satellite Remote Sensing Images

A Case Study

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Abstract-This paper proposes an operating approach based on the anisotropic diffusion method to restore and denoise Satellite Remote Sensing Images (SRSIs). The contents of the approach are the motion by mean curvature to detect the noise direction for each degraded pixel and preserve the original edges of the image, and the gradient in the Gaussian kernel which restores the degraded pixel locally, assuring the estimation of its original value and saving the contrast of the image. The algorithm, concluded by our proposed system, treats noised SRSIs regardless of noise type, so better restoration is achieved. Experiments of the proposed system and of other approaches were conducted in MATLAB in order to demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed approach and its performance was confirmed through evaluation with PSNR and SSIM.

Keywords-image restoration; anisotropic diffusion; regularization; satellite remote sensing images

I. INTRODUCTION

Satellite Remote Sensing Images (SRSIs) are known for their fussy response or tendency to be corrupted due to multiple aspects of noise that might occur, such as time, feedbacks, accuracy, lighting, landforms, surface reflections, and reflection angles. Mathematically, image denoising is an ill-posed problem due to the fact that the added noise has divergent characteristics. Partial Differential Equations (PDE) in the anisotropic diffusion method provide a safe executive solution for image restoration, as a consequence of the multidirectional gradient through the noised (corrupted) pixel

neighborhoods, and assist an easy transpass from a system to another when we change the noise type.

The earlier works in the image denoising field, start with the Marr-Hildreth edge detector [1] by finding the zero-crossing of the second derivative D^2 of intensity. Author in [2] considers the image structure using the divergence of the image, focusing on blurred ones. Perona-Malik equation [3] has been applied many times. In [4], motion by mean curvature appears in the degenerate diffusion term, which diffuses the image in the orthogonal direction to its gradient and does not diffuse at all in the direction of the gradient. More recently, authors in [5], proposed an improved Empirical Mode Decomposition and Adaptive Center-Weighted Average (EMD-ACWA) denoising scheme by estimating the noise energies of all intrinsic mode functions, using an energy model, called noise-only model. It turns out that the empirical mode decomposition acts on fractional Gaussian noise as a dyadic filter bank. Authors in [6] worked on speckle noise elimination. The denoising research was applied to color images in [7].

There are many studies regarding SRSIs [8] using different techniques, such as as curvelet transform [9], wavelet packet transform [10], multifractal analysis[11], undecimated discrete wavelet transform [12], etc.

II. RECENT WORKS ABOUT SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING IMAGE DENOISING

Authors in [13] extended the existing learning-based methods in several aspects. Their work combines a realistic

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physical noise model of the camera with real noise samples from dark frames to generate realistic training data. They formulated a physical noise model for a Charge Coupled Device (CCD) sensor and presented a novel application of learning-based lowlight image denoising suitable for lunar surface images. They combined a physical noise model with real noise samples and scene selection based on three dimension (3D) ray tracing to generate training data and by conditioning the model on the camera's environmental metadata at the time of image capture.

Authors in [14] resort to the Plug-and-Play (PnP) framework to address the Hyperspectral Image (HSI) denoising task by proposing a PnPHSI (Plug-and-Play- Hyperspectral Images) denoising model with low-rank representation and a prior CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) denoiser. In the proposed PnP framework, the eigen-images are denoised by a DRUNet (Dilated-Residual U-NET) submodel. In [15], the enhanced Adaptive Generalized Gaussian Distribution (AGGD) and the improved AGGD threshold function enhanced the qualitative and quantitative results of TNN and optimization-based noise removal. The improved AGGD consists of two main parts. In the interval $[-t, t]$, the function is adaptive GGD (Generalized Gaussian Distribution), and behind the interval, it is a non-linear function.

III. THE PROPOSED METHOD FOR SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING IMAGES DENOISING

In this paper, we propose an Anisotropic Diffusion approach on the basis of PDE, containing motion by mean curvature, convolution product, Gaussian kernel, and time of processing term:

$$\begin{cases} I_t = c(t) \cdot |\nabla G_\sigma * I| \cdot |\nabla I| \cdot \text{div} \left(\frac{\nabla I}{|\nabla I|} \right) \\ I(0, x, y) = I_0(x, y) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where I_t is the enhanced image from the noised image I and $c(t) = 1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{4+t^2}}$ is the diffusion problem coefficient term

that helps to enhance the image contrast and keeps it from turning darker during the execution process. The motion by the mean curvature term is the degenerated diffusion term

$|\nabla I| \cdot \text{div} \left(\frac{\nabla I}{|\nabla I|} \right)$ which precises the noised pixel and noise

direction in its multidirectional neighboring, and $|\nabla G_\sigma * I|$ is the Gaussian kernel mask with σ standard deviation. For noised pixel restoration we used a $\sigma \times \sigma$ mask to redefine the value of the noised pixel from its neighboring pixels.

The numerical solution of the PDE in the earlier system, is found by the Finite Differences (FD) method [16], Simpsons improved method [16], and the convolution product [17, 18], where the image pixel is the step for the mesh required in the numerical treatment of the image, that means we will work locally for each pixel in the digital image. For the image

clarification sought during the image acquisition process, the time step is calculated as:

$$\tau = \frac{T}{N} \quad (2)$$

where T is the time range, N' the number of iterations, and $k=1..T$ the time index.

Fig. 1. The image regularization process.

IV. PROBLEM STABILITY

In this section, the following theorem is used to prove the stability of the proposed method [19].

Theorem: Let $L.U = f$ be the problem and $L.U^{(h)} = f^{(h)}$ its perturbed version. The Euler explicit schema of the problem $L.U = f$ is stable if $\exists \delta > 0; \exists h_0 > 0 \forall h < h_0, \forall \delta f^{(h)} \in F_h$ such that $L.U^{(h)} = f^{(h)} + \delta f^{(h)}$ accepts a unique solution $Z^{(h)} \in U_h$. Furthermore: $\|Z^{(h)} - U^{(h)}\|_{U_h} \leq \alpha \|f^{(h)}\|_{F_h}$, where α is a constant, $Z^{(h)}$ the approximated solution, U_h the approximated solution space, $f^{(h)}$ the approximated function, and F_h the approximated function space.

We apply the previous theorem on our problem, when the subset Ω is associated with the norm sup.

In $I_t = \frac{\partial I}{\partial t}$ the operator $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}$ is linear, so we prove that $\|I^{(h)}\|_{\Omega_h} \leq \alpha \|f^{(h)}\|_{\Omega_h}$, where $I_t = \frac{I(t+1,x,y) - I(t,x,y)}{\tau}$, I is the image, and $I_t = f(k, i, j)$, so we have $\frac{I(k+1,i,j) - I(k,i,j)}{\tau} = f(k, i, j)$. Then we have:

$$I(k+1, i, j) = I(k, i, j) + \tau \cdot f(k, i, j)$$

$$|I_{ij}^{k+1}| = |I_{ij}^k + \tau \cdot f_{ij}^k|$$

$$\max_{i,j} |I_{ij}^k| \leq \max_{i,j} |I_{ij}^{k-1}| + \tau \cdot \max_{i,j} |f_{ij}^k|$$

$$\max_{i,j} |I_{ij}^1| \leq \max_{i,j} |I_{ij}^0| + \tau \cdot \max_{i,j} |f_{ij}^k|$$

By adding side by side, we get:

$$\max_{i,j} |I_{ij}^k| \leq \max_{i,j} |I_{ij}^0| + n.\tau. \max_{i,j} |f_{ij}^k|$$

$$\|I^{(h)}\|_{\Omega_h} \leq \alpha \|f^{(h)}\|_{\Omega_h}$$

where the schema is stable for $\alpha = 1+T$.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to estimate the efficiency of the proposed image restoration model, we applied it on different types of noise (salt and pepper, Gaussian, speckle). We carried out the algorithm simulations using a Windows 32 bit PC powered by an Intel 2.6GHz processor with 2GB RAM. The experiments were performed in MATLAB R2017 [20, 21] due to its image processing toolbox, with time intervals took between $\tau=01s$ and $\tau=60s$ according to the image size and the number for iterations, noting that :

- PSNR: Peak Signal to Noise Ratio. It gives a noise free $m \times n$ monochrome for image I and its noisy approximation.
- SSIM: Structure Similarity Index metric. It is a method for predicting the perceived quality of measuring the similarity between two images, usually an original and a restored image.

The Euler Explicit schema extracted from the discretization of the system (1) concludes the algorithm programmed in MATLAB and gives the process to the noised image restoration. The manipulation gets into the following steps:

- Step 1: Program the convolution product based on the Gaussian kernel as a $\sigma \times \sigma$ mask with σ standard deviation and scale parameter.
- Step 2: Verify the image dimension that should be $\dim(I)=2$. Then convert the image grayscale with single values for pixels.
- Step 3: Filter the image by motion by mean curvature to detect degraded pixels.
- Step 4: Determine time step τ , number of iterations K , and standard deviation σ .
- Step 5: Start a loop from $k=1$ to $k=K$ restoring the degraded pixels and enhancing the image, calculating PSNR and SSIM to measure the improvement from the achieved results.

Tables II-IV demonstrate the manipulation results for different types of noise applied on the images (Figures 1-5) in Table I. The iteration number of the denoising process is between 10 and 20 for remarkable enhancement with high PSNR, whilst Table V describes a comparison with the results obtained by the works mentioned above (see Section II) and the obtained results by the proposed Anisotropic Diffusion method where there is a round-trip in PSNR and the clarity of images.

TABLE I. IMAGE DESCRIPTION

		Image size	Image name
Figure 1		1.28 mega	Map of Brussels view satellite-Belgium
Figure 2		520 ko	Band8 crop chip
Figure 3		812 ko	Shannon Airplane Irlande
Figure 4		925 ko	Algerian Sahara
Figure 5		1.02 mega	IRLANDE

TABLE II. REDUCED SALT AND PEPPER NOISE FOR $D=0.1, K=10$

Original image	Noised image	Restored image	PSNR	SSIM
	29.3953	0.5774		
	27.4245	0.8199		
	30.2833	0.7961		
	27.6886	0.8725		
	26.3484	0.8521		

TABLE III. REDUCED GAUSSIAN NOISE $\sigma = 0.1, K=10$

Original image	Noised image	Restored image	PSNR	SSIM
	31.7707	0.5347		
	28.9869	0.6346		
	28.7726	0.5922		
	27.8323	0.7509		
	29.4133	0.6985		

TABLE IV. REDUCED SPECKLE NOISE $\sigma = 0.1, K = 20$

Original image	Noised image	Restored image	PSNR	SSIM
	30.2091	0.5137		
	24.1765	0.6187		
	25.2453	0.5092		
	27.8884	0.4084		
	25.4414	0.6341		

The algorithm outperforms the other approaches regarding the regularization of the noised image for Gaussian and speckle noise. It also did not turn the image darker due to the gradient, as can be also seen in the comparison part.

VI. CONCLUSION

Image denoising and enhancement in order to improve image quality for more exact information extracting is a trending research topic. Especially the capturing of Satellite Remote Sensing Images has the obstacle of the long distance barrier between objects and sensors, so captured images are more liable for noise like environment effects, light concentration and camera sharpness. The partial differential equation systems give a reliable point of view that helps this development, based on the multidirectional gradient that allows noise detection in several directions independently and locally for better regularization, unlike the total variation method which treats the noised image globally.

TABLE V. COMPARISON RESULTS WITH RECENT WORKS

	Other works				Proposed	
	Original image	Noised image	Restored image	PSNR	Restored image	PSNR
[13]		38.58				
[14]		40.76				
[15]		35.79				

REFERENCES

[1] D. Marr and E. Hildreth, "Theory of edge detection," *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London, Series B. Biological Sciences*, vol. 207, no. 1167, <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.1980.0020>.

[2] J. J. Koenderink, "The structure of images," *Biological Cybernetics*, vol. 50, pp. 363–370, 1984.

[3] P. Perona and J. Malik, "Scale-space and edge detection using anisotropic diffusion," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 629–639, Jul. 1990, <https://doi.org/10.1109/34.56205>.

[4] L. Alvarez, P.-L. Lions, and J.-M. Morel, "Image Selective Smoothing and Edge Detection by Nonlinear Diffusion. II," *SIAM Journal on numerical analysis*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 845–866, Jun. 1992, <https://doi.org/10.1137/0729052>.

[5] I. Tellala, N. Amardjia, and A. Kesmia, "A Modified EMD-ACWA Denoising Scheme using a Noise-only Model," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 5470–5476, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3406>.

[6] N. Diffellah, R. Hamdini, and T. Bekkouche, "Removal of Multiplicative Gamma Noise from Images via SRAD Model Amelioration," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7917–7921, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4527>.

[7] M. V. Sarode and P. R. Deshmukh, "Image Sequence Denoising with Motion Estimation in Color Image Sequences," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 139–143, Dec. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.54>.

[8] J. Gao, *Digital Analysis of Remotely Sensed Imagery*, 1st ed. McGraw Hill, 2009.

[9] F. Nencini, A. Garzelli, S. Baronti, and L. Alparone, "Remote sensing image fusion using the curvelet transform," *Information Fusion*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 143–156, Apr. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2006.02.001>.

[10] J. Kang and W. Zhang, "Quickbird Remote Sensing Image Denoising Using Wavelet Packet Transform," in *2008 Second International Symposium on Intelligent Information Technology Application*, Shanghai, China, Sep. 2008, vol. 3, pp. 315–318, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IITA.2008.269>.

[11] M.-G. Hu, J.-F. Wang, and Y. Ge, "Super-Resolution Reconstruction of Remote Sensing Images Using Multifractional Analysis," *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 9, no. 11, pp. 8669–8683, 2009, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s91108669>.

[12] W. Wang and Y. Li, "Bayesian Denoising for Remote Sensing Image Based on Undecimated Discrete Wavelet Transform," in *2009 International Conference on Information Engineering and Computer Science*, Wuhan, China, Sep. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIECS.2009.5365574>.

[13] B. Moseley, V. Bickel, I. G. López-Francos, and L. Rana, "Extreme Low-Light Environment-Driven Image Denoising over Permanently Shadowed Lunar Regions with a Physical Noise Model," in *2021 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*

- (CVPR), Nashville, TN, USA, Jun. 2021, pp. 6313–6323, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR46437.2021.00625>.
- [14] H. Sun, M. Liu, K. Zheng, D. Yang, J. Li, and L. Gao, "Hyperspectral Image Denoising via Low-Rank Representation and CNN Denoiser," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 15, pp. 716–728, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSTARS.2021.3138564>.
- [15] N. A. Golilarz, H. Gao, S. Pirasteh, M. Yazdi, J. Zhou, and Y. Fu, "Satellite Multispectral and Hyperspectral Image De-Noising with Enhanced Adaptive Generalized Gaussian Distribution Threshold in the Wavelet Domain," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 13, no. 1, Jan. 2021, Art. No. 101, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13010101>.
- [16] V. S. Riabenki and S. K. Godounov, *Theory of Difference Schemes: An Introduction*. Algeria: University Publication Office, 1987.
- [17] A. Boucher, *Image Processing - Spatial Convolution*. Montreal, QC, Canada: University of Montreal, 2016.
- [18] V. Choqueuse, *Convolution Product - Principle and Propieties*. 2016.
- [19] Z. Li, Z. Qiao, and T. Tang, *Numerical Solution of Differential Equations*. Cambridge University Press, 2017.
- [20] J. C. Russ, *The Image Processing Cookbook*, 4th ed. CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform, 2017.
- [21] "MathWorks - Makers of MATLAB and Simulink - MATLAB & Simulink," *Mathworks*. <https://www.mathworks.com/>.

Push-over Analysis of Optimized Steel Frames

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Abstract-The traditional optimization methods are effective when dealing with small-scale problems. However, for large-scale problems, these methods fail to obtain optimal solutions, and after a long operation, several solutions are obtained. New methods, known as metaheuristics, have provided new implementations to be used in many applications. They have enabled the resolution of many complex industrial and technical problems. They have the merits of avoiding local optima and finding optimal solutions, due to their ease of understanding, flexibility, adaptation simplicity, and ability to get out of local optima traps. This article aims to model a 2D metal frame gantry with two spans and two levels already optimized by ROBOT Millennium software in order to show the effect of structural optimization in the pre-design phase and of obtaining its non-linear behavior by the pushover method. Three optimal dimensional configurations of this gantry were taken into account and the best was chosen, one which satisfied an adequate behavior in the non-linear domain while respecting the CM66 and Eurocode3 regulations.

Keywords-optimization; vulnerability; push-over method; non-linear behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing tendency to analyze structures using probabilistic information on loads, geometry, material properties, and boundary conditions. Design notes were prepared manually and as new and complex requirements and demands arose, much more urgent actions were taken to meet these requirements. Progress has been made in the construction technology sector, especially in the search for productivity gains, which has led to two main thrusts [1]:

- Industrialization, therefore prefabrication of building elements, with the verification of the validity of an object previously designed and checking its operation afterwards.

- The creation of the computer, i.e. an efficient and fast tool to automate the calculation and the verification of construction elements.

Optimization algorithms are written to minimize a function (to maximize a function, it will be simple to minimize its opposite). Optimization is a method that uses mathematics and computer science, seeking to model, analyze, and solve analytically or numerically the problems of determining which solution(s) satisfy a quantitative objective while respecting possible restraints. The quality of the results and predictions depends on the relevance of the model and the efficiency of the used algorithm. Traditional and heuristic optimization algorithms have been widely used to find the global optimum in a problem or cost function. The reason may be their reliable approaches to solve difficult optimization problems. Many metaheuristic algorithms have been proposed during the recent years, such as the Ant Lion optimizer [2], the Artificial Algae algorithm [3], the Binary Bat algorithm [4], the Black Hole algorithm [5], the Binary Cat swarm optimization [6], the Firefly algorithm [7], the Fish Swarm algorithm [8], and the Grey Wolf optimizer [9]. Some examples of the first generations of these algorithms are the genetic algorithm [10], genetic programming [11], evolutionary programming [5], Tabu search [12], and simulated annealing [13]. These are metaheuristic algorithms that are also classified into three sections [14, 15], which are: evolutionary algorithms, physics-based algorithms, and intelligent algorithms.

The traditional approach to the optimization of steel structures is essentially based on minimizing the weight of the structure while taking into account the reliability and/or vulnerability which is calculated using mathematical and numerical methods such as the Finite Element Method (FEM) to obtain a detailed structural response.

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Terki Hassaine et al.: Push-over Analysis of Optimized Steel Frames

The aim of this work is to show the effect of structural optimization in the pre-design phase, using ROBOT Millennium software, on the final response of the non-linear behavior of a steel portal frame through a comparative study of three different configurations. We will model a two-span, two-level portal frame in a simple steel frame and then proceed to determine its shear forces and bending moments using the SAP2000 software while respecting the CM66 and EUROCODE 3 codes. Finally, we try to determine the vulnerability of this gantry frame by the non-linear static pushover method.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Optimization Problems and Criteria

Optimization problems can be classified as single-objective or multi-objective, depending on the number of objective functions [16-17]. In Civil Engineering, building optimization studies often use up to 2 objective functions [18], with the exception of 3-objective functional optimization in different techniques where the objective function [19] can be linear or non-linear, convex or non-convex, unimodal or multimodal, differentiable or not, continuous or discontinuous, expensive or unaffordable in terms of computing. This results in heuristic and meta-heuristic optimization methods, simulation-based optimization, and surrogate-based optimization [20-21].

Most real-world optimization problems are described with several, often conflicting, objectives or criteria that need to be optimized simultaneously [22]. For the steel frame building design optimization problem, the variables are the components of the structure, since the variation of their characteristics directly influences the global production cost criterion chosen as the optimization objective in this research [23]. A steel frame is the result of the assembly of different components. This assembly must be designed to ensure that the resulting structure is suitable for the intended use. The early design phase, prior to any detailed calculation, concretely implies a process of analysis and verifications that can be adopted at the "maximum" according to the class of the cross-sections (Eurocode3). A comparative study will be carried out on a two-dimensional steel portal frame using the profiles available on the Algerian market, namely IPE, IPN, HEA, and HEB in order to have optimal dimensioning in the plastic domain.

B. Optimization Module in ROBOT Millennium

In order to facilitate the work, the use of ROBOT Millennium is proposed, which has a vast set of tools simplifying the study of structures. In ROBOT Millennium, the notion of objects and the creation of the model of the structure are carried out with typical construction objects: beams, columns, bracing, floors, and walls. During the study stage, the elements of the structure take on specific attributes of their own (including regulatory attributes), thus, at the model definition stage, all the regulatory parameters of the structure are defined, which allows the regulatory analysis to be carried out immediately after the static calculations. The same applies to the nodes. The notion of nodes has lost its traditional meaning since they are automatically defined during the creation of the various objects. The available optimization criteria are: weight, maximum and minimum section height, minimum flange

thickness, and minimum web thickness. The option Calculations for the entire profile family is available. The entire accessible profile database will be scanned to find the optimal profile. The sizing module is used to find the optimal profile in terms of stress. For example, we see that ROBOT recommends an IPE 240 that is identical to our initial choice (a first estimate). However, the verification of the IPE 240 in deflection shows that the profile is insufficient. Indeed, the deflection is the dimensioning element in certain structures, so it would be logical to make dimensioning in deflection. Unfortunately, automatic dimensioning in deflection is impossible. To justify this observation, we must explain how sizing works.

III. CASE STUDY

The main objective of this project was to design a building structure in CM66. However, the achievement of this objective was done in several steps. First, it was necessary to:

- Determine the load applied to the structure.
- Determine the different types of possible structures.
- Carry out the design and finally choose the most advantageous design in relation to the client's needs.

A. Description of the Structure

The project is located in Oran city, that is located in an average seismic activity zone (Zone II-a) according to the Algerian earthquake code RPA99, in zone B for snow density, and zone I for wind force according to the RNV2013. Depending on the plan view, the dimensions of the structure are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. DIMENSIONS OF THE STRUCTURE

Total length	Total width	Height from the ground level	Height of the ground floor	Height of the floors	Total height of the building
30.64m	13.4m	2.80m	3.80m	3.80m	57m

The light roof is made of TN 40 industrialized ribbed sheet metal, transoms, purlins, and bracing. The purlins and trusses are made of IPE profiles. The columns are made of HEA profiles, the distance between two purlins is 1.3m, and the external masonry walls have 6m of high. The cladding is made of the same type of sheet metal as the TN 40 roof. The cladding rails are fixed to posts or possibly to posts. The loads to the building are transmitted to the ground through the insulated reinforced concrete footings. The value of the permissible soil stress is 2.5 bars. The characteristics of reinforced concrete in the foundations are: Strength of the concrete $f_{c28} = 25$ MPa, elasticity modulus of concrete $E_c = 32164$ MPa, safety factor of concrete $\gamma_c = 1.5$, safety factor of steel $\gamma_s = 1.15$, and yield steel stress $F_c = 400$ MPa. The steel elements are made with steel grade S235, $f_y = 2350$ daN/cm². The modulus of elasticity of the steel is $E = 2100000$ daN/cm². The connections are made by means of ordinary and high strength welds and bolts.

A calculation with ROBOT software:

- Defines a structure made up of portal frames (columns + truss) in accordance with the project data. The wind actions are Calculate
- Creates the load combinations
- Analyzes the structure and dimensions of the different elements of the structure (purlins, cladding rails, truss elements, columns, and posts).
- Calculates the connections (truss elements, truss-post, and post foot).

Subsequently, the gantry was analyzed using Etabs software to apply the pushover method and see the vulnerability of the gantry. The type of structure is a planar portal frame with a total mass of 594.79kg. Figure 1 shows the studding gantry in CM with the optimized metallic profiles. However, three configurations were selected after the first step of the present study, which is the optimization of the structure with different profile sections available in the Algerian market, especially HEA, HEB, IPE, and IPN profiles.

Fig. 1. The metal frame of the case study.

B. Deformation of the Gantry

Each variant was subjected to nonlinear analysis according to the pushover method. Figure 2 shows the deformation form and the plastic hinges of the gantry with the optimized metallic profiles for all three configurations.

Fig. 2. Shape deformation with plastic hinges.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we present and compare the results. We illustrate and compare the results of two frames of the same number of stories according to the period, base shear, maximum displacement, and stiffness.

A. First Variant (Columns : HEB180, Beams: HEA240)

Table II represents the distribution of plastic hinges in the metallic gantry according to the first configuration. From Table II, we can see that 80% of the plastic hinges are in the first segment (A-IO), 20% in the second segment (IO-LS), 0% in the 3rd segment (LS-CP), and 0% in the last segment, which corresponds to failure or collapse. Figure 3 shows the evolution of the capacity curve and the performance parameters of the studied structure according to the first configuration. The capacity curve (Figure 3(a)) is defined by the elastic state corresponding to an elastic shear force of $V_y = 58.37\text{kN}$ for an elastic displacement of $d_y = 30.5\text{mm}$ and initial stiffness $K_0 = 1913.91\text{KNm}$ which represents the product of the elastic shear force and the elastic displacement. The ultimate limit state corresponding to the shear force is $V_u = 92.70\text{kN}$. From Figure 3(b) and Table II, it can be said that the performance point, which represents the intersection of the response spectrum curve with the capacity curve, is at the point that connects the shear force of 342.30kN with the displacement of 18.7mm .

Fig. 3. Response of the nonlinear analysis of the first variant. (a) Capacity curve, (b) performance parameters.

TABLE II. BASE SHEAR, MAX DISPLACEMENT, AND STIFFNESS OF THE FIRST VARIANT OF THE TWO-STOREY FRAME

Step	Monitored displacement (mm)	Base force (kN)	A-B	B-C	C-D	D-E	>E	A-IO	IO-LS	LS-CP	>CP	Total
0	0.1	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
1	30.5	58.37	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
2	60.9	116.74	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
3	91.3	175.12	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
4	121.7	233.49	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
5	152.1	291.87	19	1	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
6	172.9	324.75	18	2	0	0	0	19	1	0	0	20
7	189	344.92	17	3	0	0	0	19	1	0	0	20
8	240.7	380.51	16	4	0	0	0	17	3	0	0	20
9	298.1	409.22	15	5	0	0	0	16	4	0	0	20
10	304.1	411.71	15	5	0	0	0	16	4	0	0	20

TABLE III. BASE SHEAR, MAX DISPLACEMENT, AND STIFFNESS OF THE SECOND VARIANT OF THE TWO-STOREY FRAME

Step	Monitored displacement (mm)	Base force (kN)	A-B	B-C	C-D	D-E	>E	A-IO	IO-LS	LS-CP	>CP	Total
0	0.3	0	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
1	30.7	32.50	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
2	61.1	65.00	20	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
3	64.6	68.71	19	1	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
4	113.6	107.05	17	3	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
5	144	128.05	17	3	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
6	183.5	151.65	16	4	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
7	213.9	168.96	16	4	0	0	0	18	2	0	0	20
8	244.3	186.27	16	4	0	0	0	18	2	0	0	20
9	274.7	203.58	16	4	0	0	0	17	3	0	0	20
10	304.3	219.88	15	5	0	0	0	16	4	0	0	20

TABLE IV. BASE SHEAR, MAX DISPLACEMENT, AND STIFFNESS OF THE THIRD VARIANT OF THE TWO-STOREY FRAME

Step	Monitored displacement (mm)	Base force (kN)	A-B	B-C	C-D	D-E	>E	A-IO	IO-LS	LS-CP	>CP	Total
0	0.4	0	16	4	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
1	30.8	13.74	16	4	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
2	51.9	23.31	15	5	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
3	82.3	33.85	15	5	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
4	112.7	44.39	15	5	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
5	143.1	54.93	15	5	0	0	0	20	0	0	0	20
6	182.6	66.94	14	6	0	0	0	19	1	0	0	20
7	213	75.80	14	6	0	0	0	17	3	0	0	20
8	254	86.37	13	7	0	0	0	17	3	0	0	20
9	284.4	93.85	13	7	0	0	0	16	4	0	0	20
10	304.4	98.76	12	8	0	0	0	16	4	0	0	20

B. Second Variant (Columns : HEB180, Beams: IPE 200)

Table III represents the distribution of the plastic hinges in the metallic gantry. We can see that 80% of the plastic hinges are in the first segment (A-IO), 20% in the second segment (IO-LS), 0% in the 3rd segment (LS-CP), and 0% in the last segment, which corresponds to failure or collapse. Figure 4 shows the evolution of the capacity curve and the performance parameters of the studied structure according to the second configuration. The capacity curve (Figure 4(a)) is defined by the elastic state corresponding to an elastic shear force of $V_y = 32.50\text{kN}$ for an elastic displacement of $d_y = 30.7\text{mm}$ and initial stiffness $K_0 = 1058.63\text{kNm}$ which represents the product of the elastic shear force and the elastic displacement. The ultimate limit state corresponding to the shear force is

$V_u = 219.88\text{kN}$. From Table III and Figure 4(b), it can be said that the performance point, which represents the intersection of the response spectrum curve with the capacity curve, is at the point that connects the shear force of 0.00kN with the displacement of 0.0m . So, the performance point is not found.

C. Third Variant (Columns : HEB140, Beams: IPE180)

Table IV represents the distribution of plastic hinges in the metallic gantry. From Table IV, we can see that 80% of the plastic hinges are in the first segment (A-IO), 20% in the second segment (IO-LS), 0% in the 3rd segment (LS-CP), and 0% in the last segment, which corresponds to failure or collapse. Figure 5 shows the evolution of the capacity curve and the performance parameters of the studied structure according to the third configuration.

Fig. 4. Response of the nonlinear analysis of the second variant. (a) Capacity curve, (b) performance parameters.

Fig. 5. Response of the nonlinear analysis of the third variant. (a) Capacity curve, (b) performance parameters.

The capacity curve (Figure 5(a)) is defined by the elastic state corresponding to the elastic shear force of $V_y = 13.74\text{kN}$ for an elastic displacement of $d_y = 30.8\text{mm}$ and initial stiffness $K_0 = 446.10\text{kNm}$ which represents the product of the elastic shear force and the elastic displacement. The ultimate limit state corresponding to the shear force is $V_u = 98.77\text{kN}$. From Table IV and Figure 5(b), it can be said that the performance point, which represents the intersection of the response spectrum curve with the capacity curve, is at the point that connects the shear force of 0.00 kN for the displacement of 0.0m . So, the performance point is not found.

D. Comparison between the Results of the Treated Variants

After analyzing each model separately, the results obtained are compared according to the capacity curve and the following criteria: elastic shear force, displacement, initial stiffness, and ultimate shear force as detailed in Table V. Regarding to the elastic shear force, it can be easily noticed that variant 1 presents the highest value compared to the other two, mainly due to the geometrical characteristics of the profiles used in this variant. In the same context, variant 1, gives the lowest elastic displacement. It also presents the highest initial stiffness and ultimate shear force.

It can be said that the columns have good resistance to the applied loads and the under dimensioning of these elements can lead to low resistance.

TABLE V. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE TREATED VARIANTS

Variant	1	2	3
Elastic shear force V_y (kN)	58.37	32.50	13.74
Elastic displacement d_y (m)	0.0305	0.0307	0.0308
Initial stiffness K_0 (kN/m)	1913.91	1058.63	446.10
Ultimate shear force V_u (kN)	92.70	219.88	98.77

On the other hand, it can be said that variant 1 has the highest weight among the considered variants. This has a considerable influence on the cost of the structure. However, among the three different optimized configurations, the first variant with (HEB180 for columns and HEA240 for beams) shows the best-optimized configuration in ROBOT compared to the other two optimized configurations.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis showed that the selected models and the interpretation of the results, allow us to conclude that the choice of the profiles is appropriate, either for the columns and/or for the crossbeams, which ensure an adequate resistance, and add in the weight of the structure. The latter is one of the major criteria among the main optimization parameters. It should be noted that many questions are still open in the field of behavior of steel frames, in particular questions related to the dependence of the response on the non-linear domain.

Finding optimal solutions to engineering problems is always a difficult task. Due to the many conditions and limitations, structural engineers usually have to proceed and repeat through trial and error, in search of better design solutions in terms of improved structural performance and cost reduction.

In this paper, nonlinear analysis of a 2D steel frame was conducted and the results were compared for three different optimized configurations. The results obtained showed that in order to properly design a metallic gantry frame that meets the regulatory requirements with a light structure and minimum cost, it is necessary to introduce several parameters in the form of an algorithm that allows us to arrive at the most appropriate profiles in a simple way. For this reason, we can say that the use of genetic algorithms in this case is adequate. They are beneficial for tackling problems that are considered difficult or that require a lot of computation time with a classical algorithmic approach. It is also easy to show that when using genetic algorithms, one can improve the solution speed and make it possible to solve something in adequate time that used to be very time consuming, given the complexity of the data of physical problems.

Future work will focus on three-dimensional models to properly analyze this type of steel structure.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. I. E. Terki Hassaine, S. M. Bourdim, A. Benanane, and Y. Zelmat, "Optimization of Metallic Structures by Applying Genetic Algorithm," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Automation Innovation in Construction (CIAC-2019)*, Leiria, Portugal, 2019, pp. 341–348, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-35533-3_41.
- [2] S. Mirjalili, "The Ant Lion Optimizer," *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 83, pp. 80–98, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2015.01.010>.
- [3] S. A. Uymaz, G. Tezel, and E. Yel, "Artificial Algae Algorithm (aaa) for Nonlinear Global Optimization," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 31, pp. 153–171, Jun. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2015.03.003>.
- [4] D. Behrens, T. Schoormann, and R. Knackstedt, "Developing an Algorithm to Consider Multiple Demand Response Objectives," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2621–2626, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1819>.
- [5] A. Hatamlou, "Black hole: A new heuristic optimization approach for data clustering," *Information Sciences*, vol. 222, pp. 175–184, Feb. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2012.08.023>.
- [6] B. Crawford *et al.*, "A Binary Cat Swarm Optimization Algorithm for the Non-Unicost Set Covering Problem," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2015, Jul. 2015, Art. no. e578541, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/578541>.
- [7] J. R. Koza, "Genetically breeding populations of computer programs to solve problems in artificial intelligence," in *[1990] Proceedings of the 2nd International IEEE Conference on Tools for Artificial Intelligence*, Herndon, VA, USA, Aug. 1990, pp. 819–827, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAI.1990.130444>.
- [8] G. A. Alshammari, F. A. Alshammari, T. Guesmi, B. M. Alshammari, A. S. Alshammari, and N. A. Alshammari, "A New Particle Swarm Optimization Based Strategy for the Economic Emission Dispatch Problem Including Wind Energy Sources," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7585–7590, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4279>.
- [9] S. Mirjalili, S. M. Mirjalili, and A. Lewis, "Grey Wolf Optimizer," *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 69, pp. 46–61, Mar. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2013.12.007>.
- [10] S. Carbas and O. Tunca, "Brain Storm Optimization for Design of 2D Steel Frame Structures," in *1st International Conference on Engineering and Applied Natural Sciences*, Konya, Turkey, May 2022, pp. 1023–1029.
- [11] J. Fulcher, "Computational Intelligence: An Introduction," in *Computational Intelligence: A Compendium*, J. Fulcher and L. C. Jain, Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, 2008, pp. 3–78.
- [12] S. Palizi and A. Saedi Daryan, "Plastic Analysis of Braced Frames by Application of Metaheuristic Optimization Algorithms," *International Journal of Steel Structures*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 1135–1150, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13296-020-00347-z>.
- [13] A. Saedi Daryan and S. Palizi, "New Plastic Analysis Procedure for Collapse Prediction of Braced Frames by Means of Genetic Algorithm," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 146, no. 1, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 04019168, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ST.1943-541X.0002462](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ST.1943-541X.0002462).
- [14] C. Hopfe, M. Emmerich, R. Marijt, and J. Hensen, "Robust multi-criteria design optimization in building design," presented at the Proceedings of the 1st IBPSA-England Conference Building Simulation and Optimization, Loughborough, UK, Sep. 2012, pp. 118–125.
- [15] B. Ghogh, S. Sharifian, and H. Mohammadzade, "Tree-Based Optimization: A Meta-Algorithm for Metaheuristic Optimization," *arXiv*, Sep. 24, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1809.09284>.
- [16] J. Chun *et al.*, "EzTaxon: a web-based tool for the identification of prokaryotes based on 16S ribosomal RNA gene sequences," *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, vol. 57, no. 10, pp. 2259–2261, <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijs.0.64915-0>.
- [17] N. L. Tran and T. H. Nguyen, "Reliability Assessment of Steel Plane Frame's Buckling Strength Considering Semi-rigid Connections," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5099–5103, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3231>.
- [18] F. P. Chantrelle, H. Lahmidi, W. Keilholz, M. E. Mankibi, and P. Michel, "Development of a multicriteria tool for optimizing the renovation of buildings," *Applied Energy*, vol. 88, no. 4, pp. 1386–1394, Apr. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.10.002>.
- [19] B. Eisenhower, Z. O'Neill, S. Narayanan, V. A. Fonoberov, and I. Mezić, "A methodology for meta-model based optimization in building energy models," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 47, pp. 292–301, Apr. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2011.12.001>.
- [20] A. Torres, B. Mahmoudi, A. J. Darras, A. Imanpour, and R. G. Driver, "Achieving an Optimized Solution for Structural Design of Single-Storey Steel Buildings Using Generative Design Methodology," in *Proceedings of the Canadian Society of Civil Engineering Annual Conference 2021*, Singapore, 2021, pp. 301–312, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-0656-5_25.
- [21] R. Roy, S. Hinduja, and R. Teti, "Recent advances in engineering design optimisation: Challenges and future trends," *CIRP Annals*, vol. 57, no. 2, pp. 697–715, Jan. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2008.09.007>.
- [22] M. Hamdy, A. Hasan, and K. Siren, "Impact of adaptive thermal comfort criteria on building energy use and cooling equipment size using a multi-objective optimization scheme," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 43, no. 9, pp. 2055–2067, Sep. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2011.04.006>.
- [23] H. A. M. Yazdi and N. H. R. Sulong, "Optimization of Off-Centre Bracing System Using Genetic Algorithm," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 1435–1441, Oct. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2011.03.017>.

Performance Assessment of Traditional Software Development Methodologies and DevOps Automation Culture

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Abstract-Successful implementations of Software Development Methodologies significantly improve software efficiency, collaboration and security. Most companies are moving away from traditional development methodologies towards DevOps for faster and better software delivery. DevOps, which is a primary need of the IT industry, brings development and operation teams together to overcome communication gaps responsible for software failures. It relies on different sets of automation tools to robotize the tasks of software development from continuous integration, to testing, delivery, and deployment. The existence of several automation tools in each development phase raises the need for an integrated set of tools to reduce development time. For this purpose, we used the DevOps-based hybrid model Integrated Tool Chain (ITC), along with three sample java-based projects or code repositories to quantify the results. This paper evaluates and compares measurement metrics of java projects using traditional development methodologies and DevOps, and the results are shown in tabular and graphical format. The latest Google and Stack Overflow Trends have also been included to retrieve the best performer development methodology. This comparative and evaluative performance analysis will be beneficial to young researchers that study the metrics of software development, while also they will be introduced to the automotive environment of DevOps, the latest emerging buzzword in software development.

Keywords-automation; automation tools; DevOps; integrated tool chain; software development

I. INTRODUCTION

Software engineering is a branch of software design through the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), which consists of several development phases, from gathering requirements and thorough analysis, to design, coding, testing, deployment/delivery, and maintenance. Software development has introduced various methodologies from traditional and agile to the most recent DevOps culture. Traditional and agile development methods include models like waterfall, iterative, evolutionary, spiral, prototype, V Model, Scrum, XP RAD, etc. The availability of multiple models necessitates their careful selection for successful and quality software delivery. As

development models under traditional methodologies struggled with many defects responsible for late software delivery and budget overruns, fast and successful development was one of the major challenges for traditional development models. Agile methods provided better solutions for quick releases with small sprint sizes as they introduced flexibility into their methods, but still lacked continuity in development and operations, which is where DevOps comes in. DevOps, the industry's common term for development, is based on five software development continuums, i.e. continuous integration, continuous testing, continuous delivery, continuous development, and continuous monitoring. The continuity in the environment of DevOps is achieved through different sets of automation tools employed at each and every phase of software development. DevOps works on the principles of an infinite continuous cycle that starts from continuous integration of code repositories and continues until the monitoring stage of the software development to deliver quality successfully.

The current research quantitatively evaluates the performance of different software development methodologies, including DevOps, based on various software performance metrics. For the application of these metrics and to obtain quantitative results, three sample code repositories or java-based projects have been taken into consideration. This paper also considers our proposed [1] and implemented [2] DevOps-based hybrid model of automation Integrated Tool Chain (ITC). The proposed and implemented ITC model demands automation tools in each phase of software development. As there are various automation tools in each phase of software development, prior selection of automation tools will not only reduce development time but also ensure delivery within budget and quality. This study examines the proposed and verified ITC [2] for DevOps implementation. The result of traditional methodologies and DevOps performance evaluation based on various software metrics validate the quality of the delivered product and also helps in recovering the best performing software development methodology. The outcome of our study will be useful for young researchers/students to understand the course of action of DevOps and its automation

tools. It will also be important for software developers to choose the best execution tools from the various automation tool sets available.

SDLC contains detailed edits of the various steps or processes necessary to configure the software. It covers many methodologies such as traditional and agile methodologies and now DevOps, while these methodologies cover various models. DevOps, on the other hand, includes a set of different automation tools to achieve the goal of competitiveness in the era of digital transformation and to increase the speed of adaptation or reaction to changing software requirements [3]. DevOps, with its principles of continuity, helps companies survive in this competitive world. The main focus of the current paper is to describe and compare DevOps with traditional and agile methodologies

II. TRADITIONAL METHODOLOGIES

Traditional methodologies specifically include the waterfall model, first introduced in the 1970s. The cascade model is explained stage-by-stage [4]. Through these stages, including iterative approaches, the author introduced the development of large-scale systems. The step-by-step approach of traditional methodologies allows large-scale projects to be handled and developed more successfully. But on the other hand, traditional development methods are rigid and also fail to respond to aggressive or frequently changing customer requests [5]. Compared to the traditional methodology, the agile development methodology provides a set of practices that allow rapid adaptation to changing customer needs. In terms of research gaps, the authors discussed the failures of traditional models very well, but did not propose any solution to overcome the major flaws of traditional development methodologies. Current research included DevOps culture, with its validation analysis of out-performance, as a result of comparison with other development methodologies.

A. Agile Development Methods

Although agile methods were created to address any flaws or limitations of traditional development methodologies, they are also confirmed to be effective for large-scale distributed projects [5]. Agile approaches are drivers in huge and extremely large-scale development [6]. Therefore, the agile approaches encourage greater communication, continuous integration, and fast delivery of products using an incremental and iterative approach, but they also have several disadvantages, such as lack of planning, lack of documentation, lack of predictability, etc. [7.] To discover genuine constraints of agile approaches outside the existing literature review, the authors in [7] also performed an online survey. There are still research gaps in terms of solutions to the problems faced by flexible methods. Basic research talks about DevOps development culture to overcome many of the difficulties of software development.

B. DevOps Development Culture

DevOps proposes a solution to a variety of development and delivery challenges, including the quality of the generated product. In their research on DevOps, authors in [8] examined the effects of DevOps features on software quality. Increasing

the speed, frequency of development and product quality is the main goal of DevOps. To minimize differences or fill in all kinds of communication gaps between dev and ops teams, DevOps promises to deliver successful projects with shorter deployment or sprint times [8]. To deliver or deploy high-quality products, authors in [9] agree that development and operations teams should cooperate well [9]. Although numerous studies support the use of DevOps, others are opposed to it and discuss the lack of quantification of performance and quality measures [10]. Authors in [11] found that DevOps helps businesses to achieve their goals and also increases their speed in reacting to changes [11]. The literature also confirms the existence and successful implementation of various DevOps models in practice [12]. Similarly, many papers, including [11, 16], accept the emerging paradigm as a response to the growing awareness of the existing many types of communication or collaboration and cultural gaps between dev and ops team functions. Again, there are research gaps in terms of quantified quality outcomes provided by DevOps.

C. Motivation

The motivation behind this research is to provide quantified results of DevOps quality and on-time delivery. To this end, the current research examines the proposed [1] and implemented [2] model of hybrid integrated automation tools based on DevOps. Study is also conducted from different perspectives of model building [13, 15] to the application of cloud computing [15] or the adoption of recent approaches for development industries. Based on the existing literature and our tool model, this paper performs an evaluation of different types of parameters or software metrics for quality measurement. This research has taken three sample software projects developed in JDK environment to measure DevOps performance and quality. Lines Of Count (LOC), number of different components/modules, development time, and risk consideration are considered as evaluation metrics.

III. DEVOPS BASED HYBRID MODEL OF INTEGRATED TOOL CHAIN

For the performance evaluation of DevOps, we propose [1] and apply [2] a DevOps-based hybrid ITC model as depicted in Figure 8 of [1]. For the hybrid model, different tools are proposed from which only one automation tool is selected as the best performer tool based on several performance evaluators. The current research work considers the same set of automation tools [1] for the implementation of sample java projects, mentioned in Table I, using DevOps development and deployment culture.

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN AND DATA SET

The current research compares traditional and agile methodologies with DevOps development. For this purpose, three sample projects, i.e. a website for online faculty recruitment, a car search engine, and a scientific calculator tool in java have been designed through traditional methods and later on uploaded local repositories to GitHub for implementation through DevOps tools. Different parameters for measurement of projects were calculated.

Fig. 1. Components/modules and LOC for sample java projects.

Figure 3, gives the total count of lines of code along with different components and other parameters to consider for metric evaluation purposes. Table I shows the descriptive measures of these sample projects.

TABLE I. SOFTWARE METRIC CLASSIFICATION OF THE SOFTWARE PROJECT

Name of Java project	Size	No of components/modules	Project domain
Web site for online faculty recruitment (Project1)	2430	18	Web based
Car search application (Project2)	1579	14	Search application
Scientific calculator tool (Project3)	557	8	Tool

The sample projects mentioned in Table II have Java as the application development environment. These projects were designed in local repositories in the JDK environment and were uploaded in GitHub, which was used as a remote repository for the smooth working of the DevOps environment. After the uploading of the code, the next phase is to plan and write test cases for proper execution and implementation of the code. If the test case fails, then the test case must be rewritten after code refactoring. Successful test case execution is followed by code deployment and monitoring or the operations phase of the project. The complete step by step procedure in terms of process flow diagram for current research work is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Process flow diagram of the current research work.

As clearly depicted in the flowchart of Figure 2, writing the test cases and successful code testing is a major part of the DevOps process. For the implementation purpose, Jenkins continuous integration tool is selected which also takes charge of continuous delivery of the product. Different plugins are also installed with Jenkins to ensure smooth working of the tool. Code repository or maintenance is done through GitHub. Ansible with Jenkins is responsible for the continuous deployment of the code. Test cases were written using Junit. The build work was done by Maven. All these steps or procedures are fully automated and were done through the DevOps based hybrid model of automation tool set.

V. MEASUREMENT METRICS OF SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

Quality plays an important role in software acceptance. Software quality is not a single factor or value, but it covers many different parameters like testability, predictability, and maintainability. So, quantification of these performance or efficiency parameters becomes more important for measuring the quality value. This research work considers three types of software metrics, i.e. project, process, and product metrics. The project metrics covered in the current work are Project Defect Density (PDD) and Release Deployment Frequency (RDF), to measure defect density covered in the project along with the deployment frequency of the project. Similarly, Process metrics cover the Productivity (PP) of the whole process in the form of the throughput of the system. Lastly, product metrics involve System Risk Identification (SRI) and the reliability of the developed product. These software metrics along with their expected outcome are shown in Table II. The categorization of software metrics in Table II clearly mentions the expected results. These metrics with their calculation formulas and methods are explained below.

A. Project Defect Density (PDD)

PDD refers to whether the software can be deployed. PDD actually depends directly on the presence of defects in the

system. As defects can occur at any stage of software development, checks at regular intervals become a necessary activity of the development. The value of PDD must be low to ensure quality delivery of the software. The PDD formula is:

$$PDD = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\text{Total number of defects}}{\text{Size of software (in KLOC)}} \quad (1)$$

where n refers to the total number of components or modules in the system and n>0.

Equation (1) is used to first find the defect density of individual components or modules of the system and to get the defect density for the whole system/project by summing them up. Table III shows the PDD of the system as calculated with traditional methods of development and DevOps. TDM refers to Traditional Development Methods and DC refers to DevOps Culture.

TABLE II. CONSIDERED SOFTWARE METRICS AND THEIR EXPECTED OUTCOME

Software metric type	Software metric	Expected outcome
Project	PDD	Low
	RDF	High
Process	SRI	High
Product	PP	High

TABLE III. PDD MEASURE OF SAMPLE PROJECTS

Name of project	Size (LOC)	No of modules	Total no of defects		PDD	
			TDM	DC	TDM	DC
Project1	2430	18	30	15	12.35	6.17
Project2	1579	14	18	8	11.40	5.07
Project3	557	8	10	4	17.95	7.18

Defect density is computed by dividing the total number of defects with the size of the corresponding project as given by (1). In Table III, DevOps gives a low PDD value that clearly indicates more reliability and success of the underlying process. Figure 3 displays a graphical comparison of these methods.

Fig. 3. Graphical comparison of traditional and DevOps development for PDD measure.

B. Release Deployment Frequency (RDF)

RDF reports the total number of deployments in a particular time period. In other words, RDF refers to the rate of released deployments. The higher the value of RDF, the lesser is the chance of errors/defects in the system. The calculation is RDF is done by:

$$RDF = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\text{Total number of Deployments}}{\text{Time Unit (in Hours)}} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) calculates the total number of deployments or the release count in particular time units, taken in hours, for individual components and adding them all to get the RDF for the whole system/project. The deployment frequency data of the java projects with the usage of traditional principles and DevOps rules is shown in Table IV. Table IV clearly indicates the high value of deployments that leads to the acceptance of frequent changes in the system. The comparative graph of these development methodologies in Figure 4 shows similar results.

TABLE IV. RDF MEASURE OF SAMPLE PROJECTS

Name of project	Size (LOC)	No of deployments		Time taken to deploy (h)		RDF	
		TDM	DC	TDM	DC	TDM	DC
Project1	2430	18	20	1.8	1.1	10	18.18
Project2	1579	15	16	1.5	0.9	10	17.78
Project3	557	9	10	1	0.7	9	14.29

Fig. 4. Comparative graph for DevOps and traditional approaches.

As depicted in Figure 4, the DevOps deployment number is higher as compared to TDM. DevOps deployment speed is much higher for all types of development projects. Automation tools and prior selection of tool chain is the major reason of DevOps success over the other methodologies.

C. System Risk Identification (SRI)

SRI refers to the assessment of risk associated with the project/system to be developed. A high value reflects the identification of more risk components and ensures safe and risk-free delivery of software. The formula for SRI is:

$$SRI = \sum_{i=1}^n W_x, n>0 \quad (3)$$

where n refers to the total number of components in the system, W_x refers to the weightage assigned to each individual risk and the sum of all W_x gives the SRI number. Risk coverage analysis or risk identification gives the total number of risk sets injected with risk sets executed positively and total risks not tested or broken. Table VI depicts different risk set coverage calculated for traditional development approaches and DevOps.

TABLE V. SRI ESTIMATE OF SAMPLE PROJECTS

Project	Total risk tests	Total no of executed risks tests		Risks broken		Total risks not tested		Risks not executed		Risk coverage (%age)	
		TDM	DC	TDM	DC	TDM	DC	TDM	DC	TDM	DC
Project1	275	188	211	42	23	22	24	23	17	68.36	76.73
Project2	150	104	116	23	12	12	13	11	9	37.81	42.18
Project3	60	40	46	9	5	15	5	6	4	14.55	16.62

In Table VI, the number of total risk sets included, executed, broken, and even ignored or not tested at all in DevOps culture are compared with the similar parameters for traditional development methods. The results again indicate a better risk coverage in DevOps. The graphical comparative study in Figure 5 confirms this statement.

Fig. 5. Risk coverage comparative study graph.

D. Process Productivity (PP)

The productivity of any system is the total units of work done in a particular time period. It refers to the throughput of the system. Process or system productivity is measured by:

$$PP = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\text{Total number of user stories}}{\text{Time taken to complete}} \quad (4)$$

where user stories refers to the units of work done in a given time period.

Equation (4) finds the productivity of the process or system and computes the summation of productivity of individual components. PP is also measured as the throughput of the whole system or software. It measures the total units of work done in a particular time period. The PPs for traditional methods and DevOps are shown in Table VII. The results of Table VII and of the comparative graph of Figure 6 clearly indicate enhanced throughput/productivity measure for projects developed under the DevOps culture.

TABLE VI. PP ESTIMATION/MEASUREMENT OF CURRENT DATASET

Name of Java project	Size (LOC)	Total no of user stories	Time taken (weeks)		PP	
			TDM	DC	TDM	DC
Project1	2430	180	18	14	10	12.86
Project2	1579	117	12	9	9.75	13
Project3	557	41	4	3	10.25	13.67

Fig. 6. PP comparative graph for DevOps and traditional approaches.

Figure 8 shows speedy releases or output in terms of productivity measure for DevOps in comparison with traditional development.

Each of the performance metric and graphic visualization tools proves the effectiveness of DevOps as a symbol of quality and speedy delivery with less defect density and high coverage of risk sets.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Fast and quality delivery is an essential indicator for assessing the power of software development methodology. This study examined the efficacy of the previously proposed and implemented DevOps-based hybrid model of automation tools. In this esteem, we presented three java based projects from different domains and compared the performance of DevOps culture with traditional methods of software development based on performance metric measurement values. The measured results showed the superior performance of DevOps culture.

Although previous studies developed many models in software development, no such model has been developed to analyze the effect of prior automation tool selection, before commencement of actual development, on delivery or deployment. Our proposed, implemented and now validated, DevOps-based hybrid model of tool chains comes out to be more technically focused in terms of software development. As a part of future work, real time industry data can also be taken or our own tool can be designed to get more automated results. Finally, it would be interesting to go deeper in the analysis to identify another automation tool that could implement more DevOps projects in different arenas.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Narang and P. Mittal, "Hybrid model for software development: an integral comparison of DevOps automation tools," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 456–465, Jul. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijeecs.v27.i1.pp456-465>.
- [2] P. Narang and P. Mittal, "Implementation of DevOps based Hybrid Model for Project Management and Deployment using Jenkins Automation Tool with Plugins," *International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security*, vol. 22, no. 8, pp. 249–259, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.22937/IJCSNS.2022.22.8.31>.
- [3] M. Gomes, R. Pereira, M. Silva, J. B. de Vasconcelos, and Á. Rocha, "KPI's for Evaluation of DevOps Teams," in *Information Systems and Technologies*, Cham, 2022, pp. 142–156, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-04829-6_13.
- [4] W. W. Rovce, "Managing the Development of Large Software Systems," in *Technical Papers of Western Electronic Show and Convention*, Los Angeles, CA, USA, Aug. 1970.
- [5] G. Papadopoulos, "Moving from Traditional to Agile Software Development Methodologies Also on Large, Distributed Projects.," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 175, pp. 455–463, Feb. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.1223>.
- [6] T. Dingsøy, N. B. Moe, T. E. Fægri, and E. A. Seim, "Exploring software development at the very large-scale: a revelatory case study and research agenda for agile method adaptation," *Empirical Software Engineering*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 490–520, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10664-017-9524-2>.
- [7] A. Agrawal, Mohd. A. Atiq, and L. S. Maurya, "A Current Study on the Limitations of Agile Methods in Industry Using Secure Google Forms," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 78, pp. 291–297, Jan. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.02.056>.

- [8] A. Mishra and Z. Otaiwi, "DevOps and software quality: A systematic mapping," *Computer Science Review*, vol. 38, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 100308, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosrev.2020.100308>.
- [9] P. Debois, "Agile Infrastructure and Operations: How Infra-gile are You?," in *Agile 2008 Conference*, Toronto, ON, Canada, Dec. 2008, pp. 202–207, <https://doi.org/10.1109/Agile.2008.42>.
- [10] A. A. Khan and M. Shameem, "Multicriteria decision-making taxonomy for DevOps challenging factors using analytical hierarchy process," *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process*, vol. 32, no. 10, 2020, Art. no. e2263, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smr.2263>.
- [11] M. Ramzan, M. S. Farooq, A. Zamir, W. Akhtar, M. Ilyas, and H. U. Khan, "An Analysis of Issues for Adoption of Cloud Computing in Telecom Industries," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3157–3161, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2101>.
- [12] L. Leite, C. Rocha, F. Kon, D. Milojicic, and P. Meirelles, "A Survey of DevOps Concepts and Challenges," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 52, no. 6, Aug. 2019, Art. no. 127, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3359981>.
- [13] D. Trihinas, A. Tryfonos, M. D. Dikaiakos, and G. Pallis, "DevOps as a Service: Pushing the Boundaries of Microservice Adoption," *IEEE Internet Computing*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 65–71, Feb. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIC.2018.032501519>.
- [14] K. Aldriwish, "A Deep Learning Approach for Malware and Software Piracy Threat Detection," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7757–7762, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4412>.
- [15] M. F. Hyder and M. A. Ismail, "INMTD: Intent-based Moving Target Defense Framework using Software Defined Networks," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5142–5147, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3266>.
- [16] M. A. Silva, "Productivity Gains of DevOps Adoption in an IT Team: A Case Study," in *27th International Conference on Information Systems Development*, Lund, Sweden, 2018.
- [17] J. Stoneham, P. Thrasher, T. Potts, H. Mickman, and C. DeArdo, *DevOps Case Studies: The Journey To Positive Business Outcomes*. IT Revolution.

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Increased Efficiency of the Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm Using the Pheromone Technique

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Abstract-Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) is a powerful metaheuristic algorithm inspired by the behavior of a honey bee swarm. ABC suffers from poor exploitation and, in some cases, poor exploration. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is another metaheuristic algorithm that uses pheromones as a guide for an ant to find its way. This study used a pheromone technique from ACO on ABC to enhance its exploration and exploitation. The performance of the proposed method was verified through twenty instances from TSPLIB. The results were compared with the original ABC method and showed that the proposed method leverages the performance of ABC.

Keywords-artificial bee colony; pheromone; ant colony optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) is a well-known algorithm for solving continuous function optimization problems. Although ABC is more effective than other biologically inspired algorithms, it suffers from a slow convergence rate in large search spaces [1-3]. In addition, one of the problems of ABC is the blind search strategy for food sources. In nature, honey bees interact with each other primarily through chemistry-driven behavioral communication. However, in the conventional ABC algorithm, honeybees only dance to share information. Therefore, it is necessary to incorporate chemistry communication in addition to behavioral to comply with the reality in nature and the basic principles of ABC. The attraction pheromone and transition strategy were used in [3, 4] as a communication strategy to share information between bees and solve the blindness search. It was assumed that each bee moves to a solution and deposits the attraction pheromone that attracts other bees to the object where the pheromone strength is higher than the others. This mechanism enabled bees to search for food more effectively. Other studies used pheromones to

overcome the limitation of ABC exploitation by making bees communicate and share their findings [3, 4]. Scout bees use pheromones as a guide when looking for a new food source, and pheromones are updated at all stages. Moreover, the amount of deposit pheromones is a function of fitness measures.

ABC integrates grenade explosion and the Cauchy operator to avoid random searches and solve Dynamic Economic Emission Dispatch (DEED) problems [5]. In [6, 7], methods were used for routing and improving the performance of Wireless Sensor Networks. The memory mechanism plays a crucial role in the guide of the search process by memorizing valuable information and exploring new search spaces. In [8], the memory mechanism was used to improve ABC performance, addressing the fundamental problem of ABC, which is the exploration and late convergence. This study aimed to solve the problem of exploration and late convergence in ABC using Random Memory (RM) and Elite Memory (EM), leading to a more desirable version of ABC called ABCWOA. In the ABCWOA algorithm, RM uses the bait search stage in the Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA). At the same time, EM is dynamically controlled based on the number of iterations and used to increase the convergence rate. Furthermore, ten standard data sets from the UCI machine learning repository were used for the evaluation, showing that ABCWOA had an improved convergence rate and less noise.

ABC is used to solve many types of problems. For example, an unrelated parallel machine scheduling problem was solved with ABC using a multi-sub-colony [9]. In addition, a multi-strategy evolutionary learning ABC algorithm was proposed to solve the path problem of an unmanned autonomous helicopter [10]. This study aimed to increase the performance of ABC using pheromone as a guide for bees and to overcome the ABC exploitation and exploration problem.

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II. THE ARTIFICIAL BEE COLONY

The ABC is a well-studied algorithm developed to solve continuous function optimization problems [11], simulating the foraging behaviors of a swarm of bees to find food. ABC is used successfully in many fields including energy management in mobile devices [12] and IoT routing [13]. ABC is divided into three groups: employed, onlookers, and scout bees. At first, employed bees search for food sources and share information with an onlooker. The onlooker bee tries to search for a better food source in the neighborhood using the knowledge passed from the employed bees. If the food source is abandoned to escape the limitation of food enhancement, the bees employed for that food source become scouts and randomly search for a new food source. In ABC, employed and onlooker bees perform the exploitation, while scout bees control the exploration process. The employed bees use (1) to search for neighbors by moving from an old position x_{ij} to the new position v_{ij} , if and only if the new position's fitness is better than the old position's.

$$v_{ij} = x_{ij} + \phi_{ij}(x_{ij} - x_{kj}) \quad (1)$$

where x_i is the old position and v_i is the new position of the i^{th} employed bee, ϕ_{ij} is a random real number in the range [-1, 1], j is an arbitrary integer number between 1 and the problem's dimension, and k is a random number between 1 and the number of employed bees. The onlooker bee selects a food source and evaluates all employed bees depending on the probability:

$$p_i = \frac{fit_i}{\sum_{j=1}^{SN} fit_j} \quad (2)$$

where fit is the fitness value of the solution of the employed bee:

$$fit_i = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1+f(x_i)}, & f(x_i) \geq 0 \\ 1 + |f(x_i)|, & f(x_i) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $f(x_i)$ stands for the value of the objective function to be optimized. Like the employed bee, the onlooker bee uses (1) to update its position and explore the selected food source. When a food source cannot be further enhanced within a pre-defined trial limit, it is abandoned and the corresponding employed bee becomes a scout and randomly searches for a new food source. The combination of exploration and exploitation search in ABC is important as it enables the algorithm to search the solution space for high-quality solutions and prevents them from getting stuck in local optima. In ABC, the employed bees maintain the current solution while the onlooker bees allow the best solution to be exploited. Furthermore, scout bees try to remove stagnating solutions and explore new ones.

Fig. 1. The standard ABC.

III. ANT COLONY OPTIMIZATION

Another non-deterministic algorithm used to solve an optimization problem is Ant Colony Optimization (ACO). ACO was inspired by ants seeking the shortest route between a source of food and their colonies [14]. ACO seeks the optimal solution for the computation problem by building one solution and adding it to solution components until the wanted solution is built. ACO has been successfully applied to solve the traveling salesman problem. However, as the complexity of the problem increases the accuracy of the ACO algorithm decreases. In nature, ants use pheromones as indirect communication between them. In ACO, pheromones are represented by numeric values modified by every solution component. These values influence the movement of ants in the next iteration in a way that edges between nodes with large values (high levels of pheromones) are more likely to be visited. Furthermore, the ACO model allows for the inclusion of heuristic information to guide the ants to complete a feasible solution.

Fig. 2. The ACO algorithm.

Each ant starts from a random location and makes a trip. When being in location i at the t^{th} iteration, ant k applies a probabilistic action before it is transmitted to the next unvisited location j . Finding the probability for ant k is given by [15]:

$$P_{ij}^k(t) = \frac{[T_{ij}(t)]^\alpha \cdot [\eta_{ij}]^\beta}{\sum_{l \in N_i^k} [T_{il}(t)]^\alpha \cdot [\eta_{il}]^\beta}, \quad \text{if } j \in N_i^k \quad (4)$$

where $\eta = 1/d_{ij}$ is the value of the heuristic available in advance, α and β are two parameters that define the relative influence of the pheromone trail and the heuristic information, and N_i^k is the feasible neighborhood of the ant k . Parameters α and β play a main role in choosing the next location to be visited. If $\alpha = 0$, there is no pheromone impact on the movement of the ants. However, if $\beta = 0$, only pheromone strengthening works. It has been suggested that all ants construct the same path consequently and a trade-off exists between the pheromone trail and the impact of the heuristic information [15].

The pheromone update procedure is performed in two steps. First, the amount of pheromone on the edge that joins two locations is decreased by a constant factor. The next step is to put a certain amount of pheromone on that particular edge. The update of the pheromone is calculated by:

$$T_{ij}(t+1) = (1 - \rho) \cdot T_{ij}(t) + \sum_{k=1}^M \Delta T_{ij}^k(t) \quad (5)$$

where ρ is greater than 0 and equal to or less than 1. The parameter ρ is used to avoid accumulating a high level of the pheromone trail by lowering the pheromone level. Similarly, it helps ant to discard bad decisions early taken and discover a new solution. Moreover, $\Delta T_{ij}^k(t)$ represents the quantity of pheromone that will be added, defined as:

$$\Delta T_{ij}^K(t) = \begin{cases} 1/L_{K(t)} & \text{If edge } (i, j) \text{ is used by the ant} \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $L_{K(t)}$ is the length of the K^{th} ant's trip. Equation (6) shows that adding more pheromones to an edge gives a better ant trip, and edges with high pheromones are more likely to be visited in the next iteration. In AS, all ants add a certain quantity of pheromone on the visited edge. This method does not provide additional support for the best solution found, although letting all ants update the pheromone trails may help the algorithm avoid an early stagnation and move to different search space.

IV. USING PHEROMONES WITH ABC TO SOLVE TSP

The Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) was used as a test case for the proposed algorithm. TSP is an easy to describe well-known problem, but hard to solve. The purpose of TSP is to find the shortest path between groups of cities with minimum cost.

A. Initialization Phase

Pheromones can integrate into ABC to give memory-like behavior. The proposed algorithm initializes the parameters and then initializes the pheromones using the neighbor search algorithm to find the start path to update the pheromone using (5). Finally, the food source (solutions) is generated using (4).

```

Initialize maxIteration, popSize, limit, Beta &
initialize pheromone trails
for i = 1 to popSize/2
    foodSource[i] = InitializeUsingPheromone()
    unsuccessfulCycles[i] = 0
    fitness[i] = CalculateFitness(foodSource[i])
end for
    
```

Fig. 3. Initialization.

B. Employed Bee Phase

The employee bee is responsible for searching in the neighborhood for new solutions and changing positions if the new position is better than the old one. Figure 4 shows the employee bee phase algorithm.

```

for i = 1 to popSize/2
    newSol = neighborSeach(foodSource[i], i)
    newCost = CalculateFitness(newSol)
    if newCost < fitness[i] // greedy selection
        foodSource[i] = newSol
        fitness[i]=newCost
        unsuccessfulCycles[i] = 0
    end if
end for
    
```

Fig. 4. Employed bee phase.

C. Onlooker Bee Phase

Onlooker bee calculates the probability P_i of choosing a food source using (2). Then sends onlooker bees to a food source(i) according to the associated P_i and generates a new food source, as shown in Figure 5.

```

for i = 1 to popSize/2
    newSol = neighborSeach(foodSource[i], i)
    newCost = CalculateFitness(newSol)
    if newCost < fitness[i] // greedy selection
        foodSource[i] = newSol
        fitness[i]=newCost
        unsuccessfulCycles[i] = 0
    end if
end for
    
```

Fig. 5. Onlooker bee phase.

D. Updating Pheromone Phase

After the onlooker has explored the food source, each bee will deposit the pheromone on the link using (6). Then, the pheromones on all edges are reduced to prevent stagnation. Figure 6 shows the step for deposit and reduction.

```

Deposit pheromone on the links
Reduce pheromone levels on all edges
Memorize the best solution achieved so far
    
```

Fig. 6. Pheromone update

E. Scout Bee Phase

In the scout bee phase, each bee that couldn't enhance anymore will abandon its food source and search for a new one. Figure 7 shows the scout bee phase algorithm.

```

for i = 1 to popSize/2
    if unsuccessfulCycles [i] > limit
        foodSource[i] = InitializeUsingPheromone()
        newCost = CalculateFitness(newSol)
        fitness[i]=newCost
        unsuccessfulCycles[i] = 0
    end if
end for
    
```

Fig. 7. Scout bee phase.

F. Neighbor Operator

The neighborhood operator [16-17] is a replacement for (1) to make ABC capable of solving discrete problems. Random swap crossover was used to perform a neighbor search. Figure 8 shows the random swap crossover operation.

Fig. 8. Random swap crossover.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed method was implemented using C# and run on a 2.80GHz Intel Core i7 processor with 16GB RAM. The proposed algorithm was tested on 20 TSP instances from [18]. Table I shows the statistical variation of the results for 20 TSPs solved by the two algorithms on 30 independent runs. The results of the experiments demonstrated the superiority of the proposed method over the original ABC, as the error rate and average error rate were better in all cases. Figure 9 shows a comparison between the error rate of ABC and the proposed method, while Figure 10 shows the average rate between the two methods. The error rate was computed using:

$$error\ rate = \frac{best\ value - optimal\ value}{optimal\ value} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS ABCUPT WITH ABC

Problem	ABC		Proposed method	
	error	avg error	error	avg error
att48	15.65	25.70	6.15	12.55
eil51	18.54	25.63	6.81	12.49
berlin52	15.87	26.71	6.19	12.18
st70	36.89	53.28	15.06	20.40
eil76	36.62	45.62	12.74	20.97
pr76	39.44	52.80	18.17	27.10
kroA100	74.21	95.10	20.52	31.65
kroB100	65.13	89.32	23.24	35.24
kroC100	79.46	100.86	24.49	36.81
kroD100	72.38	91.55	20.65	31.22
kroE100	63.70	90.23	23.79	36.58
rd100	74.34	86.08	26.99	37.33
eil101	53.58	62.87	24.64	30.86
lin105	82.29	101.68	21.41	33.98
pr107	111.54	172.57	2.40	4.94
gr120	78.68	94.62	34.72	39.89
pr124	143.39	168.81	31.57	37.88
bier127	50.72	70.09	17.25	27.23
ch130	83.01	105.02	20.41	38.49
pr136	99.81	116.42	29.14	42.61

Fig. 9. Comparison between ABC and ABCUPT error rates.

The results show clearly that the proposed method is better than the original ABC. Moreover, using pheromones in ABC gives a memory-like behavior that helps exploration and exploitation but adds more complexity to ABC and increases execution time. In future work, pheromones can be used lightly to improve performance without increasing execution time. Moreover, using a local search algorithm to help bees in exploration could lead to better results.

Fig. 10. Comparison of error average rate between ABC and ABCUPT.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study introduced an enhanced artificial bee colony algorithm using pheromones. The proposed method was tested on 20 TSP problems from TSPLIB. The results were compared with the original ABC and showed that the use of pheromone improved exploration and exploitation but increased execution time. In future work, local search can be integrated to leverage results. Furthermore, the use of pheromones adds memory-like behavior to the ABC algorithm and, therefore, it is easy to integrate the pheromone into other algorithms.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Wei, J. Ji, Y. Qin, Y. Wang, and C. Liu, "A Novel Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm Based on Attraction Pheromone for the Multidimensional Knapsack Problems," in *Artificial Intelligence and Computational Intelligence*, Taiyuan, China, 2011, pp. 1–10, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-23887-1_1.
- [2] J. Ji, H. Wei, C. Liu, and B. Yin, "Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm Merged with Pheromone Communication Mechanism for the 0-1 Multidimensional Knapsack Problem," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2013, Jul. 2013, Art. no. e676275, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/676275>.

- [3] J. M. Moosa, R. Shakur, M. Kaykobad, and M. S. Rahman, "Gene selection for cancer classification with the help of bees," *BMC Medical Genomics*, vol. 9, no. 2, Aug. 2016, Art. no. 47, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12920-016-0204-7>.
- [4] A. H. Alaidi, C. S. Soong Der, and Y. Weng Leong, "Systematic Review of Enhancement of Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm Using Ant Colony Pheromone," *International Journal of Interactive Mobile Technologies*, vol. 15, no. 16, Aug. 2021, Art. no. 172, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijim.v15i16.24171>.
- [5] I. Marouani, A. Boudjemline, T. Guesmi, and H. H. Abdallah, "A Modified Artificial Bee Colony for the Non-Smooth Dynamic Economic/Environmental Dispatch," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3321–3328, Oct. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2098>.
- [6] S. D. Chavan and A. V. Kulkarni, "Event Based Clustering Localized Energy Efficient Ant Colony Optimization (EBC_LEE-ACO) for Performance Enhancement of Wireless Sensor Network," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 3177–3183, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2121>.
- [7] H. Ehteshami, S. Javadi, and S. M. Shariatmadar, "Improving the Power Quality in Tehran Metro Line-Two Using the Ant Colony Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 6, pp. 2256–2259, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1551>.
- [8] N. Rahnama and F. S. Gharehchopogh, "An improved artificial bee colony algorithm based on whale optimization algorithm for data clustering," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 79, no. 43–44, pp. 32169–32194, Aug. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-020-09639-2>.
- [9] D. Lei and H. Yang, "Scheduling unrelated parallel machines with preventive maintenance and setup time: Multi-sub-colony artificial bee colony," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 125, Aug. 2022, Art. no. 109154, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2022.109154>.
- [10] Z. Han, M. Chen, S. Shao, and Q. Wu, "Improved artificial bee colony algorithm-based path planning of unmanned autonomous helicopter using multi-strategy evolutionary learning," *Aerospace Science and Technology*, vol. 122, Mar. 2022, Art. no. 107374, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2022.107374>.
- [11] D. Karaboga and B. Basturk, "A powerful and efficient algorithm for numerical function optimization: artificial bee colony (ABC) algorithm," *Journal of Global Optimization*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 459–471, Nov. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10898-007-9149-x>.
- [12] S. ArunKumar, B. V. Kumar, and M. Pandi, "Artificial bee colony optimization based energy-efficient wireless network interface selection for industrial mobile devices," *Computer Communications*, vol. 154, pp. 1–10, Mar. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comcom.2020.01.067>.
- [13] H. Gao, Z. Fu, C.-M. Pun, J. Zhang, and S. Kwong, "An Efficient Artificial Bee Colony Algorithm With an Improved Linkage Identification Method," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 52, no. 6, pp. 4400–4414, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2020.3026716>.
- [14] C. Twomey, T. Stützle, M. Dorigo, M. Manfrin, and M. Birattari, "An analysis of communication policies for homogeneous multi-colony ACO algorithms," *Information Sciences*, vol. 180, no. 12, pp. 2390–2404, Jun. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2010.02.017>.
- [15] M. Dorigo, V. Maniezzo, and A. Coloni, "Ant system: optimization by a colony of cooperating agents," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part B (Cybernetics)*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 29–41, Oct. 1996, <https://doi.org/10.1109/3477.484436>.
- [16] S. S. Choong, L.-P. Wong, and C. P. Lim, "An artificial bee colony algorithm with a Modified Choice Function for the traveling salesman problem," *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 44, pp. 622–635, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.swevo.2018.08.004>.
- [17] M. S. Kiran, H. İşcan, and M. Gündüz, "The analysis of discrete artificial bee colony algorithm with neighborhood operator on traveling salesman problem," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 9–21, Jul. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-011-0794-0>.
- [18] G. Reinelt, "TSPLIB—A Traveling Salesman Problem Library," *ORSA Journal on Computing*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 376–384, Nov. 1991, <https://doi.org/10.1287/ijoc.3.4.376>.

Modeling and Analysis of Time Response Parameters of a PMSM-Based Electric Vehicle with PI and PID Controllers

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Abstract-This paper presents the mathematical modeling of a vector-controlled Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM) drive with either a Proportional Integral (PI) controller or a Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) controller as a propulsion system for an Electric Vehicle (EV). Most commercial drives use a standard PI controller as a speed regulator. The vector control system model consists of the PMSM, a PWM inverter, the speed controller, and vehicle dynamics for speed control. The performance analysis of the drive is evaluated under transient conditions for settling time, rise time, steady state error of speed, and the vehicle's acceleration at the wheel axle for specifically designated values validated by MATLAB/Simulink.

Keywords-Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM); electric vehicle dynamics; Proportional Integral (PI) controller; Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) controller

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, several situations related to the environment have led to reduced carbon emissions from vehicles. Electric Vehicles (EVs) can be alternatives to traditional SI or CI engine automobiles [1-2]. PMSMs have been used in various industrial applications like CNC machines, industrial robotics, air-conditioners, washing machines, wind power generation systems, EVs, etc. The PMSMs are more suitable in EVs due to their high efficiency, high power/torque density, smaller size, high torque/weight ratio, and maintenance-free operation [3]. Better dynamic responsiveness and fewer torque ripples are provided by a vector-controlled PMSM drive, which needs a constant switching frequency. The outer loop speed control significantly impacts system performance [4].

The PI controller performs well under steady-state conditions. A lot of approaches have been proposed for the

tuning of the PI controller. The Ziegler-Nichols method is the most popular, which dispenses with the need for a system design and control parameters [5]. The PI and PID controllers are simple and effective, consequently, they are often used for the control of the PMSM systems [6]. Controlling of a Battery EV (BEV) is not a simple task as the EV is essentially time-variant. The EV's primary limiting factor is the short running distance (range) per battery charge. Another limiting factor is its acceleration time to reach the maximum speed limit [7]. The EV dynamics must be suitably selected to achieve better performance.

II. VEHICLE DYNAMICS

The performance of vehicle modeling is initially obtained by the tractive effort equation. The force that drives the vehicle forward and is transmitted to the ground through the drive wheels is known as the tractive effort. This force has to overcome the rolling resistance force, aerodynamic drag force, and the elements of the vehicle's weight (including payload) acting down to the slope. It also accomplishes the force required to accelerate the vehicle for the linear and angular motion of drive wheels [7-8]. The tractive force and the corresponding force equations depend upon the vehicle dynamics, shape, size, and structure parameters, such as rolling resistance coefficient, air density, drag coefficient, gear ratio and gear efficiency, wheel radius, etc., are illustrated in Figure 1 of [9]. The respective equations for Rolling Resistance Force F_{rr} , Aerodynamic Drag Force F_{ad} , Hill Climbing Force F_{hc} , Acceleration Force F_{la} , and Angular Acceleration Force F_{wa} are respectively given by:

$$F_{rr} = \mu_{rr} * m * g \quad (1)$$

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$$F_{ad} = \frac{1}{2} * \rho * A * C_d * v^2 \quad (2)$$

$$F_{hc} = m * g * \sin \psi \quad (3)$$

$$F_{la} = m * a \quad (4)$$

$$F_{wa} = I \frac{G^2}{\eta_g r^2} \quad (5)$$

The total tractive force necessary to drive the vehicle is the sum of all forces:

$$F_{te} = F_{rr} + F_{ad} + F_{hc} + F_{la} + F_{wa} \quad (6)$$

The tractive torque corresponding to the tractive force with wheel radius r , is given by:

$$T_R = F_{te} * r \quad (7)$$

The speed and torque at the axle of the wheel are given by:

$$\omega_{axle} = \frac{\omega_e}{G} \quad (8)$$

$$T_{axle} = G \eta_g T_e \quad (9)$$

The vehicle equations are used to understand the vehicle dynamics for different force inputs [10]. The mathematical model of the speed-toque equation of the vehicle at the axle of the wheels is given by:

$$\omega_{axle} = \int \frac{1}{(mr^2 + \frac{G^2 J}{\eta_g})} [T_{axle} - T_R] dt \quad (10)$$

The specifications of the vehicle chassis chosen for the simulation are given in Table I.

TABLE I. VEHICLE CHASSIS SPECIFICATIONS

Parameter	Quantity
Net mass, m	1200Kg
Area of frontal surface, A	2.2m ²
Gear ratio, G	2
Rolling coefficient, μ_{rr}	0.01
Gear efficiency, η_g	0.9
Wheel radius, r	0.2m
Drag coefficient, C_d	0.26
Slope angle, ψ	0°

III. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE PERMANENT MAGNET SYNCHRONOUS MOTOR

A three-phase salient-pole sinusoidal wave shape back EMF PMSM with 87.75Nm, 560Vdc, and 3000rpm preset model parameters was designed mathematically. The model specifications are given in Table II. The mathematical model of the PMSM is given in (11)-(22). The rotor reference frame is chosen because the rotor magnet's position will be determined independent of the stator phase voltages, instantaneous induced phase EMFs, stator phase currents, and torque of the machine [11]. For synchronous motors, the rotating speed of the rotor and the space vector of the rotor flux are both equal to the rotating rate of the reference frame $\omega_a = \omega_r = \omega$ [12-13].

In the rotor reference frame, the stator q and d axes voltage equations in terms of flux linkages are:

$$V_{qs} = R_q i_{qs} + \frac{d\phi_{qs}}{dt} + \omega_r \phi_{ds} \quad (11)$$

$$V_{ds} = R_d i_{ds} + \frac{d\phi_{ds}}{dt} - \omega_r \phi_{qs} \quad (12)$$

The stator flux linkages are given by:

$$\phi_{qs} = L_q i_{qs} \quad (13)$$

$$\phi_{ds} = L_d i_{ds} + L_m i_f \quad (14)$$

TABLE II. PMSM SPECIFICATIONS

Parameter	Value
Stator phase resistance, R_s ($R_d = R_q = R_s$)	0.05Ω
d-axis inductance, L_d	0.0007552H
q-axis inductance, L_q	0.0008348H
Flux linkage, ϕ_{af}	0.192 Wb-turn
Inertia, J	0.011Kg m ²
Viscous damping, B	0.001417Nms
Pole pairs, P	4
Static friction, T_f	0Nm

The stator voltage equations in terms of electrical parameters are obtained by substituting the flux linkages in the stator voltage equations as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{qs} \\ V_{ds} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_q + \frac{dL_q}{dt} & \omega_r L_d \\ -\omega_r L_q & R_d + \frac{dL_d}{dt} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_{qs} \\ i_{ds} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \omega_r L_m i_f \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

The electromagnetic torque is given by:

$$T_e = \frac{3P}{2} (\phi_{ds} i_{qs} - \phi_{qs} i_{ds}) \quad (16)$$

The torque equation in terms of inductances and currents upon the substitution of flux linkages is given by [14]:

$$T_e = \frac{3P}{4} \{ \phi_{af} i_{qs} + (L_d - L_q) i_{qs} i_{ds} \} \quad (17)$$

where ϕ_{af} is the rotor flux linkage that links the stator and is given by:

$$\phi_{af} = L_m i_f \quad (18)$$

The angular speed ω_e and the instantaneous angle of the rotor θ_r of the machine are given by:

$$\omega_e = \frac{P}{2} \left[\frac{1}{J_s + B} \right] [T_e - T_m] \quad (19)$$

$$\theta_r = \int_0^t \omega_e(t) dt + \theta_r(0) \quad (20)$$

The stator q and d axes currents for a balanced three-phase operation are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{qs} \\ i_{ds} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_r & \cos \left(\theta_r - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) & \cos \left(\theta_r + \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \\ \sin \theta_r & \sin \left(\theta_r - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) & \sin \left(\theta_r + \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_a \\ i_b \\ i_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

The abc-to-dq transformation equations for stator voltages are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{qs} \\ v_{ds} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_r & \cos \left(\theta_r - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) & \cos \left(\theta_r + \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \\ \sin \theta_r & \sin \left(\theta_r - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) & \sin \left(\theta_r + \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_a \\ v_b \\ v_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM MODEL WITH PI AND PID CONTROLLER

For applications in control theory, the Proportional (P), the PI, and the PID controllers are the most commonly used controllers. As illustrated in Figure 1, the PI controller will affect the performance of the system by increasing the system's order by one and by reducing steady state error, disturbance signal rejection, and relative stability. The system's sensitivity with respect to parameters also decreases [15]. The transfer function of the PI controller is given by:

$$G_c(S) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{S} \quad (23)$$

The PI controller reduces rise time and minimizes the steady-state error [16]. Peak overshoot, settling time, order, and type of the system will be increased [15]. It functions as a low pass filter. The output equations of the PI and PID controllers are given by:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt \quad (24)$$

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt + K_d \frac{d}{dt} e(t) \quad (25)$$

A command speed ω^* is compared with the motor's speed ω_r and provides the change or error in speed $\Delta\omega$, which is given to the PI or PID controller to obtain the command torque component of stator current I_q^* . A limiter is used ahead of the controller to avoid decreased stability.

Fig. 1. PI controller block diagram.

The complete model block diagram of the PI controller of the PMSM-based BEV is illustrated in Figure 2. The command speed has been compared with the actual speed of the PMSM. An error speed signal is given to the PI controller to tune the signal with K_p and K_i values and provide the torque-producing current reference component I_q^* , which is essential to control the error speed by calculating the three-phase reference currents I_a^* , I_b^* , I_c^* . A Li-Ion battery with 100C capacity was used as the supply, which is converted into a three-phase supply voltage using a PWM inverter. The Li-Ion battery is operated with a current-controlled device with the feedback current provided by the PMSM. A sinusoidal PWM approach with the reference currents I_a^* , I_b^* , I_c^* corresponding to command speed and the actual currents I_a , I_b , I_c produced by the PMSM are collectively compared with a triangular reference signal to produce the gate pulses. Such desired gate pulses drive the three phase two-level inverter and will produce the three phase voltages for the PMSM. The characteristic equations of the PMSM building blocks are operated with inverter voltages and produce the instantaneous current, position, speed ω_e , and torque T_e of the motor. The PMSM will drive the vehicle's wheels through the transmission and differentials by considering the vehicle's dynamic losses.

Fig. 2. Model analysis diagram of the speed control of the EV with PMSM drive using a PI controller.

Fig. 3. Simulink model of dq to abc reference signals.

Fig. 4. Simulink model of the PWM inverter.

Fig. 5. Simulink model of PMSM.

Finally, the vehicle is operated smoothly with the required speed and torque. The performance results are discussed below.

In MATLAB Simulink version R2017a, the proposed work was simulated with the ode 23tb solver in continuous time mode. The design sub models like dq to abc reference, PWM inverter, PMSM model, and vehicle dynamic models are shown in Figures 3-7.

Fig. 6. Simulink model of PMSM internal characteristics.

Fig. 7. Simulink model of vehicle dynamics (motor to wheels).

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulations have been carried out with the PI and PID speed controllers for a 3-phase, 550Vdc, 1500rpm, 97.96Nm PMSM at a load torque of 80Nm and operating speed of 1500RPM or 157.079rad/sec. It can be observed that the rise time (90% of the command speed) is attained in 50.1ms with the PI controller, which is a better response than that of the PID controller. The motor speed stabilizes at a reference speed (with 2% tolerance) of 157.079rad/s in 70.1ms with the PID controller, which is slightly better performance than the one of the PI controller and with the steady state error of 0.0075rad/s or 0.0716rpm in both PI and PID controllers, as shown in Figure 8. The vehicle's acceleration (the speed at the wheels or the axle) was measured, and the time taken to reach the speed of 100Km/h is 48.1ms with the PI controller, which is superior to the performance of the PID controller, as shown in Figures 11-12. In the steady state, for a command torque of 80Nm, the torque developed by the PMSM is 80Nm.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM MODEL

Controller type and its gain values	Applied load (Nm)	Motor side - speed			Axle side - speed
		Rise time required to reach 90% of final value (ms)	Settling time needed to get steady-state value with 2% tolerance (ms)	Steady state error	Time to reach 100Km/hr (ms)
PI (Kp=0.35, Ki=16)	80	50.1	71.0	0.0075rad/s or 0.0716rpm	48.1
PID (Kp=0.35, Ki=16, Kd=0.01)	80	54.8	70.1	0.0075rad/s or 0.0716rpm	53.0

Fig. 8. Simulated speed responses with PI and PID controllers.

Fig. 9. Simulated torque responses with the PI controller.

Fig. 10. Simulated torque responses with the PID controller.

The torque available at the wheel axle is 72.5Nm, with net tractive resistance loss of 7.5Nm due to rolling resistance, aerodynamic, and hill-climbing torque losses in both PI and PID controllers. The initial transient is higher in the PID controller than in the PI controller, as seen in Figures 9-10. The pulsating ripple torques are noticed due to the residual flux variation. The data of the mathematical model of the performance of the PMSM-based electric vehicle with PI and PID controller through MATLAB simulations are given in Table III.

Fig. 11. Simulated vehicle acceleration pointing at the top speed of 100Km/hr with the PI controller.

Fig. 12. Simulated vehicle acceleration pointing at top the speed of 100Km/hr with the PID controller.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the mathematical model of a vector controlled PMSM drive with PI and PID controllers as a propulsion system for an electric vehicle is developed, and its simulation results are presented. The results demonstrate that the PI controller achieves more robust tracking response of the command speed with less steady-state error than the PID controller. Good execution time and time are noted in the performance analysis. The vehicle acceleration at the wheel axle reached the desired value within a minimal time. The overall output responses of the model show that the vehicle can run smoothly with good static and dynamic performance characteristics with the PI controller.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. C. Chan and K. T. Chau, "An overview of power electronics in electric vehicles," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 3–13, Oct. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1109/41.557493>.
- [2] *Global Electric Vehicle Outlook 2022*. France: International Energy Agency, 2022.
- [3] S. Morimoto, "Trend of permanent magnet synchronous machines," *IEEE Transactions on Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 101–108, 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1002/tee.20116>.
- [4] R. N. Hajare and A. G. Thosar, "Modeling and Simulation of Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor using MATLAB," vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 413–423, 2014.
- [5] V. V. Patel, "Ziegler-Nichols Tuning Method," *Resonance*, vol. 25, no. 10, pp. 1385–1397, Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12045-020-1058-z>.
- [6] E.-C. Shin, T.-S. Park, W.-H. Oh, and J.-Y. Yoo, "A design method of PI controller for an induction motor with parameter variation," in *IECON'03. 29th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, Roanoke, VA, USA, Aug. 2003, vol. 1, pp. 408–413, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IECON.2003.1280015>.
- [7] "Electric and Hybrid Vehicles, Design Fundamentals [Book Review]," *IEEE Circuits and Devices Magazine*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 26–27, Sep. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCD.2005.1517392>.

- [8] J. Larminie and J. Lowry, *Electric Vehicle Technology Explained*, 2nd ed. Wiley, 2012.
- [9] M. Y. Veeresh, V. N. B. Reddy, and R. Kiranmayi, "Range Estimation of Battery Electric Vehicle by Mathematical Modelling of Battery's Depth-of-Discharge," *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 3987–3992, Aug. 2019, <https://www.doi.org/10.35940/ijeat.F8800.088619>.
- [10] M. Yildirim, M. C. Catalbas, A. Gulten, and H. Kurum, "Computation of the Speed of Four In-Wheel Motors of an Electric Vehicle Using a Radial Basis Neural Network," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 1288–1293, Dec. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.889>.
- [11] P. T. Giang, V. T. Ha, and V. H. Phuong, "Drive Control of a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Fed by a Multi-level Inverter for Electric Vehicle Application," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8658–8666, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4935>.
- [12] P. Pillay and R. Krishnan, "Modeling of permanent magnet motor drives," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 537–541, Aug. 1988, <https://doi.org/10.1109/41.9176>.
- [13] C. Bowen, Z. Jihua, and R. Zhang, "Modeling and simulation of permanent magnet synchronous motor drives," in *ICEMS'2001. Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Electrical Machines and Systems*, Shenyang, China, Dec. 2001, vol. 2, pp. 905–908, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEMS.2001.971825>.
- [14] A. Mansouri and T. Hafedh, "Torque Ripple Minimization and Performance Investigation of an In-Wheel Permanent Magnet Motor," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 987–992, Jun. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.644>.
- [15] J. C. Basilio and S. R. Matos, "Design of PI and PID controllers with transient performance specification," *IEEE Transactions on Education*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 364–370, Aug. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2002.804399>.
- [16] S. Mikkili and A. K. Panda, "SHAF for mitigation of Current harmonics with p-q and Id-Iq control strategies using both PI and Fuzzy Controllers," in *International Conference on Sustainable Energy and Intelligent Systems (SEISCON 2011)*, Chennai, India, Jul. 2011, pp. 358–362, <https://doi.org/10.1049/cp.2011.0389>.

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Survey and Design of Individual Housing Projects: Situation and Solutions for Ha Tinh Province, Vietnam

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Abstract-Survey and design processes are considered essential stages and directly affect the quality and cost of construction works. This study aimed to investigate the existing limitations in the survey and design stages of individual housing projects in Ha Tinh province, Vietnam, and to propose specific solutions to improve them. These solutions can contribute to eliminating unexpected problems or errors during the construction process of individual housing projects in Vietnam.

Keywords-survey; design; individual housing; Ha Tinh province

I. INTRODUCTION

The quality management of the construction of individual houses has not attracted serious attention in Vietnam, as the regulations focus on key works and public investment projects [1-8]. For individual houses, although the state has issued regulations, the responsibility for the survey, design, supervision, and construction is on the investor [1, 4, 7]. As investors often hire a consultant or even skip the survey and design stage to save costs, without meeting the requirements, this leads to many problems and affects the safety of people and surrounding structures. Several studies investigated existing problems in construction management in various regions around the world and proposed methods or strategies to improve the management process [9-12]. Very few studies conducted in Vietnam investigated the effects of the limitations of the survey and design stages on individual housing projects. The theoretical basis of the survey and design of public investment projects was presented in [13]. Experience and lessons on housing management from some countries were

investigated in [14], proposing an application for Tien Giang province in Vietnam. Several studies related to housing theory, research, and policies have been conducted around the world [15, 16]. A survey on user satisfaction with the mass housing projects was presented in [17], led by a district municipality in Konya-Karatay, Turkey. In [18], an overview of the effects of housing conditions on human health was presented. A systematic study on the limitations of the survey and design process of individual housing projects in Vietnam has not yet been carried out.

Ha Tinh is a province located in the central region of Vietnam. With a population of more than 1.3 million people, the demand for housing construction is increasing, especially when the economy is growing. The construction of individual houses is very crucial to satisfy the needs of each individual and household. Therefore, it is necessary to study the current situation of the survey and design stages of individual housing projects in Ha Tinh to propose solutions to improve them.

II. CHALLENGES OF SURVEY AND DESIGN IN HA TINH

In recent years, the construction of individual houses in Ha Tinh has seen many changes, as the growing economy has increased the number of households that want to build individual houses. Individual housing projects appear more and more, not only in urban areas, but also in many rural areas throughout the province. Several investors pay attention to the survey and design stages before construction to create a project that meets the requirements of function, aesthetics, stability, and reasonable cost. The increasing importance of the design and survey stages in Ha Tinh province has increased the number of individual housing projects that hire survey and design units. These works satisfy the needs of people's lives

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and beautify urban spaces. However, the construction of individual housing projects still has many problems, especially in the survey and design stages.

A. Data and Limitations

A survey was conducted on 100 individual housing projects in the districts of Ha Tinh province, through data from the construction department of Ha Tinh province [19], to explore limitations in the survey and design stages. The survey results showed that the survey, design, and construction stages of individual housing projects in Ha Tinh province still have some shortcomings and limitations, as follows:

1) Geological and Topographic Survey

Figure 1 shows the proportion of individual housing projects with and without geological and topographic surveys. A small percentage (approximately 12%) carried out such a survey before design. Most individual housing projects did not perform survey work before design and construction. Failing to conduct geological surveys or improper technical surveys can lead to no or inaccurate data and can reduce the quality of the projects, increase their cost, and cause unpredictable technical problems. In addition, many works used cadastral maps, which do not ensure precise elevation and do not comply with the regulations on the transmission and protection of landmarks. Also, not using the coordinate system can lead to location deviations.

Fig. 1. Survey results: Individual housing projects that carried out geological and topographic surveys.

2) Design Stage

Many problems arise during the design process, such as over-estimated structural capacity, no or incorrect structural calculations, and improper application of regulations and standards. Figure 2 shows that most individual housing projects have typical problems. The number of projects having an authorized design registration following standards accounts for only 15%. Meanwhile, another 15% of projects are wasteful by design. The number of projects designed with unsafe and unsatisfactory structural requirements represents 25%, while 45% of the projects did not hire a design unit. This is a major problem that needs to be seriously considered and resolved.

3) Cost Estimation

Figure 3 shows the status of individual housing projects in Ha Tinh, according to cost estimation before construction.

Most individual housing design documents do not include a cost estimation or include a useless document. Only 10% of the projects had a proper cost estimation. Without an estimation of project cost, financial risks can occur.

4) Incidents

Figure 4 shows the results of the incident survey of individual housing projects in Ha Tinh. As can be observed, only 25% of projects meet structural safety and serviceability requirements. Most projects are unstable structures or affect the surrounding projects. More specifically, the number of projects with cracked walls, floor cracks, and uneven settlement accounts for 45%.

Fig. 2. Survey results: Individual housing projects having design issues.

Fig. 3. Survey results on individual housing projects relating to cost estimation.

B. Reasons

The shortcomings and limitations in the survey and design stages of individual housing projects are mainly due to the following reasons:

1) State Management Agency

Most Ha Tinh localities do not have an official state management agency in charge of survey and design works. Currently, in the whole province, only Ha Tinh city, Ky Anh town, and Hong Linh town have a specialized agency named Urban Management Department (UMD). Individual housing is managed in part-time form. The local wards and communes have only 2 cadastral officers to manage both land and basic

construction fields. The inspection, appraisal, and permits for the construction of individual houses also face many difficulties. According to the regulations for individual housing projects, the authorities are only interested in works with a floor area greater than 250m² and buildings with more than 3 floors or a height of more than 12m [1, 4, 7]. As a result, the construction process is not inspected and supervised, seriously affecting the planning and causing unsafety for people and properties. Moreover, there are many separate housing projects managed by state agencies, but violations are not handled promptly, causing difficulties and economic damage to investors in handling the consequences. In addition, the mechanisms and policies to manage the quality of construction are currently unclear, and there are no additional plans to attract human resources [2, 5, 6].

Fig. 4. Incident survey results of individual housing projects in Ha Tinh.

2) Investors

As investors in individual housing projects often lack experience and professional knowledge, there are shortcomings and limitations in the survey and design stages due to the following reasons:

- Investors often do not hire a survey and design quality management unit.
- There is no plan to choose a survey or design contractor or choosing a contractor that is unreputable, inexperienced, or has low capacity.
- Investors do not understand or have little understanding of construction. Usually, they do not employ a professional to supervise or check the process, and there are many cases where the consulting unit and the construction contractor collide. As a result, the cost increases and the quality of the project can decrease.
- Investors who build individual houses often do not make contracts when hiring a survey and design unit or, if any, the contract is made by the latter. Thus, the terms in the contract, if it exists, are often not beneficial to the investor.
- Many investors skip the survey and design stage to save costs, as it is an expensive procedure.

- Survey and design companies are not always sufficient. This can lead to over-designed (i.e. high redundancy in design) or under-designed conditions (i.e. unsafety).

Figure 5 shows the survey results regarding the reasons investors do not hire survey companies. The number of projects that do not hire a surveying agency because they do not trust them is 17%, while 20.5% do not hire a survey agency for fear of delaying the schedule, and 22.73% do not hire a survey unit because of cost. Moreover, the number of projects that do not hire a survey because the investor lacks understanding and follows the opinions of others accounts for approximately 40%.

Fig. 5. Results on reasons why investors do not hire a survey unit.

3) Geological and Topographic Survey Unit

Figure 7 summarizes the capacity of the survey units. It was found that only 25% of the projects hire qualified survey companies, while the remaining 75% do not meet the requirements of the survey process, as they lack the equipment or geological engineers. These are the main reasons for the unsatisfactory geological survey results.

Fig. 6. Results on the capacity of survey units.

4) Design Unit

The number of small design offices is increasing in Ha Tinh. Small design offices are located where few people can notice, even in their own homes. Their main form of business is

through social networks; thus, it is difficult for the authorities to check. Figure 7 shows that only 115 design companies (51.11%) have full capacity and are registered as a business. Design units that do not register as businesses but are created by qualified individuals account for 28.45%, while the proportion of design units without business registration made up of non-professional individuals accounts for 20.45%. Figure 8 shows the results of the reasons investors do not hire design companies. The main reason is the lack of understanding of the importance of the design process (40%) followed by design costs (27%), trust in the design company (22%), and concerns about effects on design time (11%).

- Number of design units with full capacity, registered business
- Number of design units that are not registered as businesses but are created by qualified individuals
- Number of design units that do not register as a business, created by individuals who are not professional

Fig. 7. Individual housing design offices in Ha Tinh.

- Number of projects that do not hire a design unit because of funding problems
- Number of projects that do not hire designers because the investor lacks understanding
- The project does not hire a designer because it does not trust the design unit
- Number of projects that do not hire designers for fear of delay

Fig. 8. Reasons why investors do not hire a design unit.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTIONS TO IMPROVE SURVEY AND DESIGN QUALITY

Based on these results, this study attempted to propose solutions to improve the quality of the survey and design stages of individual housing projects in Ha Tinh, as follows:

A. For State Authorities

- Improve organizational structure: At the district level, it is necessary to add an urban management unit with the same function as a city or town. Communes must have a full-time

official to supplement the role of individual housing management for the cadastral staff.

- Strengthen inspection and supervision: District, town, or commune urban management divisions are required to regularly inspect individual housing works before granting construction permits, and even during construction.
- The urban management department should strengthen the inspection of the capacity of design units and contractors to improve the quality of the survey stage. For example, they can check staff, machinery and equipment, office address, and contractor capacity in documents and reality. The above solutions could reduce problems and errors in the survey, design, and construction stages of individual houses. Moreover, it is necessary to strengthen the inspection and appraisal of individual housing projects according to regulations. This task must be performed seriously and promptly to assess the safety of the survey and design stages and to inspect the surrounding works or the safety conditions during construction.
- Train and foster urban management staff: In addition to the above solutions, it is necessary to organize professional training for civil servants and public employees.
- Improve mechanisms and policies: It is important to improve the role and responsibilities of the urban management department. In addition, it is necessary to have a reasonable remuneration mechanism and policy for personnel in the construction of individual houses.

B. For Investors

The survey results show that many investors do not hire a survey and design unit before construction due to lack of knowledge or funding. Therefore, many projects do not meet the requirements in terms of usability, structural safety, or architectural beauty, or have high costs. It is recommended that before construction, the investor needs to take care of the survey and design stage. The following solutions are proposed to improve the quality of the survey and design stages:

- The investor needs to hire a qualified unit for survey and design. The quality of construction works significantly depends on the survey and design stage. Therefore, the investor needs to hire professional staff, not only to supervise the investment implementation stage but also the investment preparation stage.
- Before choosing a design survey contractor, the investor should check its capacity in practice, staff, equipment, and experience based on previous contracts. Simultaneously, multiple pieces of information can be investigated to evaluate the contractor's capacity.
- The investor should regularly inspect consulting activities or hire a second individual or unit. This is essential as the owner hires a supervision consultant to check the contractors, but there is no one to check the latter. The investor or the employed person must have a thorough understanding of professional expertise, responsibilities, and the order and content of contractors' tasks.

- The administrative method is to communicate the investor's requirements through form requests or reports. The quality of a project is described by economic contracts. The quality requirements should be detailed in the contract or the contract addendum. This is a mandatory legal requirement.

C. For Survey and Design Contractors

The quality of the survey and design stages depends not only on the role of the investor and the supervision of state management agencies but also on the capacity of the contractor. To improve the contractor's capacity, it is necessary to improve the apparatus and quality management system and develop human resources.

- Improve apparatus: It is necessary to consolidate the titles according to the regulations on capacity conditions. Additionally, they should have the necessary apparatus from the office to the field. Moreover, employees must be reinspected and supervised by inspecting staff.
- Build quality assurance and management system: Another solution is to develop a quality assurance and management process, incorporating the company's goals, roadmap, and content with the quality management model. The company should have a quality policy consistent with a roadmap. At the same time, it is necessary to focus on a quality assurance plan for each project with specific measures and generate daily, weekly, and monthly reports.
- Build, train, and retrain staff: In addition to the organizational structure, it is required to enhance the team's qualifications. The contractor must have a plan for annual professional training of technicians and surveyors, especially for new employees.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the limited situations in the survey and design stages of individual houses in Ha Tinh province, Vietnam, and proposed some solutions to improve the quality of such construction projects. These results can contribute to better management and reduced potential risks in the survey, design, and construction stages of individual houses in this region. Furthermore, the results of this study are helpful references for investors, businesses, employees, and state management agencies to ensure and enhance quality management during the construction of individual houses in Vietnam.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Construction Law No. 50/2014/QH13," Vietnam, 2014.
- [2] "Housing Law No. 65/2014/QH13," Vietnam, 2014.
- [3] "Amending and supplementing a number of articles of the Law on Construction No. 62/2020/QH14," presented at the National Assembly of Vietnam Conference, Vietnam, 2020, pp. 15–28.
- [4] "Consolidated document No. 02/VBHN-VPQH of the Office of the National Assembly on Construction Law," presented at the National Assembly of Vietnam Conference, Vietnam, 2020, pp. 36–52.
- [5] "Consolidated document No. 01/VBHN-BXD of the Office of the National Assembly consolidating the Decree guiding the Housing Law," presented at the Ministry of Construction Conference, Vietnam, 2021, pp. 16–17.
- [6] "Decree No. 180/2007/N-CP Detailing and guiding the implementation of a number of articles of the Construction Law on handling violations of urban construction order," Government of Vietnam, 2007.
- [7] "Circular No. 39/2009/TT-BXD Guidance on quality management of individual housing construction," Ministry of Construction, Vietnam, 2009.
- [8] "Decision No. 28/2021/QĐ-UBND Promulgating the Regulation on decentralization of a number of contents on appraisal, organization of construction investment project management and construction work quality management in Ha Tinh province," People's Committee, Vietnam, 2021.
- [9] D. S. Jarallah and A. M. R. Mahjoob, "Supply Chain Management of Infrastructure Projects in Iraq," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8611–8616, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4904>.
- [10] C. P. Pham, P. T. Nguyen, and P. T. Phan, "Application of the Grey System Theory in Construction Management: A Case Study of Construction Paint Supplier Evaluation and Selection Criteria," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9087–9091, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5145>.
- [11] F. Khan, A. Ahmed, M. Ahmed, and M. a. U. Baig, "An Evaluation of Cost Optimization Strategies for BRT Projects in Pakistan," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8825–8830, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4956>.
- [12] M. Naghel, A. Farhi, and A. Redjem, "Household Waste Management Challenges: The Case of M'sila, Algeria," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 8675–8682, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4925>.
- [13] Q. K. Nguyen, "Researching solutions to improve the quality of construction survey and design work at the consulting center of Giong Rieng district," MSc Thesis, Thuy Loi University, 2019.
- [14] T. T. P. Nguyen, M. N. Doan, and K. N. Vo, "Study on the experience of some countries on housing management - Applying it in Tien Giang province," *Ho Chi Minh Open University Journal of Science*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 61–64, 2021.
- [15] D. Clapham, "Housing Theory, Housing Research and Housing Policy," *Housing, Theory and Society*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 163–177, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2017.1366937>.
- [16] H. Ruonavaara, "Theory of Housing, From Housing, About Housing," *Housing, Theory and Society*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 178–192, Apr. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14036096.2017.1347103>.
- [17] B. H. Şahin and A. Tereci, "Survey on the User Satisfaction with the Mass Housing Projects Led by District Municipality: Konya-Karatay Example," *Gazi University Journal of Science*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 679–693, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.35378/gujs.765147>.
- [18] X. Bonnefoy, "Inadequate housing and health: an overview," *International Journal of Environment and Pollution*, vol. 30, no. 3–4, pp. 411–429, Jan. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEP.2007.014819>.
- [19] V. T. Pham, "Situations on individual housing projects in Ha Tinh province," Department of Construction, Ha Tinh, Vietnam, 2020.

Compression Behavior of FFF Printed Parts Obtained by Varying Layer Height and Infill Percentage

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Abstract—In this research, two polymeric materials, PLA (polylactic acid) and ABS (acrylonitrile butadiene styrene) were used to 3D print compression samples at 3 layer heights (0.10, 0.15, and 0.20mm) with 3 infill percentages (50%, 75%, 100%). In order to determine the material's behavior under applied crushing loads, 135 samples were fabricated and tested. The built compression PLA specimens were subjected to common annealing treatment just above glass transition temperature and it was proved that the set of 45 samples exhibited higher resistance to the compressive load applied to the material before fracturing by an average of 9.20%.

Keywords—3D printing; annealing; compressive test; post-processing treatments

I. INTRODUCTION

Additive manufacturing has a wide range of applications and the advantage of specific application tailored part fabrication. The most common additive layer by layer technology is FFF (Fused Filament Fabrication), which consists in successively depositing filaments layer by layer. In order to meet the physical and mechanical requirements various additive manufacturing processes have been developed and a wide variety of materials have been used and studied with emphasis on compression tests (NiTi shape memory alloys processed via the laser-based directed energy deposition technique [1], fiber-reinforced PLA/TPU (thermoplastic polyurethane) [2], polymeric materials [3, 4], Ni-rich NiTi alloys [5], PA-12 nylons produced by multi-jet fusion technology [6]). Regarding tension or compression loading, significant functional risks are generated by the microstructure of 3D printed materials, characterized by an important degree of anisotropy [1]. However, industrial manufacturing processes aim to eliminate waste and to obtain higher stress, flexibility, and energy absorption. So, besides considering full volume

structures, recent researchers make reference on lattice structures [6-9]. Additive manufacturing offers the opportunity to design and create various configurations of lattice structures by controlling relative densities, material components, and microstructure [6, 7, 10]. Similar to subtractive technologies [11-13], several post treatments can be applied to additive manufactured parts depending on the processes used, with the aim to partially reduce porosity and relief internal stress. In this context, the present paper presents compression test results also on a set of PLA samples subjected to thermal treatment [1, 6] that consists in heating materials at a temperature between the glass transition and melting point temperature and by slow cooling in the oven.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Parameter Set Up

Significant 3D printing parameters have been analyzed in the recent scientific literature:

- raster orientation and printing speed [14],
- layer height and infill percentage [15-18],
- building orientation: flat, on edge, and upright oriented [19, 20].

For this research, the considered parameters were the layer height and the infill percentage, their values are shown in Table I. The material specifications were provided through manufacturers' data sheets and are also depicted in Table I. In this experimental study, the samples were fabricated with three infill percentages, i.e. 50%, 75%, 100% and in order to assess the mechanical characteristics (Table II), compressive tests were conducted made on both considered materials (PLA and ABS). For PLA polymer heat treatment was experimented in order to compare the compressive stress values. The annealing

treatment for PLA consisted in maintaining a temperature of 75°C for a period of 3h, succeeded by slow cooling in the oven.

B. Sample Preparation

A Raise E2 3D printer was used to fabricate the samples with a volume capacity of 330×240×240mm. The design of the samples, later converted in STL format, was drawn in Solid Edge Software [21] and the slicing parameters, such as internal structure pattern, infill percentage, and layer thickness were adjusted in the Idea Maker software. Samples were X-Z orientated and printed with a bed platform for better adhesion to the printing table as shown in Figure 1.

TABLE I. PRINTED SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS

Parameters	Material specifications	
	PLA	ABS
Nozzle diameter	0.40mm	0.40mm
Build orientation	Flat	Flat
Top solid layers	4 layers	4 layers
Bottom solid layers	4 layers	4 layers
Outline/perimeters shell	3 outlines	3 outlines
Internal fill pattern	Lines	Lines
External fill pattern	Rectilinear	Rectilinear
Internal infill angle offsets	45°-135°	45°-135°
Extruder temperature	210°C	240°C
Heated bed temperature	60°C	110°C
Default printing speed	70mm/s	45mm/s
Cooling fans	on	on
Filament diameter	1.75mm	1.75mm
Filament density	1.24g/cm ³	1.04g/cm ³

TABLE II. 3D PRINTED INFILL PARAMETERS

Constant parameters	Variable parameters		Materials		
	Layer height (H _s -mm)	Infill percentage (P _u -%)	ABS	PLA AS	PLA AN
Building orientation X, Y	0.10	50	15	15	15
Extrusion temperature (T _e)			15	15	15
Bed temperature (T _p)	0.15	75	15	15	15
Speed (V _p)	0.20	100	15	15	15
Filling model			15	15	15

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Sample pictures: (a) as built PLA, (b) annealed PLA.

The samples were tested on a Zwick Roell Universal Machine to obtain their compressive stress values. The preload was 20N and the test speed was 10mm/min, according to Plastics — Determination of compressive properties, ISO 604:2002(E) [21].

C. Compressive Test

Sets of 5 specimens were printed for each of the characteristics considered in the current study, as can be seen in Figure 2. The compression tests were done at the Liea laboratory, within ISIM Timișoara, on a MU 400Kn testing machine, type ZD 40/90.

Fig. 2. Geometrical features of the compressive test samples.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Values and averages of compressive stress are depicted in Tables III-V for each combination of layer height and infill percentage for the as built PLA.

TABLE III. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF AS BUILT PLA FOR 0.10 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	34	35	34	35	35	34.6
75%	48	48	47	46	46	47
100%	64	62	66	67	98	71.4

TABLE IV. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF AS BUILT PLA FOR 0.15 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	32	33	31	32	31	31.80
75%	45	45	47	46	45	45.6
100%	65	63	63	63	61	63

TABLE V. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF AS BUILT PLA FOR 0.20 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	30	30	32	32	29	30.6
75%	43	43	44	43	43	43.2
100%	59	59	60	59	61	59.6

As can be seen in Tables VI-VIII, the compressive stress values of the annealed tested samples are higher, which reveals that annealing has a positive effect in the microstructure of the material, by releasing internal stress and decreasing the porosity of the parts obtained by 3D printing. The thermal annealing post-process technique applied for improving properties of polymer extrusion-based parts has been intensively studied recently [1, 5, 6].

TABLE VI. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF ANNEALED PLA FOR 0.10 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	39	38	29	39	38	36.6
75%	52	50	52	51	52	51.4
100%	67	67	69	67	66	67.2

TABLE VII. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF ANNEALED PLA FOR 0.15 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	35	36	37	36	37	36.2
75%	53	52	52	51	51	51.8
100%	71	72	71	71	71	71.2

TABLE VIII. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF ANNEALED PLA FOR 0.20 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	37	33	34	35	34	34.6
75%	47	47	47	48	48	47.4
100%	69	65	64	64	65	65.4

TABLE IX. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF ABS FOR 0.10 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	21	22	21	22	23	21.8
75%	60	50	31	55	52	49.6
100%	61	60	63	61	62	61.4

TABLE X. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF ABS FOR 0.15 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	26	26	27	22	24	25
75%	42	42	46	43	47	44
100%	68	62	33	60	54	55.4

TABLE XI. COMPRESSIVE STRESS TEST VALUES OF ABS FOR 0.20 THICKNESS LAYER

Infill, %	Compressive Stress, MPa					
	Sample					
	1	2	3	4	5	Average
50%	31	31	27	31	23	28.6
75%	26	26	45	25	44	33.2
100%	66	18	60	61	60	53

Similar average compression stress results with [20] were obtained for 50% infill: 34.67MPa and 43.67MPa and for 100% infill: 71MPa and 93.34MPa. Values and averages of compressive stress for ABS samples are depicted in Tables IX-XI for each combination of layer height and infill percentage studied in this research. As shown in [23], compressive stress values are scattered due to the variation of the process parameters like orientation, layer thickness, raster angle, raster width, and air gap with an average of 14.63MPa comparable

with 50% average ABS values - 21.8MPa. Significant influences regarding the infill percentage can be noticed in the drawn stress-strain curves of as built PLA, annealed PLA, and ABS sample. As assumed, 100% infill percentage samples have the greatest resistance to compressive stress.

Fig. 3. Compressive stress variation of 0.10 layer thickness of as built PLA.

Fig. 4. Compressive stress variation of 0.10 layer thickness of annealed PLA.

Fig. 5. Compressive stress variation of 0.15 layer thickness of as built PLA.

As can be seen in Figures 3-8 the curves of the annealed set of samples have clearly higher compressive stress supported in the case of failure. The percentage of the average increase in compressive stress of the thermal treated PLA with 0.10mm layer thickness is 3.70%, for the 0.15mm layer thickness the average increase is 13.39%, and for the 0.20mm layer thickness the increase is 10.49%. It is noted that the compressive strength values of the annealed PLA are higher than those of plain PLA (Tables III-VIII). This can be explained by the influence of the annealing treatment that led to the homogenization of the structure and the increase of the adhesion of the deposited layers.

Analyzing the force-deformation diagrams (Figures 3-11) obtained by the test machine following the compression load, the following areas of the load-specific curve can be observed:

- A linear zone - characteristic of the behavior of the material in the elastic domain.
- A convex curve - which corresponds to the yield strength.
- A constant level - which corresponds to the flow zone at which the force remains relatively constant, the deformation increasing significantly.

Fig. 6. Compressive stress variation of 0.15 layer thickness of annealed PLA.

Fig. 7. Compressive stress variation of 0.20 layer thickness of as built PLA.

Fig. 8. Compressive stress variation of 0.20 layer thickness of annealed PLA.

After a slight increase in the compression force, the breaking phenomenon occurs (cracks appear in the material structure). This is marked on machine-drawn diagrams by a peak. Then a decrease in force with a minimum is noted on the diagram after which the force increases significantly. This growth is probably produced due to the compaction of the

material after the cracks appear. Regarding the ABS material, similar results are revealed in Figures 9-11. Also, the infill percentage has a great emphasis in the character of the stress-strain curves. The curves for ABS with 0.10 layer thickness reveal more instable graphics than the other layer thickness samples, that can be the result of a more brittle behavior also noticed in the tensile behavior studied in [15-18, 24, 25].

Fig. 9. Compressive stress variation of 0.10 layer thickness ABS.

Fig. 10. Compressive stress variation of 0.15 layer thickness ABS.

Fig. 11. Compressive stress variation of 0.20 layer thickness ABS.

B. Discussion

This paper aims to highlight the variation of mechanical characteristics (compressive stress) of annealed PLA 3D and ABS, with different parameters of the printing process. The general mechanical properties of plastics have been introduced to facilitate comparison with other classes of materials or with the same materials but having different chemical compositions. The study presents the experimentally determined values for the compression test of ABS and two types of PLA. The initial mechanical characteristics of the tested materials correspond to the specifications of the filament manufacturers (PLA-Raise and ABS-Verbatim) shown in Table I.

The research plan consisted in fabricating the samples on a Raise E2 3D printer. The considered variable research parameters were infill degree (50, 75, 100%) and layer thickness (0.10, 0.15, 0.20mm). The samples were compression tested on a Zwick Roell universal machine. The preload was 20N, and the test was performed at a speed of 10mm/min, according to ISO 604:2002(E) determination of compression properties. The shape of the researched samples is parallelepiped (Figure 2), having a square cross-section of 10×10mm and 20 mm height. Due to the elasticity of the researched materials, it was adopted that the length (height) of the test piece should be twice the side of the square.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In the case of a plastic material that does not yield in compression by a break (crack), the compressive strength is arbitrary, depending on the degree of distortion that is considered to indicate complete failure of the material. Situations may arise where plastic specimens will continue to deform in compression until they are reduced to a flat disk, the (nominal) compressive stress increasing steadily, without any well-defined material cracking. For this research, the failure criterion was considered the appearance of cracks on the surface of the studied specimen. According to the experimental research carried out, for one type of material (PLA, ABS) if the thickness of the deposited layer is kept constant with the increase of the degree of filling, the magnitude of the compression stresses increased (Tables III-V). This can be explained by the higher rigidity of the structure formed by 3D printing. To sum up, for each material type (PLA, ABS) and at the same degree of filling, the increase in the thickness of the deposited layer leads to a decrease of the magnitude of the compressive stress (Tables III-V). This can be explained by cracking at the level of the structural blocks, having a height equal to the thickness of the deposited layer.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. A. Bimber, R. F. Hamilton, J. Keist, and T. A. Palmer, "Anisotropic microstructure and superelasticity of additive manufactured NiTi alloy bulk builds using laser directed energy deposition," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 674, pp. 125–134, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2016.07.059>.
- [2] N. Narlıoğlu, "Comparison of mechanical properties of 3D-printed and compression-molded wood-poly(lactic acid) (PLA) composites :: BioResources," *BioResources*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 3291–3302, 2022.
- [3] A. Hrituc *et al.*, "Mechanical Behaviour of 3D Printed PLA Hollow Spherical Parts Under Axial Compression," *Materiale Plastice*, vol. 57, no. 1, pp. 13–20, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.37358/MP.20.1.5307>.
- [4] S. Brischetto and R. Torre, "Tensile and Compressive Behavior in the Experimental Tests for PLA Specimens Produced via Fused Deposition Modelling Technique," *Journal of Composites Science*, vol. 4, no. 3, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 140, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcs4030140>.
- [5] R. F. Hamilton, B. A. Bimber, and T. A. Palmer, "Correlating microstructure and superelasticity of directed energy deposition additive manufactured Ni-rich NiTi alloys," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 739, pp. 712–722, Mar. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2017.12.270>.
- [6] M. Ali, R. K. Sari, U. Sajjad, M. Sultan, and H. M. Ali, "Effect of annealing on microstructures and mechanical properties of PA-12 lattice structures proceeded by multi jet fusion technology," *Additive Manufacturing*, vol. 47, Nov. 2021, Art. no. 102285, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2021.102285>.
- [7] M. Saleh, S. Anwar, A. M. Al-Ahmari, and A. Alfaify, "Compression Performance and Failure Analysis of 3D-Printed Carbon Fiber/PLA Composite TPMS Lattice Structures," *Polymers*, vol. 14, no. 21, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 4595, <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym14214595>.
- [8] M. Minescu and D. G. Zisopol, *Sudarea țevilor și fittingurilor din polietilenă de înaltă densitate (HDPE Pipe & Fittings Welding)*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol-Gaze din Ploiești, 2021.
- [9] D. G. Zisopol and A. Dumitrescu, *Ecotehnologie. Studii ce caz*. Ploiesti, Romania: Editura Universității Petrol-Gaze din Ploiești, 2020.
- [10] D. G. Zisopol, A. Dumitrescu, and C. N. Trifan, *Ecotehnologie: Noțiuni teoretice, aplicații și studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania, 2010.
- [11] D. G. Zisopol and M. J. Săvulescu, *Bazele tehnologiei*. Ploiesti, Romania, 2003.
- [12] D. G. Zisopol, *Tehnologii industriale și de construcții, Aplicații practice și studii de caz*. Ploiesti, Romania, 2003.
- [13] M. J. Săvulescu and D. G. Zisopol, *Tehnologii industriale și de construcții*. Ploiesti, Romania, 2002.
- [14] M. R. Khosravani, F. Berto, M. R. Ayatollahi, and T. Reinicke, "Characterization of 3D-printed PLA parts with different raster orientations and printing speeds," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 12, no. 1, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 1016, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-05005-4>.
- [15] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Theoretical and Experimental Research on the Influence of FDM Parameters on Tensile Strength and Hardness of Parts Made of Poly(lactic Acid)," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 7458–7463, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4311>.
- [16] D. G. Zisopol, I. Nae, A. I. Portoaca, and I. Ramadan, "A Statistical Approach of the Flexural Strength of PLA and ABS 3D Printed Parts," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 8248–8252, Apr. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4739>.
- [17] A. Portoaca, I. Nae, D. G. Zisopol, and I. Ramadan, "Studies on the influence of FFF parameters on the tensile properties of samples made of ABS," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1235, no. 1, Nov. 2022, Art. no. 012008, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1235/1/012008>.
- [18] D. G. Zisopol, A. I. Portoaca, I. Nae, and I. Ramadan, "A Comparative Analysis of the Mechanical Properties of Annealed PLA," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8978–8981, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5123>.
- [19] J. M. Chacón, M. A. Caminero, E. García-Plaza, and P. J. Núñez, "Additive manufacturing of PLA structures using fused deposition modelling: Effect of process parameters on mechanical properties and their optimal selection," *Materials & Design*, vol. 124, pp. 143–157, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2017.03.065>.
- [20] Z. Mehdiyev, C. Felhő, and K. P. Zoltán, "Investigation on 3D Printing Parameters of PLA Polymers for Gear Applications," in *Vehicle and Automotive Engineering 4*, 2023, pp. 654–664, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-15211-5_55.
- [21] *ISO 604:2002 - Plastics — Determination of compressive properties*. ISO, 2002.
- [22] "3D CAD Design Software | SOLIDWORKS." <https://www.solidworks.com/>.
- [23] A. K. Sood, R. K. Ohdar, and S. S. Mahapatra, "Experimental investigation and empirical modelling of FDM process for compressive strength improvement," *Journal of Advanced Research*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 81–90, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2011.05.001>.
- [24] R. A. Cláudio, J. Dupont, R. Baptista, M. Leite, and L. Reis, "Behaviour evaluation of 3D printed poly(lactic acid) under compression," *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, vol. 21, pp. 4052–4066, Nov. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2022.10.042>.
- [25] D. G. Zisopol, D. V. Iacob, and A. I. Portoaca, "A Theoretical-Experimental Study of the Influence of FDM Parameters on PLA Spur Gear Stiffness," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9329–9335, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5183>.

One-Dimension Finite Element Modeling of Grouted Ground Anchor

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Abstract-In the present research work, a one-dimension finite element model has been developed to simulate both compression and tension types of grouted ground anchors. The steel tendon-grout interface has been modeled by using the local bond-slip model, while the soil-grout interface has been modeled with a series of perfectly elastic plastic springs. The verification of the proposed one-dimension finite element model has been made by comparison of the model results with a three-dimension finite element model developed by commercial finite element software PLAXIS, and with the results of field tests of tension-type grouted ground anchor. A parametric study has been made to study the load-transfer mechanism for both types of anchors, compression, and tension. The compression-type anchor exhibits less displacement than the tension one under the same applied load. The developed strain in the grouted body of the compression-type anchor is much smaller than the tension-type one, regardless of the type of strain.

Keywords-ground anchor; finite element; sandy soil; compression anchor; grout

I. INTRODUCTION

One dimensional finite element modeling has been widely used to model pile foundations with all types of loadings, i.e. axial, lateral, and torsional [1-3]. A pile foundation is modeled by dividing it into a certain number of elements, the type of which depends on the geometry of the problem, loading type, and boundary conditions. Two noded bar elements, with one degree of freedom per node, can be used effectively in axial loading conditions in both compression and tension. The soil resistance is modeled by using linear or nonlinear springs connected to every node. The grouted ground anchor could be modeled by the same method of pile foundation modeling, with adjustments due to differences between the two geotechnical

elements.

Many researchers have used one-dimension finite elements to model the grouted ground anchor. Authors in [4, 5] presented a one-dimensional finite element model of the compression grouted ground anchor pull-out test. Two noded bar elements with one degree of freedom in the axial direction at each node have been used to simulate the grouted body. Since the anchor is a compression type, i.e. the grouted body is always subjected to compression stress, a linear elastic model is used to model the grout. According to the loading mechanism of the compression anchor, the point of load application is located at the bottom node of the grouted body, so the strand has not been involved in the finite element model. The surrounding soil has been simulated by a nonlinear spring model governed by a (t-z) hyperbolic relation. Authors in [6] used a one-dimension finite element to simulate an instrumented field test of grouted ground anchor. Spring elements have been used to model separately the strands and the grout. Along the free length of the anchor, there are no connections between the adjacent nodes of the strand and the grout, while these nodes have been connected along the bonded length of the anchor, to model the bond between the strand and the grout, by using the damage model proposed in [7, 8]. According to it, the interface stiffness decreases as the relative displacement between adjacent nodes of strand and grout increases. The surrounding soil has been modeled by linear elastic springs connected to the nodes of the grout elements. This model was used because the strength of the surrounding soil in the field test has not reached its peak strength. Steel strand behavior has been modeled as linear elastic. The grout under compression has been modeled as linear elastic, while it has been considered to have zero stiffness under tension.

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II. FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

A finite element model has been developed to simulate the tension-type and the compression-type ground anchors in this work. Two noded rod elements have been used to model the grouted body along the free and bonded lengths. Each node has one degree of freedom in the axial direction. The tendon has been modeled along the bonded length only, by using the same element that has been used to simulate the bonded length of the grouted body. The stiffness of the bar element for both grout and tendon is calculated by using (1) and (2):

$$[K_e]_{grout} = \frac{(EA)_{grout}}{l} \times \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$[K_e]_{tendon} = \frac{(EA)_{tendon}}{l} \times \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where l is the length of the element, E is the modulus of elasticity, and A is the cross-section area respectively, for both grouted body and tendon according to the subscript.

Fig. 1. One-dimensional finite element modelling of ground anchor, A: tension type and B: compression type.

The stiffness of the bonded length is the summation of the stiffnesses of the grout and the tendon, as shown in (3). The tendon along the free length is not considered, as the load application point is located at the top end of the bonded length, for tension anchor type, as shown in Figure 1. For compression-type anchors, the load application point is located at the toe of the anchor, and the total length of the anchor is considered a free length. The stiffness of the element along the free length is only the grout stiffness, as shown in (4). The load is applied at the top node of bonded length in the case of the tension anchor, while the load is applied at the tip node of the anchor model. Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the one-dimensional finite element model for tension and compression types of ground anchors.

$$[K_e]_{bonded} = [K]_{grout} + [K]_{tendon} \quad (3)$$

$$[K_e]_{free} = [K]_{grout} \quad (4)$$

A. Soil-Grout Interface Modeling

The interface between soil and grouted body is modeled using a nonlinear spring connected to all the grouted body nodes to represent the soil's reaction forces. Elastic perfectly plastic (t-z) relation for sandy soils, suggested by the American Petroleum Institute [9], is used to represent the nonlinearity of soil springs. An elastic-perfectly plastic model has been used to simulate the pile shaft resistance, [2, 9-12]. It has been also used to model the grout-soil interface in grouted ground anchors [6, 13-15]. As shown in Figure 2, the y axis represents a percent of the mobilized shear stress along with the anchor-soil interface τ to maximum shear stress (τ_{max}), which is calculated by [16]:

$$\tau_{max} = \sigma_v \times K \times \tan \varphi \quad (5)$$

where σ_v is the vertical effective stress, K is the coefficient of lateral earth pressure, and φ is the angle of internal friction of the soil. φ was used instead of the interface angle between the grout and the soil δ , because δ is equal to φ in a good construction method and cast in place concrete to provide a rough grout interface, [17, 18].

The value of K is estimated based on field tests. It ranges from 1 to 2 for coarse silt and fine sand to dense sand and gravel, with grouting pressure less than 10 bar [19]. The stiffnesses of soil springs are added to the global stiffness matrix, as shown in (6):

$$[K]_{global} = [K]_{global} + [K]_{spring} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 2. (t-z) Load transfer relation for sand, (after API, 2005).

B. Grout Modeling

Due to the similarity of the grout material with the concrete material, the stress-strain relation of the concrete under uniaxial compression, suggested by European Standards [20] has been used to model the grouted body under compression. Figure 3 shows the used constitutive model of grout under uniaxial compression. Equations (7)-(13) describe the adopted model.

$$\sigma_c = f_{cm} \left(\frac{k\eta - \eta^2}{1 + (k-2)\eta} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$k = \frac{1.05 \times E_{cm} |\epsilon_{c1}|}{f_{cm}} \quad (8)$$

$$\eta = \frac{\epsilon_c}{\epsilon_{c1}} \quad (9)$$

$$f_{cm}(\text{MPa}) = f_{ck} + 8 \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_{cu1}(\%) = 0.35, \quad \text{for } f_{ck} \leq 50\text{MPa} \quad (11)$$

$$\epsilon_{c1}(\%) = 0.07 \times f_{cm}^{0.31} \leq 0.28\% \quad (12)$$

$$E_{cm} = 22 \left[\frac{f_{cm}}{10} \right]^{0.3} \quad (13)$$

where f_{ck} is the cylinder compression strength at 28 days, in MPa, f_{cm} is the mean of cylinder compressive strength, and all the other parameters are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Constitutive model of grout under compression, (after BS EN 1992-1-1:2004).

A linear elastic constitutive relation has been used to model the grout material under tension stresses before reaching the initial crack. The cracking strain of the grout under tension is about (1×10^{-4}) [21, 22]. The grout stiffness is ignored after reaching the cracking strain.

C. Strand-GROUT Interface Model

The grout-tendon interface is modeled by the local bond stress-slip model for a smooth bar [23], under tension stresses, along the bonded length of the anchor. The adopted model is shown in Figure 4 for smooth bars. Equations (14)-(16) describe the adopted strand-grout interface model.

Fig. 4. Local bond stress-slip model for smooth bar, after Ceb Fip, 1990.

$$\tau = \tau_{max} (s/s_1)^\alpha, \quad \text{for } 0 \leq s \leq s_1 \quad (14)$$

$$\tau = \tau_{max}, \quad \text{for } s > s_1 \quad (15)$$

$$\tau_{max} = \tau_f = 0.3 \sqrt{f_{ck}} \quad (16)$$

where τ is the shear stress between grout and bar, τ_{max} is the maximum shear stress between the grout and the bar, which is equal to τ_f , which is the residual shear stress after slippage occurs, s is the relative displacement between the grout and the bar, s_1 is the relative displacement at τ_{max} ($s_1=0.1\text{mm}$), f_{ck} is the cube strength of the grout, and $\alpha=0.5$.

The finite element formulation of the strand-grout interface model is made by modifying the applied load vector, according to the relative displacement, and the shear stress between the strand and the grout is calculated according to (14)-(16). The main applied load is reduced by $(\sum_{i=1}^n F_i)$, where n is the number of elements that the slip of the occurred strand-grout interface, and F is the strand-grout interface force which is calculated from:

$$F_i = \tau_i \times A \quad (17)$$

$$A = P_s \times L_{element} \quad (18)$$

$$P_s = m \times \left[\frac{D_s \times \pi \times Num_s}{2} \right] \quad (19)$$

where τ is the shear stress between the strand and the grout, i refers to the number of elements that the slip has occurred, A is the total outside area of all strands surrounding the grout, P_s is the outer perimeter of the strand wires, as shown in Figure 5, $L_{element}$ is element length, m is the number of strands used in the grouted ground anchor, D_s is the diameter of the strand outer single wire, (which is typically equal to 5mm), and Num_s is the number of outer wires in the single strand as illustrated in Figure 5.

Each interface force calculated from (17) is applied to the specified element at the end of each node, and one-half force is applied to each node. The location of the main applied force is changed according to the last element in which the slippage does not occur, i.e. magnitude, number, and location of the applied load are changed according to the bond-slip model between the strand and the surrounding grout, as shown in Figure 6. The interlock between grout and strand group due to using centralizers and spacers ([24]) is neglected.

Fig. 5. Section in the strand and outer perimeter of outer wires.

In the case of a compression anchor, there is no connection between the grout and tendon under compression stress (unbonded length of the anchor).

D. Nonlinearity Procedure

The nonlinear behavior of interface spring has been achieved by using the direct iteration method as shown in Figure 7. In this method, the stiffness will be modified in each iteration as described in the algorithm below [25].

Fig. 6. Change of loads locations and magnitude according to the slip model for tension anchor.

Fig. 7. Direct iteration method.

The following steps illustrate the iteration procedure used to calculate the stiffness of the soil interface, see Figure 8:

- Calculation of the initial stiffness of soil spring using [26]:

$$K_{S_initial} = \frac{2\pi L \check{G}}{\zeta} \quad (20)$$

where L is the length of the element, \check{G} is the average shear modulus at the node depth, $\zeta = \ln\left(\frac{2r_m}{d}\right)$, r_m is the max. radius at which soil deformation is very small and it could be neglected, and d is the anchor grouted body diameter.

- Adding the calculated above initial stiffness of soil spring, to the global stiffness matrix, as presented in (6).

Fig. 8. Flow chart of the iteration loop of soil spring calculation.

- Solving the finite element equation to obtain the nodal displacement (21):

$$\{\delta\}_i = [K]_{global}^{-1} \times \{f\} \quad (21)$$

- Using the nodal displacement obtained in the third step to obtain the shear stress of anchor skin at the node depth from the (t-z) curve. Nodal force is calculated by multiplying the shear stress with the side surface area of the grouted body between the centers of adjacent elements $\{A\}$, as presented in (22):

$$\{f\}_i = \{\tau\}_i \times \{A\} \quad (22)$$

- Calculating a new spring stiffness:

$$[K_{spring}]_i = \{f\}_i / \{\delta\}_i \quad (23)$$

- Adding the calculated spring stiffness to the global stiffness matrix as in (6).
- Repeat steps 3 to 6 to find the nodal displacement $\{\delta\}_{i+1}$.
- Comparing the difference between two successive calculated displacements with the convergence criterion, as in (24):

$$|\{\delta\}_{i+1} - \{\delta\}_i| \leq error \quad (24)$$

As long as the convergence criterion doesn't match, steps 3 to 6 shall be repeated until reaching the maximum number of trials, which have been chosen to be 10^3 .

E. Boundary Conditions

All nodes of the model have one degree of freedom in the vertical direction, which is the direction of the force application and no movements are allowed in the other directions. In the case of an existing structure at the head of the anchor, like the retaining structure or foundation, node no. 1 will be restricted in the vertical direction.

F. Failure Criteria

The failure criteria of the grouted ground anchor are considered below. They take place first in each element, according to the models explained previously:

- Debonding between grout and soil.
- Debonding between grout and tendon.
- Crushing of the grouted body under both tension and compression stresses.
- Tendon failure, by reaching the yield strength of the strand.

G. Development of Algorithms and Verifications

Fortran 90 programming language has been used to code the finite element algorithm, both the pre-processing and equation solver parts, to model the one-dimensional simulation of the ground anchor. Finite element FORTRAN 90 subroutines [27] have been used to build the present finite element algorithm, as described in Table I. Open-source Code Blocks (Release 20.03) IDE platform has been used to compile and run the Fortran finite element code.

TABLE I. FORTRAN 90 SUBROUTINES USED [27]

Subroutine	Purpose
formnf	Forms nodal freedom array
num_to_g	Forms element connectivity vector
fkdiag	Forms the bandwidth vector according to the skyline storage system
rod_km	Forms the stiffness matrix of the rod element
fsparv	Solve the finite element equation system using Cholesky's factorization method
sparin	
spabac	

1) 3-D Plaxis Model Verification

The finite element code has been verified with another finite element solution of grouted ground anchor to verify both the pre-processing and the equation solver. The verification is achieved by using a 3-D finite element model of the ground anchor by PLAXIS software [28]. This model is presented in PLAXIS verification manual for verifications purposes. The properties of the ground anchor model are listed below, as stated in PLAXIS verification manual.

The fixed length is 4m and the free length is 5m, which means that the total length of the anchor is 9m. The strand property is $E_A=4.095 \times 10^3$ kN. The pullout force is estimated to be 752kN [29]. The maximum skin friction along the bonded

length is obtained by dividing the pullout force by the bonded length (188kN/m). The skin friction is assumed to be uniform along the bonded length. Despite this unrealistic assumption, it has been adopted in the developed model for verification purposes. The diameter of the grouted body is 0.125m, with a modulus of elasticity equal to ($E=2.0 \times 10^7$ kN/m²).

The elements used are: 180 bar elements, with equal length of 0.05m. The load-displacement curves of the grouted body proximal end, presented in Figure 9, show very good agreement between the two models. This agreement gives validation for the developed finite element algorithm to be used in the modeling of the grouted ground anchors.

Fig. 9. Load-displacement curves for the proximal end of the verification model of the ground anchor.

2) Field Tests Modeling of the Tension Anchors

The proposed finite element model has been used to simulate pullout tests of three tension-type ground anchors constructed vertically in An-Najaf city in Iraq [30, 31]. The performance test is adopted for all the tested anchors according to the Post Tension Institute [30]. Anchors were trial anchors, they were tested to evaluate their pullout capacity for design purposes. All the tested anchors have a borehole diameter of 150mm and a strand steel area of 560mm². Strain gauges were instrumented along the grouted body of anchor no. (1), therefore, the developed strains were measured, and internal forces were calculated from these measurements. All the tested anchors did not reach failure load which makes the prediction of failure load inaccurate. Instead of that, the safe working load has been determined.

The soil profile and corrected SPT number with depth, for the test site, are shown in Figure 10. The first three trial anchors were installed at the natural ground level, while the other five anchors were installed at 8m below the natural ground. Low grouting pressure was used for grouting all the tested anchors (10kPa=0.1bar) [32]. The properties of tested anchors with the number of elements used for each anchor model are listed in Table II. The modulus of elasticity for the strand is ($E_s=200 \times 10^3$ MPa), while the modulus of elasticity of the grout is calculated according to (25) [33], which is equal to $E_g=22.044 \times 10^3$ MPa.

$$E_g = 4700 \times \sqrt{f_c} \quad (25)$$

TABLE II. PROPERTIES OF TESTED GROUND ANCHORS

Anchor no.	Bonded length (m)	Unbonded length (m)	Unbonded length from the pullout point* (m)	Total embedded length (m)	No. of elements used in the FE models
1	7	3.6	5.2	10.6	212
2	7	5.9	7.2	12.9	258
3	7.5	6	7.3	13.5	270

Figures (11)-(13) show the total displacement of the anchor head vs the applied load for the measured model and the finite element. The displacement consists of the following components:

- Elastic elongation of the tendon free length.
- Elastic displacement of anchor grouted body.
- Plastic displacement of anchor grouted body.

displacement while the calculated one, through the finite element, represents both plastic and elastic components of the anchor head displacement. Through Figures 11-13, a very good agreement could be noticed between the measured and calculated displacement, taking into account that the elastic elongation of the tendon free length represents around (80%) of the total displacement.

Fig. 10. Soil profile and corrected SPT (N_{60}) values for the test site.

Fig. 12. Load-displacement curves for field test and finite element model anchor (2).

Fig. 13. Load-displacement curves for field test and finite element model anchor (3).

Fig. 11. Load-displacement curves for field test and finite element model anchor (1).

Fig. 14. Strain along the grout of the anchor body.

Comparison with only residual displacement is not possible in the present case, because the measured displacement represents only the plastic component of the anchor head

Figure 14 presents the measured strain along the grout under four loading steps vs the calculated (via finite element modeling) strains. The comparison between the measured and

the calculated strains shows good agreement in the bonded length part with underestimation of the peak point. There is an overestimation of the strain towards the anchor end. On the other hand, the calculated strain is less than the measured strain in the free length part.

III. PARAMETRIC STUDY

According to the previous verifications, the suggested 1-D finite element model is considered reasonably valid for producing parametric studies to investigate some properties of grouted ground anchors.

A. Compression Anchor

A comparative study has been made between compression-type and tension-type anchors, by using the exact data of surrounding soil and anchor properties of trial anchor (1). The applied load in the case of compression anchor is at the lowest node of the anchor's mesh, while it is at the proximal end of the bonded length in the case of tension anchor, as stated in Figure 1. Figure 15 shows the load-displacement curves for both tension and compression anchors. It is noticed that the displacement of the compression-type anchor is less than the half of the displacement of the tension-type one, because the compression stiffness of the grout member is much higher than the tension stiffness. The calculated displacement represents the elastic and plastic components of the anchor head regardless of the elastic elongation of the strand. Both anchors are reached to fully pull out at the same load (400kN), due to the adopted failure modes and grout-soil shear stress distribution as stated in (5).

Fig. 15. Load-displacement curves for compression and tension anchor types.

The calculated strains, for both compression and tension anchors, are presented in Figure 16. Obviously, in the tension anchor, the developed strains along the bonded length are tension strains, while its compression strains are along the unbonded length. The maximum value of strain is located at the loading point, at the beginning of the bonded length with shifting towards the anchor toe when the applied load has increased according to the adopted model of debonding between the strand and the grout, see (14)-(16). In the case of a compression anchor, all the developed strains along the anchor body are compression strains. The maximum value of strains is located at the anchor toe, i.e. the loading point, and it decreases until it vanishes at the anchor tip. The tension cracking strain of the grout, which is equal to 1×10^{-4} , has been reached and

exceeded since the 1st loading (100kN) in the case of the tension anchor, while the developed strains did not reach the maximum compression strain of grout (0.003) [34] for the maximum applied load.

A comparison of the mobilized skin friction between tension and compression types is shown in Figure (18). It could be noticed obviously that the compression anchor has a larger maximum mobilized skin friction value than the tension anchor. The distribution of skin friction along the anchor body is not similar for the two types of anchor under consideration, the location of maximum skin friction value is at the anchor toe in the case of compression anchor, while the location of the maximum point is shifted from the proximal end of the bonded length toward the anchor toe with increasing of loading in the case of the tension-type anchor. The total mobilized skin friction force of both types of anchors is approximately equal. The shifting process of skin friction peak point reflects the debonding process between the strand and the grout in bonded length.

Fig. 16. Strain in the grouted body for compression (dotted line) and tension (continuous line) anchors.

Fig. 17. Skin friction along anchor length, for compression-type (broken line), and tension-type (continuous line).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A one-dimensional finite element model was developed and used to simulate both tension and compression types of grouted ground anchors. The tendon (steel) grout interface was modeled using the local bond-slip model, while the surrounding soil was modeled using a series of perfectly plastic springs. Verification of the adopted finite element model was made by comparing the results with a three-dimensional finite element model of grouted ground anchor, developed in

PLAXIS, and with the result of field tests of grouted ground anchors. The developed one-dimensional finite element model was used to make a comparison between compression and tension types of grouted ground anchors. From the verification and both comparisons, the following conclusions can be made:

- Load-displacement curves show very good agreement between the developed model and the finite element three-dimensional model, showing very good agreement with the filed test result. The comparison between the calculated and measured strains in the field test results shows some differences along the unbonded length part, but with good agreement in the bonded length part.
- The displacement of anchor head is smaller in the case of compression anchor, which makes it bear high design load.
- The developed strain in the grouted body of the compression anchor is much smaller than the tension-type, which means less cracking in the grouted body providing additional corrosion protection.

REFERENCES:

- [1] C. S. Desai and T. Kuppusamy, "Application of a numerical procedure for laterally loaded structures," in *Numerical methods in offshore piling*, Atlanta, GA, USA: ICE Publishing, 1980, pp. 93–99.
- [2] M. Georgiadis, "Interaction between torsional and axial pile responses," *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 645–650, 1987, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nag.1610110609>.
- [3] C. S. Desai and M. Zaman, *Advanced Geotechnical Engineering: Soil-Structure Interaction using Computer and Material Models*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2013.
- [4] H. J. Seo and L. Pelecanos, "Finite element analysis of soil-structure interaction in soil anchor pull-out tests," in *Numerical Methods in Geotechnical Engineering IX*, Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2018.
- [5] H. J. Seo, G. Marketos, and L. Pelecanos, "Soil-structure interaction in field pull-out tests of soil anchors and additional resistance from the reaction plate," in *XVII European Conference on Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, Reykjavik, Iceland, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–8.
- [6] J. Smet, N. Huybrechts, G. V. Lysebetten, J. Verstraelen, and S. François, "Optical Fiber Strain Measurements and Numerical Modeling of Load Tests on Grouted Anchors," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 145, no. 12, Dec. 2019, Art. no. 04019103, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0002167](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0002167).
- [7] T. S. Phan, P. Rossi, and J.-L. Tailhan, "Numerical modelling of the concrete/rebar bond," *Cement and Concrete Composites*, vol. 59, pp. 1–9, May 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2015.02.003>.
- [8] A. Spada, G. Giambanco, and P. Rizzo, "Elastoplastic Damaging Model for Adhesive Anchor Systems. I: Theoretical Formulation and Numerical Implementation," *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, vol. 137, no. 12, pp. 854–861, Dec. 2011, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EM.1943-7889.0000287](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EM.1943-7889.0000287).
- [9] *Recommended Practice for Planning, Designing and Constructing Fixed Offshore Platforms—Working Stress Design*. Washington DC, USA: American Petroleum Institute, 2005.
- [10] E. Motta, "Approximate Elastic-Plastic Solution for Axially Loaded Piles," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 120, no. 9, pp. 1616–1624, Sep. 1994, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1994\)120:9\(1616\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1994)120:9(1616)).
- [11] D. A. Mangnejo, S. J. Oad, S. A. Kalhor, S. Ahmed, F. H. Laghari, and Z. A. Siyal, "Numerical Analysis of Soil Slope Stabilization by Soil Nailing Technique," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4469–4473, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2859>.
- [12] P. H. V. Nguyen and P. C. Nguyen, "Effects of Shaft Grouting on the Bearing Behavior of Barrette Piles: A Case Study in Ho Chi Minh City," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7653–7657, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4389>.
- [13] K. Fujita, K. Ueda, and M. Kusabuka, "A method to predict the load-displacement relationship of ground anchors," *Revue Francaise de Geotechnique*, no. 3, pp. 58–62, 1978, <https://doi.org/10.1051/geotech/1978003058>.
- [14] N.-K. Kim, "Performance of Tension and Compression Anchors in Weathered Soil," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 129, no. 12, pp. 1138–1150, Dec. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(2003\)129:12\(1138\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2003)129:12(1138)).
- [15] N.-K. Kim, J.-S. Park, and S.-K. Kim, "Numerical simulation of ground anchors," *Computers and Geotechnics*, vol. 34, no. 6, pp. 498–507, Nov. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2006.09.002>.
- [16] P. Moller and S. Widing, "Anchoring in soil employing the Alvik, Lindo and JB drilling methods," in *7th International Conference for Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering*, 1969, vol. 15.
- [17] H.-Y. Fang, Ed., *Foundation Engineering Handbook*, 2nd ed. 1991. Softcover reprint of the original 2nd ed. 1991 edition. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2012.
- [18] J. G. Potyondy, "Skin Friction between Various Soils and Construction Materials," *Geotechnique*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 339–353, Dec. 1961, <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1961.11.4.339>.
- [19] G. S. Littlejohn, "Design estimation of the ultimate load-holding capacity of ground anchors," *Ground Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 25–39, Nov. 1980.
- [20] *BS EN 1992-1-1(2004), Design Of Concrete Structures. General Rules And Rules For Buildings*. London, UK: British Standards Institution, 2004.
- [21] F. Leonhardt, "Cracks and crack control at concrete structures," in *International Association for Bridge and Structural Engineering*, Versailles, Paris, France, Sep. 1987.
- [22] J.-L. Briaud, W. F. P. Iii, and D. E. Weatherby, "Should Grouted Anchors Have Short Tendon Bond Length?," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 124, no. 2, pp. 110–119, Feb. 1998, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(1998\)124:2\(110\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(1998)124:2(110)).
- [23] *Committee Euro-International du Beton, CEB-FIP Model Code 1990*. London, UK: Thomas Telford Publishing, 1990.
- [24] *Federal Highway Administration, Geotechnical Engineering Circular No. 4, Ground Anchors and Anchored Systems*. Washington, DC, US: US Department of Transportation, 1999.
- [25] A. D. Booth, *Numerical methods*, 3rd ed. Oxford, UK: Butterworths, 1966.
- [26] M. F. Randolph and C. P. Wroth, "Analysis of Deformation of Vertically Loaded Piles," *Journal of the Geotechnical Engineering Division*, vol. 104, no. 12, pp. 1465–1488, Dec. 1978, <https://doi.org/10.1061/AJGEB6.0000729>.
- [27] I. M. Smith and D. V. Griffiths, *Programming the Finite Element Method*. New York, NY, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2004.
- [28] *Plaxis Manual of Verification and Validation*, Bentley Systems Inc., 2018.
- [29] *U. Smolczyk, Geotechnical Engineering Handbook, Procedures*. Berlin, Germany: John Wiley & Sons, 2003.
- [30] N. H. Al-Baghdadi and B. A. Ahmed, "Field Tests of Grouted Ground Anchors in Sandy Soil of Najaf, Iraq," *Open Engineering Journal*, accepted for publishing on 19 July 2022.
- [31] E. M. Kara, M. Meghachou, and N. Aboubekr, "Contribution of Particles Size Ranges to Sand Friction," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 497–501, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.361>.
- [32] *PTI DC35(2014), Recommendations for Prestressed Rock and Soil Anchors*. Post Tensioning Institute, 2014.
- [33] P. Xanthakos, *Ground Anchors and Anchored Structures*. New York, NY, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 1991.
- [34] *ACI 318-(2019), Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete and Commentary*. Farmington Hills, MI, USA: ACI Concrete, 2019.

A Study on the Influence of Plasma Nitriding Technology Parameters on the Working Surface Deformation of Hypoid Gears

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Abstract-This paper presents the results of the research on the influence of plasma nitriding technology parameters on the working surface deformation of hypoid gears. Blue light technology with non-contact measuring devices is used to determine the working surface deformation of hypoid gears after plasma nitriding. The study has determined a regression equation showing the influence of plasma nitriding technology parameters on the deformation of the working surface of the hypoid gear. The minimum deformation optimization value at the planning area is 0.0071746 at permeation temperature $TL=4.89^{\circ}\text{C}$, permeation time $h=510\text{h}$, and gas flow $1\text{ GI}=6.02\text{L/h}$.

Keywords-hypoid gear; surface deformation; computer aided verification; plasma nitriding

I. INTRODUCTION

The hypoid gear pair has some special features: the axes of the gears are diagonal, the average helix angle of the active gear and the passive gear are not equal, and the tangential module of the active gear is larger than those of the passive gear. The constraining forces at the contact trace acting on the active and passive gears are equal, but the tangential forces are not equal [1]. Hypoid gears are shaped by milling [2] (Figure 1(a)). This study uses plasma nitriding to improve the working surface quality of hypoid gears. Plasma nitriding is an advanced and environmentally friendly technology that is very effective for products with simple structures. The advantage of this technology is that it can control the white layer, so it is very suitable for impregnating products that require high quality. The disadvantage of the plasma nitriding method is the occurrence of plasma amplification during the penetration of the surface. This disadvantage can be completely eliminated by controlling the plasma thickness [3, 4]. Plasma nitriding is the process of alloying the surface with nitrogen. The permeation process is carried out in a vacuum furnace at low pressure with a mixture of H_2 , N_2 , CH_4 , and Ar gases [3, 4]. Under high voltage, the gases are ionized, creating a plasma flow. Nitrogen ions are accelerated during plasma collision with the sample. This ion bombardment process heats, cleans and forms a hard layer with good wear resistance, increasing fatigue strength [5].

The ELTROPUL permeation furnace [6] uses a pre-generated plasma pulse source. It creates stable plasma under all circumstances, permeates parts with complex geometries, lowers temperatures providing for the lowest permeation and the most treated surfaces. The surface layer that is nitrified after ion nitriding is a thin, solid white layer outside and a diffuse domain inside. The properties of the surface layer (deformation, hardness, roughness, cleanliness), permeation layer depth, permeation layer properties, microscopic hardness of the material, etc. are influenced by input parameters such as voltage, current density, permeation time, permeation temperature, compositions of gas mixture, gas pressure, etc. Authors in [7] used plasma nitriding treatment to reduce wear occurring in hot forging applications, but there is a need for further optimization of the processes to achieve suitable properties for different loaded forging tools. This work presents the influence of the main process parameters on the wear properties of the mold. The effects of nitriding parameters such as temperature, nitrogen flow, and time on nitriding depth, hardness, and crack sensitivity were investigated. Authors in [8] studied the surface properties of the Fe_4N layer on steel modified by pulsed plasma nitriding [8]. Authors in [9] studied the phase structure and surface hardness value of AISI H13 ion nitrided steel under different temperatures. Authors in [10] worked on nitriding of tertiary alloys based on iron (Fe-Cr-Ti and Fe-Cr-Al) and other alloy steels [10]. There have been many studies on the mechanical properties of steel after plasma nitriding [9-11]. To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies that consider plasma nitriding of hypoid gears made of 18XIT alloy steel.

Precision inspection has been widely used in manufacturing to measure the dimensional accuracy of parts and products to meet the quality requirements. For regular geometric features, coordinate-measuring machines can be used effectively to assess the accuracy and tolerances. For parts with free-form surfaces, the inspection becomes complex. Therefore, numerous researches have been carried out to tackle both fundamental and application issues concerning free-form surface inspection. In addition to academic research, some commercial packages have also been developed [12]. This

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study used ATOS's non-contact measuring instrument to collect point cloud data of samples before and after plasma nitriding. The evaluation of surface deviations is handled by GOM software, also of ATOS. This application has never been used before with hypoid gear working surfaces.

II. PLASMA NITRIDING FOR HYPOID GEAR SAMPLES

A. Experimental Samples

The plasma nitriding sample consists of passive gear teeth, which have been machined from 18XIT and improved to a uniform hardness of 34 – 36 HRC (Figure 1). Each tooth is cut separately by wire cutting. The teeth are marked in order from 1 to 41 corresponding to the total number of teeth of the gear, as shown in Figure 1(b).

Fig. 1. Sample preparation for the experiment: (a) Passive hypoid gear, (b) teeth that are cut apart.

B. Experiment Planning

1) Selection of Input Parameters

H4580 Eltrolab is used to perform plasma nitriding. Many parameters affect the surface quality [13]:

h is the number of hours executed in each step of the program (h), m is the number of minutes executed in each step of the program (min), P is the pressure (Pa), TL the permeation temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), TG the detailed temperature rising rate over time ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$), TW the furnace wall temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), WG the furnace wall temperature rising rate over time ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$), V is the Voltage (V), PD the Pulse Duration (μs), PR the number of repetitions of the pulse, and $G1-G4$ are gas flows 1-4 respectively (l/h).

In reality, in permeation with samples of the same material and size with little change, the voltage V and pressure P are fixed. Detailed temperature rising rate over time TG , furnace wall temperature TW , and furnace wall temperature rising rate over time WG depend on TL and h . $G1-G4$ are proportional to each other [14]. According to the requirements for selecting input factors, the experimental variables were selected including TL , h , and $G1$. The remaining factors remain unchanged. The influence relationship of plasma nitriding technology parameters on the deformation of the working surface of hypoid gears is:

$$\varepsilon = f(h, TL, G1) \quad (1)$$

where ε is the absolute deviation due to thermal deformation of tooth working surface (mm).

2) The Permeation Process

When the power supply is closed under high voltage and low pressure, the first heating process, until reaching a temperature of 250-300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, passes through the surface activation stage, followed by the second heating stage until reaching the permeation temperature (510-550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The end of the permeation period, lasting from 4 to 8h (depending on the installation program), is the automatic cooling phase.

Fig. 2. Plasma nitriding of hypoid gear tooth samples and scanning of samples after permeation. (a) Samples in the permeation furnace, (b) measuring and scanning of samples after permeation.

3) The Conduct of Permeation of the Test Samples

Level 2 planning with 27 experiments and programming to control the permeation process on H4580 Eltrolab are shown in Table I. Plasma nitriding of hypoid gear tooth samples was carried out as shown in Figure 2(a).

4) Test Samples Measuring and Scanning

One of the development applications of the technique is non-contact measurement using Computer Aided Verification (CAV) to determine the deformation of the surface. Here, deformation is understood as the differences from the origin (standard). The basic CAV steps include data collection (point cloud) from the original object, data after machining (here, after permeation), superposition of 2 cloud data according to predetermined standards, and deviation evaluation.

In this study, Capture 3D-ATOS Blue Light III TRIPLE non-contact measuring device with blue light technology were used to collect point cloud data of samples before and after plasma nitriding, as shown in Figure 2(b).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After loading the sample point cloud data before and after permeating into the software and superimposing these two data sets, automatic comparison was made with the two tooth surface point cloud data, displaying the measurement results of deviation due to deformation on the tooth surfaces of each test sample as shown in Figure 3. The software produces a statistical report on the measurement results of deviation due to deformation at specified points on the gear tooth surface of each measured sample. The deviation due to surface deformation of each measured sample is the average value of the specified points on the gear tooth surface. Measurement results with 27 samples are summarized in Table II.

TABLE I. CONTROL PROGRAM OF THE PERMEATION PROCESS

Ps	h	m	Opt	P	TL	TG	TW	WG	V	PD	PR	GI	G2	G3	G4
1	4	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
2	4	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
3	4	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0
4	4	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
5	4	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
6	4	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0
7	4	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
8	4	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
9	4	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0
10	6	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
11	6	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
12	6	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0
13	6	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
14	6	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
15	6	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0
16	6	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
17	6	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
18	6	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0
19	8	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
20	8	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
21	8	2	144	250	510	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0
22	8	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
23	8	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
24	8	2	144	250	530	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0
25	8	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	4	12	0	0
26	8	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	6	18	0	0
27	8	2	144	250	550	10	530	10	470	50	100	8	24	0	0

TABLE II. SYNTHESIS OF THE DEVIATION MEASUREMENT RESULTS DUE TO THERMAL DEFORMATION OF WORK SURFACE

Trial	TL (°C)	h (h)	GI (L/h)	ε (mm)
1	4	510	4	0.0080
2	4	510	6	0.0071
3	4	510	8	0.0082
4	4	530	4	0.0086
5	4	530	6	0.0085
6	4	530	8	0.0093
7	4	550	4	0.0103
8	4	550	6	0.0099
9	4	550	8	0.0114
10	6	510	4	0.0082
11	6	510	6	0.0078
12	6	510	8	0.0080
13	6	530	4	0.0090
14	6	530	6	0.0083
15	6	530	8	0.0092
16	6	550	4	0.0105
17	6	550	6	0.0099
18	6	550	8	0.0111
19	8	510	4	0.0096
20	8	510	6	0.0087
21	8	510	8	0.0098
22	8	530	4	0.0099
23	8	530	6	0.0099
24	8	530	8	0.0101
25	8	550	4	0.0119
26	8	550	6	0.0111
27	8	550	8	0.0139

Fig. 3. Measurement result display on two gear tooth surfaces.

TABLE III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS ANALYSIS

Term	Coef	SE Coef	T-Value	P-Value	VIF
Constant	0.008207	0.000194	42.36	0.000	
TL	0.000756	0.000090	8.42	0.000	1.00
h	0.001367	0.000090	15.24	0.000	1.00
GI	0.000278	0.000090	3.10	0.007	1.00
TL×TL	0.000678	0.000155	4.36	0.000	1.00
h×h	0.000544	0.000155	3.50	0.003	1.00
GI×GI	0.000811	0.000155	5.22	0.000	1.00
TL×h	0.000042	0.000110	0.38	0.709	1.00
TL×GI	0.000033	0.000110	0.30	0.765	1.00
h×GI	0.000292	0.000110	2.66	0.017	1.00

It was found that there were some coefficients with p-value greater than the precision $\alpha=0.05$, so these coefficients were discarded, and the experimental results were reanalyzed (Table IV).

1) Influence of Input Parameters on Surface Deformation

The experimental results (Table III) were processed using Minitab software and were preliminarily analyzed [15, 16].

TABLE IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS SECOND ANALYSIS

Term	Coef	SE Coef	T-Value	P-Value	VIF
Constant	0.008207	0.000185	44.48	0.000	
<i>TL</i>	0.000756	0.000085	8.85	0.000	1.00
<i>h</i>	0.001367	0.000085	16.00	0.000	1.00
<i>GI</i>	0.000278	0.000085	3.25	0.004	1.00
<i>TL</i> × <i>TL</i>	0.000678	0.000148	4.58	0.000	1.00
<i>h</i> × <i>h</i>	0.000544	0.000148	3.68	0.002	1.00
<i>GI</i> × <i>GI</i>	0.000811	0.000148	5.48	0.000	1.00
<i>h</i> × <i>GI</i>	0.000292	0.000105	2.79	0.012	1.00

Fig. 4. The influence of input parameters (*TL*, *h*, *GI*) on surface deformation (ϵ).

The influence of the input parameters on the surface deformation is presented in Figure 4. Corresponding to the three levels (-1), (0), and (+1) of each factor, the software calculates the average value of the output response and displays it as a point (Figure 4). From there, to find out the parameter that has the most influence on the output value, it is possible to make a brief comment on the influence of the input parameters on the surface deformation. With the permeation temperature *TL*, the influence on the output is parabolic, with the minimum near the value 0, and the influence chart goes from a minimum of about 0.0080 to the maximum value of 0.0095 at the value area +1 of the planning. For permeation time *h*, the influence on the output is parabolic, with the minimum near the value 0 and the influence chart goes from the minimum value around 0.0075 towards the maximum value of 0.0100 at the value area +1 of the planning. With a gas permeation concentration of 1 *GI*, the influence on the output is parabolic, with the minimum near the value 0 and the influence chart goes from about 0.0085 to a minimum and to the maximum value of 0.0095 at the value area +1 of the planning.

With the Pareto chart in Figure 5, it is found that the parameters that greatly affect the surface deformation are *h* and *TL*. These parameters interact at level 2 of *GI*. In the standard distribution chart in Figure 6, the effect parameters are standardized. These are the parameters that affect the regression equation.

2) Regression Equation of Experimental Data

The variance (ANOVA) of the regression equation for the output object is analyzed, with the selection of removing the parameters that do not affect the determined regression

equation (Table V) [17]. The variance analysis table has all p-Values less than 0.05. This shows that these parameters all have an influence on the regression equation.

Fig. 5. Pareto chart of input parameters.

Fig. 6. Standard distribution chart of the standardized effect parameters.

TABLE V. ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value
Model	7	0.000055	0.000008	59.59	0.000
Linear	3	0.000045	0.000015	114.93	0.000
<i>TL</i>	1	0.000010	0.000010	78.24	0.000
<i>h</i>	1	0.000034	0.000034	255.98	0.000
<i>GI</i>	1	0.000001	0.000001	10.57	0.004
Square	3	0.000008	0.000003	21.53	0.000
<i>TL</i> × <i>TL</i>	1	0.000003	0.000003	20.99	0.000
<i>h</i> × <i>h</i>	1	0.000002	0.000002	13.54	0.002
<i>GI</i> × <i>GI</i>	1	0.000004	0.000004	30.05	0.000
2-Way Interaction	1	0.000001	0.000001	7.77	0.012
<i>h</i> × <i>GI</i>	1	0.000001	0.000001	7.77	0.012
Error	19	0.000002	0.000000		
Total	26	0.000057			

The suitability of the data was evaluated using a set of R^2 , adjusted R^2 , and predicted R^2 parameters. These parameters all have a value bigger than 90%, which means that the regression equation is completely consistent with the experimental data.

TABLE VI. SUITABILITY

S	R ²	R ² (adj)	R ² (pred)
0.0003624	95.64%	94.04%	91.01%

Then the general equation (1) is rewritten as a regression equation in natural form:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon = & 0.388 - 0.001656 TL - 0.001418 h \\ & - 0.00616 G1 + 0.000169 TL^2 \\ & + 0.000001 h^2 + 0.000203 G1^2 \\ & + 0.000007 h \times G1 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The chart in Figure 7 shows the domain of double interactions between the parameters. Based on these charts, the changing trend of surface deformation can be seen when changing separately the two parameters shown in each chart.

Fig. 7. Interaction charts between parameters.

3) Optimization of Permeation Technology Parameters

With the regression equation found, minimum deformation optimization is carried out with the following contour conditions:

$$\min \epsilon: \begin{cases} 4 \leq TL \leq 8 \\ 510 \leq h \leq 550 \\ 4 \leq G1 \leq 8 \end{cases}$$

Minitab software gives the optimization results shown in Table VII:

TABLE VII. MINITAB RESULTS

TL	h	G1	ε Fit
4.89	510	6.02	0.0071746

Fig. 8. Software result of minimizing deformation in the planning area.

IV. CONCLUSION

Blue light technology with a non-contact measuring device is used to determine the working surface deformation of hypoid gears after plasma nitriding. The current study has determined the regression equation showing the influence of plasma nitriding technology parameters on surface deformation. Research results show that the parameters of plasma nitriding technology that have a great influence on surface deformation are permeation time h and permeation temperature TL . The gas permeation concentration $1 G1$ has little effect on the surface deformation and the level 2 interaction with h and TL . The minimum deformation optimization value in the planning area is 0.0071746 for $TL=4.89^\circ\text{C}$, $h=510\text{h}$, and $G1= 6.02\text{L/h}$. Thus, the working surface deformation of hypoid gears after permeation is very little influenced by plasma nitriding technology parameters.

To the best of our knowledge, plasma nitriding of hypoid gears along with the use of blue light technology with non-contact gauges to determine the gear working surface deformation have not been studied before. With the technological parameters determined as above, it is possible to proceed to set up the hypoid gear plasma nitriding technology process in industrial production.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Kolivand, *Development of Tooth Contact and Mechanical Efficiency Models for Face-milled and Face-hobbed Hypoid and Spiral Bevel Gears*. Columbus, OH, USA: Ohio State University, 2009.
- [2] T. H. Le, V. B. Pham, and T. D. Hoang, "Surface Finish Comparison of Dry and Coolant Fluid High-Speed Milling of JIS SDK61 Mould Steel," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8023–8028, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4594>.
- [3] D. Pye, *Practical Nitriding and Ferritic Nitrocarburizing*. ASM International, 2003.
- [4] *ISO/TR 22849:2011(en), Design recommendations for bevel gears*. ISO, 2011.
- [5] D. Y. Chung, H. J. Kim, and H. N. Kim, "A Study on the Erosion Characteristics of the Micropulsed Plasma Nitrided Barrel of a Rifle," in *19th International Symposium of Ballistics*, Interlaken, Switzerland, May 2001.
- [6] U. Huchel, S. Strämke, and J. Cockrem, "Pulsed Plasma Nitriding of Tools." ELTRO GmbH.
- [7] H. Paschke, M. Weber, G. Braeuer, T. Yilkiran, B.-A. Behrens, and H. Brand, "Optimized plasma nitriding processes for efficient wear reduction of forging dies," *Archives of Civil and Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 407–412, Dec. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acme.2012.06.001>.
- [8] J. C. Díaz-Guillén *et al.*, "Surface Properties of Fe4N Compounds Layer on AISI 4340 Steel Modified by Pulsed Plasma Nitriding," *Journal of Materials Science & Technology*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 287–290, Mar. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2013.01.017>.
- [9] M. R. Cruz and M. H. Staia, "Ion nitrided AISI H13 tool steel Part 2 – High temperature performance under sliding wear conditions," *Surface Engineering*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 367–374, Oct. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1179/174329406X140199>.
- [10] K. S. Jung, "Nitriding of iron-based ternary alloys : Fe-Cr-Ti and Fe-Cr-Al," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart, Germany, 2011.
- [11] Z. Pokorný, J. Kadlec, V. Hruby, Z. Joska, and D. Q. Tram, "Mechanical Properties of Steels after Plasma Nitriding Process," *Journal of Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. A, no. 1A, pp. 24–25, 2011.

-
- [12] Y. Li and P. Gu, "Free-form surface inspection techniques state of the art review," *Computer-Aided Design*, vol. 36, no. 13, pp. 1395–1417, Nov. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cad.2004.02.009>.
- [13] U. Huchel and S. Strämke, "Pulsed Plasma Nitriding of Sintered Parts – Production Experiences," *Nitrierpraxis*. <http://www.nitrierpraxis.de/pulsed-plasma-nitriding-of-sintered-parts-production-experiences>.
- [14] D. Pye, *Practical Nitriding and Ferritic Nitrocarburizing*. ASM International, 2003.
- [15] D. D. Trung, "Application of EDAS, MARCOS, TOPSIS, MOORA and PIV Methods for Multi-Criteria Decision Making in Milling Process," *Strojnícky časopis - Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 71, no. 2, pp. 69–84, Nov. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.2478/scjme-2021-0019>.
- [16] N. V. Cuong and N. L. Khanh, "Parameter Selection to Ensure Multi-Criteria Optimization of the Taguchi Method Combined with the Data Envelopment Analysis-based Ranking Method when Milling SCM440 Steel," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7551–7557, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4315>.
- [17] V. C. Nguyen, T. D. Nguyen, and D. H. Tien, "Cutting Parameter Optimization in Finishing Milling of Ti-6Al-4V Titanium Alloy under MQL Condition using TOPSIS and ANOVA Analysis," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 6775–6780, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4015>.

Reliability-based Design Optimization of Steel-Concrete Composite Beams Using Genetic Algorithm and Monte Carlo Simulation

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Abstract—Steel-Concrete Composite (SCC) beams have been commonly used in civil and industrial buildings. It is the main bearing structure and accounts for 30-40% of the structural cost. Therefore, the optimal design with minimum weight and safety structure of the SCC beams is very important. Reliability is an important part of structural safety. Design according to reliability has been included in standards such as ISO 2394:2012, JB50153-92, and BS 5760-0:2014. This article aims to propose and apply a design optimization algorithm for the reliability-based design of SCC beams. The reliability-based design optimization of the SCC beams combines the safety conditions of EC-4, Genetic Algorithm, and Monte Carlo simulation. The numerical results show that with safety probability constraint conditions $P_s=98\%$, the cross-section of the SCC beams can be reduced from IPE 400 to IPE 300.

Keywords—reliability; design optimization; Genetic Algorithm (GA); Monte Carlo simulation; steel-concrete composite beams

I. INTRODUCTION

SCC beams are designed according to the American Institute of Steel Construction (AISC360-10) [1], the European Committee for Standardization 2004a (EC-4) [2], and the Japan Society of Civil Engineers (JSCE-2009). The calculation methods for design strengths of steel-concrete composite members can be divided into the Load and Resistance Factor Design (LRFD) method and the Partial Factor Method (PFM) [3]. Reliability assessment of steel and SCC beams is an open research topic. Fatigue-reliability evaluation of steel bridges according to AASHTO was proposed in [4]. Reliability assessment of SCC beams considering metal corrosion effects was published in [5]. A reliability assessment of SCC beams according to EC-4 using FORM was proposed in [6]. Seismic

reliability assessment of a two-story steel-concrete composite frame designed according to Eurocode 8 was conducted in [7].

Some recently published studies on the reliability of steel and reinforced concrete beams and design optimization can be seen in [7-17]. However, previous studies mostly focused on the structural reliability and optimization of steel and SCC structures. To the best of our knowledge, no studies have been conducted yet on the reliability-based design optimization of SCC beams combined with safety conditions according to European Committee for Standardization 2004a (EC-4), Genetic Algorithm (GA), and Monte Carlo simulations.

This study proposes an optimization algorithm for reliability-based design of SCC beams. The developed algorithm combines Monte Carlo simulation and GA. Random values of the input parameters are considered in the proposed procedure and various safety conditions according to the EC-4 are investigated. Finally, numerical validation has been performed with 5 case studies.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Safety Conditions of Steel-Reinforced Concrete Composite Beams

The steel-reinforced concrete composite beams in this study were designed according to EC-4 [2]. The safe conditions of composites steel-reinforced concrete that must be satisfied are: (i) Ultimate limit state and (ii) serviceability limit state. The destructive structure of composite steel-reinforced concrete beams has three cases, as shown in Figure 1. The safe conditions can be rewritten as in (1):

Fig. 1. Plastic design of steel-reinforced concrete beams: (a) when the PNA lies in concrete slab, (b) when the PNA lies in steel flange, (c) when the PNA lies in steel web.

$$M_{saf} = \begin{cases} \frac{\tau_{Ed} \cdot \gamma_{M0}}{f_y / \sqrt{3}} \leq 1.0; & \text{(Ultimate limit state)} \\ \frac{M_{pl,Rd}}{M_{Ed}} \leq 1.0 & \text{(Ultimate limit state)} \\ \frac{w}{w_{lim}} \leq 1.0 & \text{(Serviceability limit state)} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where M_{saf} represents the safe conditions based on EC-4.

B. Structural Reliability

The probability of failure of a structure for random strength (R) and random load (Q) is calculated according to [18]:

$$P_f = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I(r, q) f_R(r) f_Q(q) drdq \quad (2)$$

where f_R represents the load probability density functions, f_Q the strength probability density functions, and $I(r, q)$ is a function indicator and defined by:

$$I(r, q) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{failure condition} \\ 1 & \text{safety condition} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) cannot be solved in a closed form but is instead estimated using analytical or numerical techniques. Determining the reliability of the structure has been covered in detail in [18], where the reliability structure has been proposed through the first-order reliability index with the assumption that R and Q have independent normal distributions.

$$\beta_1 = \ln \frac{\left(\frac{R_m}{Q} \right)}{\sqrt{COV_R^2 - COV_Q^2}} \quad (4)$$

where R_m is the mean of "true" resistance and R_n the nominal resistance as determined by a specification procedure.

Monte Carlo simulation [18] has been proposed to estimate the probability of failure and avoid the limitations of the first-order reliability index method. The general expression (1) can be rewritten as follows:

$$P_f = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{I(x, y) f_R(x) f_Q(y)}{k_{XY}(x, y)} k_{XY}(x, y) dx dy \quad (5)$$

where $k_{XY}(x, y)$ is importance sampling density. This integral can be estimated by the sum of the discrete values as follows:

$$\hat{P}_f = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{I(x_i, y_i) f_Q(y_i)}{f_{Q^*}(y_i)} \quad (6)$$

The variance of the sampled estimated significance is given by:

$$Var(\hat{P}_f) = \frac{1}{N-1} \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left[\frac{I(x_i, y_i) f_Q(y_i)}{f_{Q^*}(y_i)} \right]^2 - \hat{P}_f^2 \right\} \quad (7)$$

C. Genetic Algorithm

GA is based on Darwinian evolution theory. The aim of GAs is to search for an optimized solution to a technical problem. GA basics can be found in [19-21]. The main structure of GA is a 5-step process:

- Step 1.** Randomize the first generation.
- Step 2.** Evaluate the fitness of each individual.
- Step 3.** Compute the probability distribution.
- Step 4.** Create the next generation via crossover and mutation.
- Step 5.** Repeat steps 2 to 5 for the desired number of generations.

D. Deterministic Model and Stochastic Model

The deterministic model is a composite steel-reinforced concrete beam design problem according to EC-4. The input parameters used include geometrical properties (L, b, IPE), material properties (f_{kc}, f_u), and total active load (g). The input parameters can be written as $\mathbf{X} = [L, b, IPE, f_{kc}, f_u, g]$. The deterministic model has the following form:

$$M_{saf} = \mathfrak{J}(\mathbf{X}) \quad (8)$$

The stochastic model was built based on the deterministic model, in which some input parameters are randomized. In this study, two input vectors have been used. The first vector consists of a deterministic inputs group $X_1 = [L, b, IPE]$ and the second vector consists of a stochastic inputs group $X_2(\omega) = [f_{kc}(\omega), f_u(\omega), g(\omega)]$, where ω characterizes the random value. The stochastic model has the form of:

$$M_{saf} = \mathfrak{F}(X_1, X_2(\omega)) \quad (9)$$

III. RELIABILITY-BASED DESIGN OPTIMIZATION OF THE STEEL-CONCRETE COMPOSITE BEAMS

A. Schematic Diagram Algorithm

In this study, reliability-based design optimization of SCC beams has been built based on the stochastic model, Monte Carlo simulation, and GA. The algorithm consists of the following steps:

Step 1. Prepare the input data (geometrical properties, material properties, and total active load)

Step 2. Design and safety testing for cross-section of SCC according to EC-4 with deterministic input parameters.

Step 3. Randomize input parameters and build the stochastic model based on the deterministic model.

Step 4. Reliability assessment based on the stochastic model and Monte Carlo simulation.

Step 5. Reliability-based design optimization of steel-concrete composite beams.

- Constraint conditions: The safety probability structure.
- Objective function: Minimum weight of steel beam.

Step 6. Reliability-based design optimization using GA.

The process diagram of the reliability-based design optimization of the SCC beams using GA and Monte Carlo simulation is shown in Figure 2. From the process diagram, a program has been built on MATLAB.

B. Optimization Analysis of Steel-Concrete Composite Beams

In this section, we apply reliability-based design optimization of SCC beams using GA and Monte Carlo simulation, considering the SCC beam example in [22] as shown in Figure 3. The deterministic and random input parameters are shown in Table I. The distribution of material properties are based on [23] and the cross-section and loading are adopted from [24]. The upper and lower bounds of the cross-section of the steel beam are shown in Table II. The safety probability constraint conditions of steel-concrete composite beams are $P_s = 98\%$ and the objective function of steel beams is minimum weight. Optimization analysis results of the steel beams through 5 case studies are shown in Table III, which shows that with deterministic input parameters and safety conditions according to EC-4 [22], the obtained cross-section design of the steel beams is IPE 400. Meanwhile, when the reliability-based design optimization was applied to the SCC beams using GA and Monte Carlo simulations with safety probability constraint conditions $P_s = 98\%$, the obtained

optimal design of the cross-section of the steel beams is IPE 300. This proves that reliability-based design optimization of the SCC beams using GA and Monte Carlo simulation has great economic and technical advantages.

Fig. 2. The schematic diagram of reliability-based design optimization of SCC beams.

Fig. 3. (a) Cross-section of slabs and (b) stress distribution of the cross-section.

TABLE I. STATISTICAL PROPERTIES OF RANDOM VARIABLES FOR RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT OF SCC BEAMS

Properties	Variables	Nominal	Mean/nominal	COV	Distribution	Ref.
Material (N/mm ²)	f_{rk}	25.0	1.10	0.06	Lognormal	[23]
	f_u	450	1.10	0.06	Lognormal	[23]
Loading (kN/m)	g_k	9.54	1.05	0.10	Normal	[24]
	q_k	13.69	1.05	0.10	Normal	[24]
Cross-section IPE 400 (mm)	b_f	180.00	1.00	0.05	Normal	[24]
	t_f	13.50	1.00	0.05	Normal	[24]
	h_a	400	1.00	0.05	Normal	[24]
	t_w	8.60	1.00	0.05	Normal	[24]
	r	21.0	1.00	0.05	Normal	[24]

* Load combinations of the overall dead load (g_k) and the service load on the floor (q_k)

TABLE II. UPPER AND LOWER BOUNDS OF THE CROSS-SECTION OF BEAM STEEL

No.	h_a (mm)	b_f (mm)	t_w (mm)	t_w (mm)	Weight (kg/m)	Area (cm ²)
IPE 300	300	150	7.1	10.7	15	42.2
IPE 330	330	160	7.5	11.5	18	49.1
IPE 360	360	170	8.0	12.7	18	57.1
IPE 400	400	180	8.6	13.5	21	66.3
IPE 450	450	190	9.4	14.6	21	77.6
IPE 500	500	200	10.2	16.0	21	90.7
IPE 550	550	210	11.1	17.2	24	106
IPE 600	600	220	12.0	19.0	24	122

TABLE III. OPTIMIZATION ANALYSIS RESULTS THROUGH 5 CASE STUDIES

Case study	Minimum weight of SCC beams (kg/m)	Cross-section of optimization	Results in [22]
1	17.60	IPE 300	IPE 400
2	18.01	IPE 300	IPE 400
3	17.50	IPE 300	IPE 400
4	16.90	IPE 300	IPE 400
5	17.56	IPE 300	IPE 400

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study proposes an optimization algorithm for reliability-based design of steel-concrete composite beams. The developed algorithm combined Monte Carlo simulations and Generic Algorithm. Random variables for input design parameters are considered in the proposed procedure. Additionally, the safety conditions according to EC-4 are investigated. Finally, a numerical validation has been performed with 5 case studies. The main points of the current paper are:

- A reliability-based design optimization algorithm of steel-concrete composite beams was developed.
- The proposed optimization procedure was successfully built on MATLAB platform and it can be convenient for design practices.
- A numerical validation has been performed with 5 case studies. The result shows that with safety probability constraint conditions of $P_s = 98\%$, the SCC beam can reduce the cross-section from IPE 400 to IPE 300.

REFERENCES

- [1] ANS/AISC 360-10: Specification for Structural Steel Buildings. Chicago, IL, USA: American Institute of Steel Construction, 2010.
- [2] "Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings," in EN 1994-1-1 (2004): Eurocode 4: Design of composite steel and concrete structures, The European Union Per Regulation 305/2011, Directive 98/34/EC, Directive 2004/18/EC, 2004.
- [3] L. Chung, J.-J. Lim, H.-J. Hwang, and T.-S. Eom, "Review of Design Flexural Strengths of Steel-Concrete Composite Beams for Building Structures," *International Journal of Concrete Structures and Materials*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 109–121, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40069-016-0146-7>.
- [4] Z. Zhao, A. Haldar, and F. L. Breen, "Fatigue-Reliability Evaluation of Steel Bridges," *Journal of Structural Engineering*, vol. 120, no. 5, pp. 1608–1623, May 1994, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9445\(1994\)120:5\(1608\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9445(1994)120:5(1608)).
- [5] T.-H. Nguyen and D.-D. Nguyen, "Reliability Assessment of Steel-Concrete Composite Beams considering Metal Corrosion Effects," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2020, Dec. 2020, Art. no. e8817809, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8817809>.
- [6] A. Mamuda, I. Abubakar, and D. Samson, "Reliability-Based Structural Safety Evaluation of Concrete-Steel Composite Beams According to Euro Code 4," *Engineering Physics*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 32–40, Nov. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ep.20180202.11>.
- [7] V. Piluso, G. Rizzano, and I. Tolone, "Seismic reliability assessment of a two-story steel-concrete composite frame designed according to Eurocode 8," *Structural Safety*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 383–395, Sep. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strusafe.2009.01.001>.
- [8] Y. Luo, A. Li, and Z. Kang, "Reliability-based design optimization of adhesive bonded steel-concrete composite beams with probabilistic and non-probabilistic uncertainties," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 33, no. 7, pp. 2110–2119, Jul. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2011.02.040>.
- [9] Y. Luo, Z. Kang, and A. Li, "Structural reliability assessment based on probability and convex set mixed model," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 87, no. 21, pp. 1408–1415, Nov. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruc.2009.06.001>.
- [10] F. N. Leitão, J. G. S. da Silva, P. C. G. da S. Vellasco, S. A. L. de Andrade, and L. R. O. de Lima, "Composite (steel-concrete) highway bridge fatigue assessment," *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 14–24, Jan. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcsr.2010.07.013>.
- [11] G. Fabbrocino, G. Manfredi, and E. Cosenza, "Modelling of continuous steel-concrete composite beams: computational aspects," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 80, no. 27, pp. 2241–2251, Nov. 2002, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-7949\(02\)00257-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0045-7949(02)00257-2).
- [12] N. L. Tran and T. H. Nguyen, "Reliability Assessment of Steel Plane Frame's Buckling Strength Considering Semi-rigid Connections," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 5099–5103, Feb. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3231>.
- [13] T. H. Nguyen, "Global Sensitivity Analysis Of In-Plane Elastic Buckling Of Steel Arches," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 6476–6480, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3833>.
- [14] N. M. Okasha, "Reliability-Based Design Optimization of Trusses with Linked-Discrete Design Variables using the Improved Firefly Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 964–971, Apr. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.675>.
- [15] Y. Liu and Z. Duan, "Fuzzy finite element model updating of bridges by considering the uncertainty of the measured modal parameters," *Science China Technological Sciences*, vol. 55, no. 11, pp. 3109–3117, Nov. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11431-012-5009-0>.
- [16] Y. Deng, Y. Ding, A. Li, and G. Zhou, "Fatigue reliability assessment for bridge welded details using long-term monitoring data," *Science China Technological Sciences*, vol. 54, no. 12, pp. 3371–3381, Dec. 2011, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11431-011-4526-6>.
- [17] C. Conceição António and L. N. Hoffbauer, "Reliability-based design optimization and uncertainty quantification for optimal conditions of composite structures with non-linear behavior," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 153, pp. 479–490, Dec. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2017.10.041>.
- [18] R. E. Melchers and A. T. Beck, *Structural Reliability Analysis and Prediction*, 3rd ed. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2018.
- [19] S. Malasri, "Optimization Using Genetic Algorithms," presented at the MAESC 1999, Memphis, TN, USA, May 1999.
- [20] D. S. Weile and E. Michielssen, "Genetic algorithm optimization applied to electromagnetics: a review," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 343–353, Mar. 1997, <https://doi.org/10.1109/8.558650>.
- [21] S. Forrest, "Genetic algorithms," *ACM Computing Surveys*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 77–80, Nov. 1996, <https://doi.org/10.1145/234313.234350>.
- [22] F. M. Bartlett, R. J. Dexter, M. D. Graeser, J. J. Jelinek, B. J. Schmidt, and T. V. Galambos, "Updating Standard Shape Material Properties

Database for Design and Reliability," *Engineering Journal*, vol. 40, pp. 2–14, 2003.

- [23] B. Ellingwood, J. G. MacGregor, T. V. Galambos, and C. A. Cornell, "Probability Based Load Criteria: Load Factors and Load Combinations," *Journal of the Structural Division*, vol. 108, no. 5, pp. 978–997, May 1982, <https://doi.org/10.1061/JSDEAG.0005959>.

Numerical Modeling of a Pile Group Subjected to Seismic Loading Using the Hypoplasticity Model

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Abstract-Various simple and complicated models have been utilized to simulate the stress-strain behavior of the soil. These models are used in Finite Element Modeling (FEM) for geotechnical engineering applications and analysis of dynamic soil-structure interaction problems. These models either can't adequately describe some features, such as the strain-softening of dense sand, or they require several parameters that are difficult to gather by conventional laboratory testing. Furthermore, soils are not completely linearly elastic and perfectly plastic for the whole range of loads. Soil behavior is quite difficult to comprehend and exhibits a variety of behaviors under various circumstances. As a result, a more realistic constitutive model is needed, one that can represent the key aspects of soil behavior using simple parameters. In this regard, the powerful hypoplasticity model is suggested in this paper. It is classified as a non-linear model in which the stress increment is stated in a tensorial form as a function of strain increment, actual stress, and void ratio. Eight material characteristics are needed for the hypoplastic model. The hypoplastic model has a unique way to keep the state variables and material parameters separated. Because of this property, the model can implement the behavior of soil under a variety of stresses and densities while using the same set of material properties.

Keywords-constitutive modeling; hypoplasticity; pile; PLAXIS 3D; seismic loading

I. INTRODUCTION

Piles are an extensively utilized deep foundation type and are usually adopted in heavy building constructions on weak soils due to their large bearing capacity, low distortion, and high reliability [1-3]. The behavior of piles under seismic stress is a complicated soil-structure interaction phenomenon that can compromise the stability of pile-supported structures to risk. In seismically active places and during earthquakes, movements go from stiffer to softer near-surface layers, they tend to increase and pass to the superstructure via the piles. As a result, structural vibrations develop in the superstructure, imposing inertial pressure on the pile cap and pilings and if the inertial load is big enough, the piles experience substantial lateral displacement and bending moment and consequently piling foundations may be severely damaged. So, in seismically

active locations, proper geotechnical and structural design techniques for pile foundations are essential. The earthquake usually creates an additional loading situation on the pile that needs special attention [4-6].

Numerical modeling by FEM of experimental efforts is comparatively advantageous, and is one of the preferred approaches widely utilized for the modeling of the behavior of piled foundations under earthquakes [7-8]. It has been noted that FEM typically produces reliable findings that meet with the experiments. In [9], a comparison of the shaking table test and numerical model was performed to simulate the piled raft foundation in a dry bed of deposited sand. The system was subjected to a strong ground motion while the simulated model was linear visco-elastic. The authors showed that the experimental and numerical results match. The effect of pile soil interaction on resistance and stiffness of pile with sandy soil was investigated under centrifuge loading in [10]. The study adopted finite element analysis to simulate the models. The test results were compared with the analytical solution in terms of bearing capacity. It was reported that the interaction effect between raft and piles reduces the stiffness of the pile group. At the same time, the increment in vertical and horizontal stresses due to the presence of the raft on subsoil causes an enhanced pile response. A three dimensional finite element numerical analysis was performed using PLAXIS 3D to investigate the behavior of pile-caps under seismic and time history loading as settlement and load shearing between the piles and foundation in [11] and the results were verified with experimental work. The maximum amplitude of displacement was decreased by burying the pile cap deeper into the ground and increasing its thickness. Furthermore, reducing the foundation's dynamic reaction was also accomplished by increasing the separation between the foundation and the relative density of the sand. 3D numerical finite element simulation with ABAQUS was conducted to predicate single-pile and pile-system behavior in soft, saturated kaolin clay during various earthquakes in [12]. The results were verified with the centrifuge results from [13]. The linear elastic model was utilized for the piles and the nonlinear kinematic hardening model with Von Mises failure criterion for the clay. The

simulation results were in good agreement with the observed acceleration and bending moment. Also, the distance between piles in a pile group had a significant influence on the amount of interaction, acceleration response, forces, and bending moments. In [14], numerical analysis was conducted to predicate the response of pile and soil-pile-structure interaction with ground improvement (cement mixing method) using ABAQUS. A single pile model with superstructure was used to examine soil-pile-structure interaction behavior with head masses of 25, 100, and 160lbs. During the Loma Prieta earthquake, the piles had a maximum horizontal acceleration of 0.16g. The simulation results agreed well with the acceleration time history at the pile head of 160lbs mass.

The hypoplasticity model was first proposed in [15] and has been in development since then. Due to the complicated calculations of such a model, FEM is used via commercially available FEM software, e.g. Plaxis, FEAT, and ABAQUS. Some of these do not have hypoplasticity as a built-in model. This problem is solved by using the subroutine UMAT with PLAXIS 3D to provide the necessary tensor entries. PLAXIS 3D was used in this research due to the high capability of the software to deal with the elastic-plastic, non-linear, and contact problems [16]. This paper aims to use the hypoplasticity model in soil structure interaction problems.

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The hypoplastic model needs eight material parameters ($\varphi_c, e_{c0}, e_{i0}, e_{d0}, n, h_s, \alpha, \beta$). In order to obtain these model parameters, a series of physical-mechanical tests was performed on sand from Baghdad city, which was utilized in this study. Its physical properties are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF SAND SAMPLE

Test name	Soil property	Value
Specific Gravity G_s	Specific gravity	2.64
Standard Compaction Test	Maximum dry unit weight γ_{max} (kN/m ³)	16.55
	Minimum dry unit weight γ_{min} (kN/m ³)	13.85
	Maximum void ratio, e_{max}	0.87
	Minimum void ratio, e_{min}	0.56
Grain size analysis	Coefficient of uniformity, C_u	3.33
	Coefficient of curvature, C_c	0.83
	Unified Soil Classification System (USCS)	SP

III. HYPOPLASTICITY MODEL INPUT PARAMETERS

A. Void Ratio (e)

The void ratio is an essential factor in the calculation of the parameter model. Three parameters are associated with the void ratio. The relationships $e_{min} \approx e_{d0}, e_{max} \approx e_{c0}$, and $\frac{e_{i0}}{e_{max}} = 1.2$ [17] can be employed.

B. Critical Angle of Friction (φ_c)

The critical angle of friction can be determined for loosely dry sand (particle size greater than 0.1mm) by the conduction angle of repose while for finer soil (particle size less than

0.1mm), the critical angle of friction can be determined by classical mechanical soil tests [18].

C. Stiffness Parameters (n and h_s)

The soil stiffness in the hypoplasticity model relies on the h_s and n parameters and is determined by the confined compression test on loose dry sandy soil [19]. C_c (the compression curve slope) describes the slope of the curve derived from the confined compression test and displayed in the $\ln \sigma$ vs. e plane:

$$c_c = \frac{\Delta e}{\Delta \ln \sigma} \quad (1)$$

The k_0 value along the normal consolidation line remains constant throughout the proportional loading, and k_0 is determined using Jacky's formula [19]:

$$k_0 = 1 - \sin \varphi_c \quad (2)$$

Then, the value of k_0 is used to find the p by:

$$\ln \sigma = \ln \left(\frac{3}{1+2k_0} p \right) = \ln \left(\frac{3}{1+2k_0} \right) + \ln p \quad (3)$$

Equation (4) used to get the value of n from the two values of C_c shown in Figure 1 [20] for two distinct values of (p_s):

$$n = \frac{\ln \left(\frac{e_1 c_{c2}}{e_2 c_{c1}} \right)}{\ln \left(\frac{p_2}{p_1} \right)} \quad (4)$$

By applying (5), the h_s can be calculated from the range of p_1 and p_2 :

$$h_s = 3p \left(\frac{ne}{c_c} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (5)$$

The compression curve is influenced by the stiffness parameters (h_s and n), where the former governs the curve's overall slope and the latter its curvature [19].

Fig. 1. Confined compression test results are used to determine the h_s and n parameters [20].

Fig. 2. Confined compression test on loosely dry sample.

Three confined compression tests were conducted on loosely dry sand soil with an initial void ratio e of 0.82 and 800kPa maximal normal stress was applied to them. As part of the sample preparation procedure, the sand was poured down a zero-height funnel to create the loosest condition [20]. The results from the confined compression test performed on loosely sand sample are shown in Figure 2.

D. α and β Parameters

The α parameter is obtained from the triaxial Consolidated Drained (CD) Test carried out on the dense sandy sample with initial void ratio $e = 0.62$, corresponding with Relative Density $Dr = 80.6\%$ and different confining pressures of 50, 100, and 200kPa as shown in Figures 3 and 4. From these tests, the α parameter was found to be equal 0.136 while the hypoplasticity model β can be set to 1 for natural [20]. The final values of the hypoplasticity model are summarized in Table II.

Fig. 3. Deviatoric stress vs. axial strain of the triaxial CD test.

Fig. 4. Volumetric strain vs. axial strain of the triaxial CD test.

TABLE II. HYPOPLASTICITY MODEL PARAMETER VALUES USED IN THIS RESEARCH

Parameter	Value
Critical friction angle ϕ_c	30
Minimum, maximum, and critical void ratio at zero pressure e_{d0}, e_{c0}, e_{i0}	0.56, 0.87, 1.044
Granular hardness h_s (MPa)	4000
Exponent relating to sensitivity of granular skeleton to changes of pressure n	0.419
Exponent describing the transition between peak and critical stress α	0.136
Exponent representing the change of stiffness at current density β	1

IV. VALIDATION PROBLEM

In order to validate the program's capabilities in modeling the hypoplasticity problem, the findings from experimental, numerical (Open Sees, SANI SAND model), and PLAXIS 3D

hypoplasticity analysis were compared. The problem involved a comparison between the results obtained from the experimental and numerical research performed by [22-24] and the results obtained from PLAXIS 3D. The problem includes conducting a number of centrifugal tests to assess the interaction between the soil and the structure of layered liquefiable soil deposits and the seismic site response. The total depth of the soil profile was 18m, consisting of a 3 layered soil of 2m coarse sand crust with a relative density $Dr = 90\%$, a 6m loose sand layer with $Dr = 40\%$, and a 10m dense sand layer with $Dr = 90\%$ at the bottom.

A. Finite Element Modeling

The geometry of the problem was modeled using finite elements under PLAXIS 3D. It is similar to that adopted in the experimental work as shown in Figure 5. A scaled version of the recorded Kobe earthquake was applied at the base of the model, which was referred to as the Kobe-L motion.

Fig. 5. The finite element model adopted in PLAXIS 3D.

B. Soil Modeling

The material behavior of sand in this study was modeled by the hypoplasticity model and the parameters of its implementation were determined by [21] as shown in Table III.

TABLE III. PARAMETERS OF THE HYPOPLASTICITY MODEL

Parameter	Value
ϕ_c	30
e_{d0}, e_{c0}, e_{i0}	0.53, 0.82, 0.94
h_s (MPa)	2000
n	0.22
α	0.25
β	1

C. Result Comparison

A comparison between the experimental test and PLAXIS 3D results is shown in Figures 6 and 7. It can be seen that the results of maximum settlement are approximately compatible with the results of finite element analysis with slightly difference at 8m depth. The vertical settlement, however, is evolving considerably more quickly according to the model than what was actually seen during the experiment, even though they are still in good agreement. The results of excess pore water pressure show a good agreement between the experimental results and numerical analysis. Finally, it can be concluded that the proposed (hypoplasticity) model and PLAXIS 3D software can manipulate the dynamic analysis with good accuracy and are considered an appropriate tool for studies of the soil pile interaction effects.

Fig. 6. Experimentally measured, numerically computed (open sees) settlement versus time after [23] and PLAXIS 3D results at depth (a) 0m, (b) 2m, and (c)=8m.

Fig. 7. Experimentally measured, numerically computed (open sees) excess pore water pressure versus time after [23] and PLAXIS 3D results at depth (a) 0m, (b) 2m, and (c) 8m.

V. PARAMETRIC STUDY

In this research, the behavior of the piled-raft system is analyzed using PLAXIS 3D under varying seismic loading. The analysis is focused on the pile response under seismic loading. Three different elements are included in the model: volume element for the soil, plate element for the raft, and building and embedded beams for the piles as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. 3D finite element model.

A. Material Properties

The properties of the sandy soil are shown in Table II. The piles have been modeled as embedded circular massive beams with 0.3m diameter.

B. Earthquake Data

Earthquake records data were utilized to study the effects of acceleration characteristics within soil and pile. Two different real acceleration records, namely Upland and Kobe earthquakes were used (Table IV and Figure 9).

TABLE IV. INFORMATION REGARDING THE EARTHQUAKE DATA [25]

Earthquake	Upland	Kobe
Region	Los Angeles area, Southern California, USA	Japan
Magnitude (MW)	5.7	6.9
Date (UTC)	1990-02-28 23:43:36	1995-01-16 20:24:52
Shaking duration (s)	20	48
Acceleration direction	N-W	N-S
Maximum acceleration (g)	0.24	0.82
Epicenter depth (km)	10	7.9
Station code	CLMCV	KIMA
Station distance to the epicenter (km)	120.3	1.0
Modified Mercalli intensity (MMI)	VII – Very Strong	VII – Very Strong
Reference	[25]	

Fig. 9. Earthquake record.

C. Results and Discussion

1) Effect of Pile Length and Pile Spacing on Vertical Settlement

The effect of pile spacing (2D, 3D, and 4D) on the response of the piled raft subject to earthquake excitation is studied in this section. Figures 10-14 show the time history of the soil settlement measured in the middle of raft (A) and at the edge of raft point (B) for both earthquake motions.

Fig. 10. Variation of the vertical settlement with time at point (A) during the Kobe earthquake at S/D = (a) 2, (b) 3, (c) 4.

Fig. 11. Variation of the vertical settlement with time at point (B) during the Kobe earthquake at S/D = (a) 2, (b) 3, (c) 4.

Fig. 12. Variation of the vertical settlement with time at point (A) during the Upland earthquake at S/D = (a) 2, (b) 3, (c) 4.

Fig. 13. Variation of the vertical settlement with time at point (B) during the Upland earthquake at S/D = (a) 2, (b) 3, (c) 4.

It can be concluded that increasing the spacing among piles to 3D and 4D from the basic 2D spacing increases the total settlement. This behavior could be attributed to the decrease in spacing between piles that applied additional lateral forces between soil particles by holding them together and providing confining media. This action resists the external forces thus decreasing total settlement. This force affects the piles as well as soil particles leading more friction forces at the pile surfaces as the friction is a function of normal forces and the friction coefficient, so increasing the skin friction leads to more resistance in total settlement as a result. The decrease in spacing between piles means that the piles are concentrated at the middle of the raft which resists the dishing effect occurring in the sand. This action leads to a decrease in probable total settlement as the maximum settlement occurs in the middle of the raft in the case of sand due to the dishing phenomenon. Finally, it can be concluded that total settlement increases as the pile spacing increases. Similar observation was noticed in [26-27]. For increasing pile length, load transfer is affected by the pile length. This factor is considered by selection of 3 different piles lengths (L/D) equal to 35, 45, and 55. Based on numerical analysis, it is found that the increase of pile length decreases the total settlement of piled foundation as shown in Figures 10-14. This behavior can be attributed to the increase of the pile length which absorbs more power applied from earthquakes and dissipates the applied forces since the settlement is a function of the applied load [26-32].

Earthquake excitation has a major influence on the piled raft behavior. Piled raft foundation placed on loose dry soil and subjected by Kobe and Upland earthquake motions was

modeled numerically to investigate the effect of the excitation on the total settlement (Figures 10-14). From these Figures, it can be concluded that the total settlement of pile raft increases as the earthquake excitation increases. Higher excitation leads to higher dynamic loading, which results in higher settlement, as the settlement is a function of loading.

2) Effect of Pile Length and Pile Spacing on Maximum Pile Bending Moment

Pile foundations can be divided into two categories based on the ratio of the effective unsupported length (L) to the average pile diameter (D), where $L/D > 30$ denotes a long pile and $L/D \leq 20$ denotes a short pile [28]. The effect of length to pile diameter L/D (35, 45, and 55) and pile spacing S/D (2, 3, and 4) on the response of piled raft subjected to two earthquake excitations is illustrated in Figures 15-17. The following points can be noted: The maximum bending moment occurred at the connection between the piles and the raft and the zero moment is located near the tip of the pile. Also, it can be concluded that increasing the spacing among piles to 3D and 4D 2D increases the bending moment along the pile shaft. This behavior can be explained by the fact that higher excitation leads to higher dynamic loading which results in higher bending moment.

Fig. 14. Variation of max. vertical settlement with S/D at point (A) for (a) Kobe and (b) Upland earthquake.

The effectiveness of the constitutive models employed in the modeling of the soil-pile interaction under the influence of earthquake motion is a key factor in the precise simulation of the numerical analysis in geotechnical engineering. There are limited numerical investigations of the behavior of soil-pile interaction using various constitutive models. Each of these models has its own unique features and advantages, most fall short of providing an adequate description of this behavior. Due to this factor, the analysis of soil-pile-structure systems subjected to seismic stress using an efficient model (the hypoplasticity model) is the goal of this study. The hypoplasticity constitutive model is implemented using the UMAT subroutine, which is then incorporated as a dynamic linked library (DLL) in the PLAXIS 3D finite element program.

Fig. 15. Variation of bending moment along pile (P11) at peak ground acceleration during the Kobe earthquake at S/D = (a) 2, (b) 3, (c) 4.

Fig. 16. Variation of bending moment along pile (P11) at peak ground acceleration during the Upland earthquake at S/D = (a) 2, (b) 3, (c) 4.

This model predicts with accuracy the soil response to various soil densities, stress levels, and loading conditions. It also requires several parameters that are easy to gather by conventional laboratory testing. The model's ability in modeling soil-pile interaction was validated with results from experimental tests and also with findings from numerical results conducted using the SANISAND constitutive model. A numerical model of a 10-story building supported by pile systems (soil-pile structure) was examined in order to look into the effects of various interactional parameters. To examine the impact of the excitation frequency, two seismic motions were used. Additionally, the effects of various pile lengths and spacings were examined.

Fig. 17. Variation of max. bending moment with S/D at pile (P11) at peak ground acceleration for (a) Kobe and (b) Upland earthquake.

VI. CONCLUSION

The hypoplasticity constitutive model and the finite element method were used in this study to investigate the dynamic soil pile interaction. The soil parameters for this model were obtained by laboratory tests and were calibrated according to known relationships. The main conclusions from this study are:

- The hypoplasticity constitutive model is quite satisfactory in representing the behavior of the response of the pile foundation under earthquake excitation.
- Increasing in the length of piles decreases the settlement of the piled raft system.
- Increasing the spacing between piles increases the settlement of the piled raft system.
- Increasing the length and pile spacing increases the bending moment.

REFERENCES

[1] R. A. Rajapakse, *Geotechnical Engineering Calculations and Rules of Thumb*, 1st ed. Oxford, UK: Butterworth-Heinemann, 2008.
 [2] R. Mackevicius, "Possibility for Stabilization of Grounds and Foundations of Two Valuable Ancient Cathedrals on Weak Soils in

- Baltic Sea Region with Grouting," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 57, pp. 730–738, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2013.04.092>.
- [3] M. Tatyana, N. Alexander, and C. Anastasia, "Reinforced Sandy Piles for Low-rise Buildings," *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 117, pp. 239–245, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.08.156>.
- [4] M. T. A. Chaudhary, M. Abe, and Y. Fujino, "Identification of soil–structure interaction effect in base-isolated bridges from earthquake records," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 21, no. 8, pp. 713–725, Dec. 2001, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0267-7261\(01\)00042-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0267-7261(01)00042-2).
- [5] B. Manna and D. K. Baidya, "Dynamic nonlinear response of pile foundations under vertical vibration—Theory versus experiment," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 456–469, Jun. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2010.01.002>.
- [6] M. T. A. Chaudhary, "FEM modelling of a large piled raft for settlement control in weak rock," *Engineering Structures*, vol. 29, no. 11, pp. 2901–2907, Nov. 2007, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engstruct.2007.02.001>.
- [7] G. W. Blaney, "Dynamic Stiffness of Piles," in *International Conference on Numerical Methods in Geotechnical Engineering*, Blacksburg, VA, USA, 1976, pp. 1001–1012.
- [8] S. Prakash, S. Kumar, and K. Sreerama, "Pile-soil-pile interaction effects under earthquake loadings," in *Eleventh World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, Acapulco, Mexico, Jun. 1996.
- [9] D. Pitilakis, M. Dietz, D. M. Wood, D. Clouteau, and A. Modaressi, "Numerical simulation of dynamic soil–structure interaction in shaking table testing," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 453–467, Jun. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2007.07.011>.
- [10] D. Giretti, "Modeling of piled raft foundations in sand," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Ferrara, Ferrara, Italy, 2010.
- [11] I. G. Abdulwahhab, "Experimental and Numerical Approach for the Behavior of Machinery Piled Raft Foundation Embedded within Cohesionless Soils," M.S. thesis, University of Technology, Baghdad, Iraq, 2017.
- [12] M. S. Ashghabadi and X. Cheng, "Investigation of Seismic Behavior of Clay-Pile Using Nonlinear Kinematic Hardening Model," *Advances in Civil Engineering*, vol. 2020, Jul. 2020, Art. no. e9617287, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/9617287>.
- [13] L. Zhang, S. H. Goh, and H. Liu, "Seismic response of pile-raft-clay system subjected to a long-duration earthquake: centrifuge test and finite element analysis," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 92, pp. 488–502, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2016.10.018>.
- [14] T. Thanapon and A. Goran, "Three-Dimensional Analysis of Soil-Pile-Structure Interaction Problem on High Rise Building on Improved Soft Soil," *International Journal of Geomate*, vol. 21, no. 88, pp. 54–60, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.21660/2021.88.gxi293>.
- [15] D. Kolymbas, "A generalized hypoelastic constitutive law," in *Proceedings of the 11th international conference on soil mechanics and foundation engineering*, San Francisco, CA, USA, 1988.
- [16] B. Hua, C. Hao, J. Zhao, C. Wang, X. Zhang, and G. Wang, "Nonlinear FEM analysis of bearing capacity and sedimentation of single pile in multi-layered soils," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computing in Civil and Building Engineering*, Shanghai, China, 2010.
- [17] K. E. Anaraki, "Hypoplasticity Investigated: Parameter Determination and Numerical Simulation," M.S. thesis, Delft University of Technology, Delft, Netherlands, 2008.
- [18] T. Kadlicek, T. Janda, and M. Sejnoha, "Calibration of Hypoplastic Models for Soils," *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, vol. 821, pp. 503–511, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.821.503>.
- [19] R. Suchomel and D. Masin, "Calibration of an advanced soil constitutive model for use in probabilistic numerical analysis," in *1st International Symposium on Computational Geomechanics*, Juan-les-Pins, France, Dec. 2009, pp. 265–274.
- [20] D. Masin, "Hypoplasticity for practical applications part 4: determination of material parameters," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Prague, Prague, Czech Republic, 2015.
- [21] I. Herle and G. Gudehus, "Determination of parameters of a hypoplastic constitutive model from properties of grain assemblies," *Mechanics of Cohesive-frictional Materials*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 461–486, 1999, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1484\(199909\)4:5<461::AID-CFM71>3.0.CO;2-P](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1484(199909)4:5<461::AID-CFM71>3.0.CO;2-P).
- [22] J. Olarte, B. Paramasivam, S. Dashti, A. Liel, and J. Zannin, "Centrifuge modeling of mitigation-soil-foundation-structure interaction on liquefiable ground," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 97, pp. 304–323, Jun. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2017.03.014>.
- [23] J. Ramirez *et al.*, "Site Response in a Layered Liquefiable Deposit: Evaluation of Different Numerical Tools and Methodologies with Centrifuge Experimental Results," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 144, no. 10, Oct. 2018, Art. no. 04018073, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0001947](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0001947).
- [24] S. S. Nagula, Y.-W. Hwang, S. Dashti, and J. Grabe, "Seismic site response of layered saturated sand: comparison of finite element simulations with centrifuge test results," *International Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 1, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 26, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40703-021-00155-2>.
- [25] "COSMOS," *COSMOS*. <http://strongmotion.org/index.html>.
- [26] S. Azhar, A. Patidar, and S. Jaurker, "Parametric Study of Piled Raft Foundation for High Rise Buildings," *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, vol. 9, no. 12, pp. 548–555, 2020.
- [27] A. El-Attar, "Dynamic analysis of combined piled raft system (CPRS)," *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 2533–2547, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2020.12.014>.
- [28] B. S. Albusoda and O. Y. Almashhadany, "Effect of Allowable Vertical Load and Length/Diameter Ratio (L/D) on Behavior of Pile Group Subjected to Torsion," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 20, no. 12, pp. 13–31, 2014.
- [29] L. Salem, "Effect Of Pile Spacing On The Behavior Of Piled Raft Foundation Under Free Vibration And Earthquake," *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 12, pp. 240–247, Jan. 2016.
- [30] M. O. Karkush, "Impacts of Soil Contamination on the Response of Piles Foundation under a Combination of Loading," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 917–922, Feb. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.616>.
- [31] J. A. Alomari, "The Effect of Mass, Depth, and Properties of the Soil Below the Raft Foundation on the Seismic Performance of R.C. Plane Frames," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4685–4688, Oct. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2943>.
- [32] T. Nagao and D. Shibata, "Experimental Study of the Lateral Spreading Pressure Acting on a Pile Foundation During Earthquakes," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 5021–5028, Dec. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.3217>.

Modeling and Simulation of Manufacturing Processes and Systems: Overview of Tools, Challenges, and Future Opportunities

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Abstract-Manufacturing is an important part of the modern economy. It is characterized by complexity in terms of systems, approaches, and interactions with intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Numerous efforts have been developed to use modeling and simulation tools to improve manufacturing efficiency and productivity and to achieve maximum quality, especially with the different mutations in the factories of today. This paper reviews the conventional and modern tools used in manufacturing system design and production improvement. Challenges that need to be addressed by the simulation community are discussed in depth. Finally, the evolution, advances, current practices, and future opportunities are discussed in the context of the contemporary manufacturing industry.

Keywords-production processes; systems; tools; simulation; modeling; mutation; Industry 4.0; Industry 5.0

I. INTRODUCTION

The majority of factories today face many challenges when trying to define how to acquire and maintain their position in the competitive business environment. A major challenge is to ensure that production, supply, and customer processes are correctly implemented and stabilized. These processes transform the input material and increase its value [1-3]. The main goal of the factories and enterprises today and in the future is to increase the value of the product effectively and to produce the smallest possible amounts of waste [4-6]. Therefore, production processes have attracted a strong interest in the modern factory design [7-9]. Consisting of various devices which have a set of tasks, triggered by specific commands, a manufacturing system is traditionally evaluated and analyzed by simulation [10-11], which is a powerful and widely recognized technique [12].

While most previous works were focused in the simulations and modeling of manufacturing systems as a tool of analysis and development, the orientation of our research into new manufacturing approaches is directed towards the area of modern manufacturing systems, using reconfigurable manufacturing systems, adaptive logistics, and the concept of

Industry 4.0. New simulation systems which must be adapted to this new requirement are therefore discussed.

The article deals with the description of the simulation tools and modeling of conventional and modern manufacturing concepts that are potentially highly applicable for use in future factories and the core descriptions of these tools in the process control for the Industry 4.0 and the emerging Industry 5.0. Therefore, after considering factory mutations, the paper investigates the evaluation, advances, current practices and future trends of simulation methods and approaches. Digital twins, suitable performance, lean in manufacturing system, IoT-enabled forms, and Virtual Reality (VR) in process design, planning, and verification are examined.

II. MUTATION OF FACTORIES

During the last decade, an increase on the demand of individualized products and natural resources has been noticed [13]. Besides, the huge evolution in technology and the smart concepts stimulate the user demand [14-17]. As a consequence, strong mutations in the society behavior, lifestyle, and consumption are noticed and are considered as new indicators of globalization [18-21]. The manufacturing systems represent a significant growing share to the global trade and become more and more challenging [22-24].

Authors in [25] are among the first who introduced the virtual manufacturing concept by integrating different factory models, whereas authors in [26] proposed virtual facilities for different ways in a smart manufacturing system, including simulation, virtual organization, and emulation facility. Actually, the most important point in the factory mutation is the appearing of the Factory of Things (FoT) [27]. FoT is based on technology characterized by the embedment of physical devices and many electronic compounds, with a wireless internet connection, known as the Internet of Things (IoT) [28-30]. It is fueling the industry 4.0 and space, health, and nanotechnology factories [30-32]. New challenges are raised by the Industry 4.0 which drives smart factories by: i) data

volumes and connectivity, ii) business intelligence capabilities, iii) human machine interaction, iv) emergence of modern transferring digital instructions to the physical world [33-37]. As a consequence, IoT is considered to be a key technology, required to support the propagation of successful Smart Manufacturing as the extension of the IoT concept to manufacturing systems [38-41]. Besides, as information is the most required input for a smart factory, advanced technologies like wireless sensor networks and cyber physical systems are needed to provide the parameters used in the analysis platform for seamless, automated simulation, optimization of shapes and geometry, and management of data and outputs [42-44]. These elements create a smart environment, and make communication between machine process compounds with central processing or various other possibilities [45]. This new concept is resumed as [26]: evolution of a system of data in terms of time, process, and manipulation: i) calculation of the time between a stop and the next start event in a manufacturing operation, ii) calculation of the number of produced parts between two steps as a second service [46].

III. DIGITAL TWINS

To create production process models, a digital twin of a physical process is needed, one that will enable process monitoring, real-time decision making, and control [47]. A digital twin represents a virtual model of a physical object which can simulate the object's behavior [48]. In that way it is possible to simulate production steps and to predict the impact on the product [49]. These simulations are highly utilized in Industry 4.0 to simulate products, robots, and humans in order to reduce failures and optimize resource consumption [50]. Numerical models are used for different manufacturing domains, beside the expansion of available data sources. They are particularly used for proving simulations of various parameters difficult to measure [51]. Therefore, hybrid digital twins are used to model the usual behavior of the underlying manufacturing process or system [52]. This hybrid concept offers new services like detecting data-driven anomalies on simulations for new protective data, virtual prototyping, or a virtual instance of a physical system (twin) [53]. The objective is to lead high precision models showing not only physical parameters, but also a representation of their behavior, for monitoring, simulation, optimization, and developing of new products [54].

IV. MANUFACTURING PROCESSES AND SYSTEMS: MODELING AND SIMULATION FOR SUITABLE PERFORMANCE

A manufacturing process is a system characterized by a continuous evolution, interaction, and mutation, as it is a complex dynamic system, composed of several elements: management approaches, production facilities, control and monitoring equipment, and machining tools and operators [55]. With the variation in user demand, the search for better performance, environmental constraints, stability of production systems, and increased competition, the manufacturing processes are becoming more and more complex [56]. Decomposition of a production system into subsystems of various depths is a necessity for the suitable analysis and effective study at the different levels of its specification [57]. Optimization of production and manufacturing processes is

established through data processing tools [58]. This approach allows dissecting and deriving, the relations between elements of technology, transport, storing, and layout subsystems. However, it is not an evident or easy engineering task [59]. Therefore, models and simulations are used to achieve effective and efficient production, by improving existing processes, or innovating a required system, to reduce time cost, improve productivity, achieve competitively, and ensure quality [60]. It can be accomplished through a simulation of varied schemes of production on relation to different intrinsic and extrinsic factors (for example, parallel, sequential, or mixed schemes of production, different types of plant layout (process layout, product layout, combination layout, fixed position layout), design of manufacturing value chain, etc.) [61-69]. It is planned as consequent data usage, transformation, integration, and aggregation driving real innovation [70].

V. SIMULATION-BASED MULTI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION AND LEAN MANUFACTURING

A. Conventional Tools

To develop and improve manufacturing processes and different related systems, we use different simulation models. A good formulation of a model which describes the function, evolution, and interaction with different related elements is based on data analysis and study [70]. Different techniques for process improvement are exploited. Linear programming, Discrete-Event Simulation (DES), System Dynamic (SD), Markov Chain Analysis, and Monte Carlo Simulation are considered the most popular conventional simulation tools [71-74]. Various modeling formalisms have been established to describe the manufacturing processes and systems for varied fields and engineering applications (e.g. model of a machine, cell, line, site, etc.) [75, 76].

1) Discrete Event Simulation Parameters

The manufacturing systems are described with much formalism. The Discrete Event System (DEVS) specification is the most popular tool for modeling deterministic systems [77-79]. The elements are interchangeable in many cases and are related by graphs, diagrams, and Petri-net formalism [80-82]. As it is a rigorous and able tool to describe discrete event models in hierarchical and modular manner, DEVS is considered an efficient way to describe production processes mathematically when they are divided into different stages within a sequence of production steps [83, 84]. Complex and stochastic flows in production lines and logistics systems are also described by this simulation tool [85-87] with relatively minor investment. As indicated in [88], DEVS can provide several scenarios despite the need of a large amount of modeling time in order to analyze system performance and to converge to an optimum solution. However, as the simulation is not an optimization tool by itself, in some cases, the improved scenario cannot give an optimized solution [89, 90]. Unavoidable parameters in this stimulation tool are illustrated in Table I.

2) Simulation Based Optimization

Simulations of processes, machines, lines, or entire factories are built for a variety of reasons including virtual

experimentation, prediction, and optimization [91]. In order to be confident in any result of such a model, it must be validated against the real system [92]. The opposite also happens, when we wish to know whether the machines are operating as expected. This is done by comparing the data gathered from the simulation to the data gathered from the smart factory [93]. It is possible to perform this validation using summary statistical information, but it can hide the dependencies present in the underlying data [94]. Stimulation Based Optimization (SBO) combined with incline devices has a tremendous potential for the framework and handle advancement in fabricating. While SBO can be utilized to analyze complex energetic frameworks with high inconstancy and an expansive sum of conceivable arrangements, incline devices can make up a base for persistent change in individual processes [95]. Be that as it may, there is frequently a need of information in order to begin working with incline devices and reenactment approaches, particularly in production lines with a long history and tradition [22].

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF DIFFERENT SIMULATION MODELS

Failures	Amounts of different kinds
	Distribution of durations
	Distribution of intervals
Cycle times	Of processes
	Of assemblies
	Of manual task (distribution)
Steps	Times (distribution)
	Dependencies between articles
Batches	Container sizes
	Delivery quantity
	Frequencies

B. Modern Tools

VR, 3D Discrete Event Simulation (DES), data analytics, and real-life data from the products, processes, and production systems are considered the most popular modern tools for simulation and optimization [96-98].

1) Virtual Reality (VR)

Integration of training in an immersive VR environment, with simulation, modeling, and data analytics, is planned to make harmonization and dissemination of knowledge more accessible [99, 100]. Demonstrating the 3D VR recreation based on genuine production line and item information envelops the as-is show of the fabricating plant, counting the consistent connections. In this stage, the substances within the VR can be considered computerized models of their physical partners [101]. The virtual tests of a computerized exhibition are based on the standards of simulation-type modeling [102]. Tests are utilized to survey the robustness and the ability of the physical equipment to comply with the prerequisites of the Terms of Reference (ToR) described within the virtual machine by the specialized computer program (SW) components [103].

2) Data Analytics and Real-Life Data from Products, Processes, and Production Systems

A virtual representation of fabrication frameworks utilizing the information from genuine industrial facilities can offer arrangements for item advancement and bolster item presentation forms, from design-to-manufacturing to

simulation-based information analytics. It can allow shrewd generation frameworks [104-108]. Appropriately, the virtual plant is a coordinated, high-fidelity recreation demonstration of a fabricating plant, which offers a progressed choice bolster capability and can back the assessment and reconfiguration of unused or existing fabricating frameworks [109, 110]. Therefore, real-time information integration between VR-enabled VF recreations is considered to be superior with higher exactness, precision, and unwavering quality [111-113].

3) 3D Discrete Event Simulation (DES) Using FlexSim Simulation Tool

FlexSim simulation tool was utilized to create a VR recreation in [114]. It is a 3D DES computer program which contains common and health-care-focused items [115-116]. Its user-friendly drag and drop interface and comprehensive visual capabilities were considered important for quick experimentation. FlexSim's inserted VR capability permits clients to show, run, and control the recreations and collect the factual information in 3D graphical VR environment [117-119]. This capability brought significant preferences in diminishing the time for approval after each reconfiguration/redesign of the VR. The interesting sentence structure of the instrument makes it challenging to create customized models [25].

4) Simulation for Learning Factories: The Example of Fischertechnik Manufacturing Plant Models

Manufacturing businesses are transitioning towards more independent and smart generation lines within the Industry 4.0. Learning production lines as small-scale physical models of shop floors is done in order to conduct inquiries about the shrewd fabricating zone without depending on costly genuine generation lines or totally mimicked information. Learning factories are used for conducting investigations within the setting of commerce administration and IoT [120]. The physical Fischertechnik manufacturing plant model mimics complex generation lines. Three case studies of combined BPM and IoT were considered in [121-125], i.e. the execution of a BPM deliberation stack on behalf of a learning manufacturing plant, the experience-based adjustment and optimization of fabricating forms, and the stream processing-based conformance checking of IoT-enabled forms. By utilizing physical manufacturing plant models as test beds for assessment, investigation is more realistic—but more challenging—than utilizing artificial information in this kind of profoundly energetic CPPS. Physical plant models empower the approval and exhibition of inquiries about artifacts in an ensured environment [125]. At the same time, this close-to-reality recreation of a genuine generation line encourages the exchange of created concepts into hone.

C. Model-Based System Engineering (MBSE)

MBSE could be a key enabler for building complex frameworks as can be seen by the expanded number of related distributions [125-127]. For effectively building Industry 4.0 frameworks, the MBSE community plays a pivotal part by empowering the previously mentioned plan standards. Model-based framework designs have appeared to encourage the improvement of such frameworks, but their application to

Industry 4.0 has not been efficiently explored [128]. To comprehend the commitment of MBSE to Industry 4.0, precise mapping has been conducted in [30, 129-130], which uncovered that computerized representation of robotized frameworks, i.e. their interfacing and information models, as well as their integration and (re)configuration are the prime Industry 4.0 concerns tended to by MBSE. Most published papers contribute strategies and ideas to illuminate specific challenges of Industry 4.0.

VI. FUTURE OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

Investigation on the evolution and recent developments of industrial simulation technology and describing the gaps and future trends in this field are important in order to explore future opportunities for more effective manufacturing processes and system implementations. In the complex item digital twin arrangement, the items display and reenact procedures that create and expand tremendous sums of (generally organized) information. The arrangement of models along the complete lifecycle of a complex item (e.g. as outlined, as fabricated, as kept up) requires advanced modeling-simulation techniques. Looking at the mechanization within the machine fabricating field and mechanical autonomy, the larger challenge is signified by the working program, particularly planning program frameworks. Another distinctive challenge is the actual execution. In this way, projection and enhancement of the computerization and mechanical autonomy program frameworks ended up critical and with issues. In this manner, the information analytics capability was not most centered on advancement. The DA capability of the recreation device was utilized to produce standard diagnostics for the shop-floor operations [131].

Nowadays, the concept of the shrewd plant is rising with the joining of the virtual and physical universes. As indicated above, the shrewd manufacturing plant could be a fabricating environment that can handle turbulences amid utilizing decentralized data and communication structures for ideal administration of generation forms. Within the case of a conventional plant, it is not fundamental to consider turbulences since the planning and execution tasks are consecutively performed. In other words, a conventional production line does not begin execution before the ultimate affirmation of the generation planning. A shrewd manufacturing plant, in any case, permits the concurrent advance of the planning and execution errands, since it has the means to handle turbulences in real-time generation [132].

This issue lead us to talk about the next generation of simulation systems, especially the need of more human-centered technology approaches, nascent in Industry 4.0, and now central to the emerging Industry 5.0, which is a value-driven concept based on three principle cores: human-centricity, sustainability, and resilience [133-135]. Simulation tools and modeling must adapt to the requirements of the new concepts of Industry 5.0: changes do not happen overnight in the systems that will use these new trends. The challenges are to find suitable modeling and simulation tools to introduce the concepts of the new paradigm in each essential segment of the manufacturing and to draw a connection matrix between key

enablers for Industry 4.0 and 5.0, particularly people, companies, and technology [136, 137].

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper at first highlighted the conventional and modern simulation and modeling tools used in manufacturing system design and production improvement. Challenges needed to be addressed by the simulation community were discussed in depth. Finally, evolution, advances, current practices and future opportunities were discussed in the context of the contemporary manufacturing industry, particularly the challenges of the Industry 4.0 and the opportunities of Industry 5.0.

This paper can be applied mainly in the field of the development of smart manufacturing systems, where the control system and the manufacturing process use simulations in order to predict efficiently the processes of future factories.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Yu and C. Zheng, "Tools, application areas and challenges of factory simulation in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises – A Review," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 104, pp. 399–404, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2021.11.067>.
- [2] N. Edh Mirzaei, P. Hilletoft, and R. Pal, "Challenges to competitive manufacturing in high-cost environments: checklist and insights from Swedish manufacturing firms," *Operations Management Research*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 272–292, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12063-021-00193-0>.
- [3] M. Masmali, "Implementation of Lean Manufacturing in a Cement Industry," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7069–7074, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4087>.
- [4] M. Kumar and M. Mani, "Sustainability Assessment in Manufacturing for Effectiveness: Challenges and Opportunities," *Frontiers in Sustainability*, vol. 3, Mar. 2022, Art. no. 837016, <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2022.837016>.
- [5] J. Kleineidam, "Fields of Action for Designing Measures to Avoid Food Losses in Logistics Networks," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 15, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 6093, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12156093>.
- [6] E. A. Boom Carcamo and R. Penabaena-Niebles, "Opportunities and challenges for the waste management in emerging and frontier countries through industrial symbiosis," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 363, Aug. 2022, Art. no. 132607, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.132607>.
- [7] M. B. Ayed, L. Zouari, and M. Abid, "Software In the Loop Simulation for Robot Manipulators," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 2017–2021, Oct. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.1285>.
- [8] L. Malburg, M.-P. Rieder, R. Seiger, P. Klein, and R. Bergmann, "Object Detection for Smart Factory Processes by Machine Learning," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 184, pp. 581–588, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.04.009>.
- [9] F. Alorifi, S. M. A. Ghaly, M. Y. Shalaby, M. A. Ali, and M. O. Khan, "Analysis and Detection of a Target Gas System Based on TDLAS & LabVIEW," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4196–4199, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2736>.
- [10] D. Mourtzis, "Simulation in the design and operation of manufacturing systems: state of the art and new trends," *International Journal of Production Research*, vol. 58, no. 7, pp. 1927–1949, Apr. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2019.1636321>.
- [11] D. Mourtzis, M. Doukas, and D. Bernidaki, "Simulation in Manufacturing: Review and Challenges," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 25, pp. 213–229, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2014.10.032>.
- [12] S. Caceres-Gelvez, M. D. Arango-Serna, and J. A. Zapata-Cortes, "Evaluating the performance of a cellular manufacturing system proposal for the sewing department of a sportswear manufacturing

- company: A simulation approach," *Journal of Applied Research and Technology*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 68–83, Mar. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.22201/icat.24486736e.2022.20.1.1335>.
- [13] A. Gupta, K. Singh, and R. Verma, "A critical study and comparison of manufacturing simulation softwares using analytic hierarchy process," *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 108–129, Mar. 2010.
- [14] S. M. Lee and S. Trimi, "Innovation for creating a smart future," *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–8, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2016.11.001>.
- [15] M. Al-Amin, M. Tanjim Hossain, and M. Jahidul Islam, "The Technology Development and Management of Smart Manufacturing System: A Review On Theoretical and Technological Perspectives," *European Scientific Journal*, vol. 17, no. 43, pp. 170–193, 2021.
- [16] "How Smart, Connected Products Are Transforming Competition." <https://hbr.org/2014/11/how-smart-connected-products-are-transforming-competition> (accessed Oct. 25, 2022).
- [17] M.-H. Hsiao, "A conceptual framework for technology-enabled and technology-dependent user behavior toward device mesh and mesh app," *Future Business Journal*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 130–138, Jun. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbj.2018.03.003>.
- [18] J. J. Yun, D. Won, and K. Park, "Dynamics from open innovation to evolutionary change," *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, vol. 2, no. 2, Jun. 2016, Art. no. 7, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40852-016-0033-0>.
- [19] Economic and Social Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, *Globalization and development: 29th session*. Brasilia, Brasil: UN, ECLAC, 2002.
- [20] B. Roach, N. Goodwin, and J. Nelson, "Consumption and the Consumer Society," in *Microeconomics in Context*, London, UK: Routledge, 2019.
- [21] V. Melnyk, F. A. Carrillat, and V. Melnyk, "The Influence of Social Norms on Consumer Behavior: A Meta-Analysis," *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 86, no. 3, pp. 98–120, May 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00222429211029199>.
- [22] S. Lockie, "Mainstreaming climate change sociology," *Environmental Sociology*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–6, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23251042.2022.2043529>.
- [23] E. R. Zuniga, M. U. Moris, and A. Syberfeldt, "Integrating simulation-based optimization, lean, and the concepts of industry 4.0," in *Winter Simulation Conference*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, Dec. 2017, pp. 3828–3839, <https://doi.org/10.1109/WSC.2017.8248094>.
- [24] C. Herrmann, C. Schmidt, D. Kurle, S. Blume, and S. Thiede, "Sustainability in manufacturing and factories of the future," *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing-Green Technology*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 283–292, Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40684-014-0034-z>.
- [25] S. J. Hu, "Evolving Paradigms of Manufacturing: From Mass Production to Mass Customization and Personalization," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 7, pp. 3–8, Jan. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2013.05.002>.
- [26] E. Yildiz, C. Moller, and A. Bilberg, "Demonstration and evaluation of a digital twin-based virtual factory," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 114, no. 1, pp. 185–203, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-021-06825-w>.
- [27] S. Jain, N. Fong Choong, K. Maung Aye, and M. Luo, "Virtual factory: an integrated approach to manufacturing systems modeling," *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, vol. 21, no. 5/6, pp. 594–608, Jan. 2001, <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443570110390354>.
- [28] D. Zuehlke, "SmartFactory—Towards a factory-of-things," *Annual Reviews in Control*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 129–138, Apr. 2010, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arcontrol.2010.02.008>.
- [29] J. Cecil, "A Collaborative Manufacturing Approach supporting adoption of IoT Principles in Micro Devices Assembly," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 26, pp. 1265–1277, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2018.07.141>.
- [30] D. T. Matt, V. Modrak, and H. Zsifkovits, Eds., *Implementing Industry 4.0 in SMEs: Concepts, Examples and Applications*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2021.
- [31] G. Tsaramiris *et al.*, "A Modern Approach towards an Industry 4.0 Model: From Driving Technologies to Management," *Journal of Sensors*, vol. 2022, Jun. 2022, Art. no. e5023011, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5023011>.
- [32] S. Paul *et al.*, "Industry 4.0 Applications for Medical/Healthcare Services," *Journal of Sensor and Actuator Networks*, vol. 10, no. 3, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 43, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jsan10030043>.
- [33] C. Bai, P. Dallasega, G. Orzes, and J. Sarkis, "Industry 4.0 technologies assessment: A sustainability perspective," *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 229, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 107776, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2020.107776>.
- [34] F. Shrouf, J. Ordieres, and G. Miragliotta, "Smart factories in Industry 4.0: A review of the concept and of energy management approached in production based on the Internet of Things paradigm," in *International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management*, Selangor, Malaysia, Dec. 2014, pp. 697–701, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEM.2014.7058728>.
- [35] G. Buchi, M. Cugno, and R. Castagnoli, "Smart factory performance and Industry 4.0," *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, vol. 150, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 119790, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2019.119790>.
- [36] J. Morgan, M. Halton, Y. Qiao, and J. G. Breslin, "Industry 4.0 smart reconfigurable manufacturing machines," *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, vol. 59, pp. 481–506, Apr. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2021.03.001>.
- [37] T. C. Ng, S. Y. Lau, M. Ghobakhloo, M. Fathi, and M. S. Liang, "The Application of Industry 4.0 Technological Constituents for Sustainable Manufacturing: A Content-Centric Review," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 7, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 4327, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14074327>.
- [38] F. Orellana and R. Torres, "From legacy-based factories to smart factories level 2 according to the industry 4.0," *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 32, no. 4–5, pp. 441–451, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0951192X.2019.1609702>.
- [39] J. Guo and M. Martinez-Garcia, "Key technologies towards smart manufacturing based on swarm intelligence and edge computing," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 92, Jun. 2021, Art. no. 107119, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compeleceng.2021.107119>.
- [40] I. Castelo-Branco, F. Cruz-Jesus, and T. Oliveira, "Assessing Industry 4.0 readiness in manufacturing: Evidence for the European Union," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 107, pp. 22–32, May 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2019.01.007>.
- [41] R. Contreras-Masse, A. Ochoa-Zezzatti, V. Garcia, J. Mejia, and S. Gonzalez, "Application of IoT with haptics interface in the smart manufacturing industry," *International Journal of Combinatorial Optimization Problems and Informatics*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 57–70, 2019.
- [42] S. Kumar, P. Tiwari, and M. Zymbler, "Internet of Things is a revolutionary approach for future technology enhancement: a review," *Journal of Big Data*, vol. 6, no. 1, Dec. 2019, Art. no. 111, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-019-0268-2>.
- [43] F. Ferracuti, A. Freddi, A. Monteriu, and M. Prist, "An Integrated Simulation Module for Cyber-Physical Automation Systems," *Sensors*, vol. 16, no. 5, May 2016, Art. no. 645, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s16050645>.
- [44] G. Lazaroiu, M. Andronie, M. Iatagan, M. Geamanu, R. Stefanescu, and I. Dijmarescu, "Deep Learning-Assisted Smart Process Planning, Robotic Wireless Sensor Networks, and Geospatial Big Data Management Algorithms in the Internet of Manufacturing Things," *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, vol. 11, no. 5, May 2022, Art. no. 277, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi11050277>.
- [45] K. Zvarikova, M. Rowland, and T. Krulicky, "Sustainable Industry 4.0 Wireless Networks, Smart Factory Performance, and Cognitive Automation in Cyber-Physical System-based Manufacturing," *Journal of Self-Governance and Management Economics*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 7–20, 2021.
- [46] A. Nabavi-Pelesaraei, S. Rafiee, S. S. Mohtasebi, H. Hosseinzadeh-Bandbafha, and K. Chau, "Integration of artificial intelligence methods and life cycle assessment to predict energy output and environmental impacts of paddy production," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol.

- 631–632, pp. 1279–1294, Aug. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.03.088>.
- [47] R. Senington, F. Baumeister, A. Ng, and J. Oscarsson, "A linked data approach for the connection of manufacturing processes with production simulation models," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 70, pp. 440–445, Jan. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2018.03.243>.
- [48] M. Perno, L. Hvam, and A. Haug, "Implementation of digital twins in the process industry: A systematic literature review of enablers and barriers," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 134, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 103558, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2021.103558>.
- [49] A. Barkanyi, T. Chovan, S. Nemeth, and J. Abonyi, "Modelling for Digital Twins—Potential Role of Surrogate Models," *Processes*, vol. 9, no. 3, Mar. 2021, Art. no. 476, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9030476>.
- [50] R. Kazala, S. Luscinski, P. Straczynski, and A. Taneva, "An Enabling Open-Source Technology for Development and Prototyping of Production Systems by Applying Digital Twinning," *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 1, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 21, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21237830>.
- [51] P. Staczek, J. Pizon, W. Danilczuk, and A. Gola, "A Digital Twin Approach for the Improvement of an Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMR's) Operating Environment—A Case Study," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 23, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 7830, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21237830>.
- [52] E. Yildiz, C. Moller, and A. Bilberg, "Demonstration and evaluation of a digital twin-based virtual factory," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 114, no. 1, pp. 185–203, May 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-021-06825-w>.
- [53] A. Bamberg, L. Urbas, S. Broecker, M. Bortz, and N. Kockmann, "The Digital Twin – Your Ingenious Companion for Process Engineering and Smart Production," *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 44, no. 6, pp. 954–961, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ceat.202000562>.
- [54] Y.-H. Kuo, F. Pilati, T. Qu, and G. Q. Huang, "Digital twin-enabled smart industrial systems: recent developments and future perspectives," *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 34, no. 7–8, pp. 685–689, Aug. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0951192X.2021.1959710>.
- [55] D. Yang, H. R. Karimi, O. Kaynak, and S. Yin, "Developments of digital twin technologies in industrial, smart city and healthcare sectors: a survey," *Complex Engineering Systems*, vol. 1, no. 1, Sep. 2021, Art. no. 3, <https://doi.org/10.20517/ces.2021.06>.
- [56] M. Gregor, J. Matuszek, and D. Plinta, "Modelling and simulation of manufacturing processes in managing and planning of machines' setup," *Advances in Manufacturing Science and Technology*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 7–17, 2013.
- [57] R. Domingo, J. Blanco-Fernandez, and J. L. Garcia-Alcaraz, "Complexity in Manufacturing Processes and Systems 2019," *Complexity*, vol. 2020, Jul. 2020, Art. no. e7286932, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/7286932>.
- [58] A. V. Deshmukh, J. J. Talavage, and M. M. Barash, "Complexity in manufacturing systems, Part I: Analysis of static complexity," *IIE Transactions*, vol. 30, no. 7, pp. 645–655, Jul. 1998, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07408179808966508>.
- [59] M. K. Chernyakov, M. M. Chernyakova, and K. Ch. Akberov, "Simulation Design of Manufacturing Processes and Production Systems," *Advances in Engineering Research*, vol. 157, pp. 124–128, 2018.
- [60] M. Lutjen and A. Ait Alla, "Risk-Optimized Design of Production Systems by Use of GRAMOSA," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2014, Mar. 2014, Art. no. e934176, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/934176>.
- [61] M. Jurkovic, Z. Jurkovic, G. Cukor, M. Brezocnik, and M. Sekulic, "Application of Modeling and Simulation in Reengineering of Manufacturing Processes," *Journal of Trends in the Development of Machinery and Associated Technology*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 63–66, 2014.
- [62] Zs. J. Viharos and L. Monostori, "Quality-oriented modelling, simulation and management of production lines," in *37th CIRP International Seminar on Manufacturing Systems, Digital enterprises, production networks*, Budapest, Hungary, Dec. 2004, pp. 457–462.
- [63] V. Schindlerova, I. Sajdlerova, and D. Lehocka, "Dynamic simulation for optimisation solution of manufacturing processes," *MATEC Web of Conferences*, vol. 244, 2018, Art. no. 01010, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201824401010>.
- [64] A. Blanco, E. Dahlquist, J. Kappen, J. Manninen, C. Negro, and R. Ritala, "Use of modelling and simulation in the pulp and paper industry," *Mathematical and Computer Modelling of Dynamical Systems*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 409–423, Nov. 2009, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13873950903375387>.
- [65] S. Benavent, P. Rosado, F. Romero, and J. V. Abellan, "Control strategies comparison for a multi-stage assembly system using simulation," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1193, no. 1, Jul. 2021, Art. no. 012089, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1193/1/012089>.
- [66] N. Daneshjo, V. Rudy, P. Drabik, and P. Malega, "Methods and Procedures Applied to Design of Production Processes and Systems," *TEM Journal*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 1435–1442, Nov. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.18421/TEM94-15>.
- [67] V. A. Dolgov, P. A. Nikishechkin, A. A. Leonov, S. S. Ivashin, and N. V. Dolgov, "Mathematical Modeling of Production Processes of Discrete Machine-Building Enterprises Based on the Interaction of Simulation Systems and Operational Planning Systems," *EPJ Web of Conferences*, vol. 248, 2021, Art. no. 04014, <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202124804014>.
- [68] B. Benderskiy, P. Frankovsky, and A. Chernova, "Numerical Simulation of Intrachamber Processes in the Power Plant," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 11, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 4990, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11114990>.
- [69] E. Gresova and J. Svetlik, "Mathematical Modeling of the Manufacturing Sector's Dominant Part as a Base for Automation," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 11, no. 7, Jan. 2021, Art. no. 3295, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11073295>.
- [70] C. Barbosa and A. Azevedo, "Hybrid Simulation for Complex Manufacturing Value-chain Environments," *Procedia Manufacturing*, vol. 11, pp. 1404–1412, Jan. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2017.07.270>.
- [71] D. S. Chang and S. C. Park, "Configuration space-based discrete event system specification formalism for a smart factory with real-time flexibility," *Concurrent Engineering*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 265–275, Sep. 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1063293X18776046>.
- [72] H. Reinhardt, M. Weber, and M. Putz, "A Survey on Automatic Model Generation for Material Flow Simulation in Discrete Manufacturing," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 81, pp. 121–126, Jan. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2019.03.022>.
- [73] H. Kanj, W. H. F. Aly, and S. Kanj, "A Novel Dynamic Approach for Risk Analysis and Simulation Using Multi-Agents Model," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 10, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 5062, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12105062>.
- [74] M. Taleb-Berrouane, F. Khan, and P. Amyotte, "Bayesian Stochastic Petri Nets (BSPN) - A new modelling tool for dynamic safety and reliability analysis," *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 193, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 106587, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2019.106587>.
- [75] W. Delaney, *Dynamic Models and Discrete Event Simulation*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2020.
- [76] R. Y. Rubinstein and D. P. Kroese, *Simulation and the Monte Carlo Method*, 3rd Edition. New York, NY, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2017.
- [77] W. D. Kelton and A. M. Law, *Simulation Modelling and Analysis*, 3rd Revised edition. New York, NY, USA: Mcgraw Hill, 2000.
- [78] K. G. Samuel, N.-D. M. Bouare, O. Maiga, and M. K. Traore, "A DEVS-based pivotal modeling formalism and its verification and validation framework," *SIMULATION*, vol. 96, no. 12, pp. 969–992, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0037549720958056>.
- [79] K. H. Kim, Y. R. Seong, T.-G. Kim, and K. H. Park, "Distributed simulation of hierarchical DEVS models: Hierarchical scheduling locally and time warp globally," *Transactions of the Society for Computer Simulation International*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 135–154, 1996.
- [80] H. O. Aliyu, O. Maiga, and M. K. Traore, "A framework for discrete events systems enactment," in *29th EURO/SIS/IEEE European Simulation & Modelling Conference*, Leicester, UK, Oct. 2015, pp. 149–156.

- [81] V. Albert and C. Foucher, "Formal Framework for Discrete-Event Simulation," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 5812–5817, Jul. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.535>.
- [82] C.-C. Huang, "Discrete event system modeling using SysML and model transformation," Ph.D. dissertation, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA, USA, 2011.
- [83] P. Fonseca i Casas, D. Lijia Hu, A. Guasch i Petit, and J. Figueras i Jove, "Simplifying the Verification of Simulation Models through Petri Net to FlexSim Mapping," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 4, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 1395, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10041395>.
- [84] S. Emami, F. Barzegaran, and A. Divsalar, "A Mathematical Model for Production Planning and Scheduling in a Production System: A Case Study," *International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management Science*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 1–16, Jul. 2019.
- [85] E. De Gentili, A. De Cicco, and J.-F. Santucci, "Devs and Fuzzy logic to model and simulate a manufacturing process," in *International Conference on Computational Intelligence for Modelling, Control and Automation and International Conference on Intelligent Agents, Web Technologies and Internet Commerce*, Vienna, Austria, Nov. 2005, vol. 1, pp. 557–564, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CIMCA.2005.1631322>.
- [86] P. Pujo, M. Pedetti, and N. Giambiasi, "Formal DEVS modelling and simulation of a flow-shop relocation method without interrupting the production," *Simulation Modelling Practice and Theory*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 817–842, Oct. 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.simpat.2006.01.001>.
- [87] C. Frydman, M. Le Goc, L. Torres, and N. Giambiasi, "Knowledge-Based diagnosis in SACHEM using DEVS models," *Special Issues of Transaction of Society for Modeling and Simulation International (SCS) on Recent Advances in DEVS Methodology*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 147–158, 2001.
- [88] V. Riccardi, P. Pujo, and C. Frydman, "DEVS Modelling For The Proactive Control By Simulation Of Kanban Production Lines," presented at the The International Workshop on Modeling & Applied Simulation (MAS 2003), Bergeggi, Italy, Jan. 2003.
- [89] J.-K. Lee, M.-W. Lee, and S.-D. Chi, "DEVS/HLA-Based Modeling and Simulation for Intelligent Transportation Systems," *SIMULATION*, vol. 79, no. 8, pp. 423–439, Aug. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0037549703040233>.
- [90] N. Giambiasi, B. Escude, and S. Ghosh, "GDEVs: A Generalized Discrete Event Specification for Accurate Modeling of Dynamic systems," *Transactions of SCS*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 120–134, 2000.
- [91] M. F. Yegul, F. S. Erenay, S. Striepe, and M. Yavuz, "Improving configuration of complex production lines via simulation-based optimization," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 109, pp. 295–312, Jul. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2017.04.019>.
- [92] P. Grznar *et al.*, "Modeling and Simulation of Processes in a Factory of the Future," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 13, Jan. 2020, Art. no. 4503, <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10134503>.
- [93] S. Robinson, "Simulation model verification and validation: increasing the users' confidence," in *Proceedings of the 29th conference on Winter simulation*, USA, Sep. 1997, pp. 53–59, <https://doi.org/10.1145/268437.268448>.
- [94] M. Dornhofer, S. Sack, J. Zenkert, and M. Fathi, "Simulation of Smart Factory Processes Applying Multi-Agent-Systems—A Knowledge Management Perspective," *Journal of Manufacturing and Materials Processing*, vol. 4, no. 3, Sep. 2020, Art. no. 89, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmmp4030089>.
- [95] J. P. C. Kleijnen, "Verification and validation of simulation models," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 82, no. 1, pp. 145–162, Apr. 1995, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217\(94\)00016-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217(94)00016-6).
- [96] A.-T. Nguyen, S. Reiter, and P. Rigo, "A review on simulation-based optimization methods applied to building performance analysis," *Applied Energy*, vol. 113, pp. 1043–1058, Jan. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.08.061>.
- [97] C. J. Turner, W. Hutabarat, J. Oyekan, and A. Tiwari, "Discrete Event Simulation and Virtual Reality Use in Industry: New Opportunities and Future Trends," *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 882–894, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1109/THMS.2016.2596099>.
- [98] I. J. Akpan and M. Shanker, "A comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of virtual reality, 3D visualization and 2D visual interactive simulation: an exploratory meta-analysis," *SIMULATION*, vol. 95, no. 2, pp. 145–170, Feb. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0037549718757039>.
- [99] A. Ismail, H.-L. Truong, and W. Kastner, "Manufacturing process data analysis pipelines: a requirements analysis and survey," *Journal of Big Data*, vol. 6, no. 1, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 1, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-018-0162-3>.
- [100] J. L. Rubio-Tamayo, M. Gertrudix Barrio, and F. Garcia Garcia, "Immersive Environments and Virtual Reality: Systematic Review and Advances in Communication, Interaction and Simulation," *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction*, vol. 1, no. 4, Dec. 2017, Art. no. 21, <https://doi.org/10.3390/mti1040021>.
- [101] S. Safikhani, S. Keller, G. Schweiger, and J. Pirker, "Immersive virtual reality for extending the potential of building information modeling in architecture, engineering, and construction sector: systematic review," *International Journal of Digital Earth*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 503–526, Dec. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2022.2038291>.
- [102] A. A. Malik, T. Masood, and A. Bilberg, "Virtual reality in manufacturing: immersive and collaborative artificial-reality in design of human-robot workspace," *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 22–37, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0951192X.2019.1690685>.
- [103] T. S. Mujber, T. Szecsi, and M. S. J. Hashmi, "Virtual reality applications in manufacturing process simulation," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 155–156, pp. 1834–1838, Nov. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2004.04.401>.
- [104] A. Gurjanov, D. Zakoldaev, A. Shukalov, and I. Zharinov, "Cloud services of digital and smart factories of the Industry 4.0," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 497, no. 1, Nov. 2019, Art. no. 012042, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/497/1/012042>.
- [105] S. J. Mazivla and J. L. M. Santos, "A review on multivariate curve resolution applied to spectroscopic and chromatographic data acquired during the real-time monitoring of evolving multi-component processes: From process analytical chemistry (PAC) to process analytical technology (PAT)," *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 157, Dec. 2022, Art. no. 116698, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2022.116698>.
- [106] M. Glisic, S. Sarfraz, B. Veluri, and D. Ramanujan, "A Systematic Framework for Quantifying Production System-Specific Challenges in Life Cycle Inventory Data Collection," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 105, pp. 210–218, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2022.02.035>.
- [107] R. Kumar *et al.*, "Live Life Cycle Assessment Implementation using Cyber Physical Production System Framework for 3D Printed Products," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 105, pp. 284–289, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2022.02.047>.
- [108] M. Wolf *et al.*, "Real Time Locating Systems for Human Centered Production Planning and Monitoring," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 55, no. 2, pp. 366–371, Jan. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2022.04.221>.
- [109] R. Woitsch, A. Sumereder, and D. Falcioni, "Model-based data integration along the product & service life cycle supported by digital twinning," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 140, Sep. 2022, Art. no. 103648, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2022.103648>.
- [110] T. Bauernhansl *et al.*, "Semantic Structuring of Elements and Capabilities in Ultra-flexible Factories," *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 93, pp. 335–340, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2020.04.010>.
- [111] C. Chauhan, V. Parida, and A. Dhir, "Linking circular economy and digitalisation technologies: A systematic literature review of past achievements and future promises," *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, vol. 177, Apr. 2022, Art. no. 121508, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121508>.
- [112] K. Seemanthini and S. S. Manjunath, "Recognition of trivial humanoid group event using clustering and higher order local auto-correlation techniques," in *Cognitive Computing for Human-Robot Interaction*, M. Mittal, R. R. Shah, and S. Roy, Eds. Cambridge, MA, United States: Academic Press, 2021, pp. 253–286.

- [113] Xie B. Xie *et al.*, "A Review on Virtual Reality Skill Training Applications," *Frontiers in Virtual Reality*, vol. 2, 2021, Art. no. 645153.
- [114] K. Aati, D. Chang, P. Edara, and C. Sun, "Immersive Work Zone Inspection Training using Virtual Reality," *Transportation Research Record*, vol. 2674, no. 12, pp. 224–232, Dec. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198120953146>.
- [115] M. Cueva, "Simulation Modeling Meets Virtual Reality, Oculus Rift," *FlexSim*, Feb. 12, 2016. <https://www.flexsim.com/fr/g%C3%A9n%C3%A9ral/simulation-modeling-meets-virtual-reality-oculus-rift/> (accessed Oct. 26, 2022).
- [116] R. Armstrong, S. de Ribaupierre, and R. Eagleson, "A software system for evaluation and training of spatial reasoning and neuroanatomical knowledge in a virtual environment," *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, vol. 114, no. 1, pp. 29–37, Apr. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2014.01.006>.
- [117] S. de Ribaupierre, R. Armstrong, D. Noltie, M. Kramers, and R. Eagleson, "VR and AR simulator for neurosurgical training," in *IEEE Virtual Reality (VR)*, Arles, France, Mar. 2015, pp. 147–148, <https://doi.org/10.1109/VR.2015.7223338>.
- [118] K. Wang and X. Wang, "Simulation Optimization Research on Logistics Distribution Center Picking Operation," in *International Conference on Logistics Engineering, Management and Computer Science*, Shenyang, China, Dec. 2014, pp. 1202–1205.
- [119] T. S. Mujber, "Development of VR-simulator software for manufacturing systems as a decision making and simulation tool," Ph.D. dissertation, Dublin City University, Dublin, Ireland, 2005.
- [120] W. B. Nordgren, "Flexible simulation (Flexsim) software: Flexsim simulation environment," in *35th Conference on Winter Simulation: Driving Innovation*, New Orleans, Louisiana, Dec. 2003, pp. 197–200.
- [121] "Driving Data Security Through IoT in Business Processes," *Technology Solutions | AI backed Knowledge Management, IoT, Device Care*, May 15, 2019. <https://www.kochartech.com/driving-efficiency-and-data-privacy-with-iot-in-bpm/> (accessed Oct. 26, 2022).
- [122] L. Malburg, R. Seiger, R. Bergmann, and B. Weber, "Using Physical Factory Simulation Models for Business Process Management Research," in *International Conference on Business Process Management*, Seville, Spain, Sep. 2020, pp. 95–107, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-66498-5_8.
- [123] P. Klein, L. Malburg, and R. Bergmann, "FTOnto: A Domain Ontology for a Fischertechnik Simulation Production Factory by Reusing Existing Ontologies," in *Proceedings of the Conference "Lernen, Wissen, Daten, Analysen" (LWDA) 2019*, 2019.
- [124] R. L. Sapena, "BT-Industry 4.0 through Fischertechnik and a Digital Twin – HSLU Technik & Architektur: Bachelor- und Master-Arbeiten 2022," B.Sc. thesis, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences, 2020.
- [125] "Factory Simulation 24V." <https://www.fischertechnik.de/en/service/elearning/simulating/fabrik-simulation-24v> (accessed Oct. 26, 2022).
- [126] A. L. Ramos, J. V. Ferreira, and J. Barcelo, "Model-Based Systems Engineering: An Emerging Approach for Modern Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C (Applications and Reviews)*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 101–111, Jan. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCC.2011.2106495>.
- [127] D. Kaslow, G. Soremekun, H. Kim, and S. Spangelo, "Integrated model-based systems engineering (MBSE) applied to the Simulation of a CubeSat mission," in *IEEE Aerospace Conference*, Big Sky, MT, USA, Mar. 2014, pp. 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1109/AERO.2014.6836317>.
- [128] B. A. Mousavi, C. Heavey, R. Azzouz, H. Ehm, C. Millauer, and R. Knobloch, "Use of Model-Based System Engineering methodology and tools for disruption analysis of supply chains: A case in semiconductor manufacturing," *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, vol. 28, Jul. 2022, Art. no. 100335, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jii.2022.100335>.
- [129] A. Akundi and V. Lopez, "A Review on Application of Model Based Systems Engineering to Manufacturing and Production Engineering Systems," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 185, pp. 101–108, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2021.05.011>.
- [130] A. Wortmann, B. Combemale, and O. Barais, "A Systematic Mapping Study on Modeling for Industry 4.0," in *20th International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems*, Austin, TX, USA, Sep. 2017, pp. 281–291, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MODELS.2017.14>.
- [131] G. Styles and R. Kalawsky, "Research Top Challenges for MBSE in Industry 4.0 and IoT – Workshop Report 291015," Oct. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4556.7767>.
- [132] Emre E. Yildiz and C. Moller, "Building a virtual factory: an integrated design approach to building smart factories," *Journal of Global Operations and Strategic Sourcing*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 608–635, Jan. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGOSS-11-2019-0061>.
- [133] R. Sindhvani, S. Afridi, A. Kumar, A. Banaitis, S. Luthra, and P. L. Singh, "Can industry 5.0 revolutionize the wave of resilience and social value creation? A multi-criteria framework to analyze enablers," *Technology in Society*, vol. 68, Feb. 2022, Art. no. 101887, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2022.101887>.
- [134] S. Nahavandi, "Industry 5.0—A Human-Centric Solution," *Sustainability*, vol. 11, no. 16, Jan. 2019, Art. no. 4371, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11164371>.
- [135] D. Ivanov, "The Industry 5.0 framework: viability-based integration of the resilience, sustainability, and human-centricity perspectives," *International Journal of Production Research*, pp. 1–13, Sep. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2022.2118892>.
- [136] S. Grabowska, S. Saniuk, and B. Gajdzik, "Industry 5.0: improving humanization and sustainability of Industry 4.0," *Scientometrics*, vol. 127, no. 6, pp. 3117–3144, Jun. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04370-1>.
- [137] D. Mourtzis, J. Angelopoulos, and N. Panopoulos, "A Literature Review of the Challenges and Opportunities of the Transition from Industry 4.0 to Society 5.0," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 17, Jan. 2022, Art. no. 6276, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15176276>.

Experimental Analysis of the Dynamic Response of Saturated Clayey Soil Under Impact Loading

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Abstract-The impact of loads on machine foundations is a typical cause of vibrations in industrial applications. Typically, these foundations will transfer vertical dynamic loads to the surface, which will result in earth vibrations that may cause structural damage to nearby structures. Dynamic impacts can vary from significant failure of sensitive sensors or systems to evident structural damage. The current work investigates the behavior of saturated clay soil under a single impulsive load. Deflectometry via falling weights was conducted to produce single pulse energy by dropping different weights from various elevations. The reactions of soils at various places were investigated (vertical displacement at topsoil surface). Such reactions consist of displacements, velocities, and accelerations caused by the impact occurring at the surface depth. The maximum displacement reaction of stiff soil was reduced by 80% in comparison with soft soil under the same impact load. The average percentage of change for stiff soil was 49% larger than for soft soil, as a result of kinetic energy caused by an increased contact surface. Maximum displacements increased with increasing operational frequency and dynamic load.

Keywords-impact load; saturated clay; circular footings; displacement; surface level

I. INTRODUCTION

Foundations are regarded as the backbone of buildings. For their construction, we must have prior knowledge of the soil characteristics, such as shear strength and water absorption [1]. Saturated soils are subjected to a variety of dynamic/cyclic loading types, including high-strain (earthquake and blast) and low-strain loading (machine vibrations, traffic loading, and wave loading). Under these conditions, particle structure breakdown causes instability in the soil mass, which severely damages structures [2]. Dynamic soil properties determine the soil response to impact loads. The response of dynamic loading is evaluated in order to estimate the active soil properties. Dynamic studies consider stiffness, damping ratio, and unit weight [3]. Many studies have been conducted with regard to the surface depth and loading frequency effects upon shallow foundations in stiff and soft clay soil. Impact loads and excess pore water pressure are evaluated at the soil surface under the foundation. Maximum displacement increases with increasing

operational frequency and the excess pore water pressure increases with increased dynamic load. The dynamic properties of the soil layers affect the site seismic response. This response impacts the performance of inserted or overlying structures. Identification and inverse problem-solving techniques are essential to value in situ soil factors and calibrating simulations of soil system dynamic forces. The increasing availability of high-quality laboratory and field data aided the rise in soil investigation system identification studies [4].

Hammers, presses, and turbines are supported by foundations that experience significant dynamic and vibratory effects [5]. The dynamical behavior of the soil-foundation systems is the most significant factor in ensuring the successful operation of a machine. The basic purpose of the design of a machine's foundation is to limit its motion to amplitudes that neither risk the machine's functioning, nor disturb nearby employees. Consequently, a vital element of a solid design of foundations, the plan is the engineering analysis of the footings' reaction to the anticipated dynamical force caused by the use of the machinery. Additionally, when significant movements of an existing footing restrict the operation of the supported machinery, an inquiry must be conducted to identify the fundamental causes of the problem. Therefore, in the investigation, Soil-Structure Interaction (SSI) phenomena that are exposed to impact load are studied [6]. Firstly, the dynamic SSI subject to impact forces is tested using vibrating tables. SSI impacts were then explored by contrasting the soil-structure system with a solid footing condition. After that, a mathematical analysis that passes the SSI tests is given. The nonlinear behavior of soil in the finite element simulation is modeled independently using a boundary surface deformation method and a related linear approach. The estimation results from the boundary surface plasticity model turn out to be more accurate than the experiments. Lastly, geometrical analysis is used to study the effects of different soils and structural features on SSI. The analysis shows that SSI greatly decreases the dynamical responsiveness of buildings, and this effect increases with the frequency of the superstructure relatively to the velocity of the soil. The impact of the contact between soil and structures is reduced by increased soil shear wave velocity.

This is crucial of the way SSI affects the response of structures and also for uses in the design process [7]. The coupling of the reactions of their different elements makes the mechanics of saturated clay more complex than that of single-phase materials. For saturated clay, when the permeability is low and transient loading is rapid, because the soil pores are filled with water, the permeability is low and transient loading is rapid. This relationship should be considered for an appropriate assessment of the behavior of earth constructions and foundations [8]. When the applied loads to the structure increase and exceed the cracking load, the damaged supporter of individual groups exhibits a relatively high rate of stiffness drop [9, 10] as a result of a portion of the pre-stressing force, which increases the rate of cracking and displacements. Many researchers have looked into the way machinery moves. Authors in [11-15] looked into the way vertical vibrations affect surface footings.

II. EXPERIMENTAL MODELS AND WITH MATERIALS

A. Soil Used and Material Properties

Brown clayey soil was taken from a depth of 1.0m from the soil subsurface of a brick factories site in the Al-Nahrawan city, 54km east of Baghdad. The tests were conducted following the standards for identifying the physical and chemical properties of the soil. The specifics of these requirements are detailed in Table I. A consolidation test was conducted for both stiff and soft clay according to [16]. The consolidation test results for both types of clay are shown in Table II. The experimental program consists of a series of 16 tests done on stiff and soft clay soil with dynamic loading of varied sources of energy, evaluated at the soil's surface (OB), with 2 different foundation sizes, where B is the diameter of the foundation. Systematic tests were carried out to test the dynamic reaction of foundations when subjected to an impactor. Figure 1 displays the equipment adopted for testing. It consisted of a steel container having a wall made of 2.0mm -thick plating and a basis as a soil container, as well as a falling weight deflectometer to apply impact loads to a modeling technique with a ground baseplate that remains measured as a surface footing on the topsoil under impactor. The dimensions of the steel container were 1200.0mm length, 1200.0mm width, and 800.0mm height. Trial tests were carried out to assess the efficiency of the preparation method, before the preparation of the soil. A relation between the water content and the soil's undrained shear strength can be seen found in Figure 3. The soil layers in the steel container were prepared as follows:

- The soil was left to dry in the air. Then, it was crashed into small pieces with a hammer and crushed with a machine.
- The dry soil was separated into two groups, 25kg each.
- Every grouping for each soil model was combined in mixing with enough water to provide an undrained shear strength (Cu) of 20-25kPa for the soft clay state and 73kPa for the stiff clay state. The value of moisture content was selected from Figure 4.
- Clay was mixed with water and added to steel containers in stages. Every level was then pressed down using special wooden compacting hammers that were 150mm×150mm in

size. Every layer's outcome was around 50mm. The process was carried out until the clay bed's full depth.

- After the end of the clay layers' preparations, it was blanketed using nylon sheeting and then left for a curing time of 4 days.
- Using a portable vane shear apparatus, the undrained shear strength was determined every day to reach the nearest value of shear strength as seen in Figure 2.

TABLE I. SOIL PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

Property	Value	Standard of the test
Specific gravity Gs	2.71	ASTM D854
Gravel (> 4.75mm) %	0	ASTM D422
Sand (4.75 - 0.075mm) %	3	
Silt (0.075 - 0.005mm) %	40	
Clay (< 0.005mm) %	57	
Liquid Limit (LL)	39	ASTM D4318
Plastic Limit (PL)	22	
Plasticity index	17	
Gypsum content (CaSO ₄ 2H ₂ O) %	0.23	BS 1377-3
Total Dissolved Salts (TDS) %	0.39	ASTM D5907
SO ₃ content %	0.19	BS 1377-3
Organic Matter (OM) %	0.2	ASTM D2974
Ph value	9.18	ASTM D4972
Classification according to USCS	CL	ASTM D2487

Fig. 1. The experimental soil model's setup.

Fig. 2. Portable vane shear device used to control the undrained shear strength.

TABLE II. CONSOLIDATION TEST RESULTS FOR STIFF AND SOFT CLAY

Parameter	Stiff state	Soft state
Cu (kN/m ²)	73	20-25
e o	0.58	0.73
γ dry	19.12	16.45
γ sat	21.4	19.4

Fig. 3. Relations between shear strength and liquidity index.

Fig. 4. Undrained shear strength versus moisture content.

Fig. 5. Data acquisition system.

B. Measuring Instruments

The bearing plates were positioned directly at the soil surface and dropping masses used to apply the soil model in the vertical impact dynamic loading had different weights (5.0 or

10.0kg) and heights to simulate different impact values (500.0 or 250.0mm). Foundation contact plates were used in 2 sizes: 100.0 and 150.0mm, to determine the topsoil response to an impactor. Then, two pore water pressure gauges were inserted in the middle of the clay level in the vertical position beneath the centroid of the bearing plates at a depth of B or 2B, depending on the size of the bearing plates. Data collection was organized in such a way that all information could be analyzed and captured continuously. The transmitted impulse response record, displacement-time history, and soil surface depths could all be measured with this technique. The acceleration-time history was computed using an accelerometer transducer and surface levels for each test. The basic design of the FWD mechanism consisted of a base structure with an integrated accelerometer and an indicator unit. The card reader could collect and retain a variety of different calculations. The indicator shows the peak load value and the displacement value. Its storage card's data can be directly transmitted to a computer or through the indicator. The program includes a load cell and an accelerometer to assess the impact load and displacement after dropping the small FWD major body's weight in free fall. By integrating the measurements twice in the accelerometer, the displacement is calculated. For a measuring system that employs a laptop, measurement/processing software is necessary. In this system, the data transmitted to the indicators were sent, directly from the indicators, to the laptop, to recognize the acceleration in the clay.

C. Testing Procedure

The following stages outline the testing process:

- Prepare the clay layers for stiff and soft states with a total depth of 800.0mm (100.0mm per level).
- Embed the accelerometer sensor in the middle of the clay layer in the vertical position underneath the bearings plate's center at depths of B or 2B depending on the bearing size.
- Place the sensors horizontally at a depth of 10.0mm, close to the surface.
- Mount the FWD in the middle of the model's ground and confirm its perpendicularity to the model's area after laying the ground.
- The reaction to delivering the impacting mass will be monitored and displayed on a laptop by the data acquisition system shown in Figure 5.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regarding the behavior of saturated clayey soils, it is important to specify that trials were conducted on stiff and soft clay states. A variety of load factors were used in impact testing on the plates ranging between 100.0mm and 150.0mm, depending on the bearing plate's size. They were positioned on the topsoil surface level (0B). A weight of 5.0 or 10.0kg was dropped out of a height of 500.0 or 250.0mm to generate the impact force. Figures 6 to 13 display the dynamic testing results. The data are represented in the (a), (b), (c), and (d) subfigures from every Figure with each reaction, accordingly, including load history, displacement, acceleration, and velocity

functions of time. All these reactions were immediately measured beneath the plates. The variations in vertical displacement (below the plates) are shown in the subfigure (c) of every Figure.

Fig. 6. Dynamic test results for the SOsPI0M5H25 model. (a), (c) impact force-time history with displacements, (b) acceleration time-history, and (d) velocity time-history.

Fig. 7. Dynamic test results for the SOsPI0M5H50 model. (a), (c) impact force-time history with displacements, (b) acceleration time-history, and (d) velocity time-history.

A. Impact and Displacement Responses

The reaction relates to the displacements of the soil surface layer beneath vertically impact energy (measured under the center of the impact plate at 0B depth only). Such reactions were represented in the lower segment of the portion (c) of Figures 6 to 13. There are typical characteristics related to impacts, and they include:

Fig. 8. Dynamic test results for the SOsPI0M10H25 model. (a), (c) impact force-time history with displacements, (b) acceleration time-history, and (d) velocity time-history.

Fig. 9. Dynamic test results for the SOsPI0M10H50 model. (a), (c) impact force-time history with displacements, (b) acceleration time-history, and (d) velocity time-history.

- Maximum impact loads and maximum displacement for stiff clay state occur when the impact plate is located at the topsoil surface of the foundation area (100.0mm) and 10.0kg impactor plate for an elevation of 500.0mm, as is clearly shown in Figure 9.
- Maximum impact loads and maximum displacement for the soft clay state do not occur as for the stiff state to the same soil model.
- The acceleration-time history with velocity-time history are represented in subfigures (a) and (c) of each Figure respectively. The impulsive waves (force-time histories) were discovered to consist of a single half-sine wave pulse. Sometimes in instances, there was no pulse's negative

phase, whereas in a minority of cases, a minor negative phase was observed. This tendency indicates that a stiff clayey stratum acts as a perfect continuous solid, regardless of its density. Because there is a significantly reduced void ratio, impulsive waves are more probable to reflect and refract, which produces the perfect solid-impact behavior.

- The vertical displacements of the foundation block caused by the first hammer blows were computed using the fatigue damage model proposed in this research, and were compared with the analytical results [17]. It can be shown that the simulation findings for vertical displacement are in good agreement with the analytical results.

Fig. 10. Dynamic test results for the SOsP15M5H25 model. (a), (c) impact force-time history with displacements, (b) acceleration time-history, and (d) velocity time-history.

Fig. 11. Dynamic test results for the SOsP15M5H50 model. (a), (c) impact force-time history with displacements, (b) acceleration time-history, and (d) velocity time-history.

Fig. 12. Dynamic test results for the SOsP15M10H25 model. (a), (c) impact force-time history with displacements, (b) acceleration time-history, and (d) velocity time-history.

Fig. 13. Dynamic test results for the SOsP15M10H50 model. (a), (c) impact force-time history with displacements, (b) acceleration time-history, and (d) velocity time-history.

Two piezometers were put under experimental bearing plates to monitor the pore water pressure during the impacts. Figures 14 - 21 represent the excess pore water pressure-time histories recorded by pore water pressure sensors positioned at levels B and 2B underneath the bearing plate's center. The soil-foundations system displays the following behavior:

- For the stiff clay state, based on decreasing the water content, it was determined that the resultant impulse waves have a higher peak than the related soft clay in all observed instances.
- The peak displacement reactions inside the soft clay soil were always higher than those in the stiff clay soil. The rise

in reactions was seen to be higher when the falling hammer's kinetic energy increased (mass and level of fall), when either the mass of the hammer or the elevation of the fall was doubled (from 5.0 to 10.0kg or from 250.0mm to 500.0mm).

- The vertical displacements in soft soil are approximately 78% greater than in the stiff soil at the depth of 0B from the topsoil surface.
- The excess pore water pressure inside the topsoil is shown as a result of three important parameters: impact energy (hammer weight and elevation of drop), size of foundations exposed to the impactor, and soil type. For soft clay soils with constant impact energy, increasing the impact area causes the excess pore water pressure to decrease. In that instance, a 125.0% increase in the plate area (from 100.0 to 150.0mm in diameter) causes a 30–40% drop in the pore water pressure.
- This approach makes sense, given that the excess pore water pressure of stiff clay in comparison to soft clay was decreased by almost 100.0 %, as a result of the decrease in the water content ratio and the increase in the density of clay particles. Conversely, in the case of soft soils.

Fig. 14. Pressure-time history of excess pore water at depth B for the SOsP10M5H25 model.

Fig. 15. Pressure-time history of excess pore water at depth B for the SOsP10M5H25 model.

Fig. 16. Pressure-time history of excess pore water at depth B for the SOsP10M10H25 model.

Fig. 17. Pressure-time history of excess pore water at depth B for the SOsP10M10H50 model.

Fig. 18. Pressure-time history of excess pore water at depth B for the SOsP15M5H25 model.

Fig. 19. Pressure-time history of excess pore water at depth B for the SOsP15M5H50 model.

Fig. 20. Pressure-time history of excess pore water at depth B for the SOsP15M10H25 model.

Fig. 21. Pressure-time history of excess pore water at depth B for the SOsP15M10H50 model.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results can be seen in Figures 6-21. The main conclusions from the results of the current study are:

- The average stiff to soft soil reduction percentage in maximum displacement reaction was 80% under the same

impact load, because stiff soil has 49% stresses generated by a rising in the contact surface than soft soil.

- The excess pore water pressure of soft soil is increased in comparison to stiff soil. Due to the little water content in stiff soil, there was no measured effect of pore water pressures.
- Compared to stiff clay, the amplitude of the force-time history in soft clay is reduced by 40-57%. This reduction happens since the voids are filled with water, causing fewer contact points between particles.
- The frequency ratio (frequency of the impact/frequency of the vibration foundation-soil system) is an important factor in impact load-related concerns.
- The ideal amplitude of the force-time history for stiff soil under impact stress is a single pulse.
- Once the operation frequency increases, the amplitude of displacements on the foundations, total stress, and pore water pressure increased for soft clay circular foundations at the soil's surface.
- The maximum displacement increased with increasing operational frequency and dynamic load.
- The dynamic response increases rapidly with the degree of damage, which in turn affects the transmission of damage in the foundation and the soil due to the higher stresses concentrating near the foundation regions. From the computational analysis of the dynamic features of soil damage, it can be observed that as damage rises, the effects of hammer blows on the surface and depth of the soil near the foundation become more important. This enables the development of a method for managing the damage and its progression in a damaged material, as well as the dynamic response of a damaged structure.

Following these conclusions, it is advised that pile foundations in saturated clay soils can be used in future works with the same standard specifications.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. F. Ali, M. Y. Fattah, and B. A. Ahmed, "Response of circular footing on dry dense sand to impact load with different embedment depths," *Earthquakes and Structures*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 323-336, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.12989/eas.2018.14.4.323>.
- [2] T. A. Rind, H. Karira, A. A. Jhatial, S. Sohu, and A. R. Sandhu, "Particle Crushing Effect on The Geotechnical Properties of Soil," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 4131-4135, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2730>.
- [3] S. Pandya and A. Sachan, "Experimental Studies on Effect of Load Repetition on Dynamic Characteristics of Saturated Ahmedabad Cohesive Soil," *International Journal of Civil Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 781-792, Jun. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40999-019-00392-8>.
- [4] D. Pitilakis, M. Dietz, D. M. Wood, D. Clouteau, and A. Modaressi, "Numerical simulation of dynamic soil-structure interaction in shaking table testing," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 453-467, Jun. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2007.07.011>.
- [5] A. G. Chehab and M. H. El Naggar, "Response of block foundations to impact loads," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 276, no. 1, pp. 293-310, Sep. 2004, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2003.07.028>.

- [6] S. Liu, P. Li, W. Zhang, and Z. Lu, "Experimental study and numerical simulation on dynamic soil-structure interaction under earthquake excitations," *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*, vol. 138, Nov. 2020, Art. no. 106333, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soildyn.2020.106333>.
- [7] A. Khoubani and M. M. Ahmadi, "Numerical study of ground vibration due to impact pile driving," *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 167, no. 1, pp. 28–39, Feb. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeeng.11.00094>.
- [8] Z. Zhang and X. Cheng, "A fully coupled THM model based on a non-equilibrium thermodynamic approach and its application," *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 527–554, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1002/nag.2569>.
- [9] H. Q. Abbas and A. H. Al-Zuhairi, "Flexural Strengthening of Prestressed Girders with Partially Damaged Strands Using Enhancement of Carbon Fiber Laminates by End Sheet Anchorages," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 8884–8890, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5007>.
- [10] B. F. Abdulkareem, A. F. Izzet, and N. Oukaili, "Post-Fire Behavior of Non-Prismatic Beams with Multiple Rectangular Openings Monotonically Loaded," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 7763–7769, Dec. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4488>.
- [11] G. Gazetas and K. H. Stokoe, "Free Vibration of Embedded Foundations: Theory versus Experiment," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 117, no. 9, pp. 1382–1401, Sep. 1991, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1991\)117:9\(1382\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1991)117:9(1382)).
- [12] A. S. Abdulrasool, M. Y. Fattah, and N. M. Salim, "Experimental Investigation for Dynamic Response of Saturated Clay Under Machine Foundation," in *Modern Applications of Geotechnical Engineering and Construction*, Singapore, 2021, pp. 365–374, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-9399-4_30.
- [13] S. Bhattacharya *et al.*, "Chapter 11 - Physical modeling of interaction problems in geotechnical engineering," in *Modeling in Geotechnical Engineering*, P. Samui, S. Kumari, V. Makarov, and P. Kurup, Eds. Academic Press, 2021, pp. 205–256.
- [14] A. A. Allawi and Q. S. Mohammed, "Dynamic Behavior of Machine Foundations on layered sandy soil under Seismic Loadings," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 28, no. 8, pp. 1–20, Aug. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.31026/j.eng.2022.08.01>.
- [15] T. K. Al-Azawi, R. K. Al-Azawi, and Z. K. Al-Jaberi, "Stiffness and damping properties of embedded machine foundation," *Journal of Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 429–444, Jun. 2006.
- [16] ASTM D2435-04: Standard Test Methods for One-Dimensional Consolidation Properties of Soils Using Incremental Loading. ASTM, <https://doi.org/10.1520/D2435-04>.
- [17] X. Xue, T. Ren, and W. Zhang, "Analysis of fatigue damage character of soils under impact load," *Journal of Vibration and Control*, vol. 19, no. 11, pp. 1728–1737, Aug. 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077546312450732>.

A Comparative Study of Reinforced Soil Shear Strength Prediction by the Analytical Approach and Artificial Neural Networks

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Abstract-For the prediction of the shear strength of reinforced soil many approaches are utilized which are complex and they depend on laboratory tests and several parameters. In this study, we aim to investigate and compare the ability of the Gray and Ohashi (GO) model and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) to predict the shear strength of reinforced soil. To achieve this objective, this work was divided into two parts. In the first part and in order to evaluate the impact of different fiber reinforcing parameters on the behavior of the soil, many direct shear experiments were carried out. The results revealed a significant improvement in shear strength values with fiber reinforcement. The increase in shear strength is a function of the fiber length, proportion, and direction. In the second part, we used the results of our experimental study to develop the ANN model. The obtained results agree reasonably well with the experiment ones, with very acceptable error (RMSE =1.714, MAE=5.981, R²=0.960, and E = -1.601%). The comparative study showed that the ANN model was more accurate and statistically more stable than the GO model, and the ANN model took all the conditions of the reinforced soil into one equation. On the other hand, the GO model does not take reinforcement failure and uses several equations.

Keywords-shear strength; reinforced soil; natural fibers; Gray & Ohashi model; artificial neural networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Soil instability can be dangerous and destructive. Soil reinforcement takes into consideration several factors, such as the reinforcement's form, texture, and rigidity [1], its cost-effectiveness, and its environmental friendliness [2-3]. In this work, we used soil reinforced by natural fibers. The prediction of its shear strength is necessary in order to study the soil behavior [1]. Different methods for estimating shear strength in

soils have occurred, generally based on variable theories such as force equilibrium [1, 4-5], statistical analysis [6-7], the approach of superposition of the effects of soil and fibers [8-9], and the energy dissipation approach [10-13]. Gray and Ohashi (GO) [1] suggested that with the addition of discrete fibers, physical and mechanical properties increase, and post-peak strength loss decreases. Based on the force equilibrium approach, the GO model established the shear strength of fiber-reinforced soil (τ_{ff}) as a combination of shear strength increment (ΔS) and unreinforced soil shear strength (τ_{ur}) parameters. The behavior of composite soils is complex since it depends on laboratory tests and many parameters [14]. In this regard, artificial intelligence methods such as the ANNs are promising and can be applied for the development of an approximate function that determines the shear strength under various conditions, considering the complexity of the approach models and the high cost of empirical experiments. During the recent years, the increased use of ANNs to tackle different engineering challenges has become popular in the domains of electronics [15-16], geophysics [17], hydraulics [18], etc. ANNs are used less in geotechnical engineering than in other domains even though there is success in solving such problems (e.g. prediction of pile deflection [19], bearing capacity of foundations [20], seismic deformation of rooted slopes [21], etc.).

The purpose of the current article is to investigate and compare the ability of the GO model and ANNs to predict the shear strength of soil reinforced with natural fibers. The results of the experimental program were utilized to develop the database used in the creation of the ANN structure. This research was carried out at the Laboratory of Civil and Environmental Engineering (LGCE) of the University of Jijel.

II. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

A. Materials

Figure 1 presents the particle size analysis (according to NF P 94-056 and NF P 94-057). Table I describes the physical properties of the studied soil. The soil class is "Sm" according to the LPC code. Alfa fiber "esparto grass" was used as reinforcement. Table II describes its mechanical properties.

Fig. 1. Grain size distribution of the studied soil.

TABLE I. SOIL GEOTECHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Property	Value	Code
Sand equivalent E_s (%)	34	NF P 18-598
Water content (%)	25.85	NF P 94-050
Liquid limit (%)	8.27	NF P 94-051
Plastic limit (%)	1.00	NF P 94-051
Plasticity index (%)	7.27	NF P 94-051
Initial void ratio	0.521	
Methylene blue index (%)	0.215	NF P 94-068
Wet density (KN/m ³)	19	NF P 94-054
Specific gravity G_s	2.65	NF P 94-049

TABLE II. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FIBERS USED [22]

Property	σ (GPa)	ϵ (%)	E (GPa)
Average value	63.83	3.12	2.05
Standard deviation	16.80	0.63	0.77
Coefficient of variance	26.31	20.12	37.55

TABLE III. OBTAINED RESULTS IN DIFFERENT ORIENTATIONS OF THE FIBERS

Direction	Fiber (%)	τ_{ff} (KPa) experimental			τ_{ff} (KPa) GO model [1]			Observation
		$\sigma_n = 100\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 200\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 300\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 100\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 200\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 300\text{KPa}$	
Unreinforced	0.00	52.22	124	160.77	-	-	-	-
	0.25	65.85	170.97	177.91	70.78	121.17	182.04	
	0.50	60.20	111.07	191.41	73.24	137.86	198.54	
	0.75	89.27	187.37	267.82	80.67	141.60	205.69	
Vertical	1.00	79.94	142.75	205.70	101.18	170.60	238.12	$E = 2.89\%$
	0.25	79.30	136.00	192.65	62.14	117.63	172.87	
	0.50	73.04	123.32	170.68	68.56	126.37	183.36	
	0.75	69.50	111.32	170.22	75.42	131.78	190.15	
Inclined	1.00	65.56	111.56	164.5	78.81	141.25	195.58	$E = 5.22\%$
	0.25	78.32	152.5	214.04	59.57	114.25	169.74	
	0.50	71.49	134.61	246.57	61.36	116.62	171.76	
	0.75	71.43	170.10	211.28	63.06	120.55	174.79	
Horizontal	1.00	76.25	134.72	215.47	64.72	123.19	183.76	$E = -18.68\%$

B. Experimental Procedure

Direct shear tests were conducted to a stainless metal box of a squared section of 6x6 cm² and 3cm high (according to NF P 94-071-1). The samples were prepared in undrained conditions and under normal stresses of 100, 200, and 300KPa (with 0.02mm/s loading velocity). Firstly, each sample was mixed with a constant fiber length of 1cm. After that, we added different fiber ratios ρ_f from 0 to 1% by weight of dry soil with a step of 0.25%, in different directions (horizontal, vertical, and inclined at 45°). Then, each sample was mixed with a constant fiber ratio. Then, we added different fiber lengths L_f from 1 to 2.5cm, with an increment step of 0.5cm in different directions (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Specimen preparation in the inclined direction of the alfa fibers.

C. Experimental Results

1) Variation in Fiber Ratio

From Table III, we can see that there is an improvement in shear strength relatively to the increase in reinforcements up to an optimum value. Above that, τ_{ff} decreases. These findings are consistent with those of [1, 14]. The average relative error (1) between the experimental results and the predicted results of shear strength from the GO model varies from 2.32 to -18.68%. The results show acceptable agreement between these two values.

$$E (\%) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\tau_{ff}(\text{experimental}) - \tau_{ff}(\text{predict})}{\tau_{ff}(\text{experimental})} (\%) \quad (1)$$

2) Variation of Fiber Length

The unreinforced soil's shear strength improves in each direction and is limited by the optimum fiber length (Table IV). The fiber direction changes the peak fiber length. This can be caused by the variation in the tensile fiber stress for each direction. The average relative error between the experimental results and the predicted results from the GO

model of shear strength varies from 18.16 to -7.56%. The results show acceptable agreement between these two values. In the vertical direction and at a length of 2.5cm, we observed a higher value of the error (= 59.69%). In this case, and during the test, we observed failure in the fibers. This inaccuracy can be explained by the fact that the GO model does not account for the plasticity of fibers.

TABLE IV. OBTAINED RESULTS IN DIFFERENT FIBER ORIENTATIONS OF DIFFERENT LENGTHS

Direction	Fiber (cm)	τ_{ff} (KPa) experimental			τ_{ff} (KPa) Gray & Ohashi			Observation
		$\sigma_n = 100\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 200\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 300\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 100\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 200\text{KPa}$	$\sigma_n = 300\text{KPa}$	
Unreinforced	0.00	52.22	124	160.77	-	-	-	-
Vertical	1.00	65.85	170.97	177.91	70.78	121.17	182.05	$E = 18.16 \%$
	1.50	63.50	128.30	174.90	76.46	139.04	199.44	
	2.00	67.38	134.37	180.54	79.10	151.97	216.92	
	2.50	59.92	109.91	166.51	95.68	164.96	223.16	
Inclined	1.00	79.30	123.32	170.68	62.14	117.37	172.49	$E = -15.43 \%$
	1.50	74.25	145.80	196.04	65.23	123.18	179.23	
	2.00	85.10	160.30	211.60	69.79	126.11	182.03	
	2.50	89.45	148.48	293.25	70.52	128.92	187.92	
Horizontal	1.00	78.32	152.50	214.04	59.57	114.25	169.74	$E = -7.56 \%$
	1.50	68.87	161.30	207.22	60.49	115.25	171.13	
	2.00	58.32	115.30	161.37	61.56	117.01	171.58	
	2.50	54.25	129.05	162.60	68.00	117.39	174.68	

III. ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Many studies have been conducted on the influence of ANN parameters, especially the activation function, on the ANN performance to assure good model generalization [23-24]. That is why in the current study, we used the growing technique [25]. The growing approach starts with a simple construction and then adds neurons and hidden layers until the performance is satisfactory. As a result, a huge number of simulations were run to determine the best ANN model design. For this, various ANN structures were trained with a different set of activation functions, numbers of hidden layers, and hidden neurons. For the learning algorithm, we used Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) back-propagation, which is the most commonly used for supervised learning [26].

A. Architecture of the Neural Network

The dataset that is utilized to create the neural network model is the product of the previous experiments. Of the 75 data samples, 70% are used for the training, and the algorithm to compute the validation error used the rest of the data. In this research, the model's inputs are the unreinforced soil's shear strength (τ_{ur}), the mobilized tensile strength of fibers (σ_f), the fiber ratio (ρ_f), the fiber length (L_f), and the angle of shear distortion (θ). According to experimental and theoretical studies, these input parameters are the most influential on the shear strength of reinforced soil [1], which is the output of our model (see Figure 3). As we mentioned above, we trained various architectures with different activation functions to obtain an optimum ANN model. In this study, sigmoid, tangent hyperbolic, and linear activation functions through one, two, three, and four-hidden layers with a different number of neurons were investigated.

The growing technique is the method employed in this study to determine the ideal architecture for a neural network model. As a result, we assume a certain number of hidden

layers and neurons at every layer. Then, we calculate the performance criteria (RMSE, MAE, and R^2) given by (2)-(4). If these are very satisfactory, it means that the chosen architecture is performing well. Otherwise, we change the number of hidden layers and neurons until performance criteria are satisfactory.

Fig. 3. The basic structure of the proposed ANN model.

$$R^2 = 1 - \left[\frac{\sum_1^n (\tau_{ff,pr} - \tau_{ff}(\text{experimental}))^2}{\sum_1^n (\tau_{ff}(\text{experimental}) - \text{ moy}(\tau_{ff}(\text{experimental})))^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\tau_{ff,pr} - \tau_{ff}(\text{experimental})| \quad (3)$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_1^n (\tau_{ff,pr} - \tau_{ff}(\text{experimental}))^2} \quad (4)$$

where $\tau_{ff,pr}$ and $\tau_{ff}(\text{experimental})$ are the predicted and the target values of shear strength of reinforced soil respectively.

B. Application of the Neural Network

Many simulations were carried out to find the best ANN model. We started with a simple structure and neurons and

hidden layers were added with various activation functions until the performance was adequate. Table V presents the architecture of the created MLPs. The best obtained models for each combination using different numbers of neurons are indicated.

C. Results and Discussion

Table VI shows the RMSE, MAE, and R² considering the training dataset, testing dataset, and all datasets in each best

ANN model. The last model (A15), which consists of 57 neurons and 4 hidden layers, performs best (see Figure 4). For A1, A2, and A11 models, the training was good but not enough to ensure good generalization ability. By considering the RMSE, MAE, and R² of models A7, A8, and A9, it can be concluded that the sigmoid transfer function in the output layer performs worse than other transfer functions.

TABLE V. DIFFERENT ARCHITECTURES OF MLP MODELS

ANN modes	Number of hidden layers	Number of neurons in hidden layers	Activation Function		Best ANN model
			Input	Output	
A1	1	1 to 30	Sigmoid	Linear	24
A2	1	1 to 30	Tangent Hyperbolic	Linear	12
A3	1	1 to 30	Linear	Linear	29
A4	1	1 to 30	Tangent Hyperbolic	Tangent Hyperbolic	2
A5	1	1 to 30	Linear	Tangent Hyperbolic	29
A6	1	1 to 30	Sigmoid	Tangent Hyperbolic	30
A7	1	1 to 30	Sigmoid	Sigmoid	25
A8	1	1 to 30	Tangent Hyperbolic	Sigmoid	25
A9	1	1 to 30	Linear	Sigmoid	6
A10	2	1 to 30 1 to 30	Tangent Hyperbolic Tangent Hyperbolic	Tangent Hyperbolic	3 - 19
A11	2	1 to 30 1 to 30	Tangent Hyperbolic Tangent Hyperbolic	Linear	4 - 9
A12	2	1 to 30 1 to 30	Linear Linear	Linear	8 - 11
A13	2	1 to 30 1 to 30	Linear Linear	Tangent Hyperbolic	8- 1
A14	3	1 to 30 1 to 30 1 to 30	Linear Linear Linear	Linear	3 - 9 - 6
A15	4	1 to 30 1 to 30 1 to 30 1 to 30	Tangent Hyperbolic Linear Linear Linear	Linear	12 - 10 - 25 - 10

TABLE VI. PREDICTION PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT ANN MODELS

	RMSE Training	MAE Training	RMSE Testing	MAE Testing	RMSE	MAE	E %	R ² Training	R ² Testing	R ²
A1	0.081	3.080	72.053	21.741	5.382	10.596	-3.664	0.992	0.820	0.886
A2	6.286	11.303	18.713	19.196	0.602	13.715	-0.253	0.938	0.827	0.900
A3	0.013	15.561	3.220	19.006	0.242	16.949	2.235	0.851	0.797	0.832
A4	0.002	33.104	4.506	38.780	0.293	34.839	11.550	0.339	0.262	0.318
A5	9.707	17.560	23.161	20.371	0.555	18.419	4.079	0.827	0.821	0.819
A6	63.194	16.608	24.453	28.551	4.613	20.257	0.287	0.903	0.492	0.757
A7	259.847	51.872	202.907	56.492	38.738	53.284	54.801	0.141	0.115	0.108
A8	321.020	46.351	231.911	53.502	46.635	48.536	58.461	0.554	0.344	0.501
A9	352.123	52.086	125.542	45.105	42.760	50.258	56.758	0.407	0.139	0.297
A10	38.635	25.309	59.366	21.533	7.662	24.155	-3.500	0.634	0.833	0.684
A11	8.993	10.752	23.499	23.085	0.648	14.520	1.090	0.938	0.748	0.879
A12	0.039	13.916	70.602	23.188	4.595	16.749	-0.645	0.894	0.802	0.833
A13	18.476	17.295	17.734	21.041	2.970	18.439	6.193	0.851	0.731	0.817
A14	15.639	18.039	18.039	21.197	16.069	0.155	17.437	0.806	0.892	0.836
A15	6.004	2.080	35.422	14.848	1.714	5.981	-1.601	0.998	0.891	0.960

Fig. 4. The architecture of the optimal ANN model (A15).

Equations (5)-(9) are used to predict the shear strength of the reinforced soil:

$$\tau_{ff_pr} = \text{purelin.}(LW_{i4} \cdot A_i^4 + b_i^5) \quad (5)$$

$$[A_i^4] = \text{purelin.}(LW_{i3} \cdot A_i^3 + b_i^4) \quad (6)$$

$$[A_i^3] = \text{purelin.}(LW_{i2} \cdot A_i^2 + b_i^3) \quad (7)$$

$$[A_i^2] = \text{purelin.}(LW_{i1} \cdot A_i^1 + b_i^2) \quad (8)$$

$$[A_i^1] = \text{tansig.}(IW_i \cdot p + b_i^1) \quad (9)$$

where p is the matrix of inputs, $IW_i \cdot p$ is the weight matrix, representing the connection of the weights between the input layer neurons and the first hidden layer neurons, LW_{i1} is the weight matrix representing the connection of the weights between the first and the second hidden layer neurons, LW_{i2} is the weight matrix representing the connection of the weights between the second and the third hidden layer neuron, LW_{i3} is the weight matrix representing the connection of the weights between the third and the fourth hidden layer neurons, LW_{i4} is the weight matrix representing the connection of the weights between the fourth hidden layer neurons and the output neurons, $b_i^1, b_i^2, b_i^3, b_i^4$ and b_i^5 are the bias vectors of the first, second, third, and fourth hidden layer neurons, and the bias vector of the output layer respectively, $\text{purelin}(x) = x$, and $\text{tansig}(n) = \frac{2}{1+e^{-2n}} - 1$.

Fig. 5. Correlation results analysis of the model using the training data set.

Fig. 6. Correlation results analysis of the model using the testing data set.

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the training and testing data correlation between the target and predicted shear strength of reinforced soil using the optimal ANN model (A15). The values of RMSE (6.004), MAE (2.080), and R^2 (0.998) indicate that the target and predicted values for the training dataset are quite close. The testing dataset's RMSE (35.422), MAE (14.848), and R^2 (0.891) values are adequate proof that the proposed ANN model is the most reliable approach.

Because the shear strength of the reported instances in the dataset is different, we plotted the measured and estimated shear strength in Figure 7 against each other for all given cases. As shown in this Figure, the overall agreement between the predicted values obtained by the approximated function developed in this study and the values of the experimental model is indeed good, which is confirmed by the low values of RMSE (1.714), MAE (5.981), R^2 (0.960), and the relative average error value ($E = -1.601\%$).

Table VII presents the comparison between the GO model and the developed ANN model of this study. The different performance values (RMSE, MAE, R^2 , and E) obtained by the two models show that the optimum ANN model estimates the shear strength of reinforced soil more precisely than the GO model.

TABLE VII. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE PERFORMANCE VALUES OBTAINED BY THE GO MODEL AND THE DEVELOPED ANN MODEL

	Gray and Ohashi model				ANN developed model			
	RMSE	MAE	R^2	E (%)	RMSE	MAE	R^2	E (%)
Vertical	31.93	26.00	0.680	10.53	1.714	5.981	0.960	-1.601
Inclined	28.44	20.50	0.732	-5.10				
Horizontal	30.81	24.91	0.719	-13.12				

Fig. 7. Comparison of all experimental and predicted shear strengths evaluated by the ANN model of this study.

IV. CONCLUSION

An ANN model was built in this paper to predict the behavior of reinforced soil. The experimental results of the shear strength of reinforced soil was compared with the predicted results from the GO model and the ANN model. A parametric study to explain the impact of various factors on the behavior of reinforced soil was conducted. The main conclusions of this study are:

- The improvement of the shear strength of reinforced soil is not only influenced by the fiber length and ratio, but also by their direction.
- The fiber direction changes the optimal fiber ratio and the optimal fiber length. This can be due to the variation in fiber tensile stress for each direction.
- From the experimental study, the GO model does not take into account the plasticity of fibers.
- The shear strength of unreinforced soil (τ_{ur}), the mobilized tensile strength of fibers (σ_f), the fiber ratios (ρ_f), the fiber length (L_f), and the angle of shear distortion (θ) are the major factors influencing the behavior of reinforced soil, according to the parametric study and the theoretical analysis.
- The excellent agreement between the predictions of the optimal ANN model and the laboratory shear tests suggests that the developed model can quickly and conveniently predict the shear strength of reinforced soil for different values of reinforced parameters, which was confirmed by the values of RMSE (1.714), MAE (5.981), R^2 (0.960), and E (-1.601%).
- The developed optimal ANN model predicts the shear strength of reinforced soil more precisely than the GO model. Moreover, the GO model is based on many equations and it doesn't take into consideration the case of

the fiber failure. Instead, the proposed ANN model considers all conditions in one equation with minimal error and the best correlation. Therefore, the ANN model developed in this study is a robust and efficient alternative.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. H. Gray and H. Ohashi, "Mechanics of Fiber Reinforcement in Sand," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 109, no. 3, pp. 335–353, Mar. 1983, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1983\)109:3\(335\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1983)109:3(335)).
- [2] R. Ramkrishnan, V. Karthik, M. R. Sruthy, and A. Sharma, "Soil Reinforcement and Slope Stabilization Using Natural Jute Fibres," in *Civil Infrastructures Confronting Severe Weathers and Climate Changes Conference*, HangZhou, China, Jul. 2018, pp. 130–143, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-95744-9_11.
- [3] S. M. Hejazi, M. Sheikhzadeh, S. M. Abtahi, and A. Zadhoush, "A simple review of soil reinforcement by using natural and synthetic fibers," *Construction and Building Materials*, vol. 30, pp. 100–116, May 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2011.11.045>.
- [4] R. A. Jewell and C. P. Wroth, "Direct shear tests on reinforced sand," *Geotechnique*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 53–68, Mar. 1987, <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1987.37.1.53>.
- [5] L. J. Waldron, "The Shear Resistance of Root-Permeated Homogeneous and Stratified Soil," *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 843–849, 1977, <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1977.036159950041000500005x>.
- [6] M. H. Maher and D. H. Gray, "Static Response of Sands Reinforced with Randomly Distributed Fibers," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 116, no. 11, pp. 1661–1677, Nov. 1990, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1990\)116:11\(1661\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1990)116:11(1661)).
- [7] R. L. Michalowski and A. Zhao, "Continuum versus Structural Approach to Stability of Reinforced Soil," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 121, no. 2, pp. 152–162, Feb. 1995, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1995\)121:2\(152\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1995)121:2(152)).
- [8] S. K. Shukla, N. Sivakugan, and A. K. Singh, "Analytical model for fiber-reinforced granular soils under high confining stresses," *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, vol. 22, pp. 935–942, Sep. 2010, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0000081](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0000081).
- [9] J. G. Zornberg, "Discrete framework for limit equilibrium analysis of fibre-reinforced soil," *Geotechnique*, vol. 52, no. 8, pp. 593–604, Oct. 2002, <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.2002.52.8.593>.

- [10] R. L. Michalowski and A. Zhao, "Failure of Fiber-Reinforced Granular Soils," *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, vol. 122, no. 3, pp. 226–234, Mar. 1996, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9410\(1996\)122:3\(226\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1996)122:3(226)).
- [11] R. L. Michalowski and J. Cermak, "Triaxial Compression of Sand Reinforced with Fibers," *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, vol. 129, no. 2, pp. 125–136, Feb. 2003, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(2003\)129:2\(125\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2003)129:2(125)).
- [12] A. Diambra and E. Ibraim, "Fibre-reinforced sand: interaction at the fibre and grain scale," *Geotechnique*, vol. 65, no. 4, pp. 296–308, Apr. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.14.P.206>.
- [13] R. L. Michalowski, "Limit analysis with anisotropic fibre-reinforced soil," *Geotechnique*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 489–501, Aug. 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.2008.58.6.489>.
- [14] S. K. Shukla, *Fundamentals of Fibre-Reinforced Soil Engineering*. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 2017.
- [15] L. T. H. Nhung, T. T. Phung, H. M. V. Nguyen, T. N. Le, T. A. Nguyen, and T. D. Vo, "Load Shedding in Microgrids with Dual Neural Networks and AHP Algorithm," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 8090–8095, Feb. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4652>.
- [16] N. T. T. Vu, N. P. Tran, and N. H. Nguyen, "Recurrent Neural Network-based Path Planning for an Excavator Arm under Varying Environment," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7088–7093, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4125>.
- [17] A. Sokhal, Z. Benaissa, S. A. Ouadfeul, and A. Boudella, "Dynamic Rock Type Characterization Using Artificial Neural Networks in Hamra Quartzites Reservoir: A Multidisciplinary Approach," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4397–4404, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2861>.
- [18] F. Belaabed, K. Goudjil, L. Arabet, and A. Ouamane, "Utilization of computational intelligence approaches to estimate the relative head of PK-Weir for submerged flow," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 33, no. 19, pp. 13001–13013, Oct. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-021-05996-7>.
- [19] K. Goudjil and L. Arabet, "Assessment of deflection of pile implanted on slope by artificial neural network," *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 1091–1101, Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-020-04985-6>.
- [20] R. Nazir, E. Momeni, K. Marsono, and H. Maizir, "An Artificial Neural Network Approach for Prediction of Bearing Capacity of Spread Foundations in Sand," *Jurnal Teknologi*, vol. 72, no. 3, Jan. 2015, <https://doi.org/10.11113/jt.v72.4004>.
- [21] T. Liang, J. A. Knappett, A. Leung, A. Carnaghan, A. G. Bengough, and R. Zhao, "A critical evaluation of predictive models for rooted soil strength with application to predicting the seismic deformation of rooted slopes," *Landslides*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 93–109, Jan. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-019-01259-8>.
- [22] M. Dallel, "Evaluation du potentiel textile des fibres d'Alfa (Stipa Tenacissima L.): caractérisation physico-chimique de la fibre au fil," Ph.D. dissertation, Haute-Alsace University, Mulhouse, France, 2012.
- [23] C. Ozkan and F. S. Erbek, "The Comparison of Activation Functions for Multispectral Landsat TM Image Classification," *Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing*, vol. 69, no. 11, pp. 1225–1234, Nov. 2003, <https://doi.org/10.14358/PERS.69.11.1225>.
- [24] I. S. Isa, Z. Saad, S. Omar, M. K. Osman, K. A. Ahmad, and H. A. M. Sakim, "Suitable MLP Network Activation Functions for Breast Cancer and Thyroid Disease Detection," in *Second International Conference on Computational Intelligence, Modelling and Simulation*, Bali, Indonesia, Sep. 2010, pp. 39–44, <https://doi.org/10.1109/CIMSiM.2010.93>.
- [25] M. T. Hagan, H. B. Demuth, and M. Beale, *Neural network design*. Boston, MA, USA: PWS Publishing, 1997.
- [26] J. J. Jeremiah, S. J. Abbey, C. A. Booth, and A. Kashyap, "Results of Application of Artificial Neural Networks in Predicting Geo-Mechanical Properties of Stabilised Clays—A Review," *Geotechnics*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 147–171, Sep. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/geotechnics1010008>.

The Effect of a Blast Load from Propane Gas Leakage on an RC Structure

A Case Study in Batna, Algeria

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Abstract-The knowledge of the way a gas explosion affects a structure is still in its development. In this study, structural analysis software was used to construct a simplified approach to predict the impact of a Dynamic Blast Load (DBL) from gas leakage. During the explosion process, the overpressure distribution in a room is decomposed to maximum dynamic pressure point (DPPmax), where the explosion damages the most the structure. The simulation of the DBL was compared with the real consequences of gas explosion with the phenomenological data of a case study in Batna, Algeria. The results show that the simulation reproduced by our modeling of the DBL at structural scale is in good agreement with a real explosion. The distribution of stresses and strains over time indicates that the gas explosion inside residential buildings affected the entire surrounding of the area of the blast.

Keywords-Dynamic Blast Load (DBL); maximum Dynamic Pressure Point (DPPmax); propane; gas leakage; RC structure

I. INTRODUCTION

The global demand for natural gas is expected to increase during the next five years [1]. Gas leakage and explosion incidents have often happened inside buildings. 531 gas explosions were reported in China [2] and more than 52 more were observed during 2021 with the most devastating one documented in the city of Batna, Algeria. Many theoretical and experimental studies have been conducted on the damage caused in buildings by dynamic explosive loads [3-5]. Although an explosion from gas propane leakage in a building can only be modeled in the punctual point of pressure, empirical VCE (Vapor Cloud Explosion) models are best suited for such tasks. The TNT equivalent, the TNO multi-energy approach, and the Baker-Strehlow models explain the behavior of an explosion, although they cannot be directly applied to study gas explosion events at structural size. While the structural analysis of a structure damaged by a gas explosion has been understudied, the use of FEM to analyze and calibrate experimental data to fulfill the necessary requirements for the comprehension of the behavior of explosion was successful [6].

Machine learning models for predicting the compressive strength are developed to determine its optimal value [7]. A machine learning model can incorporate more data for its learning process by constant feeding with more parametric simulations that can eventually enhance the compressive strength of concrete that will be considered for the design of RC structure under a dynamic blast load.

Our objective is to study the dynamic characteristics of gas explosions. In order to properly integrate the dynamic blast load at the structural level, we must first understand the dynamic features of gas explosions. The pressure peak is numerically simulated for various proposed models that have been experimentally calibrated. In the meantime, the modeling results are compared with the aftereffects of an actual explosion. Additionally, the structural properties of explosive overpressure (stress, strain, and deformations) are examined. As a case study we will look in an unfortunate incident occurred in a residential building in Batna, Algeria. As shown in Figures 1-2, the ceilings, floor, interior, and exterior walls were blown away. Crack patterns can be seen along with extreme damages to the beams and columns on the floor level from the blast of the explosion, thus confirming the motivation toward an investigation on the effect of the blast over the integrity and stability of an RC structure.

Fig. 1. Indoor explosion scene in the city of Fesdis, Batna, Algeria.

Fig. 2. The damage of the frame of the RC structural elements.

II. PRESSURE-TIME HISTORY AND PRESSURE MODELS

The estimation of the strength of a blast is a difficult problem which can be overcome depending on the required accuracy and the available resources. Blast loads are extremely complex phenomena characterized by a sudden increase to a maximum peak value of pressure and then decaying to atmospheric pressure [3] in microseconds or even milliseconds. The ambient pressure P_0 is the reference or zero pressure for the positive and negative pressure values. After the explosion, the blast wave front reaches a target point in time t_A and reaches the peak incident pressure P_{s0} which is the maximum positive pressure. Then it promptly decays to the atmospheric pressure P_0 . Researchers have been in search for models that can calculate the P_{s0} along with other parameters of shock wave for free air burst and surface burst scenarios. In this paper, we will focus on the surface burst models that mimic an indoors explosion.

III. SURFACE BURST MODELS

The latest developed models that can evaluate P_{s0} are summarized in Table I. $W=E/P_{s0}$ is the TNT equivalent weight (kg), R is the stand-off distance (m), and Z is the scaled distance defined [7] below:

$$Z = R/(E/P_{s0})^{1/3} \quad (1)$$

TABLE I. MODELS TO EVALUATE P_{s0}

Model 1	$P_{s0} = 0.6784 W/R^3 + 0.294 W^{1/2}/R^{3/2}$ (2)	Newmark and Hansen model
Model 2	$P_{s0} = 1.059 [R/W^3]^{-2.01}$ (3)	Wu and Hao model
Model 3	$P_{s0} = 1.017 [R/W^3]^{-1.91}$ (4)	Siddiqui and Ahmad model
Model 4	$P_{s0} = 2.46 [R/W^3]^{-2.67}$ (5)	Ahmad et al. model
Model 5	$P_{s0} = 1.026 [R/W^{1/3}]^{-2.67}$ (6)	Iqbal and Ahmad model
Model 6	$P_{s0} = 4.34 W^{-2.84}$ (7)	Badshah model

The results for the same initial conditions are shown in Figures 3-4. The P_{s0} values diverge, which clearly indicates

the particularity of each model developed for the specification of its own calibrated experiment. The values of the TNT equivalences as functions of overpressure for propane/oxygen were found in [9] and were calculated using the fitting coefficients shown in Table II.

$$W = J + K \ln Z + L (\ln Z)^2 + M (\ln Z)^3 \quad (8)$$

TABLE II. FITTING COEFFICIENTS

	J	K	L	M
Propane/Oxygen	0.4580	0.2150	-0.1442	0.0292
Propane	1.2020	1.2464	-0.6410	0.1034

IV. BLASTING DYNAMIC LOAD

An explosion generates an imposed dynamic load on any object in its field. This blasting dynamic load is characterized by a rapidly reaching maximum peak value which then decreases as the blast wave decays. The net effect of the load depends both on the nature of the blast wave and on the geometry and construction of the object [9]. The blast is predicted by:

$$V = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \quad (9)$$

$$P_s = W \cdot V \cdot P_i \quad (10)$$

$$P_i = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot S \cdot V_i^2 \quad (11)$$

$$P(t) = 4 \cdot P_s \cdot [e^{-t/\sqrt{2}} - e^{-\sqrt{2}t}] \quad (12)$$

where V_i is the blasting velocity, and S the density of the explosives.

V. DATA USED

TABLE III. PROPANE PARAMETERS

	Propane g/cm ³	Propane Kg/m ³
Blasting velocity V	347	
Explosive density S	0.493	493

Fig. 3. The peak positive incident pressure (P_{s0}).

As explained above, the results for the peak positive incident pressure (P_{s0}) are very diverse due to the calibration of each model to the chemical components proprieties of the explosion. The blasting velocity and explosion density of

propane (Table III) lead us to the inevitability of more exorbitated field experiment.

Authors in [10] experimentally proved that sequences of explosion of the propane air mixture give symmetrical flame propagation. After ignition, the flame speed increased quickly to 2384 m/s. Two milliseconds (0.002s) later the flame reaches the end and stops propagating.

Fig. 4. Dynamic blast load history for a 75m³ chamber filled with 90% propane and the model adopted in the current study.

Data from [10] were used and the results were compared with the results of other models. The significance of the right set of experiments to be used to oversee the dynamic blast of propane explosion was clearly shown. Figure 4 indicates the difference in the proportionality of Pso over time.

TABLE IV. PROPANE PARAMETERS USED IN BLAST LOAD CALCULATIONS

Sensor	Peak pressure (kPa)	Sensor	Peak pressure (kPa)
P1	29.76	P2	14.28
P3	15.39	P4	10.98
P5	25.45	P6	12.84
P7	10.85	P8	12.33

Moreover, the setting of pressure sensors shows that the maximum dynamic pressure point DDP_{max}, as Table IV indicates, is located on the frontal central of the faces of the explosion.

VI. MODELING APPROACH OF DBL

The structural modeling approach of the phenomena is summarized below:

- Designate the explosive material, in our case propane (natural) gas and its flammable characteristics.
- Define the Dynamic Blast Load (DBL) history expression that we are going to use for the assessments.
- Assign the DBL to the corresponding DDP_{max}. In the case of structural walls without openings, the DDP_{ma} will be in the center of the wall, for walls with openings (windows,

doors), the DDP_{ma} will be located on the center of each edge of the opening surface.

- Define the DBL force in a structural analysis software (ex. Autodesk Robot structural analysis 2022) as time history analysis as the Figure 5 show.

Fig. 5. Location of the DBL force in the structure and time history analysis.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our approach follows the results of [10] and replicates the propagation wave of the DBL. We can observe that the maximal displacement measured in the damaged structure as shown in Figure 2 is 38cm in a principal beam. On the contrary, our simplified approached with the adopted VCE model, gave 33cm displacement along the position of the punctual point of the peak pressure of the explosion as shown in Figure 6(g).

Figures 7-8 indicate that the distribution and arrow orientation of stress show clearly that our model mimics to a certain degree the scale of the actual damage the structure has sustained. As Figure 9 shows, the crack propagation pattern is similar to that of the adopted simplified approach, since the distribution of maximum stress resembles the propagated cracks from the blast.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

The current study showed that all the considered models are specific to a type of an explosion rather than just a generalization of behavioral phenomena, hence the Pso in all the developed models shows an empirical blast load, either for free air burst or for a surface burst, something that shows a large variation. The current paper is the first milestone toward the implementation of blast load in structural design with a suitable and simplified approach, showing similar results with the case study.

Brick masonry is a principal component in structural construction and infill material in many parts of the world. Therefore, response of clay brick masonry against blast loading will be examined in the future.

Fig. 6. Nodal and column /beam displacement for each incremental time.

Fig. 7. Distribution of stress at the maximal peak pressure.

Fig. 8. Arrow orientation of the stress.

Fig. 9. Distibutionof the propagted cracks from the blast.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. R. Martins, G. F. M. de Souza, and N. H. Ikeda, "Consequence Analysis of a Liquefied Natural Gas Floating Production Storage Offloading (LNG FPSO) Leakage," presented at the ASME 2011 30th International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering, Oct. 2011, pp. 291–298, <https://doi.org/10.1115/OMAE2011-49396>.
- [2] K. Zuo, J. Tang, Y. Zhang, F. Wang, S. Cha, and M. Luo, "Safety management effectiveness evaluation of indoor gas facilities based on SE-DEA," *Oil & Gas Storage and Transportation*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 486-492+532, 2018.
- [3] W. M. A. Khalifa and K. F. O. El-Kashif, "Computational Model for the Evaluation of Reinforced Concrete Silos Subjected to Thermal Load," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 4411–4418, Aug. 2019, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.2874>.
- [4] A. M. Remennikov and T. A. Rose, "Modelling blast loads on buildings in complex city geometries," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 83, no. 27, pp. 2197–2205, Oct. 2005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruc.2005.04.003>.
- [5] P. D. Smith and T. A. Rose, "Blast wave propagation in city streets—an overview," *Progress in Structural Engineering and Materials*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 16–28, 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pse.209>.
- [6] J. U. Rehman, C. N. Nguyen, T. A. Nguyen, T. C. Vo, T. K. Nguyen, and V. Q. Nguyen, "Prediction of the Stress Wave Amplification Factor of a Spherical Blast Source Using Numerical Simulations," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 9395–9399, Oct. 2022, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.5233>.
- [7] Y. Almoosi, J. McConnell, and N. Oukaili, "Evaluation of the Variation in Dynamic Load Factor Throughout a Highly Skewed Steel I-Girder Bridge," *Engineering, Technology & Applied Science Research*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 7079–7087, Jun. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.48084/etasr.4106>.
- [8] A. Garg *et al.*, "Machine learning models for predicting the compressive strength of concrete containing nano silica," *Computers and Concrete*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 33–42, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.12989/cac.2022.30.1.033>.
- [9] D. A. Crowl and J. F. Louvar, *Chemical Process Safety: Fundamentals with Applications Fourth Edition*, 4th ed. Boston, MA, USA: Pearson, 2019.
- [10] F. Heymes, L. Aprin, P. Slangen, P. Lauret, E. Lapebie, and Antoine Osmont, "An experimental study on vapor cloud explosion of propane-oxygen stoichiometric mixture," *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, vol. 53, pp. 61–66, Sep. 2016, <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1653011>.